

NaijaFLO, Version 1.0: A verified checklist of vascular plants of Nigeria

Authors

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LYCOPODIACEAE

Huperzia brachystachys (Baker) Pic.Serm.

Lycopodium dacrydioides var. brachystachys
Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Huperzia mildbraedii (Herter) Pic.Serm.

Lycopodium mildbraedii Herter

Chapman, JD 2939; 1972-7-6 [WAG.1725225]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Huperzia selago (L.) Bernh. ex Schrank & Mart. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Huperzia staudtii (Nessel) Pic.Serm.

Urostachys staudtii Nessel

Unwin A.H. 130; 22-09-1907 [K]

Total: 3.

Lycopodiella affinis (Bory) Pic.Serm.

Lycopodium affine Bory

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63252; 1970-4-3
[WAG.1351309]

Total: 1.

Lycopodiella cernua (L.) Pic.Serm.

Lycopodium cernuum L.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 278; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1351514]

Total: 36; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1,
Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Lycopodium clavatum L.

Chapman J.D. 3711; 10-02-1975 [K]

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Sokoto
1.

ISOETACEAE

Isoetes aequinoctialis Welw. ex A.Braun

Literature

Total: 0.

Isoetes biafrana Alston

Henry Jarvis Savorys.n.; 1953-- [BM001240665]
[3773416332]

Total: 1.

Isoetes melanotheca Alston

M.E Dyer952; 1981-9-12 [1196495] [1988761855]

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Isoetes nigriflora A.Braun

Literature

Total: 0.

Isoetes schweinfurthii A.Br.

Jan Kazimierz Kornaś6272; 1977-10-26

[BM000097933] [1055978293]

Total: 4; Borno 3, Yobe 1.

Isoetes welwitschii A.Braun ex Kuhn

Charles Barter 1020; -- [BM000785278]

Total: 1.

SELAGINELLACEAE

Selaginella blepharophylla Alston

Hall J.B. 627; 23-08-1968 [K]

Total: 5; Ondo 3, Plateau 1.

Selaginella buchholzii Hieron.

J. T. Baldwin 13795; 1949-11-25 [US 2608915]

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Enugu 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun
1, Oyo 2.

Selaginella cathedriformis Spring

J. T. Baldwin 13779; 1949-11-20 [US 2608913]

Total: 8; Abia 3, Cross River 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Selaginella goudotiana Spring

Chapman, J.D. 3376; 1974-11-02 [K006129718]

Total: 3; Ondo 1, Sokoto 1.

Selaginella kalbreyeri Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Selaginella leoneensis Hieron.

Gbile Z.O.; WitZOG 917; 1971-11-8 [66979]

[1990431466]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 5, Osun 1.

Selaginella molleri Hieron.

Lowe J.4455; 1983-11-27 [101472] [1990433394]

Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Ondo 5, Plateau 2,
Taraba 1.

Selaginella molliceps Spring

J. T. Baldwin 13811; 1949-12-3 [US 2608912]

Total: 9; Abia 2, Cross River 4, Ebonyi 1, Niger 1,
Taraba 1.

Selaginella myosurus (Sw.) Alston

Lycopodium myosurus Sw.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 302; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1725443]

Total: 71; Abia 8, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 6, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 13, Delta 4, Edo 9, Enugu 4, Imo 3, Niger 2, Ondo 2, Rivers 5, Taraba 2.

Selaginella njamnjamensis Hieron.

Peter James Wanstall s.n.; 1966-4-24 [BM000788756]

Total: 10; Ekiti 1, Oyo 9.

Selaginella subcordata A.Braun ex Kuhn

Drew E.A. 244; -- [BR0000015471314]

Total: 7; Sokoto 3.

Selaginella tenerrima A.Braun ex Kuhn

Hepper F.N 1333; 13-11-1957 [K]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Plateau 2.

Selaginella thomensis Alston

Richards P.W. 4005A; 06-03-1948 [K]

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Selaginella versicolor Spring

Eijnatten, CLM van 1484; 1966-5-10 [WAG.1726347]

Total: 53; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 6, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3, Niger 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 7, Osun 5, Oyo 6, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Selaginella vogelii Spring

J. T. Baldwin 13760; 1949-11-20 [US 2608907]

Total: 43; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 15, Edo 9, Enugu 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1.

PSILOTACEAE

Psilotum nudum (L.) P.Beauv.

Lycopodium nudum L.

Dent Young, J. 272 (K)

Total: 2; Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

OPHIOGLOSSACEAE

Ophioglossum ammophilum C.D.Adams

Literature

Total: 0.

Ophioglossum costatum R.Br.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 394; 1978-5-10 [WAG.1725984]

Total: 63; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 10, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 6, Kwara 4, Niger 6, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 2.

Ophioglossum gomezianum Welw. ex

A.Braun

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3830; 1971-7-28 [WAG.1725998]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Oyo 3.

Ophioglossum latifolium (Prantl)

J.E.Burrows

Ophioglossum gomezianum var. latifolium Prantl 497; 1958-10-12 [K000506243]

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Ophioglossum reticulatum L.

Onochie, C.F.A. 35133; 1956-8-17 [K000506256]

Total: 27; Abia 2, Benue 4, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Rivers 2.

MARATTIACEAE

Eupodium cicutifolium (Kaulf.) Lehtonen —

Introduced

Marattia cicutifolia Kaulf.

Dr Kadiri A.B; 2008-12-1 [2263]3808443090

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Ptisana fraxinea (Sm.) Murdock —

Introduced

Marattia fraxinea Sm.

Pilz GE Pilz, GE 1961; 1977-04-24 [WAG.1732609]

Total: 36; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Osun 6, Taraba 10.

Ptisana pellucida (C.Presl) Murdock —

Introduced

Marattia pellucida C.Presl

Onyeachusim, H.D.;Latilo; 1964-2-25 [P01646594]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1.

Ptisana senterreana Christenh.

Literature

Total: 0.

OSMUNDACEAE

Osmunda hilsenbergii Grev. & Hook.

Literature

Total: 0.

Osmunda regalis L. — Introduced

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1951; 1972-5-10 [WAG.1320697]

Total: 18; Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Osun 1, Plateau 4, Rivers 1, Taraba 6.

GLEICHENIACEAE

Dicranopteris linearis (Burm.f.) Underw.

Polypodium lineare Burm.f.

Stubbings, H.G. 145; 1958-01-12 (K)

Total: 58; Anambra 3, Bauchi 2, Cross River 13, Edo 4, Enugu 2, Imo 2, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 3, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 4.

Dicranopteris linearis var. *linearis*

Polypodium lineare Burm.f.

Sharland, R.E. 1957; 1987-07-16 (K)

Total: 5.

HYMENOPHYLLACEAE

Hymenophyllum capillare Desv. —

Introduced

Hall, Dr J.B. 2334; 1971-3-28 [K000896290]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Plateau 1.

Hymenophyllum hirsutum (L.) Sw. —

Introduced

Trichomanes hirsutum L.

H.J. Savory & R.W.J. Keay, 25119; 1948-12-20 [BM001056390]

Total: 1.

Hymenophyllum kuhnii C.Chr. —

Introduced

Hymenophyllum meyeri Kuhn

Literature

Total: 0.

Hymenophyllum splendidum Bosch —

Introduced

Dr Kadiri A.B.; 2008-12-1 [2262] [3808441796]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Trichomanes africanum Christ

M. E. Dyers.n.; 1981-10-18 [1574607] [3041313687]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Trichomanes ballardianum Alston

P. Richards 3610; 1947-12-7 [US 2360771]

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 3, Plateau 1.

Trichomanes chamaedrys Taton

Gledhill, D 885; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1307440]

Total: 1.

Trichomanes chevalieri Christ

Tilquin J.P. 150; -- [BR0000015930361]

Total: 3; Bayelsa 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1.

Trichomanes crispiforme Alston

Barter C. 1817; -- [K000435657]

Total: 11; Niger 1.

Trichomanes cupressoides Desv. —

Introduced

Chaloner W.G. 10_12; 26-03-1966 [K]

Total: 3; Abia 1, Cross River 1.

Trichomanes dregei Bosch

Literature

Total: 0.

Trichomanes erosum Willd.

Barter 2079; -- [K000435655]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 3, Niger 1, Osun 4.

Trichomanes giganteum Bory ex Willd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Trichomanes guineense Afzel. ex Sw.

Richards P.W. 3602; -- [BR0000015482853]

Total: 4; Abia 1, Edo 3.

Trichomanes liberiense Copel.

Gledhill, D 962; 1968-4-5 [WAG.1729902]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1.

Trichomanes mannii Hook.

Chapman J.D. 4384; 24-04-1976 [K]

Total: 5; Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Trichomanes melanotrichum Schtdl.

Hall J.B. 110; 14-04-1968 [K]

Total: 11; Cross River 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Trichomanes mettenii C.Chr. — Introduced

Trichomanes subsessile Mett.

Richards P.W. 3668; 16-12-1947 [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Trichomanes pyxidiferum L. — Introduced

E01032464

Total: 1.

SCHIZAEACEAE

Anemia nigerica Alston — Endemic

Gledhill, D 958; 1968-4-6 [WAG.1301169]

Total: 18; Ekiti 3, Ondo 12, Plateau 1.

Anemia rauhiana Mickel

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-10-17 [P00250364]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 1.

Anemia schimperiana C.Presl — Introduced

Lely P.526; 1930-7- [101132578]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Anemia sessilis (Jeanp.) C.Chr.

Anemia tomentosa var. *sessilis* Jeanp.

Ariwaodo J.O.; 1963-6-15 [47825]

Total: 7; Borno 1, Plateau 4, Yobe 1.

Anemia simii Tardieu — Introduced

G. de Witte 3820; 1948-5-10 [US

3011123]1320338918

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Lygodium flexuosum (L.) Sw. — Introduced

Ophioglossum flexuosum L.

Paul Westmacott Richards 3921; 1948-2-1

[BM000093526]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Lygodium microphyllum (Cav.) R.Br.

Ugena microphylla Cav.

Olorunfemi OAF15; 1979-6-26 [1183617]

Total: 54; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 4, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 6, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 9, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Lygodium smithianum C.Presl

Ariwaodo, JO 868; 1977-8-8 [WAG.1301392]

Total: 38; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 13, Edo 6, Ekiti 2, Lagos 2, Osun 1.

MARSILEACEAE

Marsilea berthautii Tardieu

A M. Jordan ; 1955-11-3 [BM001056935]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Kaduna 3.

Marsilea coromandelina Willd.

M. E. Dyer172; 1980-2-2 [1577256] [3326583374]

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Marsilea distorta A.Braun

M. E. Dyer174; 1980-2-2 [1577267] [3326589306]

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Marsilea minuta L.

W. J. Crins 4028; 1981-4-25 [1577281] [3326591355]

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 3, Sokoto 1.

Marsilea minuta var. *incurva* (A.Braun)

Launert

Marsilea diffusa var. *incurva* A.Braun

Meikle, R.D. 1387; 1950-04-06 [K006534179]

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Katsina 1.

Marsilea minuta var. *minuta*

Meikle R.D. 1221; 25-02-1950 [K]

Total: 3; Katsina 1, Sokoto 1.

Marsilea nubica A.Braun

Literature

Total: 0.

Marsilea nubica var. *nubica*

Literature

Total: 0.

Marsilea polycarpa Hook. & Grev. —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1949; 1966-9-14 [WAG.1732496]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Marsilea subterranea Lepr. ex A.Braun

Literature

Total: 0.

SALVINIACEAE

Azolla pinnata R.Br.

Gutzwiller Roman 602; -- [BR0000016331815]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2.

Azolla pinnata subsp. *africana* (Desv.)

R.M.K.Saunders & K.Fowler

Léonard J. 4349; -- [BR0000016331792]

Total: 1.

Azolla pinnata subsp. *pinnata*

Gutzwiller Roman 602; -- [BR0000016331815]

Total: 2.

Salvinia molesta D.Mitch. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Salvinia nymphellula Desv.

Évrard C. 6943; -- [BR0000019286457]

Total: 5; Edo 1, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1.

CYATHEACEAE

Alsophila camerooniana (Hook.) R.M.Tryon

Cyathea camerooniana Hook.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi FHI 8488; 1977-10-8

[WAG.1730102]

Total: 21; Abia 1, Borno 3, Cross River 6, Niger 1, Osun 8.

Alsophila camerooniana var. *camerooniana*

Cyathea camerooniana Hook.
Chaloner 336A; -- [100897984]1258211647
Total: 6; Borno 3, Cross River 2, Osun 1.

Alsophila camerooniana var. *occidentalis*
(Holttum) J.P.Roux

Cyathea camerooniana var. *occidentalis* Holttum
Gledhill 1028; -- [100898380]1258212068
Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Niger 1, Osun 4.

Alsophila dregei (Kunze) R.M.Tryon

Cyathea dregei Kunze
Daramola, BO 116; 1977-8-18 [WAG.1730490]
Total: 23; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 11.

Alsophila dregei var. *dregei*

Cyathea dregei Kunze
Bowden J.K 80; 06-04-1970 [K]
Total: 1.

Alsophila lepidoclada Christ — Introduced

Versteeg, G.; 1907-- [P01373303]
Total: 1.

Alsophila manniana (Hook.) R.M.Tryon

Cyathea manniana Hook.
Chapman, JD 2800; 1972-5-7 [WAG.1730393]
Total: 15; Borno 2, Cross River 4, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Sphaeropteris runensis (Alderw.)

R.M.Tryon — Introduced

Cyathea runensis Alderw.
Versteeg, G.; 1907-- [P01559657]
Total: 1.

LONCHITIDACEAE

Lonchitis occidentalis Baker

Hall, J.B.; 78; 1968-02-25 [K006599664]
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1.

PTERIDACEAE

Acrostichum aureum L.

A. P. D. Jones FHI. 19408; 1946-7-16 [US 2424695]
Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 2, Delta 2, Lagos 11, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Rivers 2.

Actiniopteris australis (L.f.) Link —

Introduced

Acrostichum australe L.f.
Daramola 67344; 1970-7-15 [101128338]2269021408
Total: 1; Benue 1.

Actiniopteris radiata (Sw.) Link

Asplenium radiatum Sw.
Daramola, B.; Ekwuno, P. FHI67344; 1970-7-15 [K000548563]
Total: 4; Adamawa 2, Benue 2.

Actiniopteris semiflabellata Pic.Serm. —

Introduced

Daramola B.O.; Ekwuno P. FHI67344; 15-07-1970 [K]
Total: 1.

Adiantum aethiopicum L.

Literature
Total: 0.

Adiantum capillus-veneris L.

Kornas J. 6311; 1977-3-11 [BR0000025576061V]
Total: 2; Borno 1.

Adiantum incisum Forssk.

Literature
Total: 0.

Adiantum incisum subsp. *incisum*

Literature
Total: 0.

Adiantum patens Willd.

A. Kitson s.n.; -- [US 2424932]
Total: 7; Abia 1, Bauchi 2, Plateau 2.

Adiantum patens subsp. *oatesii* (Baker)

Schelp

A. Kitson [US 2424932]
Total: 5; Bauchi 2, Plateau 2.

Adiantum philippense L.

Kornaš J. [BR0000025576177V]
Total: 38; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 4, Niger 4, Ondo 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Adiantum philippense subsp. *philippense*

Wit, HCD de 13007; 1974-6-1 [WAG.1720259]
Total: 1.

Adiantum poiretii Wikstr.

Adiantum crenatum Poir.
E. Rosenstock; 1906-01-01 [F.C0658130F]
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 2.

Adiantum poiretii var. *poiretii*

Adiantum crenatum Poir.
E. Rosenstock 242a; 1906-- [C0658130F]
Total: 1.

Adiantum schweinfurthii Kuhn

Dalziel, Dr. J.M.; -- [E00194024]

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Adiantum soboliferum Wall. ex Hook. —

Introduced

Okafor J. 36878; -- [US 2856893]

Total: 3; Kogi 2.

Adiantum stolzii Brause

Literature

Total: 0.

Adiantum tetraphyllum Humb. & Bonpl. ex

Willd. — Introduced

M. E. Dyer 817; 1981-7-18 [1593066]3446930392

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Adiantum vogelii Mett.

Pilz, GE 2581; 1980-11-25 [WAG.1720718]

Total: 27; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Oyo 3, Sokoto 1.

Anogramma leptophylla (L.) Link —

Introduced

Polypodium leptophyllum L.

Hall, J.; Lawlor, D.W. 593; 1962-9-5 [K000049350]

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Plateau 2.

Antrophyum immersum (Bory ex Willd.)

Mett.

Hemionitis immersa Bory ex Willd.

Chapman, J.D. 5237; 1978-2-9 [K000705621]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Antrophyum mannianum Hook.

Hall, Dr J.B.; Lawlor, D.W. 138; 1962-7-27

[K000049349]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Ceratopteris cornuta (P.Beauv.) Le Prieur

Pteris cornuta P.Beauv.

I. Hepburn 155; -- [US 2139698]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Lagos 2.

Ceratopteris thalictroides (L.) Brongn. —

Introduced

Acrostichum thalictroides L.

Léonard J. 4352; -- [BR0000016345447]

Total: 1.

Coniogramme africana Hieron.

Literature

Total: 0.

Doryopteris kirkii (Hook.) Alston

Cheilanthes kirkii Hook.

Gledhill, D 929; 1968-4-6 [WAG.1722192]

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Haplopteris guineensis (Desv.) E.H.Crane

Vittaria guineensis Desv.

Pilz, G.E. 1967; 1977-4-24 [K000705589]

Total: 19; Abia 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 3.

Haplopteris owariensis (Fée) E.H.Crane

Vittaria owariensis Fée

Chapman, J.D. 4367; 1976-4-20 [K000705649]

Total: 8; Lagos 4, Niger 2, Taraba 2.

Hemionitis concolor (Langsd. & Fisch.)

Christenh.

Pteris concolor Langsd. & Fisch.

Baxter; 1859-1-1 [P01247570]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Hemionitis cuspidata (Copel.) Christenh.

Doryopteris cuspidata Copel.

Literature

Total: 0.

Hemionitis doniana (J.Sm. & Hook.)

Christenh.

Pellaea doniana Hook.

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-10-21 [P01269923]

Total: 13; Bauchi 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Hemionitis dura (Willd.) Christenh. —

Introduced

Pteris dura Willd.

Usang Felix; 2005-10-6 [176] [3913474597]

Total: 1.

Hemionitis farinosa (Forssk.) Christenh.

Pteris farinosa Forssk.

Literature

Total: 0.

Hemionitis inaequalis (Kunze) Christenh.

Notholaena inaequalis Kunze

Literature

Total: 0.

Hemionitis rouxii (Fraser-Jenk. &

E.Wollenw.) Christenh. — Endemic

Aleuritopteris rouxii Fraser-Jenk. & E.Wollenw.

Literature

Total: 0.

Hemionitis schimperi (Kunze) Christenh.

Cheilanthes schimperi Kunze

Keay, R.W.J.; 1950-7-1 [P00754363]

Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 5.

Hemionitis schweinfurthii (Hieron.)
Christenh.

Pteridella schweinfurthii Hieron.

Usang Felix; 2005-10-06 [LUH.176.0]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Hemionitis welwitschii (Hook.) Christenh.

— Introduced

Cheilanthes welwitschii Hook.

Hambler, DJ 482; 1958-5-7 [U.1031112]

Total: 1.

Pityrogramma calomelanos (L.) Link —

Introduced

Acrostichum calomelanos L.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 90154; 1979-4-20
[WAG.1721558]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1,
Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Pteris atrovirens Willd.

Palisot de Beauvois; 1808-- [P00609100]

Total: 14; Edo 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1,
Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Pteris atrovirens f. *atrovirens*

Richards P.W. 3862; 14-01-1948 [K]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Pteris atrovirens f. *laevicosta* Verdc.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pteris burtonii Baker

Chaloner W.G. 326B; 1966-2 [K]

Total: 5; Edo 1, Kwara 1.

Pteris catoptera Kunze — Introduced

G. E. Pilz 2314; 1980-2-24 [C0675282F]

Total: 21; Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Ogun 1,
Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Taraba 7.

Pteris friesii Hieron. — Introduced

Magaji S.O.; Tuley P. 1780; 27-10-1969

[K000759224]

Total: 3; Kaduna 2.

Pteris hamulosa Christ

Chapman, J.D.; 3784; 1975-03-31 [K006491649]

Total: 4; Plateau 2.

Pteris intricata C.H.Wright

Literature

Total: 0.

Pteris linearis Poir.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pteris manniana Mett.

Barter C. ; Baikies 24 Niger expedition

Total: 1.

Pteris mildbraedii Hieron.

Wright, J.V. 25; 1951-01-01 [K006491508]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Delta 2, Oyo 1.

Pteris preussii Hieron. — Introduced

Bowden, J. 70; 1970-04-06 [K006491467]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Pteris pteridioides (Hook.) F.Ballard

Hypolepis pteridioides Hook.

Kentish L. ; 13-01-1903 [K]

Total: 1.

Pteris repens C.Chr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pteris similis Kuhn

A. P. Jones & C. Onochie FHI17167; -- [US 2424627]

Total: 12; Edo 1, Imo 1, Kano 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 2,
Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Pteris togoensis Hieron.

Chapman, JD 2549; 1971-9-26 [WAG.1300469]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 3, Taraba 2.

Pteris tripartita Sw.

Ajibade Mutiat; O.O.Oyebanji; 2015-01-01

[LUH.6817.0]

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Osun 1,
Taraba 3.

Pteris tripartita var. *tripartita*

Ajibade Mutiat; O.O.Oyebanji; 2015-1-1 [6817]

[3808439233]

Total: 1.

Pteris vittata L. — Introduced

Gladhill D. 760; 05-12-1967 [K]

Total: 1.

Syngramma alismifolia (C.Presl) J.Sm.

Diplazium alismifolium C.Presl

W. Brooke 10626; 1955-10-6 [US 2290687]

Total: 1; Nasarawa 1.

LINDSAEACEAE

Lindsaea ensifolia Sw.

Dalziel J.M.; 09-07-1920 [K]

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Rivers 1.

Lindsaea ensifolia var. *ensifolia*

Richards P.W. 3922; 01-02-1948 [K]

Total: 1.

DENNSTAEDTIACEAE

Blotiella currorii (Hook.) R.M.Tryon

Pteris currorii Hook.

Daramola 72464; 1973-10-8 [101176205]

Total: 29; Abia 3, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 8, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 1.

Blotiella mannii (Baker) Pic.Serm.

Pteris mannii Baker

Chaloner W.G. 6_5; 1966-2 [K]

Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Blotiella reducta (C.Chr.) R.M.Tryon

Lonchitis reducta C.Chr.

Chapman, JD 2900; 1972-6-16 [WAG.1730971]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Blotiella tisserantii (Alston & Tardieu)

Pic.Serm.

Lonchitis tisserantii Alston & Tardieu

Hall J.B. 1679; 02-04-1970 [K]

Total: 5; Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Histiopteris incisa (Thunb.) J.Sm.

Pteris incisa Thunb.

Hall J.B. 3089; 28-01-1972 [k]

Total: 1.

Hypolepis sparsisora (Schrad.) Kuhn

Cheilanthes sparsisora Schrad.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2079; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1724562]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Microlepia speluncae (L.) T.Moore

Polypodium speluncae L.

Onyeachusim, HD FHI 54218; 1964-2-28

[WAG.1724298]

Total: 13; Abia 2, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Pteridium aquilinum (L.) Kuhn —

Introduced

Pteris aquilina L.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1929; 1972-5-10

[WAG.1724126]

Total: 26; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Pteridium capense (Thunb.) Krasser

Pteris capensis Thunb.

B.E. Okoli; -- [NSW420328]

Total: 1.

ASPLENIACEAE

Asplenium adiantumnigrum subsp.

adiantumnigrum

Dalziel, J.M. 248; 1909-08-03 [K006622586]

Total: 6; Bauchi 2, Plateau 3.

Asplenium aethiopicum (Burm.f.) Becherer

— Introduced

Trichomanes aethiopicum Burm.f.

Daramola 130; 1979-4-27 [101148642]

Total: 11; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Asplenium aethiopicum subsp. *aethiopicum*

Trichomanes aethiopicum Burm.f.

Chapman J.D. 2919; 27-06-1972 [K]

Total: 1.

Asplenium africanum Desv.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11280; 1977-3-28

[WAG.1727458]

Total: 26; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 7, Ekiti 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Osun 5.

Asplenium anisophyllum Kunze

Geerling 1796; 1967-12-16 [101148173]

Total: 1; Benue 1.

Asplenium barteri Hook.

Gledhill, D 882; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1727780]

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Niger 2, Osun 3.

Asplenium biafranum Alston & F.Ballard ex Ballard Hook.

Gbile 13; 1985-9-27 [101148560]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Asplenium blastophorum Hieron.

65; 1904-7-7 [K000423931]

Total: 5; Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Asplenium buettneri Hieron.

B.O. Daramola; 1979-04-27 [MO.1.01148642E8]

Total: 5; Ondo 1, Osun 1.

Asplenium buettneri var. *buettneri*

Daramola 130; 1979-4-27 [101148642][2332697599]

Total: 1.

Asplenium cuneatum Lam. — Introduced

Gregory, J.W. s.n.; 1893-4-1 [CANB 279492.1]

Total: 1.

Asplenium currorii Hook.

Richards P.W. 3826; 05-01-1948 [K]

Total: 5; Ondo 2, Osun 2.

Asplenium dognyense Rosenst.

Franc 95; [US 1096863]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Asplenium dregeanum Kunze

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63326; 1970-4-6
[WAG.1336601]

Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Ondo
6, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Asplenium emarginatum P.Beauv. —

Introduced

Chapman J.D. 5378; 18-04-1978 [K]

Total: 5; Anambra 1, Taraba 2.

Asplenium erectum Bory ex Willd. —

Introduced

Chapman J.D. 5155; 01-01-1978 [K000381438]

Total: 1.

Asplenium eylesii Sim — Introduced

Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. FHI46501; 31-07-1962 [K]

Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Asplenium formosum Willd.

A.P.D. Jones & C.F.A. Onochie 18756; 1946-5-20
[BM001056690]

Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Ondo 8,
Osun 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Asplenium formosum var. *formosum*

Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. 590; 05-09-1962 [K]

Total: 1.

Asplenium friesiorum C.Chr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Asplenium gemmascens Alston

H.J. Savory & R.W.J. Keay 25201; 1948-12-29
[BM000785456]

Total: 1.

Asplenium hemitomum Hieron.

Gledhill, D 957; 1968-4-6 [WAG.1723420]

Total: 10; Abia 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Ondo 2,
Osun 1, Sokoto 1.

Asplenium inaequilaterale Willd.

Chapman J.D. 3981; 01-12-1975 [K]

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Asplenium jaundeense Hieron.

M. E. Dyer 355; 1980-7-18 [1607760]3409058400

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 4, Taraba
1.

Asplenium laurentii J.Bommer

Literature

Total: 0.

Asplenium mannii Hook. — Introduced

Chapman, JD 2922; 1972-6-27 [WAG.1723114]

Total: 3; Borno 1, Taraba 2.

Asplenium megalura Hieron. — Introduced

A. P. Jones & C. Onochie 18757; 1946-5-20 [US
2424639]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Asplenium paucijugum F.Ballard

Onochie C.F.A. FHI36276X; 04-02-1957 [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Asplenium preussii Hieron.

Hepper F.N. 1581; -- [BR0000016312357]

Total: 12; Adamawa 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Asplenium protensum Schrad.

Hepper F.N. 2164; -- [BR0000016312487]

Total: 1.

Asplenium sandersonii Hook.

Literature

Total: 0.

Asplenium stuhlmannii Hieron.

Hambler, DJ 426; 1958-4-21 [U.1000616]

Total: 10; Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 4.

Asplenium subintegrum C.Chr. —

Introduced

Wright J.V. 6; 19-05-1951 [K]

Total: 4; Benue 1, Delta 1.

Asplenium theciferum (Kunth) Mett. —

Introduced

Davallia thecifera Kunth

Chapman, JD 2920; 1972-6-27 [WAG.1728076]

Total: 4; Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Asplenium theciferum var. *cornutum*

(Alston) Benl — Introduced

Asplenium cornutum Alston

Chapman, JD 2521; 1971-8-30 [WAG.1723887]

Total: 3; Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Asplenium uhligii Hieron.

Literature

Total: 0.

Asplenium variabile Hook.

Ariwaodo, JO 299; 1977-2-23 [WAG.1728460]

Total: 8; Cross River 4, Edo 2.

Athyrium ammifolium (Mett.) C.Chr.

- Asplenium ammfolium* Mett.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Athyrium filix-femina* (L.) Roth —
Introduced
Polypodium filix-femina L.
s.n.; 1860-- [1616198]3770155454
Total: 1; Plateau 1.
- Athyrium schimperi* Moug. ex Fée
Chapman J.D. 3496; 12-11-1974 [K]
Total: 2; Lagos 1.
- Blechnum attenuatum* (Sw.) Mett.
Onoclea attenuata Sw.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Blechnum tabulare* (Thunb.) Kuhn
Pteris tabularis Thunb.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Deparia boryana* (Willd.) M.Kato
Aspidium boryanum Willd.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Deparia boryana* subsp. *boryana*
Aspidium boryanum Willd.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Diplazium proliferum* (Lam.) Kaulf.
Asplenium proliferum Lam.
Gledhill, D; Oyewole, SO 873; 1968-3-16
[WAG.1309008]
Total: 7; Osun 3, Taraba 1.
- Diplazium sammatii* (Kuhn & Decken)
C.Chr.
Asplenium sammatii Kuhn
Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [343A]1990271841
Total: 10; Abia 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1.
- Diplazium welwitschii* (Hook.) Diels
Asplenium welwitschii Hook.
Ekwuno PFO.489; 1978-8-29
[101272047]3071245331
Total: 2; Kogi 1.
- Hymenasplenium unilaterale* (Lam.) Hayata
Asplenium unilaterale Lam.
Chapman, JD 2951; 1972-7-7 [WAG.1728570]
Total: 5; Anambra 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Taraba 1.
- Phegopteris cruciata* (Willd.) Mett.
- Aspidium cruciatum* Willd.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Stenochlaena tenuifolia* (Desv.) T.Moore
Lomaria tenuifolia Desv.
Specimen seen
Total: 1.
- Thelypteris afra* (Christ) C.F.Reed
Dryopteris afra Christ
Croat, TB 53461; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1301619]
Total: 1.
- Thelypteris bergiana* (Schltdl.) Ching
Polypodium bergianum Schltdl.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Thelypteris blastophora* (Alston) C.F.Reed
Cyclosorus blastophorus Alston
H.J. Savory & R.W.J. Keay FHI 25062; 1948-12-20
[BM001056527]
Total: 1.
- Thelypteris chaseana* Schelpe
Bowden J.K. 71; 06-04-1970 [K]
Total: 1.
- Thelypteris confluens* (Thunb.) C.V.Morton
Pteris confluens Thunb.
Bowden, J. 71; 1970-04-06 [K006651033]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.
- Thelypteris dentata* (Forssk.) E.P.St.John
Polypodium dentatum Forssk.
Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 47; 1979-4-20
[WAG.1301777]
Total: 1; Adamawa 1.
- Thelypteris guineensis* (Christ) Alston
Dryopteris guineensis Christ
Literature
Total: 0.
- Thelypteris hispidula* (Decne.) C.F.Reed
Aspidium hispidulum Decne.
Richards, P.W.; 17545.0 [K]
Total: 2.
- Thelypteris hispidula* var. *hispidula*
Aspidium hispidulum Decne.
Richards P.W. 3861; 13-01-1948 [K]
Total: 1.
- Thelypteris interrupta* (Willd.) K.Iwats.
Pteris interrupta Willd.
C. Thorold 2001; 1956-7-7 [US 2424856]
Total: 1.

Thelypteris madagascariensis (Fée) Schelpe
Goniopteris madagascariensis Fée

Literature

Total: 0.

Thelypteris microbasis (Baker) Tardieu
Nephrodium microbasis Baker

Barter 571; -- [K000435804]

Total: 1.

Thelypteris oppositifformis (C.Chr.) Ching
Dryopteris oppositifformis C.Chr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Thelypteris pauciflora (Hook.) C.F.Reed
Menisium pauciflorum Hook.

Literature

Total: 0.

Thelypteris pulchra (Bory ex Willd.)
Schelpe

Aspidium pulchrum Bory ex Willd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Thelypteris striata (Schumach.) Schelpe
Aspidium striatum Schumach.

Croat, TB 53454; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1301952]

Total: 1.

× *Chrismatopteris holttumii* Quansah &
D.S.Edwards — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

DIDYMOCHLAENACEAE

Didymochlaena truncatula (Sw.) J.Sm.
Aspidium truncatulum Sw.

Hall J.B. 2909; 21-06-1973 [K]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

POLYPODIACEAE

Arthropteris boutoniana (Hook.) Pic.Serm.
— Introduced

Aspidium boutonianum Hook.

DO.102.; 1979-4-23 [C0672249F]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Arthropteris monocarpa (Cordem.) C.Chr.
Nephrodium monocarpum Cordem.

Gbile 15; 1985-9-27 [101138909]

Total: 9; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Arthropteris orientalis (J.F.Gmel.) Posth.
Polypodium orientale J.F.Gmel.

Daramola 102; 1979-4-23 [101138969]

Total: 25; Bauchi 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 3, Ondo 10, Osun 1, Plateau 1.

Arthropteris orientalis var. *orientalis*
Polypodium orientale J.F.Gmel.

Arthropteris palisotii (Desv.) Alston
Aspidium palisotii Desv.

Palisot de Beauvois; 1808-- [P00483345]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Ogun 1.

Bolbitis acrostichoides (Afzel.) Ching
Hemionitis acrostichoides Afzel.

Dalziel J.M. 242; -- [BR0000016338661]

Total: 30; Adamawa 3, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 4, Plateau 4, Taraba 4.

Bolbitis auriculata (Lam.) Alston
Acrostichum auriculatum Lam.

Lowe, J. 1923; 1969-11-28 [K000888738]

Total: 11; Cross River 1, Edo 3, Ogun 1.

Bolbitis fluviatilis (Hook.) Ching
Acrostichum fluviatile Hook.

Schlechter, R. 12874 [K006587635]

Total: 2; Abia 1.

Bolbitis gaboonensis (Hook.) Ching
Acrostichum gaboonense Hook.

A. P. Jones & C. Onochie FHI17514; -- [US 2424629]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Bolbitis gemmifer (Hieron.) C.Chr.
Leptochilus gemmifer Hieron.

Hall J.B. 135; 10-04-1968 [K]

Total: 2.

Bolbitis heudelotii (Bory ex Fée) Alston
Gymnopteris heudelotii Bory ex Fée

Chapman, J.D. 4701; 1977-2-22 [K000897540]

Total: 11; Borno 1, Osun 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Bolbitis salicina (Hook.) Ching
Acrostichum salicinum Hook.

J. T. Baldwin 13763; 1949-11-20 [US 2610410]

Total: 3; Abia 1.

Ctenitis cirrhosa (Schumach.) Ching —
Introduced

Aspidium cirrhosum Schumach.

Chapman J.D. 4590; 07-08-1976 [K]

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Davallia chaerophylloides (Poir.) Steud.

Trichomanes chaerophylloides Poir.

Hall J.B. 140; 15-04-1968 [K]

Total: 2; Enugu 1.

Davallia denticulata (Burm.f.) Mett. —

Introduced

Adiantum denticulatum Burm.f.

Hall, Dr J.B. 140; 1968-4-15 [K000558492]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Benue 1, Edo 1, Kogi 2, Ondo 3.

Drynaria laurentii (Christ) Hieron.

Polypodium propinquum var. laurentii Christ ex
De Wild. & Durand

Gledhill, D 853; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1321011]

Total: 7; Enugu 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Plateau 2.

Drynaria volkensii Hieron. — Introduced

Chapman J.D. 4408; 28-04-1976 [K]

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Dryopteris affinis (Lowe) Fraser-Jenk.

Nephrodium affine Lowe

Literature

Total: 0.

Dryopteris affinis subsp. *borreri* (Newman)

Fraser-Jenk.

Dryopteris filix-mas var. borreri Newman

Pierre Villaret ; 1953-06-29 [19899.0]

Total: 1.

Dryopteris athamantica (Kunze) Kuntze

Aspidium athamanticum Kunze

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1318; 1972-5-10

[WAG.1309235]

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Dryopteris filix-mas (L.) Schott —

Introduced

Polypodium filix-mas L.

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/1948981034>

Total: 1.

Dryopteris glandulosopaleata J.P.Roux

Lely H.V. 308; 27-06-1921 [K]

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Dryopteris manniana (Hook.) C.Chr.

Polypodium mannianum Hook.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 355; 1977-10-13

[WAG.1731525]

Total: 6; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 2.

Dryopteris occidentalis J.P.Roux

Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. 737; 08-09-1962 [K]

Total: 1.

Dryopteris pentheri (Krasser) C.Chr.

Nephrodium pentheri Krasser

Literature

Total: 0.

Elaphoglossum barteri (Baker) C.Chr.

Acrostichum barteri Baker

Barter 1816; -- [K000435748]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Delta 1.

Hovenkampia schimperiana (Mett.) Li Bing

Zhang & X.M.Zhou

Polypodium schimperianum Mett.

Literature

Total: 0.

Lepisorus excavatus (Bory ex Willd.) Ching

Polypodium excavatum Bory ex Willd.

D.W.Lawlor & J.B.Hall 597; -- [BR0000017581943]

Total: 8; Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Lomariopsis decrescens (Baker) Kuhn

Acrostichum decrescens Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Lomariopsis guineensis (Underw.) Alston

Stenochlaena guineensis Underw.

Gledhill, D 914; 1968-4-5 [WAG.1736764]

Total: 24; Cross River 3, Edo 3, Niger 1, Ogun 4,

Ondo 5, Osun 1.

Lomariopsis hederacea Alston

Literature

Total: 0.

Lomariopsis mannii (Underw.) Alston

Stenochlaena mannii Underw.

Literature

Total: 0.

Lomariopsis muriculata Holttum

A. P. Jones & C. Onochie 18647; 1946-5-24 [US

2424633]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Lomariopsis palustris (Hook.) Mett.

Acrostichum palustre Hook.

Barter 1452; -- [K000435711]

Total: 7; Anambra 2, Delta 3.

Lomariopsis rossii Holttum

Gledhill, D 851; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1736656]

Total: 14; Edo 4, Osun 1.

Loxogramme abyssinica (Baker) M.G.Price

Gymnogramma abyssinica Baker

Gledhill, D 887; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1736503]

Total: 16; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 2, Osun 5, Taraba 1.

Loxogramme lanceolata (Sw.) C.Presl —
Introduced

Grammitis lanceolata Sw.
1945-5-4 [2252245875]
Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Loxogramme subecostata (Hook.) C.Chr. —
Introduced

Polypodium subecostatum Hook.
A. P. Jones & C. Onochie 3090; 1956-12-2 [US
2293580]
Total: 1; Nasarawa 1.

Megalastrum lanuginosum (Willd. ex
Kaulf.) Holttum

Aspidium lanuginosum Willd. ex Kaulf.
Literature
Total: 0.

Microgramma geminata (Schrad.)
R.M.Tryon & A.F.Tryon — Introduced

Polypodium geminatum Schrad.
Mann, G. 18615; 1946-5-16 [US 2424635]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Microgramma lycopodioides (L.) Copel. —
Introduced

Polypodium lycopodioides L.
Paul Westmacott Richards 3008; 1935-1-22
[BM000904554]
Total: 9; Cross River 3.

Microgramma mauritiana (Willd.) Tardieu
Polypodium mauritianum Willd.

Richards P.W. 3883; -- [BR0000017874946]
Total: 16; Abia 2, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 3.

Microsorium punctatum (L.) Copel.

Acrostichum punctatum L.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1383 a; 1966-4-16
[WAG.1732113]
Total: 10; Benue 1, Delta 2, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1,
Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Microsorium scolopendria (Burm.f.) Copel.
Polypodium scolopendria Burm.f.

Daramola, BO FHI 71118; 1974-8-4 [WAG.1732309]
Total: 9; Imo 1, Lagos 3, Ondo 5.

Nephrolepis biserrata (Sw.) Schott

Aspidium biserratum Sw.
Odewo, TK; Adedeji 326; 1983-5-17 [WAG.1320138]

Total: 46; Anambra 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 1, Delta
2, Edo 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Ogun
6, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Nephrolepis cordifolia (L.) C.Presl —
Introduced

Polypodium cordifolium L.
Literature
Total: 0.

Nephrolepis exaltata (L.) Schott —
Introduced

Polypodium exaltatum L.
Chapman, JD 2532; 1971-9-12 [WAG.1320201]
Total: 2; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Nephrolepis undulata (Afzel. ex Sw.) J.Sm.
Aspidium undulatum Afzel. ex Sw.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 355 A; 1977-10-13
[WAG.1731707]
Total: 54; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2,
Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Niger 2,
Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 10, Taraba 6.

Oleandra distenta Kunze

Haggs D.H. 152; 28-08-1948 [K]
Total: 8; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River
1, Enugu 1, Ondo 2.

Parapolystichum barterianum (Hook.)
Rouhan

Polypodium barterianum Hook.
O.O.Oyebanji; Ajibode Mutiu; 2015-1-1 [6820]
[3808441443]
Total: 6; Osun 6.

Parapolystichum currorii (Mett.) Rouhan
Aspidium currorii Mett.

Alan Philip Dalby Jones 4806; 1943-1-13
[BM001056793]
Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Parapolystichum currorii subsp. *currorii*
Aspidium currorii Mett.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI36032X; 18-01-1957 [K]
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Parapolystichum nigritianum (Baker)
Rouhan

Polypodium nigritianum Baker
Gledhill, D 859; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1731789]
Total: 7; Edo 1, Osun 2, Taraba 2.

Parapolystichum subsimile (Hook.) Rouhan
Gymnogramma subsimilis Hook.

Ariwaodo, JO FHI 88655; 1977-2-23 [WAG.1724907]
Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Parapolystichum vogelii (Hook.) Rouhan

Polypodium vogelii Hook.

Brenan J.P.M. [BR0000017581615]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Phymatosorus scolopendria (Burm.f.)

Pic.Serm.

Chaloner, W.G. 15/2; 1966-04-01 [K006437808]

Total: 25; Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ondo 3, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1.

Platyserium allicorne (P.Willemet) Desv.

— Introduced

Acrostichum allicorne P.Willemet

Usang felix; 2005-10-18 [372]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Platyserium elephantotis Schweinf.

Gledhill, D 852; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1732253]

Total: 6; Osun 4.

Platyserium stemaria (P.Beauv.) Desv.

Acrostichum stemaria P.Beauv.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO 792; 1971-11-2 [WAG.1740890]

Total: 12; Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Pleopeltis macrocarpa (Willd.) Kaulf.

Polypodium macrocarpum Willd.

Thresh, J.M.; 1; 1955-04-10 [K006503538]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Taraba 1.

Pyrrosia lanceolata (L.) Farw.

Acrostichum lanceolatum L.

M. Henderson 20149; 1928-3-31 [US 1704945]

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Pyrrosia longifolia (Burm.f.) C.V.Morton

— Introduced

Acrostichum longifolium Burm.f.

M. Henderson 20362; 1928-4-12 [US 1704965]

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Pyrrosia schimperiana (Mett.) Alston

Polypodium schimperianum Mett.

Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. 427; 16-08-1962 [K]

Total: 4; Bauchi 3, Nasarawa 1.

Tectaria angelicifolia (Schumach.) Copel.

Polypodium angelicifolium Schumach.

A. P. Jones & C. Onochie 18773; 1946-5-20 [US 2424628]

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Tectaria barberi (J.Sm.) C.Chr.

Aspidium barberi J.Sm.

Literature

Total: 0.

Tectaria camerooniana (Hook.) Alston

Polypodium cameroonianum Hook.

Chapman, J.D.; 4627; 1977-02-11 [K000709986]

Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Tectaria fernandensis (Baker) C.Chr.

Polypodium fernandense Baker

O.O.Oyebanji; Ajibode Mutiu; 2015-1-1 [6818] [3808439695]

Total: 8; Ondo 3, Osun 2, Taraba 2.

Triplophyllum buchholzii (Kuhn) Holttum

Aspidium buchholzii Kuhn

Hall J.B. 933; 28-02-1969 [K]

Total: 5; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Edo 1.

Triplophyllum fraternum (Mett.) Holttum

Aspidium fraternum Mett.

Ekwuno PFO.558; 1978-8-30 [101317668]3946791849

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Triplophyllum heudelotii Pic.Serm.

Literature

Total: 0.

Triplophyllum jenseniae (C.Chr.) Holttum

Dryopteris jenseniae C.Chr.

Glynne, M.D. 245 [K006476660]

Total: 1.

Triplophyllum pilosissimum (J.Sm. ex

T.Moore) Holttum

Lastrea pilosissima J.Sm. ex T.Moore

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI5813; 15-05-1946 [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Kwara 1.

Triplophyllum protensum (Afzel. ex Sw.)

Holttum

Aspidium protensum Afzel. ex Sw.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11306; 1977-3-31 [WAG.1306711]

Total: 31; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Delta 3, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kogi 3, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Triplophyllum securidiforme (Hook.)

Holttum

Nephrodium subquinquefidum var. securidiforme Hook.

D. Coombe 165; 1955-3-11 [US 2856879]

Total: 18; Abia 1, Cross River 7, Osun 5.

Triplophyllum securidiforme var. *nanum*

(Bonap.) Holttum

Dryopteris securidiformis var. nana Bonap.

Holland J.B. 193; 28-12-1949 [K]

Total: 2.

Triplophyllum securidiforme var.
securidiforme

Nephrodium subquinquefidum var. securidiforme
Hook.

Gledhill D. 973; 07-04-1968 [K]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Osun 2.

Triplophyllum subquinquefidum (P.Beauv.)
Pic.Serm.

Aspidium subquinquefidum P.Beauv.

Palisot de Beauvois; 1808-- [P00483160] [438119167]

Total: 1.

Triplophyllum troupinii (Pic.Serm.) Holttum
Ctenitis troupinii Pic.Serm.

Chaloner W.G 23_11; 1966-7 [K]

Total: 4; Abia 1.

Triplophyllum varians (T.Moore) Holttum
Dictyopteris varians T.Moore

Paul Westmacott Richards 3992; 1948-3-6
[BM001056745]

Total: 19; Abia 4, Cross River 8, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Triplophyllum varians subsp. *varians*
Dictyopteris varians T.Moore

Ariwaodo J.O. 1230; 02-06-1966 [K000727927]

Total: 2; Abia 1.

Triplophyllum vogelii (Hook.) Holttum
Aspidium vogelii Hook.

Vogel 250; -- [K000351121]

Total: 10; Cross River 2, Niger 1, Ondo 4.

CYCADACEAE

Cycas circinalis L. — Introduced

2807; 1989-7-24 [2807]

Total: 1; Imo 1.

ZAMIACEAE

Encephalartos barteri Carruth. ex Miq.

Meikle, R.D.; 1950-01-23 [K.23494.0]

Total: 34; Kwara 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 13.

Encephalartos barteri subsp. *allochrous*
L.E.Newton — Endemic

Newton, L. E. 1209a; 1972-4-6 [K000076204]

Total: 22; Plateau 13.

Encephalartos barteri subsp. *barteri*

Newton, L. E. 1209a; 1972-4-6 [K000076204]

Total: 1.

PODOCARPACEAE

Nageia wallichiana (C.Presl) Kuntze —
Introduced

Podocarpus wallichianus C.Presl

Eijnatten, CLM van 1388; 1966-4-15 [WAG.1361115]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Podocarpus milanjianus Rendle

Chapman, J.D. 4775; 1977-2-26 [K000289985]

Total: 15; Adamawa 4, Benue 1, Cross River 1,
Taraba 4.

PINACEAE

Pinus ayacahuite Ehrenb. ex Schtdl. —
Introduced

Chapman, JD 2984; 1972-12-25 [WAG.1360306]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Pinus canariensis C.Sm. ex DC. —
Introduced

Chapman, JD 2995; 1972-12-30 [WAG.1360337]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Pinus caribaea Morelet — Introduced

Lawal Monsurat; 2012-9-15 [5257] [3808439272]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Pinus oocarpa Schiede ex Schtdl. —
Introduced

Chapman, JD 2985; 1972-12-1 [WAG.1360682]

Total: 3; Lagos 1, Taraba 2.

Pinus sylvestris L. — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2005-8-7 [44E]1990271863

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

CUPRESSACEAE

Callitris columellaris F.Muell. —
Introduced

Usang Felix; 2005-10-12 [224]3913474481

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Callitris preissii Miq. — Introduced
1970-4-22 [2252242857]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Hesperocypris arizonica (Greene) Bartel

— Introduced

Cupressus arizonica Greene

Eijnatten, CLM van 2081; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1733402]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Borno 1.

Platyclusus orientalis (L.) Franco —

Introduced

Thuja orientalis L.

Usang Felix; 2005-10-3 [30]3913474610

Total: 4; Adamawa 2, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Thuja occidentalis L. — Introduced

Dr. Lawal; 2010-8-26 [2798]

Total: 5; Lagos 2, Oyo 3.

TAXACEAE

Taxus baccata L. — Introduced

Héribaud-Joseph s.n.; -- [US 2859173]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

GNETACEAE

Gnetum africanum Welw.

Ndueso, J.U. s.n.; 1982-12-06 (K)

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Lagos 2.

Gnetum buchholzianum Engl.

Okafor, J.C. 36387; 1957-02-18 (K)

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

CABOMBACEAE

Brasenia schreberi J.F.Gmel.

Literature

Total: 0.

NYMPHAEACEAE

Nymphaea guineensis Schumach. & Thonn.

McClintock, A. (Miss); 127; 1955-01-01

[K004056246]

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Katsina 1, Niger 5, Plateau 1.

Nymphaea heudelotii Planch.

Meikle, R.D.M. [K.11931.0]

Total: 5; Niger 2, Oyo 3.

Nymphaea lotus L.

Hereźniak, J. s.n.; 1975-02-12 (POZG)

Total: 57; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 4, Bayelsa 1, Borno 5, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 12, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Nymphaea lotus var. *lotus*

Hereźniak, J. s.n.; 1975-02-12 (POZG)

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 2.

Nymphaea maculata Schumach. & Thonn.

Zach, B. 172; 1994-10-15 (FR)

Total: 4; Borno 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Nymphaea micrantha Guill. & Perr.

Geerling, C. 3292; 1970-10-31 (WAG)

Total: 13; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Ondo 1.

Nymphaea nouchali Burm.f.

Barter, C 1064; 1857-1-1 [U.1446849]

Total: 1.

Nymphaea nouchali var. *caerulea* (Savigny)

Verdc. — Introduced

Barter, C 1064; 1857-1-1 [U.1446849]

Total: 1.

ARISTOLOCHIACEAE

Aristolochia albida Duch.

Ataholo, M. 1101; 1995-09-12 (FR)

Total: 7; Borno 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Aristolochia baetica L.

Alleizette, AC d' s.n.; 1918-8-1 [L.3965125]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Aristolochia bracteolata Lam.

Vogel, E. 45

Total: 1.

Aristolochia ceropegioides S.Moore

Pilz, GE 1971; 1977-4-24 [WAG.1583534]

Total: 1; Benue 1.

Aristolochia elegans Mast. — Introduced

Key, R.W.J. 46307; 1962-06-16 (K)

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Plateau 2.

Aristolochia goldieana Hook.f.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI21984; 1947-04-22 (K)

Total: 25; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Aristolochia littoralis Parodi

Literature

Total: 0.

Aristolochia macrocarpa Duch.

Talbot, P.A. 1542; 1912; -- [K000350282]

Total: 11; Kaduna 3, Ogun 2, Osun 2.

Aristolochia mannii Hook.f.

Mann, G. 2323; 1863-02 (K)

Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Rivers 1.

Aristolochia promissa Mast.

Talbot, P.A. 1642; 1912 (K)

Total: 10; Cross River 3, Kaduna 2, Ogun 1.

Aristolochia ringens Vahl — Introduced

Aristolochia grandiflora Vahl

Pilz, G.E. 2300; 1979-10-23 (WAG)

Total: 24; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 9, Ogun 2, Oyo 7.

Aristolochia triactina Hook.f.

Moloney, A. 18; 1883-04 (K)

Total: 2.

Aristolochia zenkeri Engl.

Brenan, J.P.M. 8467; 1947-11-11 (K)

Total: 3; Edo 2, Ogun 1.

Hydnora abyssinica A.Br.

Literature

Total: 0.

PIPERACEAE

Peperomia exigua (Blume) Miq.

Piper exiguum Blume

Literature

Total: 0.

Peperomia fernandopoiana C.DC.

F.W.H. Migeod [MO.1.01182014E8]

Total: 6; Cross River 3.

Peperomia fernandopoiana var.

fernandopoiana

Meer, PPC van 1844; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1166954]

Total: 1.

Peperomia molleri C.DC.

Latilo, M.G.; FHI67543; 1973-09-26 [K004450282]

Total: 5; Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Peperomia molleri subsp. *molleri*

Peperomia pellucida (L.) Kunth

Piper pellucidum L.

Vogel [K000350415]

Total: 44; Anambra 1, Edo 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 14, Plateau 1.

Peperomia pellucida var. *pellucida*

Piper pellucidum L.

Pilz, GE 2050; 1977-5-14 [WAG.1167069]

Total: 1.

Peperomia retusa (L.f.) A.Dietr.

Piper retusum L.f.

Meer, PPC van 1828; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1168060]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 5, Taraba 2.

Peperomia tetraphylla (G.Forst.) Hook. & Arn.

Piper tetraphyllum G.Forst.

Chapman, J.D. 3510; 1974-11-14 [K004450144]

Total: 4; Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Peperomia thomeana C.DC.

Hall, J.B. 3021; 1971-03-15 [K004450298]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Peperomia vulcanica Baker & C.H.Wright

Chapman, JD 2965; 1972-7-9 [WAG.1167212]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Piper capense L.f.

B.O. Daramola; 1968-07-03 [MO.1.01224071E8]

Total: 16; Cross River 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 12.

Piper capense var. *capense*

Daramola, BO 203; 1977-8-25 [WAG.1167527]

Total: 1.

Piper guineense Schumach. & Thonn.

Meer, PPC van 927; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1167830]

Total: 68; Abia 2, Adamawa 3, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 8, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 10, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 7, Oyo 14.

Piper nigrum L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1331; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1167915]

Total: 7; Lagos 2, Oyo 3.

Piper umbellatum L. — Introduced

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32692; 1981-6-15

[WAG.1168186]

Total: 44; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 3, Benue 2, Cross River 6, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

MYRISTICACEAE

Coelocaryon botryoides Vermeesen

1952-6-21 [2252243387]

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Kogi 3.

Coelocaryon oxycarpum Stapf

Kennedy J.D. 1739; 1931-8- [BR0000016696457]

Total: 2; Edo 2.

Coelocaryon preussii Warb.

Kennedy J.D. 1848; -- [BR0000013965051]

Total: 20; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Delta 3, Edo 4.

Myristica fragrans Houtt. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1613; 1966-6-13 [WAG.1112163]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Pycnanthus angolensis (Welw.) Warb.

Myristica angolensis Welw.

[K.14331.0]

Total: 38; Abia 5, Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 6, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 4.

Pycnanthus angolensis subsp. *angolensis*

Myristica angolensis Welw.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32853; 1981-6-20

[WAG.1112341]

Total: 4; Delta 1, Oyo 1.

Pycnanthus microcephalus (Benth.) Stapf

Myristica microcephala Benth.

Binuyo, A.; FHI41399; 1959-07-22 [K003693863]

Total: 4; Abia 1, Cross River 1.

Scyphocephalum mannii (Benth.) Warb.

Myristica mannii Benth.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70558; 1973-3-11

[WAG.1112443]

Total: 19; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 6.

Staudtia kamerunensis Warb.

Binuyo, A FHI 41437; 1959-8-8 [WAG.1112557]

Total: 37; Abia 1, Borno 9, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Kaduna 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Staudtia kamerunensis var. *gabonensis*

(Warb.) Fougilloy

Kennedy J.D. 1925; -- [BR0000013978006]

Total: 26; Borno 9, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

ANNONACEAE

Annickia affinis (Exell) Versteegh & Sosef

Enantia affinis Exell

Brenan 8610 (BM, K)

Total: 2.

Annickia chlorantha (Oliv.) Setten & Maas

Enantia chlorantha Oliv.

Ariwaodo, JO 64 (WAG, FHI)

Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 6, Ebonyi 4, Edo 3, Kano 2, Lagos 6, Ogun 3.

Annickia polycarpa (DC.) Setten & Maas ex

I.M. Turner

Unona polycarpa DC.

Obaseki, F.A. FHI 22854 (K)

Total: 7; Edo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Annona glabra L.

Bels, L 99 (U)

Total: 8; Lagos 5, Yobe 1.

Annona muricata L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1460; 1966-5-2 [WAG.1425939]

Total: 45; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Lagos 16, Ogun 5, Osun 4, Oyo 11, Rivers 1.

Annona reticulata L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1304; 1966-3-26 [WAG.1425965]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Oyo 5.

Annona senegalensis Pers.

Eimunjjeze, VE; Adebunsi, JK; Macauley, S FHI

66972; 1973-5-23 [WAG.1426180]

Total: 248; Adamawa 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 15, Benue 2, Borno 11, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 6, Gombe 7, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 21, Kano 5, Kebbi 6, Kogi 7, Kwara 13, Lagos 10, Nasarawa 3, Niger 30, Ogun 10, Ondo 4, Osun 8, Oyo 31, Plateau 12, Sokoto 2, Taraba 11, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Annona senegalensis subsp. *oulotricha* Le

Thomas

Chapman, JD 2838; 1972-5-28 [WAG.1426151]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Annona senegalensis subsp. *senegalensis*

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66003

Total: 37; Bauchi 3, Borno 6, Enugu 1, Gombe 5, Kaduna 10, Niger 5, Ondo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Annona senegalensis var. *areolata* Le

Thomas

1969-06-03 [2252242795]

Total: 1.

Annona squamosa L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1681; 1966-7-9 [WAG.1426205]

Total: 14; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Anonidium mannii (Oliv.) Engl. & Diels

Annona mannii Oliv.

Mann, G. 2231 (B) (isotype); Brenan, J.P.M. 9110 (K)
Total: 59; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Benue 1, Cross River
13, Edo 19, Imo 1, Ondo 8, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Artabotrys coccineus Keay

Onochie, CFA FHI 40296 (Talbot, P.A., #1322 type)
Total: 30; Edo 7, Ondo 1, Oyo 17, Taraba 2.

Artabotrys dahomensis Engl. & Diels

Thomas, N.W.; 1399; 1911-01-01 [K003313236]
Total: 1.

Artabotrys insignis Engl. & Diels

Onochie, C.F.A. 35000; 1956-10-26 [7124]
Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Artabotrys rufus De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Artabotrys stenopetalus Engl. & Diels

NO collection from Nigeria reported
Total: 1.

Artabotrys thomsonii Oliv.

Mann s.n. ; 1863-- [B 10 0154054]
Total: 12; Cross River 7.

Artabotrys velutinus Scott Elliot

Lely, H.V. 541; 1921-8-17 [K000198866]
Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2,
Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba
1.

Cananga odorata (Lam.) Hook.f. &

Thomson — Introduced

Uvaria odorata Lam.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70576; 1973-3-12
[WAG.1379381]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 5, Delta
1, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Cleistopholis patens (Benth.) Engl. & Diels

Oxymitra patens Benth.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 38341 (FHI, WAG)
Total: 82; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 3,
Cross River 6, Edo 11, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi
5, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 9, Ondo 5,
Osun 4, Oyo 11, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Cleistopholis staudtii (Engl. & Diels) Engl.
& Diels

Oxymitra staudtii Engl. & Diels

POWO

Total: 1.

Dennettia tripetala Baker f.

R.E. Dennett 44 (holotype: K (K000040961)

Total: 7; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Ogun 1.

Duguetia barteri (Benth.) Chatrou

Annona barteri Benth.

C. Barter .f45(holotype, K!)

Total: 1.

Duguetia staudtii (Engl. & Diels) Chatrou

Uvaria staudtii Engl. & Diels

Talbot 1494 (BM, Z)

Total: 6; Cross River 4.

Goniothalamus angustifolius (A.C.Sm.)

B.Xue & R.M.K.Saunders

Polyalthia angustifolia A.C.Sm.

Ugwuozor P.O. ; 2014-02-18 [188B]

Total: 1.

Greenwayodendron oliveri (Engl.) Verdc.

Polyalthia oliveri Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1228 (WAG)

Total: 16; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 10.

Greenwayodendron suaveolens (Engl. &
Diels) Verdc.

Polyalthia suaveolens Engl. & Diels

Meer, PPC van 1795 (WAG)

Total: 19; Cross River 12, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Ogun 1,
Taraba 1.

Hexalobus crispiflorus A.Rich.

Onochie FHI 31206 (FHO); 1948, Russell FHI 22551
(K)

Total: 49; Benue 1, Cross River 3, Ekiti 1, Imo 1,
Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Niger 1,
Ogun 3, Ondo 12, Osun 2, Oyo 7.

Hexalobus monopetalus (A.Rich.) Engl. &
Diels

Uvaria monopetala A.Rich.

Bamps 7711 (BR, MO, WAG)

Total: 47; Adamawa 12, Bauchi 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna
5, Katsina 3, Kogi 7, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2,
Plateau 2.

Isolona campanulata Engl. & Diels

Binuyo FHI 41274 (BR, FHI, FHO, K, WAG)

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2.

Isolona deightonii Keay

Chapman 4573 (FHO)

Total: 1.

Isolona dewevrei (De Wild. & T.Durand)
Engl. & Diels

Monodora dewevrei De Wild. & T.Durand
[Adebusuyi 43592 \(K\)](#)
Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Isolona hexaloba (Pierre) Engl. & Diels
Monodora hexaloba Pierre
[Kennedy 1568 \(A, BEDF, F, FHO, L, M, MO, S, US\)](#)
Total: 12; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Ogun 3.

Isolona pleurocarpa Diels
[Latilo FHI 41347 \(K\)](#)
Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Niger 1, Osun 1.

Isolona thonneri (De Wild. & T.Durand)
Engl. & Diels
Monodora thonneri De Wild. & T.Durand
[Hide 38/1 \(FHO\)](#)
Total: 1.

Mischogyne elliotiana (Engl. & Diels)
R.E.Fr. ex Le Thomas
Uvaria elliotiana Engl. & Diels
[Symington C.F. \[FHI.5073.0\]](#)
Total: 4; Oyo 2.

Mischogyne elliotiana var. *elliotiana*
Uvaria elliotiana Engl. & Diels

Monanthes angustifolia (Exell) Verdc.
Enneastemon angustifolius Exell
[Paul W. Richards; 1935-05-17 \[MO.3591355.0\]](#)
Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Monanthes barberi (Baill.) Verdc.
Popowia barberi Baill.
[Talbot, P.A. 1550 \(BM,K\)](#)
Total: 2.

Monanthes cauliflora (Chipp) Verdc.
Popowia cauliflora Chipp
[Thomson, W.C. s.n. \(K\)](#)
Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Monanthes enghiana (Diels)
P.H.Hoekstra
Popowia enghiana Diels
[Talbot, P.A. 1246 \(BM\)](#)
Total: 1.

Monanthes farquharii (Hutch. & Dalziel) Couvreur, P.H.Hoekstra, Wieringa
— Endemic
[Farquhar, J.H.J., 73 \(K\)](#)
Total: 2.

Monanthes filamentosa (Diels) Verdc.
Popowia filamentosa Diels
[Keay, R.W.J.; FHI28187; 1950-12-09 \[K003818823\]](#)

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Monanthes foliosa (Engl. & Diels)
Verdc.

Popowia foliosa Engl. & Diels
[Akpabla, G.K. 1112 \(K\)](#)
Total: 15; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Edo 5, Imo 1.

Monanthes foliosa var. *foliosa*
Popowia foliosa Engl. & Diels
[Meer, P.P.C. van 1851 \(WAG\)](#)
Total: 1.

Monanthes glaucifolia (Hutch. & Dalziel) P.H.Hoekstra
Oxymitra glaucifolia Hutch. & Dalziel
[Talbot, P.A. 1255; 1911-- \[BM001125031\]](#)
Total: 1.

Monanthes gracilis (Hook.f.)
P.H.Hoekstra
Uvaria gracilis Hook.f.
[Daramola, B.O. 484 \(FHI,MO,WAG\)](#)
Total: 28; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Monanthes hirsuta (Benth.)
P.H.Hoekstra
Unona hirsuta Benth.
[Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28187 \(K,P\)](#)
Total: 3; Edo 1.

Monanthes laurentii (De Wild.) Verdc.
Popowia laurentii De Wild.
[Daramola, B.O. 403 \(MO\)](#)
Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Taraba 2.

Monanthes lucidula (Oliv.) Verdc.
Unona lucidula Oliv.
[K. Schmitt; H. Onyeachusium; 1994-04-11 \[MO.976574.0\]](#)
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Monanthes montana (Engl. & Diels)
P.H.Hoekstra
Unona montana Engl. & Diels
[Ahmed; Chizea; 1948-7-23 \[19780\]](#)
Total: 1.

Monanthes schweinfurthii (Engl. & Diels) Verdc.
Popowia schweinfurthii Engl. & Diels
[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Monanthes vogelii (Hook.f.) Verdc.
Uvaria vogelii Hook.f.

Dalziel, J.M. 712 (BM,K,MO,MO,P)

Total: 22; Benue 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Monanthes vulcanica P.H.Hoekstra

Chapman, J.D. 3675 (FHO,K)

Total: 1.

Monanthes whytei (Stapf) Verdc.

Popowia whytei Stapf

Laan, F.M. van der 364 (WAG)

Total: 5; Kogi 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1.

Monodora angolensis Welw.

Meer, P.P.C. van 1213 (WAG)

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 2.

Monodora crispata Engl.

Talbot, P.A. 1499 (WAG)

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Monodora myristica (Gaertn.) Dunal

Annona myristica Gaertn.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 38301 (WAG)

Total: 49; Anambra 1, Cross River 6, Edo 10, Enugu 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 2.

Monodora tenuifolia Benth.

Binuyo, A. FHI 41249 (WAG)

Total: 130; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 12, Edo 18, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 5, Ogun 10, Ondo 4, Osun 6, Oyo 33, Plateau 2, Rivers 3.

Monodora undulata (P.Beauv.) Couvreur

Xylopia undulata P.Beauv.

Olorunfemi, J. FHI 38063 (P,K)

Total: 11; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Edo 4, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Monoon longifolium (Sonn.) B.Xue &

R.M.K.Saunders — Introduced

Uvaria longifolia Sonn.

Ugwuzor P.O.; 2011-01-31 [FHI.70A]

Total: 1.

Neostenanthera gabonensis (Engl. & Diels)

Exell

Oxymitra gabonensis Engl. & Diels

Alwyn H. Gentry; George E. Pilz; 1981-06-21

[MO.756065.0]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Neostenanthera hamata (Benth.) Exell

Oxymitra hamata Benth.

Daramola B.O.; 1966-03-25 [FHI.56441.0]

Total: 1.

Neostenanthera myristicifolia (Oliv.) Exell

Oxymitra myristicifolia Oliv.

J. D. Kennedy 1701 (FHO)

Total: 27; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Delta 4, Edo 12, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 2.

Piptostigma fugax A.Chev. ex Hutch. &

Dalziel

Literature

Total: 0.

Piptostigma glabrescens Oliv.

Literature

Total: 0.

Piptostigma pilosum Oliv.

Meer, P.P.C. van 1198 (WAG)

Total: 13; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Kwara 1, Niger 2.

Polyceratocarpus parviflorus (Baker f.)

Ghesq.

Alphonseopsis parviflora Baker f.

Talbot P.A. [BR0000014036576]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 1, Edo 2.

Sphaerocoryne gracilipes (Benth.) X.Guo &

R.M.K.Saunders

Oxymitra gracilipes Benth.

Jones, A.P.D. FHI 18798; 1946-5-24 (FHO)

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Uvaria afzelii Scott Elliot

Latilo, M.G. FHI 27628 (K)

Total: 10; Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Uvaria angolensis Welw. ex Oliv.

Olatubosun O.O.; 1971-02-06 [LUH.15.0]

Total: 8; Anambra 1, Enugu 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Uvaria angolensis subsp. *guineense* Keay

Onochie, C.F.A.; FHI35851; 1956-05-23

[K003529545]

Total: 1.

Uvaria annonoides Baker f.

Talbot P.A. 1558 (K)

Total: 1.

Uvaria chamae P.Beauv.

Meer, P.P.C. van 1057 (WAG)

Total: 207; Abia 13, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 5, Bauchi 4, Benue 2, Borno 2, Cross River 6, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 8, Enugu 7, Imo 1, Kaduna 23, Katsina 2, Kogi 6, Kwara 1, Lagos 17, Nasarawa 6, Niger 3, Ogun 12, Ondo 8, Osun 7, Oyo 23, Plateau 22, Taraba 4.

Uvaria forbesii (Baker f.) L.L.Zhou,

Y.C.F.Su & R.M.K.Saunders

- Rauwenhoffia forbesii* Baker f.
John D.; 1980-11-10 [1089] 2274829372
Total: 1; Cross River 1.
- Uvaria muricata* Pierre ex Engl. & Diels
Klaine, R.P.; 1896-08-01 [B 10 0153099]
Total: 1.
- Uvaria obanensis* Baker f.
Talbot, P., 1603; -- [K000198780]
Total: 9.
- Uvaria scabrida* Oliv.
Ariwaodo, J.O., #1092
Total: 17; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 2, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.
- Uvariastrum insculptum* (Engl. & Diels) Sprague & Hutch.
Uvaria insculpta Engl. & Diels
Daramola, B.O. 94/ 581 (F, MO)
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 1.
- Uvariastrum pierreanum* Engl.
Brenan, J.P.M. 8901 (COI, FHO, K, P)
Total: 22; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 14, Kaduna 4.
- Uvariastrum zenkeri* Engl. & Diels
Talbot, P.A. 1341 (FHO, P)
Total: 4; Cross River 2.
- Uvariadendron angustifolium* (Engl. & Diels) R.E.Fr.
Uvaria angustifolia Engl. & Diels
Daramola 94/ 337 (K, MO)
Total: 20; Ogun 1, Ondo 9, Osun 2, Oyo 5.
- Uvariadendron calophyllum* R.E.Fr.
J.O. Ariwaodo 447 (FHI, WAG)
Total: 18; Cross River 11, Oyo 5.
- Uvariadendron connivens* (Benth.) R.E.Fr.
Uvaria connivens Benth.
P.P.C. van Meer 1430 (WAG)
Total: 17; Abia 1, Benue 1, Cross River 12.
- Uvariadendron occidentale* Le Thomas
Anakwense, F FHI 19701 (K)
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Ondo 1.
- Uvariopsis bakeriana* (Hutch. & Dalziel) Robyns & Ghesq.
Tetrastemma bakerianum Hutch. & Dalziel
P.A. Talbot 1517 (holotype: K; isotype: BM);
Total: 15; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Niger 2.
- Uvariopsis dioica* (Diels) Robyns & Ghesq.
Tetrastemma dioicum Diels
- R.W.J. Keay FHI 28066 (K, P)
Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 1, Edo 2.
- Xylopia aethiopica* (Dunal) A.Rich.
Unona aethiopica Dunal
Daramola 441 (F, MO)
Total: 50; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1.
- Xylopia africana* (Benth.) Oliv.
Melodorum africanum Benth.
van Meer 1768 (WAG)
Total: 8; Benue 1, Cross River 4, Imo 1, Kaduna 2.
- Xylopia calva* D.M.Johnson & N.A.Murray
Ross R.202 (K)
Total: 2.
- Xylopia cupularis* Mildbr.
Daramola FHI 45672 (K)
Total: 4; Anambra 1, Edo 2.
- Xylopia elliotii* Pierre ex Engl. & Diels
Chapman, JD 2725; 1972-3-9 [WAG.1540880]
Total: 3; Taraba 3.
- Xylopia katangensis* De Wild.
Hepper 1143 (BR, K, P)
Total: 3; Kaduna 2.
- Xylopia letestui* Pellegr.
Talbot s. n. (BM)
Total: 1.
- Xylopia longipetala* De Wild. & T.Durand
Geerling, C. 3098 (WAG)
Total: 31; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Benue 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 7, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.
- Xylopia monticola* D.M.Johnson & N.A.Murray
Chapman 4730 (K)
Total: 6; Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.
- Xylopia parviflora* Spruce
Croat, TB 53409; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1540635]
Total: 8; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 1.
- Xylopia phloiodora* Mildbr.
Kennedy 2612 (A, BR, F, MO, PR, US, YF)
Total: 1; Cross River 1.
- Xylopia pynaertii* De Wild.
Catterall 51 (K)
Total: 3; Cross River 2.
- Xylopia quintasii* Pierre ex Engl. & Diels

Kennedy 1662 (A, BM, K, PR, US, YF)
[BR0000014130038]
Total: 38; Adamawa 1, Cross River 4, Edo 8, Kaduna
5, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 1.

Xylopia rubescens Oliv.

Wit & Wit FHI 64927 (K, WAG)
Total: 19; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Lagos
1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3.

Xylopia sericea A.St.-Hil.

Apejoye F. I.; 2011-3-16 [1094] 2274829409
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Xylopia staudtii Engl. & Diels

Rosevear C.21 (K)
Total: 2; Abia 1.

Xylopia talbotii Exell

1601; -- [K000199068]
Total: 4; Cross River 1.

Xylopia thomsonii Oliv.

Talbot 1353 (BM)
Total: 3; Abia 1, Cross River 1.

Xylopia villosa Chipp

Kennedy 2574 (A, BM, F, MO, US)
Total: 34; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Gombe
1, Imo 4, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 6, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

HERNANDIACEAE

Illigera pentaphylla Welw.

Medler, JA 62; 1969-7-20 [WAG.1568556]
Total: 10; Edo 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Illigera vespertilio (Benth.) Baker f.

Dioscorea vespertilio Benth.

Literature

Total: 0.

LAURACEAE

Beilschmiedia caudata (Stapf) A.Chev.

Afrodaphne caudata Stapf

Gentry 32938; 1981-6-21 [52750] [1261236667]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Beilschmiedia conferta (S.Moore) Robyns &
R.Wilczek — Endemic

Tylostemon confertus S.Moore

Talbot, P.A.; 3399; 1912-01-01 [K000350215]
Total: 1.

Beilschmiedia foliosa (S.Moore) Robyns &
R.Wilczek — Endemic

Tylostemon foliosus S.Moore

Talbot P.A. 2342; 1912-- [BM000910528]
Total: 4; Oyo 1.

Beilschmiedia gaboonensis (Meisn.) Benth.
& Hook.f. ex B.D.Jacks.

Oreodaphne gaboonensis Meisn.

Talbot P.A. 3399; -- [BR0000015616852]
Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.

Beilschmiedia hutchinsoniana Robyns &
R.Wilczek

Tylostemon macrophyllus Hutch. & Dalziel

Zalht, R.A. 2301; -- [K000350211]
Total: 3; Niger 1.

Beilschmiedia insularum Robyns &
R.Wilczek

Mann, G.; 1863-- [P00540849]
Total: 1.

Beilschmiedia mannii (Meisn.) Benth. &
Hook.f. ex B.D.Jacks.

Oreodaphne mannii Meisn.

Mann, G. 2255; -- [K000350210]
Total: 19; Abia 3, Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Cross River
4, Imo 4, Kwara 1, Taraba 2.

Beilschmiedia minutiflora (Meisn.) Benth. &
Hook.f. ex B.D.Jacks.

Oreodaphne minutiflora Meisn.

Latilo M.G. FHI45803; 21-11-1962 [K]
Total: 2.

Beilschmiedia myrciifolia (S.Moore) Robyns
& R.Wilczek

Tylostemon myrciifolius S.Moore

Talbot P.A. 2334; 1912-- [BM000910524]
Total: 2.

Beilschmiedia staudtii Engl.

Latilo M.G.; *Onyechusim* FHI54256; 12-03-1964
[K000461449]
Total: 1.

Beilschmiedia talbotiae (S.Moore) Robyns
& R.Wilczek

Tylostemon talbotiae S.Moore

Talbot P.A. 1539; -- [K000350213]
Total: 11; Cross River 2, Edo 2, Niger 2, Osun 1.

Cassytha filiformis L.

Pilz, GE 1847; 1976-11-14 [WAG.1694414]

Total: 39; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 7, Lagos 5, Niger 3, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Sokoto 1.

Cinnamomum camphora (L.) J.Presl —
Introduced

Laurus camphora L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cinnamomum verum J.Presl — Introduced

Laurus cinnamomum L.

Obi F.O. FHI17083; 21-09-1951 [K]

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1.

Hypodaphnis zenkeri (Engl.) Stapf

Ocotea zenkeri Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1362; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1694065]

Total: 31; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Edo 10, Kaduna 6, Ondo 1.

Persea americana Mill. — Introduced

Laurus persea L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1161; 1965-12-12

[WAG.1693256]

Total: 25; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 13, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

MONIMIACEAE

Steghanthera hirsuta Perkins — Introduced
Philipson, W.R.; Kairo, A.; 1979-7-11 [P01962592]
Total: 1.

Xymalos monospora (Harv.) Baill.

Xylosma monospora Harv.

Dr Kadiri A.B.; 2008-12-1 [322] [3808438578]

Total: 10; Sokoto 1, Taraba 5.

SIPARUNACEAE

Glossocalyx longicuspis Benth.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70548; 1973-3-9

[WAG.1103675]

Total: 15; Abia 2, Cross River 8, Niger 1.

ARACEAE

Alocasia macrorrhizos (L.) G.Don —
Introduced

Arum macrorrhizon L.

[D. S. M. Gurta] s.n.; 1967-05-01 [K002822015]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Amorphophallus abyssinicus (A.Rich.)
N.E.Br.

Arum abyssinicum A.Rich.

Blom-van Teyn, M van 173; 1972-7-12

[WAG.1661377]

Total: 22; Benue 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Oyo 2, Taraba 2.

Amorphophallus abyssinicus subsp.
abyssinicus

Arum abyssinicum A.Rich.

Hall, J.B. 1728; 03-04-1970 [K002978903]

Total: 15; Benue 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Oyo 2, Taraba 2.

Amorphophallus abyssinicus subsp. *akeassii*
Ittenb.

Amorphophallus baumannii (Engl.) N.E.Br.

Hydrosme baumannii Engl.

Geerling, C 3580; 1971-7-20 [WAG.1661323]

Total: 12; Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Oyo 4.

Amorphophallus calabaricus N.E.Br.

Wit, P 2226; 1972-7-3 [WAG.1661314]

Total: 11; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Oyo 3.

Amorphophallus calabaricus subsp.
calabaricus

Brenan J.P.M. 8554; 19-12-1947 [K000541785]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Amorphophallus consimilis Blume —
Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Amorphophallus dracontioides (Engl.)
N.E.Br.

Hydrosme dracontioides Engl.

Meer, PPC van 675; 1968-3-11 [WAG.1661301]

Total: 16; Kogi 1, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1.

Amorphophallus gracilior Hutch.

Amorphophallus gracilis A.Chev.

Killick, H.J. 56564; 1965-1-10 [K000499379]

Total: 6; Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1.

Amorphophallus johnsonii N.E.Br.

Bels, L 77; 1950-4-16 [U.1093682]

Total: 10; Edo 4, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Amorphophallus zenkeri (Engl.) N.E.Br.

Hydrosme zenkeri Engl.

Unknown s.n.; -- [L.4289281]

Total: 2.

Amorphophallus zenkeri subsp. *zenkeri*

Hydrosme *zenkeri* Engl.

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 1300; 30-01-1912
[K000541779]

Total: 1.

Anchomanes abbreviatus Engl.

[34595]

Total: 2.

Anchomanes dalzielii N.E.Br.

Dalziel, J.M. 563; 1911-6-16 [K000345894]

Total: 14; Kaduna 4, Niger 10.

Anchomanes difformis (Blume) Engl.

Amorphophallus difformis Blume

Laan, FM van der 858; 1985-4-22 [WAG.1661110]

Total: 58; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 9, Delta 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Osun 5, Oyo 13, Rivers 4, Taraba 1.

Anchomanes nigritianus Rendle

Percy Amaury Talbot 1247; 1911-- [BM000050810]

Total: 1.

Anubias afzelii Schott — Introduced

Morton 1202; 1961-5-1 [100908365]

Total: 1; Abia 1.

Anubias barteri Schott

Reid, J s.n.; 1983-11-22 [WAG.1965701]

Total: 34; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 15, Kano 1, Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Anubias barteri var. *angustifolia* (Engl.)

Crusio

Meer, PPC van 1406; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1660944]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Anubias barteri var. *barteri*

s.coll.36037; 1957-1-18 [K000499348]

Total: 3; Abia 2.

Anubias barteri var. *caladiifolia* Engl.

Anubias barteri var. *glabra* N.E.Br.

Reid J.C. 18; 01-07-1983 [K002556563]

Total: 16; Abia 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Kano 1, Rivers 1.

Anubias gillettii De Wild. & T.Durand

Lowe J. 1946; 04-01-1970 [K002556581]

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Anubias hastifolia Engl.

Daramola, B. O.; 2010-7-30 [3337]

Total: 9; Cross River 2, Edo 4, Lagos 1.

Anubias pynaertii De Wild. — Introduced

Morton K 1201; 1961-1-8 [100909540]

Total: 1; Abia 1.

Caladium bicolor (Aiton) Vent. —

Introduced

Arum bicolor Aiton

Swarbrick J.T; 1962-6- [E01048665]

Total: 13; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Edo 2, Imo 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Cercestis afzelii Schott

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI18753; 19-05-1946
[K002556697]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Cercestis camerunensis (Ntépé-Nyamè)

Bogner

Rhektophyllum camerunense Ntépé-Nyamè

Onochie, C.F.A. 34829; 1955-3-14 [K000345919]

Total: 3; Abia 2.

Cercestis dinklagei Engl.

Croat 53494; 1981-11-18 [2378277]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Cercestis kamerunianus (Engl.) N.E.Br.

Alocasiophyllum kamerunianum Engl.

Brenan, J.P.M., Jones, E.W., Onochie, C.F.A.,

Richards, P.W.; 1947-- [B 10 0844087]

Total: 10; Edo 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 3.

Cercestis mirabilis (N.E.Br.) Bogner

Rhektophyllum mirabile N.E.Br.

T. B. Croat 53495; 1981-11-18 [US 2980169]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Colocasia esculenta (L.) Schott —

Introduced

Arum esculentum L.

Ugwuzor P.O.; 2014-9-8 [147A]1990271741

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Culcasia ekongoloi Ntépé-Nyamè

Hepper F.N. 1582; 12-12-1957 [K000499441]

Total: 1.

Culcasia insulana N.E.Br.

Chapman J.D. 4025; 01-12-1975 [K002556790]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Culcasia lanceolata Engl.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI18607; 1946-5

[K000499439]

Total: 1.

Culcasia mannii (Hook.f.) Engl.

Aglaonema mannii Hook.f.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1611; 1966-6-13 [WAG.1666775]
Total: 10; Cross River 4, Oyo 6.

Culcasia panduriformis Engl. & K.Krause
Brenan J.P.M. 8526D; 21-12-1947 [K000541584]
Total: 1.

Culcasia parviflora N.E.Br.
Alan Philip Dalby Jones 6585; 1942-5-29
[BM013718669]
Total: 3; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Kwara 1.

Culcasia scandens P.Beauv.
Pilz, GE 1921; 1977-1-8 [WAG.1666495]
Total: 104; Abia 2, Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1,
Bayelsa 1, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Ebonyi 2, Edo 9,
Enugu 5, Kaduna 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger
3, Ogun 9, Ondo 3, Oyo 15, Rivers 3.

Culcasia seretii De Wild.
Literature
Total: 0.

Culcasia simiarum Ntépe-Nyamè
Literature
Total: 0.

Culcasia striolata Engl.
Pilz, GE 2646; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1666220]
Total: 18; Edo 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 1.

Culcasia tenuifolia Engl.
Pilz, GE 2648; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1666164]
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1.

Epipremnum aureum (Linden & André)
G.S.Bunting
Pothos aureus Linden & André
Felix; 2005-10-22 [397]3913474558
Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Lasimorpha senegalensis Schott
Lowe, J 1726; 1969-3-31 [WAG.1665794]
Total: 37; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 4,
Delta 2, Edo 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo
2, Rivers 1.

Lemna aequinoctialis Welw.
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11217; 1977-3-17
[WAG.1054859]
Total: 35; Cross River 1, Edo 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 1,
Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Osun 2, Oyo 10.

Nephtytis afzelii Schott
Literature
Total: 0.

Nephtytis afzelii var. *afzelii*

Literature
Total: 0.

Nephtytis poissonii (Engl.) N.E.Br.
Oligogynium poissonii Engl.
Keay, R.W.J. [K.29047.038]
Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 9, Edo 7, Lagos
1, Oyo 1.

Nephtytis poissonii var. *constricta*
(N.E.Br.) Ntépe-Nyamè
Nephtytis constricta N.E.Br.
Lowe J. UIH21165; 25-03-1987 [K002976432]
Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Lagos 1.

Nephtytis poissonii var. *poissonii*
Oligogynium poissonii Engl.
Ariwaodo, JO 320; 1977-3-8 [WAG.1665649]
Total: 1.

Pistia stratiotes L.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1189; 1966-2-23 [WAG.1665503]
Total: 33; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Edo 3,
Enugu 1, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 10, Niger 2, Ogun 1,
Oyo 3, Rivers 2.

Remusatia vivipara (Roxb.) Schott
Arum viviparum Roxb.
Savory, H.J. 307 [K002820790]
Total: 1; Rivers 1.

Rhaphidophora africana N.E.Br.
Pilz, GE 2645; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1665394]
Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo
3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 6, Osun 4, Oyo 1, Plateau
1.

Rhaphidophora pusilla N.E.Br.
Talbot P.A. 1575; 1911-- [BM000581405]
Total: 1.

Spirodela polyrhiza (L.) Schleid.
Lemna polyrhiza L.
Broadbent, Dr J.A. 12; 1968-1-21
[6049.103]912061826
Total: 10; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Lagos
4, Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Stylochaeton hypogeum Lepr.
Hepper, F.N. 3893; 1969-11-12 [K000211553]
Total: 1.

Stylochaeton lancifolium Kotschy & Peyr.
Dalziel, J.M. 237; 1909-4-17 [K000099455]
Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Borno 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2,
Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Wolffia arrhiza (L.) Horkel ex Wimm.
Lemna arrhiza L.

Broadbent, Dr J.A. 7; 1968-1-16 [6049.081]
Total: 18; Abia 3, Edo 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 8.

Wolffiella hyalina (Delile) Monod
Lemna hyalina Delile

McFarlane, MG s.n.; 1966-5-10 [L.1423738]
Total: 4; Kaduna 2, Kano 2.

Wolffiella welwitschii (Hegelm.) Monod
Wolffia welwitschii Hegelm.

Brenan, JPM 8788; 1998-1-1 [L.3887131]
Total: 5; Edo 3, Ogun 1.

Xanthosoma sagittifolium (L.) Schott
Arum sagittifolium L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1494; 1966-5-11 [WAG.1665242]
Total: 10; Ogun 2, Oyo 5.

Zantedeschia albomaculata (Hook.) Baill.
Richardia albomaculata Hook.

Chapman, JD 2780; 1972-4-30 [WAG.1665117]
Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Zantedeschia albomaculata subsp.
albomaculata

Richardia albomaculata Hook.
Chapman J.W.F. 46; 07-07-1958 [K002976727]
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

ALISMATACEAE

Albidella glandulosa (Thwaites) Lehtonen
Alisma glandulosum Thwaites

Barter C. 1062; [K003192945]
Total: 1.

Burnatia enneandra Micheli

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3799; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1403793]
Total: 9; Niger 6, Oyo 2.

Butomopsis latifolia (D.Don) Kunth
Butomus latifolius D.Don

Geerling, C 3258; 1970-10-30 [WAG.1057953]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Borno 1.

Caldesia parnassifolia (Bassi) Parl.
Alisma parnassifolium Bassi

Daramola B.O & Ekwuno P. FHI67315; 14-07-1970
[K003192955]
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Benue 1.

Limnophyton angolense Buchenau

Jones A.P.D. FHI628; 09-02-1943 [K003194311]
Total: 3.

Limnophyton fluitans Graebn.

Literature

Total: 0.

Limnophyton obtusifolium (L.) Miq.
Sagittaria obtusifolia L.

Dalziel J.M. 199; 1908-5 [K003194278]
Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Sokoto 2.

Ranalisma humile (Rich. ex Kunth) Hutch.
Alisma humile Rich. ex Kunth

Geerling, C 3452; 1971-2-26 [WAG.1404036]
Total: 4; Bauchi 2, Niger 1.

Sagittaria guayanensis Kunth

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Niger 1.

Sagittaria guayanensis subsp. *lappula*
(D.Don) Bogin

Geerling, C 3252; 1970-10-30 [WAG.1404065]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Niger 1.

Wiesneria schweinfurthii Hook.f.

Dalziel, J.M. 202; K003194490
Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

APONOGETONACEAE

Aponogeton subconjugatus Schumach. &
Thonn.

Dalziel, J.M. 226; -- [K000452148]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Borno 1.

Aponogeton vallisnerioides Baker

Keay, R.W.J. 25961; 1950-7-12 [24326]
Total: 4; Borno 1, Kaduna 3.

CYMODOCEACEAE

Halodule wrightii Asch.

Literature
Total: 0.

HYDROCHARITACEAE

Najas horrida A.Braun ex Magnus
1065; 1858-- [BR0000090034008]

Total: 3; Kogi 2.

Najas marina L.

Benthem, W s.n.; 1989-3-1 [L.1199676]
Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Najas pectinata (Parl.) Magnus

Caulinia pectinata Parl.

Barter 1065; -- [K000346030]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Najas testui Rendle

Meikle, R.D. 710; 1949-12-3 [K000346026]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2.

Najas welwitschii Rendle

COOK Flotrop181280; 1970-01-01 [1948976927]

Total: 1.

Ottelia ulvifolia (Planch.) Walp.

Damasonium ulvifolium Planch.

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-12-05 [K.27181.0]

Total: 24; Adamawa 1, Benue 2, Borno 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Plateau 6, Zamfara 1.

Ottelia ulvifolia subsp. *ulvifolia*

Damasonium ulvifolium Planch.

Léonard J. 4545; 1968-2-19 [BR0000019634623]

Total: 1.

Vallisneria spiralis L.

Barter, E. 20163 [K002907051]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

POTAMOGETONACEAE

Potamogeton octandrus Poir.

Hydrogeton heterophyllus Lour.

Charles Barter [BM000638513]

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Yobe 1.

Potamogeton octandrus subsp. *octandrus*

Hydrogeton heterophyllus Lour.

Geerling, C 3447; 1971-2-25 [WAG.1554442]

Total: 1.

Potamogeton parvifolius Buchenau

Literature

Total: 0.

Potamogeton schweinfurthii A.Benn.

Benthem, W s.n.; 1989-3-1 [L.1200084]

Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Borno 1.

Stuckenia pectinata (L.) Börner —

Introduced

Potamogeton pectinatus L.

Literature

Total: 0.

RUPPIACEAE

Ruppia maritima L.

Literature

Total: 0.

BURMANNIACEAE

Afrothismia hydra Sainge & T.Franke

Keay FHI 25540; 1949-11-2 [100576426]

Total: 2; Ondo 2.

Afrothismia winkleri (Engl.) Schltr. —

Introduced

Thismia winkleri Engl.

Keay, R.W.J.; 1949-11-2 [B 10 0086316]

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Burmammia latialata Pobég.

Literature

Total: 0.

Burmammia madagascariensis Baker —

Introduced

Gledhill, D 1026; 1968-10-25 [WAG.1489072]

Total: 4; Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Campylosiphon congestus (C.H.Wright)

Maas

Gymnosiphon congestus C.H.Wright

Mann, G. 515; -- [K000366035]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 2.

Gymnosiphon longistylus (Benth.) Hutch.

Dictyostega longistyla Benth.

Literature

Total: 0.

DIOSCOREACEAE

Dioscorea abyssinica Hochst. ex Kunth

Dalziel, J.M. 671; -- [K001145707]

Total: 16; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Osun 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Dioscorea alata L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1730; 1966-8-1 [WAG.1781159]

Total: 8; Kano 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1.

Dioscorea baya De Wild.

s.coll 6; -- [K001146047]

Total: 16; Cross River 4.

Dioscorea bulbifera L.

Pilz, GE 2166; 1977-10-9 [WAG.1783350]

Total: 61; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Cross River 5, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 16, Plateau 10.

Dioscorea cayenensis Lam.

Thomas, N.W. [K001145770]

Total: 70; Benue 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 7, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Dioscorea cayenensis subsp. *cayenensis*

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO FHI 71104; 1974-8-2 [WAG.1783300]

Total: 1.

Dioscorea cayenensis subsp. *rotundata*

(Poir.) J.Miège

Thomas, N.W. 671; -- [K001145835]

Total: 21; Osun 1.

Dioscorea dregeana (Kunth) T.Durand & Schinz — Introduced

Helmia dregeana Kunth

Literature

Total: 0.

Dioscorea dumetorum (Kunth) Pax

Helmia dumetorum Kunth

Wit, P; Oguntayo, ST 2303; 1972-8-10 [WAG.1262559]

Total: 58; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 6, Cross River 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 8.

Dioscorea esculenta (Lour.) Burkill — Introduced

Oncus esculentus Lour.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1732; 1966-8-1 [WAG.1783683]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Dioscorea hirtiflora Benth.

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot [BM001051652]

Total: 60; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Kogi 6, Niger 7, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 23, Plateau 6.

Dioscorea hirtiflora subsp. *hirtiflora*

Pilz, GE 1842; 1976-11-7 [WAG.1783644]

Total: 1.

Dioscorea mangenotiana J.Miège

Ibhanesebhor, G; Osanyinlusi 70; 1982-7-16 [WAG.1783608]

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Lagos 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 3.

Dioscorea minutiflora Engl.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32700; 1981-6-15 [WAG.1783556]

Total: 25; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 5, Kano 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 6.

Dioscorea praehensilis Benth.

Pilz, GE 2125; 1977-9-16 [WAG.1786216]

Total: 80; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 1, Cross River 16, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Niger 18, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Oyo 19.

Dioscorea preussii Pax

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot [BM001051758]

Total: 64; Cross River 10, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Niger 7, Oyo 16, Plateau 2.

Dioscorea preussii subsp. *preussii*

Pilz, GE 2163; 1977-10-9 [WAG.1786153]

Total: 1.

Dioscorea quartiniana A.Rich.

Sharland, R.E. 1872; 1981-4-26 [K001145533]

Total: 17; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 6, Osun 1, Plateau 2.

Dioscorea sagittifolia Pax

Daramola, B.O. 253; 1993-7-29 [K001145718]

Total: 6; Bauchi 3, Kogi 1, Ogun 1.

Dioscorea sagittifolia var. *lecardii* (De Wild.) Nkounkou

Baquar, S.R. [K001150815]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Dioscorea sansibarensis Pax

Lowe, J. 4853; 1989-5-1 [K001146129]

Total: 4; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Dioscorea schimperiana Hochst. ex Kunth s.coll [K001145598]

Total: 7; Bauchi 4, Plateau 2.

Dioscorea smilacifolia De Wild. & T.Durand

Eijnatten, CLM van 1048; 1966-1-15 [WAG.1571845]

Total: 41; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Niger 4, Ogun 2, Oyo 15.

Dioscorea togoensis R.Knuth

MG 711; -- [K000809833]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Tacca leontopetaloides (L.) Kuntze

Leontice leontopetaloides L.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi DO 85; 1979-4-23 [WAG.1839420]

Total: 63; Abia 2, Bauchi 7, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Niger 7, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 4, Rivers 2, Sokoto 2, Yobe 1.

PANDANACEAE

Pandanus candelabrum P.Beauv.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1326; 1972-4-20 [WAG.1145422]

Total: 18; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Plateau 4.

TRIURIDACEAE

Sciaphila ledermannii Engl.

Percy Amaury Talbot 710; 1912-- [BM001011693]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

VELLOZIACEAE

Xerophyta schnizleinia (Hochst.) Baker

Hypoxis schnizleinia Hochst.

Keay, R.W.J. 22903; 1948-05-07 (K)

Total: 19; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Kaduna 13, Niger 1.

Xerophyta schnizleinia var. *occidentalis* (Milne-Redh.) Behnke

Vellozia schnizleinia var. *occidentalis* Milne-Redh.

Keay, R.W.J. 22903; 1948-05-07 (K)

Total: 13; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Kaduna 10.

COLCHICACEAE

Gloriosa simplex L.

Ariwaodo, JO 40; 1978-7-10 [WAG.1305407]

Total: 58; Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 6, Rivers 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 7.

Gloriosa superba L.

Pilz, GE 2174; 1977-10-22 [WAG.1305568]

Total: 52; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Enugu 5, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Osun 2, Oyo 11, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Iphigenia pauciflora Martelli

Geerling, C 4144; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1056590]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2.

Wurmbea tenuis (Hook.f.) Baker

Melanthium tenue Hook.f.

Gbile ZO; 1970-04-05 [WAG.1057652]

Total: 2.

Wurmbea tenuis subsp. *tenuis*

Melanthium tenue Hook.f.

Gbile, ZO s.n.; 1970-4-5 [WAG.1057652]

Total: 1.

SMILACACEAE

Smilax anceps Willd.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1967; 1966-9-17 [WAG.1057090]

Total: 45; Adamawa 1, Cross River 4, Delta 2, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 4, Lagos 5, Niger 3, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Taraba 3.

Smilax calophylla Wall. ex A.DC. —

Introduced

Takeuchi, W.; Kulang, J.; 1996-11-4 [P02065431]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

ORCHIDACEAE

Aerangis biloba (Lindl.) Schltr.

Angraecum bilobum Lindl.

Eimunjze, V.E.; Binuyo, A. s.n. 28/07/1967; FHI

Total: 49; Cross River 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Oyo 20, Plateau 2.

Aerangis calantha (Schltr.) Schltr. —

Introduced

Angraecum calanthum Schltr.

Seret, F. 642 26/08/1906; BR

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Aerangis gravenreuthii (Kraenzl.) Schltr.

Aeranthes gravenreuthii Kraenzl.

Balding, S.; Sivell, D. 82 28/08/1993

Total: 1.

Aerangis kotschyana (Rchb.f.) Schltr.

Angraecum kotschyianum Rchb.f.

Speke, Grant, 716 12/1862

Total: 12; Borno 1, Plateau 7.

Aerangis verdickii (De Wild.) Schltr.

Angraecum verdickii De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Afropectinariella gabonensis (Summerh.)

M.Simo & Stévant — Introduced

Angraecum gabonense Summerh.

Le Testu, G. 384 14/02/1927; K

Total: 2.

Afropectinariella pungens (Schltr.) M.Simo & Stévant

Angraecum pungens Schltr.

Schlechter, F.R.R. 15774 27/09/1905; K

Total: 4; Cross River 2.

Afropectinariella subulata (Lindl.) M.Simo & Stévant

Angraecum subulatum Lindl.

Unknown, 1139; BR

Total: 23; Delta 1, Edo 2, Imo 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Ancistrochilus rothschildianus O'Brien

Rothschild, 62-08 12/1908; K

Total: 26; Cross River 1, Edo 12, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Ancistrochilus thomsonianus (Rchb.f.) Rolfe

Pachystoma thomsonianum Rchb.f.

Gentil, L. s.n. 26/01/1903; BR

Total: 4; Edo 2.

Ancistrorhynchus akeassiae Pérez-Vera

Assi, A. 8874 31/05/1966; K

Total: 1.

Ancistrorhynchus capitatus (Lindl.)

Summerh.

Angraecum capitatum Lindl.

Letouzey, R. 14049 20/07/1975; K

Total: 4; Edo 1, Imo 1, Ondo 1.

Ancistrorhynchus cephalotes (Rchb.f.)

Summerh.

Listrostachys cephalotes Rchb.f.

Sanford, W.W. 1680/65 08/01/1965; FHI

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Imo 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1.

Ancistrorhynchus clandestinus (Lindl.)

Schltr.

Angraecum clandestinum Lindl.

Devred, R. 2618 09/10/1955; IUK

Total: 27; Bauchi 3, Cross River 3, Edo 6, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Ancistrorhynchus metteniae (Kraenzl.)

Summerh.

Listrostachys metteniae Kraenzl.

Daramola, B.O.; Emwiogbon, J.A. s.n. 07/08/1963; FHI

Total: 6; Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Oyo 1.

Ancistrorhynchus recurvus Finet

Pobéguin H., 788 07/1901; P

Total: 3; Delta 1, Osun 1.

Ancistrorhynchus schumannii (Kraenzl.) Summerh.

Angraecum schumannii Kraenzl.

Braun, J.M. 20: BR

Total: 1.

Ancistrorhynchus serratus Summerh.

Head, D. 95 26/05/1962; K

Total: 9; Cross River 5, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1.

Ancistrorhynchus straussii (Schltr.) Schltr.

Angraecum straussii Schltr.

Schlechter, F.R.R. 15771 27/09/1905; BM

Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2.

Angraecopsis elliptica Summerh.

Gregory, H. 194' K

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Angraecopsis ischnopus (Schltr.) Schltr.

Angraecum ischnopus Schltr.

Bâthie H. 11359 12/1912; P

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Angraecum angustipetalum Rendle

Sanford, W.W. s.n. 01/01/1969; FHI

Total: 9; Edo 3, Niger 1.

Angraecum angustum (Rolfe) Summerh.

Mystacidium angustum Rolfe

Holland, J.H. 27 20/04/1897; K

Total: 2; Abia 2.

Angraecum aporoides Summerh.

Laurent, M. 1902 15/03/1962; K

Total: 2.

Angraecum bancoense Burg

Burg, W.J. 304 14/05/1975; G

Total: 12; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Imo 2, Ondo 2.

Angraecum birrimense Rolfe

Miles, W.A.C. s.n. 10/1913; K

Total: 20; Abia 1, Delta 4, Edo 4, Imo 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 4, Rivers 1.

Angraecum claessensii De Wild.

Claessens, J. 748 06/1910; K

Total: 1.

Angraecum distichum Lindl.

Christiaensen, A.R. 1825 08/11/1956; LWI

Total: 19; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Angraecum egertonii Rendle

Talbot, P.A. 889 1911; BM

Total: 8; Cross River 3, Delta 2, Kaduna 1.

Angraecum eichlerianum Kraenzl.

Jacques-Felix, H. 4740 07/01/1939; WAG

Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Angraecum eichlerianum var. *eichlerianum*

Angraecum infundibulare Lindl.

Germain, R. 5256, 06/01/1949; IUK

Total: 1.

Angraecum lisowskianum Szlach. & Olszewski

Sanford, W.W. 6099 27/02/1969; K

Total: 1.

Angraecum moandense De Wild.

Chevalier, A.J.B. 21690 26/05/1909; P

Total: 12; Cross River 3, Kaduna 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 6.

Angraecum multinominatum Rendle

Listrostachys clavata Rendle

Scott Elliot, G.F. 5555; K

Total: 19; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ogun 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 2.

Angraecum podochiloides Schltr.

Schlechtr, R. 15769 19/10/1905; K

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Angraecum pyriforme Summerh.

Talbot, P.A. 888 1911; BM

Total: 6; Delta 1, Imo 1.

Angraecum sacciferum Lindl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ansellia africana Lindl.

Gossweiler, J. 12 01/01/1900; COI

Total: 15; Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Arachnis flos-aeris (L.) Rchb.f. —

Introduced

Epidendrum flos-aeris L.

Emwiogbon J.A.; 1968-9-17 [61148]2013042516

Total: 1; Delta 1.

Auxopus kamerunensis Schltr.

Chevalier, A.J.B. 1702526/05/1907; P

Total: 14; Cross River 2, Edo 6, Imo 1.

Auxopus macranthus Summerh.

Brenan, J.P.M.; Jones, E.W. 8777 11/01/1948; K

Total: 5; Edo 5.

Bolusiella maudiae (Bolus) Schltr.

Angraecum maudiae Bolus

Saunders, K 6270; K

Total: 4; Kaduna 4.

Bolusiella talbotii (Rendle) Summerh.

Angraecum talbotii Rendle

Talbot, P.A. 941 1911; BM

Total: 3; Edo 2.

Bonatea speciosa (L.f.) Willd. — Introduced

Orchis speciosa L.f.

Lely 397; -- [101295092]3334483306

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Brachycorythis buchananii (Schltr.) Rolfe

Platanthera buchananii Schltr.

Buchanan, J. 190 07/01/1895; E

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Brachycorythis conica (Summerh.)

Summerh.

Diplacorchis conica Summerh.

Callens, H. 3815 26/12/1952; YBI

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Brachycorythis conica subsp. *conica*

Diplacorchis conica Summerh.

Callens, H. 3815 26/12/1952; YBI

Total: 1.

Brachycorythis macrantha (Lindl.)

Summerh.

Gymnadenia macrantha Lindl.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 07/11/1950; FHI

Total: 22; Cross River 3, Kaduna 3, Ondo 6, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Brachycorythis ovata Lindl.

Rudatis, A.G.H. 552 14/12/1908; L

Total: 24; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 5, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 9, Niger 1.

Brachycorythis ovata subsp. *schweinfurthii* (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Sillitoe, F. 143; K

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1.

Brachycorythis pleistophylla Rchb.f.

Laurent, E. s.n. 10/01/1895; BR

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Plateau 2.

Brachycorythis pleistophylla var. *pleistophylla*

Laurent, E. s.n. 10/01/1895; BR

Total: 1.

Brachycorythis pubescens Harv.

Baum, H. 542 14/12/1899; S

Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Brachycorythis pumilio (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Penthea pumilio Lindl.

Mann, G. N904 04/1861; K

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Brachycorythis sceptrum Schltr.

Sanford, W.W. 1785/65 25/07/1965; FHI

Total: 6; Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Brachycorythis tenuior Rchb.f.

Dummer, R.A. 5533 09/1922; K

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Bulbophyllum acutebracteatum De Wild. —

Introduced

Bulbophyllum platyrhachis De Wild.

Laurent, E.M. 1055 1905; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum acutebracteatum var.

rubrobrunneopapillosum (De Wild.)

J.J.Verm.

Bulbophyllum rubrobrunneopapillosum De Wild.

Meer, PPC van 1579; 1971-5-11 [WAG.1130682]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Bulbophyllum apertiflorum (Summerh.)

Govaerts & J.M.H.Shaw — Endemic

Genyorchis apertiflora Summerh.

Keay, R.W.J. 25545; FHI

Total: 4; Ondo 4.

Bulbophyllum apetalum Lindl.

Braun, J.M. s.n.; HOH

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Bulbophyllum barbigerum Lindl.

Jones, A.P.D.; Onochie, C.F.A., s.n. 21/05/1946; FHI

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Bulbophyllum calvum Summerh.

Thomson, D.W. 4866 30/10/1985; YA

Total: 6; Taraba 6.

Bulbophyllum calyptratum Kraenzl.

Schlechter, R. 12369 04/1899; BM

Total: 16; Cross River 6, Edo 5, Imo 1.

Bulbophyllum calyptratum var. *calyptratum*

Schlechter, R. 12369 04/1899; BM

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Bulbophyllum calyptratum var.

graminifolium (Summerh.) J.J.Verm.

Glanville, R.R. 5744 06/1951; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum cochleatum Lindl.

Bequaert, J. 6413 29/12/1914; BR

Total: 32; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Cross River 7, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Taraba 11.

Bulbophyllum cochleatum var. *bequaertii*

(De Wild.) J.J.Verm.

Hepper F.N. 1918; 1958-2-11 [BR0000020031930]

Total: 2.

Bulbophyllum cochleatum var. *cochleatum*

Bequaert, J. 6413 29/12/1914; BR

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Bulbophyllum cochleatum var. *tenuicaule*

(Lindl.) J.J.Verm.

Mann, G. 648 12/1860; K

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Bulbophyllum colubrinum (Rchb.f.) Rchb.f.

Megaclinium colubrinum Rchb.f.

van Imschoot, M.A. s.n, 01/01/1982; K

Total: 6; Edo 1, Ondo 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Bulbophyllum comatum Lindl.

Mann, G. 642 01/01/1982; K

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Bulbophyllum comatum var. *comatum*

Zapfack, L. 944 01/03/2001; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum dolabriforme J.J.Verm. —

Endemic

Smith, G. 570 11/1981

Total: 2.

Bulbophyllum encephalodes Summerh.

Bidgood, S. 4483 28/05/2000; NHT

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum falcatum (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Megaclinium falcatum Lindl.

Dinklage, M.J. 1852 24/10/1897; WAG

Total: 90; Abia 6, Benue 1, Cross River 11, Delta 2, Edo 31, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 11, Oyo 2.

Bulbophyllum falcatum var. *bufo* (Lindl.)

Govaerts

Megaclinium bufo Lindl.

Schlechtr, F.R.R. 12898 01/01/1983; K

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Bulbophyllum falcatum var. *falcatum*

Megaclinium falcatum Lindl.

Wheatley, J.I. 460 01/05/1994; K

Total: 3.

Bulbophyllum falcatum var. *velutinum*

(Lindl.) J.J.Verm.

Megaclinium velutinum Lindl.

Barter, 20118; K

Total: 8; Abia 3, Edo 2, Ogun 1.

Bulbophyllum falcipetalum Lindl.

Unknown, 509-09 01/01/1982; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum fuscum Lindl.

Meikle, R.D. 599 14/11/1949; K

Total: 15; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Plateau 3.

Bulbophyllum fuscum var. *fuscum*

Gosline, G. 73 01/08/1999; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum fuscum var. *melinostachyum*

(Schltr.) J.J.Verm.

Schlechtr, R. 12250 11/04/1898; BM

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum imbricatum Lindl.

Laurent, L.L. s.n. 06/11/1903; K

Total: 4; Abia 2, Edo 1.

Bulbophyllum intertextum Lindl.

Mann, G. 527 09/1860; K

Total: 15; Cross River 8, Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Bulbophyllum ivorense P.J.Cribb & Pérez-Vera

Perez-Vera, 137 23/10/1873; K

Total: 3.

Bulbophyllum josephi (Kuntze) Summerh.

Bulbophyllum aurantiacum Hook.f.

Keay, R.W.J. 25439 01/01/1987; K

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Plateau 2.

Bulbophyllum josephi var. *josephi*

Bulbophyllum aurantiacum Hook.f.

Mann, G. 2124 11/1862; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum josephi var. *mahonii* (Rolfe)

J.J.Verm.

Bulbophyllum mahonii Rolfe

None; BR

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum leucorhachis (Rolfe) Schltr.

— Introduced

Megaclinium leucorhachis Rolfe

05/05/1890; K

Total: 3; Edo 3.

Bulbophyllum lupulinum Lindl.

Mann, G. 783 01/01/1983; K

Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Bulbophyllum magnibracteatum Summerh.

Miles, A.C. 11 01/01/1982; K

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Bulbophyllum maximum (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Megaclinium maximum Lindl.

Barter, s.n. 01/01/1982; K

Total: 16; Cross River 2, Delta 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 3, Taraba 1.

Bulbophyllum nigericum Summerh.

King, D.E.S 124; K

Total: 13; Plateau 6, Taraba 2.

Bulbophyllum nigritianum Rendle

Talbot, P.A. 933 01/01/1983; K

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Bulbophyllum oreonastes Rchb.f.

Zenker, G.A. s.n. 01/01/1983; K

Total: 25; Benue 1, Cross River 9, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Bulbophyllum oxychilum Schltr.

Bunting, R.H. 29; K

Total: 11; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Plateau 2.

Bulbophyllum pipio Rchb.f.

Miles A.G. 19; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum porphyrostachys Summerh.

Keay, R.W.J. 22711 01/01/1983

Total: 24; Edo 15, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Bulbophyllum pumilum (Sw.) Lindl.

Dendrobium pumilum Sw.

Wikler, H.J.P. 157 01/01/1983; K

Total: 63; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 3, Delta 2, Edo 12, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 2.

Bulbophyllum resupinatum Ridl.

Wheatley, J.I. 82 01/01/1996; K

Total: 2.

Bulbophyllum resupinatum var. *filiforme*
(Kraenzl.) J.J.Verm.

Hort.Brux., s.n.; BR

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum resupinatum var. *resupinatum*

Wheatley, J.I. 82 01/01/1996; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum saltatorium Lindl.

Stevart, P. 322 16/04/2002

Total: 16; Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 4, Imo 1.

Bulbophyllum saltatorium var. *albociliatum*

(Finet) J.J.Verm.

Letouzey, R. 14533 23/03/1976; K

Total: 3; Edo 1, Imo 1.

Bulbophyllum saltatorium var. *calamarium*

(Lindl.) J.J.Verm.

Keay R.W.J. ; 1950-12-01 [28687.0]

Total: 1; Delta 1.

Bulbophyllum saltatorium var. *saltatorium*

Bulbophyllum sandersonii subsp.

sandersonii

Megaclinium sandersonii Hook.f.

Rudatis, A.G.H. 1549 01/01/1982; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum sandersonii subsp.

stenopetalum (Kraenzl.) J.J.Verm.

Megaclinium sandersonii Hook.f.

S.coll. 356; K

Total: 1.

Bulbophyllum scaberulum (Rolfe) Bolus

Megaclinium scaberulum Rolfe

Pobeguín 925 01/01/1982; K

Total: 48; Cross River 6, Edo 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 12, Oyo 7, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Bulbophyllum scaberulum var.

fuerstenbergianum (De Wild.) J.J.Verm.

Megaclinium fuerstenbergianum De Wild.

Fuersterberg, 1903; BR

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Bulbophyllum scaberulum var. *scaberulum*

Megaclinium scaberulum Rolfe

Chevalier, A. 12838 04/1905; K

Total: 13; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Ondo 4, Plateau 2, Rivers 1.

Bulbophyllum schimperianum Kraenzl.

Thorold, C.A. TN36 24/11/1950; K

Total: 3; Abia 1, Delta 2.

Bulbophyllum schinzianum Kraenzl.

Percy Amaury Talbot 3724; 1916-- [BM000517452]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 1, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1.

Bulbophyllum schinzianum var. *phaeopogon*

(Schltr.) J.J.Verm.

Seegerback, B. 1209 26/03/1976; FHI

Total: 3; Imo 1.

Bulbophyllum schinzianum var. *schinzianum*

Etuge, M. 2512 02/07/1996; K

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Bulbophyllum summerhayesianum (Szlach.

& Olszewski) Govaerts & J.M.H.Shaw —

Endemic

Genyorchis summerhayesiana Szlach. &

Olszewski

Preuss, P.R. 1061 1891; K

Total: 2.

Calanthe sylvatica (Thouars) Lindl.

Centrosis sylvatica Thouars

Commerson, P. s.n.; MPU

Total: 1.

Calanthe tankervilleae (Banks) M.W.Chase,

Christenh. & Schuit.

Limodorum tankervilleae Banks

; [11748.0]

Total: 1.

Calyptrochilum christyanum (Rchb.f.)

Summerh.

Angraecum christyanum Rchb.f.

Kirk, 12 25/06/1879; K

Total: 61; Abia 3, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 5, Imo 3, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Niger 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 9, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Calyptrochilum emarginatum (Afzel. ex

Sw.) Schltr.

Limodorum emarginatum Afzel. ex Sw.

Evrard, C. 1677 22/08/1955; IUK

Total: 28; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Chauliodon deflexicalcaratum (De Wild.)

L.Jonss.

Angraecum deflexicalcaratum De Wild.

Bunting, R.H. 9 01/01/1978; K

Total: 4; Edo 3.

- Cheirostylis lepida* (Rchb.f.) Rolfe
 Monochilus lepidus Rchb.f.
 Mann, G. 2130 11/1862; K
 Total: 5; Benue 1, Cross River 2.
- Corymborkis corymbis* Thouars
 Mann, G. 7925 07/01/1885; L
 Total: 28; Cross River 6, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Ondo 4, Osun 6, Oyo 5.
- Cynorkis anacamptoides* Kraenzl.
 Stuhlmann, F. 2346; HBG
 Total: 2; Taraba 1.
- Cynorkis anacamptoides* var. *anacamptoides*
 Williamson, G. 233; K
 Total: 1.
- Cynorkis debilis* (Hook.f.) Summerh.
 Habenaria debilis Hook.f.
 Mann, G. 2127 11/1862; K
 Total: 1.
- Cyrtorchis arcuata* (Lindl.) Schltr.
 Angraecum arcuatum Lindl.
 Drege, j.F. 4580d 14/12/1829; P
 Total: 21; Kaduna 10, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Plateau 1.
- Cyrtorchis arcuata* subsp. *arcuata*
 Angraecum arcuatum Lindl.
 Drege, j.F. 4580c 14/12/1829; P
 Total: 1.
- Cyrtorchis aschersonii* (Kraenzl.) Schltr.
 Angraecum aschersonii Kraenzl.
 Seret, F. 1001 09/02/1907; BR
 Total: 12; Abia 1, Edo 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1.
- Cyrtorchis brownii* (Rolfe) Schltr.
 Listrostachys brownii Rolfe
 Borwn, E. 248 06/1905; K
 Total: 1.
- Cyrtorchis chailluana* (Hook.f.) Schltr.
 Angraecum chailluanum Hook.f.
 Mann, G. 521 09/1860; K
 Total: 15; Abia 3, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.
- Cyrtorchis hamata* (Rolfe) Schltr.
 Sanford, WW 1617 /65; 1965-8-7 [L.1505384]
 Total: 32; Edo 2, Lagos 1, Ondo 14, Osun 1, Oyo 9.
- Cyrtorchis monteiroae* (Rchb.f.) Schltr.
 Listrostachys monteiroae Rchb.f.
 Preuss, P.R. 418; K
 Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.
- Cyrtorchis okuensis* Droissart, Azandi & M.Simo
 Literature
 Total: 0.
- Cyrtorchis ringens* (Rchb.f.) Summerh.
 Listrostachys ringens Rchb.f.
 Mann, G. 2114 11/1862; K
 Total: 5; Cross River 4.
- Diaphananthe bidens* (Afzel. ex Sw.) Schltr.
 Limodorum bidens Afzel. ex Sw.
 Troupin, G. 2447 09/03/1956; YBI
 Total: 36; Abia 2, Edo 9, Imo 1, Kwara 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 9, Rivers 1.
- Diaphananthe divitiflora* (Kraenzl.) Schltr.
 Listrostachys divitiflora Kraenzl.
 Keay, R.W.J. 22562; 1948-09-21 [10276.000]
 Total: 1; Ondo 1.
- Diaphananthe dorotheae* (Rendle) Summerh. — Endemic
 Angraecum dorotheae Rendle
 Talbot, P.A. 915 1911; BM
 Total: 7; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1.
- Diaphananthe ichneumonea* (Lindl.) P.J.Cribb & Carlsward
 Angraecum ichneumoneum Lindl.
 Mann, G. 520 09/1860; K
 Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Edo 1.
- Diaphananthe lanceolata* (Summerh.) P.J.Cribb & Carlsward
 Chamaeangis lanceolata Summerh.
 Meikle, R.D. 607 15/11/1949; K
 Total: 12; Cross River 1, Edo 9.
- Diaphananthe lecomtei* (Finet) P.J.Cribb & Carlsward
 Listrostachys lecomtei Finet
 Literature
 Total: 0.
- Diaphananthe odoratissima* (Rchb.f.) P.J.Cribb & Carlsward
 Angraecum odoratissimum Rchb.f.
 Letouzey, R. 14218 10/08/1975; K
 Total: 5; Abia 1, Cross River 2.
- Diaphananthe pellucida* (Lindl.) Schltr.
 Angraecum pellucidum Lindl.
 Thorne, F. 93 09/1896; K

Total: 28; Abia 1, Benue 2, Cross River 4, Delta 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Diaphananthe plehniana (Schltr.) Schltr.

Angraecum plehnianum Schltr.

Schlechter, F.R.R. 12780 05/04/1945; K

Total: 11; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 5.

Diaphananthe spiralis (Stévant & Droissart)

P.J.Cribb & Carlsward

Chamaeangis spiralis Stévant & Droissart

Literature

Total: 0.

Diaphananthe vesicata (Lindl.) P.J.Cribb &

Carlsward

Angraecum vesicatum Lindl.

Tweedie, E.M. 2481 10/1962

Total: 20; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 8, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Dinklageella liberica Mansf.

Cheek, M. 9144 01/08/1999; K

Total: 1.

Disa equestris Rchb.f.

Welwitsch 717; K

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Disa erubescens Rendle

Scott Elliot, G.F. 7809 1893;K

Total: 9; Cross River 2, Taraba 5.

Disa erubescens subsp. *erubescens*

Bauer, P.J. 70 16/05/1970; K

Total: 1.

Disa hircicornis Rchb.f.

Stolz, A. 2454 26/01/1914; K

Total: 5; Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Disa nigerica Rolfe

Nelson, R.G.P. 5 03/07/1912; K

Total: 9; Bauchi 3, Taraba 1.

Disa ochrostachya Rchb.f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Disa perplexa H.P.Linder

Robinson, E.A. 4126 30/11/1960; K

Total: 1.

Disa welwitschii Rchb.f.

Busse, W. 834 09/01/1901; K

Total: 6; Taraba 4.

Disa welwitschii subsp. *occultans* (Schltr.)

H.P.Linder

Dummer, R. 738 17/04/1979; K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Disa welwitschii subsp. *welwitschii*

Welwitsch 715 17/04/1979; K

Total: 1.

Disperis anthoceros Rchb.f.

Scimper 1295; K

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Disperis anthoceros var. *anthoceros*

Disperis johnstonii Rchb.f. ex Rolfe

Stolz, A. 672 09/11/1966; K

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Disperis mildbraedii Schltr. ex Summerh.

— Introduced

Milbread, J. 6312 01/08/1911; HBG

Total: 3; Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Disperis thomensis Summerh.

Thomas, D.W. 9210 26/09/1992; K

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Disperis togoensis Schltr.

Maitland, T.D. 1519 04/1931; K

Total: 1.

Epidendrum ibaguense Kunth — Introduced

Latilo M.G; 1966-3- [58540]1990430909

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Epipogium roseum (D.Don) Lindl.

Limodorum roseum D.Don

Inayat, K. 25386 09/06/1901; K

Total: 3; Kogi 1.

Eulophia adenoglossa (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Cymbidium adenoglossum Lindl.

Barter s.n. 1859; K

Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Niger 3.

Eulophia alta (L.) Fawc. & Rendle

Limodorum altum L.

Anon s.n.; LINN

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Eulophia angolensis (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Cymbidium angolense Rchb.f.

Welwitsch F.M.J. 734 11/1859; P

Total: 50; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 5, Kaduna 3, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Niger

3, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Eulophia barteri Summerh.

Barter 1481; K

Total: 4; Niger 2.

Eulophia bouliawongo (Rchb.f.) J.Raynal

Galeandra bouliawongo Rchb.f.

Welwitsch 673; K

Total: 3.

Eulophia brevipetala Rolfe

Scott-Elliot 5224; BM

Total: 5; Kaduna 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Eulophia buettneri (Kraenzl.) Summerh.

Lissochilus buettneri Kraenzl.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 24/02/1946; FHI

Total: 6; Oyo 4, Plateau 2.

Eulophia caricifolia (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Lissochilus caricifolius Rchb.f.

Onochie, C.F.A. s.n. 15/05/1956; FHI

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Edo 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Eulophia cristata (Afzel. ex Sw.) Steud.

Limodorum cristatum Afzel. ex Sw.

de Wilde, J. 235 20/02/1949; BR

Total: 50; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 6, Kwara 3, Lagos 5, Ogun 5, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Eulophia cucullata (Afzel. ex Sw.) Steud.

Limodorum cucullatum Afzel. ex Sw.

Saeger, H. 176 21/02/1952; LWI

Total: 85; Abia 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 9, Kano 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 7, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 11, Taraba 6.

Eulophia euglossa (Rchb.f.) Rchb.f. ex

Bateman

Galeandra euglossa Rchb.f.

Hort.Brux., s.n. 15/10/1913; BR

Total: 10; Benue 1, Ondo 5.

Eulophia filicaulis Lindl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Eulophia flavopurpurea (Rchb.f.) Rolfe

Cyrtopera flavopurpurea Rchb.f.

Rowland 86 1893; K

Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Enugu 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Niger 4, Oyo 1.

Eulophia galeoloides Kraenzl.

Leonard, A. 5779 08/12/1959; BR

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Eulophia gracilis Lindl.

Onochie, C.F.A. s.n. 19/01/1956; FHI

Total: 23; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 4.

Eulophia guineensis Lindl.

Welwitsch, F. 656 02/01/1855; LISU

Total: 63; Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 4, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 18, Plateau 5, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Eulophia horsfallii (Bateman) Summerh.

Lissochilus horsfallii Bateman

Burt-Davy, J. 2900 06/09/1906; K

Total: 49; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 9, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Eulophia horsfallii subsp. *horsfallii*

Lissochilus horsfallii Bateman

Osmaston, H.A. 1343 06/10/1951; UH

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Eulophia juncifolia Summerh.

Espirito-Santo, J.V.G. 2317 20/10/1946; LISC

Total: 8; Ogun 3, Oyo 5.

Eulophia latilabris Summerh.

Lissochilus schweinfurthii Rchb.f.

Schweinfurth, G. 3776 25/05/1870; BM

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Eulophia leonensis Rolfe

Scott-Elliot 5536; K

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 4, Plateau 4.

Eulophia maculata (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Thomas, N.W. 2196; 1913-01-09 [K000453765]

Total: 4; Oyo 1.

Eulophia massokoensis Schltr. —

Introduced

Sanford W.W.; 1966-- [112085]1990433927

Total: 2.

Eulophia mechowii (Rchb.f.) T.Durand &

Schinz

Orthochilus mechowii Rchb.f.

Welwitsch, F. 720

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Eulophia milnei Rchb.f.

Luja, P.E. 49 27/09/1898; BR

Total: 4; Edo 1, Oyo 2.

Eulophia monile Rchb.f.

King, D.E.S. 139; 1958-04-01 [K17.000]

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Eulophia odontoglossa Rchb.f.

Medley, W.J. 11775 09/01/1904; K

Total: 25; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 11.

Eulophia orthoplectra (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Lissochilus orthoplectrus Rchb.f.

Schmitz, A. 1944 16/07/1948; BR

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Eulophia parvula (Rendle) Summerh.

Lissochilus parvulus Rendle

Scott-Elliott, G.F. 7081 01/1894; K

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Eulophia penduliflora Kraenzl.

Goetze, W. 1383 10/1899; K

Total: 3; Kaduna 3.

Eulophia pyrophila (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Lissochilus pyrophilus Rchb.f.

Schweinfurth, G. 2795 01/05/1870; P

Total: 1.

Eulophia ramifera Summerh.

Eulophia elliottii Rolfe

Drummond, R.B. 4927 09/1955; K

Total: 4; Plateau 4.

Eulophia saundersiana Rchb.f.

Seegerback, B. 1213; 1976-02-22 [K 37270.000]

Total: 5; Imo 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2.

Eulophia sordida Kraenzl. — Introduced

Warnecke, O. 95; HBG

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Eulophia stachyodes Rchb.f.

Schweinfurth, G. 3554 20/04/1876; K

Total: 7; Bauchi 2, Plateau 3.

Eulophia tenella Rchb.f. — Introduced

HEPPER Flotrop185555; 1957-01-01 [1948981131]

Total: 1.

Eurychone rothschildiana (O'Brien) Schltr.

Angraecum rothschildianum O'Brien

Eimunjeze, V.E.; Binuyo, A. s.n. 06/06/1974; FHI

Total: 15; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Graphorkis lurida (Sw.) Kuntze

Limodorum luridum Sw.

Gillet, J. 2806 07/01/1902; BR

Total: 33; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1.

Habenaria anaphysema Rchb.f. —

Introduced

Welwitsch, F.M.J. 744; BM

Total: 1.

Habenaria armatissima Rchb.f.

Goldblatt, P.; Manning, J.C. 8820 22/03/1988; NBG

Total: 1.

Habenaria barrina Ridl.

Quintas, s.n.' BM

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 3.

Habenaria bongensium Rchb.f.

Schweinfurth, G. 3974 09/07/1870; BM

Total: 10; Kaduna 4, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Habenaria buettneriana Kraenzl.

Buttner, R. 288 1880; K

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Osun 2, Oyo 1.

Habenaria chirensis Rchb.f.

Leeuwenberg, A.J.M. 10199 11/07/1972; K

Total: 10; Edo 1, Niger 1, Plateau 7.

Habenaria cirrhata (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Bonatea cirrhata Lindl.

Dawe, M.T. 1026 26/11/1910; K

Total: 16; Kaduna 9, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3.

Habenaria clavata (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Bonatea clavata Lindl.

Drege, J.F. 4568; K

Total: 1.

Habenaria cornuta Lindl.

Drege, J.F. 4570; K

Total: 6; Plateau 6.

Habenaria dalzielii Summerh.

Dalziel, J.M. 222 03/08/1909; K

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Habenaria dinklagei Kraenzl.

Jones A.P.D.; 1946-8-25 [20721]1990427694

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Habenaria engleriana Kraenzl.

Irwin, H.S. 19246 26/01/1968; RB

Total: 14; Kaduna 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Habenaria filicornis Lindl.

Orchis filicornis Thonn.

Schimper, W. 606 08/06/1852; P

Total: 11; Borno 2, Plateau 7.

Habenaria genuflexa Rendle

Welwitsch, F. 681 01/1837; K

Total: 25; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 12, Taraba 1.

Habenaria holubii Rolfe

Kassner 23971 26/01/1908; K

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Plateau 4.

Habenaria huillensis Rchb.f.

Welwitsch, F. 724 02/01/1860; LISU

Total: 20; Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 11.

Habenaria ichneumonea (Sw.) Lindl.

Orchis ichneumonea Sw.

Reekmans, M. 8698 03/06/1980; BJA

Total: 1.

Habenaria keayi Summerh.

Keay, R.W.J. 25395; K

Total: 21; Kaduna 5, Kwara 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Habenaria laurentii De Wild.

Laurent, E.; Laurent, M. s.n. 25/11/1903; BR

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 4, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Habenaria lecardii Kraenzl.

Lecard, Th. 190; BR

Total: 1.

Habenaria lelyi Summerh.

Lely, H.V. 457 19/07/1921; K

Total: 13; Kaduna 6, Niger 1, Plateau 3.

Habenaria lelyi var. *lelyi*

Lely, H.V. 457 19/07/1921; K

Total: 1.

Habenaria linguiformis Summerh. —

Endemic

Lely, H.V. 343A 04/07/1921; K

Total: 6; Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Plateau 1.

Habenaria longirostris Summerh.

Lely, H.V. 462 22/07/1921; K

Total: 19; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Plateau 5.

Habenaria macrandra Lindl.

Unknown, 518 10/1860; K

Total: 11; Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 4, Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Habenaria macrura Kraenzl.

Baum, H. 603 01/01/1900; G

Total: 1.

Habenaria maitlandii Summerh. —

Introduced

Maitland, T.D. 1386 06/1931; K

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Habenaria malacophylla Rchb.f.

Duvigneaud, P. 51550R 21/01/1960; BRLU

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Habenaria malacophylla var. *malacophylla*

Duvigneaud, P. 51550R 21/01/1960; BRLU

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Habenaria mannii Hook.f.

Jacques-Felix, H. 8207 18/09/1967; YA

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Taraba 1.

Habenaria nigerica Summerh.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 27/07/1950; FHI

Total: 11; Kaduna 7, Plateau 4.

Habenaria nigrescens Summerh.

Daramola, B.O. FHI41568 07/07/1959; K

Total: 1.

Habenaria occidentalis (Lindl.) Summerh.

Amphorkis occidentalis Lindl.

Barter 1487; K

Total: 10; Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Niger 5.

Habenaria papyracea Schltr.

Stolz, A. 2585 14/03/1914; K

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Habenaria parva (Summerh.) Summerh.

Cynorkis parva Summerh.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 06/01/1930; FHI

Total: 8; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 4, Plateau 2.

Habenaria pauper Summerh.

Maitland, T.D. 1562 05/1931; K

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Habenaria peristyloides A.Rich.

Quartin-Dillon, R. 3; P

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Habenaria phylacocheira Summerh. —

Endemic

Lely, H.V. 451 19/07/1921; K

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Habenaria physuriformis Kraenzl.

Jongkind, C.C.H. 5285 01/01/2004; K

Total: 1.

Habenaria prionocraspedon Summerh. —

Endemic

Rosevear 61/29 1929; K

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Habenaria procera (Afzel. ex Sw.) Lindl.

Orchis procera Afzel. ex Sw.

Farron, C. 4588 23/08/1965; P

Total: 32; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Ondo 10, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 3.

Habenaria schimperiana Hochst. ex A.Rich.

— Introduced

Schimper, G.W. s.n. 09/05/1838; S

Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Habenaria walleri Rchb.f.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 20/07/1950; FHI

Total: 14; Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 5, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Habenaria weileriana Schltr.

Cheek, M. 9133 11/02/1998; K

Total: 5; Cross River 1.

Habenaria zambesina Rchb.f.

Chapman, JD 2883; 1972-6-9 [WAG.1137347]

Total: 42; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Niger 4, Oyo 9, Plateau 7, Taraba 4.

Hetaeria heterosepala (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Cheirostylis heterosepala Rchb.f.

Chaves, M. 2; K

Total: 1.

Hetaeria mannii (Rchb.f.) Benth. ex Durand

& Schinz — Introduced

Rhamphidia mannii Rchb.f.

Bates, G.L. 299 02/07/1895; K

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Hetaeria occidentalis Summerh.

Punch, C. s.n. 27/09/1900; K

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Edo 2.

Hetaeria tetraptera (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Monochilus tetrapterus Rchb.f.

Mann, G. 1701 07/1862; K

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Himantoglossum hircinum (L.) Spreng. —

Introduced

Satyrium hircinum L.

S.C. s.n.; P

Total: 1.

Holothrix aphylla (Forssk.) Rchb.f.

Orchis aphylla Forssk.

Ledermann, C. 1988 01/10/1959; K

Total: 5; Borno 1, Plateau 2.

Kylicanthe bueae (Schltr.) Farminhão,

Stévant & Droissart — Introduced

Angraecum bueae Schltr.

Gregory, H. 153 18/07/2017

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Lankesteriana escalerensis (Carnevali &

Luer) Karremans — Introduced

Pleurothallis escalerensis Carnevali & Luer

Apejaye F. I.; 2005-9-3 [1042]2274829324

Total: 1.

Liparis caillei Finet

Caille, O. s.n. 1906; P

Total: 4; Kaduna 2, Taraba 1.

Liparis epiphytica Schltr.

Schlechter, R. 12694 08/1899; K

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Edo 1.

Liparis goodyeroides Schltr.

Brunt, M.A. 479 01/01/2011

Total: 1.

Liparis nervosa (Thunb.) Lindl.

Ophrys nervosa Thunb.

Hooker, J.D. s.n. 13/10/2009; K

Total: 52; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Enugu 3, Imo 4, Ondo 10, Osun 2, Oyo 11, Plateau 4, Taraba 4.

Liparis nervosa subsp. *nervosa*

Ophrys nervosa Thunb.

Hooker, J.D. s.n. 13/10/2009; K

Total: 3; Imo 2.

Liparis platyglossa Schltr.

van Meer s.n. 15/05/1971; FHI

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Liparis rufina (Ridl.) Rchb.f. ex Rolfe

Liparis elata var. rufina Ridl.

Morze, G. 55; ZM

Total: 2; Abia 1.

Liparis suborbicularis Summerh.

Thomas, D.W. 2254 07/1983; P

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 1, Osun 1.

Liparis tridens Kraenzl.

Zenker, G. 1387 1897; K

Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ondo 8.

Listrostachys pertusa (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Angraecum pertusum Lindl.

Latilo et al. s.n. 14/10/1974; FHI

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 3, Edo 1.

Malaxis chevalieri Summerh.

Chevalier, a. 21786 31/05/1909; BR

Total: 3; Niger 1, Ogun 2.

Malaxis katangensis Summerh.

von Hirschberg, C. 152 09/12/1923; PRE

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3.

Malaxis katangensis var. *katangensis*

Hirschberg, C.W. 111 30/11/1923; K

Total: 1.

Malaxis maclaudii (Finet) Summerh.

Microstylis maclaudii Finet

Hirschberg, C.W. 111 30/11/1923; K

Total: 18; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Ondo 5.

Malaxis prorepens (Kraenzl.) Summerh.

Microstylis prorepens Kraenzl.

Doumenge, C. 461 01/01/1994; K

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Ondo 2.

Manniella gustavi Rchb.f.

Mann, 1047; AMES

Total: 1.

Microcoelia caespitosa (Rolfe) Summerh.

Angraecum caespitosum Rolfe

Bates, G.L. 353 28/08/1896; K

Total: 15; Edo 1, Imo 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 4.

Microcoelia globulosa (Hochst.) L.Jonss.

Angraecum globulosum Hochst.

Schimper, W. 1565 01/05/1840; BM

Total: 9; Bauchi 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Microcoelia koehleri (Schltr.) Summerh.

Angraecum koehleri Schltr.

Firth, E.P. s.n. 02/03/1958; K

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Microcoelia konduensis (De Wild.)

Summerh.

Angraecum konduense De Wild.

Pial, S. 260 13/10/2001

Total: 4; Edo 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Microcoelia macrorrhynchia (Schltr.)

Summerh.

Angraecum macrorrhynchium Schltr.

Smith, G. 525 11/1981

Total: 12; Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Microcoelia microglossa Summerh.

Talbot, P.A. s.n. 1911; K

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Nervilia adolphi Schltr.

Stolz, A. 1870 01/01/1912; M

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 2.

Nervilia adolphi var. *adolphi*

Stolz, A. 1870 01/01/1912; M

Total: 1.

Nervilia bicarinata (Blume) Schltr.

Pogonia bicarinata Blume

Welwitsch 739 12/1860; K

Total: 30; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 10, Plateau 8.

Nervilia fuerstenbergiana Schltr.

King, D.E.S 95; K

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 2.

Nervilia kotschy (Rchb.f.) Schltr.

Pogonia kotschy Rchb.f.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 04/03/1962; FHI

Total: 11; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Plateau 3.

Nervilia kotschy var. *kotschy*

Pogonia kotschy Rchb.f.

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 04/03/1962; FHI

Total: 1.

Nervilia petraea (Afzel. ex Sw.) Summerh.

Arethusa petraea Afzel. ex Sw.

Maitland, T.D. 1528 05/1931; K

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Nervilia shirensis (Rolfe) Schltr. —

Introduced

Pogonia shirensis Rolfe

Buchanan 134201/01/1991; K

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Oyo 3.

Nervilia simplex (Thouars) Schltr.

Arethusa simplex Thouars

Stolz, A. 1791 01/01/1991; K

Total: 18; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Oeceoclades maculata (Lindl.) Lindl.

Angraecum maculatum Lindl.

Pirani, J.R. et al. 5458 06/04/2004; K

Total: 13; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 6.

Oeceoclades saundersiana (Rchb.f.) Garay & P.Taylor

Eulophia saundersiana Rchb.f.

Treun 96; K

Total: 18; Edo 2, Kwara 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 4, Oyo 5.

Phaius tankervilleae (Banks) Blume —

Introduced

Limodorum tankervilleae Banks

; -- [11748]2821281854

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Platycoryne buchananiana (Kraenzl.) Rolfe

— Introduced

Habenaria buchananiana Kraenzl.

Buchanan, J.C.M.G. 739 01/01/1891; G

Total: 1.

Platycoryne crocea Rolfe — Introduced

Habenaria crocea Schweinf. ex Rchb.f.

Schweinfurth, G.A. 3968 29/06/1870; G

Total: 1.

Platycoryne megalorrhyncha Summerh.

Maitland, T.D. 1509 04/1931; K

Total: 5; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Taraba 2.

Platycoryne paludosa (Lindl.) Rolfe

Habenaria paludosa Lindl.

Lecard, Th. 204; BR

Total: 25; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 8, Katsina 1, Niger 2, Plateau 7, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Platylepis glandulosa (Lindl.) Rchb.f.

Notiophrys glandulosa Lindl.

Medley-Wood 4122 03/01/1889; GRA

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Lagos 3.

Plectrelminthus caudatus (Lindl.) Summerh.

Angraecum caudatum Lindl.

Wilde, J.J.F.E. de 8414 13/08/1975; K

Total: 14; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Taraba 1.

Plectrelminthus caudatus var. *caudatus*

Angraecum caudatum Lindl.

Wilde, J.J.F.E. de 8414 13/08/1975; K

Total: 1.

Podangis dactyloceras (Rchb.f.) Schltr.

Listrostachys dactyloceras Rchb.f.

Deistel, H. s.n.4; K

Total: 15; Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Ondo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Podangis rhipsalisocia (Rchb.f.) P.J.Cribb & Carlsward

Angraecum rhipsalisocium Rchb.f.

Welwitsch, 662 16/11/1948; K

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Imo 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 7.

Polystachya adansoniae Rchb.f.

Germain, G.=R.G.A. 3404 15/01/1945; YBI

Total: 23; Bauchi 1, Cross River 6, Edo 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 5, Taraba 1.

Polystachya affinis Lindl.

Bowling, J.C. GC38171 20/02/1968; GC

Total: 28; Abia 1, Edo 7, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 5, Plateau 1.

Polystachya albescens Ridl.

Brunt, M.A. 450 19/05/1962; K

Total: 7; Borno 1, Cross River 1.

Polystachya albescens subsp. *albescens*

Brunt, M.A. 450 19/05/1962; K

Total: 4.

Polystachya albescens subsp. *imbricata* (Rolfe) Summerh.

Keay R. 2241; -- [BR0000009937772]

Total: 2; Borno 1, Cross River 1.

Polystachya alpina Lindl.

Talbot, P.A. 19/10/1909; K

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Polystachya anthoceros la Croix & P.J.Cribb

Spurrier, M. 17 31/10/1993; K

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Polystachya bennettiana Rchb.f.

Lisowski, S. 65944 15/11/1969; BR

Total: 3; Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Polystachya bicalcarata Kraenzl.

Deistel, H. 62c & 79; HBG

Total: 2.

Polystachya bifida Lindl.

Mann, G. 2115; BR

Total: 3; Cross River 2, Plateau 1.

Polystachya calluniflora Kraenzl.

La Croix, 629 05/09/1984; K

Total: 1.

Polystachya camaridioides Summerh.

Unknown 01/07/1955

Total: 1.

Polystachya concreta (Jacq.) Garay & H.R.Sweet

Epidendrum concretum Jacq.

Rottler, J.P. s.n.; K

Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 9, Edo 2, Imo 3, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 1.

Polystachya cooperi Summerh.

Lowe, J. 2662 08/01/1973

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Polystachya coriscensis Rchb.f.

Mann, G. 1884 08/1862; K

Total: 9; Abia 1, Edo 2.

Polystachya dalzielii Summerh.

Dalziel, J.M.8433 03/09/1927; P

Total: 1.

Polystachya dolichophylla Schltr.

Schlechter, R. 12837; BR

Total: 37; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kaduna 4, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 13, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Polystachya elegans Rchb.f.

Mann, G. 1338 01/1862; K

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Plateau 1.

Polystachya fulvilabia Schltr.

Zenker, s.n. 07/1916; B

Total: 2.

Polystachya galeata (Sw.) Rchb.f.

Dendrobium galeatum Sw.

Babilon, J. 81 21/01/1986; BR

Total: 16; Delta 1, Edo 6, Oyo 1.

Polystachya golungensis Rchb.f.

Welwitsch, F.M.J. 674 03/1856; BM

Total: 13; Cross River 3, Kaduna 4, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Polystachya kingii Summerh. — Endemic

Howard, W.J.

Total: 4; Taraba 4.

Polystachya laxiflora Lindl.

Bates, G.L. 477 05/01/1896; BR

Total: 21; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Imo 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Ondo 4, Oyo 1.

Polystachya letouzeyana Szlach. &

Olszewski

Letouzey, R. 9372 18/04/1968; P

Total: 1.

Polystachya modesta Rchb.f.

Welwitsch 675 03/01/1857; LISU

Total: 18; Adamawa 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Polystachya mukandaensis De Wild.

Gentil, L. 45; BR

Total: 10; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Polystachya obanensis Rendle

Talbot, P.A. 930 1911; K

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Polystachya oblanceolata Summerh. —

Introduced

Roberty, G. 17764 05/03/1955; G

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Polystachya odorata Lindl.

Jones, A.P.D. 20729 25/08/1946; K

Total: 57; Abia 4, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 5, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 21, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 3.

Polystachya odorata subsp. *odorata*

Jones, A.P.D. 20729 25/08/1946; K

Total: 22; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 2.

Polystachya odorata subsp. *trilepidis*

(Summerh.) Stévert

Jones, A.P.D. 20729 25/08/1946; FHI

Total: 12; Ondo 12.

Polystachya paniculata (Sw.) Rolfe

Dendrobium paniculatum Sw.

Germain, R. 3551 20/02/1945; BR

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Polystachya parva Summerh.

Milne-Redhead, E. 4369 27/01/1938; K

Total: 4; Taraba 2.

Polystachya polychaete Kraenzl.

Preuss, P. 881; HBG

Total: 1.

Polystachya pyramidalis Lindl.

Preuss, P.R. 1072; K

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Polystachya ramulosa Lindl.

Le Testu, G. 5775 21/11/1921; K

Total: 5; Abia 1, Edo 2.

Polystachya rhodoptera Rchb.f. —

Introduced

Christiaensen, A.R. 551 15/07/1954; LWI

Total: 8; Abia 1, Delta 1, Edo 3, Oyo 2.

Polystachya saccata (Finet) Rolfe

Epiphora saccata Finet

Hepper, F.N.; Malsy, J. 7742 1984

Total: 6; Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 1.

Polystachya seticaulis Rendle

Talbot, P.A. 926 1911; BM

Total: 5; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Polystachya steudneri Rchb.f.

Froment, D. 64 23/02/1957; YBI

Total: 5; Bauchi 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Polystachya subulata Finet

Keay, R.W.J. s.n. 01/05/1948; FHI

Total: 11; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 6, Plateau 1.

Polystachya supfiana Schltr.

LeTestu, G. 5924 11/04/1926; BM

Total: 9; Abia 1, Edo 2.

Polystachya valentina la Croix & P.J.Cribb

— Introduced

; -- [60944]912062640

Total: 1.

Porpax elaidium (Lindl.) Schuit., Y.P.Ng & H.A.Pedersen

Bulbophyllum elaidium Lindl.

Jongkind C.C.H, et al. 5447 26/11/2002; K

Total: 1.

Porpax repens (Rolfe) Schuit., Y.P.Ng & H.A.Pedersen

Polystachya repens Rolfe

Milne-Redhead, E. 3385 24/11/1937

Total: 9; Abia 2, Edo 4.

Porpax repens var. *repens*

Polystachya repens Rolfe

Milne-Redhead, E. 3385 24/11/1937

Total: 1.

Rangaeris longicaudata (Rolfe) Summerh.

Mystacidium longicaudatum Rolfe

Millen, H. 188 26/03/1896; K

Total: 5; Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Rangaeris muscicola (Rchb.f.) Summerh.

Aeranthes muscicola Rchb.f.

Welwitsch 699; K

Total: 14; Cross River 1, Kwara 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 4.

Rangaeris trilobata Summerh.

Talbot, P.A. 3299 1912; K

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 3.

Rhipidoglossum brachyceras (Summerh.)

Farminhão & Stévant

Aerangis brachyceras Summerh.

Burt, B.D. 3123; K

Total: 2.

Rhipidoglossum confusum (P.J.Cribb)

Farminhão & Stévant

Cribbia confusa P.J.Cribb

Meer, PPC van 1863; 1971-1-1 [WAG.1130193]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Rhipidoglossum curvatum (Rolfe) Garay

Mystacidium curvatum Rolfe

Wetswood, D; 02/1954

Total: 11; Cross River 3, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Rhipidoglossum kamerunense (Schltr.)

Garay

Angraecum kamerunense Schltr.

Schlechter, F.R.R 15768 01/04/1945; K

Total: 1.

Rhipidoglossum longicalcar Summerh. —

Endemic

Talbot, P.A. 939 1911; BM

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Osun 1.

Rhipidoglossum obanense (Rendle)

Summerh.

Angraecum obanense Rendle

de Wilde, J. 235 27/08/1974; Ya

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Kaduna 1.

Rhipidoglossum paucifolium D.Johanss. —

Introduced

Johnsson, D. 577 08/12/1969; AMES

Total: 2; Ondo 2.

Rhipidoglossum polydactylum (Kraenzl.)

Garay

Listrostachys polydactyla Kraenzl.

George Nodza LUH6923; 14-10-2015 [LUH]

Total: 1.

Rhipidoglossum rutilum (Rchb.f.) Schltr.

Aeranthes rutilus Rchb.f.

Kassner, T. 741 17/05/1902; K

Total: 16; Edo 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 2.

Satyrium carsonii Rolfe

Carson, A. 3 1894; K

Total: 12; Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 3.

Satyrium coriophoroides A.Rich. —

Introduced

Quartin-Dillon, R. Petit, R. s.n.; BR

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Satyrium crassicaule Rendle

- Scott-Elliot, G.F. 7851 1893-94; Bm
Total: 5; Taraba 2.
- Satyrium nepalense* var. *ciliatum* (Lindl.)
Hook.f. — Introduced
J. W. F. Chapman 20; 1958-7-15 [barcode-
01944261]2575074265
Total: 1.
- Satyrium paludosum* Rchb.f. — Introduced
Welwitsch, F.M.J. 727 01/1860; BM
Total: 1; Taraba 1.
- Satyrium trinerve* Lindl.
Compton, R.H. 26492 17/01/1957; NBG
Total: 4; Taraba 3.
- Satyrium volkensii* Schltr.
Lugard, E.J. Major, E.J. 595 01/10/1930; EA
Total: 3; Plateau 2.
- Solenangis clavata* (Rolfe) Schltr.
Angraecum clavatum Rolfe
Scott-Elliot, G.F. 4223; BM
Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Lagos
1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 1.
- Solenangis scandens* (Schltr.) Schltr.
Angraecum scandens Schltr.
Schlechter, F.R.R. 12739 09/1899; K
Total: 12; Edo 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Rivers 1.
- Spathoglottis plicata* Blume — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1116; 1966-12-1 [WAG.1140672]
Total: 2; Oyo 2.
- Tridactyle anthomaniaca* (Rchb.f.)
Summerh.
Listrostachys anthomaniaca Rchb.f.
Monteiro, J.J. s.n. 06/1873; K
Total: 19; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Cross
River 1, Delta 2, Edo 3, Imo 1, Niger 2, Ondo 2.
- Tridactyle anthomaniaca* subsp.
anthomaniaca
Listrostachys anthomaniaca Rchb.f.
Monteiro, J.J. s.n. 06/1873; K
Total: 1.
- Tridactyle bicaudata* (Lindl.) Schltr.
Angraecum bicaudatum Lindl.
Stolz, A. 716 10/05/1911; K
Total: 9; Kaduna 1, Plateau 4.
- Tridactyle bicaudata* subsp. *bicaudata*
Angraecum bicaudatum Lindl.
Stolz, A. 716 10/05/1911; K
Total: 2; Kaduna 1.
- Tridactyle brevicarata* Summerh.
Le Testu, G. 5.564 05/10/1925; K
Total: 1.
- Tridactyle crassifolia* Summerh. —
Introduced
Le Testu, G. 5.173 02/01/1925; K
Total: 2; Imo 1.
- Tridactyle filifolia* (Schltr.) Schltr.
Angraecum filifolium Schltr.
Schlechter, F.R.R. 12791 09/01/1899; BR
Total: 1.
- Tridactyle gentilii* (De Wild.) Schltr.
Angraecum gentilii De Wild.
Gentil, L. s.n. 01/01/1903; BR
Total: 4; Nasarawa 2, Plateau 2.
- Tridactyle lagesensis* (Rolfe) Schltr.
Angraecum lagesense Rolfe
Moloney, A. s.n. 13/11/1947; K
Total: 4; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.
- Tridactyle muriculata* (Rendle) Schltr.
Angraecum muriculatum Rendle
Talbot, P.A. 904 12/11/1947; K
Total: 3; Cross River 3.
- Tridactyle oblongifolia* Summerh.
Le Testu, G. 4.314 15/11/1922; K
Total: 1.
- Tridactyle tridactylites* (Rolfe) Schltr.
Angraecum tridactylites Rolfe
Deistel 593 1905; K
Total: 31; Benue 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 1,
Ondo 7, Osun 5, Oyo 2, Plateau 6.
- Tridactyle tridentata* (Harv.) Schltr.
Angraecum tridentatum Harv.
Eggeling, W.J. 5277 04/01/1944; EA
Total: 4; Imo 2, Kwara 1.
- Vanilla africana* Lindl.
Barter, C. 47; K
Total: 5; Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Lagos 1.
- Vanilla crenulata* Rolfe
Cummings, H.A. 4 29/01/1896; K
Total: 3; Cross River 2.
- Vanilla imperialis* Kraenzl.
Luja, P.E. s.n.; BR
Total: 1; Cross River 1.
- Vanilla nigerica* Rendle
Percy Amaury Talbot 776; 1911-- [BM000062725]
Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Vanilla ramosa Rolfe

Barter 20134; K

Total: 5; Cross River 3.

Zeuxine africana Rchb.f.

Welwitsch, F.M.J. 669 02/1856; BM

Total: 1; Sokoto 1.

Zeuxine elongata Rolfe

Guile, D.P. WS/824/66 28/02/1966; FHI

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Zeuxine stammleri Schltr.

Annet, E. 349 06/1918; P

Total: 11; Cross River 3, Edo 4, Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

HYPOXIDACEAE

Curculigo pilosa (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Engl.

Gethylis pilosa Schumach. & Thonn.

Bininyo 36917; 1958-03-31 (K)

Total: 38; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Lagos 9, Niger 3, Oyo 8, Taraba 2.

Curculigo pilosa subsp. *major* (Baker)

Wiland

Curculigo gallabatensis var. *major* Baker

Barter, C. 1506; 1858 (P)

Total: 2.

Curculigo pilosa subsp. *pilosa*

Gethylis pilosa Schumach. & Thonn.

Hypoxis angustifolia Lam.

Chapman, J.W.F. 66; 1958-07-01 (BR)

Total: 16; Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 6, Taraba 4.

Hypoxis angustifolia var. *luzuloides*

(Robyns & Tournay) Wiland

Keay, R.W.J. 25779 (K)

Total: 1.

Hypoxis suffruticosa Nel

Wit, P., Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O. 1352; 1972-04-20 (WAG)

Total: 10; Niger 4, Plateau 5.

TECOPHILAEACEAE

Cyanastrum cordifolium Oliv.

Lowe, J 1785; 1968-4-15 [WAG.1839159]

Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

IRIDACEAE

Afrosolen erythranthus (Klotzsch ex Klatt)

Goldblatt & J.C.Manning

Ovieda erythrantha Klotzsch ex Klatt

Lely, H.V. 189; 1921-05-18 (K)

Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Plateau 5.

Aristea abyssinica Pax

Chapman, J.W.F. 74; 1958-06-17 (BR)

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Aristea alata Baker

Okafor, JC; Binuyo, A FHI 47827; 1963-6-15

[WAG.1399818]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Aristea angolensis Baker

Chapman, J.W.F. 75; 1958-06-17 (BR)

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Aristea angolensis subsp. *angolensis*

Chapman, J.W.F. 75; 1958-06-17 (BR)

Total: 1.

Aristea djalonis Hutch.

Lely, H.V. 342; 1921-07-04 (K)

Total: 6; Benue 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Gladiolus dalenii Van Geel

Chapman, J.D. 2742; 1972-03-28 (WAG)

Total: 37; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 8, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 4, Zamfara 1.

Gladiolus dalenii subsp. *dalenii*

Chapman, J.D. 2742; 1972-03-28 (WAG)

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 7, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Gladiolus gregarius Welw. ex Baker

Gbile, Z.O.; Wit, P.; Daramola, B.O. FHI64146; 1971-09-20 (WAG)

Total: 37; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Delta 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Niger 11, Oyo 1, Plateau 5.

Gladiolus mirus Vaupel

FHI67425; 1970-07-17 [K002432739]

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Nasarawa 4, Plateau 4.

Gladiolus murielae Kelway

[SANT.11754.0]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Gladiolus roseolus Chiov.

Summerhayes, G.V. 92 1957-05-04 (BR)

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Gladiolus unguiculatus Baker

Gladiolus cochleatus Baker

Summerhayes, G.V. 97; 1957-06-06 (BR)

Total: 26; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 7, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Moraea schimperii (Hochst.) Pic.Serm.

Hymenostigma schimperii Hochst.

Hepper, F.N. 1504; 1957-11-29 (K)

Total: 15; Abia 2, Adamawa 4, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Zygotritonia bongensis (Pax) Mildbr.

Tritonia bongensis Pax

Dalziel, J.M. 558; 1911-06-19 (K)

Total: 10; Benue 1, Katsina 1, Sokoto 4.

Zygotritonia praecox Stapf

Dalziel, J.M. 847; 1912-06-01 (K)

Total: 10; Adamawa 2, Benue 3, Kaduna 3.

ASPHODELACEAE

Aloe buettneri A.Berger

Emwiogbon 83/77; 1977-10-5 [100221724]

Total: 68; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 4, Cross River 1, Kaduna 14, Kebbi 4, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 27, Taraba 2.

Aloe macrocarpa Tod.

Keay, R.W.J. 25419; -- [1257]

Total: 18; Plateau 14.

Aloe schweinfurthii Baker

Hepper, F.N. 1603; 1957-12-18 [5563]

Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Ekiti 2, Jigawa 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 4, Taraba 2.

Aloe vera (L.) Burm.f. — Introduced

Aloe perfoliata var. *vera* L.

Muili F.O., Onwumere .K.O., Usang felix; 2005-10-17 [369]

Total: 8; Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Osun 3.

Kniphofia reflexa Hutch. ex Codd

1624; -- [K000256151]

Total: 2.

AMARYLLIDACEAE

Allium ascalonicum L. — Introduced

Adeboye.R.Olawale; 2017-3-1 [7526]

Total: 5; Lagos 5.

Allium cepa L. — Introduced

Okpara chioma; 2010-06-15 [LUH.2746.0]

Total: 10; Lagos 5.

Allium sativum L. — Introduced

Salako Kehinde; 2012-10-5 [5251]3808440523

Total: 12; Imo 1, Lagos 10.

Crinum biflorum Rottb.

Keay, R.W.J. 25864 (K)

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Crinum glaucum A.Chev.

Meikle 1108

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Crinum jagus (J.Thomps.) Dandy

Amaryllis jagus J.Thomps.

Goldie, N. s.n. (K)

Total: 42; Cross River 6, Ebonyi 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 5, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Crinum natans Baker

Chapman, J.D. 2741; 1972-03-28 (WAG)

Total: 12; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Delta 2, Edo 1, Imo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Crinum ornatum (Aiton) Herb.

Amaryllis ornata Aiton

Pilz, G.E. 1989; 1977-04-25 (WAG)

Total: 6; Benue 1, Kano 2.

Crinum purpurascens Herb.

Kalbreyer 57 (K)

Total: 5; Borno 1.

Crinum zeylanicum (L.) L. — Introduced

Amaryllis zeylanica L.

Denys E. 625; 1982-4-26 [BR0000019934020]

Total: 24; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kebbi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Hippeastrum puniceum (Lam.) Voss — Introduced

Amaryllis punicea Lam.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1060; 1966-1-20 [WAG.1376566]

Total: 3; Anambra 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 1.

Hymenocallis littoralis (Jacq.) Salisb. — Introduced

Pancratium littorale Jacq.

van Eijnatten, C.L.M. 1445; 1966-04-24
[WAG.1376566]
Total: 8; Anambra 1, Lagos 3, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Pancratium tenuifolium Hochst. ex A.Rich.
Lowe, J. 2900; 1976-04-17 (K)
Total: 22; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Kebbi 2, Kogi 6,
Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Pancratium trianthum Herb.
Küppers, K. 1915; 1997-04-30 (FR)
Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Lagos 3,
Niger 3, Oyo 6, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Scadoxus cinnabarinus (Decne.) Friis &
Nordal

Haemanthus cinnabarinus Decne.
Wit, P. & Geerling, C. 1243; 1972-03-11 (WAG)
Total: 22; Benue 2, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Lagos 3,
Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Scadoxus multiflorus (Martyn) Raf.
Haemanthus multiflorus Martyn
Küppers, K. 1929; 1997-05-05 (FR)
Total: 39; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross
River 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Oyo 2,
Plateau 3, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Scadoxus multiflorus subsp. *multiflorus*
Haemanthus multiflorus Martyn
Küppers, K. 1929; 1997-05-05 (FR)
Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Oyo
1, Plateau 2.

Scadoxus pseudocaulus (I.Bjørnstad & Friis)
Friis & Nordal
Haemanthus pseudocaulus I.Bjørnstad & Friis
Keay, R.W.J. 37024; 1957-05-22 (K)
Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 3, Ogun 1.

Zephyranthes candida Herb. — Introduced
Amaryllis candida Lindl.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1281; 1966-3-20 [WAG.1377458]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Zephyranthes citrina Baker — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1282; 1966-3-20 [WAG.1377461]
Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Zephyranthes puertoricensis Traub —
Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 150; 1960-3-27 [WAG.1377464]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Agave americana L. — Introduced
Ugwuzor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [279A][1990271839]
Total: 3; Abia 2, Enugu 1.

Agave sisalana Perrine — Introduced
K [29887][2428970993]
Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Albuca abyssinica Jacq.
Keay, R.W.J.; -- [4383]912043451
Total: 10; Kwara 1, Ondo 2, Plateau 4.

Albuca fibrotunicata Gledhill & Oyewole
Oyewole, S.O. 47; 1968-12-7 [K000257278]
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 2.

Albuca nigritana (Baker) Troupin
Urginea nigritana Baker
Hall, J.B.; 1970-4-4 [B 10 0168530]
Total: 27; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2,
Kwara 1, Niger 7, Ogun 4, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Sokoto
1, Taraba 4.

Albuca scabromarginata De Wild. —
Introduced
Oyewole, S.O. 46; 1968-12-18 [K000257279]
Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Albuca sudanica A.Chev.
; 2007-1-24 [FR-0034712]
Total: 11; Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 3, Niger 2,
Oyo 1.

Asparagus africanus Lam.
Dr.A.B.Kadiri;others; 2011-9-1 [4162]3808440509
Total: 7; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Enugu 1,
Lagos 1, Plateau 3.

Asparagus africanus var. *africanus*
Gbile Z.O.; Wit P.; Daramola B.O. FHI65346; 21-04-
1972 [K002854039]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Asparagus drepanophyllus Welw. ex Baker
Millson, A. 25; 1890-09-01 [K002853912]
Total: 1; Borno 1.

Asparagus falcatus L. — Introduced
Mida 87; 1930-10 [K002853981]
Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Asparagus flagellaris (Kunth) Baker
Asparagopsis flagellaris Kunth
Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66360; 1973-5-15
[WAG.1150352]
Total: 73; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1,
Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2,
Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Lagos 1,

ASPARAGACEAE

Nasarawa 1, Niger 15, Oyo 2, Plateau 7, Sokoto 1, Taraba 9, Zamfara 1.

Asparagus racemosus Willd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Asparagus schroederi Engl.

Gbile Z.O., Wit & Daramola B.O. 1275; 1972-5-3 [BR0000019797397]

Total: 20; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 7, Niger 5, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Chlorophytum affine Baker

Barter C. s.n.; -- [K000256811]

Total: 6; Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Oyo 1.

Chlorophytum alismifolium Baker

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO; Fagbemi, A FHI 71013; 1974-7-10 [WAG.1150855]

Total: 12; Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Osun 1.

Chlorophytum andongense Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum angustissimum (Poelln.)

Nordal

Anthericum angustissimum Poelln.

Geerling, C 4110; 1971-8-20 [WAG.1151405]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 1.

Chlorophytum blepharophyllum Schweinf.

ex Baker

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1103; 1972-4-20 [WAG.1150969]

Total: 30; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 10, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Plateau 2.

Chlorophytum blepharophyllum subsp.

blepharophyllum

Lely H.V. 113; 24-04-1921 [K003736858]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum brachystachyum Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum bracteatum Hua

Barter, C.; 1858-1-1 [P01851368]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Chlorophytum cameronii (Baker) Kativu

Lely, H.V. [K000390573]

Total: 62; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 13, Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 18, Katsina 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Plateau 9, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Chlorophytum cameronii var. *cameronii*

Daramola, B.O.; Ekwuno, P. FHI67437; 1970-7-17 [K000390582]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum cameronii var. *purpuratum*

(Rendle) Govaerts — Introduced

1510; 1957-11-30 [BR0000021754555]

Total: 14; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Nasarawa 2, Zamfara 1.

Chlorophytum caulescens (Baker) Marais & Reilly

Anthericum caulescens Baker

Barter C. 1515; -- [K000256812]

Total: 6; Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1.

Chlorophytum comosum (Thunb.) Jacques

Anthericum comosum Thunb.

O.O.Oyebanji; 2013-8-1 [9359]3808440480

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Kogi 2.

Chlorophytum dalzielii (Hutch. ex Hepper)

Nordal — Endemic

Anthericum dalzielii Hutch. ex Hepper

Dalziel, J.M. 854; 1912-6-16 [K000256814]

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 4.

Chlorophytum debile Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum filipendulum Baker

Daramola BO; 1958-06-20 [WAG.1151177]

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Chlorophytum filipendulum subsp. *filipendulum*

Daramola, BO FHI 38034; 1958-6-20

[WAG.1151177]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum gallabatense Schweinf. ex

Baker

Jones, E.W.; 1958-5-2 [P01848048]

Total: 5; Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1.

Chlorophytum gallabatense var.

gallabatense

Lowe J. 1311; 25-05-1968 [K003736766]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum geophilum Peter ex Poelln.

Jones, E.W.; 1958-6-20 [P01848036]

Total: 7; Kaduna 3, Niger 3, Plateau 1.

Chlorophytum inornatum Ker Gawl.

Meikle, R.D.; 1950-01-06 [K.15160.0]

Total: 7; Delta 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Chlorophytum lancifolium Welw. ex Baker

Geerling, C 4187; 1971-9-14 [WAG.1151308]

Total: 30; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 1.

Chlorophytum lancifolium subsp. *togoense*

(Engl.) A.D.Poulsen & Nordal

Hambler D.J. 890; 09-03-1960 [K003736773]

Total: 26; Anambra 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 1.

Chlorophytum laxum R.Br.

Geerling, C 4158; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1151333]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1.

Chlorophytum limosum (Baker) Nordal

Anthericum limosum Baker

Keay, R.W.J. 37304; 1957-12-30 [K000390632]

Total: 19; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 6, Plateau 3.

Chlorophytum longifolium Schweinf. ex

Baker

Anthericum longifolium A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum longifolium var. *aureum*

(Engl.) Meerts

Chlorophytum aureum Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum macrophyllum (A.Rich.)

Asch.

Anthericum macrophyllum A.Rich.

Chevalier, A.; 1905-1-1 [P01851316]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Chlorophytum nubicum (Baker) Katiu

Anthericum nubicum Baker

Hepper F.N. 1388; 1957-11-16 [BR0000021757983]

Total: 25; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 3, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3.

Chlorophytum orchidastrum Lindl.

Hambler, DJ 890; 1960-8-9 [WAG.1151425]

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Cross River 5, Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Chlorophytum petrophilum K.Krause

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum pusillum Schweinf. ex Baker

Lawlor, D.W.; Hall, J.B.; 109; 1962-07-27

[K003736908]

Total: 7; Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Chlorophytum sparsiflorum Baker

Savory H.J.; Keay R.W.J; 30-12-1948 [K003737021]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ogun 1.

Chlorophytum sparsiflorum var. *bipindense*

(Engl. & K.Krause) BJORÅ & Nordal

Chlorophytum sparsiflorum var.

sparsiflorum

Chlorophytum staudtii Nordal

Anthericum zenkeri Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Chlorophytum stenopetalum Baker

Keay, R.W.J.; 1950-06-27 [P01848628]

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kaduna 6, Kebbi 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

Chlorophytum stenopetalum var.

stenopetalum

Keay, R.W.J.; 1950-6-27 [P01848628]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum subpetiolatum (Baker) Katiu

Anthericum subpetiolatum Baker

Daggash, M.; 1949-08-12 [P01851815]

Total: 7; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Taraba 1.

Chlorophytum subpetiolatum var.

subpetiolatum

Anthericum subpetiolatum Baker

Daggash, M.; 1949-8-12 [P01851815]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum tordense Chiov.

Medler J. 488; 04-09-1970 [K003737015]

Total: 1.

Chlorophytum tuberosum (Roxb.) Baker

Anthericum tuberosum Roxb.

Fishwick, R.W. 42093; 1958-6-10 [K000390642]

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Cordyline fruticosa (L.) A.Chev. —

Introduced

Convallaria fruticosa L.

Usang Felix; 2005-10-2 [18]3913474715

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Dipcadi longifolium (Lindl.) Baker

Uropetalon longifolium Lindl.

Morton J.K. A3339; 02-05-1958 [K002197174]

Total: 12; Borno 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Dipcadi viride (L.) Moench

Hyacinthus viridis L.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi DO 90; 1979-4-23

[WAG.1152048]

Total: 20; Benue 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Dracaena arborea (Willd.) Link

Aletris arborea Willd.

Vermeer, D 30; 1975-10-1 [WAG.1152450]

Total: 35; Bayelsa 1, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Lagos 3, Niger 9, Ogun 2, Ondo 8, Oyo 5, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Dracaena aubryana Brongn.

Chapman, J.D. 5309; 1978-4-9 [K000402123]

Total: 13; Ekiti 3, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Dracaena bicolor Hook.

Wit, J.; Wit, P. 1142; 1972-1-27 [K000402131]

Total: 25; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 15, Edo 2, Niger 2.

Dracaena camerooniana Baker

Bos, JJ 10427; 1982-4-2 [WAG.1153340]

Total: 46; Adamawa 4, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Delta 5, Edo 23, Kogi 1, Taraba 1.

Dracaena congoensis Hua

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11256; 1977-3-26

[WAG.1153572]

Total: 22; Edo 8, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 1.

Dracaena fragrans (L.) Ker Gawl.

Aletris fragrans L.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 2382; 1973-4-2

[WAG0116782]

Total: 45; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Kogi 2, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 16, Taraba 4.

Dracaena goldieana Bullen ex Mast. & T.Moore

Holland, J.H. 195; 1899-12-25 [K000402230]

Total: 5; Abia 1, Cross River 1.

Dracaena kindtiana De Wild.

Latilo M.G.; Daramola B.O. FHI34450; 03-02-1955

[K000402124]

Total: 13; Ekiti 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 4.

Dracaena laxissima Engl.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32807; 1981-6-18

[WAG.1154148]

Total: 30; Cross River 5, Edo 3, Kogi 1, Ogun 5, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 6, Taraba 5.

Dracaena liberica (Gérôme & Labroy)

Byng & Christenh.

Sansevieria liberica Gérôme & Labroy

Etkin 138; 1988-5-27 [615089]1261330587

Total: 26; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Ondo 3, Osun 6, Oyo 2.

Dracaena mannii Baker

Gentry, AH 32708; 1981-6-16 [WAG.1154497]

Total: 47; Abia 7, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 9, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Osun 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Dracaena marina Bos ex Damen

Moloney 2; 01-11-1983 [K000402281]

Total: 2; Lagos 1.

Dracaena mokoko Mwachala & Cheek

Talbot P.A. 2402; 1912-1-1 [Z-000171038]

Total: 1.

Dracaena nyangensis Pellegr.

Talbot 2402; -- [K000402406]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Dracaena ovata Ker Gawl.

Talbot Mr P.A., Talbot Mrs. 3191; -- [K000402307]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 2.

Dracaena perrottetii Baker

Latilo M.G. FHI.22795; 1950-4-21 [30422]912028787

Total: 12; Abia 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2.

Dracaena phrynioides Hook.

Daramola, B.O. FHI72471; 1973-10-8 [K000402318]

Total: 22; Cross River 3, Edo 10, Kogi 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Dracaena surculosa Lindl.

Bos, JJ 10397; 1979-11-30 [WAG0116562]

Total: 73; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Cross River 10, Ebonyi 1, Edo 10, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 12, Taraba 5.

Dracaena surculosa var. *maculata* Hook.f.

Meikle R.D. 782; 09-12-1949 [K000402395]

Total: 40; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Cross River 4, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 12, Taraba 3.

Dracaena surculosa var. *surculosa*

Talbot P.A. 1421; 26-03-1905 [K000402324]

Total: 26; Cross River 5, Ebonyi 1, Edo 7, Lagos 2, Ogun 8, Osun 1.

Dracaena trifasciata (Prain) Mabb.

Sansevieria trifasciata Prain

Eijnatten, CLM van 1139; 1966-2-21 [WAG.1157827]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Oyo 1.

Dracaena usambarensis Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Dracaena viridiflora Engl. & K.Krause

Meer, PPC van 1837; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1154585]

Total: 16; Cross River 13, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Drimia altissima (L.f.) Ker Gawl.

Ornithogalum altissimum L.f.

Chapman, JD 2673; 1972-2-13 [WAG.1155623]

Total: 31; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Drimia elata Jacq. ex Willd.

Wimbush, S.H.; 57; 1959-02-01 [K002198364]

Total: 6; Niger 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Drimia glaucescens (Engl. & K.Krause)

H.Scholz

Urginea glaucescens Engl. & K.Krause

Denys, E 741; 1982-6-22 [WAG.1155639]

Total: 6; Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Drimia incerta A.Chev. ex Hutch.

Literature

Total: 0.

Drimia indica (Roxb.) Jessop

Scilla indica Roxb.

Geerling, C 3457; 1971-3-5 [WAG.1155654]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 1.

Drimia minuta Goldblatt & J.C.Manning —

Endemic

Urginea nana Oyewole

Literature

Total: 0.

Drimia zambesiaca (Baker) J.C.Manning &

Goldblatt

Urginea zambesiaca Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Drimiopsis barteri Baker

Denys E. 742; 1982-7-22 [BR0000008931061]

Total: 24; Borno 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Eriospermum abyssinicum Baker

Daramola, BO FHI 62903; 1969-5-25

[WAG.1155703]

Total: 12; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Furcraea foetida (L.) Haw. — Introduced

Agave foetida L.

Okafor, J.C.; Emwiogbon, J.; 48091; 1964-06-15

[K002170743]

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Ledebouria camerooniana (Baker) Speta

Scilla camerooniana Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Ledebouria sudanica (A.Chev.) Burg

Scilla sudanica A.Chev.

Hall, J.B. 1605; 1970-03-27 [K002791253]

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Ornithogalum flexuosum (Thunb.) U.Müll.-

Doblies & D.Müll.-Doblies — Introduced

Hyacinthus flexuosus Thunb.

Schlechter R.L.; 12355; 1899-3- [BR0000021415906]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

ARECACEAE

Borassus aethiopum Mart.

Barter 35109 (K)

Total: 3; Niger 3.

Borassus akeassii Bayton, Ouédr. & Guinko

No specimens known from Nigeria

Total: 1.

Borassus flabellifer L. — Introduced

[35126]2428977333

Total: 4; Lagos 4.

Butia capitata (Mart.) Becc. — Introduced

Cocos capitata Mart.

[18903]912014763

Total: 2; Edo 2.

Calamus deerratus G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Ayewoh 3854 (K)

Total: 57; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 6, Delta 1, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Cocos nucifera L.

Wit, P 737; 1971-10-20 [WAG0115468]

Total: 14; Kaduna 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 4, Oyo 5.

Elaeis guineensis Jacq.

Daramola, BO; Emwiogbon, JA FHI 32779; 1961-1-8 [WAG.1142969]

Total: 81; Abia 7, Anambra 1, Cross River 9, Edo 18, Kaduna 2, Lagos 17, Niger 6, Ogun 6, Oyo 1.

Eremospatha hookeri (G.Mann & H.Wendl.) H.Wendl.

Calamus hookeri G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Tuley 651 (K)

Total: 45; Abia 6, Bayelsa 11, Cross River 11, Delta 11, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Ondo 2.

Eremospatha laurentii De Wild.

Onochie 5243 (K°)

Total: 2; Edo 2.

Eremospatha macrocarpa Schaedtler

Calamus macrocarpus G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Daramola & Adebuseyi 38415 (K!)

Total: 74; Abia 16, Cross River 18, Edo 3, Kogi 9, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 4.

Eremospatha quinquecostulata Becc.

Tuley 653 (WAG)

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Eremospatha tessmanniana Becc.

Literature

Total: 0.

Eremospatha wendlandiana Dammer ex Becc.

Morakinyo 1001 (K)

Total: 27; Abia 4, Cross River 11, Kaduna 8.

Hyphaene thebaica (L.) Mart.

Corypha thebaica L.

Etkin 72; 1988-6-4 [293747]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Kano 2, Niger 1, Sokoto 1.

Laccosperma acutiflorum (Becc.) J.Dransf.

Ancistrophyllum acutiflorum Becc.

Morakinyo 1000 (K)

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Laccosperma laeve (G.Mann & H.Wendl.) Kuntze

Calamus laevis G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Morakinyo 1006; 1993-08-18 [K000526642]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Laccosperma opacum Drude

Calamus opacus G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Morakinyo 1006 (K)

Total: 15; Abia 4, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2.

Laccosperma robustum (Burret) J.Dransf.

Ancistrophyllum robustum Burret

Smith 53 (K)

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Edo 2.

Laccosperma secundiflorum (P.Beauv.) Kuntze

Calamus secundiflorus P.Beauv.

Arwaodo 42 (K)

Total: 86; Abia 10, Anambra 4, Bayelsa 4, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 19, Imo 3, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3.

Livistona chinensis (Jacq.) R.Br. ex Mart. —

Introduced

Latania chinensis Jacq.

Ndozi; FHI15441; -- [K000209853]

Total: 2; Abia 2.

Nypa fruticans Wurmb — Introduced

Tuley, P.; 452; 1964-02-01 [K001579393]

Total: 3; Niger 1.

Oncocalamus tuleyi Sunderl.

Morakinyo 1002 (K)

Total: 5; Abia 1, Lagos 2.

Oncocalamus wrightianus Hutch. —

Endemic

Barter 2220 (K)

Total: 8; Delta 1, Lagos 1.

Phoenix dactylifera L. — Introduced

Odewo Juwon; 2017-4-24 [7552]3460378869

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Phoenix reclinata Jacq.

H. Royer s.n.; -- [US 2107799]

Total: 40; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 5, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 5, Rivers 3, Taraba 5.

Podococcus barberi G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Tuley 600 (K)

Total: 19; Bayelsa 4, Niger 9, Rivers 2.

Raphia africana Otedoh

Otedoh, M.O. 7373 (K)

Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Ogun 2.

Raphia diasticha Burret

Literature

Total: 0.

Raphia farinifera (Gaertn.) Hyl. —

Introduced

Sagus farinifera Gaertn.

Otedoh, M.; 7402; 1971-01-01 [K000707173]

Total: 2; Abia 1.

Raphia hookeri G.Mann & H.Wendl.

Otedoh, M.O. 7201 (K)

Total: 47; Abia 28, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Imo 3, Kogi 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 10.

Raphia mannii Becc.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28200 (K); Otedoh, M.O. 7381 (K)

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Raphia monbuttorum Drude

Literature

Total: 0.

Raphia monbuttorum var. *monbuttorum* —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Raphia regalis Becc.

Otedoh, M. 7106; 1972-7-9 [K000522258]

Total: 14; Abia 4, Cross River 9.

Raphia sudanica A.Chev.

D.P. Stanfield FHI 54314 (WAG)

Total: 11; Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Sokoto 1.

Raphia taedigera (Mart.) Mart. —

Introduced

Sagus taedigera Mart.

Literature

Total: 0.

Raphia vinifera P.Beauv.

Palisot de Beauvois s.n. (type (G? BM, FI, M, P)

Total: 71; Abia 7, Bayelsa 3, Cross River 6, Delta 3, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Imo 6, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 11, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Sclerosperma mannii H.Wendl.

Tuley 654 (K)

Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 2.

Sclerosperma profizianum Valk. & Sunderl.

Literature

Total: 0.

COMMELINACEAE

Amischotolype tenuis (C.B.Clarke) R.S.Rao

Buforrestia tenuis C.B.Clarke

Morton, JK K 1211; 1961-1-11 [WAG0100882]

Total: 15; Cross River 3, Edo 6, Niger 1, Ondo 2.

Aneilema aequinoctiale (P.Beauv.) G.Don

Commelina aequinoctialis P.Beauv.

Pilz, GE 1844; 1976-11-14 [WAG.1192352]

Total: 18; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Ondo 3, Oyo 2.

Aneilema beniniense (P.Beauv.) Kunth

Commelina beniniensis P.Beauv.

Pilz, GE 2562; 1980-11-13 [WAG.1443757]

Total: 99; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 19, Delta 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 11, Ondo 8, Oyo 22, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Aneilema dispernum Brenan

Literature

Total: 0.

Aneilema lanceolatum Benth.

Vogel s.n.; -- [K000345689]

Total: 77; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 10, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Gombe 2, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 15, Kano 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 8, Ogun 4, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 5, Yobe 2.

Aneilema lanceolatum subsp. *lanceolatum*

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 397; 1978-5-10 [WAG.1443858]

Total: 52; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 9, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 10, Kano 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Ogun 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Aneilema lanceolatum subsp. *subnudum*

(A.Chev.) J.K.Morton

Meikle R.D. 1199; 1950-2-19 [BR0000019822495]

Total: 5.

Aneilema paludosum A.Chev.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1958; 1966-9-16 [WAG.1443900]

Total: 10; Niger 4, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Aneilema paludosum subsp. *paludosum*

Stanfield, DP FHI 45646; -- [WAG.1960983]

Total: 8; Niger 3, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Aneilema paludosum subsp. *pauciflorum*

J.K.Morton

Hepper F.N. 3904; 1969- [K002402543]

Total: 1.

Aneilema pomeridianum Stanf. & Brenan

Onochie, CFA FHI 35394; 1956-7-13

[WAG.1961061]

Total: 31; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Aneilema setiferum A.Chev.

Dalziel J.M.; 27-03-1905 [K002402583]

Total: 8; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 2, Niger 3, Oyo 1.

Aneilema setiferum var. *setiferum*

Geerling, C 3674; 1971-7-21 [WAG.1443990]

Total: 8; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 2, Niger 3, Oyo 1.

Aneilema silvaticum Brenan

Aneilema affine De Wild.

Meikle, R.D. 637; 1949-11-13 [2139]912017601

Total: 6; Edo 5.

Aneilema umbrosum (Vahl) Kunth

Commelina umbrosa Vahl

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 485; 1978-5-23

[WAG.1444050]

Total: 45; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 5, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Aneilema umbrosum var. *ovato-oblongum* (P.Beauv.) Brenan

Aneilema ovato-oblongum P.Beauv.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67690; 1973-2-25

[WAG.1444047]

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Aneilema umbrosum var. *umbrosum*

Commelina umbrosa Vahl

Ekwuno, PO; Adetula; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67064;

1973-8-8 [WAG.1444031]

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3.

Buforrestia mannii C.B.Clarke

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO; Fagbemi, A FHI

71046; 1974-7-18 [WAG.1444131]

Total: 14; Benue 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 5.

Coleotrype laurentii K.Schum.

Stanfield, D.P. 46a; 1957-7-20 [12957]912008124

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Edo 4, Ondo 4.

Commelina acutispatha De Wild.

Lekan A.; 1994-10-11 [105257]1990433708

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Imo 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Oyo 3.

Commelina africana L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1999; 1966-9-22 [WAG.1444286]

Total: 75; Abia 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 5, Delta 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Imo 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 10, Taraba 12.

Commelina africana subsp. *africana*

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD 134; 1972-5-4

[WAG.1444316]

Total: 48; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Delta 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 4, Taraba 8.

Commelina africana var. *krebsiana* (Kunth)

C.B.Clarke — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Commelina africana var. *villosior*

(C.B.Clarke) Brenan

Geerling, C 4125; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1444363]

Total: 5; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Ondo 1.

Commelina ascendens J.K.Morton

Jones A.P.D.; 1943-12-22 [7103]1990426585

Total: 10; Ogun 1, Ondo 6, Oyo 1.

Commelina aspera G.Don ex Benth.

Gbile Z.O.; Wit P.; Daramola B.O. 1093; 1972-4-20

[65322]1990431358

Total: 11; Imo 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 4, Plateau 3.

Commelina aspera var. *aspera*

Stanfield D.P. 156; 20-10-1957 [K003071967]

Total: 1.

Commelina benghalensis L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1085; 1966-1-23 [WAG.1444522]

Total: 25; Adamawa 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Jigawa 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Commelina bracteosa Hassk.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 320; 1977-10-12

[WAG.1495251]

Total: 46; Abia 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Enugu 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Commelina bracteosa subsp. *bracteosa*

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 248; 11-08-1962

[K003071570]

Total: 1.

Commelina bracteosa var. *lagosensis*

(C.B.Clarke) Faden

Dalziel J.M. 1418; 22-06-1919 [K003071603]

Total: 16; Cross River 3, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Commelina cameroonensis J.K.Morton

Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O. 32; 1980-10-29

[94154]1990433113

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Kano 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Commelina capitata Benth.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO 1015; 1971-11-19 [WAG.1444765]

Total: 94; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 41, Enugu 5, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 4, Osun 3, Oyo 2, Taraba 6.

Commelina congesta C.B.Clarke

Daramola B.O.; 1973-10-5 [72319]1990431788

Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 3, Bauchi 1, Cross River 7, Edo 4, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Taraba 1.

Commelina diffusa Burm.f.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66006; 1973-2-15

[WAG.1444916]

Total: 103; Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Borno 10, Cross River 14, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Imo 3, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 12, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 7, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Commelina diffusa subsp. *diffusa*

Daramola B.O.; 1965-9-15 [56405]1990430737

Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 2, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 8, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Commelina diffusa subsp. *montana*

J.K.Morton

Medler J. 827; 17-08-1973 [K000541690]

Total: 1.

Commelina erecta L.

Geerling, C 4111; 1971-8-20 [WAG.1495003]

Total: 123; Bauchi 10, Benue 2, Borno 3, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 7, Kaduna 6, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 12, Ogun 7, Ondo 6, Oyo 23, Plateau 4, Rivers 2, Taraba 4.

Commelina erecta subsp. *erecta*

Wit P. FHI27560; 1971-8-17 [BR0000019849263]

Total: 73; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 7, Kano 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Oyo 20, Plateau 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 3.

Commelina erecta subsp. *livingstonii*

(C.B.Clarke) J.K.Morton

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 94; 1977-10-5

[WAG.1495104]

Total: 37; Bauchi 7, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Commelina erecta subsp. *maritima*

(J.K.Morton) J.K.Morton

Lowe J. 4910; 11-11-1990 [K003071604]

Total: 4; Lagos 2.

Commelina forskaolii Vahl

Gbile Z.O.; Odewo T.K. 171/10; 1981-10-23 [102526]

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 1.

Commelina gambiae C.B.Clarke

Geerling, C 3958; 1971-8-12 [WAG.1495209]

Total: 27; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Edo 1, Enugu 4, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 3, Rivers 1, Yobe 1.

Commelina imberbis Ehrenb. ex Hassk.

Stanfield D.P. FHI45709; 1961-11-17

[BR0000025100860]

Total: 4; Oyo 4.

Commelina longicapsa C.B.Clarke

Onochie, CFA FHI 38304; 1958-3-28

[WAG.1495331]

Total: 12; Cross River 2, Edo 9.

Commelina macrospatha Gilg & Ledermann
ex Mildbr.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1450; 1972-4-22

[WAG.1495337]

Total: 14; Bauchi 2, Benue 4, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Commelina macrosperma J.K.Morton

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65862; 1972-10-10

[WAG.1495340]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 2, Benue 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 1, Ondo 6, Taraba 1.

Commelina nigritana Benth.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2005; 1966-9-22 [WAG.1495378]

Total: 28; Anambra 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 2, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Commelina nigritana subsp. *nigritana*

Ohaeri A.O. 997; 1975-10-8 [78856]1990432207

Total: 24; Anambra 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Commelina petersii Hassk.

Noble H.L. 4; 30-08-1949 [K003071546]

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Commelina schweinfurthii C.B. Clarke

Chapman H.M. 112; 1973-8-18 [70907]

Total: 6; Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Commelina schweinfurthii subsp.
schweinfurthii

Lely H.V. P 666; 1930-8- [11013]K003071567

Total: 1.

Commelina subulata Roth

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63200; 1972-8-8

[WAG.1495502]

Total: 26; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 5, Kwara 2, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1.

Commelina zambesica C.B. Clarke

Kamphorst, A 155; 1960-1-1 [WAG.1495549]

Total: 22; Benue 1, Kaduna 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 8, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Cyanotis angusta C.B. Clarke

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66026; 1973-2-26

[WAG.1495701]

Total: 34; Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Enugu 13, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Niger 5, Oyo 1, Plateau 4.

Cyanotis arachnoidea C.B. Clarke

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 64794; 1972-10-19

[WAG.1495691]

Total: 34; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 3, Niger 1, Ondo 22, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Cyanotis arachnoidea var. *pilosa* Brenan

Onochie C.F.A. FHI33351; 18-07-1953 [K]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Cyanotis caespitosa Kotschy & Peyr.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1282; 1972-5-3

[WAG.1495725]

Total: 42; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Cross River 2, Kaduna 8, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 11, Zamfara 1.

Cyanotis hepperi Brenan

Hepper F.N. 1360; 14-11-1957 [K000345755]

Total: 2.

Cyanotis lanata Benth.

Denys, E 798; 1982-8-4 [WAG.1495852]

Total: 137; Adamawa 2, Anambra 6, Bauchi 5, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Edo 3, Gombe 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 3, Kwara 8, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 14, Ogun 8,

Ondo 14, Osun 2, Oyo 25, Plateau 10, Rivers 1, Sokoto 3, Taraba 3.

Cyanotis longifolia Benth.

Gbile, ZO ZMO 38; 1985-9-27 [WAG.1495952]

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Enugu 2, Niger 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Cyanotis longifolia var. *longifolia*

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63163; 1972-6-26

[WAG.1496022]

Total: 5; Enugu 2, Plateau 3.

Cyanotis somaliensis C.B. Clarke —
Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Cyanotis vaga (Lour.) Schult. & Schult.f.

Tradescantia vaga Lour.

Chapman J.D. 3430; 05-11-1974 [K]

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Floscopa africana (P.Beauv.) C.B. Clarke

Aneilema africanum P.Beauv.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 32; 1979-4-20

[WAG.1496210]

Total: 92; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 14, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kebbi 1, Lagos 6, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 10, Osun 2, Oyo 17, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Floscopa africana subsp. *africana*

Aneilema africanum P.Beauv.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 205; 1977-10-8

[WAG.1496243]

Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 7, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 2.

Floscopa africana subsp. *majuscula*

(C.B. Clarke) Brenan

Floscopa africana var. *majuscula* C.B. Clarke

Latilo, MG FHI 64611; 1971-11-12 [WAG.1501261]

Total: 23; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 3, Ondo 5, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Floscopa aquatica Hua

G. E. Pilz 2223; 1977-11-27 [US 2950017]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Edo 4, Imo 1, Rivers 1.

Floscopa confusa Brenan

Hepper, F.N. 1719; 1958-1-20 [K000345786]

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Cross River 1, Taraba 2.

Floscopa flavida C.B. Clarke

Lely, H.V.; 554; 1921-08-27 [K002794970]

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Plateau 1.

Floscopa glomerata (Willd. ex Schult. & Schult.f.) Hassk.

Tradescantia glomerata Willd. ex Schult. & Schult.f.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2088; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1501362]

Total: 33; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 8, Kwara 2, Niger 3, Ondo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 4, Zamfara 1.

Floscopa glomerata subsp. *glomerata*

Tradescantia glomerata Willd. ex Schult. & Schult.f.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 67258; 1973-11-20 [WAG.1501364]

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Floscopa glomerata subsp. *lelyi* (Hutch.)

Brenan

Floscopa lelyi Hutch.

Lely H.V. 704; 1921-11-16 [K000345788]

Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 5, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Ondo 4.

Floscopa glomerata subsp. *pauciflora*

(C.B. Clarke) J.K. Morton

Floscopa pauciflora C.B. Clarke

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1278; 1972-5-3 [WAG.1501371]

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Floscopa mannii C.B. Clarke

Talbot, P.A.; 756; 1911-01-01 [K002794985]

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Floscopa schweinfurthii C.B. Clarke —

Introduced

Schweinfurth, G.; 1869-11-17 [B 10 0165386]

Total: 1.

Murdannia nudiflora (L.) Brenan —

Introduced

Commelina nudiflora L.

Bels, L 25; 1951-7-15 [U.1209745]

Total: 3; Lagos 2.

Murdannia simplex (Vahl) Brenan

Commelina simplex Vahl

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66618; 1973-7-18 [WAG.1501543]

Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Murdannia spirata var. *spirata* —

Introduced

Murdannia spirata L.

Ekwuno, P.O. 267; 1975-11-21 [K002402465]

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Taraba 4.

Murdannia tenuissima (A.Chev.) Brenan

Baoullia tenuissima A.Chev.

Daramola, BO; Adebunsi, JK FHI 38419; 1958-9-16 [WAG.1501597]

Total: 9; Kogi 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Palisota ambigua (P.Beauv.) C.B. Clarke

Commelina ambigua P.Beauv.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 356; 1977-10-13 [WAG0133337]

Total: 46; Cross River 10, Edo 17, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 4, Rivers 1.

Palisota barberi Hook.f.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32689; 1981-6-15 [WAG0133366]

Total: 73; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Edo 25, Ogun 8, Ondo 12, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Palisota brachythyrso Mildbr.

Pilz, GE 2264; 1978-2-21 [WAG.1585396]

Total: 1; Ekiti 1.

Palisota bracteosa C.B. Clarke

P. Van Meer 1464; 1971-4-26 [US 3351782]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Palisota hirsuta (Thunb.) K.Schum.

Dracaena hirsuta Thunb.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70507; 1973-3-5 [WAG0133563]

Total: 99; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 2, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 9, Edo 10, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 13, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ogun 7, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 18, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Palisota mannii C.B. Clarke

Talbot P.A. 908; 1911-- [BM000835690]

Total: 24; Adamawa 1, Cross River 7, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Taraba 2.

Palisota mannii subsp. *mannii*

Richards P.W. 5115; 04-03-1955 [K002792154]

Total: 1.

Palisota mannii subsp. *megalophylla*

(Mildbr.) Faden

Pilz, G.E.; 1977-4-24 [B 10 0134488]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Palisota preussiana K.Schum. ex
C.B.Clarke
Chapman JD; 1972-05-13 [WAG.1501742]
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Palisota schweinfurthii C.B.Clarke
Chapman, JD 2820; 1972-5-13 [WAG.1501742]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Pollia condensata C.B.Clarke
Ariwaodo, JO 479; 1977-3-27 [WAG.1501958]
Total: 35; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 7, Ekiti 2,
Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2,
Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Pollia mannii C.B.Clarke
Daramola, BO; Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI
71050; 1974-8-1 [WAG.1501994]
Total: 23; Kaduna 1, Ondo 9, Osun 2, Plateau 3,
Taraba 1.

Polyspatha hirsuta Mildbr.
Daramola, BO; Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI
71050; 1974-8-1 [WAG.1501993]
Total: 40; Bauchi 1, Edo 14, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi
1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 1,
Taraba 3.

Polyspatha oligospatha Faden
Brenan J.P.M. 8566; 1947-12-21 [BR0000008304216]
Total: 1; Edo 1.

Polyspatha paniculata Benth.
Pilz, GE 2567; 1980-11-25 [WAG.1502146]
Total: 30; Cross River 5, Edo 9, Ogun 4, Ondo 4, Oyo
1, Taraba 3.

Stanfieldiella axillaris J.K.Morton
Meikle R.D. 566; 14-11-1949 [K002794543]
Total: 3; Edo 1, Lagos 1.

Stanfieldiella brachycarpa (Gilg &
Ledermann ex Mildbr.) Brenan
Buforrestia brachycarpa Gilg & Ledermann ex
Mildbr.
Onochie, C.F.A.; Brenan, Prof. J.P.M. 9090; 1948-2-
21 [K000345738]
Total: 7; Edo 7.

Stanfieldiella imperforata (C.B.Clarke)
Brenan
Buforrestia imperforata C.B.Clarke
Brenan J.P.M. 8508; 1947-12-13 [BR0000020274924]
Total: 36; Edo 17, Lagos 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 8, Osun 1.

Stanfieldiella imperforata var. *imperforata*
Buforrestia imperforata C.B.Clarke

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO FHI 71011; 1974-7-10
[WAG.1502350]
Total: 27; Edo 12, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 7, Osun 1.

Stanfieldiella oligantha (Mildbr.) Brenan
Buforrestia oligantha Mildbr.
Pilz, GE 2638; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1502365]
Total: 23; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 7,
Ondo 6, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1.

Tradescantia spathacea Sw. — Introduced
Oladejo F.M; 1982-5-5 [1508]3808440985
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 3.

Tradescantia zebrina Bosse — Introduced
Ohadiugha C.J; 1982-2-6 [952]3808440981
Total: 3; Lagos 2, Ogun 1.

Tradescantia zebrina var. *zebrina* —
Introduced
Saibu S.O. ; 1982-6-1 [9329]
Total: 1.

PHILYDRACEAE

Helmholtzia novoguineensis (K.Krause)
Skotts. — Introduced
Astelia novoguineensis K.Krause
Ledermann,C.L.; 1912-10-28 [B 10 0278896]
Total: 2.

PONTERIACEAE

Heteranthera callifolia Rchb. ex Kunth
Daggash, M. 31405; 1951-12-10 [K000211617]
Total: 16; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1,
Lagos 1, Ogun 4, Oyo 1.

Pontederia crassipes Mart. — Introduced
O. O. Oyebanji; 2014-8-6 [6755] [3808441387]
Total: 6; Lagos 6.

Pontederia diversifolia (Vahl) M.Pell. &
C.N.Horn — Introduced
Heteranthera diversifolia Vahl
Onochie, C.F.A. 36370; 1956-7-10 [25010]912021661
Total: 13; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1,
Niger 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Pontederia natans P.Beauv.
Pilz, GE 2281; 1979-3-18 [WAG.1939454]
Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 1,
Ogun 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

STRELITZIACEAE

Ravenala madagascariensis Sonn. —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Strelitzia reginae Banks — Introduced

Dr.A.B.Kadiri; 2010-3-15 [2661] [3808442829]

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Sokoto 1.

HELICONIACEAE

Heliconia pendula Wawra — Introduced

Iwuanyanwu Uche; 2014-3-5 [6074] [3808441872]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

MUSACEAE

Ensete livingstonianum (J.Kirk) Cheesman

Musa livingstoniana J.Kirk

Onochie, C.F.A. 35747; 1956-8-25 [K000480824]

Total: 24; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 3, Cross River 1, Kaduna 13, Niger 4.

Musa acuminata Colla — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Musa textilis Née — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1659; 1966-6-30 [WAG.1111435]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Musa × *paradisiaca* L. — Introduced

T.K.Odewo; 2013-3-7 [5578] [3808439342]

Total: 1.

CANNACEAE

Canna indica L. — Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 312; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1511438]

Total: 37; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Edo 4, Gombe 1,
Imo 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 8.

MARANTACEAE

Afrocalathea rhizantha (K.Schum.)

K.Schum.

Calathea rhizantha K.Schum.

Daramola B.O. FHI55320; 10-10-1964 [K002188133]

Total: 1.

Halopegia azurea (K.Schum.) K.Schum.

Donax azurea K.Schum.

Talbot P.A. 57; 1911-- [BR0000021431630]

Total: 13; Cross River 5, Edo 5.

Hypselodelphys poggeana (K.Schum.)

Milne-Redh.

Trachypodium poggeanum K.Schum.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11214; 1977-3-17

[WAG.1933428]

Total: 39; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2,
Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1,
Rivers 2.

Hypselodelphys scandens Louis & Mullend.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 17; 1979-4-11

[WAG.1933385]

Total: 9; Cross River 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Hypselodelphys violacea (Ridl.) Milne-

Redh.

Trachypodium violaceum Ridl.

Pilz, GE 2359; 1980-5-5 [WAG.1932910]

Total: 19; Cross River 2, Edo 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 5,
Ondo 1, Oyo 4.

Maranta arundinacea L. — Introduced

Eijnatten CLM van; Eijnatten, CLM van 1654; 1966-
06-30 [WAG.1932798]

Total: 8; Abia 2, Oyo 3.

Marantochloa conferta (Benth.) A.C.Ley

Calathea conferta Benth.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32808; 1981-6-18

[WAG.1933237]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Edo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 1,
Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Marantochloa congensis (K.Schum.)

J.Léonard & Mullend.

Donax congensis K.Schum.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11319; 1977-4-1 [WAG.1932707]

Total: 19; Bauchi 2, Delta 1, Edo 7, Imo 2, Niger 1,
Osun 3, Taraba 1.

Marantochloa cordifolia (K.Schum.)

Koechlin

Clinogyne cordifolia K.Schum.

Lowe J. 3790; 18-02-1979 [K000541871]

Total: 1.

Marantochloa cuspidata (Roscoe) Milne-Redh.

Maranta cuspidata Roscoe
; -- [E01039954]3397229320
Total: 1.

Marantochloa filipes (Benth.) Hutch.

Phrynium filipes Benth.
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 358; 1977-10-13
[WAG.1932539]
Total: 10; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Oyo 2.

Marantochloa leucantha (K.Schum.) Milne-Redh.

Donax leucantha K.Schum.
Gbile, ZO; Wit, P 974; 1971-11-26 [WAG.1932338]
Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 8, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 7, Oyo 4.

Marantochloa leucantha var. *lasiocolea* (K.Schum.) Koechlin

Clinogyne lasiocolea K.Schum.
Onochie, CFA FHI 38325; 1958-3-31
[WAG.1932396]
Total: 3; Borno 1, Edo 2.

Marantochloa leucantha var. *leucantha*

Donax leucantha K.Schum.
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 388; 1977-10-15
[WAG.1932340]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Marantochloa mannii (Benth.) Milne-Redh.

Calathea mannii Benth.
Keay, R.W.J.37268; 1967-12-11 [23044] [912019490]
Total: 7; Edo 6, Ondo 1.

Marantochloa monophylla (K.Schum.)

D'Orey
Clinogyne monophylla K.Schum.
Schmitt 224; 1994-12-1 [976615] [1261904323]
Total: 2; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Marantochloa purpurea (Ridl.) Milne-Redh.

Clinogyne purpurea Ridl.
Odewo, TK; Adedeji 266; 1983-5-13 [WAG.1933783]
Total: 31; Abia 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 6, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 4, Plateau 3.

Marantochloa ramosissima (Benth.) Hutch.

Phrynium ramosissimum Benth.
Pilz, GE 2013; 1977-4-26 [WAG.1933703]
Total: 11; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7.

Megaphrynium macrostachyum (K.Schum.) Milne-Redh.

Phyllodes macrostachya K.Schum.
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70512; 1973-3-5
[WAG.1934072]
Total: 30; Cross River 4, Edo 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 2.

Sarcophrynium brachystachyum (Benth.) K.Schum.

Maranta brachystachys Benth.
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11296; 1977-3-30
[WAG.1934214]
Total: 20; Cross River 5, Delta 2, Edo 5, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Sarcophrynium prionogonium (K.Schum.) K.Schum.

Phyllodes prionogonia K.Schum.
Onochie, C.A.; 1955-06-27 [K.27159.0]
Total: 21; Cross River 5, Edo 9.

Sarcophrynium prionogonium var. *ivorense* Schnell

Onochie C.F.A. FHI38309; 29-03-1958 [K]
Total: 11; Cross River 2, Edo 6.

Sarcophrynium prionogonium var. *prionogonium*

Phyllodes prionogonia K.Schum.
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 346; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1934663]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Thalia geniculata L.

Latilo, MG FHI 63526; 1971-10-24 [WAG.1090151]
Total: 36; Adamawa 3, Benue 1, Edo 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Oyo 4, Taraba 2.

Thaumatococcus daniellii (Benn.) Benth. ex Eichler

Phrynium daniellii Benn.
Verwilghen 39; 1997-3-20 [BR0000013326791]
Total: 31; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Lagos 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Thaumatococcus daniellii var. *daniellii*

Phrynium daniellii Benn.
Onochie C.F.A. FHI7654; 05-09-1944 [K002918835]
Total: 1.

Thaumatococcus daniellii var. *puberulifolius* Dhetchuvi & Diafouka

Hutchinson J. S.N.; 1912-06-11 [BR0000013326869]
Total: 2; Borno 2.

Trachyprynium braunianum (K.Schum.)
Baker

Hybophrynium braunianum K.Schum.

Laan, FM van der 339; 1981-5-28 [WAG.1090351]
Total: 52; Abia 3, Anambra 2, Cross River 4, Delta 4,
Ebonyi 1, Edo 6, Imo 2, Katsina 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2,
Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

COSTACEAE

Chamaecostus cuspidatus (Nees & Mart.)

C.D.Specht & D.W.Stev. — Introduced

Globba cuspidata Nees & Mart.

Dr.Bankole; 2021-8-9 [8833]3808442292

Total: 1.

Costus afer Ker Gawl.

Pilz, GE 2194; 1977-10-30 [WAG.1872770]

Total: 49; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1,
Delta 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 4,
Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Osun 7, Oyo 2,
Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Costus dinklagei K.Schum.

Jones, A.P.D.; Onochie, C.F.; 18913; 1946-05-26
[K002189390]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Costus dubius (Afzel.) K.Schum.

Zingiber dubium Afzel.

Lowe, J. 3331; 1977-5-31 [E00235412]

Total: 11; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa
3, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Costus lateriflorus Baker

Onochie, CFA FHI 33177; 1953-5-15
[WAG.1872549]

Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 6, Cross River 5.

Costus lilaceus Maas & H.Maas —

Introduced

Savory, H.J.; Keay, R.W.J.; FHI25202; 1948-12-29
[K002189433]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Costus lucanusianus J.Braun & K.Schum.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 382; 1977-10-15
[WAG.1867763]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 4, Delta 2,
Edo 2, Niger 2.

Costus phyllocephalus K.Schum.

Talbot P.A. 839; 1911-- [BM000915402]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Costus schlechteri H.J.P.Winkl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Costus spectabilis (Fenzl) K.Schum.

Cadalvena spectabilis Fenzl

Wit, P 1303; 1972-4-19 [WAG0028340]

Total: 19; Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 1,
Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 5, Taraba 4.

Costus talbotii Ridl. — Endemic

Dalziel, J.M. 560; -- [K000099616]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Costus tappenbeckianus J.Braun &
K.Schum.

Talbot, P.A. 839a; 1911-01-01 [K002189480]

Total: 1.

Costus woodsonii Maas — Introduced

Dr.Bankole; 2021-8-9 [8835]3808442291

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Hellenia speciosa (J.Koenig) S.R.Dutta —
Introduced

Banksea speciosa J.Koenig

Dr.Bankole; 2021-6-29 [8797]3808442291

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Paracostus englerianus (K.Schum.)

C.D.Specht

Costus englerianus K.Schum.

A.P.D. Jones & C.F.A. Onochie 16669; 1946-3-11
[BM000915392]

Total: 19; Cross River 4, Edo 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1,
Osun 1, Rivers 2.

ZINGIBERACEAE

Aframomum alboviolaceum (Ridl.)

K.Schum.

Amomum alboviolaceum Ridl.

Daramola B.O. FHI38031; 1958-6-19
[BR0000017223911]

Total: 11; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1,
Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1.

Aframomum angustifolium (Sonn.)

K.Schum.

Amomum angustifolium Sonn.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1078; 1971-12-28
[WAG.1194271]

Total: 30; Abia 3, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1,
Ondo 2, Osun 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 13.

Aframomum citratum (J.Pereira) K.Schum.

Amomum citratum J.Pereira

Talbot 33 (BM)

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Aframomum daniellii (Hook.f.) K.Schum.

Amomum daniellii Hook.f.

Meer, PPC van 1147; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1962624]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 11, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Osun 1.

Aframomum fragrans D.J.Harris & Wortley

Literature

Total: 0.

Aframomum glaucophyllum (K.Schum.)

K.Schum.

Amomum glaucophyllum K.Schum.

Eimunjeze; Ekwuno; Onijamowo FHI69903;

[K002670829]

Total: 1.

Aframomum kayserianum (K.Schum.)

K.Schum.

Amomum kayserianum K.Schum.

Jones, E.W. 80; 1958-5-12 [26786]912023799

Total: 2; Nasarawa 2.

Aframomum limbatum (Oliv. & D.Hanb.)

K.Schum.

Amomum limbatum Oliv. & D.Hanb.

Lowe, J. 675; 1965-3-5 [E00957868]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Ekiti 1.

Aframomum makandensis Dhetchuvi

Talbot P.A. 32; 1911-- [BM000547917]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Aframomum melegueta K.Schum.

Amomum melegueta Roscoe

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD FHI 65885; 1972-10-10 [WAG.1201724]

Total: 16; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Aframomum pilosum (Oliv. & D.Hanb.)

K.Schum.

Amomum pilosum Oliv. & D.Hanb.

Literature

Total: 0.

Aframomum plicatum D.J.Harris & Wortley

Talbot P.A. 1595; 1912-- [BM000547920]

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Aframomum polyanthum (K.Schum.)

K.Schum.

Literature

Total: 0.

Aframomum stanfieldii Hepper

Stanfield, D.P. 47087; 1964-3-11 [K000743693]

Total: 10; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 1.

Aframomum zambesiaceum (Baker)

K.Schum.

Amomum zambesiaceum Baker

1973-1-4 [2252242815]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Curcuma longa L. — Introduced

Mariam Yusuf; 2014-5-26 [6105] [3808440678]

Total: 13; Benue 1, Kano 2, Lagos 6, Ogun 2.

Hedychium coronarium J.Koenig —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 362; 1960-8-15 [WAG.1202128]

Total: 4; Abia 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Hedychium flavescens Carey ex Roscoe —

Introduced

s.coll. s.n. [K002427321]

Total: 4.

Renalmia africana Benth.

Talbot P.A. 1652; 1911-- [BM000838030]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Renalmia cinnamata (K.Schum.) T.Durand & Schinz

Ethanium cinnamatum K.Schum.

FHI.44103; 1960-9-21 [BR0000014515125]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1.

Siphonochilus aethiopicus (Schweinf.)

B.L.Burt

Cienkowskia aethiopica Schweinf.

Geerling, C 3551; 1971-4-30 [WAG.1867862]

Total: 28; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Siphonochilus nigericus (Hutch. ex Hepper)

B.L.Burt

Kaempferia nigerica Hutch. ex Hepper

Blom-van Teyn, M van 125; 1971-7-3

[WAG.1867798]

Total: 26; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Zingiber officinale Roscoe — Introduced

Amomum zingiber L.

Mr. Yaya; 2011-11-30 [4396]3808440750

Total: 20; Kano 1, Lagos 9.

TYPHACEAE

Typha angustifolia L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Typha domingensis Pers.

Bentham, W s.n.; 1989-3-27 [L.1193387]

Total: 12; Bauchi 3, Borno 4, Lagos 2, Ogun 1.

Typha latifolia L.

Dr.A.B.Kadiri; 2011-5-14 [3847] [3808442211]

Total: 2; Katsina 1, Sokoto 1.

BROMELIACEAE

Ananas comosus (L.) Merr. — Introduced

Bromelia comosa L.

Esther Etopidiok; 2016-2-6 [7012]

Total: 5; Lagos 5.

XYRIDACEAE

Xyris anceps Lam.

J. T. Baldwin; 1950-01-08 [US 2672895]

Total: 21; Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Xyris anceps var. *anceps*

Daramola, BO FHI 43285; 1964-12-12

[WAG.1872887]

Total: 1.

Xyris anceps var. *minima* (Steud.) Lock

Xyris angularis N.E.Br.

Killick, H.J.; 285; 1965-12-31 [K002063149]

Total: 2; Enugu 1.

Xyris barteri N.E.Br.

Barter, C. s.n.; -- [K000321234]

Total: 6; Kogi 2, Niger 3, Plateau 1.

Xyris capensis Thunb.

Hepper F.N.; 1957-10-29 [BR0000019449043]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 4.

Xyris capensis var. *capensis*

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1943; 1972-5-10

[WAG.1193881]

Total: 1.

Xyris congensis Büttner

Hepper F.N. 1771; 1958-1-25 [BR0000021800986]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Xyris decipiens N.E.Br.

Barter, C.; -- [K000321235]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2.

Xyris filiformis Lam.

2091, 1972-05-11 [K002063183]

Total: 4; Taraba 1.

Xyris fugaciflora Rendle — Introduced

Hepper F.N. 972; 1957-10-9 [BR0000021804779]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Xyris rehmannii L.A.Nilsson

Hepper F.N. 1758; 1958-1-23 [BR0000021806056]

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Xyris rubella Malme

Dalziel, J.M. 240; 1908-11-10 [K000321240]

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Xyris straminea L.A.Nilsson

Gledhill, D 1028; 1968-10-25 [WAG.1194132]

Total: 15; Kogi 4, Niger 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

ERIOCAULACEAE

Eriocaulon abyssinicum Hochst.

Hepper, H.; 1957-10-23 [P00443046]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Jigawa 1.

Eriocaulon afzelianum Wikstr. ex Körn.

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-11-7 [P00443000]

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Eriocaulon asteroides S.M.Phillips

Tuley, P. 2052; 1969-11-19 [K000346115]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Eriocaulon bamendae S.M.Phillips

1748 [K000541865]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Eriocaulon bongense Engl. & Ruhland

Meikle R.D. 1015; 1950-1-14 [BR0000024720762]

Total: 14; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Plateau 3.

Eriocaulon elegantulum Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Eriocaulon fulvum N.E.Br.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63259; 1970-4-3

[WAG.1795727]

Total: 28; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Eriocaulon latifolium Sm.

Vogel s.n.; -- [K000346093]

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Eriocaulon meikleii Moldenke

Hepper, F.N. 1450; 1957-11-24 [K000384249]

Total: 5; Adamawa 2, Niger 3.

Eriocaulon melanocephalum Kunth —

Introduced

Barter 1021; -- [K000346116]

Total: 2; Niger 2.

Eriocaulon nigericum Meikle

Jones, A.P.D. 20718; 1946-8-25 [K000346102]

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 3.

Eriocaulon porembskii S.M.Phillips &

Mesterházy

15388; 1962-08-22 [K002183620]

Total: 4; Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Eriocaulon setaceum L.

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-10-15 [P00458970]

Total: 10; Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Plateau 3.

Eriocaulon teuschii Engl. & Ruhland

Lely, H.V. 283; 1921-6-20 [K000346092]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Eriocaulon togoense Moldenke

Eriocaulon xeranthemoides Van Heurck & Müll.Arg.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3827; 1971-7-28 [WAG0107114]

Total: 35; Edo 2, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Niger 9, Ondo 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 1.

Eriocaulon zambesiense Ruhland

Literature

Total: 0.

Mesanthemum jaegeri Jacq.-Fél.

Savory, H.J.; Keay, R.W.J. ; 1948-12-21 [P00443212]

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Mesanthemum radicans (Benth.) Körn.

Eriocaulon radicans Benth.

Onochie, CFA FHI 32099; 1953-5-12

[WAG.1931106]

Total: 24; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Edo 3, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 1.

Syngonanthus wahlbergii (Wikstr. ex Körn.)

Ruhland

Eriocaulon wahlbergii Wikstr. ex Körn.

Literature

Total: 0.

Syngonanthus wahlbergii var. *wahlbergii*

Eriocaulon wahlbergii Wikstr. ex Körn.

Literature

Total: 0.

CYPERACEAE

Abildgaardia ovata (Burm.f.) Kral

Carex ovata Burm.f.

R.W.J. Keay FHI 25907 (K001418828)

Total: 6; Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Sokoto 1.

Actinoscirpus grossus (L.f.) Goetgh. &

D.A.Simpson — Introduced

Scirpus grossus L.f.

1939-8-31 [KR-M-0022732 / 484905 /

16049]2845977698

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Afrotrilepis pilosa (Boeckeler) J.Raynal

Trilepis pilosa Boeckeler

R.W.J. Keay FHI 22877 (K000211762)

Total: 61; Bauchi 4, Ekiti 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 7, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ondo 15, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Arthrostylis aphylla R.Br. — Introduced

Hall, J.B.; 1970-7-17 [9518]1086615359

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Bulbostylis abortiva (Steud.) C.B.Clarke

Fimbristylis abortiva Steud.

J.B. Hall CC 570 (K001418840)

Total: 51; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 3, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Bulbostylis angolensis (C.B.Clarke)

Larridon & Roalson

Scirpus angolensis C.B.Clarke

J.B. Hall 808 (K001418832)

Total: 3; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1.

Bulbostylis barbata (Rottb.) C.B.Clarke

Scirpus barbatus Rottb.

Gbile, ZO 19; 1975-5-27 [WAG.1411721]

Total: 43; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 6, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Bulbostylis barbata subsp. *barbata*

Scirpus barbatus Rottb.

J. Lowe UIH 12667 (K001418831)

Total: 1.

Bulbostylis briziformis (Hutch.) Larridon & Roalson

Scirpus briziformis Hutch.

Lowe J. 2336; 1971-10-23 [31978]1989850554

Total: 13; Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Ondo 4, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Bulbostylis briziformis subsp. *briziformis*

Scirpus briziformis Hutch.

F.N. Hepper 1067 (K001418833)

Total: 1.

Bulbostylis capillaris (L.) Kunth ex

C.B. Clarke — Introduced

Scirpus capillaris L.

Gledhill, D 961; 1968-4-6 [WAG.1411853]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Bulbostylis cioniana (Pi.Savi) Lye

Fimbristylis cioniana Pi.Savi

R.W. Haines 205 (K001418844)

Total: 11; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2.

Bulbostylis coleotricha (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

C.B. Clarke

Fimbristylis coleotricha Hochst. ex A.Rich.

R.W.J. Keay FHI 25949 (K001418841)

Total: 29; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 5, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Bulbostylis congolensis De Wild.

J. Lowe 2286 (K001418839)

Total: 38; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 5, Kwara 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 17, Plateau 6.

Bulbostylis densa (Wall.) Hand.-Mazz. — Introduced

Scirpus densus Wall.

Unknown 1562; -- [U.1297142]2517404856

Total: 9; Borno 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Bulbostylis densa subsp. *densa*

Scirpus densus Wall.

J. Lowe 2731 (K001418837)

Total: 1.

Bulbostylis filamentosa (Vahl) C.B. Clarke

Scirpus filamentosus Vahl

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 387 (K001418834)

Total: 35; Bauchi 2, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 8, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 4, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Bulbostylis hensii (C.B. Clarke) R.W. Haines

Fimbristylis hensii C.B. Clarke

B.O. Daramola FHI 90220 (WAG0390557)

Total: 1; Ekiti 1.

Bulbostylis hispidula (Vahl) R.W. Haines

Scirpus hispidulus Vahl

Geerling, C 4048; 1971-8-19 [WAG.1763967]

Total: 198; Abia 5, Adamawa 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 4, Benue 2, Borno 4, Cross River 6, Edo 6, Ekiti 2, Enugu 11, Gombe 2, Imo 3, Kaduna 12, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 8, Lagos 8, Niger 15, Ogun 7, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 26, Plateau 11, Rivers 4, Sokoto 3, Taraba 4, Yobe 3, Zamfara 1.

Bulbostylis hispidula subsp. *brachyphylla* (Cherm.) R.W. Haines

Fimbristylis exilis var. brachyphylla Cherm.

D. Gledhill 649 (K001418845)

Total: 20; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 5, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Oyo 1.

Bulbostylis hispidula subsp. *hispidula*

Scirpus hispidulus Vahl

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 419 (K001418846)

Total: 1.

Bulbostylis hispidula subsp. *senegalensis* (Cherm.) Vanden Berghen

Fimbristylis exilis var. senegalensis Cherm.

B. Moiser 132 (K001418847)

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Sokoto 2.

Bulbostylis laniceps C.B. Clarke ex

T. Durand & Schinz

A. Kamphorst 198A (WAG0272384)

Total: 2; Enugu 1, Niger 1.

Bulbostylis lanifera (Boeckeler) Kük.

Scirpus lanifer Boeckeler

H.J. Killick 252 (K001418842)

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Bulbostylis oritrephes (Ridl.) C.B. Clarke

Fimbristylis oritrephes Ridl.

Jackson, J.K.; Magaji, S.O.; Tuley, P.; 1899; 1969-11-16 [K002095183]

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Bulbostylis oritrephes subsp. *oritrephe*s

Fimbristylis oritrephes Ridl.

J.B. Hall 1824 (K001418843)

Total: 1.

Bulbostylis pilosa (Willd.) Cherm.

Schoenus pilosus Willd.

J. Lowe 4428 (K001418836)

Total: 64; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Delta 3, Edo 11, Enugu 8, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 4, Lagos 6, Niger 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Bulbostylis pusilla (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

C.B. Clarke

Fimbristylis pusilla Hochst. ex A.Rich.

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 551 (K001418838)

Total: 21; Bauchi 5, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1.

Bulbostylis scabricaulis Cherm.

J. Lowe 2655 (K001418835)

Total: 37; Benue 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Bulbostylis schoenoides (Kunth) C.B. Clarke

Isolepis schoenoides Kunth

E. Ujor FHI 30306 (K001418848)

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Enugu 1, Oyo 1.

Bulbostylis trichobasis (Baker) C.B. Clarke

— Introduced

Scirpus trichobasis Baker

1958-1-9 [2252242583]

Total: 1.

Bulbostylis viridecarinata (De Wild.)

Goetgh.

Fimbristylis viridecarinata De Wild.

C. Goerling 3913 (FHI0045370)

Total: 2; Niger 2.

Carex neochevalieri Kük. ex A.Chev.

J.B. Hall 2932 (K001418775)

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Plateau 1.

Carex petitiiana A.Rich.

Total: 4; Taraba 1.

Carex petitiiana subsp. *petitiiana*

P. Tuley 2033 (K001418777)

Total: 4; Taraba 1

Cladium mariscus (L.) Pohl — Introduced

Schoenus mariscus L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Coleochloa abyssinica (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Gilly

Eriospora abyssinica Hochst. ex A.Rich.

H.M. Chapman 176 (FHI0102083)

Total: 2.

Cyperus acuticarinatus Kük.

P.O. Ekwuno 942 (FHI0097016)

Total: 16; Cross River 1, Kwara 7, Niger 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Cyperus aethiops Welw. ex Ridl.

P. Tuley 1885 (K001496177)

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Cyperus africanus (S.S. Hooper) Reynders

Pycreus divulsus subsp. africanus S.S. Hooper

No specimens at K nor on GBIF

Total: 1.

Cyperus afro-occidentalis (Lye) Huygh

Kyllinga afro-occidentalis Lye

[H. V. Lehl]; P475; 1930-08-01 [K003206669]

Total: 1.

Cyperus afrorobustus Lye

Kyllinga robusta Boeckeler

J.M. Baker 19 (K001496149)

Total: 3; Lagos 2, Rivers 1.

Cyperus aggregatus var. *aggregatus* —
Introduced

Mariscus aggregatus Willd.

Bels, L 119; 1950-4-16 [U.1286119]

Total: 1.

Cyperus alatus (Nees) F. Muell.

Kyllinga alata Nees

Total: 11; Bauchi 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 1, Yobe 2.

Cyperus alatus subsp. *albus* (Nees) Lye

Kyllinga alba Nees

P.N. de Leeuw 1072A (K001496151)

Total: 11; Bauchi 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 1, Yobe 2.

Cyperus albescens (Steud.) Larridon &
Govaerts

Kyllinga albescens Steud.

J.C. Okafor FHI 59227 (K001496159)

Total: 82; Abia 2, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Enugu 6, Jigawa 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Katsina 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 5, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Plateau 11, Taraba 13.

Cyperus albopilosus (C.B. Clarke) Kük.

Mariscus albopilosus C.B. Clarke

J.B. Hall 1940 (K001496116)

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Cyperus alopecuroides Rottb.

M.G. Latilo FHI 62633 (K001418854)

Total: 3; Borno 1, Kebbi 2.

Cyperus alternifolius L.

Ohaeri A.O.; 1976-12-27 [FHI.101835.0]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Osun 1.

Cyperus alternifolius subsp. *flabelliformis*

Kük.

A.O. Ohaeri 1215 (FHI0101835)

Total: 1.

Cyperus amabilis Vahl

P. Wit, Z.O. Gbile & B.O. Daramola 297

(K001496112)

Total: 51; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 3, Gombe 5, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Niger 4, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus angolensis Boeckeler

F.N. Hepper 1777 (K001496115)

Total: 16; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Cyperus aromaticus (Ridl.) Mattf. & Kük.

Kyllinga aromatica Ridl.

K.A. Kershaw 900654 (K001496136)

Total: 30; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Imo 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Cyperus articulatus L.

Latilo et al. FHI 69415 (K001418855)

Total: 58; Benue 1, Borno 12, Cross River 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kebbi 3, Kogi 5, Lagos 19, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Cyperus ascocapensis Bauters

Platylepis capensis Kunth

R.W. Haines 98 (K001496131)

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Cyperus ascopusillus Goetgh.

Ascolepis pusilla Ridl.

F.N. Hepper 3898 (K001496129)

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Niger 3, Oyo 1.

Cyperus baronii C.B. Clarke

P. Tuley 1992 (K001496097)

Total: 9; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Niger 1, Taraba 3.

Cyperus bifax C.B. Clarke

Literature

Total: 0.

Cyperus blepharoleptos Steud.

B.O. Daramola FHI 072530 (FHI072530-1)

Total: 9; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus brasiliensis (Kunth) Bauters

Platylepis brasiliensis Kunth

R.D. Meikle 1041 (K001496132)

Total: 5; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus brevifolius (Rottb.) Hassk.

Kyllinga brevifolia Rottb.

J. Lowe 2386 (K001496153)

Total: 1.

Cyperus brevifolius var. *brevifolius*

Kyllinga brevifolia Rottb.

J. Lowe 2386 (K001496153)

Total: 1.

Cyperus breviglumis Lye

Kyllinga tisserantii Cherm.

J.B. Hall 561 (K001496145)

Total: 1.

Cyperus buchholzii Boeckeler

J. Lowe 1003 (K001496099)

Total: 4; Abia 1, Cross River 3.

Cyperus bulbosus Vahl

F. Golding 14B (K001418861)

Total: 2; Anambra 1, Borno 1.

Cyperus capillifolius A. Rich.

J.B. Hall 510 (K001496176)

Total: 14; Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Oyo 4, Yobe 1.

Cyperus cataphyllatus (Huygh & Schouppe)

Huygh

Kyllinga cataphyllata Huygh & Schouppe

F.N. Hepper 2097 (K001496155)

Total: 1.

Cyperus cataractarum (C.B. Clarke)

K. Schum. ex Engl.

Pycreus cataractarum C.B. Clarke

J.B. Hall 1866 (K001496172)

Total: 7; Cross River 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus ceylanicus T. Koyama —

Introduced

Hypaelyptum sphacelatum Vahl

Wit P.; Daramola B.O. 2814; 1973-4-20 [78359]1989852068

Total: 28; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 5, Osun 2, Oyo 5.

Cyperus clavinus C.B. Clarke

E. Vogel 64/65 (BM000922477)

Total: 2; Borno 2.

Cyperus compressus L.

J. Lowe 2657 (K001496093)

Total: 36; Abia 1, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Delta 3, Edo 4, Imo 4, Kano 2, Kwara 7, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Cyperus crassipes Vahl

C.F.A. Onochie FHI 33490 (K001496113)

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 7.

Cyperus cuspidatus Kunth

J. Lowe 2506 (K001496111)

Total: 28; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 2.

Cyperus cyperoides (L.) Kuntze

Scirpus cyperoides L.

W.H. Batten-Poole 396 (K001496127)

Total: 193; Abia 2, Anambra 6, Bauchi 2, Benue 6, Borno 1, Cross River 14, Edo 9, Ekiti 2, Enugu 3, Gombe 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 10, Kogi 4, Kwara 9, Lagos 22, Niger 9, Ogun 27, Ondo 13, Oyo 21, Plateau 8, Rivers 1, Taraba 12.

Cyperus denudatus L.f.

C.F.A. Onochie FHI 35711 (K001496109)

Total: 12; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Cyperus difformis L.

M.G. Latilo 80 (K001496102)

Total: 93; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 3, Enugu 4, Gombe 3, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Niger 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Osun 3, Oyo 19, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus diffusus Vahl — Introduced

Onochie, CFA FHI 15537; 1953-4-27

[WAG.1770100]

Total: 49; Abia 3, Cross River 2, Edo 10, Enugu 2, Imo 3, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 8, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Cyperus digitatus Roxb.

Barter C; 1857-01-01 [WAG.U.1286099]

Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 5, Katsina 3, Kogi 2, Niger 4, Ogun 1.

Cyperus digitatus subsp. *auricomus* (Sieber ex Spreng.) Kük.

J.B. Hall 340 (K001418850)

Total: 13; Kaduna 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Niger 3.

Cyperus dilatatus Schumach.

C.D.K. Cook 310 (K001496084)

Total: 113; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Delta 3, Edo 12, Enugu 3, Gombe 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 5, Kebbi 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 3, Lagos 10, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 7, Ondo 4, Osun 3, Oyo 12, Plateau 7, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus dipsacoides (Schumach.) Bauters

Kyllinga dipsacoides Schumach.

F.N. Hepper 3903 (K001496130)

Total: 13; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 4, Oyo 4.

Cyperus distans L.f.

Cyperus elatus Rottb.

R.D. Meikle 1473 (K001496089)

Total: 132; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 4, Borno 2, Cross River 9, Delta 2, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 3, Niger 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 14, Osun 3, Oyo 14, Plateau 16, Rivers 1, Taraba 17.

Cyperus dubius Rottb.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1953-07-18 [FHI.33249.0]

Total: 43; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Jigawa 1, Kano 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 13, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Cyperus dubius var. *dubius*

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall FHI 46502 (K001496117)

Total: 1.

Cyperus elegantulus Steud.

J.B. Hall 1642 (coll. J. Medler) (K001496170)

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Cyperus erectus (Schumach.) Mattf. & Kük.

Kyllinga erecta Schumach.

Brenan JPM; 1947-12-29 [WAG.1770199]

Total: 68; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 5, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Lagos 15, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Cyperus erectus var. *erectus*

Kyllinga erecta Schumach.

J. Lowe 2474 (K001496141)

Total: 1.

Cyperus esculentus L.

J.B. Hall A72 (K001418860)

Total: 83; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Borno 12, Cross River 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Jigawa 2, Kaduna 5,

Katsina 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus exaltatus Retz.

Magbagbeola; Ariwaodo J. O.; Osanyinlusi; Adedeji [FHI.94585.0]

Total: 37; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 2, Borno 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Katsina 4, Kogi 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Cyperus exaltatus var. *exaltatus*

R.W.J. Keay FHI 25901 (K001418851)

Total: 1.

Cyperus fertilis Boeckeler

E. Ujor FHI 23924 (K001496100)

Total: 41; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 16, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Rivers 1.

Cyperus flavescens L.

D.E.S. King 14/74 (K001496181)

Total: 72; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 4, Cross River 9, Kaduna 15, Katsina 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 7, Yobe 1.

Cyperus hamulosus M.Bieb.

A. McClintock 117 (K001496125)

Total: 6; Borno 5.

Cyperus haspan L.

J.P.M. Brenan 8661 (K001496108)

Total: 146; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 9, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 12, Delta 4, Edo 6, Ekiti 3, Enugu 3, Gombe 2, Imo 3, Kaduna 12, Kano 2, Katsina 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 6, Niger 13, Ogun 2, Ondo 6, Oyo 11, Plateau 5, Rivers 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 10, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus hortensis (Salzm. ex Steud.) Dorr

Kyllinga hortensis Salzm. ex Steud.

A. McClintock 192 (K001496148)

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 2.

Cyperus imbricatus Retz.

C.D.K. Cook 307 (K001418852)

Total: 65; Abia 2, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 4, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 14, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Cyperus incompressus C.B. Clarke

P. Wit, Z.O. Gbile & B.O. Daramola FHI 64309 (K001496094)

Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Cyperus iria L.

J. Lowe 4755 (K001496092)

Total: 17; Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Yobe 1.

Cyperus isolepis (Nees) Bauters

Hemicarpha isolepis Nees

J.B. Hall 829 (K001496161)

Total: 4; Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Oyo 1.

Cyperus karlschumannii C.B. Clarke

W.H. Batten-Poole 395 (K001322115)

Total: 7; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 4.

Cyperus kernii (Raymond) Bauters

Scirpus kernii Raymond

J.B. Hall 1462 (K001496162)

Total: 16; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 4, Gombe 2, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5.

Cyperus koyaliensis Cherm.

F.N. Hepper 1259 (K001496090)

Total: 11; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Cyperus kyllingiella Larridon

Kyllinga microcephala Steud.

E.W. Jones 105 (K001496156)

Total: 7; Borno 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 1.

Cyperus laevigatus L.

Wit P.; Daramola B.O.; 1973-04-16 [FHI.78268.0]

Total: 12; Borno 7, Gombe 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Cyperus laevigatus subsp. *laevigatus*

P. Tuley 1133 (K001496120)

Total: 1.

Cyperus lanceolatus Poir.

D.P.M. Guile A4 (K001496174)

Total: 38; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kwara 3, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Cyperus leptorhachis Mattf. & Kük.

Kyllinga debilis C.B. Clarke

D. Clayton DC 1257 (K001496147)

Total: 3; Kaduna 3.

Cyperus leucaspis (J. Raynal) Bauters

Lipocarpha leucaspis J. Raynal

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 238 (K001496163)

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Cyperus ligularis L.

B.O. Daramola FHI 46933 (K001496123)

Total: 36; Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 15, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 5.

Cyperus lipofiliformis Goetgh.

Hypaelyptum filiforme Vahl

J. Blum 2458 (K001496160)

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 2.

Cyperus locuples C.B. Clarke — Endemic

C. Barter 187 (B 10 0166516)

Total: 1.

Cyperus longus L.

Golding, J.S.; 79; 1933-05-03 [K002355559]

Total: 4; Borno 2.

Cyperus longus subsp. *longus*

A.W. Gwynn 116 (K001418857)

Total: 1.

Cyperus macrostachyos Lam.

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 385 (K001496182)

Total: 43; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 6, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Cyperus maculatus Boeckeler

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000019694191]

Total: 45; Benue 1, Borno 8, Cross River 2, Gombe 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Niger 9, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus maculatus subsp. *maculatus*

R.W. Haines 49 (K001418858)

Total: 1.

Cyperus mapanioides C.B. Clarke

P. Wit 2252 (K001496101)

Total: 39; Abia 7, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Enugu 3, Imo 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 7, Osun 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Cyperus margaritaceus Vahl

C.D.K. Cook 499 (K000743803)

Total: 51; Abia 1, Anambra 3, Edo 4, Enugu 14, Kogi 2, Lagos 10, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 4, Sokoto 1.

Cyperus melanospermus (Nees) Valck.Sur.

Kyllinga melanosperma Nees

Hely H.V.; 1929-04-01 [FHI.11222.0]

Total: 6; Bauchi 2, Imo 1, Plateau 2.

Cyperus melanospermus subsp. *melanospermus*

Kyllinga melanosperma Nees

J.G. Okafor FHI 59252 (K001496137)

Total: 1.

Cyperus melas Ridl.

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 620 (K001496175)

Total: 7; Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Niger 2, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1.

Cyperus metzii (Hochst. ex Steud.) Mattf. & Kük.

Kyllinga metzii Hochst. ex Steud.

J.B. Hall 250 (K001496152)

Total: 20; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Cyperus michelianus (L.) Delile

Scirpus michelianus L.

Total: 22; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Oyo 3.

Cyperus microbolbos C.B. Clarke —

Introduced

Hepper F.N. 1528; 1957-12-4 [BR0000026805191V]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Borno 1.

Cyperus mindorensis (Steud.) Huygh

Kyllinga mindorensis Steud.

J.B. Hall 1161 (K001496150)

Total: 17; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 8, Osun 1.

Cyperus mertonii (S.S. Hooper) Lye

Pycnus mertonii S.S. Hooper

D. Gledhill 731 (K001496183)

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Cyperus mundii (Nees) Kunth

Pycnus mundii Nees

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000018189902]

Total: 23; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 10, Kebbi 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2.

Cyperus mundii var. *mundii*

Pycnus mundii Nees

A. McClintock 69 (K001496180)

Total: 1.

Cyperus nduru Cherm.

J.B. Hall 3007 (K001322054)

Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Cyperus neobarteri T. Koyama

Lipocarpha barteri C.B. Clarke

R.W. Haines 21 (K001496158)

Total: 8; Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Oyo 3.

Cyperus nitidus Lam.

A.W. Gwynn 112 (K001496168)

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Oyo 1.

Cyperus niveus Retz.

Total: 50; Adamawa 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 20, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7.

Cyperus niveus var. *leucocephalus* (Kunth) Fosberg

R.W.J. Keay FHI 25772 (K001322125)

Total: 14; Kaduna 4, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Cyperus niveus var. *tisserantii* (Cherm.) Lye

R.D. Meikle 1201 (K001322007)

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Plateau 2.

Cyperus nuerensis Boeckeler

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall FHI 46642 (K001496184)

Total: 3; Plateau 3.

Cyperus obtusatus (J.Presl & C.Presl) Matff. & Kük.

Kyllinga obtusata J.Presl & C.Presl

H.G. Stubbings 57 (K001496140)

Total: 13; Bayelsa 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Niger 1.

Cyperus odoratus L.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1954-10-28 [FHI.34335.0]

Total: 14; Borno 1, Edo 1, Lagos 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1.

Cyperus odoratus subsp. *odoratus*

C.F.A. Onochie FHI 34335 (K001496118)

Total: 1.

Cyperus papyrus L.

R. [Whecher] Harris; 1963-04-07

[BR0000024403948]

Total: 21; Borno 8, Edo 1, Lagos 9.

Cyperus papyrus subsp. *papyrus*

Ejofor, Horne et al. FHI 29400 (K001418849)

Total: 1.

Cyperus pauper Hochst. ex A.Rich.

No specimens at K nor on GBIF

Total: 2; Sokoto 1.

Cyperus pectinatus Vahl

R.W. Haines 229 (K001496119)

Total: 25; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Delta 2, Edo 5, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Osun 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1.

Cyperus pedunculatus (R.Br.) J.Kern

Remirea pedunculata R.Br.

R.W. Haines 25 (K001496166)

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 7.

Cyperus persquarrosus T.Koyama

Lipocarpha pulcherrima Ridl.

J.B. Hall 655 (K001496164)

Total: 5; Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Cyperus podocarpus Boeckeler

D. Clayton DC 1258 (K001496096)

Total: 10; Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Cyperus polystachyos Rottb.

Jones [BR0000018194883]

Total: 57; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 19, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 9, Rivers 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 2.

Cyperus polystachyos var. *polystachyos*

R.D. Meikle 1415 (K001496178)

Total: 7; Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Cyperus prieurianus (Steud.) T.Koyama

Lipocarpha prieuriana Steud.

J.B. Hall 838 (K001496165)

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3.

Cyperus procerus Rottb.

J.B. Hall 436 (K001418856)

Total: 11; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kebbi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus proteus (Welw.) Bauters

Ascolepis protea Welw.

F.N. Hepper 3902 (K001496128)

Total: 33; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Kaduna 9, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 7, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Cyperus pseudodiaphanus (S.S.Hooper) Lye

Pycreus pseudodiaphanus S.S.Hooper

Geerling C.; 1971-10-27 [FHI.46477.0]

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Oyo 2.

Cyperus pseudodiaphanus var. *occidentalis*

(S.S.Hooper) Reynders

Pycreus pseudodiaphanus var. *occidentalis*

S.S.Hooper

G. Jackson & Apejaye 9-12973 (K001496186)

Total: 2; Kaduna 1.

Cyperus pseudodiaphanus var.

pseudodiaphanus

Pycreus pseudodiaphanus S.S.Hooper

R.W. Haines 95 (K001496185)

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1.

Cyperus pulchellus R.Br.

J.M. Dalziel 240 (K001496114)

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Yobe 1.

Cyperus pumilus L.

K.A. Kershaw 900427 (K001496179)

Total: 25; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 3, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 4, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 4.

Cyperus purpureoluteus (Ridl.) Bauters

Lipocarpa purpureolutea Ridl.

E.W. Jones 171 (K001496157)

Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 5, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Cyperus pustulatus Vahl

J. Lowe A46 (K001496095)

Total: 98; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 4, Anambra 1, Bauchi 6, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 15, Katsina 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 10, Ogun 3, Oyo 9, Plateau 11, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Cyperus reduncus Hochst. ex Boeckeler

M.G. Latilo FHI 64640 (K001496103)

Total: 48; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 7, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Zamfara 1.

Cyperus remotispicatus S.S.Hooper

F.N. Hepper 3900 (K001496106)

Total: 3; Edo 1, Niger 1.

Cyperus renschii Boeckeler

H.J. Savory & R.W.J. Keay FHI 24185 (K001496098)

Total: 8; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Osun 2, Plateau 2.

Cyperus richardii Steud.

Kyllinga macrocephala A.Rich.

J. Lowe 2649 (K001496134)

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 1.

Cyperus rotundus L.

J. Lowe 4892 (K001418859)

Total: 82; Abia 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 19, Cross River 4, Edo 4, Gombe 2, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 8, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 11, Plateau 1, Sokoto 3, Zamfara 3.

Cyperus rubidomontanus (Browning)

Larridon

Pycneus rubidomontanus Browning

J.D. Chapman 3575 (FHI0102084-0)

Total: 1.

Cyperus scaettae (Cherm.) Reynders

Pycneus scaettae Cherm.

Cyperus scaettae var. *scaettae*

Pycneus scaettae Cherm.

J.B. Chapman 3735 (K001496171)

Total: 1.

Cyperus sesquiflorus (Torr.) Mattf. & Kük.

Kyllinga sesquiflora Torr.

Kennedy JD; 1944-09-01 [WAG.L.1377879]

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus sesquiflorus subsp. *appendiculatus* (K.Schum.) Lye

Kyllinga appendiculata K.Schum.

J.D.K. ; [7297.0]

Total: 1.

Cyperus sesquiflorus subsp. *cylindricus* (Nees) T.Koyama

Kyllinga cylindrica Nees

D. Clayton DC 1110 (K001496142)

Total: 1.

Cyperus sesquiflorus subsp. *sesquiflorus*

Kyllinga sesquiflora Torr.

J.D. Kennedy FHI 7297 (K001496144)

Total: 1.

Cyperus smithianus Ridl.

J. Lowe 2687 (K001496173)

Total: 13; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Cyperus soyauxii Boeckeler

Onochie C.F.A.; Daggash M.; 1947-05-05

[FHI.21997.0]

Total: 17; Anambra 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Oyo 3, Rivers 3.

Cyperus soyauxii subsp. *soyauxii*

R.W. Haines 210 (K001496124)

Total: 1.

Cyperus sphaelatus Rottb.

R.W. Haines 47 (K001496083)

Total: 90; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 8, Delta 1, Edo 13, Enugu 1, Imo 4, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 6, Lagos 10, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 12, Rivers 5.

Cyperus squarrosus L.

D. Gledhill 656 (K001496126)

Total: 53; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kebbi 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 11, Sokoto 4, Taraba 4.

Cyperus sublimis (C.B.Clarke) Dandy —
Introduced

Mariscus sublimis C.B.Clarke

Kamphorst, A 115; 1960-4-1 [WAG.1765734]

Total: 60; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 4, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 6, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kebbi 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 9, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1.

Cyperus submicrolepis Kük.

Cyperus microlepis Boeckeler

Z.O. Gbile, P. Wit & B.O. Daramola FHI

63400(K001496091)

Total: 15; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kwara 2, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Cyperus tenax Boeckeler

J.M. Dalziel 1114 (K001496110)

Total: 3; Lagos 2, Ogun 1.

Cyperus tenuiculmis Boeckeler

Dalziel J.M. 260; 1909-06-25 (BR0000024426558)

Total: 91; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 8, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 8, Niger 7, Ogun 7, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 20, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Cyperus tenuiculmis var. *guineensis*

(Nelmes) S.S.Hooper

K.A. Kershaw 900680 (K001496088)

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Ondo 1.

Cyperus tenuiculmis var. *schweinfurthianus*

(Boeckeler) S.S.Hooper

D. Clayton DC 1181 (K001496086)

Total: 43; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Taraba 1.

Cyperus tenuiculmis var. *tenuiculmis*

A. Vaillant 877 (K001496087)

Total: 1.

Cyperus tenuifolius (Steud.) Dandy

Kyllinga tenuifolia Steud.

Keay R.W.J.; 1948-05-12 [FHI.22977.0]

Total: 21; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 4, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus tenuis Sw.

K.A. Kershaw 900648 (K001496121)

Total: 88; Abia 5, Anambra 2, Cross River 11, Delta 2, Edo 13, Imo 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 14, Ondo 6, Osun 2, Oyo 16, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Cyperus tenuispica Steud.

A. Vaillant 2778 (K001496105)

Total: 12; Abia 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Rivers 1, Yobe 1.

Cyperus testui (Cherm.) Reynders

Pycreus testui Cherm.

P. Wit, Z.O. Gbile & B.O. Daramola 2055

(K001496167)

Total: 6; Oyo 2, Taraba 3.

Cyperus tibialis (Poit. ex Ledeb.) Govaerts

Kyllinga tibialis Poit. ex Ledeb.

Barter 1849 [K003206324]

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Cyperus tisserantioides (Mtot.) Lye

Kyllinga tisserantioides Mtot.

J. Lowe 2497 (K001496146)

Total: 1.

Cyperus tomaiophyllus K.Schum.

P. Tuley 468 (K001496122)

Total: 7; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Plateau 1.

Cyperus tonkinensis C.B.Clarke

Wit P.; 1972-05-07 [FHI.66674.0]

Total: 8; Niger 4, Taraba 1.

Cyperus tonkinensis var. *baikiei* (C.B.Clarke
ex Kük.) S.S.Hooper

P. Wit, Z.O. Gbile & B.O. Daramola FHI 66674

(K001496091)(K001418796)

Total: 6; Niger 3.

Cyperus tuberosus Willd. ex Kunth

Latilo M.G. ; 1987-04-08 [21001.0]

Total: 14; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 8, Taraba 1.

Cyperus uniolooides R.Br.

Latilo & Taylor FHI 43398 (K001496169)

Total: 7; Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cyperus ustulatus A.Rich. — Introduced

DR A.B. Kadiri; others; 2011-9-10 [4152]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Cyperus welwitschii (Ridl.) Lye

Kyllinga welwitschii Ridl.

J.R. Charaer FHI 38784 (FHI0038784)

Total: 6; Borno 2, Cross River 1, Oyo 1, Yobe 1.

Cyperus zollingeri Steud.

L. Bels 38 (U.1286047)

Total: 3; Benue 1, Lagos 1.

Diplacrum africanum (Benth.) C.B.Clarke

Scleria africana Benth.
F.N. Hepper 1239 (K000874246)
Total: 16; Adamawa 4, Edo 2, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Diplacrum capitatum (Willd.) Boeckeler

Scleria capitata Willd.
J.B. Hall UIH 16813 (K000874245)
Total: 9; Edo 2, Lagos 4.

Eleocharis acutangula (Roxb.) Schult.

Scirpus acutangulus Roxb.
Davey J.T.; 1949-11-20 [FHI.27104.0]
Total: 19; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2.

Eleocharis acutangula subsp. *acutangula*

Scirpus acutangulus Roxb.
C.F.A. Onochie FHI 35794 (K001418792)
Total: 6; Anambra 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

Eleocharis atropurpurea (Retz.) J.Presl & C.Presl

Scirpus atropurpureus Retz.
P. Wit & Z.O. Gbile 965 (K001418796)
Total: 4; Edo 2.

Eleocharis brainii Svenson

D. Clayton DC 1508 (FHI0042003)
Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Eleocharis complanata Boeckeler

J.B. Hall 831 (K001418798)
Total: 17; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Eleocharis confervoides (Poir.) Steud.

Scirpus confervoides Poir.
C.F.A. Onochie FHI 34310 (K001418801)
Total: 4; Edo 4.

Eleocharis dulcis (Burm.f.) Trin. ex Hensch.

Andropogon dulcis Burm.f.
O.B. Lean 104 (K001418795)
Total: 8; Edo 6.

Eleocharis geniculata (L.) Roem. & Schult.

Scirpus geniculatus L.
R.W. Haines 22 (K001418797)
Total: 21; Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 3, Ondo 1, Rivers 2.

Eleocharis minima Kunth

Clayton, D. Dc 1508; 1958-02-01 [K002423886]
Total: 1.

Eleocharis mutata (L.) Roem. & Schult.

Scirpus mutatus L.

B. Anderson 1411 (K001418793)
Total: 4; Plateau 1.

Eleocharis naumanniana Boeckeler

Lowe J.; 1967-02-17 [FHI.27367.0]
Total: 7; Edo 5, Imo 1.

Eleocharis naumanniana var. *naumanniana*

J. Lowe 2459 (K001418799)
Total: 1.

Eleocharis setifolia (A.Rich.) J.Raynal

Isolepis setifolia A.Rich.
Clayton W.D.; 1957-08-01 [FHI.39846.0]
Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Eleocharis setifolia subsp. *schweinfurthiana*

(Boeckeler) D.A.Simpson
Eleocharis schweinfurthiana Boeckeler
D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 442 (K001418800)
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Eleocharis setifolia subsp. *setifolia*

Isolepis setifolia A.Rich.
No specimens at K nor on GBIF
Total: 0.

Eleocharis variegata (Poir.) C.Presl

Scirpus variegatus Poir.
J. B. Hall 925 (K001418794)
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Edo 2.

Fimbristylis albiviridis C.B.Clarke

C.F.A. Onochie FHI 34225 (K001418818)
Total: 10; Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Ondo 7.

Fimbristylis aphylla Steud.

D. Gledhill 629 (K001418824)
Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Fimbristylis barteri Boeckeler

R.W.J. Keay FHI 25899 (FHI0025899)
Total: 5; Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Fimbristylis bisumbellata (Forssk.) Bubani

Scirpus bisumbellatus Forssk.
P. Wit et al. 1645 (K001418819)
Total: 19; Bauchi 4, Borno 2, Gombe 3, Kogi 1, Niger 4, Ondo 3.

Fimbristylis complanata (Retz.) Link

Scirpus complanatus Retz.
R.W. Haines 82 (K001418826)
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Fimbristylis cymosa R.Br.

Killick, H.J.; 85; 1956-01-02 [K002803927]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 7, Ondo 1.

Fimbristylis cymosa subsp. *cymosa*

K. Moody UIH 15035 (K001418826)

Total: 3.

Fimbristylis debilis Steud.

Grove 2 (K001418830)

Total: 2; Katsina 1, Oyo 1.

Fimbristylis dichotoma (L.) Vahl

Scirpus dichotomus L.

Herbarium Wildlife Staff. [FHI.91609.0]

Total: 255; Abia 5, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 4, Bauchi 7, Benue 9, Borno 5, Cross River 27, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 15, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Imo 4, Kaduna 9, Kano 1, Katsina 3, Kebbi 2, Kogi 9, Kwara 8, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 23, Ogun 12, Ondo 14, Osun 1, Oyo 23, Plateau 13, Rivers 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 19, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Fimbristylis dichotoma subsp. *dichotoma*

Scirpus dichotomus L.

F.N. Hepper 1639 (K001418816)

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Fimbristylis dichotoma subsp. *podocarpa*

(Nees) T.Koyama

Fimbristylis podocarpa Nees

P.N. de Leeuw 1211B (K001418817)

Total: 1.

Fimbristylis dichotoma var. *dichotoma*

Scirpus dichotomus L.

Tuley P; Magaji SO; 1969-09-25 [WAG.1764143]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Fimbristylis dipsacea (Rottb.) C.B.Clarke

Scirpus dipsaceus Rottb.

Eimunjeze;Ekwuno;Onijamowo; 1973-03-22 [FHI.70395.0]

Total: 4; Kogi 2, Ogun 1.

Fimbristylis dipsacea var. *dipsacea*

Scirpus dipsaceus Rottb.

Eimunjeze et al. FHI 70395 (K001418814)

Total: 1.

Fimbristylis ferruginea (L.) Vahl

Scirpus ferrugineus L.

R.W. Haines 14 (K001418821)

Total: 17; Bayelsa 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 7, Rivers 2.

Fimbristylis littoralis Gaudich.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1956-08-19 [FHI.35420.0]

Total: 18; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Rivers 3.

Fimbristylis littoralis var. *littoralis*

H.M. Schmidt et al. 2226 (K001418822)

Total: 1.

Fimbristylis microcarya F.Muell.

[D. P. M. Guile]; A3; 1966-10-01 [K002803975]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Oyo 1.

Fimbristylis microcarya var. *microcarya*

D.P.M. Guile A17 (K001418829)

Total: 1.

Fimbristylis nigritana C.B.Clarke

Barter 623 (K000416652)

Total: 2; Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Fimbristylis pilosa Vahl

R.W. Haines 220 (K001418820)

Total: 44; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Edo 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 14, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Fimbristylis quinquangularis (Vahl) Kunth

Scirpus quinquangularis Vahl

Lowe J.; 1971-01-17 [FHI.27480.0]

Total: 9; Edo 3, Gombe 3, Osun 1.

Fimbristylis quinquangularis subsp.

quinquangularis

Scirpus quinquangularis Vahl

P. Tuley 19 (K001418823)

Total: 2; Osun 1.

Fimbristylis scabrida Schumach.

B.O. Daramola FHI 62977 (K001418825)

Total: 56; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 3, Kaduna 13, Kogi 3, Niger 9, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 8, Sokoto 1.

Fimbristylis schoenoides (Retz.) Vahl

Scirpus schoenoides Retz.

J. Lowe 2632 (FHI0061003)

Total: 3; Abia 2, Ebonyi 1.

Fimbristylis squarrosa Vahl

Barter C; 1857-01-01 [WAG.U.1239772]

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Kano 1, Niger 6.

Fimbristylis squarrosa var. *squarrosa*

J.B. Hall 1133 (K001418815)

Total: 1.

Fuirena ciliaris (L.) Roxb.

Scirpus ciliaris L.
O. Hagerup; 1927-12-03 [US 1596680]
Total: 10; Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 2,
Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1.

Fuirena ciliaris f. *ciliaris*
Scirpus ciliaris L.
R.W. Haines 90 (K001418790)
Total: 1.

Fuirena leptostachya Oliv.
J. & A. Raynal 5344 (K000391970)
Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Fuirena leptostachya f. *leptostachya*
B. Moisie 157 (K000416805)
Total: 1.

Fuirena leptostachya f. *nudiflora* Lye
Moiser; 1921-12-13 [K000416805]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1.

Fuirena stricta Steud.
Barter C; 1857-01-01 [WAG.U.1285162]
Total: 24; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross
River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Plateau
4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 7.

Fuirena stricta subsp. *chlorocarpa* (Ridl.)
Lye
F.N. Hepper 1772 (K001418789)
Total: 7; Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Fuirena stricta subsp. *stricta*
R.W. Haines 68 (K001418788)
Total: 1.

Fuirena umbellata Rottb.
Z.O. Gbile 511 (K001418791)
Total: 167; Abia 3, Adamawa 5, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1,
Bayelsa 2, Benue 4, Borno 2, Cross River 8, Delta 4,
Edo 16, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 3, Kogi 8,
Kwara 9, Lagos 8, Niger 6, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 2,
Oyo 16, Plateau 15, Rivers 4, Taraba 9, Zamfara 1.

Hypolytrum heteromorphum Nelmel
J.O. Ariwaodo UFH 292 (FHI092536-1)
Total: 10; Abia 3, Cross River 3, Delta 1.

Hypolytrum purpurascens Cherm. —
Introduced
Kennedy JD; 1936-01-01 [WAG.1764495]
Total: 25; Abia 2, Cross River 2, Edo 9, Kaduna 1,
Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1.

Hypolytrum testui Cherm.
J.P.M. Brenan et al. 9216 (K000874250)
Total: 1.

Isolepis fluitans (L.) R.Br.
Scirpus fluitans L.
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Isolepis fluitans var. *fluitans*
Scirpus fluitans L.
J.B. Hall 1630 (K001418802)
Total: 1.

Machaerina articulata (R.Br.) T.Koyama —
Introduced
Cladium articulatum R.Br.
Osakwe A. O.; 1982-5-15 [1222]3808439442
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 2.

Mapania amplivaginata K.Schum.
J.P.M. Brenan 9250 (K000874248)
Total: 13; Abia 1, Cross River 11.

Mapania rhynchocarpa Lorougnon &
Raynal
P.W. Richards 5148 (K000874249)
Total: 6; Abia 2, Cross River 1.

Microdracoides squamosa Hua
R. Catterall s.n. (K000874247)
Total: 2; Cross River 1, Lagos 1.

Rhynchospora brevirostris Griseb.
F.N. Hepper 1247 (K001418785)
Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Rhynchospora candida (Nees) Boeckeler
Psilocarya candida Nees
K.A. Kershaw 900319 (K001418782)
Total: 6; Kaduna 4, Zamfara 1.

Rhynchospora corymbosa (L.) Britton
Scirpus corymbosus L.
F.N. Hepper 1741 (K001418780)
Total: 115; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2,
Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 5, Bauchi 3,
Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 8, Delta 2, Edo 3, Ekiti
1, Enugu 8, Kaduna 10, Kwara 2, Lagos 9, Niger 2,
Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 16, Plateau 11, Rivers 1, Taraba
6.

Rhynchospora eximia (Nees) Boeckeler
Spermodon eximius Nees
Z.O. Gbile 510 (K001418783)
Total: 25; Cross River 1, Delta 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5,
Kwara 4, Niger 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Rhynchospora gracillima Thwaites
Total: 1; Niger 1, Plateau 3.

Rhynchospora gracillima subsp.
subquadrata (Cherm.) J.Raynal

- R.W. Haines 97 (K001418784)
Total: 5; Niger 1, Plateau 2.
- Rhynchospora perrieri* Cherm.
C.F.A. Onochie FHI 35797 (K001418786)
Total: 5; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1.
- Rhynchospora rubra* (Lour.) Makino
Schoenus ruber Lour.
Total: 1; Lagos 1.
- Rhynchospora rubra* subsp. *africana*
J.Raynal
R. Samowicz s.n. (K001418778)
Total: 2; Lagos 1.
- Rhynchospora rugosa* (Vahl) Gale
Schoenus rugosus Vahl
Hepper F.N.; 1958-01-27 [FHI.53382.0]
Total: 7; Ondo 1, Taraba 5.
- Rhynchospora rugosa* subsp. *brownii*
(Roem. & Schult.) T.Koyama
Rhynchospora laxa R.Br.
R.W. Haines 231 (K001418787)
Total: 1.
- Rhynchospora triflora* Vahl
J. Lowe 2283 (K001418781)
Total: 5; Edo 3, Oyo 1.
- Schoenoplectiella articulata* (L.) Lye
Scirpus articulatus L.
J.M. Dalziel 242 (K001418803)
Total: 5; Borno 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.
- Schoenoplectiella brachyceras* (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) J.R.Starr & Jim.Mejías
Scirpus brachyceras Hochst. ex A.Rich.
R.W.J. Keay FHI 21441 (K001418809)
Total: 1.
- Schoenoplectiella corymbosa* (Roth ex Roem. & Schult.) J.R.Starr & Jim.Mejías
Isolepis corymbosa Roth ex Roem. & Schult.
O.B. Lean 7 (K001418810)
Total: 11; Niger 1, Osun 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.
- Schoenoplectiella erecta* (Poir.) Lye
Scirpus erectus Poir.
Total: 1.
- Schoenoplectiella erecta* subsp. *erecta*
Scirpus erectus Poir.
G. Jackson 2574 (K001418811)
Total: 1.
- Schoenoplectiella juncea* (Willd.) Lye
Schoenus junceus Willd.
F. Golding 30 (K001418812)
Total: 1.
- Schoenoplectiella lateriflora* (J.F.Gmel.) Lye
Scirpus lateriflorus J.F.Gmel.
J.M. Dalziel 1307 (K001418813)
Total: 3; Lagos 1.
- Schoenoplectiella mucronata* (L.) J.Jung & H.K.Choi
Scirpus mucronatus L.
J.B. Hall 1692 (K001418805)
Total: 2; Plateau 1.
- Schoenoplectiella muricinux* (C.B.Clarke) J.R.Starr
Scirpus muricinux C.B.Clarke
D.E.S. King s.n. (K001418806)
Total: 2.
- Schoenoplectiella oxyjulos* (S.S.Hooper) Lye
Scirpus oxyjulos S.S.Hooper
R.W.J. Keay FHI 20127 (K001418807)
Total: 2; Kaduna 2.
- Schoenoplectiella praelongata* (Poir.) Lye
— Introduced
Scirpus praelongatus Poir.
D.W. [Lawlan]& J.B. Hall 622; 1962-8-31 [BR0000025727531V]
Total: 11; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Yobe 1.
- Schoenoplectiella roylei* (Nees) Lye
Isolepis roylei Nees
P.N. de Leeuw 1337 (K001418808)
Total: 1; Borno 1.
- Schoenoplectiella senegalensis* (Steud.) Lye
Isolepis senegalensis Steud.
N. Johnston 88 (K001418804)
Total: 17; Bauchi 4, Borno 4, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Oyo 2.
- Scirpus atrovirens* Willd. — Introduced
Bailey Wm.M.; Julius R. Swayne 727; 1949-6-21 [80722]1989852191
Total: 1; Kaduna 1.
- Scleria achtenii* De Wild.
R.W. Haines 77 (K001418766)
Total: 4; Edo 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.
- Scleria boivinii* Steud.
J. Lowe 4255 (K001418773)

Total: 16; Anambra 3, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Ogun 1.

Scleria bulbifera Hochst. ex A.Rich.

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 561 (K000874239)

Total: 52; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 3, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 12, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Niger 16, Plateau 4, Sokoto 2, Taraba 3.

Scleria catophylla C.B.Clarke

Scleria hirtella var. *aterrima* Ridl.

C.F.A. Onochie FHI33474 (K000874241)

Total: 8; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2.

Scleria depressa (C.B.Clarke) Nelmes

Scleria racemosa var. *depressa* C.B.Clarke

K.A. Kershaw 900024 (K001418769)

Total: 63; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 4, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Scleria distans Poir.

Kershaw, K.A.; 900713; 1964-08-31 [K002785577]

Total: 11; Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1.

Scleria distans var. *distans*

R.W.J. Keay FHI22559 (K000874240)

Total: 1.

Scleria foliosa Hochst. ex A.Rich.

H.V. Lely P445 (K000874236)

Total: 30; Bauchi 4, Borno 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 10, Katsina 1, Osun 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Scleria gaertneri Raddi

R.E. Okeke FHI 38444 (K001418772)

Total: 3; Anambra 1, Niger 1.

Scleria globonux C.B.Clarke

J.M. Dalziel 238 (K000874232)

Total: 2.

Scleria gracillima Boeckeler

D. Gledhill 732 (K000874231)

Total: 4; Niger 2, Oyo 2.

Scleria iostephana Nelmes

J. Olorunfemi FHI 55663 (K000455466)

Total: 12; Delta 1, Kaduna 7, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 2.

Scleria lacustris C.Wright

Literature

Total: 0.

Scleria lagoensis Boeckeler

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 712 (K001418774)

Total: 33; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Scleria lithosperma (L.) Sw.

Scirpus lithospermus L.

Alan Philip Dalby Jones, Ronald William John Keay, Charles Francis Akado Onochie; 1945-11-01 [BM013839832]

Total: 4; Kaduna 2, Ogun 1.

Scleria lithosperma var. *lithosperma*

Scirpus lithospermus L.

L.U. Egbuta FHI 30254 (FHI0030254)

Total: 1.

Scleria melanomphala Kunth

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 729 (K001418770)

Total: 26; Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 4, Taraba 5.

Scleria melanotricha Hochst. & A.Rich.

H.V. Lely P439 (K000874242)

Total: 10; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1.

Scleria mikawana Makino

B.A. Oso 18 (K000874235)

Total: 2; Rivers 1.

Scleria naumanniana Boeckeler

J. Lowe 2364 (K001418771)

Total: 60; Abia 4, Anambra 8, Cross River 8, Delta 4, Edo 5, Enugu 2, Imo 5, Kaduna 3, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Rivers 4.

Scleria pergracilis (Nees) Kunth

Hypoporum pergracile Nees

F.N. Hepper 1241 (K000874244)

Total: 24; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Scleria pooides Ridl.

B. Sinsin 3194 (K001324506)

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Scleria schimperiana Boeckeler

P.N. de Leeuw 1387A (K000874237)

Total: 3; Yobe 1.

Scleria tessellata Willd.

Barter [K000363315]

Total: 28; Adamawa 3, Borno 1, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Yobe 2.

Scleria tessellata var. *sphaerocarpa*

E.A. Rob.

F.N. Hepper 1246 (K000874233)

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1.

Scleria tessellata var. *tessellata*

F.N. Hepper 3883 (K000874234)

Total: 2.

Scleria tricholepis Nelmes

D.W. Lawlor & J.B. Hall 621 (K000874243)

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Scleria verrucosa Willd.

R.W. Haines 89 (K001418767)

Total: 28; Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Scleria vogelii C.B. Clarke

B. Anderson s.n. (K001418768)

Total: 10; Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 6.

Scleria woodii C.B. Clarke

K.A. Kershaw 900612 (K000874238)

Total: 31; Benue 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 8, Katsina 2, Plateau 7, Taraba 4.

FLAGELLARIACEAE

Flagellaria guineensis Schumach.

Coombe D.E. 115; 1955-2-26 [BR0000024729956]

Total: 14; Delta 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 2, Osun 1.

Flagellaria indica L. — Introduced

Obalola Yusuf; 2013-7-7 [5906] [3808438386]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

POACEAE

Acritochaete volkensii Pilg.

Magaji et al. s.n., 1968, K

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Acroceras amplexans Stapf

Freeman S144, 1947, K

Total: 22; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Acroceras gabunense (Hack.) Clayton

Panicum gabunense Hack.

Latilo 34016, 1960, K

Total: 2; Kogi 1, Ogun 1.

Acroceras zizanioides (Kunth) Dandy

Panicum zizanioides Kunth

Jackson 219968, 1968, K

Total: 16; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 7, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Adenochloa ecklonii (Nees) Zuloaga

Panicum ecklonii Nees

Gbile & Daramola 63281, 1970, K

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Taraba 4.

Adenochloa hymeniocchila (Nees) Zuloaga

Panicum hymeniocchilum Nees

Tuley 1868, 1969, K

Total: 4; Osun 1, Zamfara 2.

Aira caryophyllea L.

Tuley 2024, 1969, K

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Taraba 3.

Alloteropsis angusta Stapf

de Leeuw 1808, 1966, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Alloteropsis cimicina (L.) Stapf

Milium cimicinum L.

de Leeuw 1031, 1964, K

Total: 5; Borno 1, Katsina 2, Yobe 2.

Alloteropsis paniculata (Benth.) Stapf

Urochloa paniculata Benth.

Wright 59, 1952, K

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Kogi 4, Niger 1.

Alloteropsis semialata (R.Br.) Hitchc.

Panicum semialatum R.Br.

Keay FHI22948, 1948, K

Total: 17; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Kwara 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Alloteropsis semialata subsp. *semialata*

Panicum semialatum R.Br.

Geerling, C 2609; 1968-4-21 [PRE0960588-0]

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Anadelphia afzeliana (Rendle) Stapf

Andropogon afzelianus Rendle

Lawlor & Hall 641, 1962, K

Total: 26; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 3, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 6.

Anadelphia leptocoma (Trin.) Pilg.

Andropogon leptocomus Trin.

Anderson 1379, 1964, K

Total: 9; Bayelsa 1, Lagos 5, Oyo 3.

Anatherum africanum (Franch.) Roberty

Andropogon africanus Franch.

Lely, H.V. 758; 1930-09-01 K003091919

Total: 12; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2.

Andropogon africanus Franch.

Jackson 2362, 1959, K

Total: 15; Ekiti 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 8.

Andropogon amethystinus Steud.

Gambles 26a, no date, K

Total: 1.

Andropogon auriculatus Stapf

Tuley 491, 1964, K

Total: 16; Abia 4, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Andropogon canaliculatus Schumach.

Ward L139, 1950, K

Total: 4; Benue 1.

Andropogon chinensis (Nees) Merr.

Homoeatherum chinense Nees

Keay FHI21422, 1947, K

Total: 34; Bauchi 6, Borno 1, Kaduna 7, Kwara 3, Niger 2, Oyo 12.

Andropogon distachyos L.

Boughey, A.S. 10621 [K003092945]

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Andropogon gayanus Kunth

Keay FHI37295, 1957, K

Total: 198; Adamawa 5, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 6, Bauchi 16, Benue 4, Borno 9, Cross River 1, Delta 3, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 12, Kano 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 16, Lagos 2, Niger 24, Ogun 9, Ondo 1, Oyo 15, Plateau 8, Rivers 1, Taraba 5, Yobe 1, Zamfara 6.

Andropogon macrophyllus Stapf

Magaji & Tuley 1767, 1969, K

Total: 11; Enugu 2, Lagos 5, Oyo 3.

Andropogon perligulatus Stapf

Clayton 369, 1955, K

Total: 16; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Niger 3.

Andropogon pseudapricus Stapf

Andropogon apricus var. *africanus* Hack.

Keay 5440, 1947, K

Total: 78; Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 1, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 13, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Niger 19, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Sokoto 5, Yobe 2.

Andropogon pusillus Hook.f.

Tuley 2054, 1969, K

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Andropogon schirensis Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Jackson 2366, 1959, K

Total: 90; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 14, Kebbi 3, Kogi 5, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 7, Oyo 7, Plateau 9, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Andropogon schweinfurthii Hack.

MG 263; 1968-10-24 [K002286726]

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Niger 1.

Andropogon tectorum Schumach. & Thonn.

Hubbard S579, 1948, K

Total: 120; Anambra 8, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 8, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Lagos 10, Niger 8, Ogun 15, Ondo 7, Osun 6, Oyo 17, Plateau 7, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Andropogon tenuiberbis Hack.

Jackson 2335, 1959, K

Total: 13; Imo 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 6.

Antheaphora ampullacea Stapf & C.E.Hubb.

Keay FHI22277, 1947, K

Total: 7; Anambra 2, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kogi 1.

Antheaphora cristata (Döll) Hack. ex De Wild. & T.Durand

Antheaphora elegans var. *cristata* Döll

Dawodu 17, 1899, K

Total: 7; Lagos 6, Ogun 1.

Antheaphora nigritana Stapf & C.E.Hubb.

Latilo FHI62751, 1969, K

Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Kano 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Niger 5, Oyo 1, Sokoto 3, Yobe 1.

Antheaphora pubescens Nees

O. Hagerup 635; 1927-12-1 [US 1448022]

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Anthoxanthum nivale K.Schum.

W.de Wilde cs.9139; 1965-12-4 [75997]

[1989899349]

Total: 1.

Aristida adscensionis L.

Freeman S129, 1947, K

Total: 35; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 7, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Aristida cumingiana Trin. & Rupr.

Hepper 1175, 1957, K

Total: 8; Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 3.

Aristida funiculata Trin. & Rupr.

de Leeuw 2074, 1968, K

Total: 3; Kaduna 1.

Aristida hordeacea Kunth

Keay FHI21137, 1947, K

Total: 29; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Borno 8, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Niger 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4, Yobe 1.

Aristida junciformis Trin. & Rupr.

Tuley 2030, 1969, K

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Aristida kerstingii Pilg.

Olorunfemi FHI24366, no date, K

Total: 24; Adamawa 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Aristida kunthiana Trin. & Rupr.

Denys E. 702; 1982-7-12 [BR0000021849091]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Aristida mutabilis Trin. & Rupr.

Golding 15, no date, K

Total: 9; Bauchi 2, Borno 5, Yobe 1.

Aristida recta Franch.

Daramola FHI40600, 1959, K

Total: 14; Abia 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Aristida sieberiana Trin.

Meikle 807, 1949, K

Total: 25; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 4, Kano 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Sokoto 2.

Aristida stipoides Lam.

Clayton 1380, 1957, K

Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Sokoto 2, Yobe 4.

Arthraxon hispidus (Thunb.) Makino

Phalaris hispida Thunb.

Tuley 1029, 1964, K

Total: 11; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Arthraxon lancifolius (Trin.) Hochst.

Andropogon lancifolius Trin.

Clayton 1305, 1957, K

Total: 9; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 2.

Arundinella pumila (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Steud.

Acratherum pumilum Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Chapman 2621, 1971, K

Total: 5; Nasarawa 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Arundo donax L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Axonopus compressus (Sw.) P.Beauv. —

Introduced

Milium compressum Sw.

Brenan 8976, 1948, K

Total: 28; Edo 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 15, Plateau 1.

Axonopus flexuosus (Peter) Troupin

Digitaria flexuosa Peter

Tuley 988, 1964, K

Total: 24; Anambra 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Niger 1, Osun 1, Plateau 2, Rivers 5.

Bambusa bambos (L.) Voss — Introduced

Arundo bambos L.

Oderinde A.A; 1988-1-4 [1392A]3808442634

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Bambusa vulgaris Schrad. ex J.C.Wendl. —

Introduced

Onochie FHI8215, 1945, K

Total: 28; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Benue 2, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 5, Plateau 3.

Bewsia biflora (Hack.) Gooss.

Diplachne biflora Hack.

Tuley 1643, 1969, K

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Bothriochloa bladhii (Retz.) S.T.Blake

Andropogon bladhii Retz.

Lowe 4397, 1983, K

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Yobe 1.

Bothriochloa insculpta (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

A.Camus

Andropogon insculptus Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Lowe 4939, 1991, K

Total: 2; Enugu 1, Oyo 1.

Brachypodium flexum Nees

Tuley 2035, 1969, K

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Cenchrus americanus (L.) Morrone

Panicum americanum L.

Okere NGT0082, 2016, K

Total: 80; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 8, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 15, Kano 1, Katsina

11, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 4, Taraba 1.

Cenchrus biflorus Roxb.

Clayton 436, 1955, K

Total: 71; Bauchi 2, Borno 18, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Gombe 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 7, Kogi 7, Kwara 4, Lagos 14, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Sokoto 4, Zamfara 1.

Cenchrus caudatus (Schrad.) Kuntze

Gymnotrix caudata Schrad.

Chapman 5136, 1977, K

Total: 10; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Cenchrus ciliaris L.

Daggash FHI24963, 1950, K

Total: 14; Borno 6, Edo 1, Oyo 5.

Cenchrus clandestinus (Hochst. ex Chiov.)

Morrone — Introduced

Pennisetum clandestinum Hochst. ex Chiov.

Wheeler Haines 366, 1965, K

Total: 9; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 2, Taraba 2.

Cenchrus divisus (J.F.Gmel.) Verloove,

Govaerts & Buttler

Panicum divisum J.F.Gmel.

Wit, P. 2798065;1971-09-16 [1304324372]

Total: 1.

Cenchrus echinatus L. — Introduced

Wheeler Haines 183, 1962, K

Total: 6; Borno 1, Lagos 4.

Cenchrus geniculatus Thunb.

Jackson, J.K.; Magaji, S.O.; Tuley, P. 2099; 1969-11-19 [K002202114]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Cenchrus hordeoides (Lam.) Morrone

Panicum hordeoides Lam.

Gambles 13, 1960, K

Total: 18; Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Cenchrus laxius (Clayton) Zon

Beckeropsis laxior Clayton

Savory & Keay FHI25448, 1949, K

Total: 15; Kaduna 1, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 7.

Cenchrus monostigma (Pilg.) Morrone

Pennisetum monostigma Pilg.

Tuley 2098, 1969, K

Total: 4; Adamawa 2, Taraba 2.

Cenchrus pedicellatus (Trin.) Morrone

Pennisetum pedicellatum Trin.

Clayton 301, 1955, K

Total: 143; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Adamawa 5, Bauchi 7, Benue 1, Borno 16, Delta 1, Gombe 4, Kaduna 14, Kano 4, Katsina 9, Kogi 3, Kwara 8, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 9, Oyo 3, Plateau 10, Sokoto 3, Taraba 3, Yobe 1, Zamfara 8.

Cenchrus pedicellatus subsp. *pedicellatus*

Pennisetum pedicellatum Trin.

Cenchrus polystachios subsp. *atrichus*

(Stapf & C.E.Hubb.) Morrone

Panicum polystachion L.

KZOG. 233; 1979-10-10 [FHI91646] 1914118089

Total: 1.

Cenchrus prieurii (Kunth) Maire

Pennisetum prieurii Kunth

Butler S107, 1947, K

Total: 2; Jigawa 1.

Cenchrus purpureus (Schumach.) Morrone

Pennisetum purpureum Schumach.

Blair Raines 204, 1974, K

Total: 102; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 7, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 15, Plateau 10, Rivers 1, Taraba 12.

Cenchrus ramosus (Hochst.) Morrone

Gymnotrix ramosa Hochst.

Davey FHI27111, 1949, K

Total: 15; Borno 5, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 2.

Cenchrus setaceus (Forssk.) Morrone

Phalaris setacea Forssk.

hafsatdarma0714; 2017-10-20 [1699368431]

Total: 1.

Cenchrus setigerus Vahl

Simpson 12, 1938, K

Total: 1.

Cenchrus setosus Sw.

Lely 439, 1930, K

Total: 55; Adamawa 2, Anambra 4, Borno 2, Edo 1, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 5, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Ogun 3, Oyo 12, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Cenchrus setosus subsp. *setosus*

Eijnatten CLM van [WAG.1395894]

Total: 39; Adamawa 2, Anambra 4, Edo 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 4, Kebbi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Cenchrus sieberianus (Schltdl.) Verloove

Penicillaria sieberiana Schldl.
 Barter 1376; -- [K000281302]
 Total: 6; Borno 3, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Cenchrus unisetus (Nees) Morrone
 Gymnotrix unisetata Nees
 Latilo FHI36689, 1957, K
 Total: 72; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 7,
 Cross River 3, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 13,
 Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 1,
 Oyo 7, Plateau 6, Taraba 2.

Cenchrus violaceus (Lam.) Morrone
 Panicum violaceum Lam.
 de Leeuw 2047, 1968, K
 Total: 25; Borno 17, Kano 1.

Centotheca lappacea (L.) Desv.
 Cenchrus lappaceus L.
 Latilo & Oguntayo 67794, 1973, K
 Total: 65; Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 9,
 Edo 11, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Lagos 3, Niger 3, Ogun 5,
 Osun 2, Oyo 12, Plateau 1.

Chasmopodium caudatum (Hack.) Stapf
 Rottboellia caudata Hack.
 Jackson 119968, 1968, K
 Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1,
 Lagos 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Chloris barbata Sw.
 Wheeler Haines 160, 1962, K
 Total: 8; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5.

Chloris gayana Kunth
 Scholz 130, 1969, K
 Total: 10; Borno 3, Niger 1, Oyo 3.

Chloris pilosa Schumacher.
 Holland 274, 1900, K
 Total: 60; Abia 2, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 4, Borno 10,
 Delta 1, Enugu 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 3, Kwara
 3, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 2, Sokoto
 1, Yobe 1.

Chloris pycnothrix Trin.
 Lawlor & Hall FHI46593, 1962, K
 Total: 20; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2,
 Kaduna 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Chloris robusta Stapf
 Keay FHI25642, 1950, K
 Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
 Adamawa 1, Gombe 2, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7,
 Ogun 3, Osun 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Chloris virgata Sw.
 de Leeuw 2072, 1968, K

Total: 5; Enugu 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Chrysochloa hindsii C.E.Hubb.
 de Leeuw 1573, 1965, K
 Total: 1.

Chrysopogon aciculatus (Retz.) Trin. —
 Introduced
 Andropogon aciculatus Retz.
 Gledhill 628, 1967, K
 Total: 9; Borno 1, Lagos 5, Oyo 3.

Chrysopogon fulvibarbis (Trin.) Veldkamp
 Andropogon fulvibarbis Trin.
 Latilo, MG FHI 61420; 1971-10-28 [WAG.1566803]
 Total: 7; Adamawa 4, Niger 2.

Chrysopogon nigritanus (Benth.) Veldkamp
 Andropogon nigritanus Benth.
 Geerling, C 3949; 1971-8-12 [WAG.1453004]
 Total: 69; Adamawa 6, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Borno
 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 5, Kebbi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 1,
 Niger 18, Ogun 4, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba
 2, Yobe 2.

Chrysopogon zizanioides (L.) Roberty —
 Introduced
 Phalaris zizanioides L.
 Umar Musa 2023-10-05 [4436073094]
 Total: 1.

Coelachyrum brevifolium Hochst. & Nees
 Golding 37, no date, K
 Total: 4; Kogi 1.

Coix lacryma-jobi L. — Introduced
 Thomas, NW; 1915-01-01 [PRE0951042-0]
 Total: 16; Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1,
 Ogun 1, Osun 3, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Coix lacryma-jobi var. *lacryma-jobi* —
 Introduced
 Gbile FHI20574, 1969, K
 Total: 1.

Ctenium canescens Benth.
 Hepper 1137, 1957, K
 Total: 7; Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Niger 2, Plateau 2.

Ctenium concinnum Nees
 Barter s.n., 1857 - 1859, K
 Total: 1.

Ctenium elegans Kunth
 Johnston 32, 1950, K
 Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1,
 Sokoto 1, Zamfara 3.

Ctenium ledermannii Pilg.

Tuley 1019, 1964, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Ctenium newtonii Hack.

Jackson 2355A, 1959, K

Total: 49; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 4, Kwara 5, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Cymbopogon citratus (DC.) Stapf —

Introduced

Andropogon citratus DC.

Odewo; Robert Obi; 2012-9-6 [9234]3808443878

Total: 29; Anambra 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 3, Lagos 15, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 3.

Cymbopogon densiflorus (Steud.) Stapf

Andropogon densiflorus Steud.

Latilo M.G. FHI28979; 1955-1-1

[BR0000019999081]

Total: 2; Kogi 1, Taraba 1.

Cymbopogon giganteus Chiov.

Andropogon giganteus Hochst.

Keay FHI37225, 1957, K

Total: 57; Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 5, Edo 1, Gombe 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 8, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2.

Cymbopogon nardus (L.) Rendle —

Introduced

Andropogon nardus L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cymbopogon schoenanthus (L.) Spreng.

Andropogon schoenanthus L.

Golding 4, no date, K

Total: 15; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Niger 2, Sokoto 2, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Cymbopogon schoenanthus subsp. *proximus* (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Maire & Weiller

Andropogon proximus Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Denys, E 604; 1982-4-4 [WAG.1818541]

Total: 12; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Cynodon aethiopicus Clayton & J.R.Harlan

Scholz 108b, 1969, K

Total: 1.

Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers.

Panicum dactylon L.

de Leeuw 1894, 1967, K

Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 6, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2.

Cynodon nlemfuensis Vanderyst —

Introduced

Gledhill 647, 1968, K

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1.

Cynodon nlemfuensis var. *nlemfuensis*

Gledhill, D.; 647; 1967-10-28 [K003053438]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Cyrtococcum chaetophoron (Roem. & Schult.) Dandy

Panicum chaetophoron Roem. & Schult.

Tuley 1776, 1969, K

Total: 6; Edo 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Dactyloctenium aegyptium (L.) Willd.

Cynosurus aegyptius L.

Meikle 657, 1949, K

Total: 66; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Borno 10, Cross River 5, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 4, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 2.

Dendrocalamus strictus (Roxb.) Nees —

Introduced

Bambos stricta Roxb.

Onochie FHI34330, 1954, K

Total: 6; Ogun 6.

Deschampsia mildbraedii Pilg.

Jacques Félix, H. [284]; 1938-01-01 [K003386772]

Total: 1.

Dichanthium caricosum (L.) A.Camus —

Introduced

Andropogon caricosus L.

Oche, M.O. MRK151; 1969-11-15 [K003163648]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Diectomis fastigiata (Sw.) P.Beauv.

Andropogon fastigiatus Sw.

Keay FHI28126, 1950, K

Total: 54; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Ebonyi 2, Enugu 7, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 12, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Digitaria abyssinica (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Stapf

Panicum abyssinicum Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Tuley 1849, 1969, K

Total: 15; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 7.

Digitaria acuminatissima Stapf

Latilo FHI62640, 1969, K

Total: 10; Benue 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Oyo 1.

Digitaria argillacea (Hitchc. & Chase)

Fernald

Syntherisma argillacea Hitchc. & Chase

Tuley 1577, no date, K

Total: 33; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 2, Delta 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Niger 6, Oyo 5, Plateau 4.

Digitaria atrofusca (Hack.) A.Camus

Panicum atrofuscum Hack.

de Leeuw 1951A, 1967, K

Total: 15; Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 4, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Digitaria barbinodis Henrard

Philcox 1005, 1958, K

Total: 8; Plateau 2.

Digitaria ciliaris (Retz.) Koeler

Panicum ciliare Retz.

Geerling, C 4089; 1971-8-20 [WAG.1311103]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Yobe 2.

Digitaria compressa Stapf

Keay FHI22865, 1948, K

Total: 6; Kaduna 5.

Digitaria debilis (Desf.) Willd.

Panicum debile Desf.

Tuley 626, 1964, K

Total: 20; Benue 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 7, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Digitaria delicatula Stapf

Hall 301, 1968, K

Total: 17; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Digitaria diagonalis (Nees) Stapf

Panicum diagonale Nees

Onochie FHI35713, 1956, K

Total: 21; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Digitaria eriantha Steud. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Digitaria exilis (Kippist) Stapf

Paspalum exile Kippist

Philcox 1006, 1958, K

Total: 3; Plateau 3.

Digitaria fuscescens (J.Presl) Henrard

Paspalum fuscescens J.Presl

Wheeler Haines 176, 1962, K

Total: 4; Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Digitaria gayana (Kunth) A.Chev.

Panicum gayanum Kunth

Tuley 812, 1964, K

Total: 39; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ondo 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2, Yobe 1.

Digitaria horizontalis Willd.

Wheeler Haines 177, 1962, K

Total: 64; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Borno 6, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 8, Kaduna 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Niger 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Taraba 1.

Digitaria iburua Stapf

Philcox 1007, 1958, K

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Plateau 2.

Digitaria leptorhachis (Pilg.) Stapf

Panicum leptorhachis Pilg.

Tuley 1638, 1969, K

Total: 30; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 2, Enugu 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Digitaria longiflora (Retz.) Pers.

Paspalum longiflorum Retz.

Tuley 873, 1964, K

Total: 53; Bauchi 7, Cross River 2, Edo 6, Gombe 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 6, Rivers 2.

Digitaria nuda Schumach.

Jackson 2.11670, 1970, K

Total: 31; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Niger 4, Plateau 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 2.

Digitaria sanguinalis (L.) Scop. —

Introduced

Panicum sanguinale L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Digitaria ternata (A.Rich.) Stapf

Cynodon ternatus A.Rich.

de Leeuw 1317, 1964, K

Total: 7; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1.

Digitaria velutina (Forssk.) P.Beauv.

Phalaris velutina Forssk.

Wheeler Haines, R. 369; 1965-04-13 [K001390871]

Total: 1.

Diheteropogon amplexens (Nees) Clayton

Andropogon amplexens Nees

Magaji 180, 1967, K

Total: 7; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Diheteropogon amplexens var. *catangensis* (Chiov.) Clayton

Andropogon amplexens var. *catangensis* Chiov.

Magaji 180, 1967, K

Total: 4; Gombe 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Diheteropogon filifolius (Nees) Clayton

Heteropogon filifolius Nees

Tuley 883, 1964, K

Total: 14; Anambra 1, Enugu 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Diheteropogon hagerupii Hitchc.

de Leeuw 1255, 1964, K

Total: 13; Bauchi 3, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 2.

Dinebra panicea (Retz.) P.M.Peterson & N.Snow

Poa panicea Retz.

Clayton, D. DC493; 1956-03-01 [K003627531]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1.

Dinebra retroflexa (Vahl) Panz.

Cynosurus retroflexus Vahl

Wickens G.M.; 1975-12-11 [BR0000021872914]

Total: 12; Borno 8, Gombe 1, Sokoto 1.

Dinebra retroflexa var. *retroflexa*

Cynosurus retroflexus Vahl

Johnston N89, 1950, K

Total: 1.

Diplachne fusca (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.

Festuca fusca L.

Jackson 2579, 1963, K

Total: 13; Borno 8, Jigawa 1, Niger 2, Sokoto 1.

Diplachne fusca subsp. *fusca*

Festuca fusca L.

Jackson 2579, 1963, K

Total: 1.

Echinochloa callopus (Pilg.) Clayton

Panicum callopus Pilg.

de Leeuw 1233, 1964, K

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Echinochloa colonum (L.) Link

Panicum colonum L.

Lowe 4380, 1983, K

Total: 65; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 18, Cross River 6, Imo 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 4, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 5, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6, Yobe 1.

Echinochloa crus-galli (L.) P.Beauv. —

Introduced

Panicum crus-galli L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Echinochloa crus-pavonis (Kunth) Schult.

Oplismenus crus-pavonis Kunth

Meikle 1241, 1950, K

Total: 24; Borno 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Osun 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Echinochloa frumentacea Link —

Introduced

Panicum frumentaceum Roxb.

Literature

Total: 0.

Echinochloa obtusiflora Stapf

Hubbard S574, 1948, K

Total: 17; Adamawa 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Taraba 1.

Echinochloa pyramidalis (Lam.) Hitchc. & Chase

Panicum pyramidale Lam.

Dalziel 1327, 1917, K

Total: 58; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 10, Edo 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 6, Katsina 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 6, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Echinochloa rotundiflora Clayton

Panicum obtusiflorum Hochst. ex A.Rich.

de Leeuw 1171, 1964, K

Total: 2; Borno 1, Kaduna 1.

Echinochloa stagnina (Retz.) P.Beauv.

Panicum stagninum Retz.

Dalziel 479, 1910, K

Total: 31; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Kano 1, Kebbi 4, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 1.

Eleusine africana Kenn.-O'Byrne

Dalziel 281, 1908, K

Total: 6; Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Eleusine coracana (L.) Gaertn.

Cynosurus coracanus L.
 Dalziel 280, 1908, K
 Total: 23; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Eleusine indica (L.) Gaertn.
Cynosurus indicus L.
 Brenan 8633, 1947, K
 Total: 133; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1, Benue 2, Borno 4, Cross River 2, Delta 4, Edo 7, Enugu 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 9, Kwara 9, Lagos 11, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 15, Oyo 24, Plateau 4, Rivers 1, Taraba 9.

Elionurus ciliaris Kunth
 Freeman S177, 1947, K
 Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 6, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 2.

Elionurus elegans Kunth
 Wit & Oguntayo 2288, 1972, K
 Total: 12; Niger 8, Sokoto 1.

Elionurus hirtifolius Hack.
 Taylor 23, 1930, K
 Total: 42; Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 3, Kaduna 8, Kogi 5, Niger 8, Plateau 7.

Elionurus muticus (Spreng.) Kuntze
Lycurus muticus Spreng.
 Meikle 1227, 1950, K
 Total: 12; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Elionurus royleanus Nees ex A.Rich.
 KERSHAW NGA-29347; 1966-03-01 [1948978141]
 Total: 1.

Elymandra androphila (Stapf) Stapf
Andropogon androphilus Stapf
 de Leeuw & Magaji 2000, 1967, K
 Total: 8; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Elymus repens (L.) Gould — Introduced
 Literature
 Total: 0.

Elytrophorus spicatus (Willd.) A.Camus
Dactylis spicata Willd.
 Magaji & Tuley 1835, 1969, K
 Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Enteropogon prieurii (Kunth) Clayton
Chloris prieurii Kunth
 Dalziel 279, 1908, K
 Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Borno 6, Yobe 1.

Eragrostis aegyptiaca (Willd.) Delile
Poa aegyptiaca Willd.
 Gwynn 132, no date, K
 Total: 6; Borno 1, Katsina 2, Niger 2, Yobe 1.

Eragrostis arenicola C.E.Hubb.
 Hepper 1132, 1957, K
 Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 7, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Eragrostis aspera (Jacq.) Nees
Poa aspera Jacq.
 Freeman S136, 1947, K
 Total: 43; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Kogi 5, Kwara 7, Niger 4, Oyo 5.

Eragrostis atrovirens (Desf.) Trin. ex Steud.
Poa atrovirens Desf.
 Keay FHI28287, 1950, K
 Total: 153; Abia 1, Adamawa 7, Anambra 4, Bauchi 6, Benue 2, Borno 10, Cross River 7, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 13, Kano 2, Katsina 4, Kebbi 3, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 12, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 25, Rivers 3, Sokoto 4, Taraba 13, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Eragrostis barteri C.E.Hubb.
 Keay FHI21155, 1947, K
 Total: 33; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 4, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 2, Delta 1, Jigawa 1, Kogi 2, Niger 7, Ogun 7, Oyo 3.

Eragrostis blepharostachya K.Schum.
 Clayton 534, 1956, K
 Total: 9; Osun 4.

Eragrostis camerunensis Clayton
 Biswas 227, 1981, K
 Total: 7; Cross River 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 5.

Eragrostis cenolepis Clayton
 Freeman S164, 1947, K
 Total: 10; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kaduna 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Eragrostis cilianensis (All.) Vignolo ex Janch.
Poa cilianensis All.
 Magaji & Ayuba 1545a, 1965, K
 Total: 25; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Borno 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1.

Eragrostis ciliaris (L.) R.Br.
Poa ciliaris L.
 Jones 4375, 1943, K
 Total: 101; Abia 1, Adamawa 4, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 3, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 1,

Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Jigawa 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 4, Kebbi 1, Kogi 9, Kwara 3, Lagos 11, Niger 4, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 16, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Eragrostis curvula (Schrad.) Nees —

Introduced

Poa curvula Schrad.

Ward 71, 1948, K

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Kwara 2.

Eragrostis elegantissima Chiov.

Latilo M.G. FHI43762; 1959-11-11

[BR0000025172898]

Total: 1; Jigawa 1.

Eragrostis gangetica (Roxb.) Steud.

Poa gangetica Roxb.

Brenan 8950, 1948, K

Total: 102; Bauchi 3, Borno 14, Cross River 4, Imo 2, Jigawa 2, Kaduna 12, Kano 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 10, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 3, Rivers 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Eragrostis interrupta P.Beauv. —

Introduced

; -- [Hagerup 613 (US)]3818405708

Total: 1.

Eragrostis invalida Pilg.

Keay FHI22679, 1948, K

Total: 4; Ondo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Eragrostis japonica (Thunb.) Trin.

Poa japonica Thunb.

Johnston N78, 1950, K

Total: 38; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 10, Gombe 4, Kaduna 2, Kogi 4, Niger 4, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1.

Eragrostis lehmanniana Nees — Introduced

Ward 68, 1948, K

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Eragrostis macilentia (A.Rich.) Steud.

Poa macilentia A.Rich.

Lawlor & Hall FHI45567, 1962, K

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Eragrostis mokensis Pilg.

Tuley 64, 1956, K

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Eragrostis palustris Zon

Geerling, C 4222; 1971-9-28 [WAG.1452931]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Eragrostis papposa (Roem. & Schult.) Steud.

Megastachya papposa Roem. & Schult.

J. D. Chapman 2826; -- [US 3642840]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Eragrostis patula (Kunth) Steud. —

Introduced

Poa patula Kunth

; -- [20035]230847335

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Eragrostis pilosa (L.) P.Beauv.

Poa pilosa L.

de Leeuw 1931, 1967, K

Total: 37; Bauchi 2, Borno 9, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Eragrostis pobeguinii C.E.Hubb.

Ujor FHI30323, 1951, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Eragrostis prolifera (Sw.) Steud.

Poa prolifera Sw.

Wheeler Haines 163, 1963, K

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ogun 2.

Eragrostis scotelliana Rendle

Latilo FHI62285, 1968, K

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 1.

Eragrostis secundiflora J.Presl —

Introduced

G. Jackson 431170; -- [US 2694543]

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Eragrostis soratensis Jedwabn. —

Introduced

Lowe J. 4496; 1983-12-16 [101508]1891253018

Total: 15; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Jigawa 1, Kwara 1, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Eragrostis squamata (Lam.) Steud.

Poa squamata Lam.

Maitland 63, 1927, K

Total: 29; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Eragrostis superba Peyr.

Biswas 7, 1978, K

Total: 3; Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1.

Eragrostis tenella (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.

Poa tenella L.

Ward 76, 1948, K

Total: 53; Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 5, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 11, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Eragrostis tenuifolia (A.Rich.) Hochst. ex Steud.

Poa tenuifolia A.Rich.

Tuley 481, 1964, K

Total: 28; Borno 1, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Plateau 12, Taraba 5.

Eragrostis tremula Hochst. ex Steud.

Wheeler Haines 151, 1963, K

Total: 107; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 7, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Imo 4, Kaduna 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 6, Kwara 8, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 4, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Sokoto 8, Taraba 3, Yobe 8, Zamfara 2.

Eragrostis turgida (Schumach.) De Wild.

Poa turgida Schumach.

Cook 311, 1965, K

Total: 66; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 11, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Eragrostis viscosa (Retz.) Trin.

Poa viscosa Retz.

Magaji & Tuley 1847, 1969, K

Total: 9; Borno 1, Edo 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Eragrostis volkensii Pilg.

Tuley 2032, 1969, K

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1.

Eragrostis welwitschii Rendle

Tuley 1855, 1969, K

Total: 21; Enugu 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 10, Taraba 2.

Eriochloa barbatus (Trin.) S.Yadav & M.R.Almeida

Helopus barbatus Trin.

de Leeuw 2073, 1968, K

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1.

Eriochrysis brachypogon (Stapf) Stapf

Saccharum brachypogon Stapf

de Leeuw 1790, 1966, K

Total: 7; Kaduna 2, Niger 4, Osun 1.

Eriochrysis pallida Munro

de Leeuw 1752, 1966, K

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Euclasta condylotricha (Hochst. ex Steud.)

Stapf

Andropogon condylotrichus Hochst. ex Steud.

Daramola FHI62323, 1968, K

Total: 52; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 5, Kwara 2, Niger 4, Ogun 5, Oyo 17, Taraba 1.

Festuca abyssinica A.Rich.

Rich A.1221; 1930-12- [11389] [1989898390]

Total: 1.

Festuca bromoides L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Festuca rigidiuscula E.B.Alexeev

Boughy, A.S. 12671; 1952-12-16 [K003062050]

Total: 2; Adamawa 2.

Festuca simensis Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Amshoff G.J.M.8271; 1965-10-14 [75862]

[1989899363]

Total: 1; Abia 1.

Guaduella densiflora Pilg.

Keay 28156, 1950, K

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Guaduella humilis Clayton

Coombe 173, 1955, K

Total: 8; Cross River 5.

Guaduella macrostachys (K.Schum.) Pilg.

Microbambus macrostachys K.Schum.

Tuley 672, 1964, K

Total: 6; Cross River 5.

Guaduella oblonga Hutch. ex Clayton

Ariwaodo J.O.Ariw.811; 1977-7-11 [99408]

[1989899667]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Gynerium sagittatum (Aubl.) P.Beauv. —

Introduced

Saccharum sagittatum Aubl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Hackelochloa granularis (L.) Kuntze

Cenchrus granularis L.

Tuley 1516, 1969, K

Total: 93; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 3, Cross River 7, Edo 2,

Enugu 7, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 7, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Oyo 11, Plateau 8, Taraba 8, Yobe 1.

Hemarthria altissima (Poir.) Stapf & C.E.Hubb.

Rottboellia altissima Poir.

Hall 467, 1968, K

Total: 6; Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Heteranthoecia guineensis (Franch.) Robyns

Dinebra guineensis Franch.

Meikle 1091, 1950, K

Total: 10; Enugu 1, Kogi 4, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Heteropogon contortus (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.

Andropogon contortus L.

Tuley 1604, 1969, K

Total: 52; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Delta 1, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 5, Kogi 8, Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Sokoto 2.

Heteropogon melanocarpus (Elliott) Benth.

Andropogon melanocarpus Elliott

de Leeuw & Magaji 1994, 1967, K

Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Kogi 1.

Hordeum vulgare L. — Introduced

Thoruton s.n., 1922, K

Total: 5; Borno 1, Niger 3.

Hymenachne amplexicaulis (Rudge) Nees

— Introduced

Panicum amplexicaule Rudge

Egunyomi A.; 1992-6-6 [104808]1989899803

Total: 2; Benue 1, Delta 1.

Hyparrhenia bagirmica (Stapf) Stapf

Cymbopogon bagirmicus Stapf

Clayton 1379, 1957, K

Total: 25; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 14, Katsina 3, Kogi 1.

Hyparrhenia barteri (Hack.) Stapf

Andropogon barteri Hack.

Ward L145, 1950, K

Total: 28; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Hyparrhenia bracteata (Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd.) Stapf

Andropogon bracteatus Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd.

Tuley 1023, 1964, K

Total: 10; Osun 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Hyparrhenia collina (Pilg.) Stapf

Cymbopogon collinus Pilg.

Tuley 2073, 1969, K

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Hyparrhenia cyanescens (Stapf) Stapf

Cymbopogon cyanescens Stapf

Keay FHI5490, 1947, K

Total: 47; Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 1, Enugu 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 9, Katsina 2, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Oyo 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Hyparrhenia cymbaria (L.) Stapf

Andropogon cymbarius L.

Hepper 1645, 1958, K

Total: 15; Gombe 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 9.

Hyparrhenia diplandra (Hack.) Stapf

Andropogon diplandrus Hack.

Latilo & Daramola FHI28794, 1954, K

Total: 51; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 13, Taraba 17.

Hyparrhenia familiaris (Steud.) Stapf

Andropogon familiaris Steud.

Tuley 1924, 1969, K

Total: 22; Cross River 3, Niger 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 12.

Hyparrhenia figariana (Chiov.) Clayton

Cymbopogon figarianus Chiov.

Lawlor & Hall 339, 1962, K

Total: 1.

Hyparrhenia filipendula (Hochst.) Stapf

Andropogon filipendulus Hochst.

Daramola 77, 1979, K

Total: 45; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 4, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 5, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 15.

Hyparrhenia filipendula var. *filipendula*

Andropogon filipendulus Hochst.

Daramola 77, 1979, K

Total: 2; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 1.

Hyparrhenia filipendula var. *pilosa* (Hochst.) Stapf

Andropogon filipendulus var. *pilosus* Hochst.

Clayton 581, 1956, K

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Hyparrhenia glabriuscula (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Stapf

Andropogon glabriusculus Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Tuley 1825, 1969, K

Total: 14; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Yobe 1.

Hyparrhenia involucrata Stapf

Gledhill 661, 1968, K

Total: 117; Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 25, Katsina 2, Kogi 9, Kwara 10, Niger 12, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 29, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 2.

Hyparrhenia involucrata var. *involucrata*

Gledhill 661, 1968, K

Total: 45; Bauchi 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 18, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Hyparrhenia newtonii (Hack.) Stapf

Andropogon newtonii Hack.

Hepper 1424, 1957, K

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Taraba 2.

Hyparrhenia newtonii var. *newtonii*

Andropogon newtonii Hack.

Hepper 1424, 1957, K

Total: 1.

Hyparrhenia poecilotricha (Hack.) Stapf

Andropogon poecilotrichus Hack.

Blair Raines 228, 1974, K

Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Hyparrhenia quarrei Robyns

Tuley 1879, 1969, K

Total: 6; Benue 1, Katsina 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Hyparrhenia rudis Stapf

Tuley 1722, 1969, K

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Hyparrhenia rufa (Nees) Stapf

Trachypogon rufus Nees

Ogua FHI7825, 1944, K

Total: 159; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 6, Borno 7, Cross River 3, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 24, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 16, Nasarawa 1, Niger 13, Ogun 8, Oyo 24, Plateau 16, Taraba 9.

Hyparrhenia rufa var. *rufa*

Trachypogon rufus Nees

Hyparrhenia smithiana (Hook.f.) Stapf

Andropogon smithianus Hook.f.

Daramola FHI62466, 1963, K

Total: 64; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 5, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 9, Kano 1, Katsina

1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ogun 3, Oyo 7, Plateau 7, Taraba 3.

Hyparrhenia smithiana var. *major* Clayton

Geerling, C 3922; 1971-8-11 [WAG.1453103]

Total: 33; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Hyparrhenia smithiana var. *smithiana*

Andropogon smithianus Hook.f.

Hyparrhenia subplumosa Stapf

Onochie FHI8115, 1944, K

Total: 168; Abia 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Enugu 13, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 31, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 11, Niger 4, Ogun 12, Oyo 32, Plateau 13, Taraba 7, Zamfara 1.

Hyparrhenia umbrosa (Hochst.) Andersson
ex Clayton

Andropogon umbrosus Hochst.

Latilo & Daramola FHI28995, 1955, K

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Hyparrhenia violascens (Stapf) Clayton

Hyparrhenia soluta var. *violascens* Stapf

Hepper 1282, 1957, K

Total: 31; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Katsina 3, Niger 3, Ondo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Yobe 2, Zamfara 2.

Hyparrhenia welwitschii (Rendle) Stapf

Cymbopogon welwitschii Rendle

Rose-Innes 268, 1975, K

Total: 31; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Hyperthelia dissoluta (Nees ex Steud.)

Clayton

Anthistiria dissoluta Nees ex Steud.

Jones 6257, 1942, K

Total: 105; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 7, Benue 1, Borno 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 9, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 10, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 3, Niger 12, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 7, Sokoto 2, Taraba 4, Yobe 2.

Hypseochloa cameroonensis C.E.Hubb.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 65274; 1970-4-5 [WAG.1472649]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Imperata cylindrica (L.) Raesch.

Lagurus cylindricus L.

Lawlor & Hall 721, 1962, K

Total: 64; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 5, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 11, Plateau 7, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Isachne albens Trin.

Brenan 8856, 1948, K

Total: 14; Cross River 2, Edo 6, Enugu 1, Rivers 1.

Isachne albens var. *buettneri* (Hack.)

Veldkamp

Brenan 8856, 1948, K

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Rivers 1.

Isachne angolensis Rendle

Daramola FHI62431

Total: 1.

Isachne kiyalaensis Robyns

Onochie FHI34089, 1953, K

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kogi 1.

Isachne mauritiana Kunth

Tuley 1033, 1964, K

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Ischaemum afrum (J.F.Gmel.) Dandy

Andropogon afer J.F.Gmel.

Jackson 3.12770, 1970, K

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Nasarawa 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Ischaemum amethystinum Lebrun

Lawlor & Hall FHI46648, 1962, K

Total: 12; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 6.

Ischaemum barbatum Retz. — Introduced

Onochie FHI33425, 1953, K

Total: 2; Delta 2.

Ischaemum rugosum Salisb. — Introduced

Reid J.C.407; 1984-11-30 [104325] [1914119470]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Ischaemum timorense Kunth — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Ixophorus unisetus (J.Presl) Schltl. —

Introduced

Urochloa unisetata J.Presl

Eijnatten, CLM van 46; 1960-6-3 [WAG.1473192]

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Koordersiochloa longiarista (A.Rich.)

Veldkamp

Trisetum longiaristum A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Leersia drepanothrix Stapf

de Leeuw 1853a, 1966, K

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Leersia hexandra Sw.

Tuley 1541, 1969, K

Total: 64; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 7, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 13, Taraba 5.

Leersia triandra C.E.Hubb.

Reid 401, 1984, K

Total: 1.

Leptaspis zeylanica Nees ex Steud.

Pilz 2016, 1977, K

Total: 70; Cross River 11, Edo 12, Kaduna 1, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 6, Oyo 6, Plateau 2, Taraba 7.

Leptochloa coerulescens Steud.

Jones 1416, 1942, K

Total: 44; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 4, Cross River 3, Delta 2, Ebonyi 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 2.

Leptochloa mucronata (Michx.) Kunth —

Introduced

Eleusine mucronata Michx.

Eijnatten, CLM van 80; 1960-5-28 [WAG.1531598]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Leptochloa panicea (Retz.) Ohwi —

Introduced

Poa panicea Retz.

West 2, no date, K

Total: 1.

Leptochloa panicea subsp. *brachiata*

(Steud.) N.Snow — Introduced

Leptochloa brachiata Steud.

West 2, no date, K

Total: 1.

Loudetia annua (Stapf) C.E.Hubb.

Trichopteryx annua Stapf

Lely P650, 1930, K

Total: 20; Bauchi 4, Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Loudetia arundinacea (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Hochst. ex Steud.

Tristachya arundinacea Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Hepper 1373, 1957, K

Total: 84; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 5, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Delta 2, Edo 13, Enugu 8, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 3, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 3, Taraba 9, Zamfara 1.

Loudetia coarctata (A.Camus) C.E.Hubb.

Tristachya coarctata A.Camus

Keay FHI5447, 1947, K

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Kebbi 1, Taraba 1.

Loudetia flavida (Stapf) C.E.Hubb.

Trichopteryx flavida Stapf

Tuley 1699, 1969, K

Total: 20; Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 2, Gombe 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 6, Plateau 1.

Loudetia hordeiformis (Stapf) C.E.Hubb.

Trichopteryx hordeiformis Stapf

Gledhill 709, 1968, K

Total: 67; Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 2, Edo 1, Enugu 7, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 9, Kwara 2, Niger 12, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 2.

Loudetia kagerensis (K.Schum.) C.E.Hubb.

Trichopteryx kagerensis K.Schum.

de Leeuw 1789, 1966, K

Total: 13; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Osun 1, Taraba 9.

Loudetia phragmitoides (Peter) C.E.Hubb.

Trichopteryx phragmitoides Peter

Gambles 7, 1960, K

Total: 52; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 3, Gombe 5, Kaduna 2, Kwara 4, Lagos 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 5, Taraba 3.

Loudetia simplex (Nees) C.E.Hubb.

Tristachya simplex Nees

Okigbo 124, 1962, K

Total: 108; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Enugu 3, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 16, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 21, Ogun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 17, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Loudetia togoensis (Pilg.) C.E.Hubb.

Trichopteryx togoensis Pilg.

Clayton 1310, 1957, K

Total: 27; Bauchi 3, Borno 4, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 8, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Yobe 2.

Loudetiopsis ambiens (K.Schum.) Conert

Trichopteryx ambiens K.Schum.

Magajie & Tuley 2148, 1971, K

Total: 8; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Loudetiopsis chrysothrix (Nees) Conert

Tristachya chrysothrix Nees

Lely P493, 1930, K

Total: 10; Bauchi 3, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 4.

Loudetiopsis glabrata (K.Schum.) Conert

Trichopteryx glabrata K.Schum.

Keay FHI22666, 1948, K

Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Ekiti 3, Ondo 8, Osun 3, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Loudetiopsis kerstingii (Pilg.) Conert

Trichopteryx kerstingii Pilg.

Gbile FHI64205, 1971, K

Total: 11; Kogi 5, Kwara 3, Plateau 1.

Loudetiopsis scaettae (A.Camus) Clayton

Tristachya scaettae A.Camus

Howard BV950, 1974, K

Total: 6; Benue 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1.

Loudetiopsis trigemina (C.E.Hubb.) Conert

Loudetia trigemina C.E.Hubb.

Clayton 1409, 1957, K

Total: 8; Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Louisiella fluitans C.E.Hubb. & J.Léonard

1961-11-23 [2252245778]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Loxodera ledermannii (Pilg.) Launert

Elionurus ledermannii Pilg.

Keay FHI25759, 1950, K

Total: 9; Kaduna 5, Kwara 2, Niger 2.

Megastachya mucronata (Poir.) P.Beauv.

Poa mucronata Poir.

Jeffreys 32, 1915, K

Total: 43; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 14, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 3.

Megathyrus maximus (Jacq.) B.K.Simon & S.W.L.Jacobs

Panicum maximum Jacq.

Wheeler Haines 303, 1964, K

Total: 63; Anambra 2, Benue 4, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 5, Kaduna 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 24, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Melinis effusa (Rendle) Stapf

Melinis minutiflora var. effusa Rendle

Kennedy 27, 1943, K

Total: 4; Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Melinis longiseta (A.Rich.) Zizka

Tricholaena longiseta A.Rich.
Lawlor & Hall FHI45574, 1962, K
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Melinis longiseta subsp. *bellespicata*
(Rendle) Zizka

Tricholaena bellespicata Rendle
Lawlor & Hall FHI45574, 1962, K
Total: 1.

Melinis macrochaeta Stapf & C.E.Hubb.
Lawlor & Hall 633, 1962, K
Total: 24; Anambra 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 2,
Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Melinis minutiflora P.Beauv.
Hepper 1363, 1957, K
Total: 31; Adamawa 4, Anambra 1, Cross River 4,
Lagos 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 14.

Melinis repens (Willd.) Zizka
Saccharum repens Willd.
Hall K22, 1962, K
Total: 141; Adamawa 4, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue
3, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Enugu 6, Gombe 1,
Kaduna 1, Kogi 13, Kwara 16, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 1,
Niger 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 18, Plateau 27, Rivers 1, Taraba
10.

Melinis repens subsp. *grandiflora* (Hochst.)
Zizka — Introduced
Rhynchelythrum grandiflorum Hochst.
Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO FHI 64048; 1971-9-
15 [WAG.1545286]
Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Melinis repens subsp. *repens*
Saccharum repens Willd.
Hall K22, 1962, K
Total: 44; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2,
Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 3,
Ogun 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 12, Taraba 1.

Melinis tenuissima Stapf
Stanfield FHI55610, 1964, K
Total: 15; Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba
5.

Micrachne obtusiflora (Benth.)
P.M.Peterson
Microchloa obtusiflora Benth.
Jackson UIH10426, 1973, K
Total: 3; Kaduna 1.

Microchloa indica (L.f.) P.Beauv.
Nardus indica L.f.
Wit & Oguntayo 2309, 1972, K

Total: 37; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 5,
Katsina 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 3, Niger 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 4,
Sokoto 1.

Microchloa kunthii Desv.
Microchloa setacea Kunth
Hall K9, 1962, K
Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1,
Ondo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Monocymbium cerasiiforme (Nees) Stapf
Andropogon cerasiiformis Nees
Jones 6231, 1942, K
Total: 72; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi
1, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Ekiti 4, Enugu 5,
Imo 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Nasarawa
1, Niger 8, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 6,
Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Monocymbium deightonii C.E.Hubb.
No specimen is found
Total: 2; Katsina 1, Oyo 1.

Moorochloa eruciformis (Sm.) Veldkamp
Panicum eruciforme Sm.
1995-9-18 [FR-0019981] [3046043193]
Total: 1; Borno 1.

Olyra latifolia L.
Lowe 4360, 1982, K
Total: 117; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 11,
Ekiti 5, Enugu 4, Gombe 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 5, Kogi 6,
Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 3, Ogun 17,
Ondo 6, Osun 4, Oyo 12, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba
8.

Oplismenus burmanni (Retz.) P.Beauv.
Panicum burmanni Retz.
Pilz 2185, 1977, K
Total: 58; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River
5, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Imo 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 4,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 8, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo
16.

Oplismenus hirtellus (L.) P.Beauv.
Panicum hirtellum L.
Onochie FHI8131, 1944, K
Total: 117; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Cross River 6, Edo 14, Ekiti 3,
Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Nasarawa
2, Niger 7, Ogun 13, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 15, Plateau
4, Taraba 15.

Oryza barthii A.Chev.
Dalziel 268, 1908, K
Total: 19; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 7, Delta 1, Edo 2,
Katsina 1, Kogi 1.

Oryza glaberrima Steud.

Hardcastle s.n., 1957, K

Total: 18; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Oryza longistaminata A.Chev. & Roehr.

Sampson 15, 1929, K

Total: 27; Adamawa 4, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Yobe 4.

Oryza punctata Kotschy ex Steud.

Newell 1450, 1976, K

Total: 8; Borno 2, Oyo 3.

Oryza sativa L. — Introduced

Lowe 2471, 1972, K

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1.

Oxyrhachis gracillima (Baker) C.E.Hubb.

Rottboellia gracillima Baker

Hepper 2069, 1959, K

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Taraba 1.

Oxytenanthera abyssinica (A.Rich.) Munro

Bambusa abyssinica A.Rich.

Tuley 2135, 1969, K

Total: 32; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 7, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 5.

Panicum acrotrichum Hook.f.

Latilo 36, 1975, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Panicum anabaptistum Steud.

Tuley 1821, 1969, K

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Panicum antidotale Retz. — Introduced

Ward 69, 1948, K

Total: 3; Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1.

Panicum brevifolium L.

Jones 6256, 1942, K

Total: 78; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 15, Edo 12, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 2, Ondo 6, Osun 5, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Panicum calvum Stapf

Gledhill, D 800; 1968-1-10 [WAG.1243537]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Panicum coloratum L. — Introduced

Ward 72, 1948, K

Total: 10; Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Kwara 2, Oyo 4.

Panicum comorense Mez

Gambles 64, 1960, K

Total: 6; Ogun 3, Oyo 3.

Panicum curviflorum Hornem. —

Introduced

Brenan, J. P. M.; Keay, R. W. J. 8658; 1948-1-1 [K000256829]

Total: 4; Ondo 4.

Panicum deustum Thunb.

1971-9-17 [2252244147]

Total: 3; Enugu 1, Kwara 2.

Panicum dregeanum Nees

Lely 423, 1930, K

Total: 12; Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Taraba 1.

Panicum fluviicola Steud.

Latilo FHI61419, 1971, K

Total: 85; Abia 2, Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 7, Delta 1, Edo 3, Enugu 3, Kano 1, Kogi 11, Kwara 6, Lagos 8, Niger 11, Ogun 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Panicum griffonii Franch.

Savory & Keay FHI25447, 1949, K

Total: 9; Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1.

Panicum hochstetteri Steud.

Tuley 1028, 1964, K

Total: 6; Delta 2, Taraba 4.

Panicum humile Steud.

Clayton 473, 1955, K

Total: 10; Jigawa 2, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Niger 3, Plateau 1.

Panicum laetum Kunth

Johnston N54, 1950, K

Total: 19; Bauchi 2, Borno 12, Gombe 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Panicum monticola Hook.f.

Tuley 1031, 1964, K

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Panicum nigerense Hitchc.

de Leeuw 1162, 1964, K

Total: 1; Katsina 1.

Panicum pansum Rendle

Kennedy FHI7281, 1944, K

Total: 39; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 5, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 3, Niger 8, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Panicum paucinode Stapf

de Leeuw 1820, 1966, K

Total: 9; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Panicum phragmitoides Stapf

de Leeuw 1080, 1964, K

Total: 30; Bauchi 6, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 6.

Panicum pilgeri Mez

Gambles 4, 1960, K

Total: 11; Kogi 2, Niger 6.

Panicum porphyrrhizos Steud.

Geerling, C 4139; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1452941]

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Panicum pusillum Hook.f.

Tuley 1909, 1969, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Panicum repens L.

de Leeuw 1714, 1966, K

Total: 45; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 4, Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 2, Imo 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 10, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 6, Rivers 3.

Panicum subalbidum Kunth

de Leeuw 1086, 1964, K

Total: 61; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 10, Borno 6, Cross River 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 2, Katsina 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Nasarawa 3, Niger 6, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Panicum sublaetum Stapf

Eijnatten, CLM van 339; 1960-11-29 [WAG.1175234]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1.

Panicum trichoides Sw.

Gillett 15265, 1962, K

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Lagos 1, Ondo 1.

Parahyparrhenia annua (Hack.) Clayton

Andropogon annuus Hack.

KERSHAW NGA-29319; 1966-02-01 [1948977602]

Total: 1.

Paratheria prostrata Griseb.

Dalziel 1423, 1920, K

Total: 1.

Paspalum conjugatum P.J.Bergius —

Introduced

Dalziel 1314, 1918, K

Total: 58; Abia 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 9, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 15, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Paspalum dilatatum Poir. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Paspalum distichum L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 241; -- [WAG.1394253]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Paspalum lamprocaryon K.Schum.

s.coll. [Bam/19]; 1949-10-01 [K003929589]

Total: 1.

Paspalum notatum Flügge — Introduced

Lowe 2570, 1972, K

Total: 2; Enugu 1, Oyo 1.

Paspalum orbiculare G.Forst. — Introduced

Kingsley s.n., 1896, K

Total: 24; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 2.

Paspalum paniculatum L.

Wheeler Haines 168, 1963, K

Total: 2; Anambra 1, Lagos 1.

Paspalum scrobiculatum L. — Introduced

Baldwin 14010, 1950, K

Total: 238; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 2, Anambra 5, Bauchi 6, Bayelsa 2, Benue 4, Borno 2, Cross River 16, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 11, Enugu 3, Gombe 3, Imo 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kebbi 4, Kogi 12, Kwara 9, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 4, Niger 21, Ogun 10, Ondo 6, Osun 1, Oyo 27, Plateau 14, Rivers 7, Sokoto 1, Taraba 13, Yobe 2.

Paspalum urvillei Steud. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Paspalum vaginatum Sw.

Letilo FHI54899, 1964, K

Total: 21; Abia 1, Lagos 15, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Perotis hildebrandtii Mez

Kennedy 2682, 1935, K

Total: 21; Abia 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Perotis indica (L.) Kuntze

Anthoxanthum indicum L.

Tuley 613, 1964, K

Total: 23; Cross River 3, Edo 9, Ekiti 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 2.

Perotis patens Gand.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 235; 1978-5-2

[WAG.1537763]

Total: 27; Benue 1, Jigawa 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Niger 3, Oyo 6.

Perotis scabra Willd. ex Trin.

Daramola; Others 162; 1980-8- [103013]
[1914118661]

Total: 18; Ekiti 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 6, Nasarawa 2, Oyo 6.

Phacelurus gabonensis (Steud.) Clayton

Jardinea gabonensis Steud.

Ward L104, 1950, K

Total: 38; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Phragmites australis (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud.

Arundo australis Cav.

Geerling, C 3196; 1970-10-29 [WAG.1453001]

Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 6, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 1.

Phragmites australis subsp. *australis*

Arundo australis Cav.

Geerling, C 3196; 1970-10-29 [WAG.1453001]

Total: 1.

Phragmites australis subsp. *isiacus*

(Arcang.) ined.

Arundo maxima Forssk.

Wickens 3548, 1975, K

Total: 1.

Phragmites karka (Retz.) Trin. ex Steud.

Arundo karka Retz.

Lowe 1591, 1968, K

Total: 53; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Bayelsa 2, Borno 2, Delta 1, Gombe 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 6, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Phragmites mauritianus Kunth

O. Hagerup 762; 1927-12-13 [US 1448093]

Total: 2; Benue 1, Niger 1.

Phyllostachys aurea (Andre) Riviere &

C.Riviere — Introduced

Bambusa aurea André

Dundas, G. FHI13903; 1945-12-03 [K002364411]

Total: 2.

Poa schimperiana Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Jackson 2036, 1969, K

Total: 1.

Poecilostachys oplismenoides (Hack.)

Clayton

Panicum oplismenoides Hack.

Savory FHI25257, 1948, K

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Pogonarthria squarrosa (Licht.) Pilg.

Poa squarrosa Licht.

Hepper 1127, 1957, K

Total: 14; Bauchi 4, Jigawa 2, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 2.

Polypogon monspeliensis (L.) Desf.

Alopecurus monspeliensis L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Polytrias indica (Houtt.) Veldkamp

Phleum indicum Houtt.

Maitland 64, 1929, K

Total: 2.

Pseudechinolaena polystachya (Kunth)

Stapf

Echinolaena polystachya Kunth

Brenan 8506, 1947, K

Total: 20; Cross River 3, Edo 5, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 4.

Rhytachne rottboellioides Desv.

Biswas 235, 1982, K

Total: 17; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Rhytachne triaristata (Steud.) Stapf

Lepturopsis triaristata Steud.

Clayton 1313, 1957, K

Total: 30; Abia 1, Adamawa 4, Anambra 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 10, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Rottboellia afraurita Stapf

de Leeuw 1749, 1966, K

Total: 3; Bauchi 1.

Rottboellia cochinchinensis (Lour.) Clayton

Stegosia cochinchinensis Lour.

Dalziel 509, 1910, K

Total: 36; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Imo 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Saccharum officinarum L. — Introduced

Lely 139, 1919, K

Total: 3; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Saccharum spontaneum subsp. *aegyptiacum*

(Willd.) Hack.

Vogel 33, 1895, K

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Kwara 3, Taraba 2.

Sacciolepis africana C.E.Hubb. & Snowden
Jones 3122, 1943, K

Total: 41; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kebbi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Rivers 2, Sokoto 4, Taraba 2, Yobe 2.

Sacciolepis chevalieri Stapf
Child G.S. 730; 1971-11-24 [30394]
Total: 4; Kwara 3.

Sacciolepis cymbiandra Stapf
Clayton 642, 1957, K
Total: 2; Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Sacciolepis indica (L.) Chase
Aira indica L.
Clayton 1307, 1957, K
Total: 25; Kaduna 3, Kwara 5, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Sacciolepis micrococca Mez
Wheeler Haines 353, 1964, K
Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 10, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Sacciolepis typhura (Stapf) Stapf
Panicum typhurum Stapf
Gambles 5, 1960, K
Total: 2; Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Sarga purpureosericea (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Spangler
Andropogon purpureosericeus Hochst. ex A.Rich.
Magaji 192, s.dat., K
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Borno 1.

Schizachyrium brevifolium (Sw.) Nees ex Buse
Andropogon brevifolius Sw.
Wheeler Haines 339, 1964, K
Total: 28; Benue 1, Borno 3, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Schizachyrium delicatum Stapf
Clayton 1311, 1957, K
Total: 1.

Schizachyrium exile (Hochst.) Pilg.
Andropogon exilis Hochst.
Ward 27, 1948, K
Total: 36; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Borno 4, Ebonyi 2, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Katsina 3, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 8, Taraba 1.

Schizachyrium gresicola Jacq.-Fél.
Tuley 1716, 1969, K
Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Schizachyrium maclaudii (Jacq.-Fél.) S.T.Blake
Schizachyrium brevifolium var. maclaudii Jacq.-Fél.
Biswas 101, 1981, K
Total: 4; Kwara 1, Rivers 1.

Schizachyrium nodulosum (Hack.) Stapf
Andropogon nodulosus Hack.
de Leeuw & Magaji s.n., 1967, K
Total: 7; Borno 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Niger 2, Sokoto 1.

Schizachyrium platyphyllum (Franch.) Stapf
Andropogon brevifolius var. platyphyllum Franch.
Kennedy 9, 1943, K
Total: 5; Edo 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Schizachyrium pulchellum (D.Don ex Benth.) Stapf
Andropogon pulchellus D.Don ex Benth.
Killick 259, 1965, K
Total: 12; Cross River 1, Lagos 6.

Schizachyrium rupestre (K.Schum.) Stapf
Andropogon rupestris K.Schum.
Biswas 84, 1978, K
Total: 1.

Schizachyrium sanguineum (Retz.) Alston
Rottboellia sanguinea Retz.
Onochie FHI34071, 1953, K
Total: 70; Anambra 4, Bauchi 3, Benue 3, Cross River 1, Delta 3, Edo 1, Enugu 8, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 11, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Osun 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 7, Zamfara 1.

Schizachyrium schweinfurthii (Hack.) Stapf
Andropogon schweinfurthii Hack.
Magaji 248, 1968, K
Total: 4; Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Oyo 1.

Schizachyrium urceolatum (Hack.) Stapf
Andropogon urceolatus Hack.
Jackson S19968, 1968, K
Total: 6; Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Schoenefeldia gracilis Kunth
Daggash FHI24885, 1949, K
Total: 36; Bauchi 2, Borno 13, Jigawa 1, Kano 5, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Sehima ischaemoides Forssk.
de Leeuw 1861, 1966, K

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Gombe 1.

Setaria barbata (Lam.) Kunth

Panicum barbatum Lam.

Jones 1527, 1942, K

Total: 147; Abia 1, Adamawa 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 5, Bauchi 4, Benue 3, Borno 6, Cross River 11, Delta 3, Edo 2, Enugu 3, Gombe 1, Imo 3, Jigawa 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 9, Kwara 7, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 5, Ogun 15, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 15, Plateau 6, Rivers 1, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Setaria geminata (Forssk.) Veldkamp

Panicum geminatum Forssk.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1473; 1972-4-25 [WAG.1820516]

Total: 20; Borno 6, Kebbi 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Sokoto 4.

Setaria incrassata (Hochst.) Hack.

Panicum incrassatum Hochst.

de Leeuw 1315, 1964, K

Total: 3; Borno 1, Kaduna 1.

Setaria italica (L.) P.Beauv. — Introduced

Panicum italicum L.

Geerling, C 4079; 1971-8-20 [WAG.1451354]

Total: 30; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Delta 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 7, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Setaria kagerensis Mez

Tuley 1579, 1969, K

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Setaria longiseta P.Beauv.

Hepper 1108, 1957, K

Total: 72; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 11, Osun 4, Oyo 10, Plateau 3, Rivers 3, Taraba 2.

Setaria megaphylla (Steud.) T.Durand & Schinz

Panicum megaphyllum Steud.

Tuley 668, 1964, K

Total: 90; Abia 1, Anambra 3, Cross River 12, Delta 1, Edo 10, Ekiti 6, Kaduna 5, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 5, Niger 3, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Osun 6, Oyo 4, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Setaria nigrirostris (Nees) T.Durand & Schinz

Panicum nigrirostre Nees

de Leeuw & Magaji s.n., 1967, K

Total: 1; Gombe 1.

Setaria palmifolia (J.Koenig) Stapf

Panicum palmifolium J.Koenig

Clayton 559, 1956, K

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Setaria parviflora (Poir.) Kerguelen —

Introduced

Cenchrus parviflorus Poir.

Emwiogbon 292/77; 1977-10-12 [100850141]

Total: 226; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Adamawa 4, Anambra 2, Bauchi 8, Bayelsa 1, Benue 4, Borno 2, Cross River 10, Edo 3, Enugu 14, Gombe 1, Imo 6, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 19, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 12, Kwara 9, Lagos 15, Niger 18, Ogun 7, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 36, Plateau 9, Rivers 2, Taraba 4.

Setaria poiretiana (Schult.) Kunth

Panicum poiretianum Schult.

Tuley 668, 1964, K

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Setaria pumila (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.

Panicum pumilum Poir.

Jones FHI6689, 1942, K

Total: 90; Adamawa 4, Anambra 2, Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 16, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 5, Nasarawa 3, Niger 7, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Sokoto 1, Yobe 7.

Setaria sphacelata (Schumach.) Stapf & C.E.Hubb. ex Moss

Panicum sphacelatum Schumach.

Tuley 1525, 1969, K

Total: 124; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 3, Bauchi 8, Benue 1, Borno 6, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Kaduna 12, Kogi 7, Kwara 6, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 5, Niger 5, Oyo 5, Plateau 19, Sokoto 1, Taraba 12, Yobe 5.

Setaria sulcata Raddi — Introduced

Panicum sulcatum Bertol.

M. Jeffreys13; 1915-10-12 [US 1037938] [3005719814]

Total: 4; Edo 1, Oyo 1.

Setaria verticillata (L.) P.Beauv.

Panicum verticillatum L.

Palmer 25, 1933, K

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 3.

Setaria viridis (L.) P.Beauv. — Introduced

Panicum viride L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Sorghastrum incompletum (J.Presl) Nash

Andropogon incompletus J.Presl
Latilo FHI63534, 1971, K
Total: 35; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 10, Oyo 1, Yobe 3.

Sorghastrum incompletum var. *africanum* (Franch.) ined.

Andropogon nutans var. *africanus* Franch.
Latilo, MG FHI 63534; 1971-10-25 [WAG.1452261]
Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 4, Yobe 1.

Sorghastrum stipoides (Kunth) Nash

Andropogon stipoides Kunth
de Leeuw 1133, 1964, K
Total: 9; Niger 5, Yobe 2.

Sorghum arundinaceum (Desv.) Stapf

Rhaphis arundinacea Desv.
Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70652; 1973-2-27 [WAG.1452394]
Total: 44; Anambra 3, Borno 8, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 3, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Sorghum bicolor (L.) Moench

Holcus sorghum L.
Johnston N26, 1950, K
Total: 305; Abia 1, Anambra 5, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 14, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 93, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 6, Lagos 6, Niger 10, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 8, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1.

Sorghum bicolor nothosubsp. *drummondii* (Nees ex Steud.) de Wet ex Davidse

Andropogon × *drummondii* Nees ex Steud.
Sampson 25, 1929, K
Total: 305; Abia 1, Anambra 5, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 14, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 93, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 6, Lagos 6, Niger 10, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 8, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1.

Sorghum bicolor subsp. *bicolor* — Introduced

Holcus sorghum L.
; -- [VIR301003599]
Total: 1.

Sorghum bicolor subsp. *verticilliflorum* (Steud.) de Wet ex Wiersema & J.Dahlb.

Andropogon verticilliflorus Steud.
Sampson 27, 1930, K
Total: 42; Anambra 3, Benue 1, Borno 9, Cross River 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 3.

Sorghum halepense (L.) Pers. — Introduced
Holcus halepensis L.

Marks GR17, 1982, K
Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Sporobolus africanus (Poir.) Robyns & Tournay

Agrostis africana Poir.
Wheeler Haines 144, 1964, K
Total: 27; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Plateau 4, Taraba 14.

Sporobolus centrifugus (Trin.) Nees

Vilfa centrifuga Trin.
F. Hepper 1789; 1958-1-27 [US 2433085]
Total: 3.

Sporobolus cordofanus (Hochst. ex Steud.) Hérincq ex Coss.

Triachyrum cordofanum Hochst. ex Steud.
Latilo FHI62594, 1969, K
Total: 5; Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Sporobolus festivus Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Dalziel 503, 1910, K
Total: 80; Bauchi 8, Benue 1, Borno 3, Edo 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Katsina 5, Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 9, Plateau 5, Sokoto 4, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Sporobolus helvolus (Trin.) T.Durand & Schinz

Vilfa helvola Trin.
Davey FHI27171, 1949, K
Total: 9; Borno 6, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Sporobolus indicus (L.) R.Br.

Agrostis indica L.
Jackson 2360, 1959, K
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Sporobolus infirmus Mez

Biswas 94, 1978, K
Total: 28; Bauchi 1, Katsina 2, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 2.

Sporobolus microprotus Stapf

Daggash FHI24886, 1949, K
Total: 6; Borno 2, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Yobe 1.

Sporobolus molleri Hack.

Biswas 215, s.dat., K
Total: 10; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Sporobolus montanus Engl.

Chapman 2744, 1972, K
Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Sporobolus myrianthus Benth.

Batten-Poole 126, 1946, K

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 4.

Sporobolus natalensis (Steud.) T.Durand & Schinz

Vilfa natalensis Steud.

Chapman 4456, 1976, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Sporobolus paniculatus (Trin.) T.Durand & Schinz

Vilfa paniculata Trin.

Hall 509, 1968, K

Total: 23; Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Niger 1, Ondo 3, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Sporobolus pectinellus Mez

Wit 465, 1971, K

Total: 31; Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 3, Ekiti 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Sporobolus pellucidus Hochst.

Wit FHI47315, 1972, K

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Sporobolus pilifer (Trin.) Kunth

Vilfa pilifera Trin.

Lawlor & Hall 336, 1962, K

Total: 1.

Sporobolus pyramidalis P.Beauv.

Lowe 1791, 1969, K

Total: 168; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Anambra 5, Bauchi 7, Benue 5, Borno 3, Cross River 5, Edo 8, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 4, Lagos 12, Nasarawa 3, Niger 11, Ogun 7, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 28, Plateau 13, Rivers 4, Taraba 8.

Sporobolus rigidifolius (Trin.) Mez ex Veldkamp

Vilfa rigidifolia Trin.

Hepper F.N. 1789; 1958-1-27 [BR0000021610325]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Sporobolus robustus Kunth

Baker 5, 1983, K

Total: 1; Rivers 1.

Sporobolus sanguineus Rendle

Lely 448, 1930, K

Total: 8; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 1.

Sporobolus spicatus (Vahl) Kunth

Agrostis spicata Vahl

Golding 18, s.dat., K

Total: 8; Borno 6.

Sporobolus stapfianus Gand.

Lely 196, 1921, K

Total: 2.

Sporobolus subglobosus A.Chev.

Clayton 599, 1956, K

Total: 23; Bayelsa 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Niger 9, Oyo 5.

Sporobolus subtilis Kunth

Wheeler Haines 359, 1965, K

Total: 3; Borno 1, Plateau 1.

Sporobolus subulatus Hack.

Chapman 3699, 1975, K

Total: 2; Abia 1, Taraba 1.

Sporobolus tenuissimus (Mart. ex Schrank) Kuntze

Panicum tenuissimum Mart. ex Schrank

Wheeler Haines 180, 1962, K

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Kwara 1.

Stapfochloa lamproparia (Stapf) H.Scholz

Chloris lamproparia Stapf

Jackson 110870, 1970, K

Total: 7; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Yobe 1.

Steinchisma laxum (Sw.) Zuloaga

Panicum laxum Sw.

Wheeler Haines 187, 1962, K

Total: 28; Abia 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Delta 2, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 1.

Stenotaphrum secundatum (Walter) Kuntze

Ischaemum secundatum Walter

Jeffreys 18, 1915, K

Total: 4; Bayelsa 1.

Stipagrostis acutiflora (Trin. & Rupr.) De Winter

Aristida acutiflora Trin. & Rupr.

J. Newby 2P191*; 1979-4-14 [US 3642818]

Total: 1; Zamfara 1.

Stipagrostis hirtigluma (Steud. ex Trin. & Rupr.) De Winter

Aristida hirtigluma Steud. ex Trin. & Rupr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Stipagrostis hirtigluma var. *hirtigluma*

Aristida hirtigluma Steud. ex Trin. & Rupr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Stipagrostis plumosa (L.) Munro ex
T.Anderson

Aristida plumosa L.

J. Newby 2P189; 1979-4-14 [US 3642817]

Total: 1; Zamfara 1.

Streptogyna crinita P.Beauv.

Tuley 1777, 1969, K

Total: 24; Bauchi 2, Cross River 4, Ebonyi 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Thelepogon elegans Roth

Lely 775, 1921, K

Total: 69; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 7, Gombe 3, Kaduna 9, Kano 1, Katsina 3, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 7, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 12, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Themeda triandra Forssk.

Tuley 1626, 1969, K

Total: 3; Niger 1, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Themeda villosa (Lam.) A.Camus

Anthistiria villosa Poir.

Chapman 2571, 1971, K

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Trachypogon chevalieri (Stapf) Jacq.-Fél.

Homopogon chevalieri Stapf

Biswas 104, 1978, K

Total: 6; Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Trachypogon spicatus (L.f.) Kuntze

Stipa spicata L.f.

Clayton 1388, 1957, K

Total: 14; Kaduna 8, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 3.

Tragus berteronianus Schult. — Introduced

A.B. Kadiri ; 2009-7-30 [1753]3808442712

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Trichantheium brazzavillense (Franch.)

Zuloaga & Morrone

Panicum brazzavillense Franch.

Lawlor & Hall 634, 1962, K

Total: 34; Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4.

Trichantheium dinklagei (Mez) Zuloaga &
Morrone

Panicum dinklagei Mez

Usang felix; 2015-10-8 [347] [3913474442]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Trichantheium eickii (Mez) Zuloaga

Trichantheium eickii Mez

Lowe, J. 2280; 1971-07-15 [K003406074]

Total: 4; Anambra 1, Edo 2, Taraba 1.

Trichantheium glaucocladum (C.E.Hubb.)

Zuloaga & Morrone

Panicum glaucocladum C.E.Hubb.

Hunder, FD 73; 1962-1-1 [WAG.1453132]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Trichantheium gracilicaule (Rendle)

Zuloaga & Morrone

Panicum gracilicaule Rendle

Peter & Tuley 16, 1965, K

Total: 17; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Benue 1, Delta 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Trichantheium mueense (Vanderyst)

Zuloaga & Morrone

Panicum mueense Vanderyst

Brenan 8896, 1948, K

Total: 6; Edo 5, Ogun 1.

Trichantheium nervatum (Franch.) Zuloaga
& Morrone

Isachne nervata Franch.

Latilo FHI37968, 1959, K

Total: 36; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 12, Lagos 5, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Trichantheium parvifolium (Lam.) Zuloaga
& Morrone

Panicum parvifolium Lam.

Latilo FHI64722, 1971, K

Total: 25; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Trichantheium praealtum (Afzel. ex Sw.)

Zuloaga & Morrone

Panicum praealtum Afzel. ex Sw.

Tuley 870, 1964, K

Total: 13; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Enugu 7, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Trichantheium strictissimum (Afzel. ex

Sw.) Zuloaga & Morrone

Panicum strictissimum Afzel. ex Sw.

Jones 6691, 1942, K

Total: 3; Anambra 2, Edo 1.

Trichantheium tenellum (Lam.) Zuloaga &
Morrone

Panicum tenellum Lam.

Keay FHI5500, 1947, K

Total: 14; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 2.

Trichoneura mollis (Kunth) Ekman

Leptochloa mollis Kunth

Moiser 135, 1921, K

Total: 4; Borno 2.

Trichopteryx elegantula (Hook.f.) Stapf

Arundinella elegantula Hook.f.

Tuley 978, 1964, K

Total: 12; Cross River 3, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Trichopteryx marungensis Chiov.

Daramola FHI62430, 1968, K

Total: 5; Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Trigonochloa uniflora (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

P.M.Peterson & N.Snow

Leptochloa uniflora Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Thomas 1000, 1911, K

Total: 15; Abia 1, Delta 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6.

Tripogon major Hook.f.

Tuley 2027, 1969, K

Total: 3; Kwara 1, Taraba 1.

Tripogon major subsp. *major*

Tripogonella minima (A.Rich.)

P.M.Peterson & Romasch.

Festuca minima A.Rich.

Wheeler Haines 331, 1964, K

Total: 23; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Tripsacum andersonii J.R.Gray —

Introduced

; -- [26521] [1989898596]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Trisetopsis elongata (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Röser & A.Wölk

Danthonia elongata Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Chapman 3619, 1974, K

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Tristachya superba (De Not.) Schweinf. & Asch.

Loudetia superba De Not.

Oche MG96, 1965, K

Total: 12; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 3, Niger 5.

Tristachya thollonii Franch.

Dalziel 886, 1913, K

Total: 4; Benue 2, Kaduna 2.

Triticum aestivum L. — Introduced

Sampson 15a, 1939, K

Total: 122; Borno 48, Jigawa 3, Kaduna 8, Katsina 25, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 24, Yobe 1.

Triticum aestivum subsp. *aestivum* —
Introduced

D.A. Sampson 15b; 1938-- [BM000086196]

Total: 5; Katsina 2, Sokoto 1.

Urelytrum agropyroides (Hack.) Hack.

Rottboellia agropyroides Hack.

Bumpus 29, 1944, K

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Urelytrum annuum Stapf

de Leeuw MRK150, 1969, K

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Urelytrum auriculatum C.E.Hubb. —

Endemic

Saunders 36A, 1932, K

Total: 6; Kaduna 2, Plateau 4.

Urelytrum digitatum K.Schum.

Chapman 5085, 1977, K

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Urelytrum giganteum Pilg.

Dalziel 902, 1912, K

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2.

Urelytrum muricatum C.E.Hubb.

Clayton 1299, 1957, K

Total: 28; Kaduna 13, Lagos 1, Plateau 2, Zamfara 3.

Urochloa arrecta (Hack. ex T.Durand & Schinz) Morrone & Zuloaga

Panicum arrectum Hack. ex T.Durand & Schinz

Wheeler Haines 334, 1964, K

Total: 4; Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Taraba 1.

Urochloa brizantha (A.Rich.) R.D.Webster

Panicum brizanthum A.Rich.

Hepper 1047, 1957, K

Total: 66; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 6, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 8, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 13, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Urochloa comata (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Sosef

Panicum comatum Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Oche 87, 1967, K

Total: 11; Adamawa 3, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Taraba 1.

Urochloa comorense (Mez) Oulo, Zon & Sosef

Panicum comorense Mez

Jackson, G. 1181168; 1968-11-18 [K003208122]

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Ogun 2.

Urochloa deflexa (Schumach.) H.Scholz

Panicum deflexum Schumach.

Cook 498, 1965, K

Total: 84; Bauchi 2, Borno 5, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 3, Enugu 1, Imo 3, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Niger 2, Ogun 9, Ondo 8, Oyo 21, Yobe 2.

Urochloa dictyoneura (Fig. & De Not.)

Veldkamp

Panicum dictyoneurum Fig. & De Not.

Lely 405, 1930, K

Total: 7; Nasarawa 1, Plateau 5.

Urochloa distachyoides (Stapf) Sosef

Brachiaria distachyoides Stapf

MacGregor 163, 1902, K

Total: 17; Borno 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 4.

Urochloa distachyos (L.) T.Q.Nguyen

Panicum distachyon L.

Biswas 120, 1978, K

Total: 10; Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 2.

Urochloa eminii (Mez) Davidse —

Introduced

Panicum eminii Mez

Akomaye Ferdinand 2019-02-01 [3909079442]

Total: 1.

Urochloa falcifera (Trin.) Zon

Panicum falciferum Trin.

Kamphorst, A 233; 1960-4-1 [WAG.1317323]

Total: 1.

Urochloa jubata (Fig. & De Not.) Sosef

Panicum jubatum Fig. & De Not.

Cook 420, 1965, K

Total: 85; Bauchi 4, Benue 4, Borno 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 11, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 7, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 16, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 12, Taraba 2.

Urochloa lachnantha (Hochst.) A.M.Torres & C.M.Morton — Introduced

Panicum lachnanthum Hochst.

Wit P., Gbile Z.O. & Daramola B.O. 1829; 1972-5-7 [BR0000024470377]

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Taraba 1.

Urochloa lata (Schumach.) C.E.Hubb.

Panicum latum Schumach.

Dalziel 252, 1908, K

Total: 77; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 15, Cross River 1, Imo 2, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 11, Lagos 2, Niger 16, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Sokoto 7, Taraba 2.

Urochloa mutica (Forssk.) T.Q.Nguyen

Panicum muticum Forssk.

Clayton 1450, 1957, K

Total: 25; Borno 10, Cross River 1, Katsina 1, Kebbi 2, Kwara 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2.

Urochloa ramosa (L.) T.Q.Nguyen

Panicum ramosum L.

de Leeuw 1088, 1964, K

Total: 9; Borno 5, Yobe 3.

Urochloa serrata (Thunb.) Sosef

Holcus serratus Thunb.

Clayton 1101, 1957, K

Total: 25; Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 5, Niger 10, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Urochloa stigmatisata (Mez) K.M.Ibrahim & P.M.Peterson

Panicum stigmatisatum Mez

de Leeuw 1052, 1964, K

Total: 36; Abia 1, Bauchi 3, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 3, Kwara 5, Niger 5, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 2.

Urochloa trichopus (Hochst.) Stapf

Panicum trichopus Hochst.

de Leeuw 1836, 1966, K

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Kwara 1.

Urochloa villosa (Lam.) T.Q.Nguyen

Panicum villosum Lam.

Jackson 2347, 1959, K

Total: 105; Abia 3, Anambra 4, Bauchi 7, Benue 1, Borno 2, Enugu 6, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 7, Lagos 13, Nasarawa 1, Niger 9, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 16, Plateau 4, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Urochloa xantholeuca (Hack.) H.Scholz

Panicum xantholeucum Hack.

Clayton 1254, 1957, K

Total: 38; Borno 8, Gombe 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 6, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 4, Niger 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Urochloa xantholeuca var. *xantholeuca*

Panicum xantholeucum Hack.

Denys E. 675; 1982-7-19 [BR0000024456258]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Vossia cuspidata (Roxb.) Griff.

Ischaemum cuspidatum Roxb.

Dalziel 291, 1908, K

Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Borno 9, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Sokoto 1.

Zea mays L. — Introduced

Thomas 553, 1911, K

Total: 16; Delta 1, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Zea mexicana (Schrad.) Kuntze —

Introduced

Euchlaena mexicana Schrad.

Gurli 134, 1967, K

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Zoysia matrella (L.) Merr. — Introduced

Agrostis matrella L.

Adetula; Onijamuwo [FHI.67571.0]

Total: 3; Oyo 2.

Zoysia matrella var. *matrella* — Introduced

Agrostis matrella L.

Lowe J.3919; 1980-5-26 [97703] [1989899656]

Total: 1.

CERATOPHYLLACEAE

Ceratophyllum demersum L.

Leonard, J.; 1968-2-28 [P03502937]

Total: 16; Borno 4, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

Ceratophyllum demersum var. *demersum*

Brenan J.P.M., Onochie C., Jones E.W. & Richards P.W. 8409; -- [BR0000014848803]

Total: 9; Borno 3, Edo 1, Niger 2.

Ceratophyllum muricatum Cham.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ceratophyllum muricatum subsp. *muricatum*

Literature

Total: 0.

Ceratophyllum submersum L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ceratophyllum submersum var. *submersum*

Literature

Total: 0.

PAPAVERACEAE

Argemone mexicana L. — Introduced

Küppers, K. 1902; 1997-04-23 (FR)

Total: 40; Abia 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Kano 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 6, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 5, Zamfara 2.

Chelidonium majus L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

MENISPERMACEAE

Chasmanthera dependens Hochst.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32975; 1981-6-23

[WAG.1100733]

Total: 71; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 11, Imo 7, Kaduna 2, Lagos 8, Ogun 8, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 21.

Cissampelos mucronata A.Rich.

Geerling, C 3412; 1971-1-15 [WAG.1100824]

Total: 73; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 4, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 13, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Plateau 9.

Cissampelos owariensis P.Beauv. ex DC.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 480; 1978-5-23

[WAG.1100983]

Total: 72; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 5, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 17, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Cocculus pendulus (J.R.Forst. & G.Forst.)

Diels

Epibaterium pendulum J.R.Forst. & G.Forst.

Rosevear D.R. FHI26611; 20-05-1949 [K]

Total: 1.

Dioscoreophyllum cumminsii (Stapf) Diels

Rhopalandra cumminsii Stapf

Keay, R.W.J.; Keay, J.M.; FHI16240; 1946-08-06 [K003546512]

Total: 11; Edo 2, Lagos 2, Oyo 5.

Dioscoreophyllum cumminsii var. *cumminsii*

Rhopalandra cumminsii Stapf

Dioscoreophyllum volkensii Engl.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32684; 1981-6-14
[WAG.1101240]
Total: 14; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 6,
Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Jateorhiza macrantha (Hook.f.) Exell &
Mendonça

Cocculus macranthus Hook.f.
Meer, PPC van 1869; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1101409]
Total: 46; Cross River 8, Edo 10, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1,
Kwara 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 6.

Jateorhiza palmata (Lam.) Miers —
Introduced

Menispermum palmatum Lam.
Literature
Total: 0.

Kolobopetalum auriculatum Engl.
Meer, PPC van 1292; 1971-4-15 [WAG.1101496]
Total: 16; Cross River 5, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Oyo 5.

Kolobopetalum chevalieri (Hutch. &
Dalziel) Troupin

Rhigiocarya chevalieri Hutch. & Dalziel
Onochie C.F.A. 33204; 1953-5-19 [17652]
Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Kolobopetalum ovatum Stapf
Onochie C.F.A. FHI33204; 19-05-1953 [K]
Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Penianthus longifolius Miers
Meer, PPC van 1151; 1971-4-3 [WAG.1101727]
Total: 6; Cross River 6.

Penianthus zenkeri (Engl.) Diels
Heptacyclum zenkeri Engl.
Meer, PPC van 1668; 1971-5-18 [WAG.1101725]
Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 3.

Perichasma laetificata Miers
Akpabla GK; 1948-03-16 [WAG.1101903]
Total: 21; Cross River 6, Edo 11.

Perichasma laetificata var. *laetificata*
Akpabla, GK 1093; 1948-3-16 [WAG.1101903]
Total: 1.

Perichasma laetificata var. *obovata* Kundu
& S.Guha — Endemic
Literature
Total: 0.

Platytnospora buchholzii (Engl.) Diels
Tinospora buchholzii Engl.
P.Wit & B.Daramole 1094 [K:MC-0093498]
Total: 3.

Rhigiocarya racemifera Miers
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63108; 1971-8-6
[WAG.1102028]
Total: 14; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo
6.

Sphenocentrum jollyanum Pierre
Odewo, TK; Adedeji 205; 1983-5-11 [WAG.1102144]
Total: 51; Cross River 1, Edo 5, Enugu 2, Lagos 5,
Ogun 7, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 14.

Stephania abyssinica (Quart.-Dill. &
A.Rich.) Walp.
Clypea abyssinica Quart.-Dill. & A.Rich.
Daramola, BO FHI 62745; 1969-5-20
[WAG.1102249]
Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Gombe 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Stephania abyssinica var. *abyssinica*
Clypea abyssinica Quart.-Dill. & A.Rich.
Medler J. 780; 12-04-1973 [K]
Total: 1.

Stephania abyssinica var. *tomentella* Oliv.
Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1965; 1972-5-10
[WAG.1102321]
Total: 8; Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Stephania cyanantha Welw. ex Hiern
Medler J. 592; 04-01-1971 [K]
Total: 4; Borno 3.

Stephania dinklagei (Engl.) Diels
Cissampelos dinklagei Engl.
Richards P.W. 3372; 1935-4-20 [BR0000018280760]
Total: 7; Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 2.

Synclisia scabrida Miers
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 311; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1102422]
Total: 13; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 2, Bauchi
1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1.

Syntriandrium preussii Engl.
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 422; 1977-10-18
[WAG.1102448]
Total: 18; Abia 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 5, Kogi
1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Tiliacora funifera Oliv.
Pilz, G.E.; 1977-10-22 [B 10 1013691]
Total: 12; Ogun 2, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.

Tiliacora nigerica Troupin — Endemic
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25493; 1949-10-28 [K000230121]
Total: 2; Ondo 2.

Tinospora bakis (A.Rich.) Miers

Cocculus bakis A.Rich.
1963; 1981-8-15 [1963]2302319478
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1.

Triclisia dictyophylla Diels
Richards P.W. 5092; 1955-2-23 [BR0000018261523]
Total: 13; Edo 8, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Triclisia gillettii (De Wild.) Staner
Tiliacora gillettii De Wild.
Latilo F.H.I. 33685; 1954-1-18 [8993] [912077530]
Total: 3; Edo 3.

Triclisia lanceolata Troupin
Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI17554; 11-02-1946 [K]
Total: 1; Niger 1.

Triclisia subcordata Oliv.
Geerling, C 4194; 1971-9-15 [WAG.1102807]
Total: 16; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 8.

RANUNCULACEAE

Clematis brachiata Thunb.
Sharland R.E. 1082; 1980-1 [K]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Clematis grandiflora DC.
Talbot 239 (K)
Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Clematis hirsuta Guill. & Perr.
Salzmann, U. 78; 1994-10-24 (FR)
Total: 39; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Gombe 5, Imo 1, Kaduna 10, Kogi 4, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 9.

Clematis hirsuta var. *hirsuta*
Salzmann, U. 78; 1994-10-24 (FR)
Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Clematis simensis Fresen.
Sanford 5494 (MO)
Total: 2; Enugu 1.

Clematis villosa DC.
Sanford 5162 (MO)
Total: 43; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Ondo 1, Plateau 14, Taraba 9.

Clematis villosa subsp. *kirkii* (Oliv.) Brummitt
Hepper, F.N. 1822; 1958-01-31
Total: 10; Kaduna 4, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Clematis villosa subsp. *oliveri* (Hutch.) Brummitt
Sanford 5162 (MO)
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Clematis villosa subsp. *villosa* — Introduced
Baker T.C.N. 1232; 08-08-1980 [ABUH]
Total: 20; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 4.

Delphinium dasycaulon Fresen.
Tamajong S.; 1948-12-30 [BR0000013217730]
Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Nigella sativa L. — Introduced
Ayinla Abdulbasit Abiodun LASU_0000176
Total: 2.

Ranunculus multifidus Forssk.
Hepper FN; 1958-03-01 [WAG.1372126]
Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Taraba 3.

Ranunculus volkensii Engl. — Introduced
HEPPER NGA-32556; 1957-01-01 [1948981225]
Total: 1.

Thalictrum rhynchocarpum Quart.-Dill. & A.Rich.
Meer PPC van; 1971-05-25 [WAG.1421987]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

PROTEACEAE

Faurea rochetiana (A.Rich.) Chiov. ex Pic.Serm.
Leucospermum rochetianum A.Rich.
Hepper, F.N. 1105; 1957-10-22 (P)
Total: 17; Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 5.

Grevillea robusta A.Cunn. ex R.Br. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 2096; 1966-1-1 [WAG.1450952]
Total: 1.

Protea madiensis Oliv.
Lely, H.V. 381; 1921-05-07 (K)
Total: 42; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 13, Taraba 2.

Protea madiensis subsp. *madiensis*
Elliott, W.R.; 1903-09-07 [K000423515]
Total: 20; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 2, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 9, Taraba 1.

Protea madiensis subsp. *occidentalis*
(Beard) Chisumpa & Brummitt

Keay R.W.J. FHI37809; 17-06-1960 [K]

Total: 12; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1,
Niger 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

BUXACEAE

Buxus acutata Friis

Macropodandra acuminata Gilg

Binuyo, A FHI 41207; 1959-4-9 [WAG.1496471]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Buxus macowanii Oliv. — Introduced

Amachi; Igboeli; 1958-7-28 [38278]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

DILLENIACEAE

Dillenia indica L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1330; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1781393]

Total: 5; Oyo 4.

Tetracera alnifolia Willd.

Latilo, MG FHI 53957; 1964-2-13 [WAG.1781067]

Total: 27; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1,
Gombe 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 7, Plateau 2, Rivers
1.

Tetracera alnifolia subsp. *alnifolia*

Latilo, MG FHI 53957; 1964-2-13 [WAG.1781067]

Total: 8.

Tetracera alnifolia var. *alnifolia*

Hepper F.N. 2224; -- [BR0000020406875]

Total: 8.

Tetracera alnifolia var. *podotricha* (Gilg)

Staner

Literature

Total: 0.

Tetracera eriantha (Oliv.) Hutch.

Tetracera obtusata var. *eriantha* Oliv.

Keay R.W.J. FHI28273; 16-12-1950 [K]

Total: 6; Cross River 2.

Tetracera podotricha Gilg

Onyeagocha S.C. FHI7787; 24-12-1944 [K]

Total: 15; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Cross
River 1, Enugu 1, Oyo 1.

Tetracera potatoria Afzel. ex G.Don

Miller S.N.; -- [BR0000015559791]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 2,
Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Tetracera stuhlmanniana Gilg

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 277; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1781309]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Ogun 1.

CRASSULACEAE

Crassula alba Forssk. — Introduced

Chapman J.W.F. 37; -- [BR0000015369352]

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Crassula vaginata Eckl. & Zeyh.

Literature

Total: 0.

Crassula vaginata subsp. *vaginata*

Literature

Total: 0.

Kalanchoe crenata (Andrews) Haw.

Verea crenata Andrews

Chapman, JD 2628; 1971-11-28 [WAG.1212024]

Total: 14; Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1,
Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Kalanchoe daigremontiana Raym.-Hamet &
H.Perrier — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Kalanchoe laciniata (L.) DC. — Introduced

Cotyledon laciniata L.

John D.; 1981-8-8 [1164]3460374340

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Kalanchoe lanceolata (Forssk.) Pers.

Cotyledon lanceolata Forssk.

Ohaeri A.O. 2709; 18-12-1980 [ABUH]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Kalanchoe pinnata (Lam.) Pers. —
Introduced

Cotyledon pinnata Lam.

Ibukun Oni; Mrs Lorge; 2016-4-15 [6970]3808438436

Total: 31; Cross River 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 17,
Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 3.

HALORAGACEAE

Laurembergia repens P.J.Bergius

Onochie C.F.A.; 1953-5-12 [32915] [2013041297]

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 2, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Laurembergia tetrandra (Schott) Kanitz

Haloragis tetrandra Schott

Hall, J.B.; Daramola, B.O. FHI67442; 1970-07-01 [K004251247]

Total: 1; Benue 1.

Myriophyllum verticillatum L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

PERIDISCACEAE

Medusandra richardsiana Brenan

Adebusuyi, JK FHI 44034; 1960-5-14

[WAG.1090489]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Soyauxia floribunda Hutch.

Dr.A.B.Kadiri; 2010-7-1 [3123] [3808438560]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Soyauxia gabonensis Oliv.

Ariwaodo, JO 681; 1977-5-1 [WAG.1090548]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4.

Soyauxia talbotii Baker f.

Daramola, BO; Emwiogbon, JA FHI 32796; 1961-1-29 [WAG.1090613]

Total: 14; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ogun 1, Osun 3.

Soyauxia velutina Hutch. & Dalziel

Unknown FHI 33188; -- [WAG.1090612]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 1.

SAXIFRAGACEAE

Saxifraga moschata Wulfen — Introduced

Unknown s.n.; -- [WAG.1299674]

Total: 1.

VITACEAE

Afrocayratia debilis (Baker) J.Wen &

L.M.Lu

Vitis debilis Baker

Meer, PPC van 828; 1968-7-11 [WAG.1194753]

Total: 21; Cross River 4, Edo 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3.

Afrocayratia delicatula (Willems) J.Wen &

Z.D.Chen

Cissus delicatula Willems

Geerling C.3560; 1971-7-20 [BR0000019033501]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Afrocayratia gracilis (Guill. & Perr.) J.Wen & Z.D.Chen

Cissus gracilis Guill. & Perr.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1554; 1966-5-25 [WAG.1194873]

Total: 13; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Afrocayratia ibuensis (Hook.f.) J.Wen & V.C.Dang

Cissus ibuensis Hook.f.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1873; 1972-5-8 [WAG.1194935]

Total: 20; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Niger 4, Ondo 1, Taraba 1.

Ampelocissus abyssinica (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Planch.

Vitis abyssinica Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ampelocissus africana (Lour.) Merr.

Botria africana Lour.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32979; 1981-6-23 [WAG.1871873]

Total: 23; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 6, Oyo 4, Sokoto 1.

Ampelocissus africana var. *africana*

Botria africana Lour.

Keay R.W.J. FHI22991; 14-05-1948 [K]

Total: 2; Gombe 1.

Ampelocissus bombycina (Baker) Planch.

Vitis bombycina Baker

Wit, HCD de; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 464; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1871830]

Total: 47; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 3, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 5.

Ampelocissus gracilipes Stapf

Onochie, C.F.A. 36465; 1957-3-6 [25682]912022316

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Ampelocissus leonensis (Hook.f.) Planch.

Cissus leonensis Hook.f.

Hambler, D.J. 443; 1958-5-18 [K000384304]

Total: 11; Kogi 1, Niger 8, Oyo 1.

Ampelocissus macrocirrha Gilg & M.Brandt

Onochie C.F.A. FHI36484x; 06-02-1957

[FHI036484X-1]

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Ampelocissus multistriata (Baker) Planch.

Vitis multistriata Baker

Odewo, TK; Adedeji FHI 100004; 1983-5-16

[WAG.1194633]

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Ogun 2.

Cayratia nervosa (Planch.) Suess. —

Introduced

Cissus nervosa Planch.

Forbes, H.O.; 1885-- [P02440256]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Cissus adnata Roxb. — Introduced

; -- [62485]2429009883

Total: 2; Bauchi 2.

Cissus angustata Ridl. — Introduced

Felix ; 2005-10-23 [350]3913474547

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Cissus aralioides (Welw. ex Baker) Planch.

Vitis aralioides Welw. ex Baker

Onochie C.; 1955-10-31 [BR0000020143619]

Total: 27; Bayelsa 1, Edo 2, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 10, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Cissus aralioides subsp. *aralioides*

Vitis aralioides Welw. ex Baker

Pilz, GE 1838; 1976-10-31 [WAG.1871661]

Total: 1.

Cissus arguta Hook.f.

Geerling, C 4088; 1971-8-20 [WAG0042263]

Total: 20; Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Lagos 2, Oyo 8.

Cissus barbeyana De Wild. & T.Durand

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65655; 1972-5-30

[WAG.1872163]

Total: 11; Benue 2, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1.

Cissus barteri (Baker) Planch.

Vitis barteri Baker

Meikle, RD 618; 1949-11-16 [WAG.1872144]

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 4.

Cissus caesia Afzel.

B.O. Daramola 12; 1979-7-26 [1347232]

[1258566245]

Total: 14; Cross River 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cissus cornifolia (Baker) Planch.

Vitis cornifolia Baker

Geerling, C 3482; 1971-3-21 [WAG.1872141]

Total: 21; Bauchi 6, Borno 1, Kaduna 6, Katsina 3, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Zamfara 1.

Cissus corylifolia (Baker) Planch.

Vitis corylifolia Baker

Dalziel, J.M.673; 1912-4-30 [15878] [912011407]

Total: 8; Benue 3, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Cissus diffusiflora (Baker) Planch.

Vitis diffusiflora Baker

Meikle, R.D.631; 1949-11-16 [9809] [912078465]

Total: 11; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Lagos 1, Ondo 2, Plateau 1.

Cissus dinklagei Gilg & M.Brandt —

Introduced

T. K. Odewo; 2009-12-24 [2099] [3808441114]

Total: 2; Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Cissus doeringii Gilg & M.Brandt

Okafor; Daramola B.O. FHI54614; 16-04-1964 [K]

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Cissus glaucophylla Hook.f.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI34235; 21-11-1954 [K]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Cissus kouandeensis A.Chev.

Wit, HCD de; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 462; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1871496]

Total: 4; Kogi 2.

Cissus leonardii Dewit

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65674; 1972-5-30

[WAG.1871327]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Ogun 1.

Cissus oreophila Gilg & M.Brandt

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86301;

1978-5-8 [WAG.1871158]

Total: 10; Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 1.

Cissus palmatifida (Baker) Planch.

Vitis palmatifida Baker

Pilz, GE 2074; 1977-5-21 [WAG.1871126]

Total: 24; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 1, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Oyo 5.

Cissus petiolata Hook.f.

Pilz, GE 1839; 1976-11-7 [WAG.1871027]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 8.

Cissus planchoniana Gilg

Meikle, RD 631; 1949-11-16 [WAG.1862705]

Total: 3; Edo 3.

Cissus polyantha Gilg & M.Brandt

K. Schmitt; T.O. IbiangSchmitt 162; 1994-11-29 [976590] [1261904286]

Total: 7; Bauchi 2, Cross River 4, Lagos 1.

Cissus populnea Guill. & Perr.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3834; 1971-7-28 [WAG.1201312]

Total: 43; Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 12, Taraba 1.

Cissus producta Afzel.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 293; 1983-5-14 [WAG.1201419]

Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Kogi 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 1.

Cissus quadrangularis L.

Lowe, J 1603; 1968-11-18 [WAG.1201481]

Total: 17; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 2.

Cissus quadrangularis var. *quadrangularis*

Cissus repanda var. *repanda* — Introduced

Cissus repanda Wight & Arn.

[K:EBC-000062484]

Total: 4; Bauchi 4.

Cissus rotundifolia Vahl — Introduced

Akomaye F.; 2019-04-01 [3903848495]

Total: 1.

Cissus rubiginosa (Welw. ex Baker) Planch.

Vitis rubiginosa Welw. ex Baker

Latillo s.n.; 1974-5-21 [1353239] [1258572695]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 3.

Cissus rufescens Guill. & Perr.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11329; 1977-4-4 [WAG.1201709]

Total: 35; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Delta 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 2, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Cyphostemma adenocaulis (Steud. ex

A.Rich.) Desc. ex Wild & R.B.Drumm.

Cissus adenocaulis Steud. ex A.Rich.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 242; 1977-10-10 [WAG.1194994]

Total: 23; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Niger 5, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cyphostemma adenocaulis subsp. *adenocaulis*

Cissus adenocaulis Steud. ex A.Rich.

Daramola 60; 1979-7-27 [1346165] [1258565070]

Total: 2; Kwara 1, Taraba 1.

Cyphostemma adenopodum (Sprague) Desc.

Cissus adenopoda Sprague

Pilz, GE 2112; 1977-6-11 [WAG.1861883]

Total: 15; Edo 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 9, Taraba 1.

Cyphostemma crinitum (Planch.) Desc.

Cissus crinita Planch.

Latilo, MG; Okeke, RE; Odewo, TK FHI 69379; 1974-5-21 [WAG.1872085]

Total: 16; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Plateau 3.

Cyphostemma crotalarioides (Planch.) Desc. ex Wild & R.B.Drumm.

Cissus crotalarioides Planch.

Wit, P; Geerling, C 1272; 1972-3-19 [WAG.1861801]

Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Niger 4, Plateau 4.

Cyphostemma cymosum (Schumach. & Thonn.) Desc.

Cissus cymosa Schumach. & Thonn.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cyphostemma cymosum subsp. *cymosum*

Cissus cymosa Schumach. & Thonn.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cyphostemma flavicans (Baker) Desc.

Vitis flavicans Baker

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI.35373; 1956-7-20 [28205]

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1.

Cyphostemma juncea (Webb) Desc. ex Wild & R.B.Drumm.

Cissus juncea Webb

Keay R.W.J.; 18-05-1950 [K]

Total: 18; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 6, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Cyphostemma juncea subsp. *jatrophioides* (Welw. ex Baker) Verdc.

Vitis jatrophioides Welw. ex Baker

Wit P.; Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O. 1865; 08-05-1972 [K]

Total: 8; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Taraba 1.

Cyphostemma juncea subsp. *juncea*

Cissus juncea Webb

Lely H.V. 206; 1929-4 [K]

Total: 1.

Cyphostemma lageniflorum (Gilg & M.Brandt) Desc.

Cissus lageniflora Gilg & M.Brandt

Keay R.W.J. FHI22570; 21-09-1948 [K]

Total: 3; Ondo 1.

Cyphostemma lelyi (Hutch.) Desc.

Cissus lelyi Hutch.

Dalziel J.M. 77; 20-05-1907 [K]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Plateau 5, Yobe 1.

Cyphostemma rubrosetosum (Gilg & M.Brandt) Desc.

Cissus rubrosetosa Gilg & M.Brandt

Daramola, B.O; 2012-5-30 [1237]3460379250

Total: 5; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Cyphostemma serpens subsp. *serpens* —

Introduced

Cissus serpens Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Latilo, MG; Okeke, RE; Odewo, TK FHI 69371; 1974-5-21 [WAG.1871508]

Total: 1.

Cyphostemma sokodense (Gilg & M.Brandt)

Desc.

Cissus sokodensis Gilg & M.Brandt

Pilz 2067; 1977-5-21 [1368286]1258589237

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Oyo 1.

Cyphostemma vogelii (Hook.f.) Desc.

Cissus vogelii Hook.f.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji ODA 232; 1983-5-12 [WAG.1862104]

Total: 20; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Cyphostemma waterlotii (A.Chev.) Desc.

Cissus waterlotii A.Chev.

Okafor; Daramola B.O. FHI54657; 23-04-1964 [K]

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Leea guineensis G.Don

Croat, TB 53480; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1866391]

Total: 104; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 15, Delta 2, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 4, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 10, Osun 3, Oyo 13, Plateau 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 13.

Rhoicissus tridentata (L.f.) Wild &

R.B.Drumm.

Rhus tridentata L.f.

Tuley, P.; 1591; 1969-06-05 [K004130757]

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Plateau 5.

Rhoicissus tridentata subsp. *cuneifolia*

(Eckl. & Zeyh.) Urton

Cissus cuneifolia Eckl. & Zeyh.

Tuley P. 1591; 05-09-1969 [K]

Total: 3; Plateau 2.

ZYGOPHYLLACEAE

Balanites aegyptiaca (L.) Delile

Ximenia aegyptiaca L.

Klee, M. 3; 1994-01-15 (FR)

Total: 16; Borno 1, Kano 4, Katsina 2, Niger 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Balanites aegyptiaca var. *aegyptiaca*

Ximenia aegyptiaca L.

Klee, M. 3; 1994-01-15 (FR)

Total: 1.

Balanites wilsoniana Dawe & Sprague

Keay FHI28198; 1950-12-09 (K)

Total: 12; Cross River 3, Oyo 2.

Balanites wilsoniana var. *glabripetalus*

Sands

Kennedy, J.D. 1949 (K)

Total: 5; Cross River 2.

Balanites wilsoniana var. *wilsoniana*

Keay FHI28198; 1950-12-09 (K)

Total: 1.

Guaiacum officinale L. — Introduced

Kennedy J.D. 286; 1928-12-11 [BR0000020445614]

Total: 4; Borno 1.

Kallstroemia pubescens (G.Don) Dandy —

Introduced

Tribulus pubescens G.Don

Latilo, M.G. FHI60987; 1967-09-22 (BR)

Total: 6; Gombe 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Tribulus terrestris L.

Neumann, K. 1409; 1994-10-11 (FR)

Total: 18; Borno 8, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Tribulus terrestris var. *terrestris*

Neumann, K. 1409; 1994-10-11 (FR)

Total: 1.

Tribulus zeyheri Sond.

Adebusuyi J.K. FHI57185; 08-11-1965 [K]

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Zygophyllum bruguieri (DC.) Christenh. &

Byng

Fagonia bruguieri DC.

IS. T 54; s.n [k]

Total: 1.

Zygophyllum coccineum L.

IS. T 50; s.n [K]

Total: 1.

Zygophyllum olivieri (DC.) Christenh. &

Byng

Fagonia olivieri DC.

IS. T 24; s.n [k]

Total: 1.

Zygophyllum paulayanum (J.Wagner &

Vierh.) Christenh. & Byng

Fagonia paulayana J.Wagner & Vierh.

[K]

Total: 2; Sokoto 1.

Zygophyllum qatarense Hadidi

IS. T 1; s.n [K]

Total: 3; Sokoto 2.

Zygophyllum simplex L.

s.coll. 51 [K005032165]

Total: 2; Sokoto 2.

FABACEAE

Abrus canescens Welw. ex Baker

Latilo Fhi 64726

Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 7, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Abrus fruticosus Wall. ex Wight & Arn.

— Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65800; 1972-10-7

[WAG.1000217]

Total: 7; Anambra 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Abrus melanospermus Hassk.

Total: 22; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Abrus melanospermus subsp. *suffruticosus*

(Boutique) D.K.Harder

Jackson 133

Total: 6; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Abrus melanospermus subsp. *tenuiflorus*

(Spruce ex Benth.) D.K.Harder

Latilo FHI 62268

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Abrus precatorius L. — Introduced

Gledhill, D 794; 1968-1-1 [WAG.1000359]

Total: 49; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Delta 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun 3, Oyo 11, Plateau 1.

Abrus precatorius subsp. *africanus* Verdc.

Binuyo, A. FHI 45450; 1962-09-17 [K003833960]

Total: 12; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Oyo 1.

Acacia auriculiformis A.Cunn. ex Benth. —

Introduced

Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O. 40; 1974-11-23

[73625][1944996875]

Total: 18; Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 1, Oyo 7.

Acacia pycnantha Benth. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Acaciella glauca (L.) L.Rico — Introduced

Mimosa glauca L.

O. Hagerup 681; 1927-12-6 [US 1596721]

Total: 41; Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 3, Ogun 7, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 18, Rivers 2.

Adenanthera pavonina L. — Introduced

Lawal A.O; 2010-8-14 [109732][1945002023]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 6.

Adenanthera pavonina var. *pavonina* —

Introduced

Adenocarpus mannii (Hook.f.) Hook.f.

Cytisus mannii Hook.f.

Chapman 4461

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 7.

Adenodolichos paniculatus (Hua) Hutch.

Dolichos paniculatus Hua

Latilo FHI 37972

Total: 46; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 4, Lagos 2, Niger 9, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 9, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Adenopodia scelerata (A.Chev.) Brenan

Entada scelerata A.Chev.

Onochie FHI 38598

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Aeschynomene abyssinica (A.Rich.) Vatke

Rueppelia abyssinica A.Rich.

Olorunfemi FHI 56977

Total: 10; Niger 1, Plateau 5, Sokoto 3.

Aeschynomene afraspera J.Léonard

Booker FHI 50807

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Aeschynomene americana L. — Introduced

Daramola et al. FHI 67284

Total: 8; Borno 1, Niger 1, Oyo 5.

Aeschynomene americana var. *americana*

— Introduced

Aeschynomene baumii Harms

Chapman 4476

Total: 13; Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Aeschynomene baumii var. *baumii*

Aeschynomene crassicaulis Harms

Latilo FHI 62642

Total: 8; Adamawa 3, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Sokoto 1.

Aeschynomene cristata Vatke

Latilo FHI 60581

Total: 6; Borno 1, Lagos 1, Rivers 1.

Aeschynomene elaphroxylon (Guill. & Perr.)
Taub.

Herminiera elaphroxylon Guill. & Perr.

Jackson FHI 14952

Total: 9; Borno 6, Niger 1.

Aeschynomene indica L.

Latilo, MG FHI 63470; 1971-10-19 [WAG.1000955]

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Gombe 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Aeschynomene kerstingii Harms —

Introduced

1995-9-30 [FR-0018962][3046114150]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Aeschynomene lateritia Harms

Soladoye et al. FHI 83579

Total: 23; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Aeschynomene mimosifolia Vatke —

Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [461A][1990271864]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Aeschynomene neglecta Hepper — Endemic

Lely 570

Total: 9; Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2.

Aeschynomene pfundii Taub.

Wickens 3510

Total: 5; Borno 3, Taraba 1.

Aeschynomene schimperi Hochst. ex

A.Rich.

Gbile & Daramola FHI 63595

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Aeschynomene sensitiva Sw.

Daramola FHI 46334

Total: 11; Edo 3, Gombe 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Plateau 1.

Aeschynomene uniflora E.Mey.

Lawlor & Hall 217

Total: 3; Bauchi 2.

Afroamphica africana (Hook.f.) H.Ohashi &
K.Ohashi

Shuteria africana Hook.f.

Tuley, P.; Jackson, J.K.; Magaji, S.O. 1990; 1969-11-19 [K003987704]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Afzelia africana Sm. ex Pers.

Chapman 3851

Total: 121; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 4, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Lagos 2, Niger 14, Ogun 15, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 26, Plateau 7, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Afzelia bella Harms

Daramola FHI 55208

Total: 94; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 13, Delta 5, Edo 37, Imo 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 7, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 5.

Afzelia bipindensis Harms

Brenan 8889

Total: 48; Edo 22, Kaduna 5, Lagos 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Plateau 2.

Afzelia pachyloba Harms

Ekwuno et al. FHI 87497

Total: 34; Cross River 2, Edo 16, Ogun 5, Ondo 6, Oyo 3.

Aganope gabonica (Baill.) Polhill

Andira gabonica Baill.

Daramola FHI 56435

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 6, Osun 1.

Aganope impressa (Dunn) Polhill

Ostryoderris impressa Dunn

Onochie FHI 67762

Total: 24; Cross River 5, Edo 5, Plateau 1.

Aganope leucobotrya (Dunn) Polhill

Ostryoderris leucobotrya Dunn

Daramola FHI 55519

Total: 6; Abia 2, Anambra 2, Imo 1, Nasarawa 1.

Aganope stuhlmannii (Taub.) Adema

Deguelia stuhlmannii Taub.

Latilo FHI 62559

Total: 15; Benue 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 2, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 3.

Airyantha schweinfurthii (Taub.) Brummitt

Baphia schweinfurthii Taub.

Richards P.W. [BR0000016708303]

Total: 52; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 9, Anambra 4, Cross River 13, Enugu 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 2.

Airyantha schweinfurthii subsp. *confusa*

(Hutch. & Dalziel) Brummitt

Baphia confusa Hutch. & Dalziel

Daramola & Okafor FHI 72426

Total: 23; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Enugu 2, Ondo 1, Rivers 1.

Alantsilodendron pilosum Villiers —

Introduced

Dichrostachys cinerea R.Vig.

Denys E. 647; -- [BR0000015848802]

Total: 4.

Albizia adianthifolia (Schumach.) W.Wight

Mimosa adianthifolia Schumach.

Gbile FHI 84303

Total: 54; Anambra 6, Cross River 1, Edo 9, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Albizia adianthifolia var. *adianthifolia*

Mimosa adianthifolia Schumach.

Albizia adianthifolia var. *intermedia* (De

Wild. & T.Durand) Villiers

Albizia intermedia De Wild. & T.Durand

Emwiogbon FHI 45512

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Taraba 1.

Albizia altissima Hook.f.

Latilo FHI 47108

Total: 16; Anambra 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 2, Enugu 3, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Albizia chevalieri Harms

Wit et al. FHI 51203

Total: 28; Bauchi 4, Borno 3, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Yobe 1.

Albizia chinensis (Osbeck) Merr. —

Introduced

Mimosa chinensis Osbeck

Lisowski S. ; 1973-03-16 [POZG-V-0063748]

Total: 2; Katsina 2.

Albizia coriaria Welw. ex Oliv.

Keay & Taylor FHI 37850C

Total: 6; Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Taraba 1.

Albizia dinklagei (Harms) Harms

Mimosa dinklagei Harms

Olateju Monsurat Abiola; Dr. Kadiri; 2010-03-13 [LUH.3157.0]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Albizia ferruginea (Guill. & Perr.) Benth.

Inga ferruginea Guill. & Perr.

Onochie FHI 30147

Total: 21; Edo 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Albizia glaberrima (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Benth.

Mimosa glaberrima Schumach. & Thonn.

Keay FHI 37699

Total: 19; Anambra 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 5.

Albizia glaberrima var. *glaberrima*

Mimosa glaberrima Schumach. & Thonn.

Albizia gummifera (J.F.Gmel.) C.A.Sm.

Sassa gummifera J.F.Gmel.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000016023321]

Total: 26; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Lagos 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 10.

Albizia gummifera var. *ealensis* (De Wild.)

Brenan

Albizia ealensis De Wild.

Talbot, P.; 1314; 1911-01-01 [K003114256]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Albizia gummifera var. *gummifera*

Sassa gummifera J.F.Gmel.

Chapman FHI 73721

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Albizia laurentii De Wild.

Wilks, C 2748; 1993-8-14 [PRE0911959-0]

Total: 1; Yobe 1.

Albizia lebbeck (L.) Benth. — Introduced

Mimosa lebbeck L.

[FHI.55980.0]

Total: 147; Adamawa 4, Anambra 9, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 2, Cross River 5, Edo 9, Enugu 4, Kaduna 5,

Kano 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 8, Lagos 8, Ogun 12, Ondo 5, Oyo 44, Plateau 7, Rivers 1, Sokoto 7, Taraba 1.

Albizia malacophylla (A.Rich.) Walp.

Inga malacophylla A.Rich.

Keay FHI 23435

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Albizia malacophylla var. *malacophylla*

Inga malacophylla A.Rich.

Albizia malacophylla var. *ugandensis* Baker

f.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI23435; 1948-02-26 [K003114263]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Albizia niopoides (Spruce ex Benth.)

Burkart — Introduced

Pithecellobium niopoides Spruce ex Benth.

Ross, A.F.; R25; 1931-11-20 [K003047648]

Total: 2.

Albizia niopoides var. *niopoides* —

Introduced

Pithecellobium niopoides Spruce ex Benth.

Albizia odoratissima (L.f.) Benth. —

Introduced

Mimosa odoratissima L.f.

Stanfield D.P.; 1962-03-31 [FHI.45743-1]

Total: 5; Oyo 5.

Albizia zygia (DC.) J.F.Macbr.

Inga zygia DC.

Emwiogbon FHI 47469

Total: 67; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Ekiti 3, Enugu 9, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 13, Plateau 3, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Alysicarpus glumaceus (Vahl) DC.

Hedysarum glumaceum Vahl

Latilo FHI 62696

Total: 25; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Borno 3, Gombe 3, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Alysicarpus glumaceus subsp. *glumaceus*

Hedysarum glumaceum Vahl

Alysicarpus ovalifolius (Schumach.)

J.Léonard

Hedysarum ovalifolium Schumach.

Okeke et al. FHI 71288

Total: 51; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 7, Gombe 4, Kano 5, Kogi 5, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 4, Zamfara 2.

Alysicarpus rugosus (Willd.) DC.

Hedysarum rugosum Willd.

Lowe 1850

Total: 48; Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 10, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Yobe 3, Zamfara 1.

Alysicarpus rugosus subsp. *rugosus*

Hedysarum rugosum Willd.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000016716223]

Total: 2.

Alysicarpus vaginalis (L.) DC.

Hedysarum vaginae L.

Hill 36

Total: 4; Kaduna 1.

Alysicarpus vaginalis var. *vaginalis*

Hedysarum vaginae L.

Alysicarpus zeyheri Harv.

Hall 1799

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Amblygonocarpus andongensis (Welw. ex Oliv.) Exell & Torre

Tetrapleura andongensis Welw. ex Oliv.

Latilo & Taylor FHI 43238

Total: 22; Abia 1, Bauchi 3, Gombe 5, Niger 2, Oyo 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2.

Amphimas ferrugineus Pierre ex Pellegr. —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Amphimas pterocarpoides Harms

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 93639

Total: 22; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 8.

Andira inermis (W.Wright) DC.

Geoffroea jamaicensis var. inermis W.Wright

Stanfield FGI 45736

Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 3, Niger 1, Osun 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Andira inermis subsp. *inermis*

Geoffroea jamaicensis var. inermis W.Wright

Iyizoba, A.A.N.; FHI20813; 1952-01-01

[K002501756]

Total: 5; Cross River 3, Niger 1.

Andira inermis subsp. *rooseveltii* (De Wild.)

J.B.Gillett ex Polhill

Milletia rooseveltii De Wild.

Chapman 4203

Total: 5; Osun 1, Taraba 1.

Angylocalyx oligophyllus (Baker) Baker f.

Sophora oligophylla Baker

Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 67789

Total: 49; Abia 3, Benue 1, Cross River 8, Edo 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 11, Rivers 2.

Angylocalyx pynaertii De Wild.

Daramola FHI 45667

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2.

Angylocalyx talbotii Baker f. ex Hutch. &

Dalziel

Talbot 239

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Annea afzelii (Oliv.) Mackinder & Wieringa

Cynometra afzelii Oliv.

Latilo FHI 40349

Total: 68; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 12, Edo 20, Imo 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 4, Ondo 6, Oyo 4, Rivers 1.

Anthonotha crassifolia (Baill.) J.Léonard

Vouapa crassifolia Baill.

Lowe 2447

Total: 17; Cross River 2, Edo 3, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Anthonotha fragrans (Baker f.) Exell & Hillc.

Macrolobium fragrans Baker f.

Onochie FHI 36128X

Total: 6; Cross River 4.

Anthonotha lamprophylla (Harms)

J.Léonard

Macrolobium lamprophyllum Harms

Talbot 272

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1.

Anthonotha macrophylla P.Beauv.

Daramola FHI 47052

Total: 124; Abia 4, Adamawa 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 9, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 17, Delta 3, Edo 29, Ekiti 4, Enugu 3, Imo 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 6, Ondo 6, Osun 3, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 9.

Anthonotha noldeae (Roszbach) Exell & Hillc.

Macrolobium noldeae Roszbach

Nodza G; 2020-07-11 [3999609371]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Taraba 2.

Antopetitia abyssinica A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Aphanocalyx microphyllus (Harms)

Wieringa

Monopetalanthus microphyllus Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Aphanocalyx microphyllus subsp. *microphyllus*

Monopetalanthus microphyllus Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Arachis hypogaea L. — Introduced

Fagbemi FHI 89893

Total: 36; Borno 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Osun 2, Oyo 3.

Arachis prostrata Benth. — Introduced

CNF; 1977-2-13 [1844890388]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Argyrolobium aequinoctiale Welw. ex

Baker

Chapman 2854

Total: 7; Taraba 5.

Aubrevillea kerstingii (Harms) Pellegr.

Piptadenia kerstingii Harms

Okafor FHI 41773

Total: 19; Adamawa 2, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Aubrevillea platicarpa Pellegr.

Daramola FHI 55978

Total: 1.

Baikiaea insignis Benth.

Talbot 1749

Total: 13; Cross River 4, Lagos 3, Plateau 1.

Baikiaea plurijuga Harms — Introduced

Daramola B.O.; 1979-5- [91301]1944999402

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Baphia capparidifolia Baker

Vogel; s.n.; 1843-01-01 [K000555652]

Total: 40; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 14, Edo 1, Enugu 3, Imo 2, Oyo 1, Rivers 3.

Baphia capparidifolia subsp. *polygalacea*

Brummitt

Okeke et al. FHI 72617

Total: 36; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 13, Enugu 3, Imo 2, Oyo 1, Rivers 2.

Baphia dewildeana Soladoye

Daramola et al. FHI 55238

Total: 1.

Baphia eriocalyx Harms

Van Meer 1922

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Baphia latiloi Soladoye

Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 67722

Total: 4; Anambra 1, Cross River 3.

Baphia laurifolia Baill.

Latilo FHI 41349

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Osun 1.

Baphia leptobotrys Harms

Talbot 591

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Baphia leptostemma Baill.

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Baphia leptostemma subsp. *gracilipes*

(Harms) Soladoye

Latilo & Onyeachusim FHI 53968

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Baphia leptostemma subsp. *leptostemma*

Baphia mambillensis Soladoye

Chapman 3138

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Baphia maxima Baker

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 90677

Total: 13; Cross River 8.

Baphia multiflora Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Baphia multiflora subsp. *multiflora*

Literature

Total: 0.

Baphia nitida G.Lodd.

Olorunfemi FHI 41506

Total: 189; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 6, Borno 2, Cross River 23, Delta 5, Ebonyi 1, Edo 10, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 18, Niger 9, Ogun 18, Ondo 2, Osun 9, Oyo 49, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Baphia obanensis Baker f.

Talbot 1682

Total: 1.

Baphia pubescens Hook.f.

Eimunjeze et al. FHI 69880

Total: 62; Anambra 3, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 11, Enugu 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Niger 9, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2.

Bauhinia acuminata L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1355; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1703011]

Total: 5; Ogun 3, Oyo 2.

Bauhinia galpinii N.E.Br. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1357; 1966-04-04

[WAG.1702951]

Total: 5; Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Bauhinia monandra Kurz — Introduced

Keay & Okeke FHI 18249

Total: 29; Enugu 3, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 14.

Bauhinia purpurea L. — Introduced

[DNS.LUH:6646]

Total: 5; Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Bauhinia rufescens Lam.

Latilo et al. FHI 693982

Total: 56; Adamawa 6, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 9, Cross River 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 6, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Sokoto 8, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Bauhinia tomentosa L. — Introduced

Jackson 5200

Total: 28; Kaduna 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 8, Ondo 1, Oyo 12, Rivers 1.

Bauhinia variegata L. — Introduced

Ross 18

Total: 5; Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Bauhinia variegata var. *candida* Voigt — Introduced

[11752]2821275862

Total: 1.

Bauhinia variegata var. *variegata* — Introduced

Total: 4.

Berlinia auriculata Benth.

Okafor et al. FHI 60179

Total: 25; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Imo 1, Rivers 8.

Berlinia bracteosa Benth.

Daramola FHI 55577

Total: 25; Abia 4, Cross River 14, Niger 4.

Berlinia confusa Hoyle

Stanfield FHI 45615

Total: 57; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 10, Edo 24, Enugu 4, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2.

Berlinia congolensis (Baker f.) Keay

Berlinia heudelotiana var. *congolensis* Baker f.

Talbot 3110

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Ogun 2.

Berlinia coriacea Keay

Onochie FHI 31230

Total: 36; Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 19, Lagos 3, Ogun 4.

Berlinia craibiana Baker f.

Hall FHI 88166

Total: 64; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 17, Edo 27, Enugu 1, Niger 1, Rivers 1.

Berlinia giorgii De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Berlinia grandiflora (Vahl) Hutch. & Dalziel

Westia grandiflora Vahl

Okafor FHI 36866

Total: 223; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 21, Benue 3, Cross River 8, Delta 5, Edo 8, Ekiti 4, Enugu 21, Kaduna 2, Kogi 6, Kwara 3, Lagos 13, Nasarawa 4, Niger 14, Ogun 10, Ondo 4, Osun 4, Oyo 29, Plateau 7, Rivers 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 4.

Berlinia hollandii Hutch. & Dalziel

Holland 30

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Biancaea decapetala (Roth) O.Deg. — Introduced

Reichardia decapetala Roth

Chapman FHI46186

Total: 11; Adamawa 2, Edo 1, Ondo 1, Taraba 6.

Biancaea sappan (L.) Tod. — Introduced

Caesalpinia sappan L.

Ross A.F.; 1931-11-20 [FHI.9802.0]

Total: 5; Edo 1, Ogun 4.

Bobgunnia fistuloides (Harms) J.H.Kirkbr. & Wiersema

Swartzia fistuloides Harms

Kennedy 1696

Total: 5; Cross River 1.

Bobgunnia madagascariensis (Desv.)

J.H.Kirkbr. & Wiersema

Swartzia madagascariensis Desv.

Oni FHI 34561

Total: 45; Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Cross River 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 10, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Bouffordia dichotoma (Willd.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi — Introduced

Hedysarum dichotomum Willd.

IL-17772

Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Bowringia mildbraedii Harms

Ariwaodo FHI 88641

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Ondo 3.

Brachystegia eurycoma Harms

Oseni FHI 40290

Total: 80; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 3, Enugu 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 9, Osun 6, Oyo 23, Plateau 3, Taraba 5.

Brachystegia kennedyi Hoyle

Latilo FHI 58861

Total: 51; Cross River 2, Edo 28, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Brachystegia leonensis Hutch. & Burt Davy — Introduced

J. D. Kennedy [US 1719566]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1.

Brachystegia nigerica Hoyle & A.P.D.Jones — Endemic

Soladoye & Daramola FHI 85569

Total: 84; Abia 2, Anambra 8, Cross River 7, Edo 12, Ekiti 2, Kwara 1, Ogun 8, Ondo 11, Osun 1, Oyo 17, Rivers 2.

Brownea ariza Benth. — Introduced

Kennedy J.D. 27; 1928-1- [1428-1]1949702966

Total: 2; Ogun 2.

Burkea africana Hook.

Stanfield FHI 44412

Total: 86; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 7, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Enugu 5, Gombe 2, Kaduna 6, Kano 6, Kogi 3, Kwara 8, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Oyo 15, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Butea monosperma (Lam.) Kuntze — Introduced

Erythrina monosperma Lam.

Hereźniak J.; 1975-2-1 [POZG-V-0040907]

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Caesalpinia pulcherrima (L.) Sw. —

Introduced

Poinciana pulcherrima L.

Jackson 5199

Total: 40; Cross River 1, Delta 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 11, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 17, Rivers 1.

Cajanus cajan (L.) Huth — Introduced

Cytisus cajan L.

Ariwaodo FHI 89237

Total: 37; Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 4, Osun 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Cajanus kerstingii Harms

Soladoye et al. FHI 87492

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Borno 2.

Cajanus scarabaeoides (L.) Thouars —

Introduced

Dolichos scarabaeoides L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cajanus scarabaeoides var. *scarabaeoides*

— Introduced

Dolichos scarabaeoides L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Calliandra haematocephala Hassk. —

Introduced

Alli O.W; 1982-03-27 [LUH.1166.0]

Total: 11; Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 2.

Calliandra haematocephala var.

haematocephala — Introduced

Total: 11.

Calliandra surinamensis Benth. —

Introduced

Daramola, B.O.; FHI55525; 1965-02-17

[K003027945]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Calopogonium mucunoides Desv. —

Introduced

Soladoye & Daramola FHI 92629

Total: 41; Anambra 2, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 1.

Calpocalyx cauliflorus Hoyle

Keay FHI 28151

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 4.

Calpocalyx dinklagei Harms

Okafor et al. FHI 56040

Total: 15; Abia 1, Cross River 8, Enugu 1, Osun 1.

Calpocalyx winkleri (Harms) Harms

Piptadenia winkleri Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Camoensia brevicalyx Benth.

Olorunfemi et al. OAF/85

Total: 6; Abia 2, Cross River 4.

Canavalia africana Dunn

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 197; 1971-9-14 [WAG.1006611]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1.

Canavalia ensiformis (L.) DC. —

Introduced

Dolichos ensiformis L.

Hepper 3857

Total: 25; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Canavalia regalis Dunn

Barter, C. [K000263359]

Total: 4.

Canavalia rosea (Sw.) DC.

Dolichos roseus Sw.

Daramola FHI 46335

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2.

Cassia arereh Delile

Chapman FHI 56076

Total: 25; Adamawa 5, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1.

Cassia fistula L. — Introduced

[FHI.36568.0]

Total: 22; Enugu 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 12, Plateau 1.

Cassia javanica L. — Introduced

Onyeachusim H.D.; Ekwuno; 1960-04-07

[FHI.58282.0]

Total: 13; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 5.

Cassia javanica subsp. *agnes* (de Wit)

K.Larsen — Introduced

Gledhill 1011

Total: 1.

Cassia javanica subsp. *nodosa* (Buch.-Ham. ex Roxb.) K.Larsen & S.S.Larsen —

Introduced

Ohaeri A.O. 425; 16-04-1971 [ABUH]

Total: 1.

Cassia mannii Oliv.

Rosevear 20/28

Total: 2; Imo 1.

Cassia roxburghii DC. — Introduced

Cassia marginata Roxb.

; -- [11843]2821321862

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Cassia sieberiana DC.

Latilo FHI 43899

Total: 98; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 7, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Niger 6, Ogun 8, Osun 2, Oyo 18, Sokoto 4, Taraba 5, Yobe 1, Zamfara 8.

Cenostigma pluviosum var. *peltophoroides* (Benth.) Gagnon & G.P.Lewis —

Introduced

Caesalpinia peltophoroides Benth.

Daramola B.O.; Odewo T.K. ; 1974-04-19 [72531-1]

Total: 1.

Centrosema molle Mart. ex Benth. —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Centrosema plumieri (Turpin ex Pers.)

Benth. — Introduced

Clitoria plumieri Turpin ex Pers.

Binuyo FHI 45435

Total: 15; Borno 1, Edo 7, Gombe 1, Oyo 1.

Centrosema pubescens Benth. — Introduced

Ekwuno FHI 95647

Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 12.

Centrosema virginianum (L.) Benth. —

Introduced

Clitoria virginiana L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Chamaecrista absus (L.) H.S.Irwin &

Barneby — Introduced

Cassia absus L.

Latilo FHI 63475

Total: 21; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 5, Sokoto 3.

Chamaecrista absus var. *absus* —

Introduced

Cassia absus L.

Total: 21.

Chamaecrista kirkii (Oliv.) Standl.

Cassia kirkii Oliv.

Daramola FHI 78609

Total: 57; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Cross River 2, Ekiti 4, Enugu 1, Imo 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 5, Niger 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 14.

Chamaecrista kirkii var. *guineensis* (Steyaert) Lock

Cassia kirkii var. *guineensis* Steyaert

Talbot, P.A. s.n.; 1912-01-01 [K002504227]

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Chamaecrista kirkii var. *kirkii*

Cassia kirkii Oliv.

Levy, H.V.; P747; 1930-09-01 [K002504212]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Plateau 2.

Chamaecrista mimosoides (L.) Greene

Cassia mimosoides L.

Daramola FHI 46330

Total: 249; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Bayelsa 2, Benue 1, Borno 12, Cross River 21, Delta 6, Edo 11, Ekiti 1, Enugu 15, Gombe 1, Imo 4, Kaduna 11, Kano 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 11, Kwara 20, Lagos 6, Niger 30, Ogun 9, Ondo 5, Osun 3, Oyo 16, Plateau 10, Rivers 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 9, Zamfara 1.

Chamaecrista nigricans (Vahl) Greene

Cassia nigricans Vahl

Fagbemi FHI 89870

Total: 36; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 16, Niger 5, Plateau 6.

Chamaecrista rotundifolia (Pers.) Greene — Introduced

Cassia rotundifolia Pers.

Jackson 178

Total: 125; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 4, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 10, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 10, Lagos 7, Niger 3, Ogun 9, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 25, Plateau 12, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Chamaecrista rotundifolia var. *rotundifolia* — Introduced

Cassia rotundifolia Pers.

Clitoria falcata Lam. — Introduced

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 92194

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Ondo 1.

Clitoria falcata var. *falcata* — Introduced

Talbot, P.; 1305; 1911-01-01 [K003219031]

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Clitoria falcata var. *glabrescens* (Verdc.)

Fantz — Introduced

Clitoria rubiginosa var. *glabrescens* Verdc.

Foster, E.W. 319; 1907-08-20 [K003219038]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Clitoria laurifolia Poir. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Clitoria ternatea L.

Olorunfemi FHI 57065

Total: 21; Gombe 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Zamfara 1.

Copaifera mildbraedii Harms

Keay FHI 21591

Total: 4; Ogun 1.

Cordyla pinnata (A.Rich.) Milne-Redh.

Calycandra pinnata A.Rich.

Stanfield FHI 55965

Total: 14; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 5, Oyo 3.

Craibia atlantica Dunn

Patel FHI 51721

Total: 30; Adamawa 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 4, Lagos 3, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 6, Taraba 2.

Craibia simplex Dunn

Milne 1866

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Crotalaria alata Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Crotalaria anthyllopsis Welw. ex Baker

Jackson FHI 21843

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 3.

Crotalaria arenaria Benth.

Golding 51

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Borno 1.

Crotalaria atrorubens Hochst. ex Benth.

Gbile & Daramola FHI 63638

Total: 33; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Gombe 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Crotalaria bamendae Hepper

Latilo FHI 77401

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Crotalaria barkae Schweinf.

Latilo FHI 62843

Total: 11; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Yobe 1.

Crotalaria barkae subsp. *barkae*

Total: 11.

Crotalaria bongensis Baker f.

Gbile et al. FHI 64603

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Crotalaria brevidens Benth.

Sharland 962

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1.

Crotalaria calycina Schrank

Jackson 3

Total: 11; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Osun 1.

Crotalaria caudata Welw. ex Baker

Gbile ZO; Daramola BO; 1970-04-03

[WAG.1008899]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Crotalaria cephalotes Steud. ex A.Rich.

Latilo FHI 45493

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Crotalaria chrysochlora Baker f. ex Harms

— Introduced

Nodza, Ogundipe; 2012-06-10 [3999609580]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Crotalaria cleomifolia Welw. ex Baker

Lawlor & Hall 747

Total: 10; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Crotalaria comosa Baker

Tuley 930

Total: 13; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Crotalaria confusa Hepper

Soladoye & Daramola FHI 86068

Total: 39; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 5, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Crotalaria cuspidata Taub.

Stanfield s.n.

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1.

Crotalaria cylindrocarpa DC.

Latilo FHI 54699

Total: 41; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 9, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Crotalaria doniana Baker

Olorunfemi FHI 55652

Total: 10; Cross River 5, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Crotalaria glauca Willd.

Chapman 5030

Total: 32; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Crotalaria glaucifolia Baker

Chapman, H.M. 98 [K003766516]

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Crotalaria goreensis Guill. & Perr.

Oyayomi et al. FHI 79519

Total: 60; Bauchi 3, Borno 5, Edo 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Crotalaria graminicola Taub. ex Baker f.

Lawlor & hall 152

Total: 34; Bauchi 4, Kaduna 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Plateau 14, Taraba 1.

Crotalaria hyssopifolia Klotzsch

Soladoye et al. FHI 83628

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 3, Plateau 3.

Crotalaria incana L.

Ebun Akinyemi; 1968-03-17 [LUH.2171.0]

Total: 10; Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Crotalaria incana subsp. *purpurascens*

(Lam.) Milne-Redh.

Odewo FHI 97383

Total: 8; Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Crotalaria juncea L. — Introduced

Eijnatten CLM van; 1960-01-01 [WAG.1009890]

Total: 5; Osun 1, Oyo 1, Zamfara 1.

Crotalaria lachnocarpoides Engl. —

Introduced

Ariwaodo 190; 1977-12-19 MO3478665[1260900143]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Crotalaria lachnophora A.Rich.

Latilo FHI 64778

Total: 22; Bauchi 4, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Crotalaria lachnosema Stapf

Latilo FHI 61338

Total: 45; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 11, Kogi 3, Niger 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 11, Taraba 4.

Crotalaria lanceolata E.Mey. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Crotalaria lanceolata subsp. *lanceolata* —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Crotalaria ledermannii Baker f.

Daramola B.O.; 1958-12-30 [BR0000018413540]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Crotalaria leprieurii Guill. & Perr.

Lawlor & Hall 431

Total: 29; Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Crotalaria longithyrsa Baker f.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2119; 1966-11-02

[WAG.1010353]

Total: 0; Oyo 2.

Crotalaria macrocalyx Benth.

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 94282

Total: 45; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 13, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Plateau 1, Yobe 2.

Crotalaria microcarpa Hochst. ex Benth.

Hepper 3859

Total: 53; Adamawa 7, Bauchi 8, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Crotalaria naragutensis Hutch.

Latilo FHI 63486

Total: 71; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 4, Gombe 4, Kaduna 11, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Niger 8, Oyo 5, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Crotalaria ochroleuca G.Don

Daramola & Binuyo FHI 61271

Total: 18; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Crotalaria ononoides Benth.

Latilo FHI 73591

Total: 15; Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 4.

Crotalaria orthoclada Welw. ex Baker

Chapman 3610

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Nasarawa 1, Taraba 6.

Crotalaria pallida Aiton

-. Claessens [US 1270219]

Total: 41; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Crotalaria pallida var. *pallida*

Hepper 1106

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Crotalaria parvula Welw. ex Baker

Latilo FHI 77343

Total: 2.

Crotalaria quartiniana A.Rich.

Hepper F.N.; 1957-11-29 [BR0000018390292]

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Crotalaria recta Steud. ex A.Rich.

Chapman 36

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Crotalaria retusa L. — Introduced

Ariwaodo FHI 73220

Total: 84; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Ekiti 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 10, Niger 3, Ogun 8, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 22, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Crotalaria retusa var. *retusa* — Introduced

Crotalaria senegalensis (Pers.) Bacle ex DC.

Crotalaria uncinella var. *senegalensis* Pers.

Latilo FHI 62698

Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Gombe 2, Kano 3, Katsina 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Crotalaria spartea R.Br. ex Baker

Soladoye et al. FHI 83550

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Crotalaria spectabilis Roth — Introduced

Keay, R.W.J.; FHI 25594; 1949-12-04 [K003198219]

Total: 3; Oyo 2.

Crotalaria sphaerocarpa Perr. ex DC.

Gwynn, A.M.; 87; 1933-10-05 [K003197842]

Total: 3; Borno 1.

Crotalaria sphaerocarpa subsp.

sphaerocarpa

Cwynn 87

Total: 1.

Crotalaria subcapitata De Wild.

Daramola B.O.; 1959-02-17 [BR0000019100449]

Total: 16; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Kogi 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 5.

Crotalaria subcapitata subsp. *oreadum*

(Baker f.) Polhill

Chapman 5034

Total: 9; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Taraba 4.

Crotalaria subcapitata subsp. *subcapitata*

Gbile ZO; 1985-09-27 [WAG.1008425]

Total: 1.

Crotalaria trichotoma Bojer — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Crotalaria vagans Polhill

Literature

Total: 0.

Crotalaria verrucosa L. — Introduced

Milne s.n.

Total: 1.

Crudia klainei Pierre ex De Wild.

Lowe 1822

Total: 47; Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 2, Delta 2, Edo 11, Lagos 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Oyo 6.

Crudia ledermannii Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Crudia senegalensis Planch. ex Benth.

Stanfield & Binuyo FHI 58443

Total: 11; Edo 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Cryptosepalum diphyllum P.A.Duvign. ex

J.Léonard

Amachi FHI 38154

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Cryptosepalum pellegrinianum (J.Léonard)

J.Léonard

Pynaertiodendron pellegrinianum J.Léonard

Caterall 1

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Cryptosepalum staudtii Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Cryptosepalum tetrphyllum (Hook.f.)

Benth. — Introduced

Cynometra tetrphylla Hook.f.

Schmitt 509; 1995-02-21 MOBOT976841
[4061957283]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Cullen plicatum (Delile) C.H.Stirt.

Psoralea plicata Delile

Vogel 93

Total: 1.

Cyamopsis tetragonoloba (L.) Taub. —

Introduced

Psoralea tetragonoloba L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1652; 1966-06-30 [2517643064]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Cyclocarpa stellaris Afzel. ex Urb.

Latilo FHI 73574

Total: 5; Anambra 1, Edo 1, Taraba 1.

Cylicodiscus gabunensis Harms

Daramola FHI 72339

Total: 39; Cross River 2, Ebonyi 2, Edo 13, Imo 1,
Kaduna 2, Niger 1.

Cynometra hankei Harms

Keay FHI 37727

Total: 12; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Bauchi 1, Cross
River 6.

Cynometra mannii Oliv.

Talbot 1708

Total: 10; Cross River 5.

Cynometra megalophylla Harms

Olorunfemi FHI 40330

Total: 52; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 5, Lagos 4, Nasarawa
1, Ogun 11, Oyo 16, Taraba 3.

Cynometra ramiflora L. — Introduced

C. Onochie 3326; 1945-1-16 [US 1993652]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Cynometra vogelii Hook.f.

Daramola FHI 38019

Total: 39; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Benue 2, Cross
River 4, Delta 1, Imo 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 4, Ogun 6, Oyo
1, Sokoto 1.

Dalbergia afzeliana G.Don

Olatilo FHI 57715

Total: 1.

Dalbergia albiflora subsp. *albiflora*

1953-09-24 [1115894.0]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Dalbergia albiflora subsp. *echinocarpa*

Hepper

Emwiogbon FHI 66614

Total: 3; Anambra 1, Cross River 1.

Dalbergia boehmii Taub. — Introduced

HEPPER NGA-32564 [1948981404]

Total: 1.

Dalbergia crispa Hepper

Okafor & Latilo FHI 57254

Total: 1.

Dalbergia dalzielii Baker f. ex Hutch. &

Dalziel

Barter 2141

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Lagos 6, Rivers 1.

Dalbergia ecastaphyllum (L.) Taub.

Hedysarum ecastaphyllum L.

Gillett 15367

Total: 19; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 2, Lagos 9, Osun
1, Rivers 2.

Dalbergia gentilii De Wild. — Introduced

Hepper F.N. 1521; 1957-12-03 [BR0000018405590]

Total: 2; Adamawa 2.

Dalbergia gillettii De Wild.

Nsimundele L.; 2008-04-25 [BR0000005016693]

Total: 1.

Dalbergia grandibracteata De Wild. —

Introduced

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot, 3179;
1912-1913 [BM013405811]

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Dalbergia heudelotii Stapf

Chapman 5276

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1, Ekiti 1.

Dalbergia hostilis Benth.

Ariwaodo FHI 88608

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1.

Dalbergia lactea Vatke

Hepper 1712

Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1,
Lagos 3, Taraba 5.

Dalbergia latifolia Roxb. — Introduced

Odewo FHI 92046

Total: 2; Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Dalbergia louisii Cronquist

Talbot s.n.

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 2, Niger 1.

Dalbergia melanoxylon Guill. & Perr.

Dalziel 34

Total: 14; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 2, Yobe 3.

Dalbergia monetaria L.f. — Introduced

Pterocarpus ovalis L.

Talbot, P.A. s.n.; 1913-- [CM150698]

Total: 1.

Dalbergia oligophylla Baker ex Hutch. &

Dalziel

Lowe 2682

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Dalbergia rostrata Hassk. — Introduced

Dr. Kadiri; Others; 2011-9-5 [4265]3808444031

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Dalbergia rufa G. Don

Emwiogbon FHI 63999

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 2.

Dalbergia saxatilis Hook.f.

Daramola FHI 44276

Total: 20; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 8, Delta 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 2.

Dalbergia sissoo Roxb. ex DC. —

Introduced

Sharland 269

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Niger 1.

Dalbergiella welwitschii (Baker) Baker f.

Ostryocarpus welwitschii Baker

Odewo & Daramola FHI 85350

Total: 28; Adamawa 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

Daniellia oblonga Oliv.

Keay s.n.

Total: 4; Edo 1, Oyo 2.

Daniellia ogea (Harms) Rolfe ex Holland

Cyanothyrus ogea Harms

Okeke FHI 44332

Total: 54; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 7, Kaduna 7, Kebbi 1, Lagos 11, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Daniellia oliveri (Rolfe) Hutch. & Dalziel

Paradaniellia oliveri Rolfe

Heper 3895

Total: 89; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 4, Adamawa 2, Anambra 4, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Edo 2,

Enugu 4, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 7, Lagos 4, Niger 15, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 4, Zamfara 3.

Daniellia thurifera Benn.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-04-04 [WAG.1638987]

Total: 4; Oyo 3.

Delonix regia (Bojer ex Hook.) Raf. —

Introduced

Poinciana regia Bojer ex Hook.

Daramola FHI 60692

Total: 22; Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 13.

Desmodium barbatum var. *emirnense* Baker

Ohaeri A.O.; 18-10-1971 [ABUH]

Total: 5; Kaduna 4.

Desmodium distortum (Aubl.) J.F. Macbr. —

Introduced

Hedysarum distortum Aubl.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-06-30 [WAG.1014801]

Total: 3; Gombe 2, Oyo 1.

Desmodium incanum (Sw.) DC. —

Introduced

Hedysarum incanum Sw.

MONOD NGA-5166; Flotrop186023 [1948981823]

Total: 1.

Desmodium intortum (Mill.) Urb. —

Introduced

Hedysarum intortum Mill.

Ekwuno FHI 77230

Total: 7; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Desmodium ospriostreblum Chiov.

Lawlor & Hall 291

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Desmodium procumbens (Mill.) C.L. Hitchc.

— Introduced

Hedysarum procumbens Mill.

Dalziel, J.M.; 24; 1907-09-18 [K003404278]

Total: 3.

Desmodium procumbens var. *procumbens*

— Introduced

Hedysarum procumbens Mill.

Dalziel 24

Total: 1.

Desmodium scorpiurus (Sw.) Desv. ex DC.

— Introduced

Hedysarum scorpiurus Sw.

Latilo FHI 54883

Total: 11; Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Desmodium tortuosum (Sw.) DC. —

Introduced

Hedysarum tortuosum Sw.

Fagbemi FHI 89828

Total: 22; Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 2.

Desmodium uncinatum (Jacq.) DC. —

Introduced

Hedysarum uncinatum Jacq.

Literature

Total: 0.

Detarium macrocarpum Harms

Keay FHI 28234

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Detarium microcarpum Guill. & Perr.

Ariwaodo FHI 89287

Total: 129; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 6, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 27, Kebbi 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 5, Nasarawa 4, Niger 27, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 12, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Zamfara 4.

Detarium senegalense J.F.Gmel.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000016559554]

Total: 32; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 4, Edo 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 9, Kogi 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Dialium angolense Welw. ex Oliv. —

Introduced

Meer, PPC van 1505; 1971-04-26 [WAG.1638460]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Dialium bipindense Harms

Onochie CFA; 1953-05-16 [WAG.1638392]

Total: 2; Rivers 2.

Dialium dinklagei Harms

Jones FHI 6823

Total: 14; Cross River 4, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 2.

Dialium guianense (Aubl.) Sandwith —

Introduced

Arouna guianensis Aubl.

M. Olufsen 750; 1927-12-13 [US 1596717]

Total: 2; Kwara 1.

Dialium guineense Willd.

Ekwuno FHI 60511

Total: 183; Abia 3, Adamawa 3, Anambra 13, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Edo 7, Ekiti 6, Enugu 6, Imo 4, Kaduna 5, Kwara 2, Lagos 15, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 29, Ondo 8, Osun 8, Oyo 22, Plateau 8, Rivers 2, Taraba 5.

Dialium pachyphyllum Harms

Jones FHI 6823

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Rivers 1.

Dialium tessmannii Harms

K. Schmitt; T.O. Ibiang; 1995-02-08 [MO.976744.0]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dichrostachys cinerea (L.) Wight & Arn.

Mimosa cinerea L.

Ekwuno FHI 87581

Total: 135; Adamawa 6, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 11, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 24, Kano 1, Katsina 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 11, Lagos 5, Niger 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 14, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 11, Zamfara 3.

Dichrostachys cinerea subsp. *africana*

Brenan & Brummitt

Binuyo A; 1958-04-01 [WAG.1705961]

Total: 15; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Dichrostachys cinerea subsp. *platycarpa*

(Welw. ex W.Bull) Brenan & Brummitt

Dichrostachys platycarpa Welw. ex W.Bull

Croat, TB 53404; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1707058]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Didelotia africana Baill.

Latilo FHI 41337

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Didelotia idae J.Léonard, Oldeman & de

Wit

Literature

Total: 0.

Didelotia unifoliolata J.Léonard

Literature

Total: 0.

Dioclea virgata (Rich.) Amshoff —

Introduced

Dolichos virgatus Rich.

Williams, M.; Williams, J.L. sn. [K003834828]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dioclea virgata var. *virgata* — Introduced

Dolichos virgatus Rich.

Distemonanthus benthamianus Baill.

- Latilo* FHI 41313
Total: 40; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Edo 14, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 1.
- Dolichos grandistipulatus* Harms
Lely s.n.
Total: 1.
- Dolichos pseudocajanus* Welw. ex Baker
s.coll. s.n. [K001350442]
Total: 2; Sokoto 2.
- Dolichos reptans* Verdc.
Hepper 1503
Total: 3.
- Dolichos schweinfurthii* Taub.
Wit & Daramola FHI 78083
Total: 21; Bauchi 4, Kaduna 1, Plateau 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6.
- Dolichos sericeus* E.Mey.
Chapman 3585
Total: 3; Oyo 1.
- Dolichos sericeus* subsp. *sericeus*
Keay R.; 1950-11-30 [BR0000018386554]
Total: 2; Oyo 1.
- Dolichos trilobus* subsp. *occidentalis* Verdc.
Wimbush 97
Total: 1.
- Dolichos trilobus* subsp. *trilobus*
Meikle R.D.; 1949-11-27 [BR0000018387025]
Total: 2; Oyo 2.
- Droogmansia ledermannii* Schindl.
Hepper 1423
Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Kogi 1, Taraba 2.
- Droogmansia mildbraedii* Schindl.
Mildbraed G. W. J. [K000087050]
Total: 4.
- Duparquetia orchidacea* Baill.
Daramola et al. FHI 78671
Total: 64; Abia 2, Borno 1, Cross River 47, Kano 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.
- Englerodendron conchyliphorum* (Pellegr.) Breteler
Macrolobium conchyliphorum Pellegr.
Meer PPC van; 1971-05-11 [WAG.1633852]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.
- Englerodendron nigericum* (Baker f.) Estrella & Ojeda
Macrolobium leptorrhachis var. nigericum Baker f.
Talbot 582
Total: 4; Cross River 3.
- Englerodendron obanense* (Baker f.) Estrella & Ojeda
Macrolobium obanense Baker f.
Okafor FHI 57636
Total: 13; Cross River 5, Edo 1, Niger 2, Ondo 4.
- Entada abyssinica* Steud. ex A.Rich.
Odewo & Oni FHI 79148
Total: 61; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 5, Ekiti 5, Enugu 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 7, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 10.
- Entada africana* Guill. & Perr.
Gbile et al. FHI 65486
Total: 93; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 8, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Gombe 4, Kaduna 8, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 14, Nasarawa 3, Niger 7, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 13, Plateau 5, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.
- Entada gigas* (L.) Fawc. & Rendle — Introduced
Mimosa gigas L.
O.O Oyebanji LUH5595; 2013-04-22 [3808438908]
Total: 1; Lagos 1.
- Entada mannii* (Oliv.) Tisser.
Piptadenia mannii Oliv.
Onochi FHI 40197
Total: 18; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Edo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.
- Entada rheedei* Spreng.
Chapman 4158
Total: 32; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 6, Osun 2, Oyo 6, Taraba 2.
- Entada rheedei* subsp. *rheedei*
Binuyo A. [BR0000016784345]
Total: 12; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Enugu 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 2.
- Entada wahlbergii* Harv.
Hambler 451
Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 1.
- Eriosema angolense* Baker f.
Hepper, F.N.; 1957-10-21 [P03092893]

Total: 2; Imo 1.

Eriosema bauchiense Hutch. & Dalziel

Hall 1671

Total: 9; Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Eriosema chrysadenium Taub.

Hepper 1428

Total: 14; Adamawa 7, Kaduna 1, Taraba 5.

Eriosema chrysadenium var. *chrysadenium*

Eriosema cordifolium Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Lawlor & Hall 595

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Eriosema elliotii Baker f.

Morton 395

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Eriosema flemingioides Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Eriosema glomeratum (Guill. & Perr.)

Hook.f.

Rhynchosia glomerata Guill. & Perr.

Ekwuno FHI 96302

Total: 66; Anambra 5, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 4, Kaduna 6, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 3, Niger 8, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 6, Sokoto 3, Taraba 4.

Eriosema glomeratum var. *elongatum* Baker

Okafor JC; 1963-06-24 [WAG.1018166]

Total: 3; Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Eriosema glomeratum var. *glomeratum*

Rhynchosia glomerata Guill. & Perr.

Onochie CFA; 1958-11-26 [WAG.1018245]

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1.

Eriosema griseum Baker

Latilo FHI 62558

Total: 45; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Edo 2, Kaduna 9, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Eriosema laurentii De Wild.

Wit, P 2318; 1972-08-13 [WAG.1018468]

Total: 2; Ondo 1, Rivers 1.

Eriosema lebrunii Staner & De Craene

Chapman J.W.F.; 1958-06-01 [BR0000017207133]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Eriosema linifolium Baker f.

Keay FHI 25957

Total: 3; Benue 1, Kaduna 1.

Eriosema macrostipulum Baker f.

Daramola FHI 62702

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Taraba 1.

Eriosema montanum Baker f.

Latilo FHGI 77400

Total: 10; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Eriosema montanum var. *montanum*

Eriosema monticola Taub.

Daramola FHI 86048

Total: 8; Adamawa 4, Plateau 2.

Eriosema nutans Schinz

Tuley 1612

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Eriosema parviflorum E.Mey.

Lowe 2477

Total: 4; Kogi 1, Ogun 2.

Eriosema parviflorum subsp. *podostachyum* (Hook.f.) J.K.Morton ex Verdc.

Literature

Total: 0.

Eriosema pellegrinii Tisser. — Introduced

KERSHAW NGA-29345 Flotrop182400 [1948977842]

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Eriosema psoraleoides (Lam.) G.Don

Crotalaria psoraleoides Lam.

Latilo FHI 18233

Total: 100; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 8, Benue 4, Cross River 4, Kaduna 11, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 15, Ogun 5, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Plateau 4, Sokoto 3, Taraba 11.

Eriosema pulcherrimum Taub.

Daramola FHI 672701

Total: 1.

Eriosema rhodesicum R.E.Fr.

Hall 1767

Total: 10; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Eriosema scioanum Avetta

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Taraba 1.

Eriosema scioanum subsp. *lejeunei* (Staner & De Craene) Verdc.

Medler 992

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Taraba 1.

Eriosema shirensense Baker f.

Gbile & Daramola FHI 63244

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 4.

Eriosema shirense var. *shirense*

Eriosema sparsiflorum Baker f.

Gbile et al. FHI 65337

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Plateau 5.

Eriosema verdickii De Wild.

Lowe 2699

Total: 5; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Eriosema verdickii var. *schoutedenianum*

(Staner & De Craene) Verdc.

Eriosema schoutedenianum Staner & De Craene

Stone, R.H. 61; 1955-08-27 [K003991381]

Total: 2; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Eriosema verdickii var. *verdickii*

Total: 1.

Eriosema youngii Baker f.

Keay FHI 25868

Total: 3; Kaduna 2, Plateau 1.

Erythrina addisoniae Hutch. & Dalziel

Onochie FHI 43512

Total: 10; Cross River 4, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Erythrina excelsa Baker

Olorunfemi & Oguntayo FHI 86643

Total: 3; Niger 1.

Erythrina fusca Lour. — Introduced

Espley, J.H.; 14; 1931-01-01 [K003237770]

Total: 4; Niger 1.

Erythrina mildbraedii Harms

Binuyo FHI 40888

Total: 18; Edo 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 12.

Erythrina poeppigiana (Walp.) O.F.Cook —

Introduced

Micropteryx poeppigiana Walp.

[J. H. Espley]; 9; 1931-01-01 [K003962588]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Erythrina senegalensis DC.

Ariwaodo FHI 97171

Total: 64; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Kaduna 11, Kano 4, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 6, Ogun 4, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Erythrina sigmoidea Hua

Chapman 4659

Total: 16; Adamawa 3, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Erythrina tholloniana Hua

Onochie FHI 43512

Total: 3; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Erythrina variegata L. — Introduced

[K.33323.0]

Total: 6; Ekiti 2, Oyo 4.

Erythrina vogelii Hook.f.

Gledhill 773

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ondo 3, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Erythrophleum africanum (Benth.) Harms

Gleditsia africana Benth.

Tuley 1636

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Gombe 1, Kwara 5, Niger 5, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Erythrophleum ivorense A.Chev.

Lawlor & Hall 319

Total: 34; Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ogun 12, Oyo 9.

Erythrophleum suaveolens (Guill. & Perr.)

Brenan

Fillaea suaveolens Guill. & Perr.

Keay FHI 36619

Total: 67; Adamawa 2, Anambra 6, Benue 4, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Enugu 5, Kaduna 9, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Oyo 9, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Faidherbia albida (Delile) A.Chev.

Acacia albida Delile

Chapman 4080

Total: 58; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Borno 9, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 5, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Sokoto 7, Taraba 1.

Falcataria falcata (L.) Greuter & R.Rankin

— Introduced

Adenanthera falcata L.

Lowe, J.L. 1917; 1969-11-02 [K003786307]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Fillaeopsis discophora Harms

Alexander FHI 34042

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2.

Flemingia grahamiana Wight & Arn. —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1115; 1966-01-31

[WAG.1964205]

Total: 4; Oyo 2, Taraba 2.

Galactia striata (Jacq.) Urb.

Glycine striata Jacq.

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Galactia striata var. *villosa* (Wight & Arn.)
Verdc.

Galactia villosa Wight & Arn.

Latilo FHI 58830

Total: 3.

Gilbertiodendron demonstrans (Baill.)

J.Léonard

Vouapa demonstrans Baill.

Latilo FHI 40914

Total: 12; Borno 1, Cross River 1.

Gilbertiodendron dewevrei (De Wild.)

J.Léonard

Macrolobium dewevrei De Wild.

Offokansi FHGI 59129

Total: 41; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 5, Cross River 4, Edo 19, Ondo 1, Rivers 3.

Gilbertiodendron grandiflorum (De Wild.)

J.Léonard

Macrolobium grandiflorum De Wild.

Onyachusim & Latilo FHI 54223

Total: 2.

Gilbertiodendron mayombense (Pellegr.)

J.Léonard

Macrolobium mayombense Pellegr.

Latilo 26

Total: 1.

Gliricidia sepium (Jacq.) Kunth —

Introduced

Robinia sepium Jacq.

Fagbemi FHI 31451

Total: 15; Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 11.

Gluema korupensis Burt

Onochie FHI 33169 (K)

Total: 1.

Glycine max (L.) Merr. — Introduced

Phaseolus max L.

Igbari, A.D; 2013-07-17, LUH9724 [3999608653]

Total: 9; Lagos 1, Taraba 1.

Glycine max subsp. *soja* (Siebold & Zucc.)

H.Ohashi — Introduced

Glycine soja Siebold & Zucc.

Kehinde Olumide; 2012-7-2 [1226A]3808441853

Total: 1.

Griffonia physocarpa Baill.

Daramola et al. FHI 86143

Total: 45; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 22, Edo 1, Imo 7, Lagos 3, Oyo 1.

Griffonia simplicifolia (Vahl ex DC.) Baill.

Schotia simplicifolia Vahl ex DC.

Onochie FHI 40268

Total: 16; Cross River 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Grona adscendens (Sw.) H.Ohashi &

K.Ohashi

Hedysarum adscendens Sw.

Ekwuno FHI 95684

Total: 24; Bauchi 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 2.

Grona barbata (L.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi

Hedysarum barbatum L.

Magaji SO; 1956-09-23 [WAG.1014813]

Total: 6; Kaduna 2, Plateau 3.

Grona barbata var. *barbata*

Hedysarum barbatum L.

Grona heterocarpos var. *strigosa*

(Meeuwen) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi —

Introduced

Hedysarum heterocarpon L.

Dalziel J.M. 338; 1910-10-16 [BR0000018353488]

Total: 1.

Grona hirta (Guill. & Perr.) H.Ohashi &

K.Ohashi

Desmodium hirtum Guill. & Perr.

Chapman FHI 68577

Total: 19; Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Grona hirta var. *hirta*

Desmodium hirtum Guill. & Perr.

Grona ramosissima (G.Don) H.Ohashi &

K.Ohashi

Desmodium ramosissimum G.Don

Soladoye et al. FHI 86294

Total: 77; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 3, Borno 2, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Oyo 10, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Grona schweinfurthii (Schindl.) H.Ohashi &

K.Ohashi

Desmodium schweinfurthii Schindl.

Lely 684

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Grona setigera (E.Mey.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi

Nicolsonia setigera E.Mey.

[Daramola FHI 62487](#)

Total: 9; Bauchi 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Grona triflora (L.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi

Hedysarum triflorum L.

[Olorunfemi et al. FHI 88383](#)

Total: 20; Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Guibourtia copallifera Benn. — Introduced

[Kennedy 2253](#)

Total: 3; Ogun 2.

Guibourtia ehie (A.Chev.) J.Léonard

Copaifera ehie A.Chev.

[Oni FHI 34565](#)

Total: 31; Cross River 10, Edo 6, Kaduna 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 7.

Guibourtia pellegriniana J.Léonard

[Milne G. \[BR0000017356961\]](#)

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Guibourtia tessmannii (Harms) J.Léonard

Copaifera tessmannii Harms

[\[K.21516.0\]](#)

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Guilandina bonduc L. — Introduced

[Gillett 15362](#)

Total: 39; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 16.

Haematoxylum campechianum L. —

Introduced

[Ross A.F.; 1931-10-29 \[FHI.2847.0\]](#)

Total: 9; Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 5.

Haplormosia monophylla (Harms) Harms

Crudia monophylla Harms

[Amachi FHI 24304](#)

Total: 11; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Ekiti 1, Lagos 1.

Humularia ledermannii (De Wild.)

P.A.Duvign.

Geissaspis ledermannii De Wild.

[Chapman 4330](#)

Total: 5; Borno 3, Plateau 2.

Hylodendron gabunense Taub.

[Chizea FHI 44516](#)

Total: 31; Anambra 2, Cross River 6, Edo 12, Kaduna 3, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 2.

Hylodesmum repandum (Vahl) H.Ohashi & R.R.Mill

Hedysarum repandum Vahl

[Latilo FHI 77405](#)

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Taraba 3.

Hymenaea verrucosa Gaertn. — Introduced

[Eijnatten, CLM van 1339; 1966-4-4 \[WAG.1634413\]](#)

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Hymenostegia aubrevillei Pellegr.

[Ariwaodo FHI 81295](#)

Total: 12; Abia 8, Edo 2, Oyo 2.

Hymenostegia bakeriana Hutch. & Dalziel

[Talbot 1567](#)

Total: 5; Cross River 1.

Hymenostegia talbotii Baker f.

[Talbot 3141](#)

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Indigastrum costatum (Guill. & Perr.)

Schrire

Indigofera costata Guill. & Perr.

[Ekwuno & Fagbemi FHI 94029](#)

Total: 4; Borno 2.

Indigastrum costatum subsp. *costatum*

Indigofera costata Guill. & Perr.

[Noble, H.L.; 28; 1949-09-29 \[K003832163\]](#)

Total: 3; Borno 2.

Indigastrum parviflorum (B.Heyne ex Wight & Arn.) Schrire

Indigofera parviflora B.Heyne ex Wight & Arn.

[Literature](#)

Total: 0.

Indigastrum parviflorum subsp. *parviflorum*

Indigofera parviflora B.Heyne ex Wight & Arn.

[Literature](#)

Total: 0.

Indigofera andrewsiana J.B.Gillett

[Latilo FHI 64776](#)

Total: 1.

Indigofera arrecta Hochst. ex A.Rich.

[Daramola FHI 85542](#)

Total: 39; Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 9, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Osun 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2.

Indigofera aspera Perr. ex DC. —

Introduced

[Dalziel, J.M. 326; 1910-09-06 \[K000354376\]](#)

Total: 7; Borno 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Sokoto 1.

Indigofera astragalina DC.

Latilo FHI 43752

Total: 22; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Katsina 3, Kogi 1, Niger 5, Oyo 2, Sokoto 4, Yobe 1.

Indigofera atriceps Hook.f.

Tuley 2044

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Indigofera atriceps subsp. *atriceps*

Indigofera barteri Hutch. & Dalziel

Lawlor & Hall 196

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Niger 6.

Indigofera berhautiana J.B.Gillett

Barter 973

Total: 2; Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Indigofera bracteolata DC.

Hepper & Keay 950

Total: 29; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 5, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 9, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Indigofera brevifilamenta J.B.Gillett

Indigofera secundiflora var. *oubanguiensis*
Tisser.

Lely, H.V.; P645; 1930-08-01 [K003124240]

Total: 4; Plateau 1.

Indigofera brevifilamenta subsp.

brevifilamenta

Indigofera secundiflora var. *oubanguiensis*
Tisser.

Indigofera capitata Kotschy

Okafor FGHI 59084

Total: 23; Bauchi 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Indigofera colutea (Burm.f.) Merr.

Galega colutea Burm.f.

Daramola FHI 86037

Total: 4; Borno 1, Taraba 2.

Indigofera colutea var. *colutea*

Galega colutea Burm.f.

Indigofera conferta J.B.Gillett

Indigofera grisea Baker

Geerling FHI 4260

Total: 8; Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2.

Indigofera congesta Welw. ex Baker

Ohaeri FHI 78921

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Indigofera congolensis De Wild. &

T.Durand

Olorunfemi FHI 55028

Total: 24; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2.

Indigofera congolensis var. *congolensis*

Indigofera conjugata Baker

Lely, H.V. [K000459918]

Total: 38; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 12, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Niger 5, Plateau 7, Taraba 1.

Indigofera conjugata var. *conjugata*

Okafor & Daramola FHI 54610

Total: 12; Adamawa 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Plateau 4.

Indigofera conjugata var. *occidentalis*

J.B.Gillett — Introduced

Lowe FHI 484354

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Indigofera dasycephala Baker f.

Hepper 1303

Total: 2; Bauchi 2.

Indigofera deightonii J.B.Gillett

Gledhill 684

Total: 26; Ekiti 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 14.

Indigofera deightonii subsp. *deightonii*

R.W.J. Keay & D.P. Stanfield [BR0000018635386]

Total: 3; Oyo 2.

Indigofera dendroides Jacq.

Gillett 14255

Total: 70; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 3, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 8, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 3.

Indigofera diphylla Vent.

Ekwuno & Fagbemi FHI 93876

Total: 5; Katsina 1, Niger 3, Yobe 1.

Indigofera drepanocarpa Taub.

Lely, H.V.; 481; 1921-08-02 [K003241313]

Total: 3; Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Indigofera elliotii (Baker f.) J.B.Gillett —

Introduced

Indigofera heudelotii var. *elliotii* Baker f.

HEPPER NGA-32555, 1957-01-01 Flotrop185505 [1948981111]

Total: 1.

Indigofera emarginella Steud. ex A.Rich.

Chapman FHI 46255

Total: 6; Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Indigofera emarginella var. *emarginella*

Chapman, J.D.; 2938; 1972-06-30 [K003124317]

Total: 5; Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Indigofera fulvopilosa Brenan

Indigofera pilosa var. *multiflora* Baker f.

Stanfield FHI 55634

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Indigofera fuscobarbata Schrire

Literature

Total: 0.

Indigofera garckeana Vatke — Introduced

Geerling, C 4123; 1971-08-21 [WAG.1022989]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1.

Indigofera geminata Baker

Gillett 15405

Total: 21; Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Oyo 7.

Indigofera hendecaphylla Jacq.

Ahmed; Adekunle AO; Chizea LG; 1948-10-04 [WAG.1023137]

Total: 9; Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Indigofera hendecaphylla var.

hendecaphylla

Indigofera heudelotii Benth. ex Baker

Frahm-Leliveld JA; 1957-01-04 [WAG.1023220]

Total: 18; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 5, Kwara 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Indigofera heudelotii var. *heudelotii*

Latilo FHI 77336

Total: 12; Cross River 1, Kaduna 4, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Indigofera hirsuta L.

Ekwuno FHI 95989

Total: 73; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Ekiti 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 5, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 12, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Indigofera hochstetteri Baker — Introduced

Indigofera ornithopodioides Hochst. & Steud. ex Jaub. & Spach

Meikle, R.D. 1097; 1950-01-23 [K000627844]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2.

Indigofera kerstingii Harms

Gbile & Daramola FHI 77572

Total: 22; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Oyo 6.

Indigofera latisepala J.B.Gillett — Endemic

Baikie 20

Total: 2.

Indigofera leprieurii (Kuntze) Baker f.

Anil leprieurii Kuntze

Okeke FHI 38450

Total: 24; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 2, Oyo 3.

Indigofera leptoclada Harms — Introduced

Geerling, C 4260; 1971-09-30 [WAG.1023785]

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Indigofera longebarbata Engl.

Young, J.D.; 45; 1922-01-01 [K003124576]

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Indigofera macrocalyx Guill. & Perr.

Latilo FHI 62293

Total: 21; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Indigofera macrophylla Schumach.

Odewo et al. FHI 88109

Total: 34; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Ekiti 2, Enugu 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Indigofera microcarpa Desv.

Dalziel 56

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Indigofera mildbraediana J.B.Gillett

Jackson 2565

Total: 19; Bauchi 6, Borno 2, Ekiti 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Plateau 3.

Indigofera mimosoides Baker

Odewo FHI 87938

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Indigofera mimosoides var. *mimosoides*

Indigofera nigricans Vahl ex Pers.

Lowe FHI 26265

Total: 5; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Taraba 1.

Indigofera nigritana Hook.f.

Latilo FHI 54396

Total: 9; Kano 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Indigofera nummulariifolia (L.) Livera ex Alston

Hedysarum nummulariifolium L.

Gbile et al. FHI 64091

Total: 48; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 10, Sokoto 1.

Indigofera oblongifolia Forssk.

Soladoye et al. FHI 83786

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Lagos 1.

Indigofera omissa J.B.Gillett

Jackson 247

Total: 3; Kaduna 2.

Indigofera omissa var. *omissa*

Indigofera paniculata Vahl ex Pers.

Daramola FHI 63211

Total: 31; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Lagos 3, Niger 5, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

Indigofera paniculata subsp. *paniculata*

Sharland, R.E.; s.n.; 1980-09-29 [K003241467]

Total: 12; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 5, Taraba 1.

Indigofera paracapitata J.B.Gillett

Literature

Total: 0.

Indigofera phyllanthoides Baker —

Introduced

Geerling C. 4299B; 1971-10-05 [BR0000018763584]

Total: 2; Kano 1, Oyo 1.

Indigofera pilosa Poir.

Gillett 15415

Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Niger 2, Oyo 3, Yobe 3.

Indigofera pilosa var. *pilosa*

Indigofera polysphaera Baker

Soladoye et al. FHI 83535

Total: 27; Benue 4, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 5, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Indigofera pretoriana Harms — Introduced

Etkin 11; 1988-7-4 [92506]1261850384

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Indigofera priureana Guill. & Perr.

Ekwuno FHI 97069

Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 4.

Indigofera pulchra Willd.

Lowe 1391

Total: 86; Abia 1, Bauchi 10, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 3, Ekiti 3, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Jigawa 4, Kaduna 14, Kano 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Indigofera radicefera Cronquist

Jackson, G.; 2825971; 1971-09-25 [K003124867]

Total: 5.

Indigofera radicefera subsp. *arthrocarpa*

Schrire

Literature

Total: 0.

Indigofera radicefera subsp. *radicefera*

Indigofera rhynchocarpa Welw. ex Baker

Daramola FHI 62907

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Indigofera secundiflora Poir.

Soladoye et al. FHI 84934

Total: 36; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Gombe 6, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Indigofera secundiflora var. *rubripilosa* De Wild. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 2032; 1966-09-23

[WAG.1024708]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Kwara 1.

Indigofera secundiflora var. *secundiflora*

Gillett, JB; 1962-07-22 [PRE0924160-0]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Indigofera senegalensis Lam.

Soladoye et al. FHI 83939

Total: 8; Borno 4, Niger 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Indigofera sessiliflora DC.

Newby, J.E. 2P185; 1979-04-13 [K003241739]

Total: 3.

Indigofera simplicifolia Lam.

Hepper 1144

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Indigofera spicata Forssk.

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 93643

Total: 29; Akwa Ibom 1, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 8, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Indigofera spicata var. *spicata*

Indigofera stenophylla Guill. & Perr.

Gillett 15414

Total: 20; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Oyo 5.

Indigofera strobilifera (Hochst.) Hochst. ex Baker

Eilemanthus strobilifer Hochst.

Gillett 15424

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Jigawa 1, Kano 3, Niger 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Indigofera strobilifera subsp. *strobilifera*

Eilemanthus strobilifer Hochst.

Hepper F.N.; 1957-11-03 [BR0000018992182]

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Jigawa 1, Kano 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Indigofera subulata Vahl ex Poir.

Pilz, G.E. [K000623319]

Total: 7; Borno 1, Katsina 1, Oyo 3.

Indigofera subulata var. *scabra* (Roth)

Meikle

Literature

Total: 0.

Indigofera subulata var. *subulata*

Daramola BO; 1969-05-29 [WAG.1025462]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Katsina 1, Oyo 1.

Indigofera suffruticosa Mill. — Introduced

Odewoi & Oni FHI 78983

Total: 10; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Oyo 3.

Indigofera tephrosioides Kunth —

Introduced

R. Schlechter 12329; 1899-3-1 [Z-000084826]

Total: 1.

Indigofera terminalis Baker

Leeuw PN de; 1966-12-22 [WAG.1025266]

Total: 3; Bauchi 2, Niger 1.

Indigofera tinctoria L. — Introduced

Stanfield FHI 59868

Total: 31; Borno 4, Gombe 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Ondo 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 3.

Indigofera tinctoria var. *tinctoria* —

Introduced

Indigofera trita L.f.

Keay, R.W.J.; Keay, J.M. FHI20195; 1946-08-17 [K003124475]

Total: 8; Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Indigofera trita var. *trita*

Indigofera wituensis Baker f.

Lely, H.V. [K000392645]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Plateau 2.

Indigofera wituensis var. *occidentalis*

J.B.Gillett — Endemic

Lely 693

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Inga edulis Mart. — Introduced

Mimosa ynga Vell.

Thomas; 1971-06-03 [FHI.90081.0]

Total: 5; Oyo 4.

Isoberlinia doka Craib & Stapf

Lowe 1674

Total: 93; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 5, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 2, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 27, Katsina 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 6, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 1, Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 6.

Isoberlinia tomentosa (Harms) Craib & Stapf

Berlinia tomentosa Harms

Soladoye et al. FHI 83962

Total: 45; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 7, Kwara 3, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Zamfara 4.

Julbernardia pellegriniana Troupin — Introduced

Paraberlinia bifoliolata Pellegr.

T.K Odewo LUH5915; 2013-02-01 [3808440155]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Julbernardia seretii (De Wild.) Troupin

Berlinia seretii De Wild.

Talbot 1586

Total: 1.

Kotschya schweinfurthii (Taub.) Dewit & P.A.Duvign.

Smithia schweinfurthii Taub.

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 94376

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 2, Plateau 2.

Kotschya speciosa (Hutch.) Hepper

Smithia speciosa Hutch.

- Chapman FHI 62138**
Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 12, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.
- Kotschya strigosa* (Benth.) Dewit & P.A.Duvign.
Smithia strigosa Benth.
- Hepper 1515**
Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Taraba 2.
- Kotschya strigosa* var. *strigosa*
Smithia strigosa Benth.
- Lablab purpureus* (L.) Sweet
Dolichos purpureus L.
Soladoye et al. FHI 91832
Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Lagos 3, Oyo 2.
- Lablab purpureus* subsp. *purpureus*
Dolichos purpureus L.
Meikle, R.D.; 1949-12-14 [K.15696.0]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1.
- Lathyrus oleraceus* Lam. — Introduced
Pisum sativum L.
- Literature**
Total: 0.
- Leonardoxa africana* (Baill.) Aubrév.
Humboldtia africana Baill.
Latilo M.G. [BR0000017331593]
Total: 6; Cross River 4.
- Leonardoxa africana* subsp. *africana*
Humboldtia africana Baill.
- Leptoderris aurantiaca* Dunn
Latilo FHI 57541
Total: 4; Bayelsa 1, Ogun 2, Taraba 1.
- Leptoderris brachyptera* (Benth.) Dunn
Lonchocarpus brachypterus Benth.
Lowe 2780
Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Oyo 13.
- Leptoderris congolensis* (De Wild.) Dunn
Derris congolensis De Wild.
Talbot 3342
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.
- Leptoderris fasciculata* (Benth.) Dunn
Lonchocarpus fasciculatus Benth.
Ekwuno et al. FHI 92679
Total: 8; Adamawa 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 4.
- Leptoderris micrantha* Dunn
- Latilo & Fagbemi FHI 67509**
Total: 12; Ekiti 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Osun 2.
- Leptospron adenanthum* (G.Mey.) A.Delgado
Phaseolus adenanthus G.Mey.
Lowe 2532
Total: 11; Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Sokoto 6.
- Leucaena diversifolia* (Schltdl.) Benth. — Introduced
Acacia diversifolia Schltdl.
B.O.Daramola, LUH1998; 2004-02-01 [3808440893]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.
- Leucaena esculenta* (Moc. & Sessé ex DC.) Benth. — Introduced
Acacia esculenta Moc. & Sessé ex DC.
; -- **[LUH:Aramide 287]3968958616**
Total: 1.
- Leucaena leucocephala* (Lam.) de Wit — Introduced
Mimosa leucocephala Lam.
Uyamadu FHI 53946A
Total: 13; Kano 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 6.
- Leucaena leucocephala* subsp. *leucocephala* — Introduced
Mimosa leucocephala Lam.
- Leucomphalos capparideus* Benth.
Ujor FHI 30840
Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Niger 2.
- Libidibia punctata* (Willd.) Britton — Introduced
Caesalpinia punctata Willd.
P. Oguia Fhi.13636; 1945-10-22 [US 1993645]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.
- Loesenera talbotii* Baker f.
Latilo & Onyeachusim FHI 54259
Total: 10; Cross River 4, Niger 1.
- Lonchocarpus sericeus* (Poir.) Kunth ex DC.
Robinia sericea Poir.
Odewo et al. FHI 85253
Total: 63; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Osun 1, Oyo 21, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1.
- Lotus arabicus* Sol. ex L.
Sharland 1672
Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Niger 1, Yobe 2.
- Lotus discolor* E.Mey.
Tuley 1981

Total: 4; Taraba 2.

Lotus discolor subsp. *discolor*

Lysiloma acapulcense (Kunth) Benth. —

Introduced

Acacia acapulcensis Kunth

Literature

Total: 0.

Machaerium lunatum (L.f.) Ducke

Pterocarpus lunatus L.f.

Jackson 2443

Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Machaerium nicaraguense Rudd —

Introduced

W. D. Stevens; Alfredo Grijalva 16329; 1979-12-13 [RSA0003536]

Total: 1.

Macropsychanthus comosus (G.Mey.)

L.P.Queiroz & Snak

Dolichos comosus G.Mey.

Okafor FHI 57156

Total: 19; Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Oyo 4.

Macropsychanthus hexander (Ralph)

L.P.Queiroz & Snak

Mucuna hexandra Ralph

Maitland T.D. [BR0000018381450]

Total: 3; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Macroptilium atropurpureum (DC.) Urb. —

Introduced

s.n. [K001366040]

Total: 1; Sokoto 1.

Macroptilium lathyroides (L.) Urb. —

Introduced

Phaseolus lathyroides L.

s.coll. s.n. [K001366038]

Total: 1; Sokoto 1.

Macrotyloma africanum (Brenan ex

R.Wilczek) Verdc.

Dolichos africanus Brenan ex R.Wilczek

Lely FHI 8540

Total: 3.

Macrotyloma axillare (E.Mey.) Verdc.

Dolichos axillaris E.Mey.

Lely 578

Total: 5.

Macrotyloma axillare var. *axillare*

Dolichos axillaris E.Mey.

Macrotyloma biflorum (Schumach. &

Thonn.) Hepper

Glycine biflora Schumach. & Thonn.

1995-10-28 [FR-0019141]

Total: 54; Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Macrotyloma biflorum var.

appressepuberulum Verdc.

Ekwuno FHI 76988

Total: 11; Oyo 2.

Macrotyloma biflorum var. *biflorum*

Glycine biflora Schumach. & Thonn.

Onochie FHI 40863

Total: 4; Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Macrotyloma brevicaule (Baker) Verdc.

Dolichos brevicaulis Baker

Latilo FHI 63485

Total: 9; Adamawa 2, Oyo 1.

Macrotyloma daltonii (Webb) Verdc.

Dolichos daltonii Webb

Lawlor & Hall 351

Total: 8.

Macrotyloma geocarpum (Harms) Maréchal

& Baudet

Kerstingiella geocarpa Harms

[K.60551.0]

Total: 9; Niger 1, Sokoto 5.

Macrotyloma geocarpum var. *geocarpum*

Kerstingiella geocarpa Harms

Macrotyloma geocarpum var. *tisserantii*

(Pellegr.) Maréchal & Baudet

Kerstingiella tisserantii Pellegr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Macrotyloma schweinfurthii Verdc.

Latilo FHI 73593

Total: 3.

Macrotyloma stenophyllum (Harms) Verdc.

Dolichos stenophyllus Harms

Emwiogbon FHI 65924

Total: 5; Enugu 1.

Macrotyloma uniflorum (Lam.) Verdc. —

Introduced

Dolichos uniflorus Lam.

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/208394762>

Total: 1.

Melliniella micrantha Harms

Hepper 3863

Total: 8; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1.

Mezoneuron benthamianum Baill.

Gbile FHI 84327

Total: 20; Anambra 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7.

Microberlinia bisulcata A.Chev.

Daramola B.O.;Ekwuno; 1965-07-15 [FHI.55600.0]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Microcharis butayei (De Wild.) Schrire

Indigofera butayei De Wild.

Latilo 61330

Total: 8; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Kogi 2, Niger 2, Taraba 1.

Microcharis longicalyx (J.B.Gillett) Schrire

Indigofera longicalyx J.B.Gillett

Daramola FHI 62386

Total: 11; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Microcharis remotiflora (Taub. ex Baker f.) Schrire

Indigofera remotiflora Taub. ex Baker f.

Gillett 15313

Total: 17; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 5, Plateau 1.

Microcharis tenella Benth.

Vogel [K000392621]

Total: 20; Borno 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Oyo 4.

Microcharis welwitschii (Baker) Schrire

Indigofera welwitschii Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Mildbraediodendron excelsum Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Millettia aboensis (Hook.) Baker

Millettia macrophylla var. *aboensis* Hook.

Emwiogbon FHI 87937

Total: 36; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 8, Ebonyi 3, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Osun 2, Rivers 1.

Millettia barteri (Benth.) Dunn

Lonchocarpus barteri Benth.

Daramola FHI 55242

Total: 28; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 3, Ekiti 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Millettia bipindensis Harms — Introduced

Meer, PPC van 1563; 1971-05-10 [WAG.1031805]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Millettia chrysophylla Dunn

Gillett 15368

Total: 8; Ondo 1.

Millettia conraui Harms

B.O. Daramola; 2008-12-01 [LUH.3284.0]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Millettia dinklagei Harms

Daramola FHI 55242

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Millettia drastica Welw. ex Baker

Okafor & Latilo FHI 57620

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Millettia griffoniana Baill.

Hepper 2268

Total: 26; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ogun 1.

Millettia hypolampra Harms

Talbot 578

Total: 1.

Millettia kennedyi Hoyle

J. D. Kennedy [GH.barcode-00065372]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 2.

Millettia macrophylla Benth.

Binuyo FHI 41439

Total: 2; Abia 1, Rivers 1.

Millettia pilosa Hutch. & Dalziel

Onochie FHI 36220X

Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 2.

Millettia thonningii (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Baker

Robinia thonningii Schumach. & Thonn.

Ayuba FHI 17952

Total: 61; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 3, Lagos 7, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1.

Millettia warneckei Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Millettia warneckei var. *warneckei*

Literature

Total: 0.

Millettia zechiana Harms

Latilo et al. FHI 71814

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 4.

Mimosa candollei R.Grether — Introduced

Schrankia leptocarpa DC.

Hossain et al. FHI 82371

Total: 21; Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.

Mimosa diplotricha C.Wright ex Sauvalle

— Introduced

s.n. 4873; 1990-02-13 [K003021354]

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Oyo 4.

Mimosa invis Mart. ex Colla — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-10-12 [FHI.42A]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Mimosa invis subsp. *invis* — Introduced

Mimosa pigra L. — Introduced

Geerling C. [BR0000018705751]

Total: 167; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 9, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 7, Bauchi 6, Bayelsa 1, Benue 2, Borno 5, Cross River 16, Delta 2, Edo 7, Enugu 1, Gombe 4, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 8, Katsina 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 18, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 16, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Mimosa pigra var. *asperata* (L.) Zarucchi,

Vincent & Gandhi — Introduced

Mimosa asperata L.

FHI66502; 1973-05-20 [K003021418]

Total: 16; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Mimosa pigra var. *pigra* — Introduced

Mimosa pudica L. — Introduced

Latilo FHI 43494

Total: 20; Benue 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 2.

Mimosa pudica var. *pudica* — Introduced

Jackson FHI 59599

Total: 1.

Mimosa rubicaulis Lam. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Mucuna balfouriana A.Murray bis

Literature

Total: 0.

Mucuna flagellipes Vogel ex Hook.f.

Okafor & Latilo FHI 57263

Total: 12; Anambra 1, Borno 2, Lagos 3, Ondo 1, Rivers 1.

Mucuna occidentalis (Hepper) T.M.Moura & G.P.Lewis

Mucuna poggei var. *occidentalis* Hepper

Odewo et al. FHI 84642

Total: 12; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 3.

Mucuna pruriens (L.) DC.

Dolichos pruriens L.

[DNS.LUH:4472]

Total: 40; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 4.

Mucuna pruriens var. *pruriens*

Dolichos pruriens L.

Ekwuno FHI 96055

Total: 4; Niger 1, Oyo 2.

Mucuna pruriens var. *utilis* (Wall. ex Wight)

Baker ex Burck — Introduced

Mucuna utilis Wall. ex Wight

Baker T.C.N. 669; 01-09-1977 [ABUH]

Total: 12; Kaduna 6, Lagos 3.

Mucuna sloanei Fawc. & Rendle

Binuyo FHI 57740

Total: 14; Lagos 1, Niger 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4.

Mucuna stans Welw. ex Baker

Latilo FHI 77299

Total: 5; Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Mucuna venenosa A.Murray bis

Literature

Total: 0.

Mundulea sericea (Willd.) A.Chev.

Cytisus sericeus Willd.

Cook 541

Total: 9; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Mundulea sericea subsp. *sericea*

Cytisus sericeus Willd.

Neltuma chilensis (Molina) C.E.Hughes &

G.P.Lewis — Introduced

Ceratonia chilensis Molina

Olorunfemi J.; Oguntayo; Ihe; 1978-10-6 [88570]1944998972

Total: 1.

Neltuma odorata (Torr. & Frém.)

C.E.Hughes & G.P.Lewis

Prosopis odorata Torr. & Frém.
 Léonard J. 4531; [BR0000016142152]
 Total: 1.

Neonotonia wightii (Wight & Arn.)
 J.A.Lackey
 Notonia wightii Wight & Arn.
 Latilo FHI 62289
 Total: 18; Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Neonotonia wightii subsp. *pseudojavanica*
 (Taub.) J.A.Lackey — Introduced
 Glycine pseudojavanica Taub.
 Latilo, M.G. 43; 1975-11-15 [K000628357]
 Total: 6; Taraba 1.

Neonotonia wightii subsp. *wightii*
 Notonia wightii Wight & Arn.
 Sharland; 871; 1979-10-01 [K003977932]
 Total: 9; Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Neorautanenia mitis (A.Rich.) Verdc.
 Dolichos mitis A.Rich.
 Lawlor & Hall 476
 Total: 24; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Delta 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Oyo 5, Plateau 2.

Neptunia oleracea Lour.
 Daggash, M.; FHI 24867; 1949-09-19 [K003702324]
 Total: 8; Borno 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Sokoto 1.

Neptunia prostrata (Lam.) Baill.
 Mimosa prostrata Lam.
 Stanfield FHI 59851
 Total: 11; Borno 2, Oyo 3, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Nesphostylis holosericea (Welw. ex Baker)
 Verdc.
 Vigna holosericea Welw. ex Baker
 Soladoye et al. FHI 84447
 Total: 19; Adamawa 1, Cross River 3, Oyo 1, Sokoto 12.

Neustanthus phaseoloides (Roxb.) Benth. —
 Introduced
 Dolichos phaseoloides Roxb.
 Olorunfemi et al. FHI 76174
 Total: 20; Abia 4, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Enugu 2, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Neustanthus phaseoloides var. *javanicus*
 (Benth.) A.N.Egan & B.Pan — Introduced
 Neustanthus javanicus Benth.
 Gbile, ZO; Latilo, MG FHI 20895; 1969-5-8
 [WAG.1040959]

Total: 1.

Neustanthus phaseoloides var. *phaseoloides*
 — Introduced
 Dolichos phaseoloides Roxb.

Newtonia buchananii (Baker) G.C.C.Gilbert
 & Boutique
 Piptadenia buchananii Baker
 Chapmann 4449
 Total: 14; Plateau 2, Taraba 12.

Ormocarpum megalophyllum Harms
 Onochie FHI 40406
 Total: 5; Edo 3, Ogun 1.

Ormocarpum pubescens (Hochst.) Cufod. ex
 J.B.Gillett
 Pictetia pubescens Hochst.
 Stanfield FHI 45619
 Total: 8; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Niger 3.

Ormocarpum sennoides (Willd.) DC.
 Hedysarum sennoides Willd.
 Meer PPC van; 1968-03-26 [WAG.1034967]
 Total: 23; Benue 2, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Ormocarpum sennoides subsp. *hispidum*
 (Willd.) Brenan & J.Léonard
 Cytisus hispidus Willd.
 Ariwaodo FHI 93273
 Total: 12; Benue 1, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Taraba 1.

Ormocarpum verrucosum P.Beauv.
 Gillett 15343
 Total: 17; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Rivers 1.

Osodendron altissimum (Hook.f.)
 E.J.M.Koenen
 Latilo, M.G., FHI47108; 1963-02-13 [K002634503]
 Total: 11; Abia 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Ondo 1, Rivers 2.

Ostryocarpus riparius Hook.f.
 Ariwaodo FHI 94636
 Total: 6; Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Pachyelasma tessmannii (Harms) Harms
 Stachyothyrsus tessmannii Harms
 Onochie FHI 40861
 Total: 2; Delta 1, Edo 1.

Parkia bicolor A.Chev.
 Latilo FHI 41306

Total: 55; Akwa Ibom 8, Borno 1, Cross River 16, Delta 2, Edo 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Parkia biglobosa (Jacq.) R.Br. ex G.Don
Mimosa biglobosa Jacq.

Gbile et al. 1170

Total: 127; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Katsina 9, Kebbi 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 15, Lagos 4, Niger 7, Ogun 5, Osun 4, Oyo 26, Sokoto 2, Taraba 3, Yobe 3, Zamfara 1.

Parkia filicoidea Welw. ex Oliv.

Chapman 4595

Total: 9; Kano 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Parkia timoriana (DC.) Merr. — Introduced
Inga timoriana DC.

; 1995-3-31 [FR-0026510]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Parkinsonia aculeata L. — Introduced

Latilo FHI 62776

Total: 31; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Peltophorum africanum Sond. — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-06-20 [FHI.211A]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Peltophorum pterocarpum (DC.) Backer ex K.Heyne — Introduced

Inga pterocarpa DC.

McMacGregor.; 1928-01-01 [FHI.2881-1]

Total: 37; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 6, Osun 1, Oyo 17, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Pentaclethra macrophylla Benth.

Gillett 15329

Total: 82; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 3, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 11, Delta 5, Edo 14, Enugu 5, Kaduna 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Pericopsis elata (Harms) Meeuwen

Afromosia elata Harms

Jones FHI 50557

Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Pericopsis laxiflora (Benth. ex Baker)

Meeuwen

Ormosia laxiflora Benth. ex Baker

Chapman 5014

Total: 76; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 11, Kano 3, Katsina 1,

Kebbi 1, Kogi 7, Lagos 1, Niger 15, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 5, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Phaseolus coccineus L. — Introduced

Etkin 65; 1988-7-3 [82065]1261541638

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Phaseolus lunatus L. — Introduced

Binuyo FHI 55440

Total: 82; Cross River 4, Delta 2, Kaduna 12, Niger 3, Oyo 47, Sokoto 9.

Phaseolus vulgaris L. — Introduced

[DNS.LUH:Aramide 251]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Philenoptera cyanescens (Schumach. & Thonn.) Roberty

Robinia cyanescens Schumach. & Thonn.

Daramola FHI 91185

Total: 66; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Enugu 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Rivers 1.

Philenoptera laxiflora (Guill. & Perr.)

Roberty

Lonchocarpus laxiflorus Guill. & Perr.

Geerling 3461

Total: 25; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 5, Borno 2, Kano 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 5.

Physostigma venenosum Balf.

Ekwuno FHI 96025

Total: 8; Cross River 5.

Piliostigma reticulatum (DC.) Hochst.

Bauhinia reticulata DC.

Olorunfemi FHI 55731

Total: 42; Bauchi 6, Borno 6, Edo 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 1.

Piliostigma thonningii (Schumach.) Milne-Redh.

Bauhinia thonningii Schumach.

Keay FHI 37156

Total: 150; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 7, Kogi 2, Kwara 15, Lagos 1, Niger 22, Ogun 16, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 25, Plateau 6, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Piptadeniastrum africanum (Hook.f.)

Brenan

Piptadenia africana Hook.f.

Okeke FHI 44319

Total: 78; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 5, Delta 2, Edo 9, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Taraba 6.

Pithecellobium dulce (Roxb.) Benth. —

Introduced

Mimosa dulcis Roxb.

[FHI.5657-2]

Total: 17; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 4, Oyo 8, Sokoto 1.

Platysepalum hirsutum (Dunn) Hepper

Milletia hirsuta Dunn

Daramola FHI 43295

Total: 1.

Platysepalum violaceum Welw. ex Baker

Total: 5; Kogi 1, Rivers 2.

Platysepalum violaceum var. *vanhouttei* (De Wild.) Hauman

Odewo & Ono FHI 80058

Total: 5; Kogi 1, Rivers 2.

Pleurolobus gangeticus (L.) J.St.-Hil. ex H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi

Hedysarum gangeticum L.

Soladoye et al. FHI 87493

Total: 42; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 1, Delta 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 5, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Pleurolobus salicifolius (Poir.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi

Hedysarum salicifolium Poir.

Latilo FHI 77379

Total: 28; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 6, Gombe 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Polhillides velutina (Willd.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi

Hedysarum velutinum Willd.

Gillett 15394

Total: 72; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 20, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Polhillides velutina subsp. *velutina*

Hedysarum velutinum Willd.

Sharland 660; 1979-09-01 [K003403709]

Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Prioria balsamifera (Vermoesen) Breteler

Pterygopodium balsamiferum Vermoesen

Onochie FHI 31173

Total: 46; Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 18, Kaduna 8, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Prioria mannii (Baill.) Breteler

Copaifera mannii Baill.

Osain FHI 14928

Total: 19; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 11, Delta 1.

Prioria oxyphylla (Harms) Breteler

Pterygopodium oxyphyllum Harms

Ainslie 10

Total: 3; Ondo 1.

Prosopis africana (Guill. & Perr.) Taub.

Coulteria africana Guill. & Perr.

Ariwaodo FHI 89251

Total: 41; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Borno 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 9, Ogun 2, Oyo 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 1, Zamfara 3.

Prosopis glandulosa Torr. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Prosopis glandulosa var. *glandulosa* — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Prosopis juliflora (Sw.) DC. — Introduced

Mimosa juliflora Sw.

Edwin Ujor [BR0000016142183]

Total: 6; Borno 4.

Prosopis juliflora var. *juliflora* —

Introduced

Mimosa juliflora Sw.

Pseudarthria confertiflora (A.Rich.) Baker

Rhynchosia confertiflora A.Rich.

Latilo & Taylor FHI 43390

Total: 8; Ogun 1, Oyo 5.

Pseudarthria fagifolia Baker

Odewo & Oni FHI 79970

Total: 15; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Rivers 1.

Pseudarthria hookeri Wight & Arn.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-09-28 [WAG.1039755]

Total: 46; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 9, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Osun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Pseudarthria hookeri var. *argyrophylla*
Verdc.

Latilo & Fagbemi FHI 64800
Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Pseudarthria hookeri var. *hookeri*
Chapman 134
Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Pseudoeriosema andongense (Welw. ex Baker) Hauman
Psoralea andongensis Welw. ex Baker
Stanfield FHI 54850
Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1.

Pseudovigna puerarioides Ern
Latilo FHI 62274
Total: 2.

Psophocarpus lancifolius Harms
Daramola FHI 62497
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Psophocarpus palustris Desv.
Ariwaodo FHI 92516
Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 3.

Psophocarpus scandens (Endl.) Verdc. —
Introduced
Diesingia scandens Endl.
Percy Amaury Talbot 1318; 1911 [BM013712385]
Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Oyo 2.

Psophocarpus tetragonolobus (L.) DC. —
Introduced
Dolichos tetragonolobus L.
Eijnatten CLM van; 1965-12-12 [WAG.1040122]
Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 2.

Pterocarpus angolensis DC. — Introduced
Ugwuzor P.O. NAUH58A 2010-06-20 [1990271914]
Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Pterocarpus brenanii Barbosa & Torre —
Introduced
B.O. Daramola LUH1997; 2004-02-01 [3808440894]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Pterocarpus erinaceus Poir.
Odewo et al. FHI 85281
Total: 22; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 4, Ogun 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Pterocarpus lucens Lepr. ex Guill. & Perr.
Latilo FHI 63474
Total: 18; Adamawa 6, Borno 1, Niger 6.

Pterocarpus lucens subsp. *lucens*
Barter [K000379385]
Total: 7; Adamawa 2, Niger 4.

Pterocarpus mildbraedii Harms
Chapman 3849
Total: 36; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Edo 12, Lagos 6, Ondo 11, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Pterocarpus osun Craib
Okeke FGI 44342
Total: 49; Borno 2, Cross River 8, Delta 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 8, Kogi 2, Lagos 8, Niger 3, Osun 1, Oyo 7.

Pterocarpus santalinoides L'Hér. ex DC.
Charter FHI 43266
Total: 57; Anambra 2, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 8, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 15, Osun 2, Oyo 14.

Pterocarpus soyauxii Taub.
Okeke FHI 24820
Total: 4.

Pterocarpus vidalianus Rolfe — Introduced
Pterocarpus erinaceus Fern.-Vill.
Dr. Kadiri A.B.; 2016-1-6 [7232]3808442982
Total: 6; Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Pueraria montana var. *lobata* (Willd.)
Maesen & S.M.Almeida ex Sanjappa &
Predeep — Introduced
Dolichos montanus Lour.
Literature
Total: 0.

Pueraria montana var. *montana* —
Introduced
Dolichos montanus Lour.
Hepper, F.N.; 1957-10-23 [P03131010]
Total: 1.

Rhynchosia ambacensis (Hiern) K.Schum.
Dolicholus ambacensis Hiern
Théodore Monod; 1949-12-17 [BM013714346]
Total: 2.

Rhynchosia ambacensis subsp. *ambacensis*
Dolicholus ambacensis Hiern

Rhynchosia buettneri Harms
Emwiogbon FHI 66012
Total: 10; Lagos 1, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Rhynchosia caribaea (Jacq.) DC. —

Introduced

Glycine caribaea Jacq.

Alan Philip Dalby Jones 950; 1942-2-14

[BM013714132]

Total: 1.

Rhynchosia congensis Baker

Latilo FHI 57718

Total: 9; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Plateau 2.

Rhynchosia congensis subsp. *congensis*

Rhynchosia densiflora (B.Heyne ex Roth)

DC.

Glycine densiflora B.Heyne ex Roth

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 96785

Total: 14; Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 6.

Rhynchosia densiflora subsp. *debilis*

(G.Don) Verdc.

Rhynchosia debilis G.Don

Latilo FHI 62248

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 2.

Rhynchosia hirta (Andrews) Meikle &

Verdc.

Dolichos hirtus Andrews

Lely 689

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Rhynchosia luteola (Hiern) K.Schum.

Dolicholus luteolus Hiern

Hepper 1538

Total: 4; Adamawa 2, Taraba 1.

Rhynchosia luteola var. *luteola*

Dolicholus luteolus Hiern

Rhynchosia mannii Baker

Daramola FHI 435682

Total: 10; Edo 7, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.

Rhynchosia minima (L.) DC.

Dolichos minimus L.

Meikle R.D.; 1949-12-11 [BR0000018334135]

Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Oyo 3.

Rhynchosia minima var. *minima*

Dolichos minimus L.

Latilo & Fagbemi FHI 70594

Total: 5; Adamawa 2, Kano 1, Niger 1.

Rhynchosia minima var. *prostrata* (Harv.)

Meikle

Rhynchosia memnonia var. *prostrata* Harv.

Ekwuno & Fagbemi FHI 93983

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 3.

Rhynchosia nyasica Baker

Lowe 67

Total: 18; Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Rhynchosia orthobotrya Harms

Keay, R.W.J.; FHI22511; 1948-02-29 [K003842274]

Total: 3; Kogi 1.

Rhynchosia preussii (Harms) Taub. ex

Harms

Cylista preussii Harms

[illegible] 1615 [K003842053]

Total: 1.

Rhynchosia procurrens (Hiern) K.Schum.

Dolicholus procurrens Hiern

Total: 8; Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Rhynchosia procurrens subsp. *floribunda*

(Baker) Verdc.

Rhynchosia floribunda Baker

Meikle R.D. [BR0000018337822]

Total: 7; Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Rhynchosia procurrens subsp. *latisepala*

(Hauman) Verdc.

Rhynchosia resinosa var. *latisepala* Hauman

Soladoye et al. FHI 83664

Total: 1.

Rhynchosia pycnostachya (DC.) Meikle

Cylista pycnostachya DC.

Latilo FHI 41550

Total: 21; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Taraba 1.

Rhynchosia resinosa (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)

Baker

Fagelia resinosa Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Morton 386

Total: 7; Plateau 6.

Rhynchosia sublobata (Schumach.) Meikle

Glycine sublobata Schumach.

Onochie FHI 40858

Total: 16; Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 7, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Rhynchosia viscosa DC.

Glycine viscosa Roth

Total: 12; Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 9.

Rhynchosia viscosa subsp. *violacea* (Hiern)
Verdc.

Dolicholus violaceus Hiern

Latilo FHI 60558

Total: 12; Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 8.

Rothia hirsuta (Guill. & Perr.) Baker

Xerocarpus hirsutus Guill. & Perr.

Daramola FHI 61585

Total: 12; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Plateau 2, Yobe 1.

Samanea saman (Jacq.) Merr. — Introduced

Mimosa saman Jacq.

Lowe FHI 77523

Total: 14; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 5.

Schotia africana (Baill.) Keay

Humboldtia africana Baill.

Talbot 1440

Total: 1.

Senegalia ataxacantha (DC.) Kyal. &
Boatwr.

Acacia ataxacantha DC.

Olorunfemi FHI 55657

Total: 75; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 15, Benue 1, Borno 6, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Ekiti 3, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Niger 2, Ogun 7, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 9, Zamfara 1.

Senegalia brevispica (Harms) Seigler &
Ebinger

Acacia brevispica Harms

Keay, R.W.J.; Okeke, R.E.; 1959-07-14 [P02878064]

Total: 2; Sokoto 1.

Senegalia brevispica subsp. *brevispica*

Acacia brevispica Harms

Senegalia dudgeonii (Craib) Kyal. &
Boatwr.

Acacia dudgeonii Craib

Latilo FHI 64752

Total: 85; Adamawa 9, Bauchi 11, Benue 2, Borno 3, Edo 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 10, Lagos 1, Niger 18, Oyo 10, Plateau 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Senegalia erythrocalyx (Brenan) Kyal. &
Boatwr.

Acacia erythrocalyx Brenan

Latiol FHI 43768

Total: 8; Kano 2, Katsina 2, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Senegalia goetzei subsp. *microphylla*
(Brenan) Kyal. & Boatwr. — Introduced

Acacia goetzei Harms

Geerling C. 4236; -- [BR0000016120174]

Total: 2.

Senegalia gourmaensis (A.Chev.) Kyal. &
Boatwr.

Acacia gourmaensis A.Chev.

Cook 348

Total: 37; Kebbi 3, Kwara 11, Niger 10, Oyo 8.

Senegalia kamerunensis (Gand.) Kyal. &
Boatwr.

Acacia kamerunensis Gand.

Okeke et al. FHI 73309

Total: 57; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 10, Edo 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 11, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Senegalia laeta (R.Br. ex Benth.) Seigler &
Ebinger

Acacia laeta R.Br. ex Benth.

Jackson FHI 14932

Total: 2; Borno 1, Jigawa 1.

Senegalia macrostachya (Rchb. ex DC.)
Kyal. & Boatwr.

Acacia macrostachya Rchb. ex DC.

Keay FHGI 37788

Total: 31; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kano 3, Katsina 6, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 6.

Senegalia mellifera (Vahl) Seigler &
Ebinger — Introduced

Mimosa mellifera Vahl

Rosevear D.R.; 1949-5-28 [26613]1944990724

Total: 2; Kwara 2.

Senegalia pennata (L.) Maslin —
Introduced

Mimosa pennata L.

[SANT.11784.0]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Senegalia pentagona (Schumach.) Kyal. &
Boatwr.

Mimosa pentagona Schumach.

Okeke et al. FHI 73307

Total: 18; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Senegalia polyacantha (Willd.) Seigler &
Ebinger

Acacia polyacantha Willd.
 Foster, E. [P03642505]
 Total: 89; Adamawa 5, Akwa Ibom 4, Bauchi 11, Benue 1, Borno 4, Gombe 4, Kaduna 7, Katsina 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 3, Niger 8, Ogun 7, Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 2.

Senegalia polyacantha subsp. *campylacantha* (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Kyal. & Boatwr.
Acacia campylacantha Hochst. ex A.Rich.
 Soladoye et al. FHI 91846
 Total: 54; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 8, Benue 1, Borno 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Katsina 2, Kwara 3, Niger 6, Ogun 4, Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Senegalia schweinfurthii (Brenan & Exell) Seigler & Ebinger — Introduced
Acacia schweinfurthii Brenan & Exell
 Jackson J.K. 5203; 1956-8-3 [57660]1944994787
 Total: 7; Kano 3, Katsina 2, Sokoto 2.

Senegalia senegal (L.) Britton
Mimosa senegal L.
 Soladoye et al. FHI 91828
 Total: 71; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Borno 25, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 4, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 3, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Senna alata (L.) Roxb. — Introduced
Cassia alata L.
 Olorunfemi FHI 94313
 Total: 41; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Edo 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 6, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Oyo 9.

Senna alexandrina Mill.
Cassia senna L.
 Total: 1; Katsina 1.

Senna alexandrina var. *alexandrina*
Cassia senna L.
 Hereźniak J.; 1975-01-29 [POZG-V-0051414]
 Total: 1; Katsina 1.

Senna auriculata (L.) Roxb. — Introduced
Cassia auriculata L.
 unknown [B.CHRB0034333]
 Total: 6; Enugu 1, Kano 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Senna bacillaris (L.f.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced
Cassia bacillaris L.f.
 P. Oguwa 13635; 1945-10-22 [US 1993646]
 Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Senna bicapsularis (L.) Roxb. — Introduced
Cassia bicapsularis L.

Assi 13669
 Total: 5; Enugu 1, Kano 1, Oyo 2.

Senna bicapsularis var. *bicapsularis* — Introduced
Cassia bicapsularis L.

Senna fruticosa (Mill.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced
Cassia fruticosa Mill.
 Oguwa P.; 1945-10-22 [13635]1944988904
 Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Senna hirsuta (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced
Cassia hirsuta L.
 Olorunfemi et al. FHI 88304
 Total: 37; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 7, Ondo 4, Osun 3, Oyo 9.

Senna hirsuta var. *hirsuta* — Introduced
Cassia hirsuta L.

Senna italica Mill.
 Soladoye et al. FHI 83784
 Total: 46; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 16, Gombe 2, Jigawa 1, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Osun 2, Sokoto 6, Zamfara 2.

Senna italica subsp. *italica*
Senna italica subsp. *micrantha* (Brenan) Lock — Introduced
 Akerigba C.U. 22; 1966-4-19 [57477]1944994619
 Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Sokoto 3.

Senna multijuga (Rich.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced
Cassia multijuga Rich.
 ; -- [11816]2821277864
 Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Senna obtusifolia (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced
Cassia obtusifolia L.
 Latilo FHI 61413
 Total: 95; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 6, Anambra 2, Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 8, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 2, Niger 11, Ogun 6, Osun 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Sokoto 3, Taraba 2.

Senna occidentalis (L.) Link
Cassia occidentalis L.
 Olorunfemi FHI 55093

Total: 62; Anambra 1, Borno 4, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Niger 2, Ogun 7, Ondo 1, Osun 8, Oyo 4.

Senna pallida var. *pallida* — Introduced

Cassia pallida Vahl

[SANT.11760.0]

Total: 1.

Senna podocarpa (Guill. & Perr.) Lock

Cassia podocarpa Guill. & Perr.

Latilo FHI 43497

Total: 38; Lagos 8, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 15.

Senna polyphylla (Jacq.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced

Cassia polyphylla Jacq.

Wit FHI 27781

Total: 8; Kano 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Senna polyphylla var. *polyphylla* — Introduced

Cassia polyphylla Jacq.

Senna septemtrionalis (Viv.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced

Cassia septemtrionalis Viv.

Denys E. [BR0000017612678]

Total: 7; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Senna siamea (Lam.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced

Cassia siamea Lam.

Pilz 1846

Total: 43; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 18, Sokoto 1.

Senna singueana (Delile) Lock

Cassia singueana Delile

Daramola FHI 62538

Total: 66; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 11, Borno 7, Gombe 4, Kaduna 7, Kano 3, Katsina 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Sokoto 3, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Senna sophera (L.) Roxb. — Introduced

Cassia sophera L.

Binuyo FHI 41351

Total: 25; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Senna spectabilis (DC.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced

Cassia spectabilis DC.

Gbile & Daramola FHI 92897

Total: 19; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Ogun 4, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Senna spectabilis var. *spectabilis* — Introduced

Cassia spectabilis DC.

Senna surattensis (Burm.f.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby — Introduced

Cassia surattensis Burm.f.

Latilo FHI 33996

Total: 18; Cross River 1, Lagos 3, Oyo 9, Rivers 2.

Senna tora (L.) Roxb.

Cassia tora L.

[SANT.11800.0]

Total: 20; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 5, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Senna × *floribunda* (Cav.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby

Cassia × floribunda Cav.

Ugbogu O.A.; Odewo T.K. ; 2001-06-21 [106230.0]

Total: 1.

Sesbania bispinosa (Jacq.) W.Wight — Introduced

Aeschynomene bispinosa Jacq.

Etkin 194A; 1988-06-27 [MOBOT92544]

Total: 6; Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Oyo 1.

Sesbania cannabina (Retz.) Pers. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Sesbania dalzielii E.Phillips & Hutch.

Ekwuno FHI 93931

Total: 13; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 4, Niger 1, Sokoto 1.

Sesbania grandiflora (L.) Poir. — Introduced

Robinia grandiflora L.

Rowland s.n.

Total: 1.

Sesbania hepperi J.B.Gillett

Lamb 69

Total: 10; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Niger 2, Taraba 3.

Sesbania leptocarpa DC.

Sampson 23

Total: 7; Borno 2, Yobe 1.

Sesbania leptocarpa var. *leptocarpa*

Sesbania macrantha Welw. ex E.Phillips & Hutch.

Hepper 1527

Total: 7; Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Sesbania macrantha var. *macrantha*

Chapman 3204

Total: 1.

Sesbania pachycarpa DC.

Olorunfemi et al. FHI 96305

Total: 36; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Sesbania pachycarpa subsp. *pachycarpa*

Latilo MG; Fagbemi A; 1972-10-21 [WAG.1043104]

Total: 2; Ekiti 1.

Sesbania rostrata Bremek. & Oberm.

s.coll. [K000239633]

Total: 8; Borno 4, Katsina 2.

Sesbania sericea (Willd.) Link

Coronilla sericea Willd.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-11-02 [WAG.1043188]

Total: 5; Borno 2, Kwara 1, Oyo 2.

Sesbania sesban (L.) Merr.

Aeschynomene sesban L.

Latilo FHI 64713

Total: 45; Abia 5, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Sesbania sesban subsp. *punctata* (DC.)

J.B.Gillett

Sesbania punctata DC.

Jackson JAD; 1963-11-28 [WAG.1304257]

Total: 21; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Rivers 1.

Sesbania sesban subsp. *sesban*

Aeschynomene sesban L.

Parsons, A.C.; 154; 1907-10-01 [K003428537]

Total: 2; Benue 1.

Sesbania sesban var. *bicolor* (Wight & Arn.)

F.W.Andrews — Introduced

Sesbania aegyptiaca var. *bicolor* Wight & Arn.

Etkin 58; 1988-3-16 [92710]1261852620

Total: 1.

Sesbania sesban var. *nubica* Chiov.

Literature

Total: 0.

Sesbania sudanica J.B.Gillett

Literature

Total: 0.

Smithia elliotii Baker f.

Chapman 3374

Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Smithia elliotii var. *elliotii*

Cheek M.R.; 1996-11-19 [BR0000009205963]

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Sohmaea laxiflora (DC.) H.Ohashi &

K.Ohashi — Introduced

Desmodium laxiflorum DC.

Sharland 1471

Total: 22; Borno 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Oyo 5.

Sophora tomentosa L.

Total: 5; Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Sophora tomentosa var. *occidentalis* (L.)

Isely

Latilo FHI 37957

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Sphenostylis schweinfurthii Harms

Latilo et al. FHI 69357

Total: 41; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 9, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Niger 3, Plateau 5, Zamfara 1.

Sphenostylis schweinfurthii subsp.

schweinfurthii

Sphenostylis stenocarpa (Hochst. ex

A.Rich.) Harms

Dolichos stenocarpus Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Barter 1804

Total: 12; Benue 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 4, Plateau 1.

Stemonocoleus micranthus Harms

Lancaster FHI 2887

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Edo 2.

Stylosanthes erecta P.Beauv.

Chapman FHI 62123

Total: 19; Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Stylosanthes fruticosa (Retz.) Alston

Arachis fruticosa Retz.

Lowe 1509

Total: 65; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 6, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 10, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 8.

Stylosanthes guianensis (Aubl.) Sw. — Introduced

Trifolium guianense Aubl.

[Oneachusim, H.O.; 1963-03-08 \[P00206227\]](#)

Total: 9; Delta 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Stylosanthes guianensis subsp. *guianensis* — Introduced

Trifolium guianense Aubl.

[Chapman 3229](#)

Total: 1.

Stylosanthes hamata (L.) Taub. —

Introduced

[Literature](#)

Total: 0.

Stylosanthes humilis Kunth — Introduced

[Literature](#)

Total: 0.

Stylosanthes viscosa (L.) Sw. — Introduced

[Literature](#)

Total: 0.

Sunhangia elegans (DC.) H.Ohashi & K.Ohashi — Introduced

Desmodium elegans DC.

[R. Schlechter 12335; 1899-3-1 \[Z-000082191\]](#)

Total: 1.

Talbotiella eketensis Baker f. — Endemic

[Keay FHI 37716](#)

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 2, Rivers 2.

Tamarindus indica L. — Introduced

[Olorunfemi FHI 55785](#)

Total: 37; Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Tephrosia bracteolata Guill. & Perr.

[Soladoye et al. FHI 86337](#)

Total: 74; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 3, Niger 3, Ogun 5, Osun 3, Oyo 25, Plateau 4.

Tephrosia bracteolata var. *bracteolata*

Tephrosia candida DC. — Introduced

[Ebun Akinyemi LUH2315; 1968-02-02 \[3808443453\]](#)

Total: 3; Oyo 2, Zamfara 1.

Tephrosia densiflora Hook.f.

[Millen 140](#)

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Tephrosia elegans Schumach.

[Tuley 1676](#)

Total: 36; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Ebonyi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Niger 6, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Tephrosia flexuosa G.Don

[Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-09-23 \[WAG.1045462\]](#)

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 8.

Tephrosia humilis Guill. & Perr.

[Olorunfemi FHI 24362](#)

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Tephrosia linearis (Willd.) Pers.

Galega linearis Willd.

[Ariwaodo 1033](#)

Total: 69; Adamawa 2, Anambra 3, Bauchi 12, Benue 3, Borno 6, Edo 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 3, Zamfara 1.

Tephrosia linearis var. *linearis*

Galega linearis Willd.

Tephrosia lupinifolia DC.

[Hepper 953](#)

Total: 4; Ebonyi 1, Niger 2.

Tephrosia mossiensis A.Chev.

[Lawlor & Hall 477](#)

Total: 13; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Kano 1, Zamfara 1.

Tephrosia nana Kotschy ex Schweinf.

[Sharland 1416](#)

Total: 23; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Gombe 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3, Ondo 1, Plateau 4.

Tephrosia nubica (Boiss.) Baker

Pogonostigma nubicum Boiss.

[Corradi, R. 4325; 1939-08-03 \[K003845975\]](#)

Total: 1.

Tephrosia obcordata (Poir.) Baker

Podalyria obcordata Lam.

[Dalziel 336](#)

Total: 4; Niger 1.

Tephrosia paniculata Welw. ex Baker

[Hepper 1077](#)

Total: 12; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Tephrosia pedicellata Baker

Latilo FHI 71933

Total: 40; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 7, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Niger 4, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 3.

Tephrosia platycarpa Guill. & Perr.

Odewo & Oni FHI 79956

Total: 28; Anambra 1, Benue 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.

Tephrosia purpurea (L.) Pers.

Cracca purpurea L.

Latilo FHI 63468

Total: 20; Bauchi 3, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 5, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Tephrosia purpurea subsp. *leptostachya* (DC.) Brummitt

Tephrosia leptostachya DC.

Daramola FHI61597

Total: 1.

Tephrosia radicans Welw. ex Baker

Sharland 867

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Tephrosia uniflora Pers.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000017342193]

Total: 12; Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Sokoto 4.

Tephrosia uniflora subsp. *uniflora*

Dalziel JM [WAG.L.2027221]

Total: 2.

Tephrosia vogelii Hook.f.

Tuley 987

Total: 37; Abia 2, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Imo 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 5, Taraba 6.

Teramnus buettneri (Harms) Baker f.

Glycine buettneri Harms

Daramola FHI 86237

Total: 2; Kwara 1.

Teramnus labialis (L.f.) Spreng.

Glycine labialis L.f.

Magaji SO; Leeuw PN de; 1965-12-01 [WAG.1047127]

Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Teramnus labialis subsp. *arabicus* Verdc.

Lely 632

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Teramnus labialis subsp. *labialis*

Glycine labialis L.f.

Jones, A.P.D.; Keay, R.W.J.; FHI14228; 1945-11-17 [K003988080]

Total: 4; Lagos 2.

Teramnus micans (Welw. ex Baker) Baker f.

Glycine micans Welw. ex Baker

Hepper 1075

Total: 5; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Teramnus micans var. *micans*

Glycine micans Welw. ex Baker

Teramnus uncinatus (L.) Sw.

Dolichos uncinatus L.

Olorunfemi, J.; FHI55060; 1964-10-13 [K003988110]

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Teramnus uncinatus subsp. *axilliflorus* (Kotschy) Verdc.

Glycine axilliflora Kotschy

Dalziel 589

Total: 2; Benue 1.

Teramnus uncinatus subsp. *ringoetii* (De Wild.) Verdc.

Glycine ringoetii De Wild.

Latilo FHI 73600

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Tetrapleura tetraptera (Schumach. & Thonn.) Taub.

Adenanthera tetraptera Schumach. & Thonn.

Odewo & Oni FHI 79844

Total: 79; Anambra 3, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Edo 8, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 30.

Tipuana tipu (Benth.) Kuntze — Introduced

Machaerium tipu Benth.

Chapman J.W.F. 5901; 1981-10-3 [BR0000016953420]

Total: 1.

Trifolium baccarinii Chiov.

Hall 1666

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Taraba 3.

Trifolium repens L. — Introduced

A. Ludwig; 1938-06-23 [KR-M-0047644 / 859712 / 342653]

Total: 1.

Trifolium rueppellianum Fresen.

Tuley 1043

Total: 3.

Trifolium simense Fresen.

[Hewan] s.n. [K003502983]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Trifolium usambarense Taub.

Hepper 1733

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Tylosema fassoglense (Kotschy ex Schweinf.) Torre & Hillc.

Bauhinia fassoglensis Kotschy ex Schweinf.

Literature

Total: 0.

Uraria picta (Jacq.) Desv. ex DC.

Hedysarum pictum Jacq.

Ariwaodo FHI 73235

Total: 47; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Vachellia amythethophylla (Steud. ex A.Rich.) Kyal. & Boatwr.

Acacia amythethophylla Steud. ex A.Rich.

Jackson FHI 17852

Total: 21; Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kwara 2, Niger 3, Sokoto 8, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Vachellia arenaria (Schinz) Kyal. & Boatwr. — Introduced

Acacia arenaria Schinz

Ajaiyeoba E.; 2002-2-3 [106141]1945001489

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Vachellia farnesiana (L.) Wight & Arn. — Introduced

Mimosa farnesiana L.

Kennedy 2163

Total: 7; Edo 1, Kaduna 1.

Vachellia gerrardii (Benth.) P.J.H.Hurter

Acacia gerrardi Benth.

A.Y. Fow [P.S-PL-10571]

Total: 21; Abia 1, Adamawa 12, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Vachellia gerrardii var. *gerrardii*

Acacia gerrardi Benth.

Cook 347

Total: 1.

Vachellia hockii (De Wild.) Seigler & Ebinger

Acacia hockii De Wild.

Latilo FHI 63477

Total: 92; Adamawa 8, Bauchi 15, Benue 2, Borno 10, Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Kano 1, Kogi 8, Kwara 8, Niger 17, Oyo 1, Plateau 11, Taraba 1.

Vachellia nilotica (L.) P.J.H.Hurter & Mabb.

Mimosa nilotica L.

Dalziel J.M. [FHI.49826.0]

Total: 114; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 2, Borno 19, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 4, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 4, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 15, Oyo 5, Plateau 2, Sokoto 11, Taraba 2, Zamfara 2.

Vachellia nilotica subsp. *adstringens* (Schumach.) Kyal. & Boatwr.

Mimosa adstringens Schumach.

Keay FHI 37328A

Total: 22; Adamawa 1, Borno 6, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 4.

Vachellia nilotica subsp. *nilotica*

Mimosa nilotica L.

Jackson FHI 14934

Total: 4.

Vachellia nilotica subsp. *tomentosa* (Benth.) Kyal. & Boatwr.

Acacia arabica var. *tomentosa* Benth.

Jackson FHI 14935

Total: 1.

Vachellia seyal (Delile) P.J.H.Hurter

Acacia seyal Delile

Latilo FHI 64738

Total: 58; Bauchi 7, Benue 1, Borno 9, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Katsina 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 4, Taraba 2, Zamfara 6.

Vachellia seyal var. *seyal*

Acacia seyal Delile

Vachellia sieberiana (DC.) Kyal. & Boatwr.

Acacia sieberiana DC.

[DNS.LUH:4170]

Total: 75; Adamawa 7, Bauchi 4, Borno 8, Gombe 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 11, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 4, Sokoto 5, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Vachellia sieberiana var. *sieberiana*

Acacia sieberiana DC.

Olorunfemi FHI 55744

Total: 44; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 2, Borno 5, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 4, Kwara 2, Niger 8, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 5, Zamfara 1.

Vachellia sieberiana var. *villosa* (A.Chev.)
Kyal. & Boatwr.

Acacia sieberiana var. villosa A.Chev.

Jackson FHI 27742

Total: 7; Kaduna 4, Niger 1.

Vachellia tortilis (Forssk.) Galasso & Banfi

Mimosa tortilis Forssk.

Dr. A.B. Kadiri; others; 2011-09-10 [LUH.4159.0]

Total: 28; Borno 17, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Vachellia tortilis subsp. *raddiana* (Savi)

Kyal. & Boatwr.

Acacia raddiana Savi

Okeke et al. FHI 69313

Total: 18; Borno 13, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1.

Vigna ambacensis Welw. ex Baker

Ekwuno FHI 76983

Total: 26; Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Gombe 2, Sokoto 19.

Vigna comosa Baker

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Vigna comosa subsp. *comosa*

Gbile et al. FHI 64580

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Vigna frutescens A.Rich.

s.coll.; s.n.; [K001357535]

Total: 12; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Sokoto 6.

Vigna frutescens subsp. *frutescens*

Hepburn 135

Total: 3; Niger 2.

Vigna frutescens var. *buchneri* (Harms)

Verdc.

Vigna gracilis (Guill. & Perr.) Hook.f.

Dolichos gracilis Guill. & Perr.

Ariwaodo FHI 73218

Total: 34; Borno 1, Cross River 10, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Vigna heterophylla A.Rich. — Introduced

Migeod F.W.H. 444; 1928-01-30

[BR0000017420778]

Total: 3.

Vigna juruana (Harms) Verdc. —

Introduced

Phaseolus juruanus Harms

Literature

Total: 0.

Vigna longifolia (Benth.) Verdc. —

Introduced

Phaseolus longifolius Benth.

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot 3294b;

-- [BM000556274]

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Vigna longissima Hutch.

Okafor FHI 59272

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Vigna marina (Burm.) Merr.

Barter 1827

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 6.

Vigna membranacea A.Rich. — Introduced

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/1302559465>

Total: 1.

Vigna multinervis Hutch. & Dalziel

Daramola FHI 29478

Total: 3.

Vigna nigrizia Hook.f.

Gbile et al. FHI 64579

Total: 4.

Vigna oblongifolia A.Rich.

Moiser 2067211

Total: 6; Sokoto 4.

Vigna oblongifolia var. *oblongifolia*

Vigna parkeri Baker — Introduced

van Eijnatten

Total: 6; Kaduna 1.

Vigna parkeri subsp. *maranguensis* (Taub.
ex Engl.) Verdc.

Eijnatten CLM van Eijnatten, CLM van 2082; 1966-
09-27 [WAG.1052533]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Vigna pubigera Baker

Geerling C; 1971-09-30 [WAG.1051957]

Total: 5; Kwara 1, Oyo 2.

Vigna pubigera var. *benuensis* (Pasquet &
Maréchal) Pasquet & Maesen

Hambler D.J.; 1960-11-09 [BR0000017428989]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Vigna pubigera var. *pubigera*

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Vigna racemosa (G.Don) Hutch. & Dalziel
ex Baker f.

Clitoria racemosa G.Don

[DNS.LUH:5194]

Total: 53; Anambra 1, Benue 3, Borno 3, Cross River 10, Delta 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 2, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Sokoto 26, Taraba 1.

Vigna radiata (L.) R.Wilczek — Introduced

Phaseolus radiatus L.

1977-08-01 [DNS.PI 425754 (MONT)]

Total: 5; Borno 1.

Vigna radiata var. *radiata* — Introduced

Phaseolus radiatus L.

[DNS.PI 425754 (MONT)]

Total: 2.

Vigna radiata var. *sublobata* (Roxb.) Verdc. — Introduced

Phaseolus sublobatus Roxb.

1995-10-01 [FR-0019451]

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Vigna radicans Welw. ex Baker

Hepper F.N.; 1957-10-21 [BR0000017431972]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Vigna reticulata Hook.f.

Sharland 1462

Total: 22; Borno 1, Kebbi 1, Sokoto 6.

Vigna subterranea (L.) Verdc.

Glycine subterranea L.

Lawlor & Hall 236

Total: 43; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 10, Kaduna 16, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Sokoto 5, Taraba 2.

Vigna triphylla (R.Wilczek) Verdc.

Haydonia triphylla R.Wilczek

Lely 828

Total: 2; Sokoto 1.

Vigna unguiculata (L.) Walp.

Dolichos unguiculatus L.

Gbile et al. FHI 65444

Total: 183; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Gombe 3, Kaduna 22, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Osun 3, Oyo 7, Sokoto 27, Taraba 1.

Vigna unguiculata subsp. *dekindtiana* (Harms) Verdc.

Vigna dekindtiana Harms

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000017437295]

Total: 6; Borno 1, Oyo 2.

Vigna unguiculata subsp. *stenophylla*

(Harv.) Maréchal, Mascherpa & Stainier

Vigna triloba var. stenophylla Harv.

Stefano Padulosi S.N.; [BR0000016152168]

Total: 1.

Vigna unguiculata subsp. *unguiculata*

Dolichos unguiculatus L.

Harold A. Royer; 1936-09-01 [BM013711302]

Total: 26; Cross River 4, Sokoto 17.

Vigna venulosa Baker — Introduced

Morton, J.K. & Gledhill: 1963-11[1302563376]

Total: 1.

Vigna vexillata (L.) A.Rich.

Phaseolus vexillatus L.

Soladoye et al. FHI 91827

Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Sokoto 10.

Vigna vexillata var. *angustifolia* (Schumach. & Thonn.) Baker

Plectrotropis angustifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Geerling, C 3307; 1970-11-03 [WAG.1053550]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Sokoto 3.

Vigna vexillata var. *vexillata*

Phaseolus vexillatus L.

Harold A. Royer; 1936-09-01 [BM013711536]

Total: 3.

Vigna wittei Baker f.

Hepper 1088

Total: 2; Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Wajira grahamiana (Wight & Arn.) Thulin & Lavin

Phaseolus grahamianus Wight & Arn.

Lely 552

Total: 2.

Xylia xylocarpa (Roxb.) W.Theob. — Introduced

Mimosa xylocarpa Roxb.

Osiyemi Seun; 2005-10-12 [FHI107359] 1945001694

Total: 7; Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 4.

Zapoteca portoricensis (Jacq.) H.M.Hern.

— Introduced

Mimosa portoricensis Jacq.

Daramola & Ehe FHI 85171

Total: 52; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 7, Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Zapoteca portoricensis subsp. *flavida* (Urb.)

H.M.Hern. — Introduced

Calliandra flavida Urb.

Literature

Total: 0.

Zapoteca portoricensis subsp. *portoricensis*

— Introduced

Mimosa portoricensis Jacq.

Thomas, N.W.; 1016; 1911-01-01 [K003183708]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Zenkerella citrina Taub.

Hall 2943

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Zornia durumensis De Wild.

Keay FHI 37324

Total: 8; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 3.

Zornia glochidiata Rchb. ex DC.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-09-15 [WAG.1053903]

Total: 37; Bauchi 1, Borno 9, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kano 3, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Zornia latifolia Sm. — Introduced

Meikle, R.D.; 1949-10-15 [K.11646.0]

Total: 30; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 6, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 6, Rivers 1.

POLYGALACEAE

Atroxima afzeliana (Oliv. ex Chodat) Stapf

Carpolobia afzeliana Oliv. ex Chodat

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70694; 1973-3-2

[WAG.1954781]

Total: 16; Bayelsa 1, Ekiti 4, Kaduna 3, Ogun 1, Osun 4, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Atroxima liberica Stapf

Meer, PPC van 1182; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1954530]

Total: 3; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2.

Carpolobia alba G.Don

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 328; 1977-10-12

[WAG.1954401]

Total: 35; Abia 3, Adamawa 2, Cross River 5, Delta 9, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Carpolobia lutea G.Don

Odewo, TK; Adedeji ODA 321; 1983-5-16

[WAG.1226227]

Total: 173; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 3, Borno 2, Cross River 17, Delta 3, Edo 31, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 17, Ogun 14, Ondo 8, Osun 9, Oyo 34.

Polygala acicularis Oliv.

Latilo, MG FHI 61428; 1971-11-3 [WAG.1424217]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1.

Polygala albida Schinz

Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Osun 1, Plateau 5.

Polygala albida subsp. *stanleyana* (Chodat)

Paiva

Young, J.D.; 10; 1922-01-01 [K003077853]

Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Osun 1, Plateau 5.

Polygala arenaria Willd.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86481; 1978-5-26

[WAG.1935463]

Total: 77; Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 7, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 6, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Polygala atacorensis Jacq.-Fél.

Croat, Thomas Bernard 53368; 1981-11-14 [98263]

[2598787004]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Polygala baikiei Chodat

Barter 564; -- [K000231581]

Total: 35; Bauchi 3, Benue 3, Borno 2, Kaduna 6, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Polygala baikiei subsp. *baikiei*

Latilo, MG FHI 64771; 1972-9-18 [WAG.1277139]

Total: 17; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Plateau 2.

Polygala butyracea Heckel

Hepper F.N.; 1957-11-16 [BR0000017147552]

Total: 11; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Polygala butyracea var. *butyracea*

Hepper F.N. 1382; 1957-11-16 [BR0000017147552]

Total: 1.

Polygala capillaris E.Mey. ex Harv.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3862; 1971-7-29 [WAG.1277210]

Total: 2; Kwara 1, Oyo 1.

Polygala capillaris subsp. *capillaris*

Geerling, C 4339; 1971-10-7 [WAG.1277274]

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Polygala erioptera DC.

; 1995-10-23 [FR-0020733] [3046112243]

Total: 9; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Imo 1, Niger 1, Rivers 1, Yobe 1.

Polygala fernandesiana Paiva

Literature

Total: 0.

Polygala guineensis Willd.

Geerling, C 3968; 1971-8-12 [WAG.1935821]

Total: 3; Niger 1.

Polygala irregularis Boiss.

Hagerup, O. ; 1927-- [P00375265]

Total: 3; Borno 1.

Polygala minuta Paiva

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 21019; 1947-11-2 [K000231589]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Polygala multiflora Poir.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO 872; 1971-11-8 [WAG.1277254]

Total: 16; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Enugu 1, Osun 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1.

Polygala myriantha Chodat

Daramola, B.O.; FHI62477; 1968-12-05 [K003732763]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Polygala persicariifolia DC.

Hepper F.N. 1344; 1957-11-14 [BR0000017816427]

Total: 17; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Lagos 2, Plateau 4.

Polygala petitiana A.Rich.

Magaji SO; Leeuw PN de; 1967-09-15 [WAG.1936489]

Total: 22; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 3, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Polygala petitiana subsp. *petitiana*

Magaji, SO; Leeuw, PN de 165; 1967-9-15 [WAG.1936488]

Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Polygala rarifolia DC.

Sharland, R.E. 1445; 1980-10-10 [K000453375]

Total: 4; Kaduna 2.

Polygala sphenoptera Fresen. — Introduced

Verdcourt3559; 1963-1-20 [CONN00148703] [699266611]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Polygala tenuicaulis Hook.f.

Total: 7; Adamawa 3, Taraba 3.

Polygala tenuicaulis var. *tayloriana* Paiva

Chapman, J.D.; 5068; 1977-11-16 [K003077948]

Total: 7; Adamawa 3, Taraba 3.

Polygala xanthina Chodat

Latilo, M.G.; FHI. 4690; 1962-11-02 [K003078001]

Total: 4; Kaduna 2, Plateau 1.

Securidaca longepedunculata Fresen.

Pilz, GE 1935; 1977-3-31 [WAG.1546403]

Total: 58; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 8, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 4, Taraba 1, Zamfara 2.

Securidaca welwitschii Oliv.

Kennedy J.D. 2063; 1931-- [BR0000016458796]

Total: 10; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Sokoto 1.

Senega capillaris (E.Mey. ex Harv.)

J.F.B.Pastore

Polygala capillaris E.Mey.

Literature

Total: 0.

Senega fernandesiana (Paiva) J.F.B.Pastore

Polygala fernandesiana Paiva

Literature

Total: 0.

ROSACEAE

Alchemilla cryptantha Steud. ex A.Rich.

Gbile, ZO FHI 62887; 1970-4-2 [WAG.1561080]

Total: 17; Gombe 1, Taraba 14.

Alchemilla kiwuensis Engl.

Hepper F.N. 2101; 1958-2-20 [BR0000017687850]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Sokoto 1.

Eriobotrya japonica (Thunb.) Lindl.

Mespilus japonica Thunb.

Eijnatten CLM van Eijnatten, CLM van 1391; 1966-04-15 [WAG.1506149]

Total: 1.

Prunus africana (Hook.f.) Kalkman

Pygeum africanum Hook.f.

Chapman J.D. 4333; 17-05-1976 [K]

Total: 8; Taraba 8.

Rosa canina L. — Introduced

Morah Christian C.; 2008-3-22 [9365] [3808441209]

Total: 4; Anambra 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Rosa × *polliniana* Spreng.

Usang Felix ; 1999-05-10 [29.0]

Total: 1.

Rubus apetalus Poir.

Hall J.B.; Daramola B.O.; 1970-07-21 [FHI.29871-1]

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Taraba 6.

Rubus apetalus var. *apetalus*

Daramola, BO D 118; 1977-8-18 [WAG.1215605]
Total: 1.

Rubus fellatae A.Chev.
Chapman J.D. 4423; 01-05-1976 [K]
Total: 5; Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Rubus kingaensis Engl.
Wit, P.; Gbile, Z.O.; Daramola, B.O. 2065; 1972-05-11 [K004675332]
Total: 4; Borno 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Rubus pinnatus Willd.
Meer, PPC van 1818; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1200229]
Total: 14; Cross River 3, Taraba 6.

Rubus rigidus Sm. — Introduced
Wit HCD de; Gbile ZO; Daramola BO
WAG.1200684; 1972-05-11 [WAG.1200684]
Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Rubus rigidus var. *camerunensis* Letouzey
Wit, HCD de; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 2065; 1972-5-11 [WAG.1200684]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Rubus rosifolius Sm. — Introduced
Chapman, JD 2653; 1972-2-5 [WAG.1200785]
Total: 10; Kogi 1, Taraba 9.

RHAMNACEAE

Gouania longipetala Hemsl.
Kennedy J.D. [BR0000017131285]
Total: 37; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Gombe 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 5, Osun 5, Oyo 5, Taraba 3.

Gouania longispicata Engl.
Keay & Savory; - [FHL-]
Total: 3; Cross River 1, Taraba 1.

Lasiodiscus fasciculiflorus Engl.
J. D. Kennedy [US 1716668]
Total: 13; Cross River 2, Edo 8.

Lasiodiscus marmoratus C.H.Wright
Olorunfemi; 18864.0 [FHL-]
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Maesopsis eminii Engl. — Introduced
Akarigbo Olugbemi; 2016-9-8 [9376] [3808440161]
Total: 11; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Rhamnus prinoides L'Hér.
Hepper F.N.; 1958-02-22 [BR0000017957878]
Total: 2.

Ventilago africana Exell
Alwyn H. Gentry; George E. Pilz; 1981-06-16 [MO.175935.0]
Total: 3; Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Ventilago diffusa (G.Don) Exell
Celastrus diffusus G.Don
Literature
Total: 0.

Ziziphus abyssinica Hochst. ex A.Rich.
Geerling C; 1970-10-22 [WAG.1192832]
Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Ziziphus jujuba Mill. — Introduced
Rhamnus zizyphus L.
Dalziel [P06791302]
Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Ziziphus lotus (L.) Lam.
Rhamnus lotus L.
Total: 2; Borno 2.

Ziziphus lotus subsp. *saharae* (Batt. & Trab.) Maire — Introduced
Ziziphus saharae Batt. & Trab.
Denys E. 681; 1982-7-19 [BR0000018056129]
Total: 2; Borno 2.

Ziziphus mauritiana Lam.
F. Ryan; 1915-09-06 [US 946655]
Total: 22; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 6, Gombe 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Ziziphus mauritiana var. *mauritiana*
Küppers K.; 35567.0
Total: 1.

Ziziphus mucronata Willd.
Kamphorst A; 1960-04-01 [WAG.1193055]
Total: 31; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Delta 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Ziziphus mucronata subsp. *mucronata*
Neumann K.; 34614.0
Total: 1.

Ziziphus pubescens subsp. *pubescens*
Amachi FHI38284 [K004370464]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Ziziphus spina-christi (L.) Desf.
Rhamnus spina-christi L.
Daggash [BR0000018457582]

Total: 26; Bauchi 2, Borno 8, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Niger 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Ziziphus spina-christi var. *spina-christi*

Rhamnus spina-christi L.

Zach B.; 34678.0

Total: 4; Bauchi 2, Niger 1.

ULMACEAE

Holoptelea grandis (Hutch.) Mildbr.

Hymenocardia grandis Hutch.

Onyeachusim, HD FHI 46996; 1963-2-7

[WAG.1852478]

Total: 18; Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 5, Osun 4, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Holoptelea integrifolia (Roxb.) Planch. —

Introduced

Ulmus integrifolia Roxb.

Punch, Cyril 151; 1901-7-25 [E00034365]574983663

Total: 1.

CANNABACEAE

Cannabis sativa L. — Introduced

Latilo, M.G. 34213; 1954-9-15 [11029]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 2.

Celtis adolfi-friderici Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Celtis africana Burm.f.

Daramola, B.; FHI43182; 1958-10-01 [K004538016]

Total: 2.

Celtis gomphophylla Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Celtis mauritiana Planch.

Literature

Total: 0.

Celtis mildbraedii Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1724; 1971-5-20 [WAG.1972001]

Total: 27; Borno 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 8, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Celtis philippensis Blanco — Introduced

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32662; 1981-6-14

[WAG.1856355]

Total: 51; Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 4, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 11, Ondo 6, Osun 4, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Celtis prantlii Priemer ex Engl.

Gentry, A.; Pilz, G.; 32662; 1981-06-14

[K004538167]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Celtis solenostigma Unwin — Endemic

Literature

Total: 0.

Celtis toka (Forssk.) Hepper & J.R.I.Wood

Ficus toka Forssk.

Blom-van Teyn, M van 153; 1972-7-8

[WAG.1852654]

Total: 49; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Osun 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Zamfara 2.

Celtis zenkeri Engl.

Verwilghen 27; 1997-3-18 [BR0000018717181]

Total: 51; Abia 1, Borno 4, Edo 6, Enugu 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 3, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 5, Oyo 8, Taraba 2.

Chaetachme aristata Planch.

Pilz, GE 1926; 1977-1-8 [WAG.1852554]

Total: 11; Ekiti 3, Kwara 1, Ogun 6.

Humulus lupulus L. — Introduced

; -- [43479] K

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Sparrea gomphophylla (Baker) X.G.Fu &

T.S.Yi

Celtis gomphophylla Baker

Chapman, J.D. 4546; 1976-08-02 [K004538017]

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Trema orientale (L.) Blume

Celtis orientalis L.

Pilz, GE 2028; 1977-4-27 [WAG.1852110]

Total: 57; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 5, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

MORACEAE

Afromorus mesozygia (Stapf) E.M.Gardner

Morus mesozygia Stapf

Chevalier, A.J.B. 16267 03/1907; P

Total: 17; Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

Antiaris toxicaria (J.F.Gmel.) Lesch.

Cestrum toxicarium J.F.Gmel.

Wit, HCD de 12672; 1966-1-1 [WAG.1104149]

Total: 30; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Osun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Antiaris toxicaria subsp. *welwitschii* (Engl.)

C.C.Berg

Antiaris welwitschii Engl.

Chevalier, A.J.B. ; 1905-7- [P00533898]

Total: 6; Oyo 2.

Antiaris toxicaria var. *africana* Scott Elliot
ex A.Chev.

Onyeachusim, HD FHI 48021; 1963-12-10

[WAG.1104164]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Oyo 1.

Artocarpus altilis (Parkinson) Fosberg —

Introduced

Sitodium altile Parkinson

Banks & Solander, s.n. 13/04/1769; BM

Total: 10; Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Artocarpus heterophyllus Lam. —

Introduced

Perez-Arbelaez, E. s.n., 12/01/1932; COL

Total: 6; Osun 1, Oyo 5.

Artocarpus integer (Thunb.) Merr. —

Introduced

Radermachia integra Thunb.

; -- [42777]2428986935

Total: 2; Delta 2.

Dorstenia africana (Baill.) C.C.Berg

Trymatococcus africanus Baill.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70533; 1973-3-8

[WAG.1104500]

Total: 21; Abia 1, Cross River 14, Edo 1.

Dorstenia barteri Bureau

Coombe D.E. 166; 1955-3-13 [BR0000016845824]

Total: 21; Abia 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 14, Niger 1.

Dorstenia barteri var. *barteri*

Meer, PPC van 1105 A; 1971-4-1 [WAG.1104561]

Total: 2; Benue 1, Cross River 1.

Dorstenia barteri var. *multiradiata* (Engl.)

Hijman & C.C.Berg

Meer, PPC van 1402; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1104580]

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Dorstenia barteri var. *subtriangularis*

(Engl.) Hijman & C.C.Berg

Talbot; Talbot, P s.n.; -- [K000243101]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dorstenia ciliata Engl.

Coombe, D.E. 174; 1955-3-12 [29497]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Dorstenia cuspidata Hochst.

Magaji, SO; Ayuba, ASM 145; 1967-8-16

[WAG.1104678]

Total: 25; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 8, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ondo 2, Osun 2.

Dorstenia cuspidata var. *cuspidata*

Keay R.W.J. FHI37777; 10-07-1959 [K]

Total: 5; Kaduna 3.

Dorstenia cuspidata var. *preussii* (Engl.)

Hijman

Keay R.W.J. FHI37046; 02-06-1957 [K]

Total: 6; Niger 2, Ondo 2.

Dorstenia kameruniana Engl. — Introduced

Welwitsch, F.M.J. 2594 01/01/1978; K

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dorstenia lujae De Wild.

Percy Amaury Talbot; 2314; 1912-01-01

[BM000911401]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 3.

Dorstenia lujae var. *lujae*

Onochie C.F.A. FHI36301X; 05-02-1957 [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Dorstenia mannii Hook.f.

Thomson, W. C. 10; -- [K000243096]

Total: 18; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 9, Lagos 1.

Dorstenia mannii var. *alternans* (Engl.)

Hijman

Meer, PPC van 1857; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1104977]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dorstenia mannii var. *mannii*

Meer, PPC van 1720; 1971-5-20 [WAG.1105022]

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Dorstenia mannii var. *mungensis* (Engl.)

Hijman

Literature

Total: 0.

Dorstenia picta Bureau

Coombe D.E. 167; 12-03-1955 [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Dorstenia poinsettiifolia Engl. —

Introduced

Tessmann, 701 10/12/1908; K

Total: 1.

Dorstenia poinsettiifolia var. *angusta*

(Engl.) Hijman & C.C.Berg

E. Bebiem et al. 1195; 1996-1-8 [1054388]

[1258261040]

Total: 1.

Dorstenia prorepens Engl.

Brenan J.P.M. 8460; 1947-12-10 [BR0000018254617]

Total: 7; Edo 5.

Dorstenia psilurus Welw. — Introduced

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO; Fagbemi, A FHI 71026; 1974-7-11 [WAG.1105245]

Total: 16; Cross River 3, Edo 3, Niger 2, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Taraba 1.

Dorstenia tenera Bureau — Introduced

Mann, G. 1776 1862; P

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Dorstenia tenera var. *obtusibracteata*

(Engl.) Hijman & C.C.Berg — Introduced

Ariwaodo, JO 233; 1977-1-31 [WAG.1105285]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Ficus abutilifolia (Miq.) Miq.

Urostigma abutilifolium Miq.

Medler, JA 578; 1971-2-6 [WAG.1105553]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 6, Zamfara 2.

Ficus adolphi-friderici Mildbr.

Meer, PPC van 1171; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1105573]

Total: 2; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Ficus ardisioides Warb.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11320; 1977-4-1 [WAG.1105669]

Total: 20; Cross River 5, Delta 4, Edo 8, Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Ficus ardisioides subsp. *camptoneura*

(Mildbr.) C.C.Berg

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32885; 1981-6-21

[WAG.1105672]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Edo 6, Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Ficus asperifolia Miq.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65852; 1972-10-7

[WAG.1105859]

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Ficus barteri Sprague

Barter, C.; 1858-- [P00434329]

Total: 11; Cross River 3, Delta 1, Kogi 1.

Ficus benamina L. — Introduced

Lanre; 2011-1-1 [3555]3808443731

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Ficus bubu Warb. — Introduced

Stolz, A. 1827 20/09/1983; K

Total: 4; Enugu 1.

Ficus capreifolia Delile

Kamphorst, A 100; 1960-4-1 [WAG.1106047]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1.

Ficus chlamydocarpa subsp. *chlamydocarpa*

— Introduced

Mildbraed, J. 6408 22/12/1954; K

Total: 1.

Ficus conraui Warb. — Introduced

Milbread 7106 01/01/1979; K

Total: 6; Edo 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Ficus cordata Thunb. — Introduced

Kotschy 257 1837; K

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Ficus craterostoma Warb. ex Mildbr. & Burret

Meer, PPC van 939; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1106261]

Total: 13; Edo 4, Kwara 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Ficus demeusei Warb.

Chapman J.D. 3606; 30-11-1974 [K]

Total: 10; Lagos 4, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Ficus dicranostyla Mildbr. — Introduced

Chevalier, A 562; K

Total: 5; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 2, Taraba 1.

Ficus elastica Roxb. ex Hornem. —

Introduced

Brass, L.J. 641 01/10/1958; K

Total: 1.

Ficus elasticoides De Wild.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI17011; 19-03-1946 [K]

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Ficus exasperata Vahl

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi FHI 38777; 1977-7-4

[WAG.1106542]

Total: 60; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 21, Ogun 9, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Taraba 1.

Ficus glumosa Delile

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 113; 1979-4-27 [WAG.1106748]

Total: 51; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 2, Gombe 3, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Zamfara 2.

Ficus heophylla Miq.

Alwyn H. Gentry; George E. Pilz Gentry 32971; 1981-06-23 [704585.0]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Ficus ingens (Miq.) Miq.

Urostigma ingens Miq.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK; Macauley, S FHI 66417; 1973-5-17 [WAG.1106945]

Total: 28; Bauchi 4, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Zamfara 3.

Ficus kamerunensis Warb. ex Mildbr. & Burret

Brenan, J.P.M. 8664; -- [15955]912011483

Total: 3; Ondo 3.

Ficus laurifolia Lam.

Etkin 24; 1987-11-7 [714495]1261433106

Total: 3; Anambra 1, Kaduna 1.

Ficus lecardii Warb.

Daramola B.O FHI62543; 09-01-1968 [K]

Total: 14; Kaduna 4, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Ficus lutea Vahl

Berg, CC 103; 1972-5-13 [WAG.1107174]

Total: 61; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 15, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 14, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Ficus lyrata Warb.

; -- [P06879493]

Total: 2.

Ficus microcarpa L.f. — Introduced

Cavalerie, J. 3601 01/10/1958; K

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Ficus mucoso Welw. ex Ficalho

Welw. 6416; K

Total: 12; Edo 1, Kaduna 4, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Ficus natalensis Hochst.

Sim, T.R. 5729 1908; K

Total: 35; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 5, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 14, Plateau 1.

Ficus natalensis subsp. *leprieurii* (Miq.)

C.C.Berg

Preuss, P.R. 544 01/08/1975; K

Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Nasarawa 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7.

Ficus oreodryadum Mildbr.

Mildbraed, J. 1031 08/1907; B

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Ficus ottoniifolia (Miq.) Miq. — Introduced

Urostigma ottoniifolium Miq.

Chapman, J.D. 567 13/05/1958; K

Total: 15; Lagos 3, Oyo 9, Taraba 1.

Ficus ottoniifolia subsp. *ottoniifolia*

Urostigma ottoniifolium Miq.

Onochie, C.F.; Jones, A.P.D. FHI17208; 1946-3-27 [K000044449]

Total: 6; Lagos 1, Oyo 3.

Ficus platyphylla Delile

Cabra, 37 1897; B

Total: 23; Bauchi 5, Kaduna 2, Kano 3, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Plateau 1, Zamfara 2.

Ficus polita Vahl

Sim, T.R. 5549 1908; K

Total: 12; Kano 1, Kebbi 2, Niger 4, Oyo 3, Zamfara 1.

Ficus polita subsp. *polita*

McWhinter, J.H. 192; K

Total: 1.

Ficus populifolia Vahl

Kotschy, 415 1837; K

Total: 9; Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Ficus preussii Warb.

Preuss, 454 1890; B

Total: 1.

Ficus pseudomangifera Hutch.

Scott Elliot, G.F. 4499 14/01/1892; K

Total: 2.

Ficus pumila L. — Introduced

Dr. A. B. Kadiri; 2009-1-5 [451]3808443657

Total: 2; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Taraba 1.

Ficus recurvata De Wild.

Laurent, M. 809 07/06/1905;

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1.

Ficus sagittifolia Warb. ex Mildbr. & Burret

- Scott Elliot, G.F. 4656; K
Total: 4; Ogun 2, Taraba 2.
- Ficus sansibarica* Warb. — Introduced
Illegible 256 01/01/1983; K
Total: 5; Kaduna 3, Taraba 2.
- Ficus sansibarica* subsp. *macrosperma*
(Warb. ex Mildbr. & Burret) C.C.Berg
Latilo, MG FHI 61441; 1971-11-5 [WAG.1108143]
Total: 4; Kaduna 2, Taraba 2.
- Ficus saussureana* DC.
Berol, H. s.n.; L
Total: 21; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 7, Enugu 4,
Kogi 2, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.
- Ficus sur* Forssk.
Hemp, A. 580 12/09/1991
Total: 91; Bauchi 7, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Enugu 2,
Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 15,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Osun 10, Oyo 12, Plateau 4,
Taraba 10.
- Ficus sycomorus* L.
Hemp, A. 5691b 19/09/2012
Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue
1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kano 2, Zamfara 3.
- Ficus tessellata* Warb. — Introduced
Mildbread 6411 12/04/1985; K
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.
- Ficus thonningii* Blume
Rob, E. 913 14/01/1922; K
Total: 48; Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 3,
Kano 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 6, Osun 1,
Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 1.
- Ficus tremula* Warb.
Kirk, 18 10/1866; K
Total: 8; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3.
- Ficus tremula* subsp. *kimuensis* (Warb.)
C.C.Berg
Gossweiler, J. 4597 28/05/1910; K
Total: 7; Abia 2, Cross River 3.
- Ficus trichopoda* Baker
Cavalerie, J. 3968 1912; E
Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 7, Benue 2, Kaduna 1,
Kogi 1, Plateau 1.
- Ficus umbellata* Vahl
Gossweiler, J. 10089 01/06/1935; COI
Total: 9; Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1,
Plateau 1.
- Ficus vallis-choudae* Delile
- Bequaert, J. 3188 24/03/1914; BR
Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 2, Ondo 1, Oyo
2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.
- Ficus variifolia* Warb.
Schweinfurth, G. 3614; K
Total: 7; Kwara 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.
- Ficus verruculosa* Warb.
Chevalier, A. 7721 03/07/1903; K
Total: 5; Niger 1, Taraba 1.
- Ficus vogeliana* (Miq.) Miq.
Sycomorus vogeliana Miq.
None, 550; K
Total: 16; Borno 1, Cross River 6, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1,
Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Rivers 2.
- Hijmania angusticornis* (Engl.)
M.D.M.Vianna — Introduced
Dorstenia angusticornis Engl.
Zenker, G.A. 3584 26/08/1975; K
Total: 2; Cross River 2.
- Hijmania turbinata* (Engl.) M.D.M.Vianna
Dorstenia turbinata Engl.
Schlechter, FRR 12871 01/01/1900; L
Total: 32; Abia 4, Cross River 23, Kogi 1, Niger 1.
- Milicia excelsa* (Welw.) C.C.Berg
Morus excelsa Welw.
Synnott, T.J. 460 17/01/1970; MHU
Total: 66; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Cross
River 2, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Niger 3,
Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 22, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.
- Morus alba* L. — Introduced
Henry, A. 5668 1885; BM
Total: 2.
- Scyphosyce manniana* Baill.
Mann, 1727 1862; K
Total: 3; Edo 2.
- Scyphosyce pandurata* Hutch.
Talbot, P.A. 2317 1912; BM
Total: 16; Abia 1, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Kogi 1,
Niger 2.
- Sloetiopsis usambarensis* Engl.
Burrows, J.E.; Burrows, S.M. 11313 23/03/2009;
BNRH
Total: 16; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Cross River 9, Oyo 2.
- Treculia acuminata* Baill. — Introduced
Mr & Mrs Talbot sn; 1912- [K]
Total: 10; Cross River 2.
- Treculia africana* Decne. ex Trécul

Mann, G. 773 02/1861; K
Total: 32; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Edo 4, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Treculia africana var. *africana*

Millson, A. s.n.; 1894-4-23 [K000243490]

Total: 6.

Treculia africana var. *inversa* Okafor —

Endemic

Literature

Total: 0.

Treculia africana var. *mollis* (Engl.)

J.Léonard

Zenker, G. 3333 1907; M

Total: 2; Borno 1, Edo 1.

Treculia obovoidea N.E.Br.

Thomson, 104; K

Total: 27; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 4, Borno 1, Cross River 11, Kwara 1, Ogun 1.

Treculia zenkeri Engl.

Zenker, G. 1045 01/01/1896; LE

Total: 1.

Trilepisium madagascariense DC.

Horne, 417 01/01/1977; K

Total: 50; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Edo 4, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

URTICACEAE

Boehmeria nivea (L.) Gaudich. —

Introduced

Urtica nivea L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1452; 1966-4-25 [WAG.1185904]

Total: 2; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Boehmeria virgata (G.Forst.) Guill.

Urtica virgata G.Forst.

Daramola, BO FHI 84525; 1977-8-18

[WAG.1185981]

Total: 13; Cross River 4, Delta 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Taraba 3.

Boehmeria virgata subsp. *macrophylla*

(Hornem.) Friis & Wilmot-Dear

Boehmeria macrophylla Hornem.

Chapman, J.D.; 2833; 1972-05-24 [K003800736]

Total: 7; Cross River 3, Kaduna 2, Taraba 1.

Boehmeria virgata var. *macrostachya*

(Wight) Friis & Wilmot-Dear

Splitgerbera macrostachya Wight

Meer PPC van Meer, PPC van 1827; 1971-05-25

[WAG.1185985]

Total: 1; Imo 1.

Boehmeria virgata var. *tomentosa* (Wedd.)

Friis & Wilmot-Dear

Boehmeria tomentosa Wedd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cecropia peltata L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Elatostema mannii Wedd.

Coombe D.E. 175; 1955-3-13 [BR0000019564173]

Total: 5; Cross River 4, Rivers 1.

Elatostema monticola Hook.f.

Chapman, JD 2872; 1972-6-3 [WAG.1186238]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Elatostema paivaeaeum Wedd.

Daramola, B.O. FHI62357; 1968-11-27

[K003416990]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Elatostema welwitschii Engl.

Savory, H.J.; Keay, R.W.J.; FHI25054; 1948-12-20

[K003416981]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Girardinia diversifolia (Link) Friis

Urtica diversifolia Link

Chapman, J.D.; 3448; 1974-11-07 [K003630946]

Total: 6; Delta 1, Taraba 2.

Girardinia diversifolia subsp. *diversifolia*

Urtica diversifolia Link

Laportea aestuans (L.) Chew

Urtica aestuans L.

Pilz, GE 2633; 1981-11-2 [WAG.1186524]

Total: 40; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Sokoto 1.

Laportea alatipes Hook.f.

Ohaeri A.O. 2605; 13-09-1988 [ABUH]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Laportea mooreana (Hiern) Chew

Adicea mooreana Hiern

Hepper F.N. & Daramola B.O. 1340; 1957-11-13

[BR0000019253794]

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Laportea ovalifolia (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Chew

Haynea ovalifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Berg, CC 117; 1972-5-15 [WAG.1186780]

Total: 39; Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 3, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 11.

Lecanthus peduncularis (Royle) Wedd.

Procris peduncularis Royle

Chapman, J.D. 3608; 1974-12-01 [K003448489]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Musanga cecropioides R.Br. ex Tedlie

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32697; 1981-6-15

[WAG.1110098]

Total: 25; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 1.

Myrianthus arboreus P.Beauv.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32709; 1981-6-16

[WAG.1110227]

Total: 42; Abia 3, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Gombe 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Myrianthus preussii Engl.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 389; 1977-10-15

[WAG.1110366]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 8, Niger 1.

Myrianthus preussii subsp. *preussii*

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 389; 1977-10-15

[WAG.1110366]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 5.

Myrianthus serratus (Trécul) Benth. &

Hook.f.

Dicranostachys serrata Trécul

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67618; 1973-2-21

[WAG.1110411]

Total: 19; Bayelsa 1, Benue 5, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Enugu 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 1.

Myrianthus serratus var. *serratus*

Dicranostachys serrata Trécul

Kamphorst, A 151; 1960-4-1 [WAG.1110447]

Total: 14; Bayelsa 1, Benue 3, Cross River 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 1.

Myriocarpa obovata Donn.Sm. —

Introduced

C. F. Baker 2489; 1903-2-20

[RSA0006373]2430223652

Total: 1.

Parietaria debilis G.Forst.

Hepper F.N. 2029; 1958-2-17 [BR0000019258058]

Total: 1.

Pilea angolensis (Hiern) Rendle

Adicea tetraphylla var. angolensis Hiern

Literature

Total: 0.

Pilea angolensis subsp. *angolensis*

Adicea tetraphylla var. angolensis Hiern

Literature

Total: 0.

Pilea microphylla (L.) Liebm. — Introduced

Parietaria microphylla L.

[SANT.11809.0]

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1.

Pilea microphylla var. *microphylla* —

Introduced

Parietaria microphylla L.

; -- [11809] [2821280853]

Total: 1.

Pilea rivularis Wedd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pilea rivularis var. *rivularis*

Literature

Total: 0.

Pilea serpyllifolia (Poir.) Wedd. —

Introduced

Parietaria serpyllifolia Poir.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1374; 1966-4-15 [WAG.1187256]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Pilea sublucens Wedd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pilea tetraphylla (Steud.) Blume

Urtica tetraphylla Steud.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pouzolzia denudata De Wild. & T.Durand

— Introduced

Berg, CC 116; 1972-5-15 [WAG.1187367]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Pouzolzia guineensis Benth.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 270; 1977-10-10
[WAG.1187404]
Total: 33; Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1,
Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 5,
Ondo 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 2.

Pouzolzia mixta Solms — Introduced
Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [79B] [1990271904]
Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Scepocarpus batesii (Rendle) T.Wells &
A.K.Monro
Uera batesii Rendle
Brenan, J.P.M.9018; 1948-2-13 [13185] [912008383]
Total: 2; Edo 2.

Scepocarpus cordifolius (Engl.) T.Wells &
A.K.Monro
Uera cordifolia Engl.
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67707; 1973-2-27
[WAG.1187626]
Total: 32; Abia 2, Cross River 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Kogi
1, Lagos 3, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 1, Taraba
1.

Scepocarpus flamignianus (Lambinon)
T.Wells & A.K.Monro
Uera flamigniana Lambinon
Literature
Total: 0.

Scepocarpus gabonensis (Pierre ex Friis)
T.Wells & A.K.Monro
Uera gabonensis Pierre ex Friis
Gentry, A.; Pilz, G. 32861; 1981-06-20 [K003734115]
Total: 3; Ondo 2.

Scepocarpus mannii Wedd.
Dalziel, J.M. 1021; -- [K000040269]
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Scepocarpus oblongifolius (Benth.) T.Wells
& A.K.Monro
Uera oblongifolia Benth.
Meer, PPC van 1294; 1971-4-15 [WAG.1187796]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Scepocarpus repens (Wedd.) T.Wells &
A.K.Monro
Laporte repens Wedd.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1594; 1966-6-7 [WAG.1187819]
Total: 16; Cross River 1, Edo 8, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo
3.

Scepocarpus rigidus (Benth.) T.Wells &
A.K.Monro

Boehmeria rigida Benth.
Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 373; 1978-5-9
[WAG.1187867]
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1.

Scepocarpus thonneri (De Wild. &
T.Durand) T.Wells & A.K.Monro
Uera thonneri De Wild. & T.Durand
Literature
Total: 0.

Scepocarpus trinervis (Hochst.) T.Wells &
A.K.Monro
Elatostema trinerve Hochst.
Eimunjze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70278; 1974-5-21
[WAG.1188029]
Total: 11; Cross River 1, Edo 3, Niger 1, Ogun 2,
Ondo 2.

Uera talbotii Rendle
Eijnatten, CLM van 1470; 1966-5-8 [WAG.1187882]
Total: 1.

Urtica dioica L. — Introduced
Usang Felix; 2005-10-13 [299] [3913474554]
Total: 1; Lagos 1.

NOTHOFAGACEAE

Nothofagus pullei Steenis — Introduced
Vink, W.; 1966-8-27 [P06806154]
Total: 1.

FAGACEAE

Castanopsis acuminatissima (Blume) A.DC.
— Introduced
Castanea acuminatissima Blume
Hartley, T.G.; 1962-7-17 [P06850619]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Lithocarpus megacarpus Soepadmo —
Introduced
Takeuchi, W.; Kulang, J.; 1996-10-28 [P06853777]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Lithocarpus rufovillosus (Markgr.) Rehder
— Introduced
Pasania rufovillosa Markgr.
Hartley, T.G.; 1964-1-24 [P06853782]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

CASUARINACEAE

Casuarina equisetifolia L. — Introduced
Ujor, EU FHI 23910; 1948-9-27 [WAG.1446461]
Total: 27; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5,
Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 13.

BETULACEAE

Alnus glutinosa (L.) Gaertn. — Introduced
Betula alnus var. glutinosa L.
F. Martínez; 1957-8-13 [MA-01-00169317]
Total: 2.

ANISOPHYLLEACEAE

Anisophyllea cabole Henriq.
Brenan, J.P.M.; 8423; 1947-12-08 [K003357051]
Total: 1.

Anisophyllea mayumbensis Exell
Brenan, J.P.M.; 9086; 1948-02-21 [K003357055]
Total: 1.

Anisophyllea meniaudii Aubrév. & Pellegr.
Latilo, M.G.; Oguntayo FHI70556; 1973-3-11
[K000040165]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Anisophyllea myriosticta Floret
Schmitt 526; 1995-3-7 [976849]
Total: 10; Abia 2, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Kwara 2,
Plateau 1.

Anisophyllea obanica Li Bing Zhang, Xin
Chen & H.He — Endemic
Schmitt 373; 1995-2-8 [976743]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Anisophyllea polyneura Floret
Latilo, M.G.; Oyeachusim, M.D.; FHI53967; 1964-02-
18 [K003357065]
Total: 3.

Anisophyllea purpurascens Hutch. &
Dalziel
Mr and Mrs Talbot, P.A.; -- [K000075948]
Total: 6; Cross River 3, Niger 3.

Poga oleosa Pierre
Onyeachusim H.D. & Latilo M.G. FHI54024; 1964-2-
18 [BR0000017070744]
Total: 11; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Kaduna 2.

CUCURBITACEAE

Bambekea racemosa Cogn.
Daramola, BO FHI 71300; 1974-7-17
[WAG.1415893]
Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Edo
9, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1.

Blastania cerasiformis (Stocks) A.Meeuse
Zehneria cerasiformis Stocks
Daramola B.O.; Josephine; 1970-11-27 [63652]
Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 1,
Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 1.

Cayaponia africana (Hook.f.) Exell
Trianosperma africanum Hook.f.
Stanfield D.P.; 1957-11-15 [FHI.40038.0]
Total: 22; Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun
2, Oyo 9.

Cayaponia africana var. *africana*
Trianosperma africanum Hook.f.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1988; 1966-9-20 [WAG.1416028]
Total: 1.

Citrullus colocynthis (L.) Schrad.
Cucumis colocynthis L.
; 1995-9-8 [FR-0018321]3046044116
Total: 1; Borno 1.

Citrullus lanatus (Thunb.) Matsum. & Nakai
— Introduced
Momordica lanata Thunb.
Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1226; 1972-5-2
[WAG.1753839]
Total: 37; Ekiti 1, Gombe 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 6,
Kano 2, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Citrullus mucospermus (Fursa) Fursa
Citrullus lanatus subsp. mucospermus Fursa
; -- [PI249010]3818312841
Total: 8.

Coccinia adoensis (Hochst. ex A.Rich.)
Cogn.

Momordica adoensis Hochst. ex A.Rich.
Wit P., Gbile Z.O. & Daramola B.O.
[BR0000016356573]
Total: 18; Adamawa 6, Benue 1, Borno 1, Imo 1,
Kano 1, Plateau 3, Zamfara 1.

Coccinia adoensis var. *adoensis*
Momordica adoensis Hochst. ex A.Rich.
Wit P.; Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O. 1795; 1972-5-5
[65094]
Total: 1.

Coccinia barteri (Hook.f.) Keay

Staphylosyce barteri Hook.f.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1648; 1966-6-29 [WAG.1578376]
Total: 51; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 10, Delta 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 8.

Coccinia grandis (L.) Voigt

Bryonia grandis L.
Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. 437; 1962-8-16 [18459]2013040605
Total: 13; Bauchi 6, Borno 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Coccinia keayana R.Fern.

Edwin Ujor; 1948-11-18 [23933]2013040877
Total: 4; Edo 2, Osun 1.

Coccinia longicarpa Jongkind

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A FHI17030; 23-03-1946 [K]
Total: 4; Ogun 2, Osun 1.

Cogniauxia podolaena Baill.

Geerling, C 3062; 1970-10-23 [WAG.1754433]
Total: 2; Bauchi 2.

Corallocarpus boehmii (Cogn.) C.Jeffrey

Kedrostis boehmii Cogn.
Hall J.B.; Daramola B.O. FHI67398; 18-07-1970 [K]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Corallocarpus epigaeus (Rottler) Hook.f.

Bryonia epigaea Rottler

Literature
Total: 0.

Cucumis ficifolius A.Rich.

collectors: Feeny Dane; 1976-2-27 [162708]3798049229
Total: 2.

Cucumis maderaspatanus L.

Latilo, MG FHI 63547; 1971-10-25 [WAG.1761254]
Total: 52; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 8, Kano 7, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Cucumis melo L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1434; 1966-4-24 [WAG.1761145]
Total: 86; Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1, Borno 15, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 4, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 6, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 3, Oyo 13, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Cucumis metuliferus Jacques

Ariwaodo J.O.; Jeffery C. 101; 1983-8-23 [100489]2013044926

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Yobe 1.

Cucumis prophetarum L.

s.coll 51; 1988-8-13 [K000731902]
Total: 14; Borno 4, Gombe 1, Niger 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Cucumis prophetarum subsp. *prophetarum*

Daramola B.O. 63705; 1970-12-4 [BR0000008924346]
Total: 2; Gombe 1.

Cucumis pustulatus Naudin ex Hook.f.

Dalziel J.M. 129; 17-10-1907 [K]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Sokoto 1.

Cucumis rostratus J.H.Kirkbr.

Brenan J.P.M. 8875; 22-01-1948 [K]
Total: 1.

Cucumis sativus L. — Introduced

; -- [CGN21634]121008071
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Cucurbita maxima Duchesne — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1898; 1966-9-1 [WAG.1761636]
Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 1.

Cucurbita moschata Duchesne —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1610; 1966-6-13 [WAG.1761539]
Total: 9; Oyo 9.

Cucurbita pepo L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1435; 1966-4-24 [WAG.1761551]
Total: 13; Cross River 3, Kano 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 4.

Eureiandra formosa Hook.f.

Daramola B.O.; Ekwuno P.; 1970-7-14 [67316]
Total: 5; Benue 1, Kogi 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Gerrardanthus lobatus (Cogn.) C.Jeffrey

Gerrardanthus grandiflorus var. lobatus Cogn.
Daramola B.O. FHI67435; 17-07-1970 [K]
Total: 4; Bauchi 2.

Gerrardanthus paniculatus (Mast.) Cogn.

Atheranthera paniculata Mast.
Talbot, Mr P.A. 1454; -- [K000242619]
Total: 4; Cross River 3, Rivers 1.

Kedrostis foetidissima (Jacq.) Cogn.

Trichosanthes foetidissima Jacq.
Dalziel J.M. 128; 20-09-1907 [K]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Niger 1.

Kedrostis leloja (Forssk. ex J.F.Gmel.)

C.Jeffrey

Turia leloja Forssk. ex J.F.Gmel.

Daramola B.O; Ekwuno P.O. FHI67487; 04-07-1970 [K]

Total: 3; Bauchi 2.

Lagenaria breviflora (Benth.) Roberty

Adenopus breviflorus Benth.

Geerling, C 3308; 1970-11-3 [WAG.1415866]

Total: 51; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Cross River 5, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 1, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Lagenaria guineensis (G.Don) C.Jeffrey

Bryonia guineensis G.Don

Redheed J.F. ; 1963-5-15 [47565]2013041939

Total: 3; Edo 1, Lagos 1.

Lagenaria rufa (Gilg) C.Jeffrey

Adenopus rufus Gilg

Cooper L.G. & Binuyo A. FHI41429; 05-08-1959 [K]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Oyo 2.

Lagenaria siceraria (Molina) Standl.

Cucurbita siceraria Molina

Geerling, C 4026; 1971-8-15 [WAG.1524062]

Total: 32; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Cross River 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Oyo 2.

Luffa acutangula (L.) Roxb. — Introduced

Cucumis acutangulus L.

; -- [E00299983]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Luffa aegyptiaca Mill. — Introduced

Momordica luffa L.

Geerling, C 4025; 1971-8-15 [WAG.1524241]

Total: 27; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Oyo 8.

Luffa echinata Roxb.

Wickens G.E. 3549; 10-12-1975 [Lake Chad]

Total: 4; Borno 3.

Melothria sphaerocarpa (Cogn.) H.Schaef.

& S.S.Renner — Introduced

Posadaea sphaerocarpa Cogn.

Wit, P 749; 1971-10-21 [WAG.1754321]

Total: 18; Benue 2, Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5.

Momordica angustisepala Harms

Meer, PPC van 1873; 1971-1-1 [WAG.1524309]

Total: 32; Cross River 2, Edo 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 10.

Momordica balsamina L.

Bartha R. S.N.; -- [BR0000015397010]

Total: 18; Bauchi 4, Borno 6, Kano 1, Yobe 2.

Momordica cabrae (Cogn.) C.Jeffrey

Dimorphochlamys cabrae Cogn.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1222; 1966-2-24 [WAG.1761500]

Total: 15; Cross River 5, Edo 1, Kogi 3, Oyo 2.

Momordica camerounensis Keraudren

; -- [M:H. Schaefer 06/99]3346512578

Total: 1.

Momordica charantia L.

Schlechter R. [BR0000014853487]

Total: 44; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 4.

Momordica charantia subsp. *charantia*

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 100; 1979-4-23

[WAG.1416037]

Total: 1.

Momordica cissoides Planch. ex Cogn.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1082; 1971-12-28

[WAG.1416146]

Total: 41; Borno 1, Cross River 4, Edo 3, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Momordica foetida Schumach.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 681; 1977-10-4

[WAG.1524653]

Total: 53; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 14, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Momordica friesiorum (Harms) C.Jeffrey —

Introduced

Calpidosicyos friesiorum Harms

Eijnatten, CLM van 1496; 1966-5-10 [WAG.1524725]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Momordica multiflora Hook.f.

[DNS.M:H. Schaefer 06/14]

Total: 7; Edo 3, Oyo 1.

Momordica multiflora var. *multiflora*

Eijnatten, CLM van 1054; 1966-1-15 [WAG.1524795]

Total: 1.

Peponium vogelii (Hook.f.) Engl.

Peponia vogelii Hook.f.

Barter 2169; -- [100261000]1257612406

Total: 13; Lagos 3, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Raphidiocystis jeffreyana R.Fern. & A.Fern.

Meer, PPC van 1749; 1971-5-22 [WAG.1760429]
Total: 1; Benue 1.

Raphidiocystis mannii Hook.f.
Gbile, ZO FHI 20888; 1969-5-8 [WAG.1760393]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Ogun 1.

Raphidiocystis phyllocalyx C.Jeffrey &
Keraudren
Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63249; 1970-3-31
[WAG.1760411]
Total: 6; Borno 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Ruthalicia eglandulosa (Hook.f.) C.Jeffrey
Adenopus eglandulosus Hook.f.
Lowe, J 4542; 1984-5-20 [WAG.1761273]
Total: 14; Edo 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 1.

Ruthalicia longipes (Hook.f.) C.Jeffrey
Phytedra longipes Hook.f.
Binuyo A.41434; 1959-8-6 [BR0000013151089]
Total: 19; Abia 2, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1,
Edo 9, Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Siraitia africana (C.Jeffrey) A.M.Lu & Zhi
Y.Zhang
Thladiantha africana C.Jeffrey
Binuyo, A FHI 41246; 1959-4-16 [WAG.1760223]
Total: 8; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 1,
Cross River 2, Niger 2.

Telfairia occidentalis Hook.f.
Irving, E.G. 69; -- [K000975595]
Total: 35; Abia 2, Anambra 2, Cross River 4, Edo 1,
Enugu 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 6, Sokoto 1.

Trichosanthes cucumerina L. — Introduced
39580; 1957-6-20 [18810]912014725
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Trochomeria macrocarpa (Sond.) Harv.
Zehneria macrocarpa Sond.
Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 366; 1978-5-8
[WAG.1760197]
Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Benue 4, Edo 1, Nasarawa 2,
Niger 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Trochomeria macrocarpa subsp.
macrocarpa
Zehneria macrocarpa Sond.
Dent Young J. sn; 1922 [K]
Total: 1.

Zehneria anomala C.Jeffrey
Gillet 1189; 1958-09-07 [K004349809]
Total: 1.

Zehneria capillacea (Schumach.) C.Jeffrey

Bryonia capillacea Schumach.
Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 850; 1971-11-4
[WAG.1760164]
Total: 20; Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo
7.

Zehneria gillettii (De Wild.) C.Jeffrey
Melothria gillettii De Wild.
Baker J.M. 69; 26-01-1983 [K]
Total: 3; Rivers 1.

Zehneria hallii C.Jeffrey
Bryonia deltoidea Schumach.
Geerling, C 3416; 1971-1-16 [WAG.1760071]
Total: 11; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 8.

Zehneria keayana R.Fern. & A.Fern.
Keay, R.W.J. FHI37145; 1957-8-19 [K000040007]
Total: 11; Edo 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Zehneria scabra (L.f.) Sond.
Bryonia scabra L.f.
Latilo; Jonathan; FHI21018; 1947-10-10
[K004349729]
Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Zehneria thwaitesii (Schweinf.) C.Jeffrey —
Introduced
Melothria thwaitesii Schweinf.
Gledhill, D 790; 1968-1-1 [WAG.1760755]
Total: 17; Kaduna 10, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo
2.

Zehneria tridactyla (Hook.f.) R.Fern. &
A.Fern.
Melothria tridactyla Hook.f.
Gledhill, D 790; 1968-1-1 [WAG.1760755]
Total: 1.

BEGONIACEAE

Begonia ciliobracteata Warb.
Richards P.W. 5177; 14-03-1955 [K]
Total: 7; Abia 2, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Osun 1.

Begonia cucullata Willd. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1725; 1956-7-7 [WAG.1572969]
Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Begonia eminii Warb.
Chapman, J.D. 2948 [K004754783]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Begonia fusialata Warb.
Jones, A.P.D.; 16938.0 [K]
Total: 2.

Begonia fusialata var. *fusialata*

Barter 2037; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 1.

Begonia heracleifolia Schlttdl. & Cham. —

Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 57968; 1966-1-11

[WAG.1162360]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Begonia hirsutula Hook.f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Begonia kisuluana Büttner

Jones A.P.D. FHI5835; 16-05-1946 [K]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Begonia longipetiolata Gilg

Meer, PPC van 1168; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1163217]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Begonia macrocarpa Warb.

Meer, PPC van 1350; 1971-4-19 [WAG0102976]

Total: 10; Cross River 4, Edo 1, Taraba 2.

Begonia mannii Hook.f.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 353; 1977-10-13

[WAG.1163465]

Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 6, Edo 7, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Plateau 1.

Begonia oxyanthera Warb.

Chapman, JD 2775; 1972-4-28 [WAG.1163740]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Begonia oxyloba Welw. ex Hook.f.

Wit, P 887; 1971-11-8 [WAG.1163820]

Total: 11; Niger 3, Ondo 3, Osun 5.

Begonia poculifera Hook.f.

Meer, PPC van 1846; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1163974]

Total: 10; Borno 1, Cross River 4, Kogi 1, Plateau 3.

Begonia polygonoides Hook.f.

Thomson, Charles Wyville 74; 1862-- [E00217702]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Begonia preussii Warb.

Meer, PPC van 1594; 1971-5-12 [WAG.1572857]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Begonia quadrialata Warb.

John D.; 1980-9-10 [1104] [3460374387]

Total: 23; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 8, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Osun 4, Rivers 1.

Begonia quadrialata subsp. *quadrialata*

Onochie, CFA FHI 33182; 1953-5-16

[WAG.1164317]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Begonia quadrialata var. *pilosa* Sosef

Killink H.J. 286; 31-12-1965 [K]

Total: 2; Enugu 1.

Begonia rostrata Welw. ex Hook.f.

Meikle, R.D. 1587; 1949-12-16 [K000211544]

Total: 16; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4.

Begonia rubromarginata Gilg

Literature

Total: 0.

Begonia salisburyana Irmsch. — Endemic

Paul Westmacott Richards 8432; 1947-7-8

[BM000902613]

Total: 13; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Lagos 1.

Begonia scapigera Hook.f.

Wit, P; Wit, J 1123; 1972-1-23 [WAG.1164432]

Total: 3; Osun 3.

Begonia scapigera subsp. *scapigera*

Gledhill, D 880; 1968-3-16 [WAG.1164431]

Total: 2; Osun 2.

Begonia schaeferi Engl.

Daramola B.O. 40536; -- [BR0000014161995]

Total: 1.

Begonia squamulosa Hook.f.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI34803; 11-03-1955 [K]

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Begonia staudtii Gilg

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67697; 1973-2-26

[WAG.1164818]

Total: 11; Borno 1, Cross River 9.

Begonia ulmifolia Willd. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van s.n.; 1966-1-1 [WAG.1572978]

Total: 3.

ELAEOCARPACEAE

Elaeocarpus blepharoceras Schltr. —

Introduced

Takeuchi, W.; Kulang, J.; 1996-11- [P05577183]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

CELASTRACEAE

Apodostigma pallens (Planch. ex Oliv.)

R. Wilczek

Hippocratea pallens Planch. ex Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1734; 1971-5-20 [WAG.1446645]

Total: 49; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 5, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 8, Plateau 7.

Apodostigma pallens var. *buchholzii* (Loes.)

N. Hallé

Hippocratea buchholzii Loes.

Meer, PPC van 981; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1446678]

Total: 6; Cross River 3, Edo 1, Oyo 2.

Apodostigma pallens var. *pallens*

Hippocratea pallens Planch. ex Oliv.

Chapman, JD 2705; 1972-3-1 [WAG.1331686]

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Bequaertia mucronata (Exell) R. Wilczek

Hippocratea mucronata Exell

Ohaeri A.O. 385; 24-02-1971 [ABUH]

Total: 2; Nasarawa 1.

Campylostemon angolensis Welw. ex Oliv.

Keay R.W.J.; 1948-4-24 [22820]1990427878

Total: 1.

Campylostemon laurentii De Wild.

Kennedy, L.D. 858; -- [K000036146]

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Ondo 1.

Campylostemon warneckeanus Loes. ex

Fritsch

Eijnatten, CLM van 1518; 1966-5-17 [WAG.1446837]

Total: 3; Oyo 2.

Cuervea macrophylla (Vahl) R. Wilczek

Hippocratea macrophylla Vahl

Clayton D. 834; 1957-2- [39536]1990429385

Total: 13; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Edo 3, Ondo 2.

Elaeodendron buchananii (Loes.) Loes.

Cassine buchananii Loes.

Chapman, JD 2705; 1972-3-1 [WAG.1331686]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Elaeodendron croceum (Thunb.) DC. —

Introduced

Ilex crocea Thunb.

Jones A.P.D.; Keay R.W.J.; Onochie C.F.A.; 1945-11- [4925]1990426412

Total: 1.

Gymnosporia buchananii Loes.

Chapman, JD 2705; 1972-3-1 [WAG.1331686]

Total: 43; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Cross River 3, Enugu 2, Kaduna 7, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 8, Taraba 8.

Gymnosporia intermedia Chiov.

Literature

Total: 0.

Gymnosporia senegalensis (Lam.) Loes.

Celastrus senegalensis Lam.

Hepper F.N. [BR0000016057647]

Total: 124; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 8, Benue 2, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 5, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 14, Ogun 9, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 17, Plateau 15, Rivers 1, Taraba 7, Zamfara 5.

Gymnosporia senegalensis subsp.

senegalensis

Celastrus senegalensis Lam.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70691; 1973-3-2

[WAG.1332124]

Total: 1.

Helictonema velutinum (Afzel.) R. Wilczek

Hippocratea velutina Afzel.

Meer, PPC van 859; 1968-7-30 [WAG.1389369]

Total: 35; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Gombe 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Osun 1, Oyo 17.

Hippocratea myriantha Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 731; 1968-4-26 [WAG.1389564]

Total: 38; Cross River 6, Delta 3, Edo 13, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 2.

Hippocratea vignei Hoyle

Meer, PPC van 796; 1968-5-17 [WAG.1389579]

Total: 5; Benue 1, Ondo 4.

Loeseneriella africana (Willd.) R. Wilczek

Tonsella africana Willd.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1948-01-31 [FHI.41665.0]

Total: 19; Bauchi 5, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Loeseneriella africana var. *africana*

Tonsella africana Willd.

Geerling, C 3428; 1971-1-21 [WAG.1389714]

Total: 1.

Loeseneriella africana var. *richardiana*

(Cambess.) N. Hallé ex R. Wilczek —

Introduced

Hippocratea richardiana Cambess.

Leeuw, PN de s.n. F; 1961-3-8 [WAG.1389731]

Total: 1.

Loeseneriella africana var. *togoensis* (Loes.)
N.Hallé

Hippocratea cymosa var. togoensis Loes.

Literature

Total: 0.

Loeseneriella apiculata (Welw. ex Oliv.)

R.Wilczek

Hippocratea apiculata Welw. ex Oliv.

Latilo M.G. FHI56866; 26-06-1965 [K]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1.

Loeseneriella apocynoides (Welw. ex Oliv.)

N.Hallé ex J.Raynal

Hippocratea apocynoides Welw. ex Oliv.

Van Meer 1746; 1971-5-22 [46701]1990429962

Total: 15; Cross River 4, Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Taraba 2.

Loeseneriella apocynoides var. *apocynoides*

— Introduced

Hippocratea apocynoides Welw. ex Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1778; 1971-5-23 [WAG.1389929]

Total: 3; Cross River 2, Taraba 1.

Loeseneriella apocynoides var. *guineensis*

(Hutch. & M.B.Moss) N.Hallé

Hippocratea guineensis Hutch. & M.B.Moss

Keay R.W.J FHI20119; 20-10-1947 [K]

Total: 8; Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1.

Loeseneriella clematoides (Loes.)

R.Wilczek

Hippocratea clematoides Loes.

Meer, PPC van 696; 1968-4-10 [WAG.1331346]

Total: 22; Edo 9, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 6.

Loeseneriella ectyopetala N.Hallé

Onochie, C.F.A.; 8948; 1948-01-31 [K005498113]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Loeseneriella iotricha (Loes. ex Fritsch)

N.Hallé

Hippocratea iotricha Loes. ex Fritsch

J. D. Kennedy [US 1741391]

Total: 16; Cross River 3, Edo 6, Enugu 1, Ondo 1.

Loeseneriella iotricha var. *iotricha*

Hippocratea iotricha Loes. ex Fritsch

J. D. Kennedy 1622; -- [US 1741391]

Total: 1.

Loeseneriella rowlandii (Loes.) N.Hallé

Hippocratea rowlandii Loes.

Gentry, AH 32735; 1981-6-16 [WAG.1331476]

Total: 34; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 7, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 9.

Maytenus undata (Thunb.) Blakelock

Celastrus undatus Thunb.

Latilo, MG FHI 47439; 1963-4-16 [WAG.1332310]

Total: 7; Kaduna 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Mystroxydon aethiopicum (Thunb.) Loes.

Cassine aethiopica Thunb.

Daramola, BO; Gbile, ZO FHI 63238; 1970-3-30 [WAG.1543800]

Total: 9; Adamawa 2, Cross River 1, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Pristimera andongensis (Welw. ex Oliv.)

N.Halle

Hippocratea andongensis Welw. ex Oliv.

Wild, H.; Goldsmith, B.; Muller, T. 6611; 1964-12-13 [K005497652]

Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Pristimera paniculata (Vahl) N.Hallé

Hippocratea paniculata Vahl

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 346; 1983-5-17 [WAG.1544002]

Total: 10; Edo 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 3.

Pristimera plumbea (Blakelock &

R.Wilczek) N.Halle

Hippocratea plumbea Blakelock & R.Wilczek

Wit, P.; Daramola, B.O. 1045; 1971-12-21 [K005497557]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Reissantia indica (Willd.) N.Hallé

Hippocratea indica Willd.

Wit, P 2248; 1972-7-6 [WAG.1544201]

Total: 59; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Niger 3, Ogun 8, Osun 4, Oyo 27, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Reissantia indica var. *astericantha* (N.Hallé)

N.Hallé

Reissantia astericantha N.Hallé

Wit, P 2248; 1972-7-6 [WAG.1544201]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Reissantia indica var. *loesneriana* (Hutch. & M.B.Moss) N.Hallé ex R.Wilczek

Hippocratea loesneriana Hutch. & M.B.Moss

Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwuno, PO FHI 68168; 1973-11-20 [WAG.1544270]

Total: 5; Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Reissantia indica var. *orientalis* N.Hallé &

B.Mathew — Introduced

MA. 140; 1983-7-21 [100665]1990433637

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Salacia alata De Wild.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A.; 1946-05-24
[FHI.18901.0]

Total: 23; Abia 1, Benue 1, Cross River 12, Delta 1,
Edo 4, Imo 2.

Salacia alata var. *alata*

Van Meer P.P. 1298; 1971-4-15 [33762]

Total: 1.

Salacia alata var. *superba* N.Hallé —

Introduced

Meer, PPC van 1298; 1971-4-15 [WAG.1544372]

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Salacia caillei A.Chev. ex Hutch. &

M.B.Moss

Emwiogbon J.A.; 1972-4-11 [46772]

Total: 5; Cross River 4, Enugu 1.

Salacia cerasifera Welw. ex Oliv.

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Salacia cerasifera var. *cerasifera*

Meer, PPC van 1744; 1971-5-22 [WAG.1544429]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Salacia chlorantha Oliv.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 567; 1978-5-30

[WAG.1544435]

Total: 20; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 2,
Ondo 6.

Salacia cornifolia Hook.f.

Mann, G.; 1859-- [4163]1231097678

Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Lagos 1.

Salacia debilis (G.Don) Walp.

Calypso debilis G.Don

Gentry 32724; 1981-6-16 [164975]1258887010

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Salacia dusenii Loes.

Ndoma 800; 1995-11-20 [1052219]1258258677

Total: 5; Benue 1, Cross River 4.

Salacia elegans Welw. ex Oliv.

Literature

Total: 0.

Salacia elegans var. *elegans*

Literature

Total: 0.

Salacia erecta (G.Don) Walp.

Calypso erecta G.Don

Savory H.J.; Keay R.W.J.; 1948-12-28 [FHI.25178.0]

Total: 8; Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Salacia erecta var. *erecta*

Calypso erecta G.Don

Van Meer P.P. 1744; 1971-5-22 [46699]1990429967

Total: 1.

Salacia hispida Blakelock

Brenan, Prof. J.P.M. 8916; 1948-1-28 [K000036164]

Total: 12; Edo 10.

Salacia howesii Hutch. & M.B.Moss

Onochie, CFA FHI 40283; 1958-10-11

[WAG.1544943]

Total: 13; Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 5, Osun 1.

Salacia lateritia N.Hallé

Onochie C.F.A. FHI31892; 17/12/ [K]

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Salacia laurentii De Wild.

J. D. Kennedy 858; [1228596900]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Salacia lehmbachii Loes.

Ariwaodo J.O. 220; 1977-1-28 [89022]1990432772

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Edo 1.

Salacia lehmbachii var. *aurantiaca*

(N.Hallé) N.Hallé

Daramola B.O FHI32799A; 03-02-1961 [K]

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Salacia lehmbachii var. *leonensis* (Hutch. &

M.B.Moss) N.Hallé

Binuyo, A FHI 41235; 1959-4-14 [WAG.1445078]

Total: 8; Cross River 7, Oyo 1.

Salacia lehmbachii var. *pes-ranulae* N.Hallé

Meer, PPC van 1453; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1256437]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Salacia lenticellosa Loes. ex Harms

Meer, PPC van 1419; 1971-4-22 [WAG.1256440]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Salacia letouzeyana N.Hallé

Meer, PPC van 1538; 1971-5-8 [WAG.1256480]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Salacia loloensis Loes.

Meer, PPC van 783; 1968-5-15 [WAG.1256503]

Total: 22; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 12, Ogun 1,
Ondo 5.

Salacia loloensis var. *loloensis*

Meer, PPC van 1488; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1256541]

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Salacia loloensis var. *sibangana* N.Hallé
Meer, PPC van 1455; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1256549]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Salacia longipes (Oliv.) N.Hallé
Hippocratea longipes Oliv.
Meer, PPC van 1527; 1971-5-8 [WAG.1256613]
Total: 23; Cross River 12, Enugu 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 4,
Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Salacia longipes var. *camerunensis* (Loes.)
N.Hallé
Salacia camerunensis Loes.
Meer, PPC van 1131; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1256607]
Total: 11; Cross River 4, Enugu 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 3.

Salacia lucida Oliv.
Thomson W.C. 102; -- [BR0000015515728]
Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Salacia mannii Oliv.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1383; 1966-4-16 [WAG.1256749]
Total: 18; Abia 1, Edo 13, Oyo 3.

Salacia nigra Cheek
Daramola 72333; 1973-10-5 [969952]1261896990
Total: 4; Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Salacia nitida (Benth.) N.E.Br.
Gymnema nitidum Benth.
Mann, G. 2275; -- [K000036173]
Total: 14; Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Imo 1,
Ondo 1.

Salacia nitida var. *nitida*
Gymnema nitidum Benth.
Onochie C.F.A. FHI35992; 14-01-1957 [K]
Total: 1.

Salacia owabiensis Hoyle
Keay R.W.J.; Meikle R.D. FHI25661; 18-02-1950 [K]
Total: 5; Borno 1, Oyo 3.

Salacia pallescens Oliv.
Odewo, TK; Adedeji 275; 1983-5-13 [WAG.1257174]
Total: 75; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 4,
Bayelsa 2, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 4,
Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 1,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 8, Ondo 15, Osun 2, Oyo
13, Plateau 1.

Salacia pynaertii De Wild.
Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A.; 1912 [K]
Total: 1.

Salacia pyriformioides Loes.
Talbot, P.A. (Mr.); Talbot, P.A. (Mrs.); 1420; 1911-
01-01 [K005697715]

Total: 5; Cross River 1.

Salacia pyriformis (Sabine) Paxton
Tonsella pyriformis Sabine
Talbot P.A. 1687; 1912-- [BM000838698]
Total: 21; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Kwara 2, Ondo 1,
Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 2.

Salacia senegalensis (Lam.) DC.
Hippocratea senegalensis Lam.
Daramola B.O.; Osanyinlusi. 147; 1979-5-1
[90256]1990432902
Total: 24; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 2,
Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Ondo 7, Oyo 2,
Plateau 1.

Salacia staudtiana Loes.
Binuyo A. [BR0000015524454]
Total: 19; Cross River 11, Kwara 2, Oyo 2.

Salacia staudtiana var. *staudtiana*
Binuyo A. 41235; -- [BR0000015524454]
Total: 1.

Salacia staudtiana var. *tshopoensis* (De
Wild.) N.Hallé
Ochie C.F.A. FHI36185X; 29-01-1957 [K]
Total: 2.

Salacia talbotii Baker f.
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70554; 1973-3-9
[WAG.1445167]
Total: 7; Cross River 7.

Salacia togoica Loes.
Wit, P 1070; 1971-12-23 [WAG.1445190]
Total: 31; Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Enugu 2,
Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Ogun 8, Osun 5, Oyo 4, Taraba
1.

Salacia tuberculata Blakelock
Literature
Total: 0.

Salacia tuberculata var. *tuberculata*
Literature
Total: 0.

Salacia volubilis Loes. & H.J.P.Winkl.
Latilo M.G. 86; 04-02-1981 [K]
Total: 1.

Salacia whytei Loes.
Ntui 717; 1995-10-31 [1036299]1258241239
Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 4.

Salacia whytei var. *vermoeseniana*
(R.Wilczek) N.Hallé
Anwodo and Opara; Tuley P. 720; 20-08-1964 [K]

Total: 7; Edo 4.

Salacia zenkeri Loes.

Gentry 32874; 1981-6-20 [163628]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Salacighia letestuana (Pellegr.) Blakelock

Salacia letestuana Pellegr.

Meer, PPC van 1143; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1445647]

Total: 15; Abia 2, Cross River 8, Edo 3, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Simicratea welwitschii (Oliv.) N.Hallé

Hippocratea welwitschii Oliv.

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO 27; 1980-2-26 [WAG.1445717]

Total: 44; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 6, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 11.

LEPIDOBOTRYACEAE

Lepidobotrys staudtii Engl.

Ainslie, J.R.; FHI2827; 1933-01-01 [K005158626]

Total: 3; Edo 1, Kano 1.

CONNARACEAE

Agelaea paradoxa Gilg

J. D. Kennedy [US 1526081]

Total: 21; Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Agelaea paradoxa var. *microcarpa* Jongkind

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32769; 1981-6-16 [WAG.1498387]

Total: 2; Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Agelaea paradoxa var. *paradoxa*

J. D. Kennedy 1592; -- [US 1526081]

Total: 1.

Agelaea pentagyna (Lam.) Baill.

Connarus pentagynus Lam.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 16; 1979-4-11 [WAG.1440264]

Total: 128; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 16, Ebonyi 3, Edo 6, Ekiti 3, Enugu 4, Imo 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Niger 2, Ogun 12, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 14, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Agelaea poggeana Gilg

Okafor, J.C.; Latilo, M.G. FHI56019 [K004820070]

Total: 2; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1.

Agelaea rubiginosa Gilg

Schmitt 262; 1994-12-15 [976651]1261904360

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Cnestis corniculata Lam.

Wit, P 161; 1971-9-11 [WAG.1440904]

Total: 92; Abia 1, Cross River 18, Edo 4, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 32, Taraba 3.

Cnestis ferruginea Vahl ex DC.

Wit, P 1034; 1971-12-8 [WAG0028896]

Total: 191; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 6, Benue 1, Cross River 26, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 13, Enugu 4, Gombe 1, Imo 4, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Ogun 11, Ondo 10, Osun 10, Oyo 34, Plateau 2, Rivers 4, Taraba 4.

Cnestis macrantha Baill.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70569; 1973-3-11 [WAG.1382516]

Total: 14; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 7.

Cnestis macrophylla Gilg ex G.Schellenb.

Gentry, AH 32759; 1981-6-17 [WAG.1382526]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Cnestis mannii (Baker) G.Schellenb.

Connarus mannii Baker

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 245; 1983-5-13 [WAG.1382560]

Total: 25; Abia 2, Cross River 5, Edo 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 10, Osun 2.

Connarus africanus Lam.

Dalziel J.M. S.N.; -- [BR0000014908828]

Total: 16; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 2, Kogi 4, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Connarus congolanus G.Schellenb.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI34828; -- [BR0000014908941]

Total: 4; Cross River 2.

Connarus griffonianus Baill.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 414; 1977-10-18 [WAG.1382923]

Total: 48; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 13, Edo 9, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Taraba 3.

Connarus longestipitatus Gilg

Meer, PPC van 1822; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1382941]

Total: 1.

Connarus staudtii Gilg

Ariwaodo 876; 1965-12-16 [58005]

Total: 2.

Connarus thonningii (DC.) G.Schellenb.

Omphalobium thonningii DC.

Geerling C.; Bokdam leg J. 427; 1967-3-8
[81649]2013043375
Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Hemadradenia chevalieri Stapf
Onochie C.F.A. 9160; 1948-2-27 [21827]
Total: 6; Benue 1, Edo 4, Ondo 1.

Hemadradenia mannii Stapf
Brenan J.P.M. 8561; -- [BR0000013813239]
Total: 13; Cross River 1, Edo 7, Kaduna 2.

Jollydora duparquetiana (Baill.) Pierre
Connarus duparquetianus Baill.
Meer, PPC van 1144; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1383327]
Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 6, Kaduna 1.

Jollydora glandulosa G.Schellenb.
Latilo M.G.; 1952-5-2 [30923]2013044587
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Manotes expansa Sol. ex Planch.
Daramola B.O.; 1993-9-27 [105146]2013044368
Total: 38; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 9, Edo 3,
Enugu 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 1,
Rivers 2.

Manotes griffoniana Baill.
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70551; 1973-3-9
[WAG.1441253]
Total: 43; Akwa Ibom 5, Benue 1, Cross River 21,
Delta 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 8.

Rourea coccinea (Schumach. & Thonn.)
Benth.
Byrsocarpus coccineus Schumach. & Thonn.
Ariwaodo, JO 285; 1977-2-22 [WAG.1441452]
Total: 141; Abia 1, Cross River 8, Edo 3, Ekiti 1,
Enugu 9, Gombe 1, Kaduna 9, Kebbi 1, Kogi 10,
Lagos 12, Nasarawa 1, Niger 10, Ogun 10, Ondo 2,
Osun 3, Oyo 23, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba
6.

Rourea coccinea subsp. *coccinea*
Byrsocarpus coccineus Schumach. & Thonn.
Odewo, TK; Adedeji 359; 1983-5-18 [WAG.1441598]
Total: 40; Enugu 4, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 2,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 12,
Plateau 1.

Rourea coccinea var. *viridis* (Gilg) Jongkind
Rourea viridis Gilg
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 303; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1441771]
Total: 23; Cross River 6, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Oyo
1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Rourea minor (Gaertn.) Alston

Aegiceras minus Gaertn.
Olorunfemi, J.; 1964-12-19 [P05612632]
Total: 51; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 2, Kaduna 14,
Katsina 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 3, Plateau 14, Taraba 3.

Rourea myriantha Baill.
Talbot P.A. 1404; 1911-- [BM000843675]
Total: 4; Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Rourea obliquifoliolata Gilg
Schmitt 65; 1994-4-11 [976573]1261904259
Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 4, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Oyo
1.

Rourea parviflora Gilg
Okafor, JC; Latilo, MG FHI 56020; 1966-1-24
[WAG.1442230]
Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 2.

Rourea solanderi Baker
Meer, PPC van 730; 1968-4-26 [WAG.1442459]
Total: 61; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3,
Anambra 1, Benue 2, Cross River 7, Delta 2, Edo 14,
Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo
1, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Rourea thomsonii (Baker) Jongkind
Connarus thomsonii Baker
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11312; 1977-3-31
[WAG.1541454]
Total: 68; Abia 2, Benue 1, Cross River 15, Delta 7,
Edo 5, Ekiti 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 4,
Ondo 4, Osun 5, Oyo 10, Plateau 1.

OXALIDACEAE

Averrhoa bilimbi L. — Introduced
Usang felix; 2005-10-12 [152]3913474569
Total: 2; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Averrhoa carambola L. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1157; 1966-1-10 [WAG.1141690]
Total: 12; Ekiti 1, Kano 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 6.

Biophytum abyssinicum Steud. ex A.Rich.
Lawlor, D.W.; Hall, J.B.; 290; 1962-08-13
[K005372278]
Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Biophytum talbotii (Baker f.) Hutch. &
Dalziel
Oxalis talbotii Baker f.
Ariwaodo, JO 663; 1977-5-10 [WAG.1141794]
Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Kogi 2.

Biophytum umbraculum Welw.

Daramola, BO 222; 1977-8-26 [WAG.1141875]
Total: 46; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Enugu 3, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Biophytum zenkeri Guillaumin

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST s.n.; 1973-2-26 [WAG.1141934]
Total: 13; Abia 4, Cross River 6, Kogi 1, Osun 1.

Oxalis corniculata L. — Introduced

Chapman, JD 3065; 1973-4-20 [WAG.1142114]
Total: 23; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 4, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Oxalis debilis Kunth — Introduced

Daramola B.O. 40575; 1950-1-7 [BR0000017648035]
Total: 8; Borno 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1.

Oxalis latifolia Kunth — Introduced

Literature
Total: 0.

Oxalis natans Thunb. — Introduced

B.O.Daramola; 2010-6-1 [1837]3808439319
Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Oxalis procumbens Steud. ex A.Rich.

Literature
Total: 0.

Oxalis procumbens subsp. *bathieana*

Lourteig
Literature
Total: 0.

PANDACEAE

Microdesmis keayana J.Léonard

Pilz, GE 2360; 1980-5-5 [WAG.1144650]
Total: 107; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 5, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Cross River 12, Edo 7, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 11, Niger 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 24, Plateau 1.

Microdesmis puberula Hook.f. ex Planch.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 361; 1977-10-13 [WAG.1145099]
Total: 298; Abia 9, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 9, Benue 4, Cross River 76, Delta 4, Edo 64, Ekiti 5, Enugu 3, Kaduna 3, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 19, Niger 1, Ogun 18, Ondo 10, Osun 14, Oyo 36, Rivers 2, Taraba 4.

Panda oleosa Pierre

Kennedy J.D. 1669; -- [BR0000013566067]

Total: 30; Benue 2, Cross River 1, Edo 15, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2.

RHIZOPHORACEAE

Anopyxis klaineana (Pierre) Engl.

Macarisia klaineana Pierre
Kennedy J.D. 352; -- [BR0000017684903]
Total: 17; Cross River 1, Edo 10.

Cassipourea afzelii (Oliv.) Alston

Weihea afzelii Oliv.
Sharland, R.E. 2036; 1981-7-20 [K000043540]
Total: 2; Cross River 1, Ogun 1.

Cassipourea barteri (Hook.f. ex Oliv.) N.E.Br.

Dactylopetalum barteri Hook.f. ex Oliv.
Kennedy J.D. 2060; 1931-- [BR0000017800914]
Total: 43; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 12, Enugu 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 2.

Cassipourea celastroides Alston — Introduced

Dalziel J.M. S.N.; 1912-- [BR0000017801348]
Total: 1.

Cassipourea congoensis R.Br. ex DC.

Kamphorst, A 171; 1960-4-1 [WAG.1193671]
Total: 54; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 8, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 8, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Cassipourea eketensis Baker f. — Endemic

Talbot P.A. 3213; 1912-- [BR0000006272739]
Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1.

Cassipourea gummiflua Tul.

Talbot P.A. 1757; -- [K000350132]
Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Taraba 2.

Rhizophora mangle L.

Freylink s.n.; 1959-1-1 [L.2495835]
Total: 35; Delta 8, Lagos 7, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Rivers 17.

Rhizophora racemosa G.Mey.

Hunder, FD 140; 1962-8-15 [WAG.1560703]
Total: 87; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 10, Borno 1, Cross River 9, Delta 6, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 32, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Rivers 9.

Rhizophora × *harrisonii* Leechm.

Coombe D.E. 158; 1955-2-26 [BR0000017070874]

Total: 1.

ERYTHROXYLACEAE

Erythroxylum coca Lam. — Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 57961; 1966-2-11
[WAG.1930896]

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Erythroxylum emarginatum Thonn.

Daramola, BO FHI 62744; 1969-5-20
[WAG.1930720]

Total: 27; Adamawa 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

EUPHORBIACEAE

Acalypha brachystachya Hornem.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1989; 1966-12-7 [WAG.1578734]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Acalypha ceraceopunctata Pax

Jackson J.A.D. 428; 1966-5-24 [58645]
Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kano 2, Sokoto 1.

Acalypha ciliata Forssk.

Isawumi & Elufisan1779; 1995-10-6 [S20-6057]
[2618548466]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Osun 2, Oyo 5.

Acalypha crenata Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Dr. A. B. Kadiri; Oladipo Vivian; 2010-3-20 [2670]
[3808443311]

Total: 28; Imo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 10, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Acalypha fimbriata Schumach. & Thonn.

Geerling, C 4037 A; 1971-8-19 [WAG.1930080]
Total: 63; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Kebbi 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 11, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 21, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1.

Acalypha hispida Burm.f. — Introduced

DR. A. B. KADIRI; OGHARANKA KEVIN; 2010-2-27 [2715] [3808443235]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 5, Oyo 2.

Acalypha indica L. — Introduced

T.A. Olugbade; 1992-- [V-031648]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Osun 1.

Acalypha manniana Müll.Arg.

Eimunjese, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66381; 1973-5-16
[WAG.1931594]

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Acalypha neptunica Müll.Arg.

Literature

Total: 0.

Acalypha neptunica var. *neptunica*

Literature

Total: 0.

Acalypha neptunica var. *pubescens* (Pax)

Hutch.

Literature

Total: 0.

Acalypha ornata Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 437; 1978-5-16
[WAG.1196325]

Total: 71; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 6, Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Ekiti 5, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Niger 8, Ogun 14, Ondo 8, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 3.

Acalypha paniculata Miq.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1671; 1966-7-3 [WAG.1196521]

Total: 24; Cross River 3, Delta 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Acalypha petiolaris Hochst.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1875; 1972-5-8
[WAG.1196608]

Total: 1.

Acalypha segetalis Müll.Arg.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1954; 1972-5-10
[WAG.1578479]

Total: 36; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Acalypha wilkesiana Müll.Arg. —

Introduced

Wit, P 529; 1971-10-3 [WAG.1578732]

Total: 55; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 14, Ogun 12, Osun 1, Oyo 13.

Alchornea cordifolia (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Müll.Arg.

Schousboea cordifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Pilz, GE 1900; 1976-12-29 [WAG.1197063]

Total: 180; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 7, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 12, Ebonyi 2, Edo 8, Enugu 8,

Imo 2, Kaduna 4, Kwara 6, Lagos 20, Niger 8, Ogun 12, Ondo 9, Osun 10, Oyo 23, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 9.

Alchornea floribunda Müll.Arg.

Latilo, MG FHI 67778; 1973-3-3 [WAG.1197393]

Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 16, Edo 10.

Alchornea hirtella Benth.

Literature

Total: 0.

Alchornea hirtella f. *comoensis* (Beille) Pax & K.Hoffm.

Literature

Total: 0.

Alchornea hirtella f. *glabrata* (Müll.Arg.) Pax & K.Hoffm.

Literature

Total: 0.

Alchornea hirtella f. *hirtella*

Literature

Total: 0.

Alchornea laxiflora (Benth.) Pax & K.Hoffm.

Lepidoturus laxiflorus Benth.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70670; 1973-2-28 [WAG.1931539]

Total: 80; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 3, Ondo 7, Osun 3, Oyo 29, Plateau 7, Taraba 3.

Aleurites moluccanus (L.) Willd. —

Introduced

Jatropha moluccana L.

MacGregor W.D. 366; 1928-11-22 [2463]1944987589

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Anthostema aubryanum Baill.

Meer, PPC van 1303; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1931205]

Total: 31; Cross River 4, Edo 8, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 6, Oyo 2.

Argomuelleria macrophylla Pax

Literature

Total: 0.

Astraea lobata (L.) Klotzsch — Introduced

Croton lobatus L.

Lely H.V. 429; 13-08-1921 [K]

Total: 145; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 3, Cross River 9, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 5, Gombe 4, Imo 1, Jigawa 2, Kaduna 10, Kogi 8, Kwara 5, Lagos 5, Niger 3, Ogun

18, Ondo 9, Osun 3, Oyo 17, Plateau 3, Taraba 1, Yobe 3.

Astraea surinamensis (Miq.) O.L.M.Silva & Cordeiro — Introduced

Cnidioscolus surinamensis Miq.

Literature

Total: 0.

Astraea trilobata (Forssk.) O.L.M.Silva & Cordeiro — Introduced

Croton trilobatus Forssk.

Literature

Total: 0.

Caperonia fistulosa Beille

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3715; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1796997]

Total: 4; Borno 2, Oyo 1.

Caperonia latifolia Pax

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1077; 1971-12-28

[WAG.1797013]

Total: 35; Akwa Ibom 2, Delta 1, Edo 10, Imo 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 3, Ondo 6, Osun 2, Oyo 2.

Caperonia palustris (L.) A.St.-Hil. — Introduced

Croton palustris L.

; 1995-9-28 [FR-0018602]3046045123

Total: 22; Anambra 2, Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5.

Caperonia serrata (Turcz.) C.Presl

Lepidococca serrata Turcz.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 90153; 1979-4-20

[WAG.1796933]

Total: 51; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Niger 13, Ondo 4, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Cephalocroton cordofanus Hochst.

Daramola B.O.; Okoro; Akin 5; 1982-10-29 [98978-1]

Total: 2; Adamawa 2.

Cephalocroton incanus M.G.Gilbert

Daramola B.O.; Okoro; Akin 5; 1982-10-29

[K000648293]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Gombe 1.

Chrozophora brocchiana Vis.

Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O.Z 63; 1974-11-25 [76930]

[1944997067]

Total: 15; Borno 4, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Osun 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Chrozophora plicata (Vahl) A.Juss. ex Spreng.

Croton plicatus Vahl

Moiser B; 10-11-1921 [K]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1.

Chrozophora senegalensis (Lam.) Spreng.

Croton senegalensis Lam.

Ayuba, ASM 43; 1966-3-1 [WAG.1175925]

Total: 47; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 5, Gombe 3, Kaduna 8, Kano 6, Kogi 1, Niger 3, Sokoto 3, Yobe 3.

Cleidion gabonicum Baill.

Olorunfemi, J FHI 41510; 1959-5-21 [WAG.1176021]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Osun 3.

Cnidoscolus aconitifolius (Mill.) I.M.Johnst.

— Introduced

Jatropha aconitifolia Mill.

Yakubu M. T.; 2007-8-14 [107768] [1945001695]

Total: 12; Edo 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Rivers 1.

Cnidoscolus stimulosus (Michx.) Engelm. & A.Gray — Introduced

Jatropha stimulosa Michx.

KADIRI ABDULLATEEF; 2012-6-18 [5018]

[3808439441]

Total: 7; Lagos 3, Ogun 3, Osun 1.

Codiaeum variegatum (L.) Rumph. ex

A.Juss. — Introduced

Croton variegatus L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65860; 1972-10-7

[WAG.1796369]

Total: 14; Anambra 3, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Lagos 7, Oyo 2.

Croton gratissimus Burch.

Leeuw, PN de 1563; 1965-9-8 [WAG.1797426]

Total: 100; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 6, Cross River 8, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 5, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Niger 3, Ogun 14, Ondo 4, Osun 3, Oyo 8, Plateau 10, Sokoto 4, Taraba 1.

Croton gratissimus var. *gratissimus*

P.F.O. Adamawa 48446; -- [BR0000016231986]

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 2.

Croton hirtus L'Hér. — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2012-10-12 [123A] [1990271710]

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Croton longiracemosus Hutch.

R.W.J. Keay & C.A.N. Nash 37110; --

[BR0000015830791]

Total: 7; Ogun 3, Osun 2, Plateau 1.

Croton macrostachyus Hochst. ex Delile

Chapman, JD 2785; 1972-5-4 [WAG.1798559]

Total: 28; Bauchi 1, Plateau 16, Taraba 10.

Croton membranaceus Müll.Arg.

Barter 615; -- [K000347407]

Total: 4; Anambra 1, Niger 2.

Croton nigritanus Scott Elliot

Daramola B.O.; 1958-6-11 [36941] [1944992114]

Total: 4; Anambra 1, Kogi 1.

Croton nitens Sw. — Introduced

Binuyo, A FHI 44939; 1963-1-18 [WAG.1796642]

Total: 6; Oyo 6.

Croton penduliflorus Hutch.

Stanfield, DP FHI 54345; 1964-6-15 [WAG.1797658]

Total: 14; Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 5, Oyo 3.

Croton pseudopulchellus Pax

Geerling, C 3287; 1970-10-31 [WAG.1797626]

Total: 8; Bauchi 5, Niger 1.

Croton speciosus Müll.Arg. — Introduced

Stanfield D.P.; Latilo M.G.; 1964-5-15

[45939]1944993165

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Croton sylvaticus Hochst.

Meer, PPC van 740; 1968-4-27 [WAG.1797447]

Total: 5; Benue 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Ogun 1.

Crotonogyne caterviflora N.E.Br.

Leeuwenberg A.J.M.11294; 1977-3-30 [80152]

[1944997510]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Crotonogyne manniana Müll.Arg. —

Introduced

Leeuwenberg A.J.M. 11294; -- [BR0000015819284]

Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Delta 2, Niger 1.

Crotonogyne neglecta Breteler

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11294; 1977-3-30

[WAG.1793516]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 7, Delta 2, Enugu 1.

Crotonogyne poggei Pax

Meer, PPC van 1319; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1793468]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Cross River 9, Niger 1.

Crotonogyne preussii Pax

Daramola B.O.; 1961-3-19 [43371-1] [1949704433]

Total: 12; Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ondo 4, Osun 4.

Cyrtogonone argentea (Pax) Prain

Crotonogyne argentea Pax

Ariwaodo, JO 667; 1977-5-12 [WAG.1793366]

Total: 16; Cross River 13, Kaduna 2.

Dalechampia ipomoeifolia Benth.

Vogel 9; -- [K000425736]

Total: 26; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 2, Enugu 5, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Rivers 4.

Dalechampia scandens L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Dichostemma glaucescens Pierre

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70557; 1973-3-11

[WAG.1792885]

Total: 22; Abia 1, Cross River 17, Kogi 1.

Discoclaoxylon hexandrum (Müll.Arg.) Pax & K.Hoffm.

Claoxylon hexandrum Müll.Arg.

Meer, PPC van 1864; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1792825]

Total: 51; Abia 1, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Edo 19, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Discoglyprena caloneura (Pax) Prain

Alchornea caloneura Pax

Binuyo, A FHI 41213; 1959-4-11 [WAG.1792694]

Total: 44; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Edo 14, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Erythrococca africana (Baill.) Prain

Trevisa africana Baill.

Daramola, BO FHI 62912; 1969-5-24

[WAG.1789965]

Total: 29; Adamawa 2, Cross River 2, Edo 7, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Erythrococca anomala (Juss. ex Poir.) Prain

Adelia anomala Juss. ex Poir.

Daramola, BO FHI 86423; 1978-5-23

[WAG.1789880]

Total: 49; Abia 2, Anambra 3, Cross River 10, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 10.

Erythrococca chevalieri (Beille) Prain

Claoxylon chevalieri Beille

Lowe, J 1710; 1969-3-27 [WAG.1789819]

Total: 14; Delta 1, Edo 10.

Erythrococca hispidula (Pax) Prain

Claoxylon hispidum Pax

Coombe, D.E. 144; 1955-3-3 [4348]

Total: 4; Ondo 2.

Erythrococca membranacea (Müll.Arg.)

Prain

Claoxylon membranaceum Müll.Arg.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66202; 1973-3-15

[WAG.1789780]

Total: 14; Abia 2, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Ogun 3, Taraba 1.

Erythrococca welwitschiana (Müll.Arg.)

Prain

Claoxylon welwitschianum Müll.Arg.

Talbot P.A. 663; 1911-- [BM012564993]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia бага A.Chev.

Lely, H.V.; 10594.0 [K]

Total: 3.

Euphorbia бага var. *бага*

Lely H.V. 63; 1929-1 [K]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia balsamifera Aiton — Introduced

Dalziel J.M. 320; -- [K000252777]

Total: 10; Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Euphorbia balsamifera subsp. *balsamifera*

— Introduced

Dalziel J.M. 320; -- [K000252777]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia cervicornu Baill.

Mann, G. 2315; -- [K000252774]

Total: 4; Abia 2.

Euphorbia convolvuloides Hochst. ex Benth.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 233; 1978-5-2

[WAG.1789203]

Total: 97; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 6, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 9, Cross River 3, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 6, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 6, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4, Yobe 3.

Euphorbia cristata B.Heyne ex Roth —

Introduced

Usang felix; 2015-10-8 [319]3913474466

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Euphorbia cuneata Vahl

Literature

Total: 0.

Euphorbia cuneata subsp. *cuneata*

Literature

Total: 0.

Euphorbia cyparissioides Pax

Literature

Total: 0.

Euphorbia deightonii Croizat

Onochie, C.F.A. 34245; 1954-11-21 [15750]
[912011255]

Total: 14; Edo 1, Ondo 10, Oyo 2.

Euphorbia depauperata Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Hepper F.N.; 1957-12-10 [FHI.53792.0]

Total: 12; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Taraba 7.

Euphorbia depauperata var. *depauperata*

Chapman, JD 2676; 1972-2-16 [WAG.1789698]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia desmondii Keay & Milne-Redh.

Lowe, J 1580; 1968-11-17 [WAG.1789643]

Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Edo 3, Gombe 4, Katsina 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5.

Euphorbia drupifera Thonn.

Meikle, R.D. ; -- [P00576935]

Total: 7; Ondo 4, Oyo 2.

Euphorbia forskalii J.Gay

Keay, R.; 1957-6-2 [P00570767]

Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 5, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Niger 2, Sokoto 1.

Euphorbia glaucophylla Poir.

Stubbings, H.G.; 1957-9-2 [P00576787]

Total: 21; Bayelsa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Oyo 3.

Euphorbia graminea Jacq. — Introduced

Lowe J. 5025; 16-08-1993 [K]

Total: 4; Edo 1, Oyo 2.

Euphorbia heterophylla L. — Introduced

Meikle R.D. [BR0000016391970]

Total: 68; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 25, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Euphorbia heterophylla var. *cyathophora*

(Murray) Griseb.

Gledhill, D 783; 1967-12-23 [WAG.1789121]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia heterophylla var. *heterophylla* —

Introduced

Pilz, GE 1862; 1976-11-28 [WAG.1794734]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia hirsuta L. — Introduced

EKORE MARY NGOZI; DR. A. B. KADIRI; 2010-3-12 [2650] [3808439871]

Total: 3; Edo 1, Ogun 2.

Euphorbia hirta L. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2283; 1979-4-8 [WAG.1794587]

Total: 165; Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 7, Bayelsa 1, Benue 5, Borno 3, Cross River 14, Delta 1, Edo 7, Ekiti 5, Gombe 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 7, Kwara 8, Lagos 8, Niger 5, Ogun 13, Ondo 10, Osun 3, Oyo 33, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 5.

Euphorbia hypericifolia L. — Introduced

Barter, C.; -- [P00567968]

Total: 19; Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Euphorbia hyssopifolia L. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2286; 1979-4-8 [WAG.1794455]

Total: 38; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 4, Oyo 8, Sokoto 1.

Euphorbia kamerunica Pax

Barter, C.; -- [P00575644]

Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Gombe 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 5.

Euphorbia kerstingii Pax

Ibhanesebhor G.; Adejimi 65; 1977-4-15 [89473]

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Euphorbia lateriflora Schumach.

Etkin 20; 1988-10-31 [139930]

Total: 41; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kano 9, Katsina 2, Lagos 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 7, Sokoto 2.

Euphorbia ledermanniana Pax & K.Hoffm.

Dalziel, J.M. 754; -- [K000252772]

Total: 6; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Taraba 1.

Euphorbia leucocephala Lotsy

Olorunfemi J. FHI55099; 09-11-1964 [K]

Total: 4; Plateau 1.

Euphorbia leucophylla Benth. — Introduced

Olorunfemi J.; 1964-11-9 [55099]1944994350

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Euphorbia milii Des Moul. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1352; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1794155]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 5.

Euphorbia monteiroi Hook.f. — Introduced

Ogunshile B.; 1976-5-31 [78815] [1944997398]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Euphorbia nubica N.E.Br.

McClintock A. 58; 05-12-1954 [K]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia paganorum A.Chev.

Meikle, R.D. 1049; 1950-1-17 [16751] [912012368]

Total: 4; Kaduna 2.

Euphorbia palustris L. — Introduced

O. O. OYEBANJI; 2016-3-8 [7348] [3808439807]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Euphorbia parviflora L. — Introduced

Dawodu TB; -- [44010]2428986718

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Euphorbia poissonii Pax

Wit, P; Geerling, C 3277; 1980-1-24 [WAG.1793740]

Total: 25; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 2,

Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 3.

Euphorbia polycnemoides Hochst. ex Boiss.

Hepper, F.N. ; 1957-11-9 [P00576213]

Total: 31; Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 1, Gombe 2,

Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5.

Euphorbia prostrata Aiton — Introduced

Gledhill, D 889; 1968-3-18 [WAG.1799870]

Total: 41; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2,

Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 2,

Osun 1, Oyo 11, Sokoto 1.

Euphorbia pulcherrima Willd. ex Klotzsch

— Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1138; 1966-2-21 [WAG.1799797]

Total: 7; Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba

1.

Euphorbia schimperiana Scheele

Hepper, F.N.; 1958-02-23 [P00576388]

Total: 4.

Euphorbia schimperiana var. *pubescens*

(N.E.Br.) S.Carter

Keay R.W.J. FHI28348; 07-04-1954 [K]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia schimperiana var. *schimperiana*

Hepper, F.N.; 1958-2-23 [P00576388]

Total: 1.

Euphorbia scordiifolia Jacq.

Keay, R.W.J.; 1957-7-7 [P00576520]

Total: 11; Benue 1, Borno 4, Jigawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun

1.

Euphorbia sepium N.E.Br.

Literature

Total: 0.

Euphorbia splendens Bojer ex Hook. —

Introduced

Magaji S.O. 766; 1975- [K]

Total: 2; Lagos 1.

Euphorbia sudanica A.Chev.

Literature

Total: 0.

Euphorbia thymifolia L. — Introduced

Onochie, C.F.A.; 1956-6-2 [P00576692]

Total: 33; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Edo 2, Ekiti

1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Ondo

2, Oyo 5, Plateau 1.

Euphorbia tirucalli L.

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [650A] [1990271906]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Euphorbia tithymaloides L. — Introduced

FATIMAH NIMAR ; 2013-5-27 [5762] [3808438642]

Total: 4; Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Euphorbia unispina N.E.Br.

Daramola B.O.; 1986-12- [102317] [1945001020]

Total: 2; Bauchi 2.

Euphorbia venefica Trémaux ex Kotschy —

Introduced

Euphorbia mamillaris Trémaux

Bally, P.R.O. E.313; 1947-3-28 [2616]912023073

Total: 1.

Excoecaria grahamii Stapf

Latilo, MG FHI 64772; 1972-9-18 [WAG.1799080]

Total: 8; Kwara 1, Niger 6.

Excoecaria guineensis (Benth.) Müll.Arg.

Stillingia guineensis Benth.

Latilo, MG; Daramola, BO FHI 28720; 1954-11-21

[WAG.1342283]

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Taraba 5.

Grossera macrantha Pax

Latilo M.G.; Daramola B.O. ; 1954-12-13 [28897]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Grossera vignei Hoyle

Amachi J.O.; 1958-11-27 [38294-1] [1949704122]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Taraba 2.

Gymnanthes inopinata (Prain) Esser

Sebastiania inopinata Prain

PROF AKINSOJI ; 2009-11-10 [2077] [3808440670]

Total: 1; Rivers 1.

Hamilcoa zenkeri (Pax) Prain

Plukenetia zenkeri Pax

Literature

Total: 0.

Hevea brasiliensis (Willd. ex A.Juss.)

Müll.Arg. — Introduced

Siphonia brasiliensis Willd. ex A.Juss.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P 888; 1971-11-4 [WAG.1293861]

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Delta 2, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 7.

Hura crepitans L. — Introduced

Meer, PPC van 778; 1968-5-15 [WAG.1293964]

Total: 22; Lagos 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 10.

Jatropha curcas L. — Introduced

Chapman, JD 2877; 1972-6-5 [WAG.1294480]

Total: 80; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Lagos 6, Niger 3, Ogun 11, Ondo 2, Osun 4, Oyo 28, Plateau 2, Taraba 4, Zamfara 1.

Jatropha gossypifolia L. — Introduced

Wit, P 2244; 1972-7-6 [WAG.1294530]

Total: 59; Anambra 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 13, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 22.

Jatropha integerrima Jacq. — Introduced

Usang felix; 2005-10-4 [213] [3913474619]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Jatropha macrorhiza Benth. — Introduced

; -- [44274]2428989051

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Jatropha multifida L. — Introduced

Wit, P 528; 1971-10-3 [WAG.1294638]

Total: 27; Edo 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 16, Rivers 1.

Jatropha neriifolia Müll.Arg.

Barter 1679; -- [K000347340]

Total: 8; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Jatropha podagrica Hook. — Introduced

Wit, P 549; 1971-10-6 [WAG.1294651]

Total: 14; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 1.

Klaineanthus gaboniae Pierre ex Prain

Meer, PPC van 1537; 1971-5-8 [WAG.1294769]

Total: 34; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 21, Edo 5.

Macaranga barteri Müll.Arg.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32774; 1981-6-16

[WAG.1805449]

Total: 80; Anambra 5, Cross River 11, Edo 10, Enugu 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 13, Ondo 7, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Macaranga heterophylla (Müll.Arg.)

Müll.Arg.

Mappa heterophylla Müll.Arg.

Brent, R.W. 401; 1913-01-06 [K004150988]

Total: 1.

Macaranga heudelotii Baill.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A.; 1946-4-11 [17424]

[1944989586]

Total: 5; Lagos 2, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Macaranga hurifolia Beille

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67638; 1973-2-22

[WAG.1805118]

Total: 48; Anambra 1, Cross River 17, Ebonyi 1, Edo 8, Kogi 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Macaranga monandra Müll.Arg.

Meer, PPC van 1562; 1971-5-10 [WAG.1807601]

Total: 34; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 21, Kogi 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Macaranga occidentalis (Müll.Arg.)

Müll.Arg.

Mappa occidentalis Müll.Arg.

Olorunfemi J.; OnijamowoSE 264; 1975-5-28 [76423]

[1944997210]

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Cross River 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Macaranga paxii Prain

Talbot 610; -- [K000425811]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Macaranga poggei Pax — Introduced

Usang felix; 2004-10-28 [106959] [3913474530]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Macaranga schweinfurthii Pax

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70517; 1973-3-8

[WAG.1806443]

Total: 20; Cross River 14, Taraba 4.

Macaranga spinosa Müll.Arg.

Gentry 32850; 1981-6-20 [141564]

Total: 7; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Ondo 2.

Macaranga staudtii Pax

Chapman J.D.2789; 1972-5-4 [46079] [1944993244]

Total: 8; Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ondo 2, Plateau 1.

Mallotus oppositifolius (Geiseler) Müll.Arg.

Croton oppositifolius Geiseler

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 362; 1983-5-18 [WAG.1801773]

Total: 262; Abia 10, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Benue 5, Borno 1, Cross

River 39, Delta 2, Edo 12, Ekiti 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 11, Kwara 2, Lagos 10, Niger 4, Ogun 34, Ondo 26, Osun 6, Oyo 52, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 4, Zamfara 1.

Mallotus subulatus Müll.Arg.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67641; 1973-2-22 [WAG.1802170]

Total: 103; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 1, Cross River 39, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 7, Imo 8, Kaduna 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Rivers 1.

Manihot carthagenensis (Jacq.) Müll.Arg.

— Introduced

Jatropha carthagenensis Jacq.

Pilz, GE 2195; 1977-10-30 [WAG.1802302]

Total: 22; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 5, Oyo 9, Plateau 1.

Manihot esculenta Crantz — Introduced

Jatropha manihot L.

Bels, L 90; 1950-4-23 [U.1269164]

Total: 43; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Imo 1, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 5, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Manihot glaziovii Müll.Arg. — Introduced

Pilz G.E. 1883; 10-12-1976 [K]

Total: 4; Oyo 3.

Manihot palmata Müll.Arg. — Introduced

Jatropha palmata Vell.

; -- [44378]2428989670

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Manniophyton fulvum Müll.Arg.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11313; 1977-3-31

[WAG.1352874]

Total: 90; Abia 9, Akwa Ibom 8, Anambra 9, Cross River 26, Delta 5, Edo 16, Imo 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Rivers 6.

Maprounea africana Müll.Arg.

Keay R.W.J.; 1950-06-06 [FHI.28053.0]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 3, Oyo 1.

Maprounea africana var. *africana*

Jackson J.A.D.432; 1966-6-12 [58761] [1944994900]

Total: 1.

Maprounea membranacea Pax & K.Hoffm.

Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70277; 1974-5-21 [WAG.1353031]

Total: 40; Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 3, Cross River 4, Edo 6, Enugu 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 10, Osun 1, Plateau 1.

Mareya micrantha (Benth.) Müll.Arg.

Acalypha micrantha Benth.

Binuyo, A FHI 45401; 1961-11-15 [WAG.1353256]

Total: 30; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Borno 1, Cross River 11, Edo 6, Rivers 1.

Mareyopsis longifolia (Pax) Pax &

K.Hoffm.

Mareya longifolia Pax

Meer, PPC van 1359; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1353332]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3, Edo 2.

Micrococca mercurialis (L.) Benth.

Tragia mercurialis L.

Meer PPC van Meer, PPC van 1718; 1971-5-20

[WAG.1353972]

Total: 25; Bauchi 3, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 6, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Rivers 2.

Microstachys chamaelea (L.) Müll.Arg.

Tragia chamaelea L.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 491; 1978-5-24

[WAG.1342483]

Total: 69; Adamawa 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Kogi 11, Kwara 6, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 7, Ondo 3, Oyo 11, Taraba 1.

Microstachys dalzielii (Hutch.) Esser

Sapium dalzielii Hutch.

Dalziel, J.M. 749; 1912-6-20 [K000425771]

Total: 2; Katsina 2.

Microstachys faradianensis (Beille) Esser

Excoecaria faradianensis Beille

Literature

Total: 0.

Neoboutonia mannii Benth.

Conceveiba africana Müll.Arg.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65813; 1972-6-4

[WAG.1354106]

Total: 22; Abia 1, Cross River 12, Kaduna 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Neoboutonia melleri (Müll.Arg.) Prain

Mallotus melleri Müll.Arg.

Chapman, JD 2609; 1971-11-18 [WAG.1354107]

Total: 17; Adamawa 2, Plateau 5, Taraba 10.

Plagiostyles africana (Müll.Arg.) Prain

Daphniphyllum africanum Müll.Arg.

Onyeachusim, HD; Latilo, MG FHI 54242; 1964-3-1 [WAG.1340875]

Total: 5; Abia 1, Cross River 2.

Plukenetia conophora Müll.Arg.

Latilo, MG FHI 67781; 1973-3-3 [WAG.1341037]

Total: 71; Anambra 1, Cross River 6, Ebonyi 1, Edo 8, Ekiti 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 7, Lagos 5, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 7, Oyo 10.

Pseudagrostistachys africana (Müll.Arg.) Pax & K.Hoffm.

Agrostistachys africana Müll.Arg.

Savory H.J.; Keay J.M.; 1948-12-29 [FHI.25207-1]
Total: 6; Cross River 5.

Pseudagrostistachys africana subsp. *africana*

Agrostistachys africana Müll.Arg.

Savory, H.J.; Keay, R.W.J. FHI25207; 1948-12-29 [K000044415]
Total: 1.

Pycnocomma cornuta Müll.Arg.

Barker 3385; -- [K000425650]

Total: 39; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Edo 7, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 7, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Pycnocomma macrophylla Benth.

K. Schmitt; T.O. IbiangSchmitt 337; 1995-2-7 [976691] [1261904395]

Total: 8; Cross River 4, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 1.

Ricinodendron heudelotii (Baill.) Heckel

Jatropha heudelotii Baill.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32657; 1981-6-14 [WAG.1341645]

Total: 53; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 10, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ogun 8, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Ricinodendron heudelotii subsp. *africanum* (Müll.Arg.) J.Léonard

Ricinodendron africanum Müll.Arg.

Kennedy J.D. 170; -- [BR0000013980672]
Total: 21; Abia 1, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Edo 2, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 2.

Ricinus communis L. — Introduced

Wit, P 2274; 1972-7-25 [WAG.1341885]

Total: 62; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 8, Ogun 8, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 18, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Sapium laurifolium (A.Rich.) Griseb. — Introduced

Stillingia laurifolia A.Rich.

Onochie C.F.A. ; 1953-4-28 [15543]1944989228
Total: 2; Cross River 1, Ogun 1.

Shirakiopsis elliptica (Hochst.) Esser

Sclerocroton ellipticus Hochst.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70686; 1973-3-2 [WAG.1342230]

Total: 67; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Ekiti 4, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 13, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 8, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 7, Sokoto 1, Taraba 8.

Stillingia sylvatica L. — Introduced

Massey J.; McWilliam A.; 1966-6-23 [80849]1949703554

Total: 1.

Suregada croizatiana J.Léonard —

Introduced

Thomas B. CroatCroat 53434; 1981-11-18 [2377956] [1259686089]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Suregada occidentalis (Hoyle) Croizat

Gelonium occidentale Hoyle

Charter J.R.; 1955-8-23 [38747]

Total: 31; Edo 2, Ogun 13, Ondo 9, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Tetrorchidium didymostemon (Baill.) Pax & K.Hoffm.

Hasskarlia didymostemon Baill.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32847; 1981-6-20 [WAG.1338171]

Total: 143; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 7, Benue 2, Cross River 31, Edo 22, Enugu 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 17, Ondo 11, Osun 5, Oyo 7.

Tetrorchidium oppositifolium (Pax) Pax

Hasskarlia oppositifolia Pax

Meer, PPC van 1707; 1972-5-19 [WAG.1338263]

Total: 19; Abia 1, Cross River 14, Oyo 1.

Tragia benthamii Baker

Tragia cordifolia Benth.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1649; 1966-7-18 [WAG.1338775]

Total: 48; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 5, Gombe 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 13, Taraba 1.

OCHNACEAE

Campylospermum calanthum (Gilg) Farron

Ouratea calantha Gilg

Meer, PPC van 1467; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1577392]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 6, Edo 6, Imo 1.

Campylospermum dybovskii Tiegh.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI32094; 12-05-1953 [K]

Total: 13; Akwa Ibom 1, Edo 4, Kwara 1, Niger 1.

Campylospermum elongatum (Oliv.) Tiegh.

Gomphia elongata Oliv.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65837; 1972-6-8

[WAG0032190]

Total: 18; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Campylospermum engleri (Tiegh.) ined.

Monelasmum engleri Tiegh.

Onochie C.F.A.; Jones A.P.D. FHI17354; 03-04-1946

[K]

Total: 1.

Campylospermum flavum (Schumach. & Thonn.) Farron

Gomphia flava Schumach. & Thonn.

Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwuno, PO FHI 68013; 1973-11-15

[WAG.1585031]

Total: 137; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 3, Borno 2, Cross River 11, Delta 2, Ebonyi 2, Edo 11, Ekiti 4, Enugu 2, Kaduna 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 29, Plateau 2, Taraba 11.

Campylospermum glaberrimum (P.Beauv.) Farron

Gomphia glaberrima P.Beauv.

Wit, P 1071; 1971-12-23 [WAG.1585621]

Total: 62; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Osun 4, Oyo 4, Rivers 4.

Campylospermum glaucum (Tiegh.) Farron

Exomicrum glaucum Tiegh.

Literature

Total: 0.

Campylospermum laxiflorum (De Wild. & T.Durand) Tiegh.

Ouratea laxiflora De Wild. & T.Durand

Nsimundele L. 2054; 2007-10-16

[BR0000005033041]

Total: 3; Edo 1, Lagos 1.

Campylospermum mannii (Oliv.) Tiegh.

Gomphia mannii Oliv.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70536; 1973-3-8

[WAG.1940724]

Total: 3; Cross River 2, Kaduna 1.

Campylospermum oliveri (Tiegh.) Farron

Notocampylum oliveri Tiegh.

Meer, PPC van 1616; 1971-6-14 [WAG.1577319]

Total: 7; Cross River 6, Nasarawa 1.

Campylospermum reticulatum (P.Beauv.) Farron

Gomphia reticulata P.Beauv.

Meer, PPC van 1291; 1971-4-15 [WAG.1940765]

Total: 27; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 10, Delta 2, Edo 4.

Campylospermum squamosum (DC.) Farron

Ochna squamosa Bosc

Dalziel J.M. S.N.; 1912-- [BR0000016947917]

Total: 1; Benue 1.

Campylospermum sulcatum (Tiegh.) Farron

Exomicrum sulcatum Tiegh.

Meer, PPC van 1410; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1940859]

Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7, Delta 2, Edo 9, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 5.

Campylospermum vogelii (Hook.f. ex Planch.) Farron

Gomphia vogelii Hook.f. ex Planch.

Pilz, GE 1976; 1977-4-24 [WAG.1940583]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Lagos 1.

Lophira alata Banks ex C.F.Gaertn.

Collector unknown FPRL 2149; -- [USw11720]

Total: 37; Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Lophira lanceolata Tiegh. ex Keay

Chapman, JD 2643; 1972-1-21 [WAG.1119570]

Total: 40; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 3.

Ochna afzelii R.Br. ex Oliv.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 46807; 1972-4-13

[WAG.1119629]

Total: 22; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Ochna atropurpurea DC. — Introduced

Emwiogbon J.A. FHI52764; 28-10-1961

[K001391503]

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Ochna calodendron Gilg & Mildbr.

Chapman J.D. 4275; 12-03-1979 [K]

Total: 1.

Ochna latisepala (Tiegh.) Bamps — Introduced

Diporochna latisepala Tiegh.

Emwiogbon J.A. FHI47157; 22-02-1963

[K001391502]

Total: 1.

Ochna membranacea Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1776; 1971-5-23 [WAG.1476879]

Total: 6; Cross River 3, Kaduna 1, Oyo 2.

Ochna multiflora DC.

Onochie, CFA FHI 33189; 1953-5-16

[WAG.1119921]

Total: 8; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Ochna rhizomatosa (Tiegh.) Keay

Ochnella rhizomatosa Tiegh.

Leeuw, PN de 67; 1961-5-1 [WAG.1120040]

Total: 16; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 5, Niger 5, Plateau 2.

Ochna schweinfurthiana F.Hoffm.

7030; 1964-3-13 [7030] [2302319568]

Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Ochna staudtii Gilg

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 227; 1983-5-12 [WAG.1120124]

Total: 5; Ogun 4, Oyo 1.

Rhabdophyllum affine (Hook.f.) Tiegh.

Gomphia affinis Hook.f.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11279; 1977-3-28

[WAG.1120488]

Total: 39; Abia 3, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Rhabdophyllum arnoldianum (De Wild. & T.Durand) Tiegh.

Ouratea arnoldiana De Wild. & T.Durand

Meer, PPC van 1426; 1971-4-22 [WAG.1120610]

Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 4, Bayelsa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Edo 5, Oyo 4.

Rhabdophyllum calophyllum (Hook.f.)

Tiegh.

Gomphia calophylla Hook.f.

R.H. Hide 13940; -- [BR0000017022033]

Total: 9; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4.

Sauvagesia erecta L.

Geerling, C 3531; 1971-4-12 [WAG.1120972]

Total: 43; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Oyo 1.

Sauvagesia erecta subsp. *erecta*

Barter, C 1733; 1857-1-1 [U.1444412]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

PHYLLANTHACEAE

Amanoa strobilacea Müll.Arg.

Edwin Ujor; 1952-7-8 [31630]1944991434

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Antidesma laciniatum Müll.Arg.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11323; 1977-4-1 [WAG.1929444]

Total: 131; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 5, Anambra 4, Cross River 31, Delta 1, Edo 19, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 31, Ondo 10, Osun 7, Oyo 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Antidesma membranaceum Müll.Arg.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 412; 1978-5-11

[WAG.1929786]

Total: 62; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Borno 2, Cross River 4, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 12, Plateau 5, Taraba 3.

Antidesma rufescens Tul.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66330; 1973-5-14

[WAG.1931910]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Antidesma venosum E.Mey. ex Tul.

Daramola, BO FHI 54675; 1964-5-20

[WAG.1931752]

Total: 100; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 4, Anambra 3, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 1, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 14, Kano 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 8, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 9, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 9, Sokoto 2, Taraba 10.

Antidesma vogelianum Müll.Arg.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32809; 1981-6-18

[WAG.1795373]

Total: 70; Akwa Ibom 8, Cross River 37, Edo 3, Kwara 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Taraba 3.

Breynia disticha J.R.Forst. & G.Forst. —

Introduced

Lowe J. 2909; 1976-5-12 [79109]1944997444

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Oyo 3.

Bridelia atroviridis Müll.Arg.

ONYEAGHUNLA COLLINS; 2014-8-6

[6160]3808439977

Total: 96; Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 21, Ekiti 5, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 11, Ondo 12, Osun 4, Oyo 17, Taraba 1.

Bridelia cathartica Bertol. — Introduced

Ugwuzor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [234A] [1990271815]

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Bridelia ferruginea Benth.

Croat, TB 53400; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1791825]

Total: 306; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 2, Benue 3, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 9, Ekiti 2, Enugu 13, Kaduna 31, Kogi 7, Kwara 18, Lagos 10, Niger 31, Ogun 28, Ondo 8, Osun 11, Oyo 49, Plateau 23, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 22.

Bridelia grandis Pierre ex Hutch.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1944-09-16 [FHI.7678.0]

Total: 14; Edo 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Oyo 3.

Bridelia grandis subsp. *grandis*

Oyayomi Osanyinlusi 91; 1977-6-27

[83027]1944998094

Total: 1.

Bridelia micrantha (Hochst.) Baill.

Candelabria micrantha Hochst.

Geerling C. [BR0000015442185]

Total: 123; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Cross River 19, Delta 1, Edo 6, Ekiti 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 5, Ogun 8, Ondo 5, Osun 7, Oyo 28, Plateau 5, Taraba 8.

Bridelia micrantha var. *micrantha*

Candelabria micrantha Hochst.

Chapman, JD FHI 68590; 1973-3-4 [WAG.1792100]

Total: 1.

Bridelia ndellensis Beille

Denys E. 840; -- [BR0000015813558]

Total: 6; Kaduna 3, Oyo 1.

Bridelia scleroneura Müll.Arg.

Hepper F.N. [BR0000015815002]

Total: 76; Adamawa 6, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Borno 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 6, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 8, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3, Niger 15, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Bridelia scleroneura subsp. *scleroneura*

Pilz, GE 2247; 1977-12-27 [WAG.1792289]

Total: 1.

Bridelia speciosa Müll.Arg.

Chapman, JD 2710; 1972-3-2 [WAG.1792309]

Total: 16; Adamawa 3, Cross River 5, Lagos 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Cleistanthus bipindensis Pax

Usang felix; 2005-10-10 [225] [3913474719]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Cleistanthus libericus N.E.Br.

Brenan J.P.M.9200; 1948-2-29 [50926-1]

[1949704580]

Total: 5; Edo 3, Osun 2.

Cleistanthus ripicola J.Léonard

Okafor J.C.;Emwiogbon J.A.; 1966-8-4 [60369] [1944995059]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Flueggea virosa (Roxb. ex Willd.) Royle

Phyllanthus virosus Roxb. ex Willd.

Geerling, C 3658; 1971-7-21 [WAG.1805892]

Total: 165; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 8, Benue 4, Borno 8, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 5, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Kogi 6, Kwara 9, Lagos 10, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 13, Ondo 9, Osun 6, Oyo 40, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Flueggea virosa subsp. *virosa*

Phyllanthus virosus Roxb. ex Willd.

Daramola, BO s.n.; 1985-12-6 [WAG.1805908]

Total: 14; Borno 2, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Zamfara 1.

Hymenocardia acida Tul.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66371; 1973-5-16 [WAG.1294174]

Total: 177; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 6, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Cross River 4, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 7, Kaduna 15, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 10, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 27, Ogun 10, Ondo 7, Osun 5, Oyo 24, Plateau 13, Taraba 5.

Hymenocardia heudelotii Planch. ex

Müll.Arg.

Daramola B.O.;Binuyo A.; 1968-2-27 [61907]1944995305

Total: 10; Anambra 1, Kogi 3, Niger 2.

Hymenocardia heudelotii var. *chevalieri*

(Beille) J.Léonard

Daramola B.O.;Binuyo A. ; 1968-02-27 [61907.0]

Total: 1.

Hymenocardia heudelotii var. *heudelotii*

Barter C. 327; 31-01-1905 [k]

Total: 4; Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Keayodendron bridelioides Leandri

Casearia bridelioides Mildbr. ex Hutch. & Dalziel

Olorunfemi, J. FHI35662; 1956-11-12 [K000044403]

Total: 33; Kaduna 5, Ogun 12, Ondo 9.

Kirganelia reticulata (Poir.) Baill.

Phyllanthus reticulatus auct.

Literature

Total: 0.

Maesobotrya barteri (Baill.) Hutch.

Pierardia barteri Baill.

Ibhanesebhor G.; Raji 732; 1978-9-28
[89711]1944999148

Total: 165; Abia 8, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 54, Delta 9, Edo 29, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 20, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Maesobotrya barteri var. *barteri*

Pierardia barteri Baill.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65847; 1972-6-9
[WAG.1800882]

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Edo 2, Taraba 1.

Maesobotrya barteri var. *sparsiflora* (Scott Elliot) Keay

Baccaurea sparsiflora Scott Elliot

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11302; 1977-3-31
[WAG.1800722]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Delta 2, Edo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Maesobotrya floribunda Benth.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11300; 1977-3-31
[WAG.1801136]

Total: 17; Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Maesobotrya klaineana (Pierre) J.Léonard

Staphysora klaineana Pierre

Meer, PPC van 1351; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1800572]

Total: 44; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 7, Cross River 26.

Maesobotrya staudtii (Pax) Hutch.

Baccaurea staudtii Pax

Meer V.1526; 1971-5-8 [34759-1] [1949704042]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 14.

Maesobotrya vermeulenii (De Wild.)

J.Léonard

Baccaurea vermeulenii De Wild.

Hepper F.N. 1827; -- [BR0000016211377]

Total: 1.

Margaritaria discoidea (Baill.) G.L.Webster

Cicca discoidea Baill.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000014401213]

Total: 140; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 8, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Enugu 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 7, Kwara 5, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 17, Ondo 5, Osun 3, Oyo 34, Plateau 11, Taraba 5.

Margaritaria discoidea var. *discoidea*

Cicca discoidea Baill.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 90117; 1979-4-9
[WAG.1353579]

Total: 28; Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

Margaritaria discoidea var. *fagifolia* (Pax) Radcl.-Sm.

Flueggea fagifolia Pax

[Baxter]; 3420; 1859-01-01 [K004833301]

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Martretia quadricornis Beille

Latilo M.G.; 1963-2-14 [47112-1] [1949704359]

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Kogi 4, Oyo 1.

Phyllanthus acidus (L.) Skeels —

Introduced

Averrhoa acida L.

Keay R.W.J.; Okeke R.E. FHI38446; 10-03-1959 [K]

Total: 3; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Phyllanthus alpestris Beille

Denys E. 783; -- [BR0000016654907]

Total: 1.

Phyllanthus amarus Schumach. & Thonn.

— Introduced

Wit, HCD de; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 64217; 1971-9-16 [WAG.1354566]

Total: 93; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 8, Delta 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 12, Niger 2, Ogun 16, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 23, Taraba 2.

Phyllanthus dusenii Hutch.

Talbot P.A. 2323; 26-03-1905 [K]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Phyllanthus fraternus G.L.Webster —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 2043; 1966-9-23 [WAG.1354873]

Total: 3; Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Phyllanthus gagnioevae Jean F.Brunel & J.P.Roux

Schlechter R. 13014; -- [BR0000016659322]

Total: 3; Abia 1.

Phyllanthus kerstingii J.F.Brunel

Lely, H.V. 819; 1930-10-01 [K004860760]

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Phyllanthus maderaspatensis L.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000016660885]

Total: 10; Borno 6, Gombe 1, Sokoto 1.

Phyllanthus maderaspatensis var. *maderaspatensis*

Dalziel J.M. 391; -- [BR0000016660885]

Total: 1.

Phyllanthus mannianus Müll.Arg.

Ekwuno P.O.311; 1975-11-26 [77250] [1944997196]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Phyllanthus muellerianus (Kuntze) Exell

Diasperus muellerianus Kuntze

Odewo, TK; Binuyo, A 111; 1982-9-8

[WAG.1801556]

Total: 166; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Borno 1, Cross River 11, Edo 10, Ekiti 4, Enugu 11, Kaduna 11, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 12, Lagos 8, Nasarawa 3, Niger 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 4, Osun 4, Oyo 28, Plateau 8, Taraba 7.

Phyllanthus nigericus Brenan

Brenan, Prof. J.P.M.; Keay, R.W.J. 8693; 1948-1-3

[K000406120]

Total: 15; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Niger 1, Ondo 6, Osun 1, Taraba 3.

Phyllanthus niruri L. — Introduced

Barter, C. ; 1858-- [P00539719]

Total: 37; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 3.

Phyllanthus niruroides Müll.Arg.

Stanfield D.P.; 1958-11-1 [19357] [1944989805]

Total: 2; Edo 1, Oyo 1.

Phyllanthus nummulariifolius Poir. —

Introduced

Lely, H.V.; P238; 1929-04-01 [K004860443]

Total: 34; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 6, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 3, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Phyllanthus nummulariifolius subsp.

nummulariifolius

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 550; 1978-5-1

[WAG.1354742]

Total: 1.

Phyllanthus nummulariifolius var. *capillaris*

(Schumach. & Thonn.) Radcl.-Sm.

Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. 600; 05-09-1963 [K]

Total: 1.

Phyllanthus odontadenius Müll.Arg.

Daramola, BO FHI 90110; 1979-4-9 [WAG.1799954]

Total: 53; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 16, Taraba 5.

Phyllanthus ovalifolius Forssk.

Lowe J. 4774; 29-03-1987 [K]

Total: 1.

Phyllanthus pentandrus Schumach. &

Thonn.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63198; 1972-8-8

[WAG.1340080]

Total: 14; Borno 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1.

Phyllanthus physocarpus Müll.Arg.

Dennett, RE 18; -- [L.4294403]

Total: 6; Ondo 1, Osun 2.

Phyllanthus polyspermus Schumach.

Literature

Total: 0.

Phyllanthus reticulatus Poir. — Introduced

Geerling, C 3487; 1971-3-24 [WAG.1340260]

Total: 51; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 4, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 9, Niger 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Phyllanthus sublanatus Schumach. &

Thonn.

Bels, L 75; 1950-4-14 [U.1472208]

Total: 16; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Cross River 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.

Phyllanthus urinaria L. — Introduced

Onochie C.F.A. ; 1975-9-7 [34311]

Total: 5; Edo 3, Rivers 1.

Phyllanthus urinaria subsp. *urinaria* —

Introduced

Daramola B.O. FHI72479; 08-10-1973 [K]

Total: 1.

Phyllanthus welwitschianus Müll.Arg.

Stanfield D.P.; 1965-5-2 [61825] [1944995254]

Total: 5; Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Protomegabaria macrophylla Hutch.

Baccaurea macrophylla Pax

Latilo, M.G.41308; 1959-3-10 [43846] [912043471]

Total: 5; Abia 2, Cross River 3.

Protomegabaria stapfiana (Beille) Hutch.

Maesobotrya stapfiana Beille

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32949; 1981-6-21

[WAG.1341216]

Total: 36; Abia 7, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 21, Kaduna 2, Niger 1.

Spondianthus preussii Engl.

Jones [FHI.20213.0]

Total: 40; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 6, Imo 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Spondianthus preussii subsp. *glaber* (Engl.)

J.Léonard & Nkounkou

Ujor E.U.; 1952-6-7 [27982] [1944990896]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Spondianthus preussii subsp. *preussii*

Ariwaodo, JO 70; 1976-12-22 [WAG.1337763]

Total: 1.

Thecacoris leptobotrya (Müll.Arg.) Brenan

Antidesma leptobotryum Müll.Arg.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 319; 1977-10-12

[WAG.1338385]

Total: 31; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 19.

Thecacoris stenopetala (Müll.Arg.)

Müll.Arg.

Antidesma stenopetalum Müll.Arg.

Latilo M.G. 6; 1959-3-16 [40905]1944992503

Total: 13; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 9.

Thecacoris viridis (Müll.Arg.) G.L.Webster

Cyathogyne viridis Müll.Arg.

1945-07-23 [FHI.3936.0]

Total: 5; Borno 1, Cross River 3.

Thecacoris viridis subsp. *viridis*

Cyathogyne viridis Müll.Arg.

Onochie C.F.A.; Okafor J.C.; 1957-1-18 [36058X-1]

Total: 1.

Uapaca acuminata (Hutch.) Pax &

K.Hoffm.

Uapaca heudelotii var. *acuminata* Hutch.

Hall J.B.17969; 1978-1-14 [88217] [1944998857]

Total: 5; Cross River 3.

Uapaca guineensis Müll.Arg.

Gentry 32879; 1981-6-20 [141766] [1258643502]

Total: 29; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 4, Cross River 13, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Uapaca heudelotii Baill.

Geerling, C; Bosch, M 5582; 1976-1-20

[WAG.1339532]

Total: 69; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 6, Ogun 11, Ondo 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 2.

Uapaca mole Pax

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 53; 1977-10-4

[WAG.1339814]

Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 10, Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Uapaca pynaertii De Wild.

Olorunfemi J.; Oguntayo S.T.211; 1977-11-9 [86721]

[1944998540]

Total: 8; Edo 3, Ondo 2.

Uapaca staudtii Pax

Gentry, AH 32879; 1981-6-20 [WAG.1810310]

Total: 28; Borno 1, Cross River 15, Edo 5, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 3.

Uapaca togoensis Pax

Chapman, JD 2758; 1972-4-17 [WAG.1810516]

Total: 136; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Cross River 19, Delta 1, Edo 5, Enugu 8, Kaduna 22, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 26, Plateau 12, Sokoto 1, Taraba 8.

Uapaca vanhouttei De Wild.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32859; 1981-6-20

[WAG.1810412]

Total: 17; Cross River 14.

ELATINACEAE

Bergia guineensis Hutch. & Dalziel

Literature

Total: 0.

Bergia suffruticosa (Delile) Fenzl

Lancretia suffruticosa Delile

Leeuw, PN de 1889; 1967-3-15 [WAG.1181658]

Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 5, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Niger 1.

Elatine triandra Schkuhr — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

MALPIGHIACEAE

Acridocarpus alternifolius (Schumach. & Thonn.) Nied.

Malpighia alternifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Meikle, R.D.; 1949-12-18 [P00135943]

Total: 1.

Acridocarpus longifolius (G.Don) Hook.f.

Anomalopterys longifolia G.Don

Mann, G.; 1860-8- [P00135897]

Total: 4; Cross River 1.

Acridocarpus macrocalyx Engl.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1093; 1971-12-28

[WAG.1072253]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Osun 2.

Acridocarpus smeathmanii (DC.) Guill. & Perr.

Heteropterys smeathmanii DC.

Meer, PPC van 545; 1968-1-23 [WAG.1072435]

Total: 4; Lagos 2, Oyo 2.

Acridocarpus smeathmannii (DC.) Guill. & Perr.

Heteropterys smeathmannii DC.

Dalziel J.M.; S.N.; 1912-01-01 [BR0000020419967]

Total: 20; Benue 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 4.

Flabellaria paniculata Cav.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11335; 1977-4-4 [WAG.1072786]

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 4, Oyo 3.

Galphimia glauca Cav. — Introduced

Nsukaba N.F; 1982-5-30 [870]3808440471

Total: 5; Lagos 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Galphimia gracilis Bartl. — Introduced

Jones A.P.D. 13731; 1945-10-19

[1193632]1258399822

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Heteropterys leona (Cav.) Exell

Banisteria leona Cav.

Daramola, BO FHI 55282; 1964-10-4

[WAG.1072863]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Triaspis odorata (Willd.) A.Juss.

Hiraea odorata Willd.

J.Opayemi; 1971-5-8 [873] [3808440449]

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Triaspis stipulata Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 899; 1969-1-1 [WAG.1073351]

Total: 13; Kaduna 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 8.

DICHAPETALACEAE

Dichapetalum angolense Chodat

Meer, PPC van 1854; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1776694]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Taraba 1.

Dichapetalum barteri Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67607; 1973-1-20

[WAG.1776855]

Total: 53; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 23, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Enugu 8, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Dichapetalum choristilum Engl.

Savory H.J.; Keay R.W.J.; 1948-12-29 [FHI.25203.0]

Total: 7; Cross River 6.

Dichapetalum choristilum var. *choristilum*

Meer, PPC van 1811; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1785030]

Total: 1.

Dichapetalum crassifolium Chodat

Meer, PPC van 1872; 1971-1-1 [WAG.1773116]

Total: 10; Cross River 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Dichapetalum crassifolium var. *crassifolium*

Van Meer P. 662; -- [BR0000014888014]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Dichapetalum dewevrei De Wild. & T.Durand

Leeuwenberg A.J.M. [BR0000014888632]

Total: 7; Edo 5.

Dichapetalum dewevrei var. *dewevrei*

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11266; 1977-3-27

[WAG.1773452]

Total: 1.

Dichapetalum fructuosum Hiern

Chizea L.G.; 1949-3-12 [24486]1944990599

Total: 2; Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Dichapetalum gabonense Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70504; 1973-3-5

[WAG.1772515]

Total: 23; Cross River 16, Edo 1, Kogi 2.

Dichapetalum heudelotii (Planch. ex Oliv.) Baill.

Chailletia heudelotii Planch. ex Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1862; 1971-1-1 [WAG.1772770]

Total: 94; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Benue 1, Cross River 49, Delta 2, Edo 5, Enugu 2, Lagos 5, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Plateau 1.

Dichapetalum heudelotii var. *heudelotii*

Chailletia heudelotii Planch. ex Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1787; 1971-5-24 [WAG.1771936]

Total: 42; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 21, Delta 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Plateau 1.

Dichapetalum heudelotii var.

longitubulosum (Engl.) Breteler

Dichapetalum longitubulosum Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70570; 1973-3-11
[WAG.1772339]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Dichapetalum insigne Engl.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1957-1-30 [36191X-1]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dichapetalum madagascariense Poir.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32795 a; 1981-6-17

[WAG.1785463]

Total: 214; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 18, Delta 1, Edo 9, Kaduna 3, Lagos 18, Niger 4, Ogun 28, Ondo 5, Osun 6, Oyo 90.

Dichapetalum madagascariense var.
madagascariense

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO 28; 1980-2-26

[WAG.1782029]

Total: 45; Cross River 8, Edo 2, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 27.

Dichapetalum mombuttense Engl. —

Introduced

Dr Kadiri; 2008-12-1 [634] [3808440520]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Dichapetalum mundense Engl.

Emwioybon, JA; Osanyinlusi 314; 1977-10-12

[WAG.1225849]

Total: 33; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 27, Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Dichapetalum obanense (Baker f.) Hutch. & Dalziel — Endemic

Dichapetalum thomsonii var. *obanense* Baker f.

Talbot, PA 1627; 1911-1-1 [WAG0001094]

Total: 6; Cross River 5.

Dichapetalum oblongum (Hook.f. ex Benth.) Engl.

Chaillietia oblonga Hook.f. ex Benth.

Latilo M.G. & Onyeachusim H.D. 54260; --

[BR0000015588340]

Total: 16; Anambra 2, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Edo 2, Kogi 1, Ogun 1.

Dichapetalum pallidum (Oliv.) Engl.

Chaillietia pallida Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1772; 1971-5-23 [WAG.1226293]

Total: 53; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 11, Kogi 2, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 6, Oyo 5.

Dichapetalum parvifolium Engl.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11324; 1977-4-1 [WAG0029529]

Total: 8; Delta 5, Edo 1.

Dichapetalum reticulatum Engl.

Umana, OA FHI 29104; 1951-5-17 [WAG.1226462]

Total: 7; Edo 2, Ondo 4, Oyo 1.

Dichapetalum rudatisii Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1339; 1971-4-17 [WAG.1226595]

Total: 37; Abia 1, Cross River 31.

Dichapetalum staudtii Engl.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70741; 1973-3-9

[WAG.1226709]

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Dichapetalum tomentosum Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67680; 1973-2-25

[WAG.1226981]

Total: 17; Cross River 15, Edo 1.

Dichapetalum trichocephalum Breteler —
Introduced

Schmitt 408; 1995-2-9 [976780]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dichapetalum umbellatum Chodat

Akpabla, GK 1087; 1948-3-16 [WAG.1227178]

Total: 25; Edo 19, Lagos 5, Ogun 1.

Dichapetalum unguiculatum Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1634; 1971-5-15 [WAG.1227268]

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Dichapetalum zenkeri Engl.

Binuyo A.; 1962-1-24 [45451-1]

Total: 6; Cross River 5, Ebonyi 1.

Tapura africana Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1353; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1782231]

Total: 9; Cross River 8.

Tapura fischeri Engl.

Jones A.P.D.; 1943-11-6 [7347] [1944988381]

Total: 22; Ogun 14, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Tragia chevalieri Beille

Talbot P.A. 1494; 1911-- [BM000911172]

Total: 1.

Tragia mildbraediana Pax & K.Hoffm.

Wit P.; Gbile Z.O.970; 1971-11-18 [64680-1]

[1949704713]

Total: 5; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Tragia plukenetii Radcl.-Sm.

Croton hastatus L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Tragia preussii Pax

Onochie C.F.A. FHI36094X; 21-01-1957 [K]

Total: 4; Benue 1, Cross River 2.

Tragia spathulata Benth.

Talbot P.A. 72

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Tragia tenuifolia Benth.

Onochie, CFA; Wit, HCD de 7489; 1958-1-16

[WAG.1338988]

Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Tragia vogelii Keay

Tragia angustifolia Benth.

Geerling, C 4128; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1339003]

Total: 36; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Delta 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Tragia volubilis L.

Jones A.P.D.; Keay R.W.J.; Onochie C.F.A.; 1945-11- [4934] [1944988035]

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Tragia wildemanii Beille

Sharland, R.E. 1325; 1980-7-8 [K000489891]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1.

Vernicia cordata (Thunb.) Airy Shaw —
Introduced

Dryandra cordata Thunb.

Latilo M.G.; Daramola B.O.; 1954-12-26 [28953-1] [1949703855]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Vernicia montana Lour. — Introduced

Ajia, B.M. FHI29056 [K004624267]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

CHRYSOBALANACEAE

Afrolicania elaeosperma Mildbr.

Meer, PPC van 980; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1390141]

Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 3, Delta 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 3.

Chrysobalanus icaco L.

Bels, L 46; 1950-3-23 [U.1202483]

Total: 120; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Bayelsa 3, Benue 2, Cross River 9, Delta 3, Edo 40, Kano 1, Lagos 25, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 3, Rivers 5.

Chrysobalanus icaco subsp. *atacorensis*
(A.Chev.) F.White

Lowe, J 1958; 1970-1-4 [WAG.1390248]

Total: 31; Delta 2, Edo 28, Rivers 1.

Chrysobalanus icaco subsp. *icaco*

Gbile, ZO; Latilo, MG FHI 20903; 1969-1-1

[WAG.1390384]

Total: 30; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 2, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Kano 1, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Dactyladenia barteri (Hook.f. ex Oliv.)

Prance & F.White

Griffonia barteri Hook.f. ex Oliv.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65935; 1972-10-30

[WAG.1390494]

Total: 109; Abia 8, Akwa Ibom 5, Anambra 18, Benue 1, Cross River 18, Edo 6, Enugu 14, Imo 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 11, Ogun 1, Oyo 8, Rivers 3.

Dactyladenia bellayana (Baill.) Prance &
F.White

Acioa bellayana Baill.

Talbot, P.A. 3123; 1913-- [CM460207]

Total: 1.

Dactyladenia campestris (Engl.) Prance &
F.White

Acioa campestris Engl.

Onochie, CFA FHI 33153; 1953-5-14

[WAG.1390576]

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 7, Cross River 4.

Dactyladenia dewevrei (De Wild. &
T.Durand) Prance & F.White

Acioa dewevrei De Wild. & T.Durand

Lowe, J. 2274; 1971-7-13 [K000103094]

Total: 8; Edo 5.

Dactyladenia dichotoma (De Wild.) Prance
& F.White — Endemic

Acioa dichotoma De Wild.

Talbot, P.A. 3048; -- [BM000842027]

Total: 2.

Dactyladenia etekensis (De Wild.) Prance &
F.White

Acioa etekensis De Wild.

Talbot P.A. & Talbot D.A. S.N.; 1912--

[BR0000008870537]

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 3.

Dactyladenia hirsuta (A.Chev. ex De Wild.)
Prance & F.White

Acioa hirsuta A.Chev. ex De Wild.

Kennedy J.D. 1961; -- [BR0000021886348]

Total: 1.

Dactyladenia johnstonei (Hoyle) Prance & F.White

Acioa johnstonei Hoyle
Hall, Dr J.B. 3021; 1971-3-14 [K000103097]
Total: 3; Borno 1, Cross River 2.

Dactyladenia lehmbachii (Engl.) Prance & F.White

Acioa lehmbachii Engl.
Olu Akpata FHI 3939; 1945-5-30 [K000103098]
Total: 8; Cross River 3, Delta 2, Edo 1, Plateau 1.

Dactyladenia pallescens (Baill.) Prance & F.White

Acioa pallescens Baill.
Okafor, JC; Latilo, MG FHI 57774; 1966-1-23 [WAG.1390786]
Total: 24; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 18, Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Dactyladenia scabrifolia (Hua) Prance & F.White

Acioa scabrifolia Hua
Onochie C.F.A. ; 1955-2- [33916]
Total: 1; Edo 1.

Dactyladenia smeathmannii (Baill.) Prance & F.White

Acioa smeathmannii Baill.
Lowe J. 2274; 1971-7-13 [31728]
Total: 5; Edo 3, Taraba 1.

Dactyladenia staudtii (Engl.) Prance & F.White

Acioa staudtii Engl.
Pilz, GE 1973; 1977-4-24 [WAG.1390820]
Total: 12; Cross River 8.

Magnistipula butayei subsp. *butayei*
Wit P.; Daramola B.O.; 1973-4-3 [77615]1944997290
Total: 1.

Magnistipula tessmannii (Engl.) Prance

Parinari tessmannii Engl.
Literature
Total: 0.

Magnistipula zenkeri Engl.
Ujor, E. FHI 30183; 1952-6-18 [K000102960]
Total: 2; Ogun 2.

Maranthes aubrevillei (Pellegr.) Prance ex F.White

Parinari aubrevillei Pellegr.
Literature
Total: 0.

Maranthes chrysophylla (Oliv.) Prance ex F.White

Parinari chrysophylla Oliv.
Keay, R.W.J.; 1950-12-13 [K000103974]
Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Maranthes chrysophylla subsp. *chrysophylla*

Parinari chrysophylla Oliv.
Keay, R.W.J. sn; 1950-12-13 [K000103974]
Total: 1.

Maranthes gabunensis (Engl.) Prance

Parinari gabunensis Engl.
Meer, PPC van 1501; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1257562]
Total: 13; Anambra 1, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Ondo 2.

Maranthes glabra (Oliv.) Prance

Parinari glabra Oliv.
Jones, E.W.; Brenan, J.P.M. 8904; 1948-1-27 [K000103995]
Total: 26; Anambra 1, Edo 12, Ekiti 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Maranthes kerstingii (Engl.) Prance ex F.White

Parinari kerstingii Engl.
Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70676; 1973-3-1 [WAG.1257664]
Total: 30; Bauchi 4, Edo 1, Ekiti 3, Enugu 5, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 5.

Maranthes polyandra (Benth.) Prance

Parinari polyandra Benth.
Daramola B.O. 62; 1979-7-27 [91182]
Total: 164; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 6, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Enugu 5, Kogi 9, Kwara 19, Lagos 1, Niger 37, Ogun 12, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 26, Taraba 10.

Maranthes robusta (Oliv.) Prance ex F.White

Parinari robusta Oliv.
Latilo, M.G. FHI47101; 1963-2-8 [K000103982]
Total: 37; Anambra 4, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 6, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Oyo 3.

Neocarya macrophylla (Sabine) Prance ex F.White

Parinari macrophylla Sabine
Jackson, JK 5341; 1966-6-20 [WAG.1257799]
Total: 26; Abia 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Kano 8, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Sokoto 5, Zamfara 2.

Parinari congensis Didr.

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD 153; 1972-5-4 [WAG.1257883]
Total: 36; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 3, Benue 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Parinari curatellifolia Planch. ex Benth.
Pilz, GE 2055; 1977-5-21 [WAG.1258002]
Total: 153; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 8, Kaduna 12, Kebbi 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 17, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 16, Ogun 8, Ondo 9, Oyo 23, Plateau 8, Taraba 13.

Parinari excelsa Sabine
Daramola, B.O. 576; 1994-11-26 [K000103696]
Total: 23; Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Parinari hypochrysea Mildbr. ex Letouzey & F.White
Literature
Total: 0.

PUTRANJIVACEAE

Drypetes aframensis Hutch.
Richards #3081 (MO 1610643!)
Total: 33; Bayelsa 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 11, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 12.

Drypetes capillipes (Pax) Pax & K.Hoffm.
Lingelsheimia capillipes Pax
Brenan #8403 (P04707091!)
Total: 25; Edo 22, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Drypetes chevalieri Beille ex Hutch. & Dalziel
Keay FHI #37279 (P04707900!)
Total: 58; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 36, Ogun 4, Ondo 9.

Drypetes floribunda (Müll.Arg.) Hutch.
Cyclostemon floribundus Müll.Arg.
Onochie FHI #21972 (K s.n.!)
Total: 43; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 15, Ondo 4, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Drypetes gilgiana (Pax) Pax & K.Hoffm.
Cyclostemon gilgianus Pax
Onochie FHI #7277 (WAG.15639131!)
Total: 74; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 9, Ondo 11, Osun 2, Oyo 27, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Drypetes gossweileri S.Moore

Coombe #183 (BR0000013609429!)
Total: 31; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 18, Kaduna 2.

Drypetes ituriensis Pax & K.Hoffm.
Jones FHI #16737 (FHO 000185771!)
Total: 3; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Drypetes ivorensis Hutch. & Dalziel
Onochie FHI36251X (K s.n.!)
Total: 9; Cross River 5, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Drypetes klainei Pierre ex Pax
Jones FHI #18908 (FHO 00018567!)
Total: 1.

Drypetes moliwensis Cheek & Radcl.-Sm.
Tuley 743 (K s.n.!)
Total: 1.

Drypetes obanensis S.Moore — Endemic
Talbot P.A. & Talbot D.A. [BR0000015196965]
Total: 12; Borno 2, Cross River 7, Kogi 1, Niger 2.

Drypetes parvifolia (Müll.Arg.) Pax & K.Hoffm.
Cyclostemon parvifolius Müll.Arg.
Barter #1032 (K0004064051!)
Total: 7; Cross River 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3.

Drypetes paxii Hutch.
Binuyo FHI #41441 (WAG.1564481!)
Total: 23; Cross River 5, Edo 5, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Oyo 3.

Drypetes peltophora S.Moore
van Meer #1367 (WAG.1564892!)
Total: 1.

Drypetes preussii (Pax) Hutch.
Cyclostemon preussii Pax
Coombe #182 (P04707220!)
Total: 5; Abia 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2.

Drypetes principum (Müll.Arg.) Hutch.
Cyclostemon principum Müll.Arg.
Tamajong FHI #20982 (FHO 00018531!)
Total: 60; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 22, Ondo 15, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 5.

Drypetes rowlandii Pax — Endemic
Rowland s.n. (K000406237!)
Total: 1.

Drypetes similis Hutch.
Talbot #619 (Z 000081328!)
Total: 6; Cross River 5, Kaduna 1.

Drypetes spinosodentata (Pax) Hutch.
Cyclostemon spinosodentatus Pax

Jones FHI #18644 (FHO 00018574!)

Total: 1.

Drypetes staudtii (Pax) Hutch.

Cyclostemon staudtii Pax

Jones FHI #16625 (P04777251!)

Total: 19; Abia 1, Cross River 6, Ogun 12.

Drypetes stevartii Sonké & Quintanar

Latilo & Daramola FHI 28890 (FHO00018584)

Total: 1.

Drypetes stipularis (Müll.Arg.) Hutch.

Cyclostemon stipularis Müll.Arg.

Pilz #2514 (MO 2835270!)

Total: 21; Cross River 7, Edo 3, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

CTENOLOPHONACEAE

Ctenolophon englerianus Mildbr.

Meer, PPC van 958; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1057979]

Total: 16; Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 7.

PASSIFLORACEAE

Adenia cissampeloides (Planch. ex Hook.)

Harms

Modecca cissampeloides Planch. ex Hook.

Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwunoo, PO 68184; 1973-11-21 [WAG.1147006]

Total: 36; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 7, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Taraba 2.

Adenia cynanchifolia (Benth.) Harms

Modecca cynanchifolia Benth.

Literature

Total: 0.

Adenia gracilis Harms

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Delta 1.

Adenia gracilis subsp. *gracilis*

Talbot, P.; 469; 1911-01-01 [K005187636]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Delta 1.

Adenia guineensis W.J.de Wilde

Literature

Total: 0.

Adenia lobata (Jacq.) Engl.

Modecca lobata Jacq.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32663; 1981-6-14 [WAG.1147419]

Total: 50; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 7, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Oyo 18, Rivers 1.

Adenia mannii (Mast.) Engl.

Modecca mannii Mast.

Talbot, P.A. (Mr.); Talbot, P.A. (Mrs.) s.n.; 1911-01-01 [K005187452]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Adenia reticulata (De Wild. & T.Durand)

Engl.

Ophiocaulon reticulatum De Wild. & T.Durand

Literature

Total: 0.

Adenia reticulata var. *reticulata*

Ophiocaulon reticulatum De Wild. & T.Durand

Literature

Total: 0.

Adenia rumicifolia Engl. & Harms —

Introduced

Binuyo, A 41252; 1959-4-18 [WAG.1147690]

Total: 8; Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Adenia venenata Forssk.

Dalziel, J.M. sn.; 1909-02-08 [K005187450]

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Barteria dewevrei De Wild. & T.Durand

Binuyo A. 41445; 1959-8-12 [BR0000017637091]

Total: 3; Abia 1, Borno 1, Edo 1.

Barteria fistulosa Mast.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70572; 1973-3-11 [WAG.1477411]

Total: 26; Abia 2, Cross River 4, Edo 7, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Barteria nigritana Hook.f.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11303; 1977-3-31

[WAG.1148005]

Total: 44; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 3, Cross River 9, Delta 3, Edo 1, Enugu 8, Lagos 8, Rivers 2.

Barteria pubescens (Sol. ex R.Br.) Byng & Christenh.

Smeathmannia pubescens Sol. ex R.Br.

Binuyo, A FHI 41277; 1959-4-28 [WAG.1148913]

Total: 1.

Barteria solida Breteler

Meer, PPC van 1792; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1477479]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Efulensia clematoides C.H.Wright

Emwiogbon, J.A. FHI44263 [K005185712]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Paropsia guineensis Oliv.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 46792; 1972-4-13

[WAG.1148355]

Total: 31; Abia 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 9, Edo 11, Enugu 2, Kogi 2.

Passiflora biflora Lam. — Introduced

MacKee, H.S.; 1964-1-22 [P00647336]

Total: 1.

Passiflora edulis Sims — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1456; 1966-5-2 [WAG.1148463]

Total: 7; Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Passiflora foetida L. — Introduced

[SANT.11803.0]

Total: 55; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 11, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 11, Rivers 1.

Passiflora foetida var. *foetida* — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2612; 1981-10-10 [WAG.1148539]

Total: 1.

Passiflora laurifolia L. — Introduced

; -- [11844]2821273857

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Tricliceras pilosum (Willd.) R.Fern.

Raphanus pilosus Willd.

1552; -- [K000232723]

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 1, Niger 2.

Turnera ulmifolia L. — Introduced

CNF; 1977-2-16 [1849335709]

Total: 2; Enugu 1, Lagos 1.

SALICACEAE

Casearia barteri Mast.

Binuyo, A FHI 41425; 1959-8-1 [WAG.1319589]

Total: 17; Abia 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Oyo 3.

Casearia dinklagei Gilg

K. 32784.000

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Casearia inaequalis Hutch. & Dalziel

Literature

Total: 0.

Casearia prismatocarpa Mast.

Kennedy, JD 1578; -- [L.2460204]

Total: 3; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Kwara 1.

Casearia stipitata Mast.

Barter 322; -- [K000231403]

Total: 3; Kogi 1.

Dissomeria crenata Hook.f. ex Benth.

Johnstone, A.T.; FHI3313; 1935-07-24 [K003476381]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Kwara 1.

Dovyalis cameroonensis Cheek & Ngolan

Hall, J.B.; 2912; 1973-06-01 [K002240116]

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Dovyalis spinosissima Gilg — Introduced

Chapman, JD 2886; 1972-6-9 [WAG.1367617]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Dovyalis zenkeri Gilg

Stanfield, DP FHI 43521; 1960-10-26

[WAG.1367670]

Total: 13; Edo 3, Imo 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 3.

Flacourtia flavescens Willd.

Keay, R.W.J.; FHI22479; 1948-02-12 [K002241683]

Total: 20; Borno 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Flacourtia indica (Burm.f.) Merr. —

Introduced

Gmelina indica Burm.f.

L. Bernardi 8809; 1962-3-26 [US 2896777]

Total: 5; Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1.

Flacourtia vogelii Hook.f.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63303; 1970-4-5

[WAG.1367975]

Total: 10; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Homalium africanum (Hook.f.) Benth.

Blakwellia africana Hook.f.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32948; 1981-6-21

[WAG.1368198]

Total: 54; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 13, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Homalium dalzielii Hutch.

Dalziel, J.M. 1259; 1917-1-9 [K000231356]

Total: 6; Lagos 5, Oyo 1.

Homalium fulviflorum Sleumer

Catkall, R. 69; -- [K000231334]

Total: 2.

Homalium letestui Pellegr.

Onyechusim, HD; Latilo, MG FHI 54027; 1964-2-18

[WAG.1368426]

Total: 29; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 11, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Homalium longistylum Mast.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70578; 1973-3-12 [WAG.1368469]

Total: 21; Abia 3, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Homalium viridiflorum Exell

Catterall, R.; 41; 1934-08-01 [K003475010]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Oncoba brachyanthera Oliv.

Latilo, M.G.; FHI47681; 1963-06-11 [K003359341]

Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Oncoba spinosa Forssk.

Wit, P 2344 a; 1972-12-8 [WAG0117812]

Total: 24; Benue 1, Cross River 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 1.

Ophiobotrys zenkeri Gilg

Caterall, R.; 9; 1935-01-01 [K003583949]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Phyllobotryon spathulatum Müll.Arg.

Ariwaodo, JO FHI 88739; 1976-5-12 [WAG.1808162]

Total: 14; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 8, Niger 1.

Salix ledermannii Seemen

Hepper F.N. 1080; 1957-10-19 [BR0000018889819]

Total: 12; Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 5.

Salix mucronata Thunb.

Chapman, JD 3007; 1973-1-4 [WAG.1213196]

Total: 14; Kogi 2, Niger 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Salix reinii Franch. & Sav. ex Seemen —
Introduced

Keay R.W.J.; 1946-11-29 [21679]1990427746

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

VIOLACEAE

Afrohybanthus enneaspermus (L.) Flicker

Viola enneasperma L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Allexis cauliflora (Oliv.) Pierre

Alsodeia cauliflora Oliv.

Tuley, P. 690; 1964-7-13 [K000044783]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Allexis obanensis (Baker f.) Melch.

Alsodeia obanensis Baker f.

Meer, PPC van 1448; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1173955]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Pigea enneasperma (L.) P.I.Forst.

Viola enneasperma L.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70760; 1973-3-12 [WAG0232913]

Total: 53; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 2, Borno 4, Cross River 4, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 9, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Rinorea angustifolia (Thouars) Baill.

Alsodeia angustifolia Thouars

Binuyo, A FHI 41224; 1959-4-13 [WAG.1174332]

Total: 7; Cross River 3, Oyo 4.

Rinorea angustifolia subsp. *ardisiiflora*
(Oliv.) Grey-Wilson

Alsodeia ardisiiflora Welw. ex Oliv.

Binuyo A. FHI41224; 1959-04-13

[BR0000019719030]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Rinorea batesii Chipp

Obomanu, I.A.I. FHI26916; 1950-11-02

[K004437139]

Total: 12; Cross River 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ondo 4, Taraba 2.

Rinorea brachypetala (Turcz.) Kuntze

Alsodeia brachypetala Turcz.

Ndoma;J. NtuiNdoma 864; 1995-12-6 [1053113]

[1258259635]

Total: 16; Cross River 8, Edo 6, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Rinorea brevircemosa Chipp

K. Schmitt;T.O. Ibiang 378; 1995-2-8 [976750]

[1261904470]

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Niger 1, Osun 1.

Rinorea claessensii De Wild.

Meer, PPC van 1222; 1971-4-8 [WAG.1174782]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 3, Edo 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Rinorea crassifolia (Baker f.) De Wild.

Alsodeia crassifolia Baker f.

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot 1260;

1911-- [BM000541011]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Rinorea dentata (P.Beauv.) Kuntze

Ceranthera dentata P.Beauv.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 252; 1983-5-13 [WAG.1174942]

Total: 116; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Benue 1, Cross River 20, Edo 18, Ekiti 2, Imo 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 5, Osun 5, Oyo 36, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Rinorea ebolowensis M.Brandt

K. Schmitt; et al. Schmitt 457; 1995-2-19 [976815] [1261904527]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Rinorea ilicifolia (Welw. ex Oliv.) Kuntze

Alsodeia ilicifolia Welw. ex Oliv.

Pilz, GE 2667; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1870750]

Total: 22; Abia 4, Cross River 3, Edo 5, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5.

Rinorea ilicifolia subsp. *ilicifolia*

Alsodeia ilicifolia Welw. ex Oliv.

L. Bernardi 8776; 1962-3-24 [US 2896875] [2235995298]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Rinorea johnstonei (Stapf) M.Brandt

Alsodeia johnstonei Stapf

Meer, PPC van 1509; 1971-4-27 [WAG.1865618]

Total: 1.

Rinorea keayi Brenan

Savory, H.J.; Keay, R.W.J. 25206; 1948-12-29 [K000231092]

Total: 6; Cross River 6.

Rinorea kibbiensis Chipp

Binuyo A. FHI.41205; 1959-4-9 [BR0000014493799]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Rinorea lindeniana (Tul.) Kuntze —

Introduced

Alsodeia lindeniana Tul.

Bebiem 1156; 1996-1-8 [1054363] [1258261001]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Rinorea longicuspis Engl.

Ntui 739; 1995-11-01 [MO1036332]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Rinorea longisepala Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70560; 1973-3-11 [WAG.1865866]

Total: 15; Abia 7, Cross River 8.

Rinorea microdon M.Brandt

Ndoma; et al. 769; 1995-11-19 [1052196] [1258258654]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Rinorea oblongifolia (C.H.Wright)

C.Marquand ex Chipp

Pittosporum oblongifolium C.H.Wright

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67761; 1973-3-1 [WAG.1854849]

Total: 51; Abia 10, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 25, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1.

Rinorea parviflora Chipp

Percy Amaury Talbot 1391; 1911-- [BM000551647]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Rinorea pilosa Chipp — Endemic

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot s.n.; 1912-- [BM000016013]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Rinorea preussii Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70573; 1973-3-11 [WAG.1854782]

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Rinorea rubra (Tul.) Baill.

Alsodeia rubra Tul.

Richards P.W. 3066; 1935-2-3 [BR0000014501128]

Total: 5; Ogun 4, Oyo 1.

Rinorea rubrotincta Chipp

Croat 53436; 1981-11-18 [2377958] [1259686138]

Total: 39; Edo 9, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Rinorea subintegrifolia (P.Beauv.) Kuntze

Ceranthera subintegrifolia P.Beauv.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST s.n.; 1973-2-22 [WAG.1865168]

Total: 62; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 5, Benue 1, Cross River 17, Edo 14, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5.

Rinorea talbotii (Baker f.) De Wild.

Alsodeia talbotii Baker f.

Meer, PPC van 1504; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1865033]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Rinorea welwitschii (Oliv.) Kuntze

Alsodeia welwitschii Oliv.

Percy Amaury Talbot, Dorothy Amaury Talbot [BM000617966]

Total: 26; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 12, Ondo 1, Taraba 1.

Rinorea welwitschii subsp. *welwitschii*

Alsodeia welwitschii Oliv.

Kennedy J.D. 411; 1929-- [BR0000019586137]

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Rinorea yaundensis Engl.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70756; 1973-3-10 [WAG.1860966]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Ekiti 2.

Viola abyssinica Steud. ex Oliv.

Daramola, BO FHI 40637; 1959-1-24
[WAG.1860255]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Kogi 1, Taraba 1.

ACHARIACEAE

Caloncoba echinata (Oliv.) Gilg

Oncoba echinata Oliv.

1960-5-16 [2252243831]

Total: 3; Ogun 2.

Caloncoba gilgiana (Sprague) Gilg

Oncoba gilgiana Sprague

Bels, L 38; 1950-3-12 [U.1051883]

Total: 15; Lagos 12.

Caloncoba glauca (P.Beauv.) Gilg

Ventenatia glauca P.Beauv.

Onochie, CFA FHI 40269; 1958-9-7 [WAG.1319281]

Total: 46; Abia 3, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Edo 2,
Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 1,
Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Caloncoba welwitschii (Oliv.) Gilg

Oncoba welwitschii Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1712; 1971-5-19 [WAG.1319337]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Camptostylus mannii (Oliv.) Gilg

Oncoba mannii Oliv.

Ariwaodo, JO ARS 1141; -- [WAG.1319395]

Total: 7; Cross River 5, Kaduna 2.

Camptostylus ovalis (Oliv.) Chipp

Oncoba ovalis Oliv.

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C.F. 17399; --

[BR0000015348227]

Total: 1.

Dasylepis blackii (Oliv.) Chipp

Pyramidocarpus blackii Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1843; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1319977]

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2.

Dasylepis racemosa Oliv.

Van Meer P. 1843; -- [BR0000015962362]

Total: 7; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Taraba 2.

Dasylepis seretii De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Dasylepis thomasii Obama & Breteler

Talbot, P.A. (Mr.); Talbot, P.A. (Mrs.) 1274; 1911-01-01 [K004435809]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Cross River 3.

Hydnocarpus pentandrus (Buch.-Ham.)

Oken — Introduced

Chilmoria pentandra Buch.-Ham.

2252243858

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Lindackeria dentata (Oliv.) Gilg

Oncoba dentata Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1804; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1812131]

Total: 55; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 13, Edo 2, Ekiti 1,
Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Oyo 7,
Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Scottellia klaineana Pierre

Meer, PPC van 979; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1825095]

Total: 45; Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 15, Kaduna 4,
Kogi 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Scottellia orientalis Gilg

Meer, PPC van 955; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1804107]

Total: 8; Oyo 5.

HUMIRIACEAE

Sacoglottis gabonensis (Baill.) Urb.

Aubrya gabonensis Baill.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32860; 1981-6-20

[WAG.1456738]

Total: 36; Abia 2, Cross River 3, Edo 10, Lagos 1,
Oyo 5, Rivers 1.

IRVINGIACEAE

Desbordesia glaucescens (Engl.) Tiegh.

Irvingia glaucescens Engl.

Jones, A.P.D.; Onochie, C.F. ; 1946-5-11 [P00137980]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Irvingia gabonensis (Aubry-Lecomte ex

O'Rorke) Baill.

Mangifera gabonensis Aubry-Lecomte ex

O'Rorke

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63114; 1972-1-10

[WAG.1615392]

Total: 127; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 10, Cross
River 4, Delta 5, Edo 12, Ekiti 2, Enugu 5, Kaduna 1,
Kwara 4, Lagos 9, Niger 4, Ogun 9, Ondo 1, Osun 4,
Oyo 26, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Irvingia grandifolia (Engl.) Engl.

Klainedoxa grandifolia Engl.
Jones, A.P.D.; Onochie, C.F.A. ; 1946-3-18
[P00137787]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Osun 1.

Irvingia smithii Hook.f.
Daramola, BO 91/ 32; 1991-2-1 [WAG.1615275]
Total: 92; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 5, Anambra 3, Bauchi 10, Bayelsa 3, Benue 2, Borno 1, Edo 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 5, Niger 32, Ogun 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Irvingia tenuinucleata Tiegh.
Schmitt 426; 1995-2-19 [976800] [1261904520]
Total: 12; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Klainedoxa gabonensis Pierre ex Engl.
Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32701; 1981-6-15
[WAG.1615094]
Total: 45; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 2, Edo 9, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 5, Oyo 5, Taraba 2.

Klainedoxa trillesii Pierre ex Tiegh.
Coombe 180 (K)
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

LINACEAE

Hugonia afzelii R.Br. ex Planch.
Binuyo, A FHI 41272; 1959-4-1 [WAG.1058075]
Total: 6; Cross River 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Hugonia foliosa Oliv.
Literature
Total: 0.

Hugonia macrophylla Oliv.
Thomson, W.C. [K000435003]
Total: 7; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ogun 2.

Hugonia macrophylla f. *macrophylla*
Gentry 32744; 1981-6-16 [114496]
Total: 1.

Hugonia obtusifolia C.H. Wright
Meer, PPC van 1215; 1971-4-7 [WAG.1058240]
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1.

Hugonia planchonii Hook.f.
Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD 165; 1972-5-5
[WAG.1058450]
Total: 14; Anambra 3, Cross River 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Hugonia platysepala Welw. ex Oliv.

Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 72573; 1974-5-23
[WAG.1058603]
Total: 11; Cross River 2, Edo 4, Kogi 1, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Hugonia spicata Oliv.
Usang felix; 2005-10-12 [3913474429]
Total: 6; Edo 3, Lagos 1.

Hugonia spicata var. *glabrescens* Keay
Thomas, N.W. 1875; 1912-10-16 [K000435002]
Total: 2; Edo 1.

Hugonia talbotii De Wild.
Kennedy J.D. 2250; -- [BR0000017418867]
Total: 4; Cross River 1.

Linum usitatissimum L. — Introduced
; -- [UF0401143]121323593
Total: 7.

IXONANTHACEAE

Phyllocosmus africanus (Hook.f.) Klotzsch
Ochthocosmus africanus Hook.f.
Latilo, MG FHI 47694; 1963-6-22 [WAG.1059982]
Total: 8; Anambra 1, Delta 1, Enugu 4.

CALOPHYLLACEAE

Calophyllum inophyllum L. — Introduced
J. Opayemi; 1972-5-26 [821]
Total: 11; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Oyo 3.

Endodesmia calophylloides Benth.
Meer, PPC van 949; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1522232]
Total: 23; Cross River 3, Delta 2, Edo 11, Oyo 1.

Mammea africana Sabine
Kennedy J.D. 1680; -- [BR0000013623524]
Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

CLUSIACEAE

Allanblackia floribunda Oliv.
Okafor, JC; Latilo, MG FHI 57624; 1966-1-27
[WAG.1453448]
Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Allanblackia gabonensis (Pellegr.) Bamps

Allanblackia floribunda var. *gabonensis* Pellegr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Garcinia afzelii Engl.

Talbot, P. 1503; -- [K000240145]

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Osun 1, Taraba 2.

Garcinia dulcis (Roxb.) Kurz — Introduced

Xanthochymus dulcis Roxb.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1343; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1480074]

Total: 4.

Garcinia epunctata Stapf

Onochie, C.F.A.; FHI38473; 1958-06-14

[K003864178]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Garcinia huillensis Welw. ex Oliv. —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Garcinia kola Heckel

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyechusim, HD 171; 1972-5-5

[WAG.1480269]

Total: 44; Anambra 3, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 4, Osun 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Garcinia livingstonei T.Anderson

Daramola, BO; Adebuseri, JK FHI 38406; 1958-9-9

[WAG.1480309]

Total: 6; Kogi 3, Niger 1.

Garcinia mannii Oliv.

Ariwaodo, JO 676; 1977-5-1 [WAG.1480576]

Total: 19; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 10, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Garcinia oleosperma P.W.Sweeney

[N. Wanbani]; Tuley, P. 1049; 1964-11-30

[K003456318]

Total: 20; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 4, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Rivers 4.

Garcinia ovalifolia Oliv.

Geerling, C 5576; 1976-1-19 [WAG.1480707]

Total: 65; Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 9, Kaduna 14, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 4, Niger 7, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Garcinia punctata Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1646; 1971-5-15 [WAG.1480910]

Total: 12; Abia 2, Cross River 9, Oyo 1.

Garcinia quadrifaria (Oliv.) Baill. ex Pierre

Xanthochymus quadrifarius Oliv.

Onochie, CFA FHI 40401; 1958-11-8

[WAG.1481001]

Total: 10; Benue 2, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1.

Garcinia quadrifaria var. *quadrifaria*

Xanthochymus quadrifarius Oliv.

Onochie, CFA FHI 40401; 1958-11-8

[WAG.1481001]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Garcinia smeathmannii (Planch. & Triana) Oliv.

Rheedia smeathmanii Planch. & Triana

Chapman, JD 2841; 1972-5-29 [WAG.1567503]

Total: 44; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bayelsa 2, Benue 2, Cross River 5, Edo 8, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 7.

Garcinia staudtii Engl.

Binuyo, A FHI 41422; -- [WAG.1567521]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Cross River 7.

Garcinia xanthochymus Hook.f. ex

T.Anderson — Introduced

Xanthochymus pictorius Roxb.

Nicholls, C. FHI5615; 1943-08-10 [K003864195]

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Pentadesma butyracea Sabine

Ariwaodo, JO FHI 88734; 1977-5-10 [WAG.1567782]

Total: 26; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 6, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1.

Pentadesma grandifolia Baker f.

Talbot P.A. 1265; -- [BR0000015709486]

Total: 1.

Symphonia globulifera L.f.

Meer, PPC van 951; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1550691]

Total: 37; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

PODOSTEMACEAE

Ledermanniella aloides (Engl.) C.Cusset

Inversodicraea aloides Engl.

Savory, H.I.; Keay, R.W.J.F.H.I. 25150; 1948-12-24 [24187] [912020699]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Ledermanniella musciformis (G.Taylor)

C.Cusset

Inversodicraea musciformis G.Taylor

Edwards, Dr Sean R; 1978-1-7 [Kk1514]
[1933044380]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Ledermanniella raynaliorum C.Cusset

Literature

Total: 0.

Ledermanniella tenuifolia (G.Taylor)

C.Cusset

Inversodicraea tenuifolia G.Taylor

Ronald William John Keay FHI28241; 1950-12-13
[BM000910401]

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Ledermanniella variabilis (G.Taylor)

C.Cusset

Inversodicraea variabilis G.Taylor

Literature

Total: 0.

Letestuella tisserantii G.Taylor

Stanfield171; 1958-1-13 [35199] [912033979]

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Edo 1, Ogun 2.

Saxicolella flabellata (G.Taylor) C.Cusset

Pohliella flabellata G.Taylor

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28240; 1950-12-13 [K000435201]

Total: 5; Abia 2, Cross River 2.

Saxicolella marginalis (G.Taylor) C.Cusset

ex Cheek

Butumia marginalis G.Taylor

R.W.J. Keay, H.J. Savory & T.A. Russell 25152;
1948-12-25 [BM000910416]

Total: 1.

Tristicha trifaria (Bory ex Willd.) Spreng.

Dufourea trifaria Bory ex Willd.

Barter, C. [P00179243]

Total: 43; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 1,
Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Edo 1, Kaduna 2,
Kwara 1, Niger 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 9, Taraba 1.

Tristicha trifaria subsp. *pulchella* (Wedd.)

C.Cusset & G.Cusset

Tristicha hypnoides var. *pulchella* Wedd.

Barter, C. ; 1858-- [P00179173]

Total: 1.

Tristicha trifaria subsp. *trifaria*

Dufourea trifaria Bory ex Willd.

Brenan J.P.M. 8731; -- [BR0000017827621]

Total: 1.

HYPERICACEAE

Harungana madagascariensis Lam. ex Poir.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11315; 1977-4-1 [WAG.1463777]

Total: 198; Abia 3, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1,
Anambra 8, Bayelsa 1, Benue 5, Borno 1, Cross River
20, Delta 4, Edo 9, Ekiti 1, Enugu 10, Imo 2, Kaduna
5, Kogi 3, Lagos 12, Niger 3, Ogun 12, Ondo 7, Osun
11, Oyo 18, Plateau 13, Rivers 3, Taraba 8, Yobe 1.

Harungana rubescens (Oliv.) Byng &
Christenh.

Vismia rubescens Oliv.

Mr & Mrs Talbot P.A. 3296; -- [BR0000015982131]

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3.

Hypericum lalandii Choisy

Pawek J. 7990; 1974-1-26 [75342] 2013043144

Total: 3.

Hypericum lanceolatum Lam. — Introduced

Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O.; 1970-4-5

[63301]2013042658

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Hypericum peplidifolium A.Rich.

Daramola, BO FHI 40455; 1959-2-10

[WAG.1464569]

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Hypericum revolutum Vahl

Chapman J.D.2873; 1972-6-3 [46162] [2013041849]

Total: 5; Kogi 1, Taraba 3.

Hypericum revolutum subsp. *revolutum*

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63301; 1970-4-5

[WAG.1464974]

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Taraba 1.

Hypericum roeperianum G.W.Schimp. ex
A.Rich.

Hepper F.N. 1669; -- [BR0000015730503]

Total: 27; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1,
Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Plateau 5,
Taraba 9.

Psorospermum aurantiacum Engl.

Chapman, JD 2717; 1972-3-1 [WAG.1522959]

Total: 20; Benue 1, Cross River 12, Ebonyi 1, Niger 1,
Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Psorospermum corymbiferum Hochr.

Olorunfemi J. 44254; -- [BR0000015709745]

Total: 145; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 7, Bayelsa 1, Borno
2, Cross River 5, Kaduna 19, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 8,
Kwara 6, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 8, Niger 20, Ogun 6,

Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 15, Plateau 9, Sokoto 2, Taraba 9, Zamfara 2.

Psorospermum corymbiferum var.
corymbiferum

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86307;
1978-5-8 [WAG.1522992]

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2,
Kwara 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Zamfara
1.

Psorospermum corymbiferum var. *doeringii*
(Engl.) Keay & Milne-Redh.

Ibhanesebhor, G; Osanyinlusi 90; 1982-7-19
[WAG.1523017]

Total: 3; Ondo 1, Plateau 2.

Psorospermum densipunctatum Engl.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji FHI 100064; 1983-5-16
[WAG.1523023]

Total: 7; Lagos 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Psorospermum febrifugum Spach

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 90279; 1979-5-4
[WAG.1523257]

Total: 136; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 4,
Bayelsa 2, Benue 3, Borno 2, Cross River 5, Delta 1,
Edo 7, Ekiti 1, Enugu 17, Kaduna 3, Kogi 9, Kwara 2,
Lagos 1, Niger 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6,
Plateau 20, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 17, Zamfara 2.

Psorospermum glaberrimum Hochr. —

Introduced

Ohaeri A.O. check my ABU database; 13-04-1971
[ABUH]

Total: 1.

Psorospermum guineense (L.) Hochr.

Hypericum guineense L.

Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70218; 1974-5-16
[WAG.1523730]

Total: 25; Abia 2, Anambra 6, Borno 1, Cross River 3,
Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1,
Sokoto 1.

Psorospermum lanatum Hochr. —

Introduced

Seaford M.M. 7064; 1971-11 [IFE]

Total: 1.

Psorospermum senegalense Spach

Geerling, C 3478; 1971-3-21 [WAG.1523379]

Total: 2; Bauchi 2.

Psorospermum tenuifolium Hook.f.

Zubair M.F.; 2008-4-1 [108318] [2013044485]

Total: 33; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 6, Anambra 1, Bayelsa
1, Cross River 7, Ebonyi 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kwara 1,
Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Rivers 3.

FRANCOACEAE

Bersama abyssinica Fresen.

B.O.Daramola; 2008-12-1 [3280] [3808442534]

Total: 31; Cross River 8, Kaduna 1, Plateau 8, Taraba
5.

Bersama abyssinica subsp. *abyssinica* —

Introduced

Latilo, MG; Okeke, RE; Odewo, TK FHI 69368;
1974-5-21 [WAG.1100395]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Bersama abyssinica subsp. *paullinioides*

(Planch.) Verdc.

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1376; -- [K000423086]

Total: 19; Cross River 6, Kaduna 1, Plateau 4, Taraba
4.

GERANIACEAE

Geranium arabicum Forssk.

Hepper, F.N. 1664; 1958-01-13 (S)

Total: 15; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1,
Taraba 4.

Geranium arabicum subsp. *arabicum*

Hepper, F.N. 1664; 1958-01-13 (S)

Total: 4.

Geranium brevipes Hutch. & Dalziel

Geranium favosum var. *sublaeve* Oliv.

Literature

Total: 0.

Geranium ocellatum Jacquem. ex Cambess.

— Introduced

Jackson, J.K.; Magaji, S.O.; Tuley, P. 2013; 1969-11-
19 [K004317240]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Monsonia angustifolia E.Mey. ex A.Rich.

de Leeuw, P.N. MG185; 1967-10-21 (WAG)

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Monsonia senegalensis Guill. & Perr.

Ekwuno, P.O. & Fagbemi, A. 166; 1980-09-26 (FHI)

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

COMBRETACEAE

Combretum aculeatum Vent.

Denys, E 636; 1982-7-14 [WAG.1308621]
Total: 37; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 5, Borno 5, Cross River 1, Gombe 3, Jigawa 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1, Yobe 2.

Combretum acutum M.A.Lawson

Dalziel 706; 1913-5- [S-PL-23693]
Total: 5; Benue 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Combretum adenogonium Steud. ex A.Rich.

Blom-van Teyn, M van 168; 1972-7-12 [WAG.1308748]
Total: 120; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 21, Kano 6, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 9, Nasarawa 2, Niger 33, Oyo 15, Plateau 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Combretum aphanopetalum Engl. & Diels

Tuley P. 854; 12-09-1964 [K]
Total: 3; Enugu 1.

Combretum auriculatum Engl. & Diels

Coombe D.E. 113; -- [BR0000015801128]
Total: 2.

Combretum baldwinii Jongkind — Endemic

Baldwin jr, JT 13793; 1949-11-24 [WAG.1477768]
Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Combretum bauchiense Hutch. & Dalziel

Dent Young, J. 92; -- [K000232564]
Total: 8; Benue 1, Plateau 7.

Combretum bipindense Engl. & Diels

Aruwaodo J.O. 143; 17-01-1977 [FHI0088637]
Total: 1.

Combretum bracteatum (M.A.Lawson)

Engl. & Diels
Cacoucia bracteata M.A.Lawson
John D.; 1981-9-30 [1149]
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Combretum brassiciforme Exell — Endemic

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-11-20 [B 10 0153738]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Combretum collinum Fresen.

Pilz, GE 2060; 1977-5-21 [WAG.1217285]
Total: 169; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 8, Bauchi 28, Benue 4, Borno 7, Gombe 8, Kaduna 21, Kano 6, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 4, Niger 16, Ogun 3, Osun 2, Oyo 13, Plateau 4, Taraba 5.

Combretum collinum subsp. *binderianum* (Kotschy) Okafa

Kershaw K.A. 900640; 15-07-1964 [ABUH]
Total: 26; Bauchi 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Combretum collinum subsp. *geitonophyllum* (Diels) Okafa

; -- [78790]2429026361
Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 5, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5.

Combretum collinum subsp. *hypopilinum* (Diels) Okafa

Daramola, BO FHI 62663; 1969-6-4 [WAG.1217462]
Total: 54; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 2, Benue 4, Borno 2, Gombe 5, Kaduna 3, Kano 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 3, Niger 7, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Combretum comosum G.Don

Meer, PPC van 566; 1968-1-25 [WAG.1486374]
Total: 80; Abia 7, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 3, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Ogun 2, Osun 3, Oyo 23, Plateau 1, Rivers 3, Taraba 1.

Combretum comosum var. *dolichopetalum* (Engl. & Diels) Jongkind

Meer, PPC van 904; 1968-11-14 [WAG0211951]
Total: 25; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 3.

Combretum comosum var. *hispidum* (M.A.Lawson) Jongkind

Jones, A.P.D. 14595; 1946-1-8 [10559]912005485
Total: 15; Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Combretum conchipetalum Engl. & Diels

Millen, H. 7; 1891-10-9 [K000232625]
Total: 3; Lagos 2.

Combretum confertum (Benth.)

M.A.Lawson
Poivre conferta Benth.
Bebiem 831; 1995-11-28 [1052261]1258258706
Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Niger 1.

Combretum constrictum (Benth.)

M.A.Lawson
Poivre constricta Benth.
Vogel 42; -- [K000226409]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Benue 2, Kogi 3, Niger 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Combretum cuspidatum Planch. ex Benth.

Ariwaodo J.O. 679; 1977-5- [92648]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Oyo 2.

Combretum demeusei De Wild.

John D.; 1982-1-13 [1150]3460374330

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Combretum excelsum Keay — Endemic

Keay R.W.J. FHI28147; 07-12-1950 [K]

Total: 7; Cross River 6.

Combretum exellii Jongkind

Keay R.W.J.; 1950-12-7 [28147-1]1949703145

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Combretum fuscum Planch. ex Benth.

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO FHI 71047; 1974-1-1 [WAG0013509]

Total: 18; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 2, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Lagos 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 3.

Combretum glutinosum Perr. ex DC.

McElderry J.C.K. ; 1944-3-2 [7637-1]

Total: 73; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 6, Borno 3, Kaduna 5, Kano 10, Katsina 4, Niger 14, Oyo 2, Plateau 7, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 13.

Combretum grandiflorum G.Don

Leeuwenberg A.J.M. 4041; 1963-4-28 [14216]1949702957

Total: 4; Lagos 1.

Combretum homalioides Hutch. & Dalziel

Barter, C 1803; -- [U.1224305]

Total: 7; Anambra 3, Delta 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Combretum indicum (L.) DeFilipps — Introduced

Quisqualis indica L.

Pilz, GE 2270; 1978-3-5 [WAG0211810]

Total: 43; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Niger 6, Ogun 10, Ondo 1, Oyo 8.

Combretum latialatum Engl.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65812; 1972-6-4 [WAG0032260]

Total: 43; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Benue 2, Cross River 4, Edo 23, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.

Combretum mannii G.Lawson ex Engl. & Diels

Baldwin J.T. 13782; 20-11-1949 [K]

Total: 2; Abia 1.

Combretum marginatum Engl. & Diels

Gentry 32894; 1981-6-21 [306415]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Combretum micranthum G.Don

Magaji, SO; Leeuw, PN de 141; 1967-8-4 [WAG0041806]

Total: 55; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 3, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 12, Katsina 7, Kwara 1, Niger 8, Oyo 2, Sokoto 8, Zamfara 4.

Combretum molle R.Br. ex G.Don

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1610; 1972-4-29 [WAG0033160]

Total: 108; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 11, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 21, Kano 1, Katsina 6, Kogi 1, Kwara 5, Niger 12, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 5, Sokoto 5, Taraba 7, Yobe 3, Zamfara 5.

Combretum mucronatum Schumach. & Thonn.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70730; 1973-3-8 [WAG.1559688]

Total: 99; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 6, Edo 1, Ekiti 4, Enugu 5, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 9, Ogun 9, Ondo 2, Osun 6, Oyo 35, Plateau 1.

Combretum nigricans Lepr. ex Guill. & Perr.

Wit, P 495; 1971-9-29 [WAG.1559800]

Total: 126; Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 29, Benue 2, Edo 1, Gombe 4, Kaduna 3, Kogi 7, Kwara 5, Niger 10, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 20, Plateau 1, Sokoto 14, Taraba 1, Zamfara 6.

Combretum nigricans var. *elliottii* (Engl. & Diels) Aubrév.

Wit, P; Wit, J 1168; 1972-2-1 [WAG0033205]

Total: 77; Bauchi 20, Edo 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 14, Sokoto 9, Zamfara 4.

Combretum obangense (Baker f.) Hutch. & Dalziel

Combretum paucinervium var. *obangense* Baker f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Combretum paniculatum Vent.

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO 26; 1980-2-26 [WAG.1253996]

Total: 98; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 6, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 5, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Ogun 6, Osun 2, Oyo 39, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Combretum paucinervium Engl. & Diels — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Combretum pecoense Exell — Introduced
Keay, R.W.J. FHI28147; 1950-12-7 [K000232557]

Total: 12; Cross River 6.

Combretum pellegrinianum Exell

Literature

Total: 0.

Combretum platypterum (Welw.) Hutch. & Dalziel

Cacoucia platyptera Welw.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 332; 1983-5-17 [WAG.1254320]

Total: 117; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 4, Borno 1, Cross River 9, Delta 2, Edo 7, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Lagos 11, Ogun 15, Ondo 7, Osun 2, Oyo 30, Rivers 1.

Combretum racemosum P.Beauv.

Chapman, JD 2975; 1972-12-19 [WAG.1254624]

Total: 92; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 6, Oyo 35, Rivers 1, Taraba 10.

Combretum riggenbachianum Gilg & Ledermann ex Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Combretum schumannii Engl. — Introduced
Apejoye F. I.; 2002-11-7 [1153]3460374329

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Combretum sericeum G.Don

Jackson, G 311272/ 1; 1972-12-31 [WAG.1254708]

Total: 55; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 11, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Niger 7, Oyo 5, Plateau 7, Taraba 3.

Combretum sordidum Exell

Onochie C.F.A. 8861; 1948-1-21 [36179A]

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Edo 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6.

Combretum zenkeri Engl. & Diels

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 69; 1977-10-4 [WAG.1254956]

Total: 62; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 6, Osun 6, Oyo 25.

Combretum zeyheri Sond.

Literature

Total: 0.

Conocarpus erectus L.

Okafor J.C.; 1966-8-11 [60312]1944995099

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 1.

Guiera senegalensis J.F.Gmel.

Denys, E 833; 1982-8-5 [WAG.1477904]

Total: 97; Adamawa 6, Bauchi 14, Benue 1, Borno 10, Gombe 2, Kaduna 21, Kano 8, Katsina 4, Niger 1, Sokoto 7, Yobe 3, Zamfara 3.

Laguncularia racemosa (L.) C.F.Gaertn.

Conocarpus racemosus L.

Gbile Z.O.; 1980-3-19 [93030]1944999581

Total: 18; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Rivers 9.

Strephonema mannii Benth. & Hook.f.

Mann, G. 2293; 1863-2- [K000226278]

Total: 12; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 8.

Terminalia albida Scott Elliot

Croat 53354; 1981-11-14 [2377821]1259686001

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Terminalia anogeissiana Gere & Boatwr. — Introduced

Conocarpus latifolius Roxb. ex DC.

; -- [78709]2429026628

Total: 4.

Terminalia avicennioides Guill. & Perr.

Pilz, GE 1889; 1976-12-28 [WAG.1478497]

Total: 232; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 11, Benue 1, Borno 5, Edo 2, Kaduna 41, Kano 4, Katsina 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 13, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 4, Niger 65, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 24, Plateau 8, Sokoto 4, Taraba 4, Yobe 1, Zamfara 12.

Terminalia bellirica (Gaertn.) Roxb. —

Introduced

Myrobalanus bellirica Gaertn.

TKO 2002; 1979-12-11 [92048]1944999481

Total: 4; Kano 3, Ogun 1.

Terminalia brownii Fresen.

Wit, P 1755; 1972-5-4 [WAG0369626]

Total: 18; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Terminalia calamansanai (Blanco) Rolfe —
Introduced

Gimbernatia calamansanai Blanco
Akariagbo Olugbemi; 2016-11-10 [7425]3808439639
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Terminalia catappa L. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1565; 1966-5-26 [WAG.1478718]
Total: 51; Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 24, Ogun 7, Ondo 1, Oyo 15.

Terminalia elliptica Willd. — Introduced
Onyeachusim H.D.; 1963-10-19 [47633-1]1949704381
Total: 1.

Terminalia engleri Gere & Boatwr.
Pteleopsis suberosa Engl. & Diels
Geerling, C 3099; 1970-10-28 [WAG.1478207]
Total: 40; Bauchi 5, Kaduna 3, Kwara 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Oyo 6, Plateau 3.

Terminalia habeensis (Aubrév. ex Keay)
Gere & Boatwr.
Pteleopsis habeensis Aubrév. ex Keay
Geerling, C 3528; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1478063]
Total: 29; Bauchi 25, Plateau 1.

Terminalia hylodendron (Mildbr.) Gere &
Boatwr.
Pteleopsis hylodendron Mildbr.
Gbile Z.O.; 1984-6-12 [101391]1945000850
Total: 3; Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kwara 1.

Terminalia ivorensis A.Chev.
Onochie C.F.A. ; 1954-10-30 [34660]
Total: 39; Cross River 2, Edo 6, Enugu 6, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Terminalia laeteviridis Gilg & Ledermann
ex Engl.
Literature
Total: 0.

Terminalia laxiflora Engl.
Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70708; 1973-3-5 [WAG.1191529]
Total: 164; Adamawa 11, Bauchi 33, Benue 4, Borno 2, Enugu 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 15, Katsina 3, Kogi 5, Kwara 4, Niger 3, Ogun 8, Ondo 2, Oyo 10, Plateau 30, Sokoto 2, Taraba 14, Zamfara 2.

Terminalia leiocarpa (DC.) Baill.
Conocarpus leiocarpus DC.
Pilz, GE 2252; 1977-12-27 [WAG.1308505]

Total: 116; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 7, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Delta 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 11, Kano 6, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 1, Niger 11, Ogun 4, Oyo 15, Plateau 3, Sokoto 9, Taraba 2, Zamfara 4.

Terminalia macroptera Guill. & Perr.
Wit, P; Geerling, C 1281; 1972-3-19 [WAG.1191590]
Total: 23; Benue 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kwara 4, Niger 8, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Terminalia mollis M.A.Lawson
; 2007-2-13 [FR-0034732]
Total: 2; Kaduna 2.

Terminalia neotaliala Capuron —
Introduced
Literature
Total: 0.

Terminalia pennyana Anozie — Endemic
Anozie, V C; Ozioko, A; Akaelu, A. U139A; 1993-5-17 [E00021696]
Total: 3; Enugu 3.

Terminalia prunioides M.A.Lawson —
Introduced
Literature
Total: 0.

Terminalia randii Baker f. — Introduced
OkoyeI M.; 2014-12-19 [110282]1945002147
Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Terminalia schimperiana Hochst
Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 536; 1978-5-30 [WAG.1191330]
Total: 77; Adamawa 2, Anambra 3, Benue 4, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Enugu 3, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 10, Ogun 7, Ondo 5, Osun 3, Oyo 8, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Terminalia sericea Burch. ex DC. —
Introduced
Ugwuzor P.O. ; 2010-6-20 [65B]1990271887
Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Terminalia superba Engl. & Diels
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11278; 1977-3-28 [WAG.1192108]
Total: 77; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 18, Enugu 3, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 7, Oyo 18, Zamfara 1.

LYTHRACEAE

Ammannia angustifolia (A.Fern. & Diniz)
S.A.Graham & Gandhi

Nesaea angustifolia A.Fern. & Diniz
Keay R.W.J.; 1950-7-5 [25929]1990428185
Total: 3; Kaduna 2, Katsina 1.

Ammannia auriculata Willd.

Barter C [WAG.U.1362819]
Total: 59; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 5, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Gombe 4, Imo 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 4.

Ammannia auriculata var. *auriculata*

Daramola B.O. FHI63702; 1970-12-2
[BR0000016861398]
Total: 1.

Ammannia baccifera L.

Magaji, SO 89; 1965-12-2 [WAG.1070606]
Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Ammannia erecta (Guill. & Perr.)

S.A.Graham & Gandhi
Nesaea erecta Guill. & Perr.
Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O.; 1970-11-23
[63640]1990431231
Total: 13; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Ammannia gracilis Guill. & Perr.

B.O. Daramola & Josephine FHI63668; --
[BR0000016862357]
Total: 3; Borno 3.

Ammannia involucreta S.A.Graham & Gandhi

Nesaea cordata Hiern
Gbile Z.O.; Olorunfemi J.; 1968-10-19 [20491]
Total: 3; Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Ammannia mossiensis (A.Chev.)

S.A.Graham & Gandhi
Nesaea mossiensis A.Chev.
Keay, R.W.J. FHI25888; 1950-06-21 [K004330575]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Katsina 1.

Ammannia prieuriana Guill. & Perr.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 51; 1979-4-20
[WAG.1070673]
Total: 16; Borno 2, Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.

Ammannia radicans (Guill. & Perr.)

S.A.Graham & Gandhi
Nesaea radicans Guill. & Perr.
Latilo M.G. ; 1968-11-20 [62506]1990431188
Total: 3; Kwara 3.

Ammannia senegalensis Lam.

B.O. Daramola & Josephine [BR0000016863842]
Total: 9; Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kebbi 1.

Ammannia senegalensis var. *senegalensis*

B.O. Daramola & Josephine FHI63667; --
[BR0000016863842]
Total: 1.

Cuphea bustamanta Lex.

Usang felix ; 2005-10-13 [27.0]
Total: 1.

Lagerstroemia indica L. — Introduced

Magaji, SO s.n.; 1965-3-24 [WAG.1070892]
Total: 21; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Oyo 6.

Lagerstroemia loudonii Teijsm. & Binn. —

Introduced
Nsukaba N.F.; 2010-5-28 [497]
Total: 5; Lagos 5.

Lagerstroemia speciosa (L.) Pers. —

Introduced
Munchausia speciosa L.
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63144; 1972-1-31
[WAG.1070904]
Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 13.

Lagerstroemia tomentosa C.Presl —

Introduced
PW.90; 1971-8-24 [27770]1990428441
Total: 8; Enugu 1, Oyo 6.

Lawsonia inermis L. — Introduced

Chapman, JD FHI 62107; 1973-9-12 [WAG.1070962]
Total: 52; Kaduna 8, Kano 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Niger 7, Ogun 8, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Punica granatum L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1897; 1966-7-1 [WAG.1337081]
Total: 4; Oyo 3.

Rotala filiformis (Bellardi) Hiern

Suffrenia filiformis Bellardi
Keay, R.W.J.; FHI20130; 1947-10-20 [K004761497]
Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1.

Rotala gossweileri Koehne
Meikle R.D. 1040; 1950-1-17 [BR0000016869257]
Total: 3; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Rotala mexicana Schltdl. & Cham.
Hepper, F.N.; 1252; 1957-11-07 [K004761438]
Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Rotala stagnina Hiern
Olorunfemi J. 24400; -- [BR0000016869967]
Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 5,
Kwara 1, Niger 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Rotala tenella (Guill. & Perr.) Hiern
Ammannia tenella Guill. & Perr.

Literature
Total: 0.

Rotala welwitschii Exell
Dalziel, J.M.; 210; 1909-11-07 [K004761474]
Total: 3; Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Trapa natans L.
68120; 1974-11-25 [68120]2302319556
Total: 8; Kaduna 5, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Trapa natans var. *bispinosa* (Roxb.) Makino
; -- [B 18 0009881] [178154684]
Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Oyo 2.

Woodfordia uniflora (A.Rich.) Koehne
Grislea uniflora A.Rich.
Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1736; 1972-5-4
[WAG.1071494]
Total: 6; Adamawa 3, Borno 2, Ondo 1.

ONAGRACEAE

Epilobium platystigmatosum C.B.Rob. —
Introduced
Fagbemi; Osanyinlusi FO 29; 1977-2-19
[82816]2013043473
Total: 1; Niger 1.

Epilobium salignum Hausskn.
Daramola B.O.; 1968-12-10 [62438] [1990431190]
Total: 8; Plateau 1, Taraba 7.

Fuchsia × *standishii* J.Harrison
Jackson J.K. 5371; 1967-06-03 [17791.0]
Total: 1.

Ludwigia abyssinica A.Rich.
Daramola, BO FHI 85483; 1977-8-17
[WAG.1128629]
Total: 81; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa
Ibom 2, Bauchi 5, Bayelsa 2, Benue 1, Cross River 4,

Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Enugu 4, Gombe 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 5,
Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger
5, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Oyo 3, Plateau 4, Rivers 2, Sokoto
1, Taraba 6, Zamfara 1.

Ludwigia adscendens subsp. *adscendens*
Jussiaea adscendens L.
Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 405; 1971-9-19
[WAG.1128667]
Total: 1.

Ludwigia adscendens subsp. *diffusa*
(Forssk.) P.H.Raven
Jussiaea adscendens L.

Wit.P; Daramola B.O.2627; 1973-4-11 [78200]
[1990432164]
Total: 43; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 3,
Bayelsa 2, Borno 4, Delta 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1,
Kano 1, Kebbi 4, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger
5, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 3, Taraba 1, Yobe
1.

Ludwigia affinis (DC.) H.Hara
Jussiaea affinis DC.
Wogu, A.; Ugborogho, R.E. 176; 1995-09-22
[K003852495]
Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Ludwigia africana (Brenan) H.Hara
Jussiaea africana Brenan
Lowe J.; 1968-1-17 [26127] [2013040961]
Total: 2; Edo 1.

Ludwigia decurrens Walter — Introduced
Odewo, TK s.n.; 1974-2-1 [WAG.1128757]
Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 11,
Edo 2, Imo 3, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1,
Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1.

Ludwigia erecta (L.) H.Hara — Introduced
Jussiaea erecta L.
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65871; 1972-10-10
[WAG.1128789]
Total: 101; Abia 1, Bauchi 6, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross
River 11, Delta 1, Edo 4, Gombe 1, Imo 5, Jigawa 1,
Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 8,
Ogun 15, Ondo 2, Osun 5, Oyo 11, Plateau 1, Sokoto
1, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Ludwigia hyssopifolia (G.Don) Exell —
Introduced
Jussiaea hyssopifolia G.Don

Leeuw, PN de 1283; 1964-10-19 [WAG.1128842]
Total: 34; Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Cross River 2,
Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna
2, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4,

Nasarawa 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Ludwigia leptocarpa (Nutt.) H.Hara

Jussiaea leptocarpa Nutt.

Dawodu T.; 1907-08-02 [BR0000019093802]

Total: 67; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 4, Edo 9, Enugu 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kebbi 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Yobe 4.

Ludwigia leptocarpa subsp. *leptocarpa*

Jussiaea leptocarpa Nutt.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 308; 1977-10-12 [WAG.1128928]

Total: 1.

Ludwigia octovalvis (Jacq.) P.H.Raven —

Introduced

Oenothera octovalvis Jacq.

Jones A.P.D.; 1943-04-02 [FHI.3110.0]

Total: 122; Abia 2, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 3, Bauchi 4, Benue 5, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 9, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 2, Lagos 14, Nasarawa 1, Niger 18, Ogun 11, Ondo 2, Oyo 10, Sokoto 3, Taraba 5.

Ludwigia octovalvis subsp. *brevisepala* (Brenan) P.H.Raven

Jussiaea suffruticosa var. *brevisepala* Brenan

Hepper, FN 1637; 1957-1-1 [WAG.1129077]

Total: 31; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7, Ogun 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 3.

Ludwigia octovalvis subsp. *octovalvis*

Oenothera octovalvis Jacq.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 23890; 1970-3-25 [WAG.1129014]

Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 2, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Niger 3, Ogun 2.

Ludwigia octovalvis subsp. *sessiliflora*

(Micheli) P.H.Raven — Introduced

Jussiaea octonervia f. *sessiliflora* Micheli

Gillett, J.B. 15236; 1962-07-28 [K003852350]

Total: 18; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Ebonyi 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Ludwigia perennis L.

599; 1979-11-6 [599]2302319582

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Ludwigia senegalensis (DC.) Troch.

Prieurea senegalensis DC.

Daramola B.O.; Josephine; 1970-11-28 [63655] [2013042682]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Ludwigia stenorraphe (Brenan) H.Hara

Jussiaea stenorraphe Brenan

Odewo T.K.; Adedeji OA71; 1981-12-14 [96876]

Total: 66; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 5, Kaduna 19, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Ludwigia stenorraphe subsp. *stenorraphe*

Jussiaea stenorraphe Brenan

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 73622; 1974-11-22 [WAG.1129217]

Total: 3; Borno 1, Taraba 1.

VOCHYSIACEAE

Erismadelphus exsul Mildbr.

Robson, M.; 1027; 1936-04-24 [21826.000]

Total: 18; Abia 5, Cross River 4, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Oyo 2.

Erismadelphus exsul var. *platyphyllus* Keay & Stafleu

Amachi, JO FHI 24313; 1951-9-15 [U.1770680]

Total: 6; Abia 4, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1.

MYRTACEAE

Corymbia citriodora (Hook.) K.D.Hill &

L.A.S.Johnson — Introduced

Eucalyptus citriodora Hook.

Ohaeri A.O. 2886; 28-03-1990 [ABUH]

Total: 4; Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Oyo 1.

Corymbia torelliana (F.Muell.) K.D.Hill &

L.A.S.Johnson — Introduced

Eucalyptus torelliana F.Muell.

Latilo, MG FHI 27601; 1950-7-26 [WAG.1114936]

Total: 10; Anambra 4, Enugu 3, Kwara 1.

Eucalyptus alba Reinw. ex Blume —

Introduced

Emiwogbon, J.A. FHI47161 [K005299178]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Eucalyptus amygdalina Labill. —

Introduced

Unwin, A.H. 23; 1913-12-11 [K005299176]

Total: 2; Niger 1, Rivers 1.

Eucalyptus camaldulensis Dehnh. —

Introduced

Chapman, JD 2526; 1971-9-10 [WAG.1114498]

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Taraba 2.

Eucalyptus deglupta Blume — Introduced

Wit P. 77; 1971-8-24 [BR0000017922005]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Eucalyptus globulus Labill. — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2011-1-31 [87A]1990271946

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Eucalyptus grandis W.Hill ex Maiden —

Introduced

Chapman, J.D. 2500 [K005299165]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Eucalyptus robusta Sm. — Introduced

Ohaeri A.O. 3254; 04-02-1991 [ABUH]

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Eucalyptus saligna Sm. — Introduced

Etkin 151; 1987-11-18 [310698]1260489925

Total: 2; Kano 2.

Eucalyptus tereticornis Sm. — Introduced

Ohaeri A.O. 2511; 30-05-1988 [ABUH]

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Lagos 2.

Eugenia buchholzii Engl.

Tuley, P.; Magajie, O.S. 2188; 1971-3-5

[K001000583]

Total: 10; Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Eugenia calophylloides DC.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 33173; 1953-5-15

[K001000755]

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 2, Kebbi 4, Kogi 6.

Eugenia coronata Vahl ex DC.

Onochie, C.F.; Jones, A.P.D.; Keay, R.W.J. 4903; --

[K001000567]

Total: 2; Lagos 1, Ogun 1.

Eugenia gilgii Engl. & Brehmer

Chapman, JD 3042; 1973-3-19 [WAG.1115325]

Total: 29; Adamawa 4, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Niger 2, Plateau 7, Rivers 1, Taraba 6.

Eugenia kerstingii Engl. & Brehmer

Fotius, G. 2023; 1974-6-16 [K001000555]

Total: 13; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Niger 6, Plateau 1.

Eugenia ledermannii Engl. & Brehmer

Hepper F.N. 1989; 1958-2-14 [BR0000017927840]

Total: 3; Enugu 2.

Eugenia obanensis Baker f.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 46801; 1972-4-13

[WAG.1115547]

Total: 63; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 9, Edo 4, Enugu 4, Imo 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 9, Niger 3, Ondo 6, Oyo 5, Plateau 4.

Eugenia staudtii Engl. & Brehmer

Hergerup, O. M763A; 1927-12-14 [K001000782]

Total: 2; Niger 2.

Eugenia talbotii Keay — Endemic

Talbot P.A. 203; 1911-- [BM000902361]

Total: 1.

Eugenia tisserantii Aubrév. & Pellegr. —

Introduced

Jones A.P.D. 6199; 1942-12-20 [K001000783]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Eugenia uniflora L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1449; 1966-4-24 [WAG.1115731]

Total: 6; Lagos 1, Oyo 3.

Melaleuca citrina (Curtis) Dum.Cours. —

Introduced

Metrosideros citrina Curtis

781; 1971-11-16 [781]2302319862

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Melaleuca leucadendra (L.) L. —

Introduced

Myrtus leucadendra L.

2511; 1981-6-11 [2511] [2302319501]

Total: 4; Kaduna 3, Lagos 1.

Pimenta racemosa var. *racemosa* —

Introduced

Caryophyllus racemosus Mill.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1852; 1966-8-23 [WAG.1116375]

Total: 1.

Psidium guajava L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1458; 1966-5-2 [WAG.1116470]

Total: 16; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 2.

Syzygium congolense Vermeesen

Schmitt 390; 1995-2-8 [976754] [1261904465]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Syzygium cumini (L.) Skeels — Introduced

Myrtus cumini L.

1008; 1950-1-18 [BR0000017296007]

Total: 1.

Syzygium gerrardii (Harv. ex Hook.f.) Burt
Davy — Introduced

Acmena gerrardii Harv. ex Hook.f.
900127; 1974-2-12 [900127]2302319844
Total: 3; Kaduna 3.

Syzygium guineense (Willd.) DC.

Calyptanthes guineensis Willd.
Leeuw, PN de H s.n.; 1961-3-31 [WAG.1116966]
Total: 39; Bauchi 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 8, Kogi 2,
Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 10,
Taraba 1.

Syzygium guineense subsp. *guineense*

Calyptanthes guineensis Willd.
Leeuw, PN de H s.n.; 1961-3-31 [WAG.1116966]
Total: 12; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1,
Niger 2, Plateau 3.

Syzygium jambos (L.) Alston — Introduced

Eugenia jambos L.
Lawal Olasunmbo LUH672; 2004-09-11
[3460378354]
Total: 1.

Syzygium littorosum Byng

Syzygium guineense var. *littorale* Keay
Meer, PPC van 953; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1117233]
Total: 1.

Syzygium malaccense (L.) Merr. &

L.M.Perry — Introduced
Eugenia malaccensis L.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1875; 1966-8-23 [WAG.1115457]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Syzygium owariense (P.Beauv.) Benth.

Eugenia owariensis P.Beauv.
Lowe, J 1956; 1970-1-4 [WAG.1117452]
Total: 5; Edo 2, Rivers 1.

Syzygium pratense Byng — Introduced

Syzygium guineense var. *macrocarpum* Engl.
Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70687; 1973-3-2
[WAG.1117272]
Total: 1.

Syzygium rowlandii Sprague

Rowland, J.W. 4/1890; -- [K000312596]
Total: 2; Lagos 2.

MELASTOMATACEAE

Amphiblemma mildbraedii Gilg ex Engl.

Lely H.V. 544; 20-08-1921 [K]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Antherotoma irvingiana (Hook.) Jacq.-Fél.

Dissotis irvingiana Hook.
Irving 119 [K000313116] syn Type.
Total: 46; Anambra 3, Borno 3, Edo 5, Enugu 1,
Gombe 3, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1,
Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 1,
Taraba 2.

Antherotoma naudinii Hook.f.

Osbeckia antherotoma Naudin
Eijnatten, CLM van 2086; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1090842]
Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1,
Niger 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Antherotoma phaeotricha (Hochst.) Naudin

Osbeckia phaeotricha Hochst.
Lely H.V. 447; 19-07-1921 [K]
Total: 11; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 1,
Plateau 1.

Argyrella amplexicaulis (Jacq.-Fél.) Ver.-

Lib. & G. Kadereit
Dissotis amplexicaulis Jacq.-Fél.
Wimbush S.H. FHI39612; 1956-11 [K001381304]
Total: 1.

Argyrella bambutorum (Gilg & Ledermann
ex Engl.) Ver.-Lib. & G.Kadereit

Dissotis bambutorum Gilg & Ledermann ex
Engl.
Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 62864; 1970-3-31
[WAG.1091753]
Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Argyrella canescens (E.Mey. ex Graham)

Harv.
Osbeckia canescens E.Mey. ex Graham
Latilo, MG FHI 64737; 1971-12-3 [WAG.1091921]
Total: 25; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Imo 1, Jigawa 1,
Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Plateau 9, Taraba 3.

Derosiphia tubulosa (Sm.) Raf.

Osbeckia tubulosa Sm.
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65872; 1972-10-10
[WAG.1094888]
Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kogi 2,
Nasarawa 2, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.

Dicellandra barberi Hook.f.

Brenan, J.P.M.9006; 1948-2-13 [8611] [912077081] --
> better to cite Barter 2113 (K), which was part of the
original material.
Total: 15; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7, Edo 3,
Plateau 1.

Dicellandra barberi var. *barberi*

Ujor E. FHI30151; 19-05-1952 [K]

Total: 1.

Dicellandra barteri var. *erecta* Mildbr. ex Jacq.-Fél.

Meer, PPC van 1429; 1971-4-22 [WAG.1091334]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dichaetanthera africana (Hook.f.) Jacq.-Fél.

Sakersia africana Hook.f.

Kennedy J.D. 2045; -- [BR0000017284400]

Total: 17; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 9.

Dinophora spenneroides Benth.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32883; 1981-6-20

[WAG.1091693]

Total: 21; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Borno 3, Cross River 6, Edo 3, Kogi 2.

Dinophora spenneroides subsp. *spenneroides*

Binuyo 45412; 1961-11-18 [100942978]

[2268843472]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dissotis grandiflora (Sm.) Benth.

Osbeckia grandiflora Sm.

N.N. Sanford 6640; 1968-7-3 [101368375]

[3946812506]

Total: 16; Kaduna 6, Niger 2, Plateau 4.

Dissotis grandiflora var. *lambii* (Hutch.) Keay

Dissotis lambii Hutch.

Lamb 58 1914-10-1 [K000313123] (the Holotype specimen).

Total: 10; Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Plateau 4.

Dissotis idanreensis Brenan — Endemic

Brenan, Prof. J.P.M.; Keat, R.W.J. 8694; 1948-01-03 [K000313129] (Holotype with material in K, B, BR, FHI & P).

Total: 18; Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Niger 2, Ondo 8, Oyo 1.

Dissotis longisetosa Gilg & Ledermann ex Engl.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 215; 1977-10-8

[WAG.1935048]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dupineta multiflora (Sm.) Raf.

Osbeckia multiflora Sm.

Timmerman-van der Slesesen, EHL 2; 1960-7-1

[WAG.1934911]

Total: 7; Kogi 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Feliciotis perkinsiae (Gilg) Ver.-Lib. & G.Kadereit

Dissotis perkinsiae Gilg

Daramola, BO D 200; 1977-8-25 [WAG.1934862]

Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 8.

Guyonia ciliata Hook.f.

Medler, J. 900; 1973-08-18 [K002834906]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Guyonia cinerascens (Hutch.) Ver.-Lib. & R.D.Stone

Dissotis cinerascens Hutch.

Daramola, BO FHI 62704; 1969-5-14

[WAG.1091924]

Total: 12; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Heterotis decumbens (P.Beauv.) Jacq.-Fél.

Melastoma decumbens P.Beauv.

Palisot de Beauvois s.n. in 1786-7 [G barcode G00014591] Type.

Total: 3; Bayelsa 1, Kaduna 1.

Heterotis fruticosa (Brenan) Ver.-Lib. & G.Kadereit — Endemic

Dissotis rotundifolia var. *fruticosa* Brenan

Keay, R.W.J. 22569; 1948-9-21 [K000313153]

Total: 13; Ondo 12, Taraba 1.

Heterotis prostrata (Thonn.) Benth.

Melastoma prostratum Thonn.

Latilo, MG FHI 67746; 1973-3-1 [WAG.1092461]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Heterotis rotundifolia (Sm.) Jacq.-Fél.

Osbeckia rotundifolia Sm.

Latilo & Fagemi 67514 [K002834323]

Total: 73; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 11, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 6, Plateau 5, Rivers 5, Taraba 1.

Lijndenia barteri (Hook.f.) K.Bremer

Memecylon barteri Hook.f.

Barter 2152 [K000230003]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 2, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Melastomastrum capitatum (Vahl) A.Fern. & R.Fern.

Melastoma capitatum Vahl

Pilz, GE 2670; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1093281]

Total: 29; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 6, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Melastomastrum segregatum (Benth.)

A.Fern. & R.Fern.

Heterotis segregata Benth.

Vogel 12 [K000313204] Lectotype; iso-:
[K000313208]

Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Edo 1, Imo 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Niger 3.

Melastomastrum theifolium (G.Don) A.Fern. & R.Fern.

Melastoma theifolium G.Don

Daramola, BO; Okoro, M 59; 1982-11-2
[WAG.1092583]

Total: 36; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Melastomastrum theifolium var. *theifolium*

Melastoma theifolium G.Don

Onochie 34110; 1953-09-25 [K12258.000]

Total: 0; Anambra 1.

Memecylon accedens R.D.Stone, Ghogue & Cheek

Memecylon afzelii var. *amoenum* Jacq.-Fél.

Latilo FHI 18232 [K, UPS].

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Ogun 1.

Memecylon afzelii G.Don

Tamajong FHI 20985 [K004411259].

Total: 15; Cross River 5, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Oyo 1.

Memecylon candidum Gilg

Talbot P.A. 696; 1911- [K]

Total: 2.

Memecylon dasyanthum Gilg & Ledermann ex Engl.

Chapman 4530 (K)

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Memecylon englerianum Cogn.

Meer, PPC van 1250; 1971-4-9 [WAG.1093688]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.

Memecylon lateriflorum (G.Don) Bremek.

Pavetta lateriflora G.Don

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1606; -- [K000242820]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Memecylon mamfeanum (Jacq.-Fél.)

R.D.Stone, Ghogue & Cheek

Memecylon afzelii var. *mamfeanum* Jacq.-Fél.

van Meer 1439 [WAG.1093447]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Memecylon normandii Jacq.-Fél.

Latilo, M.G. FHI 47678; 1963-6-10 [K000904003]

Total: 4; Abia 1, Edo 1, Kogi 1.

Memecylon occultum Jacq.-Fél.

Thornewill A.S. 218; 1920-1 [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Imo 1.

Memecylon viride Hutch. & Dalziel

Talbot 496 [BM] Type collection from s. Nigeria.

Total: 5; Cross River 3.

Memecylon zenkeri Gilg

Mann G. 2285; -- [BR0000019020037]

Total: 8; Abia 2, Cross River 4.

Myrianthemum mirabile Gilg

Talbot 587 & Talbot 1325.

Total: 1.

Nerophila congolensis (Cogn. ex Büttner)

Ver.-Lib. & R.D.Stone

Osbeckia congolensis Cogn. ex Büttner

Chapman H.M. 41; 01-08-1973 [K] --> 2025.10.13, the material in K is correctly identified.

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Phaeoneuron dicellandroides Gilg

Meikle & Keay 553 (BR, K)

Total: 1.

Rosettea elliotii (Gilg) Ver.-Lib. & G.

Kadereit

Dissotis elliotii Gilg

Tuley 1933 (K)

Total: 10; Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Rosettea riparia (Gilg & Ledermann ex Engl.) Ver.-Lib. & G.Kadereit

Dissotis riparia Gilg & Ledermann ex Engl.

Chapman, J.D. 5040; 1977-10-30 [K000461805]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Rosettea scabra (Gilg) Ver.-Lib. &

G.Kadereit

Dissotis scabra Gilg

Daramola, BO FHI 62906; 1969-5-23
[WAG.1092016]

Total: 27; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 5, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Rosettea thollonii (Cogn.) Ver.-Lib. &

G.Kadereit

Dissotis thollonii Cogn.
 Hepper, FN 1660; 1958-1-1 [WAG.1092536]
 Total: 12; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Spathandra blackioides (G.Don) Jacq.-Fél.
 Memecylon blackioides G.Don
 Meer, PPC van 947; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1093577]
 Total: 1.

Spathandra blakeoides var. *blakeoides*

Tristemma akeassii Jacq.-Fél.
 Keay R.W.J. FHI42032; 09-04-1958 [K]
 Total: 4; Edo 2, Ogun 1.

Tristemma hirtum P.Beauv.
 Palisot de Beauvois s.n. [holo-, [G00014629]; iso-: P-JU 14112], from s. Nigeria.
 Total: 35; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Rivers 3, Taraba 3.

Tristemma littorale Benth.
 Emwiogbon, JA 200; 1972-5-30 [WAG.1095448]
 Total: 26; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Imo 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Oyo 4.

Tristemma littorale subsp. *biafranum* Jacq.-Fél.
 Meer, PPC van 1130; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1095469]
 Total: 3; Abia 1, Cross River 2.

Tristemma littorale subsp. *littorale*

Tristemma mauritianum J.F.Gmel.
 Elliott 240, Keay FHI 13774 (both presumably in K).
 Total: 23; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Tristemma mauritianum var. *mauritianum*
 Onyeachusim; Latilo M.G. FHI54052; 21-02-1964 [K]
 Total: 19; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Tristemma mauritianum var. *mildbraedii* (Gilg) Jacq.-Fél.
 Tristemma mildbraedii Gilg
 Medler, J. 905; 1973-08-18 [K002843763]
 Total: 2; Borno 1, Cross River 1.

Tristemma oreophilum Gilg
 Talbot 591 [BM barcode BM000902312]
 Total: 1.

Warneckea austro-occidentalis R.D.Stone
 Latilo M.G. FHI38099; 07-03-1959 [K]
 Total: 1.

Warneckea cinnamomoides (G.Don) Jacq.-Fél.
 Memecylon cinnamomioides G.Don
 Chapman H.M.C. 679; 2004-11 [K] --> better to cite Chapman 3027 (FHO, WAG)
 Total: 3; Lagos 1, Taraba 2.

Warneckea fascicularis (Planch. ex Benth.) Jacq.-Fél.
 Spathandra fascicularis Planch. ex Benth.
 Hepper F.N. 1364; 1957-11-14 [BR0000016982581]
 Total: 2; Adamawa 2.

Warneckea fosteri (Hutch. & Dalziel) Jacq.-Fél.
 Memecylon fosteri Hutch. & Dalziel
 Foster, E.W. 359; 1907-10-27 [K000230029]
 Total: 11; Cross River 3, Ondo 4, Taraba 1.

Warneckea guineensis (Keay) Jacq.-Fél.
 Memecylon guineense Keay
 Meikle R.D. 1253; 1950-03-11 [K000230023].
 Total: 12; Benue 1, Edo 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Warneckea membranifolia (Hook.f.) Jacq.-Fél.
 Memecylon membranifolium Hook.f.
 Brenan, J.P.M. 8581; 1947-12-24 [K003524200].
 Total: 20; Cross River 4, Edo 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Warneckea memecyloides (Benth.) Jacq.-Fél.
 Spathandra memecyloides Benth.
 Richards 3014 [MO]
 Total: 15; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Warneckea pulcherrima (Gilg) Jacq.-Fél.
 Memecylon pulcherrimum Gilg
 Schmitt & Ibiang 371; 1995-2-8 [MO-5761959]
 Total: 1; Cross River 1.

BURSERACEAE

Aucoumea klaineana Pierre — Introduced
 Daramola B.O. ; Osayinlusi 96268 03/1983; FHI
 Total: 4; Oyo 2.

Boswellia dalzielii Hutch.
 Dalziel, J.M. 167 02/02/1909; K
 Total: 48; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kwara 1,

Niger 8, Ogun 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3, Yobe 1, Zamfara 5.

Boswellia papyrifera (Caill. ex Delile)

Hochst.

Amyris papyrifera Caill.

Literature

Total: 0.

Canarium acutifolium (DC.) Merr. —

Introduced

Marignia acutifolia DC.

Takeuchi, W.; -- [P04799926]731343735

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Canarium obtusifolium Scott Elliot —

Introduced

Kennedy J.D.; 1665; -- [BR0000014227035]

Total: 1.

Canarium schweinfurthii Engl.

Brenan, J.P.M.; Jones, E.W. s.n. 10/01/1948; K

Total: 66; Bauchi 3, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 19, Enugu 1, Imo 3, Kebbi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Taraba 2.

Commiphora africana (A.Rich.) Engl.

Heudelotia africana A.Rich.

Wit, P.;Gbile, Z. O.;Daramola, B. O., s.n. 04/05/1972 ; FHI

Total: 35; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 6, Borno 6, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Commiphora africana var. *africana*

Heudelotia africana A.Rich.

Commiphora glandulosa Schinz —

Introduced

Robert J. Rodin 9026; 1973-3-6 [OBI102316]

Total: 1.

Commiphora kerstingii Engl.

Dalziel, J.M. 572 04/07/1911; K

Total: 24; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Commiphora paolii Chiov.

KERSHAW NGA-29564 01/05/1966 ;Human observation Flotrop184654

Total: 1.

Commiphora pedunculata (Kotschy &

Peyr.) Engl.

Balsamodendrum pedunculatum Kotschy & Peyr.

Lawlor, D.W.; Hall, J.B. 525 22/08/1962; K

Total: 40; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 7, Borno 2, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 5, Kogi 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Commiphora quadricincta Schweinf.

Musa Daggah, s.n. 20 /09/1949; FHI

Total: 3; Kwara 1, Yobe 2.

Pachylobus edulis G.Don

Emwiogbon, J. A., s.n. s.d. ; FHI

Total: 71; Anambra 3, Cross River 7, Edo 21, Enugu 2, Kaduna 8, Kebbi 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 8, Rivers 1.

Pachylobus klaineanus (Pierre) Guillaumin

Santiriopsis klaineana Pierre

Jones, A.P.D.; Onochie, C.F. 18730, 13/05/1946; K

Total: 13; Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Santiria trimera (Oliv.) Aubrév.

Sorindeia trimera Oliv.

Olorunfemi, J.;Ariwaodo, J.O., SE.87 16/04 /1975; FHI

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 4.

ANACARDIACEAE

Anacardium occidentale L. — Introduced

Ibhanesebhor, G.;Adejimi, J., GJ. 289 28/10/1976; FHI

Total: 35; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 12, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Zamfara 1.

Antrocaryon klaineinum Pierre

Kennedy, J.D. 1131 n.d.; [E00136861]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Antrocaryon micraster A.Chev. &

Guillaumin

Latilo, M.G., s.n. 29/06/1963; FHI

Total: 21; Cross River 4, Edo 5, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1.

Haematostaphis barteri Hook.f.

Barter, C. 1341; 1858 [K000074870]

Total: 29; Adamawa 3, Gombe 3, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Niger 5, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 2.

Lannea acida A.Rich.

Latilo, M.G. FHI62557 11/4/ 1969; K

Total: 18; Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Lannea barteri (Oliv.) Engl.

Odina barteri Oliv.

Barter, C. 1109, 1858; K

Total: 44; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Borno 6, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 8, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Lannea fruticosa (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Engl.

Odina fruticosa Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Olufsen, O. 609 01/01/1927 ; IFAN

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Niger 1, Yobe 1.

Lannea glabrescens Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Lannea humilis (Oliv.) Engl.

Odina humilis Oliv.

Vogel, E. 78 04/1858; K

Total: 7; Borno 3, Niger 2.

Lannea nigritana (Scott Elliot) Keay

Odina nigritana Scott Elliot

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 31543; K

Total: 19; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 16, Taraba 1.

Lannea schimperi (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Engl.

Odina schimperi Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Meikle, R.D. 1374 05/04/1950; K

Total: 34; Bauchi 7, Borno 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 4, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 5, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Lannea triphylla (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Engl.

— Introduced

Odina triphylla Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Lannea velutina A.Rich.

s.coll. FR-0010408 22/03/1994; SMF

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Lannea welwitschii (Hiern) Engl.

Calesiam welwitschii Hiern

Emwiogbon, J. A. s.n. 25/04/1963 ; FHI

Total: 21; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 6.

Lannea welwitschii var. *welwitschii*

Calesiam welwitschii Hiern

Mangifera indica L. — Introduced

Odewo, T.K.; Adedeji, s.n. 14/12/1981; FHI

Total: 8; Kano 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Myracrodruon urundeuva Allemão — Introduced

Usang Felix; 2005-10-12 [237] 3913474566

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Ozoroa insignis Delile

n. coll. 04/1997; FR

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Ozoroa insignis var. *intermedia* R.Fern.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ozoroa mucronata (Bernh. ex C.Krauss)

R.Fern. & A.Fern. — Introduced

Heeria mucronata Bernh.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 448; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1435049]

Total: 4; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Zamfara 1.

Ozoroa pulcherrima (Schweinf.) R.Fern. & A.Fern.

Anaphrenium pulcherrimum Schweinf.

MONOD NGA-5164 18/12/1948 ; Flotrop186007 (Human observation)

Total: 35; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Kaduna 6, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Plateau 11.

Pistacia vera L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1597 06/06/1966; WAG

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Pseudospondias longifolia Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Pseudospondias microcarpa (A.Rich.) Engl.

Spondias microcarpa A.Rich.

Latilo, M.G. 30902 20/04/1952

Total: 62; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 18, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 5, Oyo 8, Plateau 1, Taraba 7.

Sclerocarya birrea (A.Rich.) Hochst.

Spondias birrea A.Rich.

Virgo, K.J. 15 06/03/1969

Total: 19; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kano 2, Yobe 3.

Sclerocarya birrea subsp. *birrea*

Spondias birrea A.Rich.

Searsia crenulata (A.Rich.) Moffett

Rhus crenulata A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Searsia longipes (Engl.) Moffett

Rhus longipes Engl.

Coombe D.E. [BR0000013845872]

Total: 11; Anambra 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 5.

Searsia longipes var. *longipes*

Rhus longipes Engl.

Searsia natalensis (Bernh. ex C.Krauss)

F.A.Barkley — Introduced

Rhus natalensis Bernh.

Latilo MG; 1971-11-22 [WAG.1436260]

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Ogun 1, Plateau 3.

Sorindeia africana (Engl.) Van der Veken

Thyrsoodium africanum Engl.

Van Meer P. [BR0000013857578]

Total: 10; Abia 2, Cross River 4, Edo 1.

Sorindeia grandifolia Engl.

Ariwaodo, J.O. 1175 17/03/1966; K

Total: 63; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Osun 1, Oyo 18, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Sorindeia juglandifolia (A.Rich.) Planch. ex Oliv.

Dupuisia juglandifolia A.Rich.

Gbile, Z.O.; Daramola, B.O; 1970-03-30 [K002228635]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Sorindeia winkleri Engl.

Ariwaodo JO; 1977-05-10 [WAG.1377758]

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3.

Spondias dulcis Parkinson — Introduced

Binuyo, A FHI 41217 12/04/ 1959; WAG

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Spondias mombin L. — Introduced

Binuyo, A. FHI41259 22/04/1959; K

Total: 62; Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 5, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Gombe 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 6, Ogun 5, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Spondias purpurea L. — Introduced

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1175; 1972-4-28 [WAG.1377895]

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Trichoscypha acuminata Engl.

Jones, A.P.D.; Onochie, C.F. 18731 05/1946; K

Total: 19; Abia 1, Cross River 16, Lagos 1, Niger 1.

Trichoscypha arborea (A.Chev.) A.Chev.

Emiliomarcelia arborea A.Chev.

Ariwaodo, J.O., JOA.227 28/01 /1977-; FHI

Total: 7; Cross River 3.

Trichoscypha bijuga Engl.

s.coll. 30925 02/05/1952; K

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Cross River 8.

Trichoscypha laxiflora Engl.

Talbot,P.A., 579a 1911 ; BM

Total: 1.

Trichoscypha longipetala Baker f. —

Endemic

Talbot,P.A.,1681 1912; BM

Total: 1.

Trichoscypha lucens Oliv.

Daramola B.O. [BR0000017376563]

Total: 16; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Lagos 3.

Trichoscypha mannii Hook.f.

Mann, G. 2238 02/1863; K

Total: 17; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 11.

Trichoscypha patens (Oliv.) Engl.

Sorindeia patens Oliv.

Onochie, C.F.A. 32911 12/05/1953; K

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 5.

SAPINDACEAE

Allophylus africanus P.Beauv.

Barter 1695 n.d.; K

Total: 235; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 4, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 6, Bauchi 6, Bayelsa 1, Benue 4, Borno 1, Cross River 21, Edo 10, Ekiti 3, Enugu 8, Imo 7, Kaduna 9, Kebbi 1, Kogi 7, Kwara 11, Lagos 11, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Ogun 2, Ondo 12, Osun 4, Oyo 33, Plateau 13, Taraba 15.

Allophylus africanus var. *africanus*

Barter [K000426177]

Total: 1.

Allophylus bullatus Radlk.

Van Meer, #1762 08/08/1971; FHI

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Allophylus chrysothrix (Radlk.) Lisowski

Allophylus africanus f. *chrysothrix* Radlk.

Idahosa, s.n. 22/09/1949; FHI

Total: 3; Borno 1, Oyo 1.

Allophylus cobbe (L.) Forsyth f. —

Introduced

Rhus cobbe L.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO FHI 64096; 1971-9-16 [WAG.1369731]

Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Jigawa 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 8, Oyo 5, Plateau 3.

Allophylus conraui Gilg ex Radlk.

Daramola B.O. 2502 25/08/1977; FHI

Total: 7; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Edo 1, Taraba 4.

Allophylus ferrugineus Taub.

Binuyo A.; 1959-04-28 [BR0000019136929]

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Allophylus ferrugineus var. *ferrugineus*

Emwioqbon J.A. 46774 11/04/1972; MO

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Allophylus grandifolius (Baker) Radlk.

Schmidelia grandifolia Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Allophylus hirtellus (Hook.f.) Radlk.

Schmidelia hirtella Hook.f.

Daramola, B. O., s.n. 04/09/1965; FHI

Total: 2; Niger 2.

Allophylus longicuneatus Verm. ex Hauman

Schmitt K; et al. 992 20/12/ 1995; MO

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Allophylus megaphyllus Hutch. & Dalziel

Talbot, P. 1393 no date; K

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Allophylus nigericus Baker f.

Talbot P.A. 442 1911; BM

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3.

Allophylus spicatus (Poir.) Radlk.

Ornitrophe spicata Poir.

Olorunfemi ; Oguntayo; Ihe 14 13/09/1978; FHI

Total: 48; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 8, Osun 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Allophylus talbotii Baker f.

Talbot P.A. 1713 1912; BM

Total: 1.

Allophylus ujori Cheek

Chapman J. D. 2670 12/02/1972; FHI, FHO, K,

Total: 1.

Aporrhiza paniculata Radlk.

Kennedy J.D.; 1931-08-01 [FHI.9269.0]

Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Aporrhiza talbotii Baker f.

Talbot, P.A.416 1911; K

Total: 19; Abia 2, Cross River 9, Edo 1, Niger 3, Ondo 1.

Blighia sapida K.D.Koenig

Binuyo, A.; Bowden, R.E.M. 37562 01/03/1958; K

Total: 121; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Imo 1, Kwara 5, Lagos 11, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 14, Ondo 5, Osun 3, Oyo 47.

Blighia unijugata Baker

Keay, R.W.J. 25690 03/04/1950; K

Total: 67; Abia 2, Anambra 2, Benue 2, Borno 2, Edo 6, Ekiti 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 24, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Blighia welwitschii (Hiern) Radlk.

Phialodiscus welwitschii Hiern

Latilo, M.; Brenan, J.P.M. 8842 19/01/1948; K

Total: 27; Cross River 5, Edo 8, Kaduna 5, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 2.

Cardiospermum corindum L. — Introduced de Wilde W.J.J.O 10536 05/04/1966; FHI

Total: 1.

Cardiospermum grandiflorum Sw.

Hamza M.A.FHI0014421 27/11/1971; FHI

Total: 65; Abia 5, Anambra 2, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 3, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 6, Lagos 4, Ogun 6, Ondo 4, Osun 5, Oyo 10, Rivers 1, Zamfara 1.

Cardiospermum halicacabum L.

Lawlor; Hall 314 15/08/1962; FHI

Total: 68; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Bayelsa 3, Benue 3, Borno 2, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Osun 4, Oyo 8, Plateau 4, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Chytranthus angustifolius Exell

Brenan, J.P.M. 8811 08/01/1948; K

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Edo 6, Kaduna 2.

Chytranthus atroviolaceus Baker f. ex Hutch. & Dalziel

Ngoka FHI.41841 15/04/1958; K

Total: 14; Cross River 7, Edo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 2.

Chytranthus cauliflorus (Hutch. & Dalziel) Wickens

Laccodiscus cauliflorus Hutch. & Dalziel

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie. C.F. 17232 01/04/1946 ; FHI

Total: 1; Osun 1.

Chytranthus ellipticus Hutch. & Dalziel

Brenan, J.P.M. 8579 23/12/1947; K

Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Niger 2.

Chytranthus gillettii De Wild.

s.coll. S.d. FHI0106496; FHI

Total: 1.

Chytranthus macrobotrys (Gilg) Exell & Mendonça

Glossolepis macrobotrys Gilg

Latilo, M.G., s.n. 11/03 /1967; FHI

Total: 33; Cross River 12, Edo 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Oyo 9.

Chytranthus setosus Radlk.

Mann, G. 2281; K

Total: 16; Cross River 8, Edo 3, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 2.

Chytranthus talbotii (Baker f.) Keay

Glossolepis talbotii Baker f.

Talbot, P. 1686 1911; K

Total: 39; Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 9, Edo 13, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1.

Chytranthus welwitschii Exell

[A. Oladijinko]; Onochie, C.; FHI20660; 1947-01-20 [K003474012]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Ogun 1.

Deinbollia calophylla Gilg & Dinkl. ex Radlk.

Meer, PPC van 1758 23/05/1971; WAG

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Deinbollia insignis Hook.f.

Onochie, C.F.A., s.n. 06/06/1947; FHI

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 3.

Deinbollia macroura Gilg ex Radlk.

K. Schmitt; et al. Schmitt 1004 20/12/1995; MO

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Deinbollia maxima Gilg

Van Mear 1758 23/05/1971; FHI

Total: 3; Benue 1, Cross River 2.

Deinbollia onanae Cheek

Chapman, H.M. 481 02/12/ 2003; FHI, K

Total: 1.

Deinbollia oreophila Cheek

Savory, H.J.; Keay, R.W.J.; FHI25182; 1948-12-28 [K003471986]

Total: 2; Benue 1.

Deinbollia pinnata (Poir.) Schumach. & Thonn.

Ornitrophe pinnata Poir.

Odewo, T.K and Adedeji, ODA. 348 17/05/1983; FHI

Total: 114; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 3, Enugu 5, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 6, Niger 4, Ogun 18, Ondo 11, Osun 6, Oyo 24, Taraba 4.

Deinbollia saligna Keay

Ujor E.U.FHI0031776 25/04/1952; FHI

Total: 4; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Osun 1.

Dodonaea viscosa Jacq.

Fagbemi A.; Osanyinlusi F.O.128 25/02/1977; FHI

Total: 33; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Lagos 10, Osun 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Dodonaea viscosa subsp. *viscosa*

Eriocoelum kerstingii Gilg ex Engl.

Latilo, M.G.; Daramola, B. O., s.n. 26/12/1954; FHI

Total: 12; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 3, Plateau 2.

Eriocoelum macrocarpum Gilg ex Radlk.

Kennedy J. D. 1676 s.d.; US

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Borno 4, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kwara 3, Oyo 1.

Eriocoelum microspermum Radlk. ex Engl.

Ejiofor, M.C., s.n. 22/11/1948; FHI

Total: 1.

Eriocoelum oblongum Keay

Talbot, P.A., 3246 1912-13; BM

Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 6.

Eriocoelum pungens Radlk. ex Engl.

Talbot, P.A., #3644 1915; BM

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Eriocoelum pungens var. *inermis* Keay — Endemic

Talbot, P.A. 3644 1915; BM

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Eriocoelum racemosum Baker

Thomas M.W. FHI0033862 1915; FHI

Total: 2.

Glenniea africana (Radlk.) Leenh.

Melanodiscus africanus Radlk.

Onochie C.F.A.; Latilo M.G. 32448 16/12/1952; FHI

Total: 10; Ogun 7, Ondo 1.

Haplocoelum foliolosum (Hiern) Bullock

Balsamea foliolosa Hiern

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Haplocoelum foliolosum subsp.

strongylocarpum (Bullock) Verdc.

Haplocoelum strongylocarpum Bullock

Jackson J.A.D. 624; 1967-11-18 [17893]1990427431

Total: 1.

Laccodiscus ferrugineus (Baker) Radlk.

Cupania ferruginea Baker

Ariwaodo J.O. JAO.633 03/05/1977; FHI
Total: 23; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 14.

Laccodiscus pseudostipularis Radlk. ex Engl.

Onochie, C.F.A., s.n. 05/03/ 1957; FHI
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Lecaniodiscus cupanioides Planch. ex Benth.

Meikle, R.D. 1310 23/03/1950; K
Total: 77; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Edo 7, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 4, Ondo 5, Osun 7, Oyo 26, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Lepisanthes senegalensis (Poir.) Leenh.
Sapindus senegalensis Poir.

Lomax A.T. 32324 01/02/1956; FHI
Total: 33; Adamawa 3, Anambra 2, Benue 4, Borno 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Taraba 3.

Lychnodiscus reticulatus Radlk.

Ahmed, H.;Chizea, L.G., s.n. 02/04/ 1949; FHI
Total: 28; Benue 4, Cross River 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 12, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Majidea fosteri (Sprague) Radlk.

Harpullia fosteri Sprague
Foster, E.W., 49 24/03/1906; M
Total: 13; Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Kano 1, Ogun 1.

Melicoccus bijugatus Jacq. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1870; 1966-8-23 [WAG.1266413]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Namataea simplicifolia D.W.Thomas & D.J.Harris

Literature
Total: 0.

Nephelium lappaceum L. — Introduced

Daramola B.O.; 1964-8-3 [55213]1990430674
Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Pancovia bijuga Willd.

Chapman J.D.1923 06/05/1977; FHI
Total: 11; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Taraba 1.

Pancovia sessiliflora Hutch. & Dalziel — Endemic

Onochie, C. 8905 27/01/1948; K
Total: 23; Cross River 4, Edo 5, Lagos 6, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Pancovia turbinata Radlk.

E. Bebiem; et al. Bebiem 1203 08/01/1996; MO
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Paullinia pinnata L.

Gregory, H. 52 06/1946; K
Total: 149; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 6, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Benue 3, Cross River 8, Edo 1, Ekiti 3, Enugu 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 2, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 11, Ogun 11, Ondo 5, Osun 6, Oyo 18, Plateau 8, Rivers 2, Taraba 6.

Placodiscus bracteosus J.B.Hall

Literature
Total: 0.

Placodiscus caudatus Pierre ex Pellegr.
s.coll.s.d. 01/04/1959; no herb. Cited
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Placodiscus glandulosus Radlk. ex Engl.

Jones, A.P.D.;Onochie, C.F.A., s.n. 21/05/1946; FHI
Total: 1.

Placodiscus oblongifolius J.B.Hall

Latilo, M.G. FHI30970; 1952-05-16 [K003474452]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Placodiscus opacus Radlk.

Binuyo A FHI 45461 29/01/1962; FHI
Total: 3; Abia 1, Cross River 2.

Placodiscus pseudostipularis Radlk.

s.coll.s.d. 29/01/1962; no herb. Cited
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Placodiscus turbinatus Radlk.

Mann, G. 2239 02/1863; K
Total: 9; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1.

Radlkofera calodendron Gilg

Keay, R.W.J. 37026 23/05/1957; K
Total: 9; Edo 7, Ogun 1.

Zanha golungensis Hiern

Keay, R.W.J., s.n. 18/05/1948; FHI
Total: 14; Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Oyo 4.

RUTACEAE

Aegle marmelos (L.) Corrêa — Introduced

Crateva marmelos L.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1872; 1966-8-22 [WAG.1548227]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Aeglopsis chevalieri Swingle

Ujor, EU FHI 32983; 1950-2-23 [WAG.1548218]

Total: 10; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 2.

Afraegle paniculata (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Engl.

Citrus paniculata Schumach. & Thonn.

Barter 3404; -- [K000199538]

Total: 29; Benue 1, Kaduna 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 9.

Balsamocitrus camerunensis Letouzey

Literature

Total: 0.

Bergera koenigii L. — Introduced

Adebajo C.A.; 1993-5-24 [105277]1990433710

Total: 1.

Chloroxylon swietenia DC. — Introduced

Swietenia chloroxylon Roxb.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1944-11-9 [8148] [1990426651]

Total: 7; Benue 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3.

Citropsis articulata (Willd. ex Spreng.)

Swingle & M.Kellerm.

Citrus articulata Willd. ex Spreng.

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C. 18703; 1946-5-10

[BR0000015672902]

Total: 15; Abia 2, Cross River 11, Oyo 1.

Citrus medica L. — Introduced

Abudu Bola; 2013-5-31 [5789] [3808440267]

Total: 11; Lagos 4, Ogun 5, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1.

Citrus × *aurantiifolia* (Christm.) Swingle —

Introduced

Limonia × *aurantiifolia* Christm.

Olubunmi Elemo; 2014-1-22 [6044] [3808440241]

Total: 1.

Citrus × *aurantium* L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1135; 1967-8-21 [WAG.1305022]

Total: 1.

Citrus × *aurantium* f. *deliciosa* (Ten.)

M.Hiroe — Introduced

Ene Ujah; 2016-8-1 [7336] [3808440160]

Total: 1.

Citrus × *limon* (L.) Osbeck — Introduced

Citrus medica var. *limon* L.

Ahmed Taofiqat; 2017-4-16 [110938] [1990433862]

Total: 1.

Clausena anisata (Willd.) Hook.f. ex Benth.

Amyris anisata Willd.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji FHI 99931; 1983-5-17

[WAG.1255552]

Total: 136; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 3, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 10, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 11, Nasarawa 1, Niger 10, Ogun 12, Ondo 7, Osun 10, Oyo 21, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 19.

Glycosmis parviflora (Sims) Little —

Introduced

Limonia parviflora Sims

Kennedy J.D. 1417; -- [BR0000019595184]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Edo 3.

Harrisonia abyssinica Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 759; 1968-5-11 [WAG.1528158]

Total: 40; Lagos 5, Ogun 24, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Zamfara 1.

Murraya paniculata (L.) Jack — Introduced

Chalcas paniculata L.

Dr. Kadiri; 2009-7-3 [1038]3808441188

Total: 11; Lagos 3, Ogun 4, Oyo 4.

Swinglea glutinosa (Blanco) Merr. —

Introduced

Limonia glutinosa Blanco

Hodgson L. 4342; 1982-6-12 [100153]1990433366

Total: 1; Delta 1.

Vepris adamaouae Onana

Chpaman, J.D. 3970; 1975-12-1 [K001286520]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Vepris afzelii (Engl.) Mziray

Teclea afzelii Engl.

Latilo M.G; 1952-5-23 [30993] [1990428723]

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Vepris glaberrima (Engl.) J.B.Hall ex

D.J.Harris

Orixiopsis glaberrima Engl.

Offokansi L.288/12; 1962-3-17 [59075] [1990430893]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Vepris grandifolia (Engl.) Mziray

Teclea grandifolia Engl.

Olatunji O.A.OLAT. 515B; 1977-5-14 [82196]

[1990432483]

Total: 4; Benue 2, Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Vepris lanceolata (Lam.) G.Don —

Introduced

Toddalia lanceolata Lam.

Jackson J.A.D. 500; 1967-5-5 [17059]1990427327

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Taraba 1.

Vepris lecomteana (Pierre) Cheek & T.Heller

Oricia lecomteana Pierre

Keay R.W.J; 1950-12-14 [28258] [1990428487]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Vepris soyauxii (Engl.) Mziray

Araliopsis soyauxii Engl.

Binuyo, A FHI 41450; 1959-8-14 [WAG.1413360]

Total: 4; Abia 2, Cross River 2.

Vepris suaveolens (Engl.) Mziray

Teclea suaveolens Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1433; 1971-4-23 [WAG.1413373]

Total: 48; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 27.

Vepris trifoliolata (Engl.) Mziray

Araliopsis trifoliolata Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1502; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1413450]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Vepris verdoorniana (Exell & Mendonça) Mziray

Teclea verdoorniana Exell & Mendonça

Daramola B.O.; 1969-5-20 [62741] [1990431218]

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Zanthoxylum bouetense (Pierre ex Letouzey)

P.G.Waterman — Introduced

Fagara bouetensis Pierre ex Letouzey

Latilo M.G.;Daramola

B.O.;Onijamowo;Ibhanesebhor; 1974-10-17 [71804] [1990431854]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Zanthoxylum buesgenii (Engl.)

P.G.Waterman

Fagara buesgenii Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Zanthoxylum dinklagei (Engl.)

P.G.Waterman

Fagara dinklagei Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1332; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1413687]

Total: 14; Cross River 7, Edo 6.

Zanthoxylum gillettii (De Wild.)

P.G.Waterman

Fagara gillettii De Wild.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32798; 1981-6-17 [WAG.1413739]

Total: 68; Abia 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 13, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 10, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 7, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Zanthoxylum lemairei (De Wild.)

P.G.Waterman

Fagara lemairei De Wild.

Unwin, A.H. 13; 1913-6-30 [K000199426]

Total: 17; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 6, Enugu 4, Oyo 1.

Zanthoxylum leprieurii Guill. & Perr.

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO; Fagbemi, A FHI 71048; 1974-8-1 [WAG.1210063]

Total: 92; Anambra 4, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 8, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 14, Ondo 12, Osun 4, Oyo 18, Plateau 5, Taraba 3.

Zanthoxylum rubescens Planch. ex Hook.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1711; 1966-9-8 [WAG.1210224]

Total: 41; Benue 3, Delta 3, Edo 5, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 11, Plateau 1.

Zanthoxylum thomense (Engl.) A.Chev. ex

P.G.Waterman

Fagara thomensis Engl.

Olorunfemi; Daramola; Fagbemi FHI71048 [K004663214]

Total: 2; Ondo 2.

Zanthoxylum viride (A.Chev.)

P.G.Waterman

Fagara viridis A.Chev.

Olatunji O.A. 509; 1976-6-30 [82174] [1990432414]

Total: 18; Cross River 1, Kaduna 4, Kwara 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 5.

Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides (Lam.) Zepern. & Timler

Fagara zanthoxyloides Lam.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 455; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1210368]

Total: 49; Abia 1, Edo 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Ogun 15, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 11.

SIMAROUBACEAE

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb. — Introduced

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/2465216323>

Total: 1.

Brucea antidysenterica J.F.Mill.

Daramola, BO FHI 86040; 1979-1-23 [WAG.1528660]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Taraba 6.

Brucea guineensis G.Don

Okafor, J.C.; Latilo, M.G. FHI36258 [K004829390]

Total: 4; Cross River 2.

Brucea tenuifolia Engl. — Introduced

Meer, PPC van 613; 1968-2-16 [WAG.1528730]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Hannoa ferruginea Engl.

Chapman, J.D.; 4884; 1977-04-09 [K004827643]

Total: 3; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Nothospondias staudtii Engl.

Ariwaodo, JO 483; 1977-3-30 [WAG.1528223]

Total: 15; Kogi 1, Oyo 10.

Odyendea gabunensis (Pierre) Engl.

Quassia gabonensis Pierre

Latilo M.G. & Daramola B.O. F.H.I.34484; 1955-2-17 [BR0000019681603]

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Odyendea klaineana (Pierre) Engl.

Quassia klaineana Pierre

Geerling, C 5578; 1976-1-19 [WAG.1525380]

Total: 1.

Pierreodendron africanum (Hook.f.) Little

Mannia africana Benth. & Hook.f.

Kennedy J.D. 1809; -- [BR0000018120257]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 2, Edo 2, Ogun 2,

Ondo 1.

Pierreodendron kerstingii (Engl.) Little

Simarubopsis kerstingii Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Quassia amara L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1647; 1966-6-24 [WAG.1525312]

Total: 8; Lagos 1, Oyo 5.

MELIACEAE

Azadirachta indica A.Juss. — Introduced

Denys E. 601; 1982-4-4 [BR0000016988941]

Total: 108; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 9, Kogi 1, Lagos 27, Niger 4, Ogun 16, Osun 5, Oyo 27, Yobe 3.

Carapa batesii C.DC.

Latilo, MG 29; 1959-3-23 [WAG0233289]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Carapa dinklagei Harms

J. D. Kennedy 2055; -- [US 1595899]

Total: 16; Cross River 4, Edo 1.

Carapa grandiflora Sprague

Savory H.J. FHI25181; 28-12-1948 [K]

Total: 1.

Carapa macrantha Harms

Meer, PPC van 1752; 1971-5-22 [WAG.1096372]

Total: 9; Cross River 5, Ogun 1, Taraba 2.

Carapa microcarpa A.Chev.

Dalziel J.M. 372; 30-01-1919 [K000625069]

Total: 2; Lagos 1.

Carapa oreophila Kenfack

van Meer 1752 (MO).

Total: 1.

Carapa parviflora Harms

Latilo, MG FHI 67753; 1973-3-1 [WAG0233287]

Total: 8; Cross River 3, Edo 3.

Carapa procera DC.

Dowsett-Lemaire F. 1230; 1988-3-17

[BR0000013592301]

Total: 90; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 4, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Cross River 21, Delta 1, Edo 16, Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Carapa zemagoana Kenfack

Latilo MG Latilo, MG 29; 1959-03-23

[WAG0233289]

Total: 1.

Cedrela odorata L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1505; 1966-5-15 [WAG.1096511]

Total: 33; Anambra 2, Edo 3, Enugu 3, Ogun 7, Oyo 12.

Chukrasia tabularis A.Juss. — Introduced

Adebusuyi J.K.; Okeke R.E.; 1959-5-13 [28300-1]1949703877

Total: 10; Anambra 1, Enugu 1, Ogun 8.

Ekebergia capensis Sparrm.

Chapman, JD 2882; 1972-6-8 [WAG.1096774]

Total: 76; Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 10, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Oyo 19, Plateau 14, Taraba 2.

Entandrophragma angolense (Welw.)

C.DC.

Swietenia angolensis Welw.

Chapman, JD 3026; 1973-3-1 [WAG.1097367]

Total: 125; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 58, Enugu 1, Kaduna 11, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 17, Plateau 1, Taraba 10.

Entandrophragma candollei Harms

Hereźniak J. ; 1975-2-14 [POZG-V-0061535]
Total: 44; Borno 2, Cross River 1, Edo 14, Kaduna 6,
Ondo 5, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Entandrophragma cylindricum (Sprague)
Sprague

Pseudocedrela cylindrica Sprague
Richards, P.W. ; 1955-2-18 [P00453170]
Total: 92; Borno 4, Cross River 2, Edo 40, Kaduna 6,
Niger 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 4, Taraba 2.

Entandrophragma utile (Dawe & Sprague)
Sprague

Pseudocedrela utilis Dawe & Sprague
Brenan, J.P.M. ; 1947-12-9 [P00453204]
Total: 25; Cross River 3, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2,
Ondo 10, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Heckeldora leonensis (Hutch. & Dalziel)
E.J.M.Koenen

Guarea leonensis Hutch. & Dalziel
Samai S.K.; 1967-4-23 [1944989555]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Heckeldora staudtii (Harms) Staner
Guarea staudtii Harms

Talbot, P.A. 1281; -- [K001044807]
Total: 23; Cross River 19, Plateau 1.

Heckeldora zenkeri (Harms) Staner
Guarea zenkeri Harms

Meer, PPC van 1122; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1097184]
Total: 5; Cross River 3.

Khaya agboensis A.Chev.

Literature
Total: 0.

Khaya anotheca (Welw.) C.DC.
Garretia anotheca Welw.

Hall J.B. GC 42551; 1971-2-20 [46640]
Total: 7; Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1.

Khaya grandifoliola C.DC.

Chapman 4146; 1976-2-10 [2312292]
Total: 88; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 3,
Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 3, Kaduna 12, Kogi 1, Lagos 2,
Ogun 5, Ondo 9, Osun 3, Oyo 14, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Khaya ivorensis A.Chev.

Oladoyinbo, A FHI 43355; 1959-8-18
[WAG.1097265]
Total: 95; Borno 1, Cross River 4, Edo 26, Kaduna 8,
Kwara 3, Niger 2, Ogun 7, Ondo 2, Oyo 7, Rivers 2.

Khaya senegalensis (Desv.) A.Juss.

Swietenia senegalensis Desr.
Wit, P 2677; 1973-4-16 [WAG0368646]

Total: 90; Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Bayelsa
1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1,
Kaduna 10, Kano 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 2, Niger
2, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Oyo 15, Plateau 3, Sokoto 4,
Taraba 1, Zamfara 3.

Leplaea cedrata (A.Chev.) E.J.M.Koenen &
J.J.de Wilde

Trichilia cedrata A.Chev.
Kennedy J.D. 536; -- [BR0000019200132]
Total: 57; Borno 1, Edo 30, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Ogun
1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 3.

Leplaea laurentii (De Wild.) E.J.M.Koenen
& J.J.de Wilde

Guarea laurentii De Wild.
Jones, A.P.D. ; -- [B 10 0293319]
Total: 1.

Leplaea thompsonii (Sprague & Hutch.)
E.J.M.Koenen & J.J.de Wilde

Guarea thompsonii Sprague & Hutch.
16; -- [K000800947]
Total: 47; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo
26, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 1.

Lovoa swynnertonii Baker f.

Brenan J.P.M.; Onochie C.F.A.; Jones E.W.; Richards
P.W.8433; 1947-12-8 [41660] [1944992641]
Total: 2; Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Lovoa trichilioides Harms

Thompson, H.N. 16; -- [K000800947]
Total: 59; Cross River 4, Edo 28, Kaduna 10, Ogun 5,
Ondo 2, Taraba 1.

Melia azedarach L. — Introduced

Léonard JGG 4533; 1968-2-18 [WAG.1097622]
Total: 24; Borno 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Niger 2,
Ogun 4, Oyo 7.

Neoguarea glomerulata (Harms)

E.J.M.Koenen & J.J.de Wilde

Guarea glomerulata Harms
Adebusuyi, JK FHI 44108; 1960-10-17
[WAG.1926072]
Total: 29; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 22,
Taraba 1.

Pseudocedrela kotschyi (Schweinf.) Harms

Cedrela kotschyi Schweinf.
Magaji, SO 46; 1959-12-10 [WAG.1097796]
Total: 67; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 11,
Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 12,
Osun 1, Oyo 17, Taraba 3.

Swietenia humilis Zucc. — Introduced

; -- [9222]1944988551

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Swietenia macrophylla G.King —

Introduced

Onyeachusim H.D.; 1965-10-30 [56129]

Total: 3; Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Toona sinensis (A.Juss.) M.Roem. —

Introduced

Cedrela sinensis A.Juss.

Onyeachusim H.D. M 602; 1963-10-23 [48007-1]1949704591

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Trichilia dregeana Sond.

Literature

Total: 0.

Trichilia emetica Vahl

Latilo M.G.; 1976-3-29 [78001]1944997312

Total: 50; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 11, Kano 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 4.

Trichilia emetica subsp. *emetica*

Latilo M.G. FHI47120; 1963-4-1

[BR0000019208848]

Total: 12; Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Trichilia emetica subsp. *suberosa* J.J.de

Wilde

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66354; 1973-5-15 [WAG.1098167]

Total: 7; Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Niger 1.

Trichilia gilgiana Harms

Binuyo A. 41415; 1939-7-29 [BR0000013954840]

Total: 11; Cross River 9, Oyo 1.

Trichilia martineau Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Kennedy 2184 (FHO); Onochie 7677 (FHO);

Tamajong FHI-20976 (K)

Total: 1.

Trichilia megalantha Harms

Onochie, CFA FHI 38331; 1958-4-29

[WAG.1098358]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Ekiti 1, Gombe 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 11, Taraba 1.

Trichilia monadelpha (Thonn.) J.J.de Wilde

Limonia monadelpha Thonn.

Gentry, AH 32973; 1981-6-23 [WAG.1098635]

Total: 94; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 11, Edo 14, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 39, Taraba 1.

Trichilia prieureana A.Juss.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000013959197]

Total: 65; Cross River 5, Edo 8, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 4, Lagos 7, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 15, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Trichilia retusa Oliv.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO FHI 65508; 1972-5-6 [WAG.1098974]

Total: 20; Abia 5, Adamawa 2, Benue 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Niger 3.

Trichilia rubescens Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1588; 1971-5-11 [WAG.1099222]

Total: 19; Abia 3, Cross River 11, Niger 1, Ondo 2.

Trichilia tessmannii Harms

Kennedy J.D. 516; -- [BR0000019217628]

Total: 22; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 9, Kaduna 4, Taraba 1.

Trichilia welwitschii C.DC.

Meer, PPC van 1540; 1971-8-5 [WAG.1099348]

Total: 8; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Lagos 1, Taraba 1.

Turraea heterophylla Sm.

Wit; Gbile; Daramola 843 [K005105283]

Total: 1.

Turraea nilotica Kotschy & Peyr.

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/1948981372>

Total: 1.

Turraea pellegriniana Keay

Keay R. & Savory H.J. 25029; 1948-12-19

[BR0000006247294]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Plateau 2.

Turraea vogelii Hook.f.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 556; 1978-5-30

[WAG.1099759]

Total: 43; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 8, Edo 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 8, Osun 1, Oyo 13.

Turraeanthus africanus (Welw. ex C.DC.)

Pellegr.

Guarea africana Welw. ex C.DC.

Latilo M.G. FHI30908; 28-04-1952 [K]

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Turraeanthus mannii Baill.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67788; 1973-3-5

[WAG.1100109]

Total: 34; Abia 5, Cross River 21, Kogi 2.

MALVACEAE

Abelmoschus esculentus (L.) Moench —
Introduced

Hibiscus esculentus L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65865; 1972-10-10

[WAG.1074570]

Total: 17; Gombe 1, Imo 2, Lagos 5, Ogun 3, Oyo 3.

Abelmoschus ficulneus (L.) Wight & Arn. —
Introduced

Hibiscus ficulneus L.

Wickens G.E. 3558; 11-12-1975 [K]

Total: 6; Borno 3.

Abelmoschus manihot (L.) Medik. —
Introduced

Hibiscus manihot L.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-11-02 [WAG.1075242]

Total: 2.

Abelmoschus manihot subsp. *manihot* —
Introduced

Hibiscus manihot L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2124; 1966-11-2 [WAG.1075242]

Total: 1.

Abelmoschus moschatus Medik. —
Introduced

Hibiscus abelmoschus L.

Dodd H. 423; 27-08-1908 [Lagos]

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Lagos 1.

Abelmoschus moschatus subsp. *moschatus*
— Introduced

Hibiscus abelmoschus L.

Shellard, Prof. Edward J.; 1974-- [93028]

Total: 4; Anambra 1.

Abelmoschus × *caillei* (A.Chev.) Stevels
Introduced

Hibiscus manihot var. *caillei* A.Chev.

Eijnatten CLM van Eijnatten, CLM van 1317; 1966-03-20 [WAG.1073656]

Total: 1.

Abroma augustum (L.) L.f. — Introduced

Theobroma augustum L.

Eijnatten, CLM van s.n.; 1965-12-4 [WAG.1245174]

Total: 5; Abia 2, Oyo 3.

Abutilon angulatum (Guill. & Perr.) Mast.

Bastardia angulata Guill. & Perr.

Dalziel, J.M.; 3044.0 [K]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Abutilon angulatum var. *angulatum*

Bastardia angulata Guill. & Perr.

Dalziel J.M. 73; 1908-5

Total: 2.

Abutilon auritum (Wall. ex Link) Sweet —
Introduced

Sida aurita Wall. ex Link

Literature

Total: 0.

Abutilon grandifolium (Willd.) Sweet —
Introduced

Sida grandifolia Willd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Abutilon hirtum (Lam.) Sweet

Sida hirta Lam.

Capt. G.M. Gosling, s.n.; nan [K006355762]

Total: 2.

Abutilon hirtum var. *hirtum*

Sida hirta Lam.

Gosling G.A. s.n.; 26-05-1905 [Northern Nigeria]

Total: 1.

Abutilon mauritianum (Jacq.) Medik.

Sida mauritiana Jacq.

Gbile, ZO FHI 73655; 1975-4-28 [WAG.1075617]

Total: 41; Abia 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Imo 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 21.

Abutilon mauritianum subsp. *mauritianum*

Sida mauritiana Jacq.

Sharland 859; 1979-10 [K]

Total: 4; Oyo 2.

Abutilon pannosum (G.Forst.) Schldtl.

Sida pannosa G.Forst.

Talbot; 1995-9-19 [FR-0019511]

Total: 9; Borno 2, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Abutilon pannosum var. *pannosum*

Sida pannosa G.Forst.

Golding J.D. 64; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 3; Yobe 1.

Abutilon ramosum (Cav.) Guill. & Perr.

Sida ramosa Cav.

Binuyo A. FHI41227; 1959-4-13 [BR0000016887862]

Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1.

Adansonia digitata L.

Blom-van Teyn, M van 83; 1971-6-4 [WAG.1391853]

Total: 34; Borno 4, Imo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 6, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 6, Zamfara 1.

Ancistrocarpus densispinosus Oliv.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 387; 1977-10-15
[WAG.1233396]

Total: 50; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 26, Edo 7,
Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 1,
Rivers 1.

Ayenia catalpifolia (Jacq.) Christenh. &
Byng

Byttneria catalpifolia Jacq.

Faremi, I.B. 446; 1974-08-27 [K006379232]

Total: 3; Ekiti 1.

Ayenia catalpifolia subsp. *africana* (Mast.)
Dorr

Byttneria africana Mast.

Faremi, I.B. 421; 1974-07-25 [K006379233]

Total: 2.

Ayenia dahomensis (N.Hallé) Christenh. &
Byng

Byttneria dahomensis N.Hallé

Millen, H. 194; -- [K000044861]

Total: 1.

Berrya cordifolia (Willd.) Burret —
Introduced

Espera cordifolia Willd.

Taylor, J.E. FHI12008 [K005054775]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Bombax buonopozense P.Beauv.

J. D. Kennedy [US 1719374]

Total: 33; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 5, Lagos 7,
Niger 2, Oyo 4.

Bombax buonopozense subsp. *buonopozense*

J. D. Kennedy 1989; -- [US 1719374]

Total: 1.

Bombax costatum Pellegr. & Vuillet

Pilz, G.E. 2244; 1977-7-27 [K000452257]

Total: 26; Borno 3, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kebbi 2, Niger
8, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Ceiba pentandra (L.) Gaertn. — Introduced

Bombax pentandrum L.

Daramola, B.O. 206; 1993-7-28 [K000211505]

Total: 50; Bauchi 1, Cross River 7, Kaduna 2, Kano 4,
Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Taraba 2.

Christiana africana DC.

A.P.D. JonesJones 4061; 1943-10-18 [1113422]

[1258324417]

Total: 3; Kaduna 2, Oyo 1.

Cienfuegosia digitata Cav.

Adeka, B FHI 40720; 1959-9-22 [WAG.1076022]

Total: 14; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano
1, Katsina 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Cienfuegosia heteroclada Sprague

Dalziel, J. M. 122; 1905-12-5 [K000240698]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 2.

Clappertonia ficifolia (Willd.) Decne.

Honkenya ficifolia Willd.

Emwiogbon, JA 189; 1972-5-6 [WAG.1233667]

Total: 25; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross
River 5, Delta 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 7, Niger 5, Ondo 1.

Clappertonia polyandra (K.Schum. ex
Sprague) Bech.

Cephalonema polyandrum K.Schum. ex Sprague

Daramola B.O. FHI55305; 08-10-1964 [K]

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 1.

Cola acuminata (P.Beauv.) Schott & Endl.

Sterculia acuminata P.Beauv.

Verwilghen 3; 1997-2-21 [WAG.1245464]

Total: 29; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Edo 6, Lagos 1,
Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4.

Cola altissima Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cola anomala K.Schum.

Russel T.A. FHI14959; 06-12-1951 [K0013026225]

Total: 1.

Cola argentea Mast.

Ujor E.U. FHI30842; 16-05-1952 [K000540717]

Total: 1.

Cola attiensis Aubrév. & Pellegr.

; -- [8866] [912077358]

Total: 1.

Cola bodardii Pellegr.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI16718; 25-02-1946
[K001302745]

Total: 3; Anambra 1, Ondo 1.

Cola brevipes K.Schum.

2286; 00-01-1900 [K0001302367]

Total: 2.

Cola cauliflora Mast.

Talbot P.A. 188; 00-01-1900 [K0001302298]

Total: 1.

Cola chlamydantha K.Schum.

Binuyo, A FHI 41449; 1959-8-14 [WAG.1245647]

Total: 4; Abia 2.

Cola cordifolia (Cav.) R.Br.

Sterculia cordifolia Cav.

Lawton R.M. 1832; 12-03-1975 [K001302075]

Total: 1.

Cola digitata Mast.

Meer, PPC van 1573; 1971-5-10 [WAG.1245854]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 4.

Cola flaviflora Engl. & K.Krause

Onochie36093; 1957-1-21 [23416] [912019874]

Total: 8; Cross River 8.

Cola flavovelutina K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1454; 1971-5-24 [WAG.1245946]

Total: 11; Cross River 10.

Cola gabonensis Mast.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO 981; 1971-11-18 [WAG.1246076]

Total: 5; Edo 4, Oyo 1.

Cola gigantea A.Chev.

Talbot 3046; 1912-- [CM183753]

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Ekiti 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 1.

Cola gigantea var. *gigantea*

Chapman H.M. 163; 01-08-1974 [K001302079]

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Cola gigantea var. *glabrescens* Brenan & Keay

Daramola B.O. 25; 01-03-1993 [K001302101]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Cola gigas Baker f. — Endemic

Talbot, P. A. 160; -- [K000240910]

Total: 11; Cross River 4, Niger 4.

Cola glabra Brenan & Keay — Endemic

Keay, R.W.J.37278; 1958-1-10 [23000] [912019400]

Total: 4; Edo 1, Ondo 3.

Cola heterophylla (P.Beauv.) Schott & Endl.

Sterculia heterophylla P.Beauv.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11292; 1977-3-30

[WAG.1246506]

Total: 13; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 3, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Cola hispida Brenan & Keay

Meer, PPC van 1158; 1971-4-3 [WAG.1246534]

Total: 17; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 6, Kaduna 2, Rivers 1.

Cola hypochrysea K.Schum.

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 3046; 06-04-1914

[K000540730]

Total: 1.

Cola lateritia K.Schum.

Talbot, P. A. [K000240891]

Total: 16; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Kaduna 2, Niger 3.

Cola lateritia var. *lateritia*

Talbot P.A. 1313; 1912-1-30 [BR0000006289454]

Total: 1.

Cola lateritia var. *maclaudii* (A.Chev.)

Brenan & Keay

Kennedy J.D. 2542; -- [BR0000019981512]

Total: 5; Borno 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 2.

Cola laurifolia Mast.

Wit, P; Geerling, C FHI 65007; 1972-3-18

[WAG.1246549]

Total: 12; Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Cola lepidota K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1115 A; 1971-4-1 [WAG.1246566]

Total: 8; Cross River 5, Edo 1, Lagos 1.

Cola mahoundensis Pellegr.

Alwyn H. Gentry; George E. Pilz Gentry 32890; 1981-6-21 [194337] [1259207307]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Cola marsupium K.Schum.

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 1338; 1911- [Oban]

Total: 1.

Cola megalophylla Brenan & Keay

Percy Amaury Talbot 192; 1911-- [BM000645958]

Total: 3; Edo 2.

Cola micrantha K.Schum.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cola millenii K.Schum.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32671; 1981-6-14

[WAG.1246750]

Total: 32; Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Osun 3, Oyo 17, Taraba 1.

Cola nigerica Brenan & Keay

Keay R. FHI37057; 1957-6-7 [BR0000018095760]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Ogun 3.

Cola nitida (Vent.) Schott & Endl.

Sterculia nitida Vent.

Pilz, GE 1857; 1976-11-28 [WAG.1246869]

Total: 23; Anambra 1, Edo 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 12.

Cola pachycarpa K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1395; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1246877]

Total: 9; Cross River 7, Kwara 1.

Cola philipi-jonesii Brenan & Keay —
Endemic

Onochie, C.F.; Jones, A.P.D. 5838; 1946-5-16
[K000240898]

Total: 5; Cross River 3.

Cola ricinifolia Engl. & K.Krause

; -- [2544] [2428970703]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2.

Cola rostrata K.Schum.

K. Schmitt; T.O. Ibiang Schmitt 402; 1995-2-9
[976772] [1261904484]

Total: 3; Cross River 2, Kogi 1.

Cola semecarpophylla K.Schum.

Latilo M.G. FHI30924; 02-05-1952 [K000541364]

Total: 1.

Cola triloba (R.Br.) K.Schum.

Courtenia triloba R.Br.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cola verticillata (Thonn.) Stapf ex A.Chev.

Sterculia verticillata Thonn.

Kennedy J.D. 418; 1929-- [BR0000019984063]

Total: 11; Edo 2, Oyo 9.

Corchorus aestuans L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65868; 1972-10-10
[WAG.1843957]

Total: 12; Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2,
Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Corchorus aestuans var. *aestuans*

Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC; Daramola, BO FHI 86283;
1978-5-5 [WAG.1843938]

Total: 1.

Corchorus capsularis L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1141; 1965-12-15
[WAG.1843877]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Corchorus fascicularis Lam.

; 1994-12-10 [FR-0016925] [3046111044]

Total: 7; Borno 5, Kaduna 1.

Corchorus olitorius L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1567; 1966-5-26 [WAG.1845594]

Total: 58; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 2, Borno 5, Gombe 2,
Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 9, Niger 3, Osun 2,
Oyo 10, Plateau 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Corchorus tridens L.

Denys, E 739; 1982-7-22 [WAG.1845430]

Total: 33; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Borno 4, Cross
River 2, Enugu 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 4, Lagos
1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Yobe 1.

Corchorus trilocularis L.

Lely H.V. 100; 04-05-1921 [K]

Total: 2; Kwara 1.

Cravenia panduriformis (Burm.f.) McLay &
R.L.Barrett

Onochie, C.F.A FHI23336; 1947-06-17
[K006276267]

Total: 12; Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Niger 2, Rivers 1.

Desplatsia dewevrei (De Wild. & T.Durand)
Burret

Grewiopsis dewevrei De Wild. & T.Durand
Eijnatten, CLM van 1326; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1845726]

Total: 52; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River
4, Edo 18, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 8.

Desplatsia subericarpa Bocq.

Verwilghen 22; 1997-3-3 [BR0000019964119]

Total: 52; Bauchi 1, Cross River 12, Edo 23, Kogi 2,
Ogun 2, Osun 3.

Dombeya buettneri K.Schum.

Meikle R.D. 857; 1949-12-21 [BR0000019776439]

Total: 30; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1,
Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 1,
Taraba 4.

Dombeya ledermannii Engl.

Soladoye, MO; Ekwuno, PO FHI 92091; 1980-2-21
[WAG.1247417]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Dombeya quinqueseta (Delile) Exell

Xeropetalum quinquesetum Delile

Lely H.B. 2; 1929-1- [K]

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba
1.

Duboscia macrocarpa Bocq.

FHI28256; 1950-12-14 [BR0000020061128]

Total: 8; Cross River 6.

Duboscia viridiflora (K.Schum.) Mildbr.

Diplantherum viridiflorum K.Schum.

Talbot, P.A.; 1729; 1912-01-01 [K006148132]

Total: 7; Cross River 3, Edo 2.

Glyphaea brevis (Biehler) Monach.

Capparis brevis Biehler

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32755; 1981-6-17
[WAG.1834789]

Total: 127; Abia 3, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross

River 15, Ebonyi 2, Edo 13, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 13, Ogun 11, Ondo 10, Osun 2, Oyo 21, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 6.

Gossypium arboreum L. — Introduced

Barter, C.; 1858-1-1 [P06722945]

Total: 28; Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Gossypium barbadense L. — Introduced

Odewo, TK; Binuyo, A FHI 100196; 1982-9-13 [WAG.1076072]

Total: 49; Edo 1, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 4.

Gossypium herbaceum L. — Introduced

J.P.R.; 1966-- [92931] [2429038487]

Total: 8; Lagos 1.

Gossypium herbaceum subsp. *herbaceum* — Introduced

Thornton, J.J. 68; 1913- [K]

Total: 1.

Gossypium hirsutum L. — Introduced

Chevalier, A.; 1905-7-1 [P06724583]

Total: 27; Jigawa 2, Lagos 1, Oyo 2.

Gossypium hirsutum var. *hirsutum* — Introduced

Barter C 1184; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 3.

Grewia barberi Burret

Wit, P; Geerling, C 1276; 1972-3-19 [WAG.1851511]

Total: 37; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kano 2, Kwara 1, Niger 16, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 2.

Grewia bicolor Juss.

Wit, HCD de; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1554; 1972-4-28 [WAG.1851864]

Total: 24; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 8, Borno 3, Jigawa 2, Katsina 3, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Grewia brunnea K.Schum.

Jones A.P.D. FHI3591; 09-05-1943 [K]

Total: 4.

Grewia carpinifolia Juss.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 220; 1983-5-12 [WAG.1851782]

Total: 74; Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 5, Ogun 18, Ondo 9, Osun 3, Oyo 19, Plateau 1.

Grewia cissoides Hutch. & Dalziel

Latilo, MG; Okeke, RE; Odewo, TK FHI 69354; 1974-5-14 [WAG.1851140]

Total: 37; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 7, Benue 2, Borno 1, Edo 1, Kwara 3, Niger 11, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Grewia flavescens Juss.

Denys E. 841; 1982-8-7 [BR0000018467192]

Total: 40; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 4, Bauchi 7, Borno 2, Ekiti 3, Jigawa 1, Katsina 3, Kebbi 1, Sokoto 3, Yobe 8, Zamfara 1.

Grewia laevigata Vahl — Introduced

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32710; 1981-6-16 [WAG0132311]

Total: 7; Edo 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Grewia lasiodiscus K.Schum.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 69987; 1973-5-12 [WAG.1972653]

Total: 37; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1, Niger 14, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 4, Taraba 2.

Grewia mollis Juss.

Daramola, BO FHI 80390; 1979-5-10 [WAG.1850495]

Total: 221; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 6, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 17, Benue 5, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 5, Gombe 2, Kaduna 20, Kano 5, Katsina 3, Kebbi 4, Kogi 13, Kwara 11, Nasarawa 2, Niger 38, Ogun 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 31, Plateau 8, Rivers 1, Sokoto 8, Taraba 12, Yobe 1, Zamfara 2.

Grewia pubescens P.Beauv.

Hambler D.J. 1073; 1961-4-4 [BR0000018772500]

Total: 86; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Ekiti 4, Enugu 3, Gombe 1, Kaduna 8, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 10, Ondo 6, Osun 4, Oyo 7, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Grewia tenax (Forssk.) Fiori

Chadara tenax Forssk.

Jackson J.A.D.; 1967-11-14 [FHI.17888.0]

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Gombe 2, Lagos 1.

Grewia tenax subsp. *tenax*

Chadara tenax Forssk.

Jackson J.A.D.619; 1967-11-14 [17888] [2013040558]

Total: 1.

Grewia villosa Willd.

Latilo, MG FHI 63519; 1971-10-24 [WAG.1850442]

Total: 15; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Taraba 4.

Helicteres isora L. — Introduced

Onochie C.F.A. FHI3695; 28-03-1944 [K]

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Hermannia tigreensis Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Dalziel J.M. 414; 1910- [K]

Total: 6; Bauchi 2, Katsina 1.

Hibiscus acetosella Welw. ex Hiern —

Introduced

Guile D.P.M. B6; 1966-10 [K]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Hibiscus articulatus Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1923; 1966-9-13 [WAG.1076370]

Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1.

Hibiscus articulatus var. *articulatus*

Lely H.V. 206; 20-05-1921 [K]

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Hibiscus articulatus var. *glabrescens* Hochr.

Onyeagocha S.C. FHI27266; 20-08-1951 [k]

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Nasarawa 1.

Hibiscus calyphyllus Cav. — Introduced

Foster G.W. 365; 10-02-1909 [K]

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Oyo 1.

Hibiscus cannabinus L.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1145; 1972-4-26 [WAG.1076717]

Total: 60; Bauchi 5, Borno 5, Enugu 1, Gombe 4, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Hibiscus congestiflorus Hochr.

Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwuno, PO FHI 68106; 1973-11-18 [WAG.1076758]

Total: 7; Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 3.

Hibiscus diversifolius Jacq.

; 1992-9-1 [FR-0014211]

Total: 3; Yobe 2.

Hibiscus gourmania Hutch. & Dalziel

Gourmania grewoioides A.Chev.

Ejiofor M.C. FHI19831; 25-02-1950 [K]

Total: 2; Niger 1.

Hibiscus grewoioides Baker f. — Endemic

Talbot P.A. 1343; -- [K000240752]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Niger 2.

Hibiscus lobatus (Murray) Kuntze

Solandra lobata Murray

Lawlor D.W.; Hall J.B. 249; 11-08-1962 [K]

Total: 6; Bauchi 2, Plateau 1.

Hibiscus lonchosepalus Hochr.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P 832; 1971-11-2 [WAG.1077027]

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Hibiscus lunariifolius Willd. — Introduced

T.K.Odewo; 2012-12-29 [2085]3808442123

Total: 19; Cross River 1, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Osun 3, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Hibiscus micranthus L.f.

Sharland 851; 1979-10 [K]

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Hibiscus mutabilis L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Hibiscus noldeae Baker f.

Ariwaodo J.O. 1048; 30-11-1966 [K]

Total: 9; Cross River 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Hibiscus owariensis P.Beauv.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 400; 1978-5-10 [WAG.1884037]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1.

Hibiscus panduriformis Burm.f.

; 2004-2-24 [FR-0034798]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Borno 4, Gombe 1, Kebbi 1, Niger 1.

Hibiscus physaloides Guill. & Perr.

Meer, PPC van 521; 1968-1-10 [WAG.1077367]

Total: 15; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 4.

Hibiscus rosa-sinensis L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 167; 1960-5-5 [WAG.1077440]

Total: 19; Lagos 8, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 7.

Hibiscus rostellatus Guill. & Perr.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65914; 1972-10-25

[WAG.1077530]

Total: 39; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Oyo 8, Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Hibiscus sabdariffa L.

Latilo, MG FHI 63844; 1971-10-19 [WAG.1077651]

Total: 43; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Cross River 2, Gombe 2, Kano 1, Lagos 8, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 8, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Hibiscus schizopetalus (Mast.) Hook.f. —

Introduced

Hibiscus × *rosa-sinensis* f. *schizopetalus* Mast.

Ejiofor M.C. FHI15276; 06-06-1949 [K]

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Hibiscus scotellii Baker f.

; 1995-9-20 [FR-0019545]

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Hibiscus sidiformis Baill.

Barter C. ; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 1.

Hibiscus sineaculeatus F.D.Wilson

Keay, R.W.J. 20117; 1947-10-20 [K000580890]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Jigawa 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Hibiscus squamosus Hochr.

Banter 1165; 00-01-1900 [K000240765]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Hibiscus sterculiifolius (Guill. & Perr.) Steud.

Pariti sterculiifolium Guill. & Perr.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63138; 1972-1-20 [WAG.1305880]

Total: 5; Enugu 2, Osun 1, Taraba 1.

Hibiscus surattensis L.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1081; 1971-12-28 [WAG.1077890]

Total: 50; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 11, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 5, Oyo 5, Rivers 1.

Hibiscus tiliaceus L.

Wit HCD de [WAG.1078059]

Total: 13; Abia 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 3.

Hibiscus tiliaceus subsp. *tiliaceus*

Anderson D. 1417; 17-11-1965 [K]

Total: 1.

Hibiscus trionum L.

; 1996-9-8 [FR-0014230]

Total: 5; Borno 5.

Hibiscus vitifolius L.

[K.65693.0]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Delta 1, Kogi 1, Osun 1.

Hibiscus vitifolius subsp. *vitifolius*

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Olorunfemi, J; Emwiogbon, JA 978; 1971-11-17 [WAG.1078222]

Total: 1; Delta 1.

Hildegardia barteri (Mast.) Kosterm.

Sterculia barteri Mast.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1045; 1965-2-15 [WAG.1833354]

Total: 27; Abia 3, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1.

Kleinhovia hospita L. — Introduced

Charter J.R. FHI31288; 1957-7 [K]

Total: 10; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Kosteletzkya adoensis (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Mast.

Hibiscus adoensis Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2100; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1078498]

Total: 10; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Kosteletzkya buettneri Gürke

Latilo, MG FHI 64741; 1971-12-4 [WAG.1078533]

Total: 5; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Kosteletzkya grantii (Mast.) Garcke

Hibiscus grantii Mast.

; -- [O.J. Blanchard, Jr. 3422 (FLAS)] [3818265725]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Kosteletzkya semota O.J.Blanch.

Kosteletzkya stellata Hutch. & Dalziel

Millen, H. 53; 1896-3-26 [K000240523]

Total: 6; Lagos 3.

Kydia calycina Roxb. — Introduced

s.n.; 1929-1-20 [US 1716378]

Total: 1; Kano 1.

Leptonychia echinocarpa K.Schum.

Latilo, MG FHI 67745; 1973-2-28 [WAG.1241391]

Total: 8; Cross River 7.

Leptonychia macrantha K.Schum.

K. Schmitt; T.O. IbiangSchmitt 243; 1994-12-13 [976639] [1261904346]

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1.

Leptonychia moyesiae Cheek

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI5843; 17-05-1946 [K000540432]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Leptonychia multiflora K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1858; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1241563]

Total: 17; Cross River 17.

Leptonychia pallida K.Schum.

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C. A32/47; 1946-5-16 [BR0000018105056]

Total: 12; Cross River 11.

Leptonychia pubescens Keay

Pilz, GE 1940; 1977-3-31 [WAG.1241624]

Total: 34; Benue 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 12.

Malachra capitata (L.)L — Introduced

Sida capitata L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Malachra radiata (L.) L.

Sida radiata L.

[Barter] 1547 [K006371764]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Malvastrum corchorifolium (Desr.) Britton
ex Small — Introduced

Malva corchorifolia Desr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Malvastrum coromandelianum (L.) Garcke

— Introduced

Malva coromandeliana L.

Mensah, K J; Ugborogho, R E; 1982-11-7

[Kk1895]1933004521

Total: 18; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 10.

Malvastrum coromandelianum subsp.
coromandelianum — Introduced

Malva coromandeliana L.

Thorton T. ; 26-08-1913 [K]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Malvaviscus arboreus Dill. ex Cav. —

Introduced

Hibiscus malvaviscus L.

Okaranwaolu O.O; 2008-3-20 [435]3808442182

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Mansonia altissima (A.Chev.) A.Chev.

Achantia altissima A.Chev.

Hunder, FD 91; 1962-1-1 [WAG.1241745]

Total: 27; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 4, Lagos 1,
Ogun 2, Ondo 7, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Mansonia altissima var. *altissima*

Achantia altissima A.Chev.

Wit P. 2273; 19727-25 [K]

Total: 1.

Mansonia altissima var. *kamerunia* Jacq.-
Fél.

Amachi J.O. FHI24334; 00-01-1900 [K000541341]

Total: 1.

Melochia corchorifolia L.

Denys, E 832; 1982-8-5 [WAG.1242036]

Total: 43; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Borno 6,
Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi
3, Kwara 3, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 1,
Sokoto 2, Taraba 4, Yobe 1.

Melochia melissifolia Benth.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 66277; 1972-10-20

[WAG.1241964]

Total: 57; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Bauchi
1, Edo 7, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 3, Kaduna
1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo
2, Osun 3, Oyo 10, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Melochia melissifolia var. *mollis* K.Schum.

Latilo, MG FHI 61434; 1971-11-4 [WAG.1241966]

Total: 5; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Edo 1.

Microcos africana (Hook.f.) Burret

Omphacarpus africanus Hook.f.

Onochie C.; Others; 1947-1-26 [20675] [2013040698]

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Microcos barombiensis (K.Schum.) Cheek

Grewia barombiensis K.Schum.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1089; 1971-12-28

[WAG.1851538]

Total: 16; Cross River 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 2,
Osun 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Microcos coriacea (Mast.) Burret

Grewia coriacea Mast.

A. H. Gentry & G. E. Pilz 32710; 1981-6-16 [US
3404815]

Total: 25; Edo 10, Ogun 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Microcos malacocarpa (Mast.) Burret

Grewia malacocarpa Mast.

Meer, PPC van 688; 1968-3-26 [WAG0132420]

Total: 27; Cross River 2, Edo 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo
12.

Microcos oligoneura (Sprague) Burret

Grewia oligoneura Sprague

Mr. and Mrs. P.A. Talbot 1460; 1911-01-01

[K001577884]

Total: 3; Edo 1.

Nesogordonia kabingaensis (K.Schum.)

Capuron ex R.Germ.

Cistanthera kabingaensis K.Schum.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32660; 1981-6-14

[WAG.1242199]

Total: 5; Delta 1, Ogun 4.

Nesogordonia papaverifera (A.Chev.)

Capuron ex N.Hallé

Cistanthera papaverifera A.Chev.

Onochie, C.F.A. ; 1943-4-17 [P00532543]

Total: 16; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Ochroma pyramidale (Cav. ex Lam.) Urb.

— Introduced

Bombax pyramidale Cav. ex Lam.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1549; 1966-5-22 [WAG.1392159]
Total: 4; Oyo 4.

Octolobus spectabilis Welw.

Richards P.W. 3115; 1935-2-14 [BR0000018113532]
Total: 25; Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Ekiti 1,
Enugu 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2,
Sokoto 1.

Pachira aquatica Aubl. — Introduced

Felix ; 2005-10-12 [246]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Pachira glabra Pasq. — Introduced

Nicholas 2428; -- [BR0000014185069]

Total: 7; Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Pachira insignis (Sw.) Savigny —

Introduced

Carolinea insignis Sw.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1346; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1392211]

Total: 4; Oyo 4.

Pavonia kotschy Hochst. ex Webb

Jackson G. 2571; 22-03-1963 [K]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Nasarawa 1.

Pavonia schimperiana Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Ekwuno P.O. 164; 15-11-1975 [K]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Pavonia senegalensis (Cav.) Leistner

Hibiscus senegalensis Cav.

Leeuw, PN de 1201; 1964-10-24 [WAG.1079398]

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Zamfara 1.

Pavonia urens Cav.

Hepper F.N. 2139; 1958-2-23 [BR0000017820509]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1,
Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6.

Pavonia urens var. *urens*

Tuley P. 2087; 19-11-1969 [K]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 1,
Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Pterygota bequaertii De Wild.

Kennedy J.D. 1633; -- [BR0000018114294]

Total: 14; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 7.

Pterygota macrocarpa K.Schum.

Oladoyinbo, A FHI 43365; 1959-9-2 [WAG.1242362]

Total: 21; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1,
Ogun 3, Ondo 5, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Pterygota mildbraedii Engl.

Chapman, J.D. 4468; 1976-05-12 [K005071184]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Rhodognaphalon brevicuspe (Sprague)

Roberty

Bombax brevicuspe Sprague

Latilo, M.G. 9 [K005969311]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Scaphopetalum acuminatum Engl. &

K.Krause

Onochie, C.F.A.; Okafor, J.C. FHI36155; 1957-01-24
[K006104254]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Scaphopetalum amoenum A.Chev.

J. Ntui; E. BebiemNtui 748; 1995-11-4 [1036345]
[1258241291]

Total: 7; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4.

Scaphopetalum blackii Mast.

Total: 7; Cross River 2.

Scaphopetalum blackii var. *letestui*

(Pellegr.) N.Hallé

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 1264; 25-03-1905 [K]

Total: 7; Cross River 2.

Scaphopetalum brunneopurpureum Engl. &

K.Krause

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67784; 1973-3-5
[WAG.1832659]

Total: 6; Cross River 6.

Scaphopetalum parvifolium Baker f.

Ariwaodo, JO 642; 1977-5-9 [WAG.1832562]

Total: 30; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 1, Cross River
17, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Rivers 2.

Scaphopetalum talbotii Baker f.

Percy Amaury Talbot 1562; 1912-- [BM000510222]

Total: 1.

Scaphopetalum zenkeri K.Schum.

Gentry 32878; 1981-6-20 [193495] [1259198022]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Sida acuta Burm.f.

Daramola, BO FHI 85476; 1977-1-11

[WAG.1079917]

Total: 110; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2,
Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ekiti 1,
Enugu 2, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos
10, Niger 4, Ogun 14, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 26,
Plateau 1, Taraba 7.

Sida alba L.

Kennedy J.D. 3026; 1936-1- [K]

Total: 19; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Sokoto 3, Taraba 1.

Sida cordata (Burm.f.) Borss.Waalk. — Introduced

Melochia cordata Burm.f.

Usang felix; 2005-10-10 [155]3913474678

Total: 12; Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Oyo 4.

Sida cordifolia L. — Introduced

[SANT.11836.0]

Total: 64; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 4, Sokoto 2, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Sida cordifolia subsp. *cordifolia*

Latilo, MG; Okeke, RE; Odewo, TK FHI 69360; 1974-5-15 [WAG.1080098]

Total: 1.

Sida cordifolia subsp. *maculata* (Cav.)

Marais

Keay R. FHI37203; 1957-11-22 [BR0000017187015]

Total: 7; Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Sida hyssopifolia C.Presl

Ibhanesebhor, G; Osanyinlusi FHI 96939; 1982-7-16 [WAG.1080206]

Total: 50; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 24, Taraba 1.

Sida javensis Cav.

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO FHI 92633; 1980-2-1 [WAG.1080271]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Oyo 5.

Sida linifolia Juss. ex Cav.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 134; 1977-10-6 [WAG.1080378]

Total: 52; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 4, Imo 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Taraba 2.

Sida ovata Forssk.

Denys, E 780; 1982-8-2 [WAG.1080442]

Total: 21; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 11, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 3, Yobe 1.

Sida planicaulis Cav. — Introduced

; -- [65836]2429014292

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Sida rhombifolia L.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 302; 1978-5-5 [WAG.1080713]

Total: 132; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Bauchi 6, Borno 2, Cross River 4, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 6, Kaduna 6, Kebbi 3, Kogi 6, Kwara 2, Lagos 12, Niger 2, Ogun 14, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 22, Plateau 8, Sokoto 1, Taraba 9.

Sida rhombifolia subsp. *alnifolia* (L.) Ugbor. — Introduced

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1413; 1972-4-21 [WAG.1080698]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Sida rhombifolia subsp. *rhombifolia*

R.W.J. Keay & D.P. Stanfield 37066; 1957-6-19 [BR0000018691726]

Total: 1.

Sida rhombifolia var. *afroscabrida* Verdc.

Literature

Total: 0.

Sida rhombifolia var. *scabrida* (Wight & Arn.) Mast.

Mekle R.D. 1410; 11-04-1950 [K]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 3.

Sida spinosa L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63104; 1972-1-7 [WAG.1080746]

Total: 20; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 8, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 2.

Sida ulmifolia Mill. — Introduced

R.W.J. Keay & D.P. Stanfield 37066; 1957-6-19 [BR0000018691726]

Total: 1.

Sida urens L.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 270; 1978-5-3 [WAG.1080866]

Total: 37; Bauchi 3, Edo 1, Ekiti 6, Kaduna 5, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Sterculia oblonga Mast.

Thompson, H. 6; 1906-3-6 [K000240968]

Total: 25; Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 10, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1.

Sterculia oblongata R.Br.

Nodza G.;Eze T.E; 2020-10-29 [8846] [3808442270]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Sterculia rhinopetala K.Schum.

Gledhill D. 814; 1968-2-2 [BR0000018071375]

Total: 26; Cross River 2, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Sterculia setigera Delile

Geerling C. 4226; 1971-9-28 [BR0000018071962]

Total: 29; Bauchi 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Sterculia tragacantha Lindl.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66016; 1973-2-22

[WAG.1832748]

Total: 54; Cross River 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 4, Oyo 10, Taraba 2.

Theobroma cacao L. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2011; 1977-4-26 [WAG.1975458]

Total: 13; Cross River 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Thespesia garckeana F.Hoffm.

Lowe, J 1568; 1968-11-16 [WAG.1075979]

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Katsina 3.

Thespesia garckeana var. *garckeana*

Daggash M. FHI35009; 03-09-1956 [K]

Total: 1.

Thespesia populnea (L.) Sol. ex Corrêa — Introduced

Hibiscus populneus L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Triplochiton scleroxylon K.Schum.

Oladoyinbo, A 43363; 1959-9-2 [WAG.1839629]

Total: 39; Cross River 2, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Sokoto 1.

Triumfetta annua L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Triumfetta brachyceras K.Schum.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 287; 1977-10-12

[WAG.1856939]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Triumfetta cordifolia A.Rich.

[SANT.11811.0]

Total: 32; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Delta 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Triumfetta cordifolia var. *cordifolia*

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86217;

1978-5-3 [WAG.1856473]

Total: 1.

Triumfetta cordifolia var. *tomentosa*

Sprague

Literature

Total: 0.

Triumfetta eriophlebia Hook.f.

Thomas, N.W. (Mr.); 195; 1911-01-01 [K000197877]

Total: 2.

Triumfetta jaegeri Hochr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Triumfetta lepidota K.Schum.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1167; 1972-4-28

[WAG.1856971]

Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Niger 1.

Triumfetta pentandra A.Rich.

Swarbrick, John T; 1960-12-11 [E00957143]

Total: 18; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1.

Triumfetta pentandra var. *pentandra*

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86207;

1978-5-3 [WAG.1856926]

Total: 1.

Triumfetta rhomboidea Jacq.

Pilz, GE 2259; 1978-1-8 [WAG.1855467]

Total: 66; Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Edo 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 9, Ogun 2, Oyo 20, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Triumfetta setulosa Mast.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2074; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1857082]

Total: 11; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Niger 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Triumfetta tomentosa Bojer ex Bouton

Sharland R.E. 1354; 19-07-1980 [K]

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 4.

Triumfetta welwitschii Mast. — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [309A]1990271829

Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Urena lobata L.

Pilz, GE 1822; 1976-10-24 [WAG.1081302]

Total: 127; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 5, Gombe 4, Imo 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 3, Kogi 4, Kwara 5, Lagos 8, Niger 6, Ogun 9, Osun 1, Oyo 18, Plateau 9, Rivers 4, Taraba 3.

Urena lobata subsp. *lobata*

Olorunfemi, J FHI 55008; 1964-9-15 [WAG.1081377]

Total: 1.

Waltheria indica L. — Introduced

Daramola, BO s.n.; 1985-12-6 [WAG.1839466]

Total: 86; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Borno 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Niger 3, Ogun 5, Osun 3, Oyo 19, Plateau 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Yobe 2.

Wissadula amplissima (L.) R.E.Fr.

Sida amplissima L.

Dr Kadiri; Other; 2012-10-20 [4610] [3808440360]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Wissadula hernandioides (L'Hér.) Garcke — Introduced

Sida hernandioides L'Hér.

Schlechter, R. (Coll. G); -- [G-G-178867/1]1144801599

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Wissadula periplocifolia (L.) Thwaites — Introduced

Sida periplocifolia L.

Leeuw, PN de; Magaji, SO 1972; 1967-10-6 [WAG.1081490]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Osun 1.

Wissadula rostrata (Schumach. & Thonn.) Hook.

Sida rostrata Schumach. & Thonn.

Lely H.V. 631; 23-09-1921 [K]

Total: 31; Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Osun 1.

THYMELAEACEAE

Craterosiphon scandens Engl. & Gilg

Thomson, W.C. [K001208106]

Total: 8; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Taraba 1.

Craterosiphon scandens var. *scandens*

Thomson, W.C. 73; -- [K001208106]

Total: 1.

Dicranolepis baertsiana De Wild. &

T.Durand — Introduced

Croat, TB 53489; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1838598]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Dicranolepis disticha Planch.

Meer, PPC van 994; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1583941]

Total: 41; Cross River 9, Edo 17, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 1.

Dicranolepis grandiflora Engl.

Latilo, MG FHI 61433; 1971-11-4 [WAG.1942461]

Total: 149; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 2, Cross River 11, Delta 2, Edo 24, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 20, Ondo 27, Osun 4, Oyo 17, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 17.

Dicranolepis persei Cummins

Olorunfemi J.; 1958-6-7 [38053] [2013041527]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Dicranolepis polygaloides Gilg ex H.Pearson

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.; 1946-5-18 [18629] [2013040615]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Dicranolepis vestita Engl.

J.D. Chapman 4616; 1977-2-3 [3024284]

[1260398211]

Total: 13; Cross River 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Gnidia bambutana Gilg & Ledermann ex Engl.

Hepper F.N. 1742; 1958-1-22 [BR0000018471076]

Total: 7; Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Gnidia chrysantha (Solms ex Schweinf.) Gilg

Arthrosolen chrysanthus Solms ex Schweinf.

Morton, JK K 376; 1955-4-16 [WAG.1844176]

Total: 37; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 14, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Plateau 4, Zamfara 1.

Gnidia foliosa (H.Pearson) Engl.

Arthrosolen foliosus H.Pearson

Daramola B.O. 279; 1993-7-30 [105094]2013044346

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1.

Gnidia involucrata Steud. ex A.Rich.

Morton, JK K 362; 1955-4-16 [WAG.1855249]

Total: 22; Bauchi 4, Cross River 2, Kaduna 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Plateau 5, Sokoto 1.

Gnidia mollis C.H.Wright — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Lachnaea grandiflora (L.f.) Baill. —

Introduced

Passerina grandiflora L.f.

Talbot 3693; -- [K000322556]

Total: 2; Rivers 1.

Lasiosiphon glaucus Fresen.

Chapman, J.D. 3339; 1974-11-04 [K006057307]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Lasiosiphon kraussianus (Meisn.) Meisn.

Gnidia kraussiana Meisn.

Geerling, C 3483; 1971-3-21 [WAG.1855178]

Total: 38; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 5, Plateau 10, Sokoto 1.

Octolepis casearia Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1659; 1971-5-18 [WAG.1232689]

Total: 48; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 1, Cross River 40, Edo 1.

Peddiea africana Harv. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Peddiea fischeri Engl.

Dr Kadiri A.B.; Others; 2008-12-1 [514] [3808439267]

Total: 5; Anambra 1, Taraba 4.

Synaptolepis alternifolia Oliv. — Introduced

Meikle 1068; 1950-1-20 [3311602]1260715552

Total: 3; Kwara 1, Niger 2.

Synaptolepis retusa H.Pearson

Meikle, R.D. ; 1960-1-20 [P00615946]

Total: 5; Niger 1.

BIXACEAE

Bixa orellana L. — Introduced

Kennedy, J.D. 1742; 1933-12 (BR)

Total: 44; Anambra 2, Cross River 3, Edo 5, Kaduna 3, Lagos 6, Ogun 5, Oyo 14, Taraba 1.

Cochlospermum planchonii Hook.f. ex

Planch.

Vogel, E. 121; 1841-09 (K)

Total: 125; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 4, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ekiti 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 10, Kano 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 7, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 18, Ogun 11, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 26, Sokoto 2, Taraba 3.

Cochlospermum tinctorium Perrier ex

A.Rich.

Ataholo, M. 1574; 1995-10-28 (FR)

Total: 75; Abia 1, Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 21, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Cochlospermum vitifolium (Willd.) Spreng.

— Introduced

Bombax vitifolium Willd.

Daramola B.O.; Binuyo A.; 1982-12-12

[99491]2013044955

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

DIPTEROCARPACEAE

Monotes glaber Sprague — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [111A] [1990271706]

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Monotes kerstingii Gilg

Onochie, CFA FHI 40252; 1995-6-25

[WAG.1785920]

Total: 32; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Zamfara 2.

MORINGACEAE

Moringa oleifera Lam. — Introduced

Guilandina moringa L.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70712; 1973-3-6

[WAG.1111278]

Total: 82; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 18, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 10, Oyo 8, Plateau 1.

CARICACEAE

Carica papaya L. — Introduced

Wit, P 557; 1971-10-6 [WAG0370088]

Total: 50; Abia 1, Kano 2, Lagos 18, Niger 2, Ogun 8, Osun 4, Oyo 12.

Cylicomorpha solmsii (Urb.) Urb.

Jacaratia solmsii Urb.

Literature

Total: 0.

CAPPARACEAE

Boscia integrifolia J.St.-Hil.

Jibrin 5152; 1943-11-13 [K000354908]

Total: 3; Kebbi 2.

Boscia salicifolia Oliv.

Leeuw, PN de 32; 1961-2-9 [WAG.1511698]

Total: 15; Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Ondo 1, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 2.

Boscia senegalensis Lam.

Olorunfemi, J FHI 55732; 1965-3-15 [WAG.1511778]
Total: 18; Bauchi 9, Borno 2, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Buchholzia coriacea Engl.

P.A. Talbot & D.A. Talbot 3645; 1914--
[BM000802369]
Total: 27; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2, Edo 11, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Rivers 1.

Cadaba farinosa Forssk.

Denys E. [BR0000015119759]
Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 1, Katsina 6, Taraba 1.

Cadaba farinosa subsp. *farinosa*

Denys E. 632; -- [BR0000015119759]
Total: 1.

Cadaba glandulosa Forssk.

Literature
Total: 0.

Cadaba rotundifolia Forssk. — Introduced

Literature
Total: 0.

Capparis brassii DC.

Onochie, CFA FHI 40256; 1958-7-5 [WAG.1512115]
Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Capparis corymbosa Lam.

Daggash M. FHI24960; 10-04-1949 [K]
Total: 1.

Capparis decidua (Forssk.) Edgew.

Sodada decidua Forssk.
; -- [67163]2429013641
Total: 2; Borno 2.

Capparis erythrocarpos Isert

[K.531.0]
Total: 3; Kaduna 2.

Capparis erythrocarpos var. *erythrocarpos*

; -- [531]2428999992
Total: 2; Kaduna 1.

Capparis fascicularis DC.

Meikle, R.D. 1366; 1950-4-3 [16178]
Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Katsina 4.

Capparis fascicularis var. *fascicularis*

; -- [FR-0034822]3046054783
Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Katsina 3.

Capparis sepiaria L.

Geerling, C 3442; 1971-2-15 [WAG.1512413]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Niger 1.

Capparis tenera Dalzell — Introduced

Daramola, BO; Adebunsi, JK FHI 38413; 1958-9-10
[WAG.1392553]
Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Capparis tomentosa Lam.

Geerling, C 3450; 1971-2-26 [WAG.1392700]
Total: 20; Bauchi 8, Borno 1, Kano 2, Plateau 2, Zamfara 1.

Capparis viminea Oliv.

Daramola B.O. Binuyo A. FHI61261; 24-02-1968 [K]
Total: 6; Benue 1, Niger 1.

Capparis viminea var. *viminea*

Daramola B.O. Binuyo A. FHI38413; 24-10-1958 [K]
Total: 5; Benue 1, Niger 1.

Crateva adansonii DC.

Chapman, J.D. 5293; 1978-3-13 [K000354945]
Total: 24; Bauchi 4, Gombe 4, Kaduna 4, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1.

Crateva adansonii subsp. *adansonii*

Leeuw, PN de 61; 1961-3-5 [WAG.1218827]
Total: 1.

Crateva eminens (Hook.f.) Christenh. & Byng

Euadenia eminens Hook.f.
Rouland S.N.; -- [BR0000015102805]
Total: 1.

Crateva monticola (Gilg & Gilg-Ben.)

Christenh. & Byng
Euadenia monticola Gilg & Gilg-Ben.
Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70155; 1974-5-15
[WAG.1218968]
Total: 21; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Crateva religiosa G.Forst. — Introduced

6967; 1978-5-17 [6967]2302319447
Total: 3; Kaduna 2, Lagos 1.

Maerua angolensis DC.

[FHI.1418.0]
Total: 33; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 7, Kano 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Taraba 2.

Maerua angolensis subsp. *angolensis*

Latilo, MG; Odewo, TK FHI 69405; 1974-5-28
[WAG.1219113]
Total: 1.

Maerua crassifolia Forssk.
Bartha, R s.n.; 1967-8-1 [WAG.1219211]
Total: 3; Bauchi 1.

Maerua duchesnei (De Wild.) F.White
Capparis duchesnei De Wild.
Meer, PPC van 669; 1968-3-8 [WAG.1219268]
Total: 12; Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 2, Lagos 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Maerua oblongifolia (Forssk.) A.Rich.
Capparis oblongifolia Forssk.
Geerling, C 3516; 1971-3-30 [WAG.1219454]
Total: 7; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Zamfara 1.

Maerua pseudopetalosa (Gilg & Gilg-Ben.) DeWolf
Courbonia pseudopetalosa Gilg & Gilg-Ben.
Geerling, C 3417; 1971-1-16 [WAG.1219490]
Total: 12; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Maerua triphylla A.Rich. — Introduced
Dalziel, J. McEwan; -- [B 10 0153700]
Total: 2.

Ritchiea albersii Gilg
Hepper F.N. 1904; -- [BR0000014005176]
Total: 7; Cross River 1, Sokoto 1.

Ritchiea capparoides (Andrews) Britten
Crateva capparoides Andrews
Geerling, C 3430; 1971-1-28 [WAG.1219785]
Total: 48; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Edo 10, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Taraba 1.

Ritchiea erecta Hook.f.
Meer, PPC van 1126; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1219824]
Total: 22; Cross River 10, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Ritchiea macrantha Pax & Gilg
Literature
Total: 0.

Ritchiea reflexa (Thonn. & Schumach.) Gilg & Gilg-Ben.
Capparis reflexa Thonn. & Schumach.
Mann G. 263; [K]
Total: 2; Lagos 1.

Ritchiea simplicifolia Oliv.
Stone R.H. 16; 28-06-1955 [K]
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

CLEOMACEAE

Cleome afrospina Iltis
Kennedy J.D. 365; 00-01-1900 [K]
Total: 11; Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Lagos 2.

Cleome foliosa Hook.f.
Literature
Total: 0.

Cleome foliosa var. *foliosa*
Literature
Total: 0.

Cleome gynandra L.
Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70764; 1973-3-12 [WAG.1219010]
Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.

Cleome iberidella Welw. ex Oliv.
Hepper F.N. 1767; -- [BR0000015091901]
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Taraba 4.

Cleome monophylla L.
Daramola, BO FHI 62715; 1969-5-16 [WAG.1393283]
Total: 20; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Cleome polyanthera Schweinf. & Gilg
Dalziel J.M. 179; 20-07-1909 [K]
Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Cleome rutidosperma DC.
[US 593328]
Total: 39; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 2, Benue 2, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 3, Imo 2, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Cleome rutidosperma var. *rutidosperma*
Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 434; 1978-5-15 [WAG.1392939]
Total: 1.

Cleome scaposa DC.
Inovaer B. 188; 15-12-1921 [K]
Total: 2; Nasarawa 1.

Cleome schimperi Pax
Wit P.; Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O. FHI66699; 10-05-1972 [K]
Total: 3.

Cleome speciosa Raf. — Introduced
Kennedy J.D. 427; 1929- [K]
Total: 1.

Cleome spinosa Jacq. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Cleome viscosa L.

illegible [BR0000015101419]

Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Bayelsa 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4, Lagos 1, Niger 5, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Cleome viscosa var. *viscosa*

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 375; 1983-5-18 [WAG.1393694]

Total: 1.

Sieruela schimperi (Pax) Roalson &

J.C.Hall

Cleome schimperi Pax

Literature

Total: 0.

BRASSICACEAE

Aethionema saxatile (L.) W.T.Aiton —

Introduced

Thlaspi saxatile L.

Anonymous collector; 1883-6- [B 10 0157503]

Total: 1.

Arabis alpina L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Brassica juncea (L.) Czern. — Introduced

Sinapis juncea L.

Ohaeri A.O. 2745; 06-06-1978 [ABUH]

Total: 1.

Brassica oleracea L. — Introduced

Bolaji Hafsoh; 2013-4-15 [5575]3808442539

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Cardamine africana L.

Hepper, FN 1583; 1957-12-12 [WAG.1750477]

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Cardamine hirsuta L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cardamine trichocarpa Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 2059; 1972-5-11

[WAG.1750038]

Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Crambe hispanica L. — Introduced

; -- [CR 3008]120957281

Total: 4.

Crambe hispanica subsp. *abyssinica*

(Hochst. ex R.E.Fr.) Prina — Introduced

; -- [VIR602000028]210219833

Total: 1.

Farsetia stylosa R.Br.

; 2004-2-27 [FR-0034813]

Total: 4; Borno 2.

Lepidium sativum L. — Introduced

Etkin 118; 1988-3-16 [58742]

Total: 3; Kaduna 2, Kano 1.

Rorippa madagascariensis (DC.) H.Hara

Nasturtium madagascariense DC.

Daramola, BO FHI 70322; 1973-2-16

[WAG.1470817]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Edo 1.

SALVADORACEAE

Salvadora persica L.

Rosevear D.R.; 1949-05-20 [BR0000018893465]

Total: 7; Borno 3.

Salvadora persica var. *persica*

Rosevear D.R. FHI26607; 1949-5-20

[BR0000018893465]

Total: 1.

PENTADIPLANDRACEAE

Pentadiplandra brazzeana Baill.

Bebiem 1167; 1996-1-8 [1054369]1258261024

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Imo 1.

BALANOPHORACEAE

Thonningia sanguinea Vahl

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3768; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1159521]

Total: 16; Benue 1, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2,

Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

OLACACEAE

Aptandra zenkeri Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1871; 1971-1-1 [WAG.1121228]

Total: 27; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 6, Oyo 14.

Coula edulis Baill.

Kennedy J.D. 1563; -- [BR0000017035019]

Total: 19; Cross River 3, Edo 2.

Diogoa retivenia (S.Moore) Breteler —

Endemic

Strombosia retivenia S.Moore

Brenan J.P.M. & Onochie C. 8996; 1928-2-12

[BR0000017035514]

Total: 11; Cross River 3, Edo 5.

Diogoa zenkeri (Engl.) Exell & Mendonça

Strombosiosis zenkeri Engl.

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1465; -- [K000226300]

Total: 6; Cross River 3, Edo 3.

Heisteria parvifolia Sm.

Pilz, GE 2580; 1980-11-25 [WAG.1121892]

Total: 47; Anambra 2, Cross River 16, Edo 6, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Rivers 2.

Octoknema affinis Pierre ex Tiegh.

Usang felix; 2015-10-7 [371] [3913474436]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1.

Octoknema borealis Hutch. & Dalziel

1959-3-15 [2252243489]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Olox gambecola Baill.

Daramola, BO; Adebuseri, JK FHI 38428; 1958-9-18

[WAG.1122480]

Total: 25; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Olox latifolia Engl.

Alwyn H. Gentry; George E. Pilz 32919; 1981-6-21

[729032] [1261448811]

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Olox mannii Oliv.

Latilo, MG FHI 67782; 1973-3-3 [WAG.1122750]

Total: 61; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 42, Ebonyi 1, Niger 2.

Olox subscorpioidea Oliv.

Pilz, GE 1983; 1977-4-25 [WAG.1122876]

Total: 121; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 6, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 14, Delta 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 15, Nasarawa 2, Niger 8, Ogun 12, Ondo 2, Osun 7, Oyo 14, Plateau 4, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Ongokea gore (Hua) Pierre

Aptandra gore Hua

Kennedy J.D. 1650; -- [BR0000015993601]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Ptychopetalum petiolatum Oliv.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67785; 1973-5-22

[WAG.1123378]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Kogi 2.

Ptychopetalum petiolatum var. *petiolatum*

Talbot P.A. 1747; 1912- [K]

Total: 1.

Strombosia grandifolia Hook.f. ex Benth.

Brenan J.P.M. & Richards P.W.8843; 1948-1-19

[BR0000013963880]

Total: 47; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 10, Edo 15, Ondo 3, Oyo 5.

Strombosia pustulata Oliv.

Brenan J.P.M. 9068; 1948-2-19 [BR0000015996824]

Total: 50; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 16, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 10, Lagos 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Strombosia pustulata var. *lucida* (J.Leonard)

Villiers

Strombosia glaucescens var. *lucida* J.Léonard

Akpabla, G.K. 883; 1943-10-14 [K005805165]

Total: 1; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1.

Strombosia pustulata var. *pustulata*

Onochie C.F.A. FHI33456; 29-08-1953 [K]

Total: 3; Kaduna 2.

Strombosia scheffleri Engl.

Schmitt 459; 1995-2-19 [976817]1261904528

Total: 9; Cross River 3, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Strombosia zenkeri Engl.

Brenan J.P.M. 9227; 1948-3-5 [BR0000015999801]

Total: 3; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Strombosiosis tetrandra Engl.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32865; 1981-6-20

[WAG.1123864]

Total: 15; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4.

Ximения americana L.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, HCD de; Daramola, BO FHI 65400;

1972-4-28 [WAG.1123995]

Total: 51; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 3, Gombe 4, Kaduna 7, Kano 3, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 9, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Ximения caffra Sond. — Introduced

Ugwuzor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [93C] [1990271936]

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

OPILIACEAE

Opilia amentacea Roxb.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 78; 1979-4-21
[WAG.1129676]

Total: 19; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Urobotrya congolana (Baill.) Hiepko

Opilia congolana Baill.

Percy Amaury Talbot s.n.; 1911-- [BM000839840]
Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5.

Urobotrya congolana subsp. *congolana*

Opilia congolana Baill.

Meer, PPC van 1137; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1129813]
Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5.

SANTALACEAE

Okoubaka aubrevillei Pellegr. & Normand

Octoknema okoubaka Aubrév. & Pellegr.

A.F.A. Lamb 1562; -- [BR0000018894240]
Total: 3; Edo 1, Kogi 1.

Santalum album L. — Introduced

Okeke, RE FHI 38447; 1959-5-12 [WAG.1324217]
Total: 4; Borno 1, Kogi 1, Ogun 2.

Thesium leucanthum Gilg

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1422; 1972-4-21
[WAG.1324607]

Total: 6; Plateau 5.

Thesium schweinfurthii Engl.

Stanfield D.P. FHI 54844; 26-06-1964 [K]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Thesium tenuissimum Hook.f.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63275; 1970-4-5
[WAG.1324793]

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 6.

Thesium viride A.W.Hill

Meikle R.D. 1198; 1950-2-19 [BR0000019121895]

Total: 19; Bauchi 4, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Viscum congolense De Wild. & T.Durand

Talbot P.A. 604; 1911- [K]

Total: 3; Katsina 1.

Viscum decurrens (Engl.) Baker & Sprague

Viscum obscurum var. *decurrens* Engl.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI27149; 23-02-1953 [K]

Total: 12; Abia 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

LORANTHACEAE

Agelanthus brunneus (Engl.) Tiegh.

Loranthus brunneus Engl.

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C. FHI16684; --
[BR0000017167031]

Total: 7; Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Taraba 3.

Agelanthus dodoneifolius (DC.) Polhill & Wiens

Loranthus dodoneifolius DC.

Geerling, C 3101; 1970-10-28 [WAG.1068026]

Total: 30; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 6, Benue 2, Borno 2, Gombe 3, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Niger 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 4.

Agelanthus heteromorphus (A.Rich.) Polhill & Wiens

Loranthus heteromorphus A.Rich.

Lawlor, D.W.; Hall, J.B. 341; 1962-08-18
[K004509971]

Total: 9; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Zamfara 1.

Englerina gabonensis (Engl.) Balle

Loranthus gabonensis Engl.

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C. FHI17304; --
[BR0000017174626]

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Englerina lecardii (Engl.) Balle

Loranthus lecardii Engl.

Ogbe G.A.E.; Jacyesimi A.K. FHI15893; 08-05-1946
[K]

Total: 1.

Englerina ochroleuca (Engl. & K.Krause) Balle

Loranthus ochroleucus Engl. & K.Krause

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 65089; 1972-5-5 [WAG.1068410]

Total: 2; Adamawa 2.

Globimetula braunii (Engl.) Danser

Loranthus braunii Engl.

Talbot P.A. 3340; -- [BM000799168]

Total: 13; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Globimetula cupulata (DC.) Danser — Introduced

Loranthus cupulatus DC.

Literature

Total: 0.

Globimetula dinklagei (Engl.) Danser —
Introduced

Loranthus dinklagei Engl.

1973-01-04 [1120654.0]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Globimetula oreophila (Oliv. ex Hook.f.)
Danser

Loranthus oreophilus Oliv. ex Hook.f.

Van Meer P. 1823; 1971-5-25 [BR0000017567725]

Total: 5; Borno 2, Cross River 2.

Helixanthera mannii (Oliv.) Danser

Loranthus mannii Oliv.

Talbot P.A. s.n.; 1913-- [CM433515]2859437791

Total: 3; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Helixanthera spathulata Wiens & Polhill —
Endemic

Onochie, C.F.A. 33216; 1953-5-20 [K000406694]

Total: 2; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1.

Phragmanthera capitata (Spreng.) Balle

Exostema capitatum Spreng.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1637; 1966-6-16 [WAG.1069221]

Total: 38; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 4,
Delta 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Niger 3,
Ondo 1, Oyo 9, Rivers 1.

Phragmanthera kamerunensis (Engl.) Balle

Loranthus kamerunensis Engl.

Dalziel J.M. 551; 16-06-1911 [K]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 2.

Phragmanthera nigrimana (Hook.f. ex
Benth.) Balle

Loranthus nigritanus Hook.f. ex Benth.

Daramola, BO FHI 85477; 1977-8-29

[WAG.1069353]

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 4,
Ogun 3, Taraba 1.

Phragmanthera polycrypta (Didr.) Balle

Loranthus polycryptus Didr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Phragmanthera polycrypta subsp.
polycrypta

Loranthus polycryptus Didr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Phragmanthera raynaliana (Balle) Polhill &
Wiens

Phragmanthera polycrypta subsp. *raynaliana*
Balle

Dowsett-Lemaire F. 1233; 25-03-1988 [K]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Phragmanthera talbotiorum (Sprague) Balle

Loranthus talbotiorum Sprague

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1281; -- [K000435486]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Niger
2.

Tapinanthus apodanthus (Sprague) Danser

Loranthus apodanthus Sprague

Hepper F.N. 2802; 14-01-1958 [K]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Tapinanthus bangwensis (Engl. &
K.Krause) Danser

Loranthus bangwensis Engl. & K.Krause

Bels L. 1; 1951-6-28 [BR0000016853966]

Total: 18; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 2,
Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Tapinanthus belvisii (DC.) Danser

Loranthus belvisii DC.

Bels, L 1; 1951-6-28 [U.1370753]

Total: 2; Abia 1, Kaduna 1.

Tapinanthus cordifolius Polhill & Wiens —
Endemic

Olorunfemi J. FHI55116; 25-11-1964 [K]

Total: 8; Bauchi 2, Plateau 3.

Tapinanthus farmari (Sprague) Danser

Loranthus farmari Sprague

Mrs. A. N. Edun; 2009-6-21 [9383] [3808440144]

Total: 4; Kaduna 4.

Tapinanthus globifer (A.Rich.) Tiegh.

Loranthus globifer A.Rich.

Pilz, GE 2556; 1980-10-29 [WAG.1070049]

Total: 56; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Borno
2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 6,
Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4,
Ogun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 4, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Tapinanthus preussii (Engl.) Tiegh.

Loranthus preussii Engl.

Zeven, AC 127; 1963-4-20 [WAG.1070335]

Total: 1; Abia 1.

TAMARICACEAE

Tamarix senegalensis DC.
Kerr, G.R.G.; s.n.; 1923-01-01 [K005289275]
Total: 5; Borno 1, Kaduna 1.

PLUMBAGINACEAE

Plumbago auriculata Lam. — Introduced
Bojnansky V.; 1986-5-23 [102408] [1990433451]
Total: 4; Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Plumbago zeylanica L.
Odewo, TK; Binuyo, A TK 145; 1982-9-12
[WAG.1169879]
Total: 69; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 3, Cross
River 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 4,
Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 3, Niger 1, Ogun 10,
Ondo 6, Osun 7, Oyo 11, Plateau 2.

POLYGONACEAE

Afrobrunnichia erecta (Asch.) Hutch. &
Dalziel
Brunnichia erecta Asch.
Brenan J.P.M. & Onochie C.F.A. 9030; 1948-2-14
[BR0000016460713]
Total: 15; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1,
Kaduna 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Antigonon leptopus Hook. & Arn. —
Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1066; 1966-1-30 [WAG.1546748]
Total: 9; Abia 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 5, Zamfara
1.

Fagopyrum snowdenii (Hutch. & Dandy)
S.P.Hong
Harpagocarpus snowdenii Hutch. & Dandy
Hepper F.N. 2033; 1958-2-17 [BR0000016463905]
Total: 1.

Oxygonum sinuatum (Hochst. & Steud. ex
Meisn.) Dammer
Ceratogonum sinuatum Hochst. & Steud. ex
Meisn.
Literature
Total: 0.

Persicaria acuminata (Kunth) M.Gómez —
Introduced
Polygonum acuminatum Kunth
1520; 1981-12-15 [1520]2302319576
Total: 7; Kaduna 7.

Persicaria attenuata (R.Br.) Sojak —
Introduced
Polygonum attenuatum R.Br.
Dalziel, J.M. 209; 1909-03-30 [K005713996]
Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun
2, Plateau 1.

Persicaria decipiens (R.Br.) K.L. Wilson
Polygonum decipiens R.Br.
Daramola, BO 163; 1977-8-23 [WAG.1448785]
Total: 28; Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1,
Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Taraba
4, Yobe 1.

Persicaria dichotoma (Blume) Masam. —
Introduced
Polygonum dichotomum Blume
Literature
Total: 0.

Persicaria glabra (Willd.) M.Gómez —
Introduced
Polygonum glabrum Willd.
Ohaeri A.O. 2029; 15-12-1981 [ABUH]
Total: 3; Kaduna 2.

Persicaria glomerata (Dammer) S.Ortiz &
Paiva
Polygonum glomeratum Dammer
Hepper F.N. 1871; 1958-2-5 [BR0000016473164]
Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2,
Zamfara 1.

Persicaria lapathifolia (L.) Delarbre —
Introduced
Polygonum lapathifolium L.
Latilo, MG; Afolayan; Fagbemi, A s.n.; 1973-11-22
[WAG.1448902]
Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kwara 2,
Lagos 1.

Persicaria limbata (Meisn.) H.Hara
Polygonum limbatum Meisn.
Denys E. 670; 1982-7-18 [BR0000016475441]
Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 3,
Niger 1, Yobe 1.

Persicaria madagascariensis (Meisn.)
S.Ortiz & Paiva
Polygonum poiretii var. madagascariensis Meisn.
Gbile, ZO; Wit, P 972; 1971-11-17 [WAG.1449224]
Total: 26; Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1,
Delta 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Lagos 1, Niger 3,
Osun 2, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Persicaria nepalensis (Meisn.) H.Gross

Polygonum nepalense Meisn.
Daramola, BO D. 91; 1977-8-17 [WAG.1431384]
Total: 16; Adamawa 2, Cross River 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Taraba 5.

Persicaria pulchra Soják — Introduced
Polygonum pulchrum Blume
O. O. Oyebanji; 2016-7-7 [7183]3808440898
Total: 1.

Persicaria senegalensis (Meisn.) Soják
Polygonum senegalense Meisn.
Latilo, MG; Afolayan; Fagbemi, A s.n.; 1973-11-22 [WAG.1431614]
Total: 76; Abia 2, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 11, Delta 1, Edo 1, Gombe 4, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 5, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Persicaria senegalensis f. *albotomentosa* (R.A.Graham) K.L.Wilson
Polygonum senegalense f. *albotomentosum* R.A.Graham
Geerling, C 4012; 1971-8-14 [WAG.1449423]
Total: 32; Borno 6, Delta 1, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Persicaria senegalensis f. *senegalensis*
Polygonum senegalense Meisn.
Lely, H.V.; 226; 1921-05-24 [K005714123]
Total: 18; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Persicaria setosula (A.Rich.) K.L.Wilson
Polygonum setosulum A.Rich.
Latilo, M.G., FHI62589 [K005714205]
Total: 1; Sokoto 1.

Polygonum aviculare L. — Introduced
Literature
Total: 0.

Polygonum plebeium R.Br.
900021; 1973-12-9 [900021] [2302319492]
Total: 10; Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 3, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.

Rumex abyssinicus Jacq.
B. O. Daramola; Dr. Kadiri; 2008-12-1 [96] [3808440890]
Total: 11; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Edo 2, Kwara 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Rumex acetosella L. — Introduced
Literature
Total: 0.

Rumex nepalensis Spreng.
Hepper F.N. 2023; 1958-2-17 [BR0000016489608]
Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 2.

DROSERACEAE

Drosera indica L.
Geerling, C; Wit, P 3824; 1971-7-28 [WAG.1783082]
Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 3.

Drosera madagascariensis DC.
Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63261; 1970-4-3 [WAG.1782961]
Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 1, Niger 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

ANCISTROCLADACEAE

Ancistrocladus abbreviatus Airy Shaw
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI40443; 1958-12-1 [K000044712]
Total: 14; Anambra 6, Cross River 4, Rivers 2.

Ancistrocladus abbreviatus subsp. *lateralis* Gereau — Endemic
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI40443; 1958-12-1 [K000044712]
Total: 2.

Ancistrocladus guineensis Oliv.
Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32832; 1981-6-18 [WAG.1425364]
Total: 32; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Lagos 2, Ogun 13.

Ancistrocladus korupensis D.W.Thomas & Gereau
Schmitt 473; 1995-2-20 [976823]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Ancistrocladus uncinatus Hutch. & Dalziel — Endemic
Literature
Total: 0.

CARYOPHYLLACEAE

Corrigiola litoralis L. — Introduced
1008; 1973-12-2 [1008]2302319768
Total: 2; Katsina 2.

Corrigiola litoralis subsp. *litoralis* — Introduced

1973-12-02 [FHI.1008.0]

Total: 1; Katsina 1.

Drymaria cordata (L.) Willd. ex Schult.

Holosteum cordatum L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2076; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1314958]

Total: 43; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 7, Taraba 5.

Drymaria villosa Schltld. & Cham. —

Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 199; 1977-10-8

[WAG.1314995]

Total: 5; Borno 2, Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Plateau 1.

Polycarpaea corymbosa (L.) Lam.

Achyranthes corymbosa L.

Leeuw PN de; 1964-09-25 [WAG0213017]

Total: 18; Bauchi 3, Borno 5, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Yobe 1.

Polycarpaea corymbosa var. *corymbosa*

Achyranthes corymbosa L.

Leeuw, PN de 1228; 1964-9-25 [WAG0213017]

Total: 1.

Polycarpaea eriantha Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Lely, H.V.; 1921-09-29 [K000354964]

Total: 20; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Polycarpaea eriantha var. *effusa* (Oliv.)

Turrill

Barter, C 808; 1857-1-1 [U.1185650]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Polycarpaea eriantha var. *eriantha*

Ariwaodo, JO 313; 1977-3-7 [WAG0212980]

Total: 1.

Polycarpaea linearifolia (DC.) DC.

Paronychia linearifolia DC.

Wit, P 2325; 1972-8-13 [WAG0041705]

Total: 77; Adamawa 3, Anambra 1, Bauchi 7, Borno 2, Edo 3, Enugu 12, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 3.

Polycarpaea stellata (Willd.) Coyte

Achyranthes stellata Willd.

Literature

Total: 0.

Polycarpon prostratum (Forssk.) Asch. & Schweinf.

Alsine prostrata Forssk.

Baker T.C.N.; 02-05-1978 [ABUH]

Total: 17; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 6, Taraba 1.

Polycarpon prostratum var. *prostratum*

Alsine prostrata Forssk.

Ohaeri A.O. 731; 14-07-1974 [ABUH]

Total: 1.

Polycarpon tetraphyllum (L.) L. —

Introduced

Mollugo tetraphylla L.

Total: 10; Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Zamfara 1.

Polycarpon tetraphyllum subsp.

tetraphyllum — Introduced

Mollugo tetraphylla L.

Denys, E 730; 1982-7-22 [WAG.1396645]

Total: 10; Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Zamfara 1.

Silene abyssinica (Hochst.) H.Neumayer

Uebelinia abyssinica Hochst.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 191; 1977-10-8

[WAG.1563711]

Total: 6; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Stellaria mannii Hook.f.

Hepper F.N. 2044; -- [BR0000014026645]

Total: 6; Taraba 1.

Stellaria media (L.) Vill. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

AMARANTHACEAE

Achyranthes abyssinica Nees

Literature

Total: 0.

Achyranthes acuminata E.Mey. ex Sonder

Literature

Total: 0.

Achyranthes annua Dinter

Literature

Total: 0.

Achyranthes aspera L.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 2070; 1972-5-11

[WAG.1404187]

Total: 39; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 5, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 6.

Achyranthes aspera var. *sicula* L.

1995-9-28 [FR-0017532]

Total: 1.

Achyranthes bidentata Blume — Introduced

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70501; 1973-3-5 [WAG.1404439]

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Achyranthes talbotii Hutch. & Dalziel

FHI FHI 28284; 1950-12-17 [K000243718]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 3.

Aerva javanica (Burm.f.) Juss. ex Schult.

Iresine javanica Burm.f.

Edwin Ujor, F.H.I. [BR0000013709778]

Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 9, Jigawa 2, Sokoto 2.

Aerva javanica var. *javanica*

Iresine javanica Burm.f.

1995-9-14 [FR-0017540]

Total: 1.

Alternanthera bettzickiana (Regel)

G.Nicholson — Introduced

Telanthera bettzickiana Regel

Guile D.P.M. 165; 1966-10 [IFE742]

Total: 3; Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Alternanthera brasiliana (L.) Kuntze —

Introduced

Gomphrena brasiliana L.

Babalola Sadat; 2006-12-24 [134]3460379033

Total: 6; Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Alternanthera littoralis P.Beauv.

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2012-9-11 [55C]

Total: 2.

Alternanthera littoralis var. *littoralis*

Seafal M.M. 7127; 08-09-1971 [IFE]

Total: 1.

Alternanthera littoralis var. *sparmannii*

(Moq.) Pedersen

Literature

Total: 0.

Alternanthera nodiflora R.Br. — Introduced

Magaji S.O. MG. 73; 25-11-1965 [FHI]

Total: 20; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Alternanthera pungens Kunth — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2107; 1977-6-11 [WAG.1404978]

Total: 15; Kano 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 5.

Alternanthera sessilis (L.) DC. —

Introduced

Gomphrena sessilis L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1032; 1966-1-7 [WAG.1346356]

Total: 79; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Bayelsa 1, Borno 8, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 8, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 10, Ogun 7, Ondo 4, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Amaranthus blitum L. — Introduced

Total: 1.

Amaranthus blitum subsp. *emarginatus*

(Salzm. ex Uline & Bray) Carretero, Muñoz

Garm. & Pedrol — Introduced

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P 791; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1346925]

Total: 1.

Amaranthus blitum subsp. *oleraceus* (L.)

Costea — Introduced

Thomas N.W. 1779; 18-11-1912 [K]

Total: 1.

Amaranthus caudatus L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Amaranthus cruentus L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1522; 1966-5-15 [WAG.1346857]

Total: 12; Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Amaranthus dubius L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Amaranthus graecizans L.

Felix; 2005-10-18 [386]3913474400

Total: 4; Anambra 1, Lagos 1.

Amaranthus graecizans subsp. *graecizans*

Barter 539; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 1.

Amaranthus graecizans subsp. *silvestris*

(Tourn. ex Vill.) Brenan

Dalziel J.M. 160; 31-07-1907 [K]

Total: 1.

Amaranthus hybridus L. — Introduced

Eijnatten CLM van; 1965-12-15 [WAG.1346785]

Total: 35; Borno 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Niger 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 9.

Amaranthus hybridus subsp. *hybridus* —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1176 a; 1965-12-15
[WAG.1346785]

Total: 1.

Amaranthus hypochondriacus L. —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Amaranthus retroflexus L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Amaranthus spinosus L. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2627; 1981-10-24 [WAG.1347098]

Total: 39; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ogun 7, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Amaranthus tortuosus Hornem. —

Introduced

Unknown [IFE13310]

Total: 1.

Amaranthus tricolor L. — Introduced

1602; 1986-8-11 [1602]2302319849

Total: 5; Kaduna 5.

Amaranthus viridis L. — Introduced

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 195; 1971-9-14
[WAG.1347201]

Total: 29; Borno 2, Cross River 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 8, Ondo 2, Oyo 7.

Blutaparon vermiculare (L.) Mears

Gomphrena vermicularis L.

Hambler, D.J.; 82; 1956-11-28 [K006070764]

Total: 1.

Celosia argentea L.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO; Wit, P FHI 64201; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1347320]

Total: 66; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 11, Cross River 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 3, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Oyo 13, Rivers 1.

Celosia bonnivairii Schinz

Brenan J.P.M. 8839; 17-01-1948 [K]

Total: 2; Ondo 1.

Celosia globosa Schinz

Mr. and Mrs. Talbot, P.A.; 4019.0 [K]

Total: 4; Taraba 1.

Celosia globosa var. *globosa*

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 1283; 1911- [K]

Total: 1.

Celosia isertii C.C.Towns.

Wit, P 1059; 1971-12-23 [WAG.1290010]

Total: 3; Osun 1.

Celosia leptostachya Benth.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 360; 1977-10-13
[WAG.1290065]

Total: 21; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 4, Taraba 2.

Celosia pseudovirgata Schinz

Brenan, J.P.M. 8839; 1948-01-17 [K005209355]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Celosia trigyna L.

Pilz, GE 2153; 1977-10-9 [WAG.1290282]

Total: 94; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 8, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Ogun 4, Ondo 6, Osun 1, Oyo 21, Plateau 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Centrostachys aquatica (R.Br.) Moq.

Achyranthes aquatica R.Br.

Latilo, MG FHI 64627; 1971-11-18 [WAG.1290429]

Total: 26; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Edo 5, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Yobe 2, Zamfara 2.

Chenopodium album L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Cyathula achyranthoides (Kunth) Moq.

Desmochaeta achyranthoides Kunth

Herb Alleizette, AC d' s.n.; 1920-1-1 [L.1690978]

Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 3.

Cyathula cylindrica Moq.

Ujor, E. 29993; 1951-8-22 [21935]912018198

Total: 2; Niger 2.

Cyathula heudelotii (Moq.) Di Vincenzo, Berends., Wondafr. & Borsch

Achyranthes heudelotii Moq.

Sharland, R.E. 1459; 1980-10-17 [K000211376]

Total: 15; Benue 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Cyathula involucrata (Moq.) Di Vincenzo, Berends., Wondafr. & Borsch

Achyranthes involucrata Moq.

Parsons, A.C. 227; 2007-09-21 [K005773649]

Total: 35; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 4.

Cyathula prostrata (L.) Blume

Achyranthes prostrata L.

Gledhill D. [BR0000013782887]

Total: 72; Abia 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 12, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 12, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Cyathula prostrata var. *pedicellata*

(C.B.Clarke) Cavaco

Cyathula pedicellata C.B.Clarke

Brenan J.P.M. & Richards P.W. [BR0000013786038]

Total: 11; Benue 1, Edo 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Cyathula prostrata var. *prostrata*

Achyranthes prostrata L.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 43; 1979-4-20

[WAG.1290709]

Total: 1.

Digera muricata (L.) Mart. — Introduced

Achyranthes muricata L.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI7077; 22-10-1943

[K]

Total: 2.

Digera muricata subsp. *muricata*

Achyranthes muricata L.

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI7077; 22-10-1943

[K]

Total: 1.

Dysphania ambrosioides (L.) Mosyakin & Clemants — Introduced

Chenopodium ambrosioides L.

B.O.Daramola; 2008-10-25 [127]3808442458

Total: 28; Benue 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 2, Plateau 5, Taraba 5.

Dysphania congolana (Hauman) Mosyakin & Clemants

Chenopodium glaucum subsp. congolanum

Hauman

Hepper F.N. 2079; -- [BR0000016051898]

Total: 2.

Gomphrena celosioides Mart. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2284; 1979-4-8 [WAG.1290991]

Total: 61; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 16, Niger 1, Ogun 13, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Taraba 1.

Gomphrena globosa L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1071; 1966-1-20 [WAG.1291047]

Total: 11; Cross River 3, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1.

Gomphrena vermicularis L.

1619; 1973-8-18 [1619]2302319756

Total: 8; Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Rivers 2.

Nothosaerva brachiata (L.) Wight

Achyranthes brachiata L.

[FR-0034817]

Total: 4; Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Ondo 1.

Ouret lanata (L.) Kuntze

Achyranthes lanata L.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 399; 1978-5-10 [WAG.1404694]

Total: 14; Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Pandiaka angustifolia (Vahl) Hepper

Gomphrena angustifolia Vahl

Odewo, TK; Binuyo, A 114; 1982-9-8

[WAG.1347537]

Total: 22; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 8, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Niger 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Pandiaka involucrata (Moq.) B.D.Jacks.

Achyranthes involucrata Moq.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65916; 1972-10-25

[WAG.1347597]

Total: 26; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Pupalia lappacea (L.) Juss.

Achyranthes lappacea L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2046; 1966-9-23 [WAG.1347908]

Total: 32; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 5.

Pupalia lappacea var. *velutina* (Moq.)

Hook.f.

Pupalia velutina Moq.

Noble H.L. A26; 10-11-1951 [K]

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Pupalia micrantha Hauman

Lely H.V. 648; 29-09-1921 [K]

Total: 2; Osun 1.

Sericostachys scandens Gilg & Lopr.

Onochie, CFA FHI 40409; 1958-11-10

[WAG.1348059]

Total: 9; Edo 3, Kaduna 3, Plateau 1.

AIZOACEAE

Sesuvium portulacastrum (L.) L.

Portulaca portulacastrum L.

2035; 1986-7-21 [2035]2302319494

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Trianthema portulacastrum L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65755; 1972-8-17

[WAG.1408528]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Enugu 3, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Lagos 1, Oyo 7.

Zaleya pentandra (L.) C.Jeffrey

Trianthema pentandrum L.

1995-9-14 [FR-0017521]3046114080

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Kogi 2, Ogun 2, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

LIMEACEAE

Limeum pterocarpum (J.Gay) Heimerl

Semonvillea pterocarpa J.Gay

Dalziel J.M. 415; -- [BR0000017456982]

Total: 8; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Niger 1, Sokoto 2.

Limeum pterocarpum var. *pterocarpum*

Semonvillea pterocarpa J.Gay

Limeum viscosum (J.Gay) Fenzl

Gaudinia viscosa J.Gay

Dalziel J.M. 417; 1911- [K]

Total: 5; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Sokoto 1.

Limeum viscosum subsp. *viscosum*

Gaudinia viscosa J.Gay

KEWACEAE

Kewa bowkeriana (Sond.) Christenh. —

Introduced

Hypertelis bowkeriana Sond.

Verdcourt 3557; 1963-1-20 [CONN00126780]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

GISEKIACEAE

Gisekia pharnaceoides L.

Neumann, K. 1254; 1992-09-01 (FR)

Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Sokoto 1.

Gisekia pharnaceoides var. *pharnaceoides*

Neumann, K. 1254; 1992-09-01 (FR)

Total: 1.

PHYTOLACCACEAE

Phytolacca dodecandra L'Hér.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11244; 1977-3-25

[WAG.1166712]

Total: 50; Bauchi 1, Cross River 6, Edo 10, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 14, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

NYCTAGINACEAE

Boerhavia coccinea Mill. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2155; 1977-10-9 [WAG.1118180]

Total: 56; Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1, Borno 3, Edo 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 11, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 11, Sokoto 2.

Boerhavia diffusa L.

Pilz, GE 1947; 1977-4-22 [WAG.1118262]

Total: 46; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Borno 7, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Osun 2, Oyo 9, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Boerhavia erecta L. — Introduced

; 1995-10-1 [FR-0019726]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Oyo 1.

Boerhavia repens L.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1731; 1972-5-4

[WAG.1118410]

Total: 17; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 3, Kaduna 4, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Sokoto 2.

Bougainvillea glabra Choisy — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1065; 1966-1-20 [WAG.1118469]

Total: 20; Kaduna 3, Lagos 6, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 7.

Bougainvillea spectabilis Willd. —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1064; 1966-1-20 [WAG.1118480]

Total: 11; Kaduna 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 5.

Commicarpus plumbagineus (Cav.) Standl.

Boerhavia plumbaginea Cav.

Dalziel, J.M. (Dr.); 196; 2007-10-30 [K006218152]

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Mirabilis jalapa L. — Introduced

[SANT.11832.0]

Total: 13; Akwa Ibom 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Mirabilis jalapa var. *jalapa* — Introduced
Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 90201; 1979-4-23
[WAG.1118747]

Total: 1.

Pisonia aculeata L. — Introduced
Meer, PPC van 877; 1968-10-4 [WAG.1118814]
Total: 18; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 1,
Oyo 13.

PETIVERIACEAE

Hillieria latifolia (Lam.) H.Walter —
Introduced

Rivina latifolia Lam.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 466; 1978-5-16
[WAG.1166458]

Total: 76; Benue 2, Cross River 4, Edo 4, Enugu 1,
Imo 2, Katsina 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Ogun 14, Ondo 6,
Osun 3, Oyo 20.

Petiveria alliacea L. — Introduced
Odewo, TK; Adedeji ODA 212; 1983-5-11
[WAG.1166535]
Total: 47; Lagos 20, Ogun 7, Osun 6, Oyo 12, Taraba
1.

Rivina humilis L. — Introduced
Lowe, J 1781; 1969-4-26 [WAG.1166808]
Total: 1.

MOLLUGINACEAE

Glinus hirtus (Thunb.) Sennikov & Sukhor.
Mollugo hirta Thunb.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67620; 1973-2-21
[WAG.1103190]

Total: 8; Bauchi 4, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Glinus lotoides L.
Dalziel J.M.; 1912-01-01 [BR0000018268539]
Total: 33; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Borno 4, Ebonyi 1,
Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Niger
6, Osun 1, Sokoto 3, Taraba 2.

Glinus lotoides var. *lotoides*
Denys E. 663; 1982-7-18 [BR0000018268546]
Total: 1.

Glinus oppositifolius (L.) Aug.DC.
Mollugo oppositifolia L.
Irving, E.G. [E.MEL 2468463A]

Total: 43; Cross River 5, Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 2,
Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Osun 2,
Oyo 5, Rivers 3.

Glinus oppositifolius var. *oppositifolius*
Mollugo oppositifolia L.

Gbile, ZO FHI 73431; 1974-5-4 [WAG.1103284]
Total: 1.

Hypertelis cerviana (L.) Thulin
Pharnaceum cerviana L.

1979-6-3 [2302319817]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1,
Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Paramollugo nudicaulis (Lam.) Thulin
Mollugo nudicaulis Lam.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 79; 1979-4-22
[WAG.1103465]

Total: 43; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2,
Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 3, Cross
River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1,
Kogi 2, Kwara 4, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1,
Osun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

BASELLACEAE

Basella alba L. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1615; 1966-6-13 [WAG.1160919]
Total: 10; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3,
Osun 1, Oyo 2.

TALINACEAE

Talinum fruticosum (L.) Juss. — Introduced
Portulaca fruticosa L.

Pilz, GE 2285; 1979-4-8 [WAG.1553811]

Total: 26; Kaduna 1, Lagos 9, Ogun 3, Oyo 5.

Talinum paniculatum (Jacq.) Gaertn. —
Introduced

Portulaca paniculata Jacq.

Gledhill, D 919; 1968-4-5 [WAG.1199962]

Total: 7; Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 2, Plateau 1.

Talinum portulacifolium (Forssk.) Asch. ex
Schweinf.

Orygia portulacifolia Forssk.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2126; 1966-11-2 [WAG.1553795]
Total: 2; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

PORTULACACEAE

Portulaca foliosa Ker Gawl.

B.O. Daramola & Josephine FHI.63669; --
[BR0000016498365]

Total: 2; Borno 1, Gombe 1.

Portulaca grandiflora Hook. — Introduced

Denys E.; 1982-07-19 [BR0000016498761]

Total: 3; Benue 1, Borno 1.

Portulaca grandiflora var. *grandiflora* —
Introduced

Denys E. 712; 1982-7-19 [BR0000016498761]

Total: 1.

Portulaca granulostellulata (Poelln.)

Ricceri & Arrigoni

Portulaca oleracea var. *granulostellulata* Poelln.

Literature

Total: 0.

Portulaca oleracea L.

Bels L; 1950-04-01 [WAG.U.1523572]

Total: 20; Borno 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara
1, Lagos 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Portulaca oleracea var. *oleracea*

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 386; 1971-9-19
[WAG.1199698]

Total: 1.

Portulaca quadrifida L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 177; 1960-4-24 [WAG.1199761]

Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1,
Lagos 2, Oyo 3.

CACTACEAE

Disocactus × jenkinsonii (McIntosh)

M.H.J.van der Meer

Cactus × jenkinsonii McIntosh

2802; 1990-06-27 [2802.0]

Total: 1.

Epiphyllum oxypetalum (DC.) Haw. —

Introduced

Cereus oxypetalus DC.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1364; 1966-4-15 [WAG.1496766]

Total: 5; Kaduna 2, Oyo 3.

Opuntia aciculata Griffiths — Introduced

B.O.Daramola; 2010-4-12 [3225]3808442935

Total: 3; Lagos 3.

Opuntia cochenillifera (L.) Mill. —

Introduced

Cactus cochenillifer L.

Hambler, D.J. 781; -- [K000100507]

Total: 5; Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Opuntia ficus-indica (L.) Mill. —

Introduced

Cactus ficus-indica L.

Daramola B.O.; 1964-8-3 [55214]1944994380

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Taraba 1.

Opuntia monacantha Haw. — Introduced

Cactus monacanthos Willd.

Daramola B.O.; Gbile Z.O. FHI62873; --

[K000100512]

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Opuntia stricta (Haw.) Haw. — Introduced

Cactus strictus Haw.

0; -- [K000100956]912147555

Total: 1.

Rhipsalis baccifera (J.S.Muell.) Stearn

Cassytha baccifera J.S.Muell.

Wit, P; Geerling, C 1248; 1972-3-11 [WAG.1496950]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1,
Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Rhipsalis baccifera subsp. *baccifera*

Cassytha baccifera J.S.Muell.

Chapman, JD 2811; 1972-5-8 [WAG.1496949]

Total: 1.

Rhodocactus grandifolius (Haw.)

F.M.Knuth — Introduced

Pereskia grandifolia Haw.

Diepen, H van s.n.; 1979-1-1 [WAG.1496838]

Total: 1.

CORNACEAE

Alangium chinense (Lour.) Harms

Stylidium chinense Lour.

Chapman, J.D. 3508; 1974-11-14 [K006134955]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

BALSAMINACEAE

Impatiens filicornu Hook.f.

Latilo M.G.; 1968-4-17 [61303]

Total: 2; Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Impatiens glandulisejala Grey-Wilson —

Endemic

Medler, J. 830; 1973-8-17 [K000419405]

Total: 7; Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 2.

Impatiens hochstetteri Warb.

Medler, J. 1587; -- [BR0000008694249]

Total: 8; Plateau 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Impatiens hochstetteri subsp. *jacquesii*

(Keay) Grey-Wilson

Hepper F.N.; 1587; -- [BR0000008694249]

Total: 7; Plateau 3, Sokoto 2.

Impatiens irvingii Hook.f.

Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70299; 1974-5-22 [WAG.1160067]

Total: 104; Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Delta 5, Edo 21, Ekiti 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 12, Niger 6, Ogun 12, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 8, Zamfara 1.

Impatiens kamerunensis Warb.

Medler J. 846; 1973-8-17 [73671]2013043139

Total: 53; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 1, Cross River 20, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Osun 7, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Impatiens kamerunensis subsp.

kamerunensis

Medler, J. 667; 1971-3-24 [K000044997]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Impatiens kamerunensis subsp. *obanensis*

(Keay) Grey-Wilson

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67700; 1973-2-26 [WAG.1160149]

Total: 30; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 12, Kogi 1, Ondo 1, Osun 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Impatiens mackeyana Hook.f.

Chapman J.D. 2876; 1972-6-5 [46165]

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Katsina 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Impatiens mackeyana subsp. *zenkeri* (Warb.)

Grey-Wilson

Daramola, BO FHI 62742; 1969-5-20 [WAG.1160205]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1.

Impatiens macroptera Hook.f.

Meer, PPC van 1810; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1160224]

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Impatiens nigeriensis Grey-Wilson —

Endemic

Stanfield, D.P. 167; 1957-12-7 [K000419393]

Total: 8; Nasarawa 1, Ondo 6.

Impatiens sakeriana Hook.f.

Chapman, J.D. 3409; 1974-11-04 [K006229536]

Total: 1; Sokoto 1.

ACTINIDIACEAE

Saurauia bifida Warb. — Introduced

Hartley, T.G.; 1961-12-24 [P04468281]

Total: 6.

Saurauia rodatzii K.Schum. & Lauterb. —

Introduced

Schlechter, F.R.R.; 1907-11-30 [P04487571]

Total: 1.

LECYTHIDACEAE

Bertholletia excelsa Bonpl. — Introduced

J.H. Espley 5; -- [BR0000015630667]

Total: 3.

Crateranthus talbotii Baker f.

Talbot P.A. 5; -- [BM000902319]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 11.

Napoleonaea angolensis Welw.

Talbot, P. 193; -- [K000225952]

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Napoleonaea beninensis Jongkind

Pilz, GE 1904; 1977-1-2 [WAG.1883715]

Total: 18; Lagos 1, Ogun 8, Oyo 9.

Napoleonaea egertonii Baker f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Napoleonaea heudelotii A.Juss.

Ohaeri A.O. 2664; 24-09-1988 [ABUH]

Total: 1.

Napoleonaea imperialis P.Beauv.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63135; 1972-1-20 [WAG.1889095]

Total: 88; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Delta 2, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 3, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 12, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Napoleonaea lutea Baker f. ex Hutch. &

Dalziel — Endemic

Onochie, C.F.A. 35763; 1956-4-12 [K000442194]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Napoleonaea reptans Baker f. ex Hutch. & Dalziel — Endemic

Percy Amaury Talbot 3175; -- [BM000902328]
Total: 2.

Napoleonaea talbotii Baker f.

Meer, PPC van 1166; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1692685]
Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.

Napoleonaea vogelii Hook. & Planch.

Percy Amaury Talbot 193; 1912-- [BM000902338]
Total: 16; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Oubanguia africana Baill.

Meer, PPC van 1436; 1971-4-23 [WAG.1528295]
Total: 1; Abia 1.

Oubanguia alata Baker f.

Meer, PPC van 1343; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1528305]
Total: 22; Abia 1, Cross River 10, Niger 4.

Oubanguia laurifolia (Pierre) Tiegh.

Egassea laurifolia Pierre

Talbot, P. 1693 [K006151751]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Petersianthus macrocarpus (P.Beauv.)

Liben

Combretum macrocarpum P.Beauv.

Kennedy J.D. 341; -- [BR0000013629335]
Total: 15; Borno 2, Cross River 4, Edo 4, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Rivers 1.

Rhaptopetalum coriaceum Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1110 A; 1971-4-1 [WAG.1528424]
Total: 11; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Osun 1.

PENTAPHYLACACEAE

Ternstroemia africana Melch.

Daramola B.O. 5533; 1964-11-26
[BR0000018801118]
Total: 4; Rivers 3.

SAPOTACEAE

Aningeria altissima (A.Chev.) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Hormogyne altissima A.Chev.

Chapman J.D4312; 1976-4-17 [106969] [1990433762]
Total: 7; Kwara 1, Taraba 4.

Aningeria pierrei (A.Chev.) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Hormogyne pierrei A.Chev.

Idahosa ; 1949-1-27 [P00512303]
Total: 1.

Autranella congolensis (De Wild.) A.Chev.

Mimusops congolensis De Wild.

Onyeagocha, S.C.; 1946-7-12 [P00512326]

Total: 12; Anambra 3, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Imo 1.

Baillonella toxisperma Pierre

S.N.; -- [BR0000020186425]

Total: 18; Cross River 7, Edo 2, Imo 2, Niger 1, Rivers 3, Zamfara 1.

Chrysophyllum cainito L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1662; 1966-7-2 [WAG.1384567]

Total: 26; Abia 3, Anambra 4, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 8.

Donella pruniformis (Engl.) Pierre ex Engl.

Chrysophyllum pruniforme Engl.

; -- [P06707156]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Donella ubangiensis (De Wild.) Aubrév.

Mimusops ubangiensis De Wild.

Adebusuyi J.K.; 1960-12-22 [51714] [1990430372]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Osun 1.

Donella welwitschii (Engl.) Pierre ex Engl.

Chrysophyllum welwitschii Engl.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11305; 1977-3-31

[WAG.1362508]

Total: 42; Anambra 8, Cross River 5, Delta 4, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Englerophytum magalismontanum (Sond.)

T.D.Penn. — Introduced

Chrysophyllum magalismontanum Sond.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1954-9-2 [34267] [1990428932]

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 3.

Englerophytum oblanceolatum (S.Moore)

T.D.Penn.

Sideroxylon oblanceolatum S.Moore

Literature

Total: 0.

Englerophytum oubanguiense (Aubrév. & Pellegr.) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Tisserantiodoxa oubanguiensis Aubrév. &

Pellegr.

Kennedy, J.D. ; 1932-- [P00417478]

Total: 1.

Englerophytum paludosum L.Gaut., Burgt & O.Lachenaud

Kennedy J.D. 1962; -- [BR0000024875264]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Englerophytum stelechantha K.Krause

Bonny 2.77 59

Total: 1.

Gambeya africana (A.DC.) Pierre

Chrysophyllum africanum A.DC.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1720; 1966-7-27 [WAG.1384458]

Total: 21; Borno 1, Cross River 8, Delta 1, Edo 4, Kaduna 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Gambeya albida (G.Don) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Chrysophyllum albidum G.Don

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32974; 1981-6-23

[WAG.1384475]

Total: 90; Anambra 4, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Edo 8, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 11, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 27, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 6.

Gambeya gigantea (A.Chev.) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Chrysophyllum giganteum A.Chev.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1961-4-19 [44551]1990429856

Total: 4; Osun 4.

Gambeya perpulchra (Mildbr. ex Hutch. & Dalziel) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Chrysophyllum perpulchrum Mildbr. ex Hutch. & Dalziel

Kennedy J.D. 2607; -- [BR0000020188689]

Total: 21; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Kebbi 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 6.

Gambeya prunifolia (Baker) Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Chrysophyllum prunifolium Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Gambeya subnuda (Baker) Pierre

Chrysophyllum subnudum Baker

Ariwaodo, JO 224; 1977-1-28 [WAG.1384895]

Total: 21; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 12, Ebonyi 1.

Malacantha alnifolia (Baker) Pierre

Chrysophyllum alnifolium Baker

Pilz, GE 2593; 1980-12-7 [WAG.1363167]

Total: 31; Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Manilkara obovata (Sabine & G.Don)

J.H.Hemsl.

Chrysophyllum obovatum Sabine & G.Don

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32642; 1981-6-14

[WAG.1363448]

Total: 138; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 3, Bauchi 8, Bayelsa 1, Benue 3, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Niger 6, Ogun 28, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 7, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Manilkara zapota (L.) P.Royen —

Introduced

Achras zapota L.

Latilo J.L.; 1965-2-1 [55923]1990430655

Total: 3; Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Mimusops andongensis Hiern

Emwiogbon, JA 578; 1974-3-6 [WAG.1363572]

Total: 14; Anambra 8, Bayelsa 1, Kano 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Mimusops kummel Bruce ex A.DC.

Pilz, GE 1984; 1977-4-25 [WAG.1830327]

Total: 37; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 4, Kaduna 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Neolemonniera batesii (Engl.) Heine

Mimusops batesii Engl.

Talbot P.A. 1574; 1912-- [BR0000019008400]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Omphalocarpum elatum Miers

Thomson 712; -- [BM000925520]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Rivers 1.

Omphalocarpum pachysteloides Mildbr. ex Hutch. & Dalziel

Ariwaodo, JO 688; 1977-5-16 [WAG.1363022]

Total: 11; Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Kwara 1.

Omphalocarpum procerum P.Beauv.

Tuley, P.826; 1964-8-25 [25703] [912022503]

Total: 4; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Planchonella forbesii (S.Moore) H.J.Lam —

Introduced

Sideroxylon forbesii S.Moore

Forbes, H.O.; 1885-1-1 [P04569056]

Total: 1.

Planchonella maclayana (F.Muell.)

Swenson — Introduced

Bassia maclayana F.Muell.

Perre, L.; 1872-8- [P04609778]

Total: 1.

Planchonella pomifera (Pierre ex Baill.)

Dubard — Introduced

Beauvisagea pomifera Pierre ex Baill.

Koster, C.; 1956-6-22 [P04585379]

Total: 1.

Synsepalum afzelii (Engl.) T.D.Penn.

Sersalisia afzelii Engl.

Kennedy J.D. 1021; -- [BR0000020183325]

Total: 18; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 2, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Oyo 1.

Synsepalum brenanii (Heine) T.D.Penn.

Vincentella brenanii Heine

Binuyo, A FHI 35589; 1956-3-9 [WAG.1530183]

Total: 2; Borno 2.

Synsepalum brevipes (Baker) T.D.Penn.

Sideroxylon brevipes Baker

Pilz, GE 1919; 1977-1-8 [WAG.1830261]

Total: 47; Adamawa 3, Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Ogun 9, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Synsepalum cerasiferum (Welw.) T.D.Penn.

Sapota cerasifera Welw.

Chapman J.D50; 1973-8-3 [70850] [1990431741]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Osun 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6.

Synsepalum dulcificum (Schumach. & Thonn.) Daniell

Bumelia dulcifica Schumach. & Thonn.

Setten, K van 217; 1978-8-30 [WAG.1840194]

Total: 24; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Synsepalum passargei (Engl.) T.D.Penn.

Bakerisideroxylon passargei Engl.

Peter & P. Tuley ; 1965-12-6 [V-169198]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Synsepalum revolutum (Baker) T.D.Penn.

Sideroxylon revolutum Baker

Pilz, GE 1966; 1977-4-24 [WAG.1530188]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Plateau 1.

Synsepalum seretii (De Wild.) T.D.Penn. — Introduced

Pachystela seretii De Wild.

Meer, PPC van 1212; 1971-4-7 [WAG.1363062]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 2.

Synsepalum stipulatum (Radlk.) Engl.

Stironeurum stipulatum Radlk.

Daramola, BO FHI 45685; 1961-12-11

[WAG.1829984]

Total: 31; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 21, Lagos 2, Taraba 1.

Tieghemella heckelii (A.Chev.) Pierre ex Heine

Dumoria heckelii A.Chev.

Literature

Total: 0.

Tridesmostemon omphalocarpoides Engl.

DR A.B. Kadiri; others; 2008-12-1 [9145]

[3808442784]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Vitellaria paradoxa C.F.Gaertn.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66347; 1973-5-14

[WAG.1530234]

Total: 103; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 12, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 7, Niger 17, Ogun 3, Oyo 15, Plateau 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Vitellaria paradoxa subsp. *paradoxa*

Évrard C. 6991; 1973-6-10 [BR0000020187033]

Total: 3; Niger 1.

EBENACEAE

Diospyros abyssinica (Hiern) F.White

Maba abyssinica Hiern

Jackson 17733; 1967-7-9 [3017621]

Total: 10; Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Diospyros abyssinica subsp. *abyssinica*

Maba abyssinica Hiern

Hambler D.J. 5176, 2/11/1958, K

Total: 3; Kaduna 2.

Diospyros barteri Hiern

Meikle R.D. 1393, 8/4/1950, K

Total: 60; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 4, Lagos 7, Ogun 7, Osun 2, Oyo 22, Taraba 1.

Diospyros canaliculata De Wild.

Diospyros cauliflora De Wild.

Latilo M.G. & Daramola B.O. FHI28719, 21/11/1954, K

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1.

Diospyros confertiflora (Hiern) Bakh. —
Introduced

Maba confertiflora Hiern

Brenan J.P.M., Onochie C., Jones E.W. & Richards
P.W.8418; -- [BR0000015666031]

Total: 1.

Diospyros conocarpa Gürke

Olorunfemi J., FHI38068, 10/6/1958, K

Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 21, Edo 2.

Diospyros crassiflora Hiern

Thomson 47, K

Total: 25; Cross River 1, Edo 5, Kaduna 7.

Diospyros dendo Welw. ex Hiern

Ejiofor, M.C. FHI24609, 30/10/1948, K

Total: 58; Cross River 2, Edo 20, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1,
Ogun 4, Ondo 9, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Diospyros elliotii (Hiern) F.White

Maba elliotii Hiern

Daramola, BO; Adebuseyi, JK FHI 38402; 1958-9-9
[WAG.1778723]

Total: 11; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1.

Diospyros ferrea (Willd.) Bakh.

Ehretia ferrea Willd.

Hepper F.N. 1061, 1957-58, K

Total: 27; Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 2,
Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Diospyros fragrans Gurke

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI33426 [K006362128]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Diospyros gabunensis Gürke

Onokie C.F.A. FHI33186, 16/5/1953, K

Total: 10; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 4.

Diospyros gracilescens Gürke

Kennedy J.D. 2611, 1/4/1935, K

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ondo 1.

Diospyros hoyleana F.White

Maba kamerunensis Gürke

Ndoma 903; 1995-12-6 [1053216] gbifID:
1258259738

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Diospyros hoyleana subsp. *hoyleana*

Maba kamerunensis Gürke

Richards P.W. 5163, 13/03/1955, K

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Diospyros iturensis (Gürke) Letouzey &
F.White

Maba iturensis Gürke

Okeke R.E. & Binuyo B. FHI36892, 5/8/1958, K

Total: 27; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross
River 3, Edo 7, Ogun 3.

Diospyros kamerunensis Gürke

B.O.Daramola; O.O.Oyebanji; 2013-1-23 [6732] gbif:
3808441963

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Diospyros mannii Hiern

Gray G.C.R. 2/11, 19/11/1934, K

Total: 5; Edo 2, Ondo 1.

Diospyros melocarpa F.White

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C.F. FHI8302, 11/5/1946,
FHI

Total: 1.

Diospyros mespiliformis Hochst. ex A.DC.

Hepper F.N. 1043, 16/10/1957, K

Total: 87; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 5,
Borno 3, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Gombe 3, Jigawa 1,
Kaduna 2, Kano 7, Katsina 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos
2, Nasarawa 3, Niger 9, Ogun 2, Oyo 9, Plateau 5,
Sokoto 1, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Diospyros monbuttensis Gürke

Brenan J.P.M. 9604, 17/4/1948, K

Total: 68; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1,
Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 8, Niger 2, Ogun 8, Ondo
6, Osun 4, Oyo 19, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Diospyros obliquifolia (Hiern ex Gürke)

F.White

Rhaphidanthe obliquifolia Hiern ex Gürke

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C.F. FHI17387, P

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Diospyros physocalycina Gürke

Onochie C.F.A. 9158, 26/2/1958, K

Total: 19; Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 3, Lagos 4,
Ondo 4, Osun 1, Taraba 1.

Diospyros piscatoria Gürke

Kennedy J.D. 1636; -- [BR0000015601902]

Total: 28; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 4, Kwara 1,
Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 8.

Diospyros platanoides Letouzey & F.White

Onyeachusim & Latilo M.G. FHI54229, 1/3/1964, K

Total: 1.

Diospyros preussii Gürke

Latilo M.G. FHI41335, 14/3/1959, K

Total: 23; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 11, Edo
1, Taraba 1.

Diospyros pseudomespilus Mildbr.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32739; 1981-6-16
[WAG.1180031]
Total: 14; Edo 4, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1,
Oyo 3.

Diospyros pseudomespilus subsp.
pseudomespilus

Olorunfemi J., FHI41520, 25/5/1959, K
Total: 8; Edo 4, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1.

Diospyros pseudomespilus subsp.
undabunda (Hiern ex Greves) F.White —
Introduced

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32739; 1981-6-16
[WAG.1180031]
Total: 1.

Diospyros soubreana F.White

Keay R.W.J. 22547, 19/4/1948, K
Total: 63; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 1,
Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 10, Osun 5, Oyo 23.

Diospyros suaveolens Gürke

Ross A.F. R.198, 1/5/1934, K
Total: 41; Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 5, Ekiti 1,
Kaduna 8, Ogun 7, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Diospyros tricolor (Schumach. & Thonn.)
Hiern

Noltia tricolor Schumach. & Thonn.

Eimunjeze, Opayemi & Ekwuno FHI70351, 2/3/1973,
K
Total: 5; Lagos 5.

Diospyros viridicans Hiern

Latilo M.G. FHI30930, 4/5/1952, K
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Imo 1.

Diospyros zenkeri (Gürke) F.White

Maba zenkeri Gürke

Tuley P. 832, 25/8/1964, K
Total: 18; Cross River 4, Edo 1, Ogun 6, Oyo 3.

PRIMULACEAE

Ardisia bamendae Cheek

Chapman, J.D. 4360; 1976-04-20 [K006391214]
Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Ardisia buesgenii (Gilg & G.Schellenb.)
Taton

Afrardisia buesgenii Gilg & G.Schellenb.
25057; 1948-12-20 [K000226002]
Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3.

Ardisia schlechteri Gilg

Brenan, J.P.M. 8894; 1948-1-25 [3370]912032375
Total: 2; Edo 2.

Ardisia staudtii Gilg

Chapman, JD 2812; 1972-5-8 [WAG.1113012]
Total: 19; Cross River 5, Edo 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1,
Taraba 2.

Ardisia zenkeri Gilg

Literature
Total: 0.

Embelia multiflora Taton — Introduced
Croat 53370; 1981-11-14 [2377846] [1259685452]
Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Embelia nilotica Oliv.

Magaji, SO 25; 1965-7-15 [WAG.1113258]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1.

Embelia rowlandii Gilg

Rowland s.n.; -- [K000226028]
Total: 5; Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Embelia schimperi Vatke

Meer, PPC van 1793; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1113320]
Total: 7; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Lysimachia arvensis (L.) U.Manns &
Anderb. — Introduced

Anagallis arvensis L.

Literature
Total: 0.

Lysimachia arvensis var. *arvensis* —
Introduced

Anagallis arvensis L.

Literature
Total: 0.

Lysimachia barbata (P.Taylor) U.Manns &
Anderb.

Anagallis pumila var. barbata P.Taylor
Geerling C. 4186; 1971-9-14 [45894]
Total: 4; Borno 1, Edo 1, Taraba 2.

Lysimachia djaloni (A.Chev.) U.Manns &
Anderb.

Anagallis djaloni A.Chev.
Ekwuno P.O.239; 1975-11-20 [77178] [1990432106]
Total: 14; Adamawa 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Kebbi
1, Taraba 6.

Lysimachia ovalis (Ruiz & Pav.) U.Manns
& Anderb.

Anagallis ovalis Ruiz & Pav.
Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO s.n.; 1974-11-22
[WAG.1221393]

Total: 25; Adamawa 2, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Lysimachia ruhmeriana Vatke

Hepper F.N. 1982; 1958-2-14 [BR0000019359977]
Total: 1.

Lysimachia tenuicaulis (Baker) U.Manns & Anderb. — Introduced

Anagallis tenuicaulis Baker
Chapman J.D.2781; 1972-5-1 [46072] [1990429913]
Total: 3; Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Maesa kamerunensis Mez

Daramola, B.O. FHI62722 [K001016176]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Maesa lanceolata Forssk.

Gbile, Wit & Daramola [US 2782015]
Total: 32; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 7, Plateau 7, Taraba 11.

Maesa lanceolata subsp. *lanceolata*

P.O. EkwunoEkwuno 92698; 1980-2-20 [100691073] [1258028945]
Total: 1.

Maesa lanceolata var. *golungensis* Hiern

Latilo, MG; Daramola, BO FHI 28991; 1955-1-4 [WAG.1113586]
Total: 5; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 2.

Myrsine melanophloeos (L.) R.Br. ex Sweet

Sideroxyylon melanophloeos L.
Chapman, J.D.; 3395; 1974-11-02 [K005936704]
Total: 3; Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Samolus valerandi L.

Literature
Total: 0.

THEACEAE

Camellia sinensis (L.) Kuntze — Introduced

Thea sinensis L.
T.K.Odewo;Ogundipe;Dr.A.B.Kadiri; 2008-08-18 [LUH.619.0]
Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Taraba 2.

Camellia sinensis var. *assamica* (Royle ex Hook.) Steenis — Introduced

Thea assamica Royle ex Hook.
Eijnatten, CLM van 2075; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1839268]
Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

ERICACEAE

Agarista salicifolia (Lam.) G.Don

Andromeda salicifolia Lam.
Chapman, JD 2688; 1972-2-23 [WAG.1182009]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Erica mannii (Hook.f.) Beentje

Ericinella mannii Hook.f.
Chapman, JD 2864; 1972-6-3 [WAG.1786976]
Total: 11; Edo 1, Taraba 7.

Erica mannii subsp. *mannii*

Ericinella mannii Hook.f.
Chapman, JD 2864; 1972-6-3 [WAG.1786976]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Erica silvatica (Welw. ex Engl.) Beentje

Blaeria silvatica Welw. ex Engl.
1951-8-17 [2252243072]
Total: 2; Sokoto 1.

METTENIUSACEAE

Apodytes dimidiata E.Mey. ex Arn.

Chapman, J.D.; 4135; 1976-02-10 [K006347677]
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Taraba 3.

Rhaphiostylis beninensis (Hook.f. ex Planch.) Planch. ex Benth.

Apodytes beninensis Hook.f. ex Planch.
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11301; 1977-3-31 [WAG.1399472]
Total: 59; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 4, Delta 2, Edo 4, Ekiti 3, Enugu 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Rhaphiostylis ferruginea Engl.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70541; 1973-3-8 [WAG.1399575]
Total: 10; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ogun 2.

Rhaphiostylis ferruginea var. *ferruginea*

Latilo, MG FHI 56851; 1965-6-22 [WAG.1399600]
Total: 1.

Rhaphiostylis preussii Engl.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI25485 [K006348462]
Total: 1; Ondo 1.

ICACINACEAE

Alsodeiopsis chippii subsp. *villosa* (Keay)
Govaerts

Alsodeiopsis villosa Keay
Ariwaodo, J.O. JOA631 [K004583215]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Alsodeiopsis rowlandii Engl.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11289; 1977-3-29
[WAG.1550576]
Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 3, Delta 3, Edo 4, Enugu 1,
Lagos 3, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Alsodeiopsis staudtii Engl.

Schlechter, FRR 13011; 1899-3-1 [WAG.1462586]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Icacina mannii Oliv.

Unknown s.n.; 2017-4-28 [WAG.1965355]
Total: 21; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 6, Edo 5,
Kwara 1.

Icacina mannii var. *mannii*

Onochie, CFA FHI 33175; 1953-5-15
[WAG.1463498]
Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 2.

Icacina oliviformis (Poir.) J.Raynal

Hirtella oliviformis Poir.
Collector unknown [BR0000021709982]
Total: 5; Niger 1, Ogun 2.

Icacina oliviformis var. *oliviformis*

Hirtella oliviformis Poir.
Collector unknown S.N.; -- [BR0000021709982]
Total: 1.

Icacina trichantha Oliv.

Pilz, GE 2655; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1463566]
Total: 80; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Anambra 3, Cross River 5, Delta 2, Edo 10, Ekiti 3,
Kogi 1, Lagos 10, Ogun 6, Osun 1, Oyo 20.

Iodes africana Welw. ex Oliv.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67764; 1973-3-1
[WAG.1463687]
Total: 33; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Edo
11, Kogi 2, Oyo 7.

Iodes kamerunensis Engl.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI36100X; 21-01-1957
[FHI0036100X]
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1.

Iodes klaineana Pierre

Talbot, P. [K000226232]
Total: 7; Cross River 3, Niger 2, Ogun 1.

Iodes klaineana var. *klaineana*

Gentry 32790; 1981-6-17 [165762]

Total: 1.

Iodes seretii (De Wild.) Boutique

Lasiodiscus seretii De Wild.
Redhead J.F. JFR655; 07-08-1964 [FHI0054932]
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Lavigeria macrocarpa (Oliv.) Pierre

Icacina macrocarpa Oliv.
Gentry 32884; 1981-6-20 [166040]
Total: 6; Cross River 4.

Pyrenacantha acuminata Engl.

Hepper F.N. 2295; -- [BR0000014268069]
Total: 3; Edo 1, Kogi 1.

Pyrenacantha rostrata (Bullock) Byng &
Utteridge — Endemic

Chlamydocarya rostrata Bullock
Literature
Total: 0.

Pyrenacantha staudtii (Engl.) Engl.

Chlamydocarya staudtii Engl.
Coombe D.E. [BR0000016755901]
Total: 33; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Kogi
2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 5, Oyo 5.

Pyrenacantha staudtii var. *staudtii*

Chlamydocarya staudtii Engl.
Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 72554; 1974-5-22
[WAG.1399274]
Total: 1.

Pyrenacantha thomsoniana (Baill.) Byng &
Utteridge

Chlamydocarya thomsoniana Baill.
Thomson, W.C. 12; -- [K000226241]
Total: 9; Cross River 4, Edo 4, Oyo 1.

Pyrenacantha undulata Engl.

Hepper, F.N. 2295; 1958-3-13 [P04472257]
Total: 4; Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Pyrenacantha vogeliana Baill.

Elizabeth Bamigboye LUH9651; s.n. [LUH]
Total: 1.

Stachyanthus occidentalis (Keay & J.Miège)
Boutique

Neostachyanthus occidentalis Keay & J.Miège
Pilz, GE 1871; 1976-12-10 [WAG.1399037]
Total: 20; Edo 1, Ogun 4, Osun 2, Oyo 11.

Stachyanthus zenkeri Engl.

Meer, PPC van 1141; 1971-4-2 [WAG.1399694]

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Vadensea tenuifolia (Oliv.) Jongkind & O.Lachenaud

Desmostachys tenuifolius Oliv.

Ariwaodo, JO 1036; 1977-10-24 [WAG.1463106]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Cross River 6, Kogi 1, Rivers 1.

RUBIACEAE

Adenorandia kalbreyeri (Hiern) Robbr. & Bridson

Gardenia kalbreyeri Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1508; 1971-4-27 [WAG.1403077]

Total: 14; Anambra 2, Cross River 7, Kogi 2, Oyo 1.

Aidia genipiflora (DC.) Dandy

Randia genipiflora DC.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32714; 1981-6-16

[WAG.1328184]

Total: 34; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Imo 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 11, Ondo 5, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Aidia micrantha (K.Schum.) Bullock ex F.White

Randia micrantha K.Schum.

Van Meer P. 722; 1968-4-25 [BR0000017977135]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Aidia rubens (Hiern) G.Taylor

Randia rubens Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1175; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1328622]

Total: 17; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 5, Cross River 10.

Aorantho cladantha (K.Schum.) Somers

Randia cladantha K.Schum.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11281; 1977-3-28

[WAG.1427882]

Total: 37; Abia 3, Anambra 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Edo 13, Kebbi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Argocoffeopsis afzelii (Hiern) Robbr. —
Introduced

Coffea afzelii Hiern

Keay R. FHI37389; 1958-1-26 [BR0000019750361]

Total: 1.

Argocoffeopsis eketensis (Wernham) Robbr.

Coffea eketensis Wernham

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD 174; 1972-5-5

[WAG.1428033]

Total: 15; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 2, Cross River 3, Enugu 1, Imo 3, Plateau 1.

Argocoffeopsis pulchella (K.Schum.) Robbr.

Coffea pulchella K.Schum.

Talbot P.A. 1536; -- [K000346936]

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.

Argocoffeopsis rupestris (Hiern) Robbr.

Coffea rupestris Hiern

L. Bernardi 8794; 1962-3-25 [S17-33053]

Total: 33; Edo 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 5, Ondo 8, Oyo 9.

Argocoffeopsis rupestris subsp. *rupestris*

Coffea rupestris Hiern

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 292; 1983-5-14 [WAG.1428047]

Total: 13; Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Oyo 5.

Argocoffeopsis subcordata (Hiern) Lebrun

Coffea subcordata Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70522; 1973-3-8

[WAG.1428127]

Total: 12; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 8.

Argostemma africanum K.Schum.

Medler J. 837; 17-08-1973 [K000510074]

Total: 1.

Atractogyne bracteata (Wernham) Hutch. & Dalziel

Afrohamelia bracteata Wernham

Daramola B.O. FHI55572; 1965-5-18 [K000042623]

Total: 5; Abia 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1.

Aulacocalyx caudata (Hiern) Keay

Randia caudata Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67717; 1973-2-27

[WAG.1428647]

Total: 20; Abia 3, Cross River 12, Ebonyi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1.

Aulacocalyx jasminiflora Hook.f.

Alwyn H. Gentry; George E. Pilz Gentry 32754; 1981-

6-17 [539436] [1261249676]

Total: 16; Edo 8, Imo 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2.

Aulacocalyx jasminiflora subsp. *jasminiflora*

Daramola B.O. FHI46017; 1962-4-17

[BR0000019753379]

Total: 11; Edo 5, Imo 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Aulacocalyx talbotii (Wernham) Keay

Dorothea talbotii Wernham

Talbot P.A. Mrs. 1546; -- [K000172555]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 5.

Belonophora coffeoides Hook.f.

Total: 18; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Belonophora coffeoides subsp. *hypoglauca*
(Welw. ex Hiern) S.E.Dawson & Cheek
Cope Morgan s.n.; -- [K000346917]
Total: 18; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Niger
1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Belonophora coriacea Hoyle
Daramola, BO; Fagbemi, A FHI 71107; 1974-8-3
[WAG.1385230]
Total: 31; Edo 9, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1,
Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Belonophora talbotii (Wernham) Keay
Diplosporopsis talbotii Wernham
Talbot P.A. 1056; 1912-- [BM000903182]
Total: 2.

Belonophora wernhamii Hutch. & Dalziel
Diplosporopsis coffeoides Wernham
Talbot P.A. 1649; -- [K000346919]
Total: 8; Cross River 5.

Bertiera adamsii (Hepper) N.Hallé
Sabicea adamsii Hepper
Literature
Total: 0.

Bertiera bracteolata Hiern
Ariwaodo, JO JOA 240; 1977-2-6 [WAG.1385741]
Total: 20; Benue 1, Cross River 12, Osun 2, Zamfara
1.

Bertiera breviflora Hiern
Binuyo A. FHI41239; 1959-4-15 [BR0000019650241]
Total: 35; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 11, Edo 6,
Imo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 1.

Bertiera chevalieri Hutch. & Dalziel
Meer, PPC van 930; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1385913]
Total: 7; Oyo 4.

Bertiera elabensis K.Krause
Onochie C.F.A. FHI33184; 16-05-1953 [K]
Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Delta 1, Rivers 1.

Bertiera laxa Benth.
Daramola B.O. FHI56380; 1965-9-4
[BR0000019652849]
Total: 16; Abia 3, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4.

Bertiera laxa var. *laxa*
Okafor, JC; Latilo, MG; Ariwaodo, JO 57603; 1966-1-
26 [WAG.1386102]
Total: 11; Abia 2, Cross River 3, Edo 4.

Bertiera racemosa (G.Don) K.Schum.
Wendlandia racemosa G.Don

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65980; 1973-1-27
[WAG.1552675]
Total: 59; Abia 9, Akwa Ibom 3, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1,
Cross River 16, Delta 3, Edo 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 2,
Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Bertiera racemosa var. *elephantina* N.Hallé
Binuyo A. FHI41448; 1959-8-13 [BR0000018017007]
Total: 23; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7, Edo 3,
Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Bertiera racemosa var. *glabrata* (K.Schum.)
Hutch. & Dalziel
Bertiera glabrata K.Schum.
Hossain M.; Opayemi J. 1204; 26-10-1971 [LUH]
Total: 1.

Bertiera racemosa var. *racemosa*
Wendlandia racemosa G.Don
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67658; 1973-2-22
[WAG.1552808]
Total: 10; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2,
Kogi 2.

Bertiera retrofracta K.Schum.
Latilo, M.G.30942; 1952-5-6 [5012] [912050292]
Total: 6; Cross River 6.

Bertiera spicata (C.F.Gaertn.) K.Schum. —
Introduced
Pomatium spicatum C.F.Gaertn.
K. Schmitt; T.O. IbiangSchmitt 360; 1995-2-8
[976715] [1261904418]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Bertiera subsessilis Hiern
Barter 1831; -- [K000414684]
Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 3, Rivers 3.

Brenania brieyi (De Wild.) E.M.A.Petit
Anthocleista brieyi De Wild.
Onochie C.F.A. FHI33163; 14-05-1953 [K]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Edo 3.

Breonadia salicina (Vahl) Hepper &
J.R.I.Wood
Nerium salicinum Vahl
Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK; Macauley, S FHI
66415; 1973-5-17 [WAG.1553520]
Total: 37; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Gombe 1,
Kaduna 6, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 5, Plateau 1,
Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2, Zamfara 3.

Calycosiphonia spathicalyx (K.Schum.)
Robbr.
Coffea spathicalyx K.Schum.
Meer, PPC van 1039; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1553704]

Total: 14; Benue 1, Ogun 8, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Canthium annonifolium Webb

Unplaced according to POWO

Total: 1.

Canthium triacanthum Webb

Unplaced according to POWO

Total: 1.

Catunaregam nilotica (Stapf) Tirveng.

Randia nilotica Stapf

Latilo, MG FHI 64715; 1971-12-3 [WAG.1543110]

Total: 18; Bauchi 7, Gombe 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Chassalia cristata (Hiern) Bremek.

Psychotria cristata Hiern

Dr Kadiri; 2008-12-1 [2404]3808440162

Total: 2; Edo 1, Taraba 1.

Chassalia cupularis Hutch. & Dalziel

J. Ntui; E. Bebiem; Ntui 694; 1995-10-31 [1036255.0]

Total: 14; Cross River 9, Niger 2.

Chassalia ischnophylla (K.Schum.) Hepper

Psychotria ischnophylla K.Schum.

Brenan J.P.M.; Onochie C.F.A. 9089; 21-02-1948 [K]

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Edo 3.

Chassalia kolly (Schumach.) Hepper

Psychotria kolly Schumach.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32675; 1981-6-14

[WAG.1437503]

Total: 92; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 4, Edo 5, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Ogun 20, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 22, Taraba 1.

Chassalia laikomensis Cheek

Meer, PPC van 1745; 1971-5-22 [WAG0233215]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Taraba 1.

Chassalia manningii O.Lachenaud

Specimen seen at K

Total: 1.

Chassalia pteropetala (K.Schum.) Cheek

Psychotria pteropetala K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1468; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1437703]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Chassalia subherbacea (Hiern) Hepper

Psychotria subherbacea Hiern

Ariwaodo, JO 218; 1977-1-28 [WAG.1437775]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Chassalia subnuda (Hiern) Hepper

Psychotria subnuda Hiern

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11286; 1977-3-29

[WAG.1437790]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Delta 4, Edo 1, Rivers 1.

Chassalia subspicata K.Schum.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70502; 1973-3-5

[WAG.1437833]

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Cinchona pubescens Vahl — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Coffea arabica L. — Introduced

Odewo 798; 1977-8-26 [1124821]

Total: 6; Lagos 3, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Coffea brevipes Hiern

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 207; 1983-5-11 [WAG.1296768]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ogun 4.

Coffea canephora Pierre ex A.Froehner

Olorunfemi, J; Daramola, BO FHI 71004; 1974-7-9

[WAG.1386743]

Total: 21; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 8, Ogun 2, Ondo 6.

Coffea carrissoi A.Chev. — Introduced

Daramola 72336; 1973-10-5 [1124352]1258336398

Total: 1.

Coffea ebracteolata (Hiern) Brenan

Psilanthus ebracteolatus Hiern

Daramola, BO; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 38411; 1958-9-10

[WAG.1403423]

Total: 5; Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Oyo 1.

Coffea liberica W.Bull

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 57928; 1966-1-27

[WAG.1386915]

Total: 14; Edo 3, Lagos 6, Ogun 2.

Coffea liberica var. *liberica*

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI17214; 29-03-1946

[K000466058]

Total: 1.

Coffea mannii (Hook.f.) A.P.Davis

Psilanthus mannii Hook.f.

Olu Adekunle A. FHI24228; 1948-10-27

[BR0000019882468]

Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Coffea mayombensis A.Chev.

Keay, R.W.J. ; 1957-11-26 [P00336575]

Total: 5; Benue 1, Edo 3.

Cordylostigma virgatum (Willd.)

Groeninckx & Dessein

Hedyotis virgata Willd.

Vogel s.n.; -- [K000414259]

Total: 4; Kogi 1.

Corynanthe johimbe K.Schum.

Osain, EJ FHI 60608; 1975-2-25 [WAG.1252557]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 4, Cross River 2, Edo 5, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Corynanthe macroceras K.Schum.

Lowe, J 1744; 1969-8-6 [WAG.1252674]

Total: 32; Borno 6, Cross River 4, Edo 12, Ogun 4.

Corynanthe pachyceras K.Schum.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32731; 1981-6-16

[WAG.1207519]

Total: 32; Cross River 5, Edo 5, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 2.

Corynanthe talbotii (Wernham) Å.Krüger & Löfstrand

Pausinystalia talbotii Wernham

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11273; 1977-3-28

[WAG.1252682]

Total: 29; Cross River 4, Edo 3, Niger 6, Ogun 8, Osun 1.

Craterispermum aristatum Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1270; 1971-4-14 [WAG0048316]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 5.

Craterispermum capitatum Taedoung & De Block

Literature

Total: 0.

Craterispermum caudatum Hutch.

Daramola, BO; Emwiogbon, JA FHI 44280; 1961-2-

12 [WAG0042689]

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Edo 2.

Craterispermum cerinanthum Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67738; 1973-2-28

[WAG0233821]

Total: 66; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 15, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 8, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Craterispermum laurinum (Poir.) Benth. —
Introduced

Coffea laurina Poir.

Wit, P; Wit, J 1182; 1972-2-3 [WAG.1586772]

Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Craterispermum schweinfurthii Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1405; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1586788]

Total: 12; Cross River 3, Kaduna 3, Plateau 5, Taraba 1.

CreMASpora thomsonii Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67719; 1973-2-27

[WAG.1207734]

Total: 11; Cross River 9.

CreMASpora triflora (Thonn.) K.Schum.

Psychotria triflora Thonn.

Laan, FM van der 377; 1981-7-9 [WAG.1207769]

Total: 68; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Anambra 1, Benue 2, Cross River 8, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 6, Niger 3, Ogun 13, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 20, Taraba 1.

CreMASpora triflora subsp. *triflora*

Psychotria triflora Thonn.

Ntui 939; 1995-12-19 [1053240]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Crossopteryx febrifuga (Afzel. ex G.Don)
Benth.

Rondeletia febrifuga Afzel. ex G.Don

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32649; 1981-6-14

[WAG.1208017]

Total: 71; Anambra 2, Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 4, Kaduna 4, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 11, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Oyo 7, Plateau 2, Taraba 6, Zamfara 1.

Cuviera acutiflora DC.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86366; 1978-5-15

[WAG.1208401]

Total: 60; Abia 4, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Osun 3, Oyo 13, Plateau 4, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Cuviera calycosa Wernham

Talbot, Mr P.A. 3300; -- [K000412057]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 1, Niger 2.

Cuviera longiflora Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1771; 1971-5-23 [WAG0114730]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Cuviera macroura K.Schum.

Millen, H. 159; -- [K000412062]

Total: 6; Benue 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 3.

Cuviera nigrescens (Elliot ex Oliv.)
Wernham

Vangueria nigrescens Elliot ex Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 857; 1968-7-30 [WAG.1208513]

Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Edo 6, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 3.

Cuviera subuliflora Benth.

Meer, PPC van 892; 1968-11-13 [WAG.1208536]

Total: 17; Cross River 1, Ondo 7, Osun 1.

Cuviera trilocularis Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1261; 1971-4-14 [WAG.1208542]

Total: 10; Cross River 10.

Cuviera truncata Hutch. & Dalziel

Chapman, JD 3008; 1973-1-5 [WAG.1208544]

Total: 16; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Didymosalpinx abbeokutae (Hiern) Keay

Gardenia abbeokutae Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1088; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1500081]

Total: 12; Cross River 3, Oyo 9.

Diodia rubricosa Hiern

Gillett, J.B.; 15262; 1962-08-03 [K006211770]

Total: 3; Lagos 2.

Diodia virginiana L. — Introduced

Usang Felix; 2005-10-14 [258]3913474544

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Dolichopentas decora (S.Moore) Kårehed &

B.Bremer

Pentas decora S.Moore

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Dolichopentas decora var. *triangularis* (De

Wild.) Kårehed & B.Bremer

Pentas triangularis De Wild.

Gledhill, D 847; 1968-3-7 [WAG.1253633]

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Edrastima goreensis (DC.) Neupane &

N.Wikstr.

Hedyotis goreensis DC.

Daramola, BO 150; 1977-3-12 [WAG.1460383]

Total: 14; Enugu 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Empogona discolor (Brenan) Tosh & Robbr.

Tricalysia discolor Brenan

Adebusuyi J.K. FHI43987; 10-09-1960 [Oban Group

F.R. Road leading to Calaro Estate]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Empogona macrophylla (K.Schum.) Tosh &

Robbr.

Tricalysia macrophylla K.Schum.

Olorunfemi J. FHI.43867; 1959-11-23

[BR0000020210816]

Total: 7; Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 3.

Empogona reflexa (Hutch.) Tosh & Robbr.

Tricalysia reflexa Hutch.

Dalziel J.M. 1379; 21-04-1919 [K]

Total: 3; Abia 1.

Empogona reflexa var. *reflexa*

Tricalysia reflexa Hutch.

Empogona talbotii (Wernham) Tosh &

Robbr.

Cremaspora talbotii Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1338; 1971-4-17 [WAG.1296525]

Total: 23; Abia 2, Cross River 13, Enugu 1.

Euclinia longiflora Salisb.

Daramola, BO; Ibhanebhor, G FHI 70303; 1973-2-18 [WAG.1500653]

Total: 28; Borno 2, Cross River 3, Edo 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 7, Oyo 5.

Eumachia domaticola (De Wild.) Razafim.

& C.M.Taylor

Psychotria domaticola De Wild.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67733; 1973-2-28 [WAG.1438252]

Total: 8; Cross River 4, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1.

Eumachia insidens (Hiern) Razafim. &

C.M.Taylor

Psychotria insidens Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1360; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1438290]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 14, Lagos 2.

Eumachia insidens subsp. *insidens*

Psychotria insidens Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1159; 1971-4-3 [WAG.1438296]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 6, Lagos 1.

Eumachia obanensis (Wernham) Razafim. &

C.M.Taylor

Psychotria obanensis Wernham

Talbot P.A. s.n.; -- [K000412373]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Eumachia oddonii (De Wild.) Razafim. &

C.M.Taylor

Psychotria oddonii De Wild.

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 3, Taraba 1.

Eumachia oddonii var. *cameroonensis*

(Verdc.) C.M.Taylor

Chazaliella oddonii var. cameroonensis Verdc.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 352; 1983-5-17 [WAG.1438513]

Total: 3; Ogun 2.

Eumachia sciadephora (Hiern) Razafim. & C.M.Taylor

Psychotria sciadephora Hiern
Lowe J. 2039; 03-03-1970 [K]
Total: 48; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 9, Edo 15, Niger 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 2.

Eumachia sciadephora var. *sciadephora*

Psychotria sciadephora Hiern
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70511; 1973-3-5
[WAG.1438666]
Total: 1.

Fadogia ancylantha Schweinf.

Dalziel J.M. 554; -- [BR0000019456058]
Total: 5; Niger 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Fadogia andersonii Robyns

Nodza; Prof. Ogundipe; 2012-4-5 [1402A]
[3808440238]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Fadogia cienkowskii Schweinf.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1102; 1972-5-17
[WAG.1500824]
Total: 36; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Enugu 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 13, Taraba 4.

Fadogia cienkowskii var. *cienkowskii*

Fadogia erythrophloea (K.Schum. & K.Krause) Hutch. & Dalziel

Vangueria erythrophloea K.Schum. & K.Krause
Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi DO. 103; 1979-4-23
[WAG.1500847]
Total: 37; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 11, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Niger 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 5.

Fadogia glaberrima Welw. ex Hiern

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63209; 1970-3-26
[WAG.1500862]
Total: 7; Adamawa 3, Kogi 1, Taraba 3.

Fadogia pobeguinii Pobég.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK; Macauley, S 66970;
1973-5-23 [WAG.1500910]
Total: 4; Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Fadogia tetraquetra K.Schum. & K.Krause

Total: 22; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Kaduna 7, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

Fadogia tetraquetra var. *grandiflora*

(Robyns) Verdc.
Dalziel, J.M. 218; 1906-2-9 [K000411918]
Total: 22; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Kaduna 7, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

Feretia apodanthera Delile

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1744; 1972-5-4
[WAG.1501154]
Total: 36; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 3, Kano 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Niger 2, Plateau 2.

Feretia apodanthera subsp. *apodanthera*

Van Blom - van Teyn 78; 1971-6-4
[BR0000015677679]
Total: 2; Kano 2.

Gaertnera bieleri (De Wild.) E.M.A.Petit

Psychotria bieleri De Wild.
Meer, PPC van 1185; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1271275]
Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 3.

Gaertnera eketensis Wernham — Endemic

Meer, PPC van 1174; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1271323]
Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 4, Edo 1.

Gaertnera paniculata Benth.

Meer, PPC van 956; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1271682]
Total: 46; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 4, Bayelsa 2, Edo 2, Enugu 4, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 9.

Galiniera saxifraga (Hochst.) Bridson — Introduced

Pouchetia saxifraga Hochst.
Akomaye F.; 2018-01-16 [3879587571]
Total: 1.

Galium aparine L. — Introduced

Chapman, H.M. 123 [K006239969]
Total: 5; Borno 1, Plateau 2.

Galium simense Fresen.

Daramola, BO FHI 40639; 1959-1-26
[WAG.1819567]
Total: 3.

Gardenia aqualla Stapf & Hutch.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO; Wit, P 1228; 1972-5-3
[WAG.1322150]
Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Lagos 1, Niger 4.

Gardenia erubescens Stapf & Hutch.

Wit, P; Geerling, C 1266; 1972-3-18 [WAG.1322217]
Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Niger 6, Oyo 1, Zamfara 1.

Gardenia imperialis K.Schum.

K. Schmitt; T.O. Ibiang-Schmitt 391; 1995-2-8
[976756] [1261904471]
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Gardenia imperialis subsp. *imperialis*

Miss A. McClintock 205; 08-02-1945 [K]

Total: 3; Edo 1.

Gardenia imperialis subsp. *physophylla*

(K.Schum.) L.Pauwels

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C.F.A. 17262; --

[BR0000008604996]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Gardenia jasminoides J.Ellis — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1446; 1966-4-24 [WAG.1322329]

Total: 4; Lagos 2, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Gardenia nitida Hook.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67790; 1973-3-5

[WAG.1322350]

Total: 16; Cross River 4, Kogi 5, Ogun 2, Oyo 5.

Gardenia sokotensis Hutch.

Geerling, C 3219; 1970-10-29 [WAG.1322410]

Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Niger 1, Sokoto 4, Taraba 1.

Gardenia ternifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Wit, P 1285; 1972-3-21 [WAG.1263760]

Total: 22; Bauchi 6, Gombe 1, Kwara 1, Niger 4, Oyo 5, Sokoto 1.

Gardenia ternifolia subsp. *jovis-tonantis*

(Welw.) Verdc.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1169; 1972-4-28

[WAG.1263761]

Total: 5; Bauchi 4, Niger 1.

Gardenia ternifolia subsp. *ternifolia*

Chapman, JD 2856; 1972-6-2 [WAG.1263830]

Total: 4; Oyo 1.

Gardenia ternifolia var. *goetzei* (Stapf & Hutch.) Verdc.

Dalziel, Dr. J.M. [E00177229]

Total: 1.

Gardenia thunbergia Thunb. — Introduced

Dalziel, Dr. J.M.; -- [E00177229]575303623

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Gardenia vogelii Hook.f.

Talbot P.A. 1243; 10-05-1912 [K]

Total: 5; Borno 1, Plateau 1.

Geophila afzelii Hiern

Pilz, GE 2642; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1264155]

Total: 25; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Edo 5, Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Geophila herbacea (Jacq.) K.Schum.

Psychotria herbacea Jacq.

Literature

Total: 0.

Geophila lancistipula Hiern

Brenan J.P.M. 8622; 1947-12-28 [BR0000008026361]

Total: 4; Edo 3.

Geophila obvallata (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Didr.

Psychotria obvallata Schumach. & Thonn.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 398; 1977-10-15

[WAG.1264315]

Total: 30; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Edo 8, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 3.

Geophila obvallata subsp. *obvallata*

Psychotria obvallata Schumach. & Thonn.

Pilz, GE 2407; 1980-5-14 [WAG.1264316]

Total: 10; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ogun 3.

Geophila repens (L.) I.M.Johnst. —

Introduced

Rondeletia repens L.

Tuley P.; Magaji S.O. 1745; 23-10-1969 [K]

Total: 15; Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 3.

Globulostylis minor Wernham

Talbot P.A. 247; 1911-- [BM000903505]

Total: 1.

Globulostylis talbotii Wernham

Talbot, Mr P.A. 2051; -- [K000412052]

Total: 1.

Hamelia patens Jacq. — Introduced

Fadayomi Babatunde; 2010-3-13 [1695]3808440254

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Heinsia crinita (Wennberg) G.Taylor

Gardenia crinita Wennberg

Mrs Falope; 2010-10-6 [2994] [3808440968]

Total: 15; Cross River 6, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Heinsia crinita subsp. *crinita*

Gardenia crinita Wennberg

Bebiem 1179; 1996-1-8 [1054377]1258261020

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Hekistocarpa minutiflora Hook.f.

Daramola B.O. FHI55567; 17-05-1965 [K]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Hexasepalum sarmentosum (Sw.) Delprete & J.H.Kirkbr.

Diodia sarmentosa Sw.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70719; 1973-3-6

[WAG.1500238]

Total: 23; Cross River 4, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Hexasepalum scandens (Sw.) J.H.Kirkbr. & Delprete — Introduced

Diodia scandens Sw.

Pilz, GE 2650; 1981-11-18 [WAG.1500285]

Total: 31; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Hexasepalum serrulatum (P.Beauv.)

J.H.Kirkbr. & Delprete

Spermacoce serrulata P.Beauv.

Palisot de Beauvois s.n.; -- [100364467]1257713091

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Hexasepalum vaginale (Benth.) Cabaña

Fader & Dessein

Diodia vaginalis Benth.

Daramola, BO FHI 46333; 1962-12-14

[WAG.1500383]

Total: 11; Bayelsa 2, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1.

Hymenocoleus hirsutus (Benth.) Robbr.

Geophila hirsuta Benth.

Pilz, GE 2568; 1980-11-25 [WAG.1419198]

Total: 15; Edo 4, Ogun 4.

Hymenocoleus neurodictyon (K.Schum.)

Robbr.

Psychotria neurodictyon K.Schum.

Ndoma; J. Ntui Ndoma 839; 1995-12-6 [1053109] [1258259637]

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Edo 4.

Hymenocoleus neurodictyon var.

neurodictyon

Psychotria neurodictyon K.Schum.

Brenan J.P.M. 8461; 1947-12-10 [BR0000006716226]

Total: 6; Edo 4.

Hymenocoleus rotundifolius (A.Chev. ex

Hepper) Robbr.

Geophila rotundifolia A.Chev. ex Hepper

Paul Westmacott Richards 3311; 1935-3-26

[BM013860191]

Total: 2; Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Hymenocoleus subipeacuanha (K.Schum.)

Robbr.

Uragoga subipeacuanha K.Schum.

Onyeachusim; Latilo M.G. FHI54285; 14-03-1964 [K]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Osun 2.

Hymenodictyon biafranum Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1813; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1419353]

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Hymenodictyon floribundum (Hochst. & Steud.) B.L.Rob.

Kurria floribunda Hochst. & Steud.

Chapman, JD 2728 a; 1972-5-2 [WAG.1419463]

Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Taraba 6.

Hymenodictyon pachyantha K.Krause

1959-4-25 [2252245796]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Ixora alba L.

Ifoh Clement; 2010-3-2 [7400] [3808441061]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Ixora bauchiensis Hutch. & Dalziel

Gbile, ZO FHI 63239; 1970-3-30 [WAG.1419681]

Total: 35; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Lagos 3, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Plateau 7, Taraba 5.

Ixora brachypoda DC.

Latilo, MG FHI 61431; 1971-11-3 [WAG.1419765]

Total: 43; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 5, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Oyo 2, Taraba 3.

Ixora coccinea L. — Introduced

Wit, P 527; 1971-10-3 [WAG.1419825]

Total: 28; Abia 1, Lagos 17, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 5.

Ixora coccinea var. *coccinea* — Introduced

Wit, P 527; 1971-10-3 [WAG.1419825]

Total: 1.

Ixora delicatula Keay

Talbot P.A. 3822; 1916-- [BM000517275]

Total: 1.

Ixora euosmia K.Schum.

Talbot P.A. 3767; -- [K000411827]

Total: 3; Rivers 3.

Ixora finlaysoniana Wall. ex G.Don —

Introduced

Daramola & Okafor 44948; -- [BR0000018348576]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Ixora foliosa Hiern

Chapman J.D. 3705; 09-02-1975 [K]

Total: 8; Sokoto 1, Taraba 5.

Ixora guineensis Benth.

Meer, PPC van 1447; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1311284]

Total: 26; Cross River 16, Edo 3, Plateau 2.

Ixora hippoperifera Bremek.

Meer, PPC van 1440; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1311346]

Total: 8; Abia 2, Cross River 3.

Ixora minutiflora Hiern

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Ixora minutiflora subsp. *chasalliensis* De Block

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST s.n.; 1973-2-26

[WAG.1311515]

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Ixora nematopoda K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1606; 1971-5-12 [WAG.1311567]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 7, Oyo 1.

Ixora nigerica Keay

Ujor, E.; FHI30176; 1952-05-17 [K005896935]

Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7.

Ixora nigerica subsp. *nigerica* — Endemic

Meer, PPC van 1709; 1971-5-19 [WAG.1311570]

Total: 6; Cross River 6.

Ixora parviflora Lam.

Chigozie; 2017-3-30 [7546]

Total: 11; Lagos 3, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Keetia acuminata Bridson

Plectronia acuminata De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Keetia cornelia (Cham. & Schltdl.) Bridson

Canthium cornelia Cham. & Schltdl.

; 2007-2-13 [FR-0034747]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Keetia gueinzii (Sond.) Bridson

Canthium gueinzii Sond.

Hepper F.N. 1897; 1958-2-10 [BR0000024869874]

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Keetia hispida (Benth.) Bridson

Canthium hispidum Benth.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 537; 1978-5-30

[WAG.1542554]

Total: 38; Cross River 7, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 10, Niger 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Keetia inaequilatera (Hutch. & Dalziel)

Bridson — Endemic

Canthium inaequilaterum Hutch. & Dalziel

Talbot P.A. 277; -- [K000422565]

Total: 3; Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Keetia leucantha (K.Krause) Bridson

Plectronia leucantha K.Krause

Meer, PPC van 876; 1968-9-19 [WAG.1312175]

Total: 8; Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 5.

Keetia mannii (Hiern) Bridson

Canthium mannii Hiern

Geerling, C 5594; 1976-1-23 [WAG.1312250]

Total: 32; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 5, Lagos 7, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Rivers 1.

Keetia molundensis (K.Krause) Bridson —

Introduced

Plectronia molundensis K.Krause

Literature

Total: 0.

Keetia molundensis var. *macrostipulata* (De

Wild.) Bridson — Introduced

Plectronia macrostipulata De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Keetia multiflora (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Bridson

Psychotria multiflora Schumach. & Thonn.

Wit, P 523; 1971-9-30 [WAG.1312268]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Oyo 2.

Keetia rufivillosa (Robyns ex Hutch. &

Dalziel) Bridson

Canthium rufivillosum Robyns ex Hutch. &

Dalziel

Baldwin, J.T. 13790; 1949-11-22 [K000043053]

Total: 3; Abia 3.

Keetia tenuiflora (Welw. ex Hiern) Bridson

Canthium tenuiflorum Welw. ex Hiern

Daramola B.O.; Adebusuyi J.K. FHI72345; 06-10-1973 [K]

Total: 2.

Keetia venosa (Oliv.) Bridson

Plectronia venosa Oliv.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 318; 1978-5-5 [WAG.1206324]

Total: 95; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 2, Benue 3, Borno 2, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Enugu 5, Kaduna 7, Kogi 5, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 8, Ondo 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 18, Taraba 4.

Knoxia hedyotoidea (K.Schum.) Puff &

Robbr.

Baumannia hedyotoidea K.Schum.

Hepper F.N. 1031; 1957-10-15 [BR0000018061109]

Total: 15; Benue 1, Niger 2, Ondo 7, Plateau 4.

Kohautia coccinea Royle

Hepper F.N. 1119; 1957-10-23 [BR0000018061758]
Total: 11; Gombe 2, Jigawa 2, Niger 1, Plateau 2,
Taraba 1.

Kohautia confusa (Hutch. & Dalziel)

Bremek.

Oldenlandia confusa Hutch. & Dalziel
Croat 53378; 1981-11-14 [2377857]
Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1.

Kohautia grandiflora DC.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO; Mogaji FHI 72891; 1974-
11-21 [WAG.1206687]

Total: 42; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1,
Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1,
Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba
2, Zamfara 1.

Kohautia tenuis (Bowdich) Mabb.

Duvaucellia tenuis Bowdich
Latilo, MG FHI 63848; 1971-10-19 [WAG.1206817]
Total: 38; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Enugu 1,
Gombe 3, Kaduna 3, Kano 3, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger
5, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 3, Yobe 2.

Lasianthus batangensis K.Schum.

Talbot, Mr P.A. 266; -- [K000172650]
Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Niger 1, Rivers 1,
Taraba 1.

Lelya osteocarpa Bremek.

Lely, H.V. P.96; -- [K000414380]
Total: 12; Bauchi 6, Plateau 5.

Leptactina arborescens (Welw. ex Benth. &
Hook.f.) De Block

Dictyandra arborescens Welw. ex Benth. &
Hook.f.
Latilo, MG FHI 67751; 1973-3-1 [WAG.1500017]
Total: 49; Abia 1, Cross River 10, Edo 7, Imo 2,
Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 6, Oyo 1,
Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Leptactina densiflora Hook.f.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 344; 1983-5-17 [WAG.1207423]
Total: 28; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Lagos 6,
Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Oyo 2.

Leptactina involucrata Hook.f.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67675; 1973-2-22
[WAG.1207486]
Total: 44; Abia 3, Benue 1, Cross River 9, Edo 3,
Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Macrosphyra brachysiphon Wernham —

Endemic

Talbot, Mr P.A. 3764; -- [K000419799]

Total: 7; Delta 1, Oyo 1.

Macrosphyra longistyla (DC.) Hook.f. ex
Hiern

Randia longistyla DC.
Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi DO 76; 1979-4-21
[WAG.1420316]
Total: 70; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 4,
Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Ogun
4, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 11, Plateau 11, Taraba 3,
Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Massularia acuminata (G.Don) Bullock ex
Hoyle

Gardenia acuminata G.Don
Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST 67632; 1973-2-22
[WAG.1420748]
Total: 63; Borno 1, Cross River 24, Edo 11, Kogi 2,
Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2,
Rivers 1.

Mitracarpus baturitensis Sucre —

Introduced

Ariwaodo 37; 1977-12-6 [100438186]1257785450
Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Mitracarpus hirtus (L.) DC. — Introduced

Spermacoce hirta L.
Croat, TB 53384; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1420945]
Total: 73; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 5,
Cross River 1, Edo 4, Imo 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 2,
Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 9, Niger 5, Ogun 3,
Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba
1.

Mitragyna ciliata Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Stanfield, DP; Aldebusuyi, JK 55929; 1965-2-22
[WAG.1264526]
Total: 6; Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Rivers 1.

Mitragyna inermis (Willd.) Kuntze

Uncaria inermis Willd.
Croat, TB 53412; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1421002]
Total: 66; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 5, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River
1, Delta 1, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 3, Kano
1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto
1, Taraba 2.

Mitragyna stipulosa (DC.) Kuntze

Nauclea stipulosa DC.
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11322; 1977-4-1 [WAG.1264643]
Total: 55; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Cross River
7, Delta 3, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3,
Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 3.

Morelia senegalensis A.Rich. ex DC.

Daramola, BO 43; 1977-8-13 [WAG.1458767]

Total: 87; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 3, Bauchi 4, Bayelsa 1, Benue 5, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 7, Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 15, Ogun 4, Oyo 5, Taraba 5.

Morinda chrysorrhiza (Thonn.) DC. —

Introduced

Psychotria chrysorrhiza Thonn.

Dalziel, J.M.8189; -- [22211] [912018561]

Total: 3; Oyo 1.

Morinda longiflora G.Don

Meer, PPC van 1005; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1458992]

Total: 15; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Lagos 2, Oyo 5, Sokoto 1.

Morinda lucida Benth.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63182; 1972-7-17

[WAG.1459091]

Total: 61; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 21, Ogun 8, Ondo 1, Osun 6, Oyo 16.

Morinda morindoides (Baker) Milne-Redh.

Gaertnera morindoides Baker

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11225; 1977-3-18

[WAG.1459279]

Total: 42; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 10, Niger 2, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 8.

Morinda titanophylla E.M.A.Petit —

Introduced

J. NtuiNtui 957; 1995-12-19 [1053276] [1258259815]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Mussaenda afzelioides Wernham —

Endemic

Percy Amaury Talbot 212; 1911-- [BM000902916]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Mussaenda arcuata Poir.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70530; 1973-3-9

[WAG.1459803]

Total: 66; Abia 6, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 10, Edo 6, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Oyo 3, Plateau 11, Taraba 6.

Mussaenda elegans Schumach. & Thonn.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi DO 74; 1979-4-21

[WAG.1517523]

Total: 84; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 9, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Lagos 9,

Nasarawa 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 14, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 5.

Mussaenda epiphytica Cheek

Meer, PPC van 1840; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1517567]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Mussaenda erythrophylla Schumach. & Thonn.

Pilz, GE 1958; 1977-4-24 [WAG.1517682]

Total: 34; Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 6, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 8, Taraba 6.

Mussaenda isertiana DC.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11218; 1977-3-17

[WAG.1517797]

Total: 59; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 4, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Enugu 6, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 14, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Mussaenda landolphioides Wernham —
Endemic

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67643; 1973-2-22

[WAG.1517813]

Total: 29; Bauchi 1, Cross River 4, Edo 5, Lagos 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Mussaenda nivea A.Chev. ex Hutch. & Dalziel — Introduced

Bels, L 78; 1950-4-16 [U.1568992]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Mussaenda polita Hiern

Latilo, MG; Onyeachusim, HD FHI 53969; 1964-2-18

[WAG.1517918]

Total: 23; Anambra 1, Cross River 9, Lagos 9, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Mussaenda tenuiflora Benth.

Pilz, GE 2015; 1977-4-26 [WAG.1518022]

Total: 30; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 11, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Rivers 1.

Mussaenda tenuiflora var. *tenuiflora*

Sharland R.E. ; 14-04-1981 [K]

Total: 1.

Mussaenda tristigmatica Cummins —
Introduced

1950-8-18 [2252244098]

Total: 1; Edo 1.

Mussaenda zenkeri Wernham

Van Meer P. 795; 1968-5-17 [BR0000019764689]

Total: 3; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Ondo 1.

Nauclea diderrichii (De Wild.) Merr.

Sarcocephalus diderrichii De Wild.
Omiyale, F FHI 44260; 1960-5-25 [WAG.1518245]
Total: 30; Abia 1, Borno 4, Edo 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1,
Niger 1, Ogun 3, Taraba 1.

Nauclea gillettii (De Wild.) Merr.

Sarcocephalus gillettii De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Nauclea latifolia Sm.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 487; 1978-5-24
[WAG.1400507]

Total: 83; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3,
Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Delta 3, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna
5, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 6, Lagos 13,
Niger 6, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 7, Taraba 10,
Zamfara 2.

Nauclea pobeguini (Pobég.) Merr.

Sarcocephalus pobeguini Pobég.

Hereźniak J. ; 1975-2-11 [POZG-V-0035110]

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Nauclea vanderguchtii (De Wild.)

E.M.A.Petit

Sarcocephalus vanderguchtii De Wild.

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1604; -- [K000394939]

Total: 15; Cross River 6, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1,
Oyo 1.

Nichallea soyauxii (Hiern) Bridson

Ixora soyauxii Hiern

Pilz, GE 2289; 1980-5-14 [WAG.1518558]

Total: 29; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 10, Edo
1, Kogi 3, Lagos 5, Ogun 3.

Oldenlandia affinis (Roem. & Schult.) DC.

Hedyotis affinis Roem. & Schult.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 329; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1518653]

Total: 48; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 3, Borno 1,
Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kogi 2,
Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Rivers 2.

Oldenlandia affinis subsp. *fugax* (Vatke)

Verdc.

Hedyotis fugax Vatke

Literature

Total: 0.

Oldenlandia capensis L.f.

Total: 12; Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1,
Katsina 3, Niger 3, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Oldenlandia capensis var. *capensis*

Wit P. 1631; 02-05-1972 [K]

Total: 12; Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Katsina 3,
Niger 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Oldenlandia capensis var. *pleiosepala*

Bremek.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63340; 1970-4-6
[WAG.1460055]

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Taraba 3.

Oldenlandia corymbosa L.

Daramola, BO 5; 1977-8-12 [WAG.1460151]

Total: 36; Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 2, Kano 2, Kogi
2, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2,
Oyo 8.

Oldenlandia corymbosa var. *caespitosa*

(Benth.) Verdc.

Vogel 51; 00-01-1900 [K000414339]

Total: 1.

Oldenlandia corymbosa var. *corymbosa*

Hambler D.J. 329; 07-07-1957 [K]

Total: 7; Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Nasarawa 1.

Oldenlandia corymbosa var. *linearis* (DC.)

Verdc.

Pilz G.E. 2238; 26-07-1977 [K]

Total: 1.

Oldenlandia corymbosa var. *microcarpa*

Bremek.

Meikle R.D. 1001; 10-01-1950 [K]

Total: 1.

Oldenlandia echinulosa K.Schum.

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Plateau 3.

Oldenlandia echinulosa var. *pellucida*

(Hiern) Verdc.

Lely H.V. P737; 1930-9 [K]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Plateau 3.

Oldenlandia herbacea (L.) Roxb.

Hedyotis herbacea L.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 1191; 1978-10-6
[WAG.1460555]

Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Edo
1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara
1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 2.

Oldenlandia herbacea var. *herbacea*

Hedyotis herbacea L.

Magaji S.O. 716; 1975- [K]

Total: 1.

Oldenlandia lancifolia (Schumach.) DC.

Hedyotis lancifolia Schumach.

Daramola, BO FHI 86085; 1977-8-19
[WAG.1460820]
Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Oldenlandia lancifolia var. *lancifolia*
Hedyotis lancifolia Schumach.
Schlechter, FRR 12344; 1899-3-1 [L.2940344]
Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Oldenlandia lancifolia var. *scabridula*
Bremek.
Dent Young J. 112; 1922- [K]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Oldenlandia rhabdina Bremek. — Endemic
Summerhayes, G.V. 44; 1954-9-28 [K000414337]
Total: 2; Bauchi 2.

Oldenlandia wauensis Schweinf. ex Hiern
Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1302; 1972-5-6
[WAG.1375153]
Total: 3; Abia 1, Taraba 1.

Oligocodon cunliffae (Wernham) Keay
Gardenia cunliffae Wernham
Talbot; Talbot, Mr P.A. 3149; -- [K000419792]
Total: 8; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Otiophora villicaulis Mildbr.
Total: 4; Adamawa 2, Taraba 2.

Otiophora villicaulis var. *villicaulis*
Daramola, BO FHI 62723; 1969-5-17
[WAG.1461140]
Total: 4; Adamawa 2, Taraba 2.

Otomeria cameronica (Bremek.) Hepper
Tapinopentas cameronica Bremek.
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 230; 1977-10-8
[WAG.1938783]
Total: 29; Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 8, Osun 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 5, Zamfara 2.

Otomeria elatior (A.Rich.) Verdc.
Sipanea elatior A.Rich.
Gbile, ZO FHI 63255; 1970-4-3 [WAG.1227587]
Total: 18; Benue 1, Niger 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Otomeria guineensis Benth.
Ariwaodo, JO FHI 88781; 1977-8-4 [WAG.1227645]
Total: 10; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 2, Rivers 2.

Otomeria micrantha K.Schum.
Literature
Total: 0.

Otomeria volubilis (K.Schum.) Verdc.
Pentas volubilis K.Schum.
Literature
Total: 0.

Oxyanthus formosus Hook.f.
Emwiogbon, JA 312; 1973-4-3 [WAG.1227855]
Total: 13; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1.

Oxyanthus gracilis Hiern
Pilz, GE 2543; 1980-9-20 [WAG.1227900]
Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 2.

Oxyanthus laxiflorus K.Schum. ex Hutch. & Dalziel
Odewo, TK; Adedeji FHI 99955; 1983-5-13
[WAG.1227971]
Total: 26; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 15, Niger 1, Ogun 2.

Oxyanthus pallidus Hiern
s.coll. s.n.; 1883-01-01 [K000043412]
Total: 1; Niger 1.

Oxyanthus racemosus (Schumach. & Thonn.) Keay
Ucristiana racemosa Schumach. & Thonn.
Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 465; 1978-5-16
[WAG.1228080]
Total: 54; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Cross River 3, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 11, Taraba 1.

Oxyanthus setosus Keay
Brenan, J.P.M.9283; 1948-3-11 [5031] [912050508]
Total: 2; Borno 1.

Oxyanthus speciosus DC.
Barter, C 1852; 1857-1-1 [U.1567478]
Total: 39; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Delta 5, Ebonyi 3, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 5.

Oxyanthus speciosus subsp. *speciosus*
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11317; 1977-4-1 [WAG0033413]
Total: 20; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Delta 5, Ebonyi 2, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 3.

Oxyanthus subpunctatus (Hiern) Keay
Mitriostigma subpunctatum Hiern
Gbile, ZO; Wit, P 885; 1971-11-4 [WAG.1228523]

Total: 25; Anambra 2, Borno 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Oxyanthus tubiflorus (Andrews) DC. —

Introduced

Gardenia tubiflora Andrews

Bels, L 66; 1950-4-7 [U.1567489]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Oxyanthus unilocularis Hiern

Latilo, MG FHI 47668; 1963-6-4 [WAG.1228656]

Total: 44; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Cross River 8, Delta 4, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Parapentas setigera (Hiern) Verdc.

Virecta setigera Hiern

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI18612; 16-05-1946 [K]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Edo 2.

Pauridiantha afzelii (Hiern) Bremek.

Urophyllum afzelii Hiern

Daramola B.O. FHI44286; 23-02-1961 [K]

Total: 3; Edo 1, Lagos 2.

Pauridiantha canthiiflora Hook.f.

Meer, PPC van 1602; 1971-5-12 [WAG.1466713]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Pauridiantha floribunda (K.Schum. & K.Krause) Bremek.

Urophyllum floribundum K.Schum. & K.Krause

Ariwaodo, JO 733; 1977-5-26 [WAG.1466855]

Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 5, Cross River 9, Edo 1, Rivers 1.

Pauridiantha hirsuta Ntore — Introduced

Jones A.P.D. & Onochie C. FH117277; 1946-4-5 [BR000008344083]

Total: 3; Delta 1, Kogi 1.

Pauridiantha hirtella (Benth.) Bremek.

Urophyllum hirtellum Benth.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11284; 1977-3-29

[WAG.1466928]

Total: 38; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 3, Delta 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 9, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Pauridiantha paucinervis (Hiern) Bremek.

Urophyllum paucinerve Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1751; 1971-5-22 [WAG.1467154]

Total: 8; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Plateau 1.

Pauridiantha rubens (Benth.) Bremek.

Urophyllum rubens Benth.

Binuyo A. FHI41290; 1959-5-12 [BR000008340009]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Pauridiantha schumannii (Bremek.)

Smedmark & B.Bremer

Poecilocalyx schumannii Bremek.

Meer, PPC van 1411; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1402730]

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Pauridiantha talbotii (Wernham) Ntore & Dessein

Urophyllum talbotii Wernham

Percy Amaury Talbot 225; 1911-- [BM000903011]

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Pavetta bidentata Hiern

Ariwaodo, JO ARIW 451; 1977-3-26

[WAG.1252776]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Kogi 2.

Pavetta bidentata var. *bidentata*

Percy Amaury Talbot [BM000903475]

Total: 1.

Pavetta corymbosa (DC.) F.N.Williams

Baconia corymbosa DC.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 508; 1978-5-25

[WAG.1252928]

Total: 123; Abia 3, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Adamawa 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Ekiti 4, Enugu 1, Kaduna 14, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 15, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 9, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 25, Plateau 7, Taraba 8.

Pavetta corymbosa var. *corymbosa*

Baconia corymbosa DC.

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70679; 1973-3-1

[WAG.1252927]

Total: 39; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 3, Kaduna 5, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 6.

Pavetta corymbosa var. *neglecta* Bremek.

Bels L. 32; 1950-2-12 [BR0000006881764]

Total: 45; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 19.

Pavetta crassipes K.Schum.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK 66368; 1973-5-16

[WAG.1252987]

Total: 25; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 5, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1.

Pavetta gardeniifolia Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86469; 1978-3-25
[WAG.1253671]

Total: 26; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1,
Ogun 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 8, Plateau 1.

Pavetta gardeniifolia var. *gardeniifolia*

Van Meer P. ; 1968-5-18 [BR0000006880699]

Total: 4; Ondo 1, Oyo 2.

Pavetta gardeniifolia var. *subtomentosa*
K.Schum.

Onochie, C.F.A. 47731; 1963-6-4 [K000211620]

Total: 5; Bauchi 3.

Pavetta genipifolia Schumach.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI15508; 16-04-1953 [K]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 2.

Pavetta grossissima S.D.Manning

K. Schmitt; et al. Schmitt 985; 1995-12-20 [1053304]
[1258259839]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Pavetta hispida Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1369; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1253194]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Pavetta hookeriana Hiern

Baconia montana Hook.f.

Hepper F.N. 2160; 1958-2-24 [BR0000017947954]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Pavetta hookeriana var. *hookeriana*

Baconia montana Hook.f.

Sharland R.E. 456; 1979-7 [K000615934]

Total: 1.

Pavetta ixorifolia Bremek.

Meer, PPC van 1318; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1253265]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Edo 2.

Pavetta neurocarpa Benth.

Talbot s.n.; -- [K000411880]

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Niger 3.

Pavetta obanica Bremek. — Endemic

Talbot, Mr P.A. s.n.; -- [K000411883]

Total: 5; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Pavetta owariensis P.Beauv.

Farquhar, J.H. 32; 1910-3-25 [K000411885]

Total: 24; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 3, Edo 6, Niger
1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Pavetta owariensis var. *glaucescens* (Hiern)

S.D.Manning

Talbot P.A. 2042; 1912- [K]

Total: 6; Cross River 3.

Pavetta owariensis var. *owariensis*

Olorunfemi J. FHI31914; 16-12-1952 [K]

Total: 2; Edo 1.

Pavetta puberula Hiern — Introduced

; -- [P03911901]607811552

Total: 1.

Pavetta rigida Hiern

Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A. FHI18761; 20-05-1946
[K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Pavetta staudtii Hutch. & Dalziel

K. Schmitt; T.O. IbiangSchmitt 205; 1994-11-30
[976608] [1261904314]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Pavetta subcana Hiern

Dalziel J.M. 40; 17-05-1909 [K]

Total: 4; Adamawa 1.

Pavetta subcana var. *subcana*

Pavetta talbotii Wernham — Endemic

Percy Amaury Talbot 1638; 1912-- [BM000903470]

Total: 1.

Pentanisia schweinfurthii Hiern

Okafor & Daramola FHI54630; --
[BR0000019616032]

Total: 13; Bauchi 4, Kano 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 4.

Pentas arvensis Hiern

Dent Young J. 120; 1922- [Vom]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Pentas lanceolata (Forssk.) Deflers

Ophiorrhiza lanceolata Forssk.

Gladhill D. 847; 07-03-1968 [K]

Total: 3.

Pentas nervosa Hepper

Daramola, BO D 240; 1977-8-29 [WAG.1293314]

Total: 5; Adamawa 3, Plateau 2.

Pentas pubiflora S.Moore

Daramola, B.O.; FHI62395; 1968-11-30
[K004724558]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Pentas purpurea Oliv.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63297; 1970-4-5
[WAG.1293352]

Total: 9; Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Pentas purpurea subsp. *purpurea*

Hajj J.B. 1827; 05-04-1970 [K]

Total: 1.

Pentodon pentandrus (Schumach.) Vatke

Hedyotis pentandra Schumach.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000018498196]

Total: 56; Abia 1, Benue 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Niger 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 15, Plateau 5, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Pentodon pentandrus var. *pentandrus*

Hedyotis pentandra Schumach.

Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwuno, PO 68173; 1973-11-21 [WAG.1293630]

Total: 1.

Petitiodon parviflorum (Keay) Robbr.

Didymosalpinx parviflora Keay

Meer, PPC van 1347; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1925920]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Phylloentas ledermannii (K.Krause)

Kårehed & B.Bremer

Pentas ledermannii K.Krause

Savory H.V.; Keay R.W.J. FHI25231; 30-12-1948 [K000616025]

Total: 1.

Phylloentas schimperi (Hochst.) Y.D.Zhou

& Q.F.Wang

Mussaenda schimperi Hochst.

Hepper F.N. 2007; 1958-2-15 [BR0000019755755]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Taraba 4.

Pleiocoryne fernandensis (Hiern) Rauschert

Gardenia fernandensis Hiern

Pilz, GE 2558; 1980-11-12 [WAG.1402638]

Total: 19; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 6.

Polysphaeria arbuscula K.Schum.

Croat, TB 53407; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1402807]

Total: 60; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Edo 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 11, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 5, Ogun 6, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Polysphaeria macrophylla K.Schum.

1953-12-31 [2252245184]

Total: 6; Anambra 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 1, Taraba 1.

Pouchetia africana A.Rich. ex DC.

1969-4-13 [2252244615]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Pouchetia africana var. *africana*

Latilo M.G. FHI62561; 13-04-1969 [K000616025]

Total: 1.

Pouchetia baumanniana Büttner

Ariwaodo J.O. 51_30; 19-02-1998 [K]

Total: 3; Niger 1, Rivers 1.

Pouchetia parviflora Benth.

Latilo, MG FHI 47146; 1963-4-3 [WAG.1403052]

Total: 13; Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6.

Preussiodora sulphurea (K.Schum.) Keay

Randia sulphurea K.Schum.

Ariwaodo, JO 132; 1977-1-17 [WAG.1403069]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Rivers 1.

Pseudomussaenda flava Verdc. —

Introduced

O.O.Oyebanji; 2011-10-31 [4293] [3808439244]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Psychotria abouabouensis (Schnell) Verdc.

Cephaelis abouabouensis Schnell

Latilo M.G. FHI67548; 26-09-1973 [K]

Total: 2; Osun 1.

Psychotria adamawae O.Lachenaud

Daramola B.O. FHI62727; 19-05-1969 [K]

Total: 4; Adamawa 3.

Psychotria alatipes Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1597; 1971-5-12 [WAG.1403592]

Total: 6; Cross River 5.

Psychotria albicaulis Scott Elliot —

Introduced

K. Schmitt et al. 958; 1995-12-20 [1053278] [1258259818]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Psychotria altimontana O.Lachenaud

Allen, MS 1; 1972-5-7 [WAG.1403628]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Taraba 7.

Psychotria aquatica O.Lachenaud

Anderson B. 1376; 1964-4-15 [BR0000024569576]

Total: 6; Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1.

Psychotria aquatica subsp. *glabra*

O.Lachenaud

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD 140; 1972-5-4 [WAG.1372591]

Total: 5; Anambra 2, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1.

Psychotria arborea Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1193; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1579756]

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4.

Psychotria articulata (Hiern) E.M.A.Petit

Grumilea articulata Hiern

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11220; 1977-3-17

[WAG.1579229]

Total: 9; Edo 3, Lagos 4.

Psychotria bifaria Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70516; 1973-3-8

[WAG.1235132]

Total: 15; Cross River 8, Edo 5.

Psychotria bifaria var. *minimicalyx*

(K.Schum.) O.Lachenaud

Brenan J.P.M. 8759; 1948-1-10 [BR0000020238964]

Total: 9; Cross River 2, Edo 5.

Psychotria bilabiata O.Lachenaud —

Endemic

Robert Ross 224; 1935-4-15 [BM001010253]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Osun 2.

Psychotria brachyantha Hiern

8753; 24-03-1962 [K]

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Psychotria brandneriana (L.Linden) Robbr.

Ardisia brandneriana L.Linden

Literature

Total: 0.

Psychotria brandneriana subsp.

brandneriana

Ardisia brandneriana L.Linden

Talbot P.A. 2043; 00-01-1900 [BM]

Total: 1.

Psychotria brassii Hiern

Van Meer P. 841; 1968-7-17 [BR0000024569880]

Total: 3; Lagos 2, Niger 1.

Psychotria calceata E.M.A.Petit —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Psychotria calva Hiern

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 353; 1978-5-8 [WAG.1235525]

Total: 67; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 5, Delta 3, Edo 7, Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 6, Oyo 9, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Psychotria calva var. *calva*

Chapman J.D. 4665; 10-02-1977 [K]

Total: 1.

Psychotria calva var. *cicatricosa*

O.Lachenaud

Guile D.P.M. FHI62726; 1966-4 [K]

Total: 1.

Psychotria calva var. *rupestris* O.Lachenaud

Daramola B.O. FHI62726; 19-05-1969 [K]

Total: 7; Bauchi 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Psychotria calva var. *talbotii* (Wernham)

O.Lachenaud

Brenan J.P.M.; Jones E.W.; Richards P.W.; Keay R.W.J. 8641; 01-01-1948 [K000510427]

Total: 5; Niger 1, Ondo 2.

Psychotria camptopus Verdc.

Camptopus mannii Hook.f.

Hopkins, B FHI 54310; 1964-3-16 [WAG.1235586]

Total: 6; Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3.

Psychotria catetensis (Hiern) E.M.A.Petit

Grumilea catetensis Hiern

Meer, PPC van 659; 1968-3-6 [WAG.1235230]

Total: 15; Ogun 3, Osun 4, Oyo 8.

Psychotria chalconeura (K.Schum.)

E.M.A.Petit

Grumilea chalconeura K.Schum.

Total: 5; Taraba 4.

Psychotria chalconeura subsp. *moseskemei*

(Cheek) O.Lachenaud

Psychotria moseskemei Cheek

Chapman J.D. 3459; 00-01-1900 [FHO]

Total: 5; Taraba 4.

Psychotria cornuta Hiern

Brenan, Prof. J.P.M. 8518; 1947-12-16 [K000379515]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 4.

Psychotria cornuta subsp. *cornuta*

Richards P.W.3078; 1935-2-5 [BR0000021330704]

Total: 1.

Psychotria densinervia (K.Krause) Verdc.

Camptopus densinervius K.Krause

Meer, PPC van 1817; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1235833]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Psychotria dorotheae Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1452; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1236066]

Total: 14; Cross River 11.

Psychotria dorotheae subsp. *dorotheae*

Psychotria duncanthomasii O.Lachenaud

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67650; 1973-2-22 [WAG.1579425]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Psychotria ebensis K.Schum.

Daramola B.O.; Emwiogbon J.A. FHI44207; 10-03-1982 [K]

Total: 4; Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Psychotria eminiiana (Kuntze) E.M.A.Petit

Uragoga eminiiana Kuntze

Dalziel, J.M. 643; 1912-8-25 [K000379563]

Total: 8; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 1.

Psychotria eminiiana var. *eminiiana*

Uragoga eminiiana Kuntze

Dalziel, J.M. ; 1912-8-25 [P00553264]

Total: 5; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 1.

Psychotria fernandopoensis E.M.A.Petit —
Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Psychotria fimbriatifolia R.D.Good

Brenan J.P.M. 8761; 1948-1-10 [BR0000008852540]

Total: 14; Edo 10, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1.

Psychotria foliosa Hiern

van Meer 1192; 00-01-1900 [WAG]

Total: 1.

Psychotria gabonica Hiern

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11287; 1977-3-29
[WAG.1291360]

Total: 26; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Delta 4, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 2.

Psychotria geoscopa O.Lachenaud

Ujor Edwin FHI30454; 09-07-1951 [K]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Psychotria globosa Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70506; 1973-3-5
[WAG.1291410]

Total: 40; Abia 3, Cross River 9, Edo 17, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Taraba 4.

Psychotria gracilicornis O.Lachenaud

Hall J.B. ; 23-05-1976 [K]

Total: 5; Edo 3, Osun 1.

Psychotria guerzeensis (Schnell)

O.Lachenaud

Uragoga guerzeensis Schnell

Okafor, J.C. FHI36329 [K006065866]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Psychotria guineensis E.M.A.Petit

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11332; 1977-4-4 [WAG.1291504]

Total: 17; Abia 2, Cross River 2, Delta 2, Edo 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 7.

Psychotria hardyi O.Lachenaud

Latilo M.G.; Oguntayo FHI67798; 05-03-1973
[K000987456]

Total: 1.

Psychotria humilis Hiern

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 403; 1977-10-15
[WAG.1579286]

Total: 17; Cross River 3, Edo 10, Ogun 2.

Psychotria hypsophila K.Schum. &
K.Krause

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70538; 1973-3-8
[WAG.1372599]

Total: 16; Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 1.

Psychotria kitsonii Hutch. & Dalziel

Meikle 513; 00-01-1900 [K, P.]

Total: 3; Edo 1, Niger 1.

Psychotria kribiensis O.Lachenaud

Leeuwenberg 11285; 00-01-1900 [BR, WAG]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Rivers 1.

Psychotria latistipula Benth.

Okafor, JC; Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66046; 1973-2-27
[WAG.1291834]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Ebonyi 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Psychotria lehmbachii (K.Schum.)

O.Lachenaud

Grumilea lehmbachii K.Schum.

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 1432; 1911- [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Psychotria leptophylla Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70537; 1973-3-8
[WAG.1291957]

Total: 11; Abia 1, Cross River 8.

Psychotria lucens Hiern

Onochie C.F.A. FHI15513; 24-04-1953 [K]

Total: 10; Ogun 2, Ondo 3.

Psychotria lucens subsp. *lucens*

Adekunle FHI24226; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 4; Ondo 2.

Psychotria mannii Hiern — Introduced

Brenan, J.P.M.8759B; 1948-1-13 [3325] [912031861]

Total: 11; Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Plateau 2.

Psychotria nigerica Hepper

Trichostachys talbotii Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1391; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1292277]

Total: 10; Abia 2, Cross River 7, Rivers 1.

Psychotria njumei Cheek

Meer, PPC van 1449; 1971-4-24 [WAG.1292303]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Psychotria onanae O.Lachenaud

Robert Ross 205; 1935-4-11 [BM001010283]

Total: 5; Edo 1, Osun 3.

Psychotria pallidicalyx O.Lachenaud

Literature

Total: 0.

Psychotria peduncularis (Salisb.) Steyererm.

— Introduced

Cephaelis peduncularis Salisb.

B.O.Daramola; 2010-7-30 [3338] [3808440108]

Total: 54; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Cross River 15, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 2.

Psychotria peduncularis var. *suaveolens*

(Schweinf. ex Hiern) Verdc.

Cephaelis suaveolens Schweinf. ex Hiern

Specimen seen at K

Total: 1.

Psychotria piolampra K.Schum.

Binuyo, A FHI 41269; 1959-4-24 [WAG.1579803]

Total: 3; Cross River 2, Ogun 1.

Psychotria podocarpa E.M.A.Petit

Talbot, Mr P.A. 234; -- [K000379535]

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Psychotria potanthera Wernham

Percy Amaury Talbot 240; 1911-- [BM000903601]

Total: 16; Cross River 7, Edo 5, Niger 1.

Psychotria potanthera subsp. *potanthera* —

Endemic

Percy Amaury Talbot; 1912-01-01 [BM000903543]

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Psychotria potanthera subsp. *sapobana*

O.Lachenaud

Kennedy J.D. 2714; 1935- [K]

Total: 6; Edo 5.

Psychotria psychotrioides (DC.) Roberty

Grumilea psychotrioides DC.

Meer, PPC van 1756; 1971-5-23 [WAG.1372743]

Total: 64; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 6, Cross River 15, Edo 3, Kaduna 9, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Psychotria punctata var. *punctata* —

Introduced

Psychotria recurva Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1694; 1971-5-19 [WAG.1432828]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Psychotria rhizomatosa De Wild.

Meer, PPC van 1179; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1890796]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Psychotria schliebenii E.M.A.Petit

Croat 53487; 1981-11-18 [1438252] [1258665647]

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Psychotria schweinfurthii Hiern

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 29; 1979-5-20

[WAG.1373025]

Total: 57; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 8, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3, Niger 2, Ogun 12, Ondo 6, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Psychotria spathulifolia O.Lachenaud

Olorunfemi, J. FHI30679 [K005049083]

Total: 1.

Psychotria subobliqua Hiern

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO 971; 1971-11-18 [WAG.1373177]

Total: 21; Abia 1, Cross River 5, Edo 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Oyo 3, Taraba 1.

Psychotria succulenta (Hiern) E.M.A.Petit

Grumilea succulenta Hiern

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO s.n.; 1972-5-10

[WAG.1373251]

Total: 19; Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 11.

Psychotria vaginalis G.Don

Specimen seen at K

Total: 1.

Psychotria venosa (Hiern) E.M.A.Petit

Grumilea venosa Hiern

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70521; 1973-3-8

[WAG.1373382]

Total: 20; Abia 3, Cross River 15, Oyo 1.

Psychotria vogeliana Benth.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 40216; 1979-4-27

[WAG.1373541]

Total: 110; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 7, Bauchi 9, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 2, Enugu 6, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 14, Ogun 7, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Psydrax acutiflora (Hiern) Bridson

Canthium kraussiioides Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1383; 1971-4-20 [WAG.1433074]
Total: 1.

Psydrax arnoldianus (De Wild. & T.Durand) Bridson

Plectronia arnoldiana De Wild. & T.Durand
Wardrop, T.N. FHI293; -- [K000043453]
Total: 3; Edo 1, Kaduna 2.

Psydrax dunlapii (Hutch. & Dalziel) Bridson

Canthium dunlapii Hutch. & Dalziel
Literature
Total: 0.

Psydrax horizontalis (Schumach. & Thonn.) Bridson

Phallaria horizontalis Schumach. & Thonn.
Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwuno, PO FHI 68088; 1973-11-16
[WAG.1433031]
Total: 25; Abia 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 8, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Psydrax latifolius (F.Muell. ex Benth.) S.T.Reynolds & R.J.F.Hend. — Introduced
Canthium latifolium F.Muell. ex Benth.

Nodza G.:Eze T.E; 2020-10-28 [8836]3808442190
Total: 1; Edo 1.

Psydrax manensis (Aubrév. & Pellegr.) Bridson

Canthium manense Aubrév. & Pellegr.
T.K.Odewo; 2008-10-18 [2397] [3808439221]
Total: 1; Osun 1.

Psydrax palma (K.Schum.) Bridson

Plectronia palma K.Schum.
J. D. Kennedy 2394; -- [US 1666539]
Total: 5; Edo 2.

Psydrax parviflora (Afzel.) Bridson

Pavetta parviflora Afzel.
Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 439; 1978-5-16
[WAG.1912674]
Total: 1.

Psydrax parviflora subsp. *parviflora*

Pavetta parviflora Afzel.
Meer, PPC van 856; 1968-7-30 [WAG.1433288]
Total: 3; Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Psydrax schimperianus (A.Rich.) Bridson

Canthium schimperianum A.Rich.
Van Blom - van Teyn 121; 1971-7-3
[BR0000021803369]
Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Plateau 2.

Psydrax schimperianus subsp. *occidentalis* Bridson

Olorunfemi, J. FHI.55723; 1965-3-10 [K000422527]
Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Psydrax splendens (K.Schum.) Bridson

Plectronia splendens K.Schum.
Onochie CFA Onochie, CFA FHI 33174; 1953-5-15
[WAG.1433392]
Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 3, Rivers 1.

Psydrax subcordata (DC.) Bridson

Canthium subcordatum DC.
Meer PPC van Meer, PPC van 969; 1968-11-14
[WAG.1433494]
Total: 1.

Richardia brasiliensis Gomes — Introduced
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66007; 1973-2-15
[WAG.1401357]

Total: 17; Anambra 2, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3.

Richardia scabra L. — Introduced
Literature

Total: 0.

Robynsia glabrata Hutch.

Kennedy J.D. 2552; 1989-8-23 [K000043460]
Total: 5; Edo 5.

Rondeletia odorata Jacq. — Introduced
Ugwuozor P.O.; 2013-4-26 [131A]1990271731
Total: 3; Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Rothmannia hispida (K.Schum.) Fagerl.

Randia hispida K.Schum.
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 417; 1977-10-18
[WAG.1401620]
Total: 43; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 1, Borno 6, Cross River 8, Edo 9, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1.

Rothmannia longiflora Salisb.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji FHI 99925; 1983-3-16
[WAG.1401838]
Total: 47; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 4, Bauchi 1, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 7, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Rothmannia lujae (De Wild.) Keay

Randia lujae De Wild.
Talbot, Mr P.A. 1267; -- [K000414798]
Total: 18; Borno 2, Cross River 3, Edo 7, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2.

Rothmannia munsae (Schweinf. ex Hiern)
E.M.A.Petit

Randia munsae Schweinf. ex Hiern

Literature

Total: 0.

Rothmannia munsae subsp. *megalostigma*
(Wernham) Somers

Randia megalostigma Wernham

Latilo M.G. FHI 58966; 13-02-1964 [K]

Total: 1.

Rothmannia octomera (Hook.) Fagerl.

Gardenia octomera Hook.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32764; 1981-6-17

[WAG.1402019]

Total: 16; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 4, Ogun 2.

Rothmannia talbotii (Wernham) Keay

Randia talbotii Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1636; 1971-5-15 [WAG.1402074]

Total: 8; Cross River 7.

Rothmannia urcelliformis (Hiern) Bullock
ex Robyns

Gardenia urcelliformis Hiern

Latilo, MG FHI 64612; 1971-11-12 [WAG.1402142]

Total: 34; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2,
Nasarawa 2, Ogun 6, Oyo 12, Taraba 6.

Rothmannia whitfieldii (Lindl.) Dandy

Gardenia whitfieldii Lindl.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji FHI 10092; 1983-5-14

[WAG.1402338]

Total: 24; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 4,
Kaduna 3, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2,
Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 2.

Rutidea decorticata Hiern

Daramola B.O. FHI56376; 1965-9-5

[BR0000019872445]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Rivers 1.

Rutidea dupuisii De Wild.

Total: 2; Osun 2.

Rutidea dupuisii subsp. *occidentalis* Bridson

Richards P.W. 3436; 1935-3-9 [BR0000019874500]

Total: 2; Osun 2.

Rutidea glabra Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1235; 1971-4-8 [WAG.1457856]

Total: 9; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 5.

Rutidea hispida Hiern

Daramola, BO FHI 43548; 1961-12-5

[WAG.1457888]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1.

Rutidea membranacea Hiern

Eimunjeze, VE; Ekwuno, PO FHI 68067; 1973-11-16
[WAG.1457954]

Total: 10; Borno 1, Cross River 6, Edo 1, Oyo 1,
Taraba 1.

Rutidea nigerica Bridson

Tamajong, S. FHI20278; 1946-12-7 [K000412167]

Total: 3; Ogun 2.

Rutidea olenotricha Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1079; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1458043]

Total: 11; Edo 2, Enugu 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 2.

Rutidea parviflora DC.

Latilo M.G. 47433; 1963-4-13 [BR0000019883755]

Total: 11; Kaduna 2, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger
1.

Rutidea rufipilis Hiern

Meer, PPC van 1802; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1458172]

Total: 17; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Delta
1, Edo 2, Lagos 1.

Rutidea smithii Hiern

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 388; 1978-5-9
[WAG.1458216]

Total: 55; Abia 2, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 10,
Gombe 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 6, Ondo 4, Osun 3,
Oyo 6, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1.

Rutidea smithii subsp. *smithii*

Rudolf Schlechter; 1899-03-01 [Z+ZT.Z-000023128]

Total: 1.

Rytigynia argentea (Wernham) Robyns —
Endemic

Vangueria argentea Wernham

Talbot, Mr P.A. 215; -- [K000412439]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Rytigynia canthioides (Benth.) Robyns

Vangueria canthioides Benth.

Meer, PPC van 867; 1968-8-16 [WAG.1458407]

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 3.

Rytigynia membranacea (Hiern) Robyns

Vangueria membranacea Hiern

Thomson., W.C. 114; 1863-4-4 [K000412435]

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 5.

Rytigynia nigerica (S.Moore) Robyns

Vangueria nigerica S.Moore

Meer, PPC van 1097; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1458603]

Total: 20; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1,
Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 7.

Rytigynia rubra Robyns

Emwiogbon, JA; Anyadieguw, JC 643; 1974-3-28 [WAG.1458646]

Total: 7; Enugu 1, Lagos 6.

Rytigynia senegalensis Blume

1974-3-28 [2252245508]

Total: 5; Benue 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1.

Rytigynia umbellulata (Hiern) Robyns

Vangueria umbellulata Hiern

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 377; 1978-5-9 [WAG.1458725]

Total: 46; Anambra 4, Delta 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 3, Oyo 11, Taraba 4.

Sabicea africana (P. Beauv.) Hepper

Stipularia africana P.Beauv.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11223; 1977-3-17

[WAG.1172663]

Total: 1.

Sabicea brevipes Wernham

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 323; 1978-5-5 [WAG0034363]

Total: 40; Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ebonyi 2, Enugu 8, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Osun 1, Plateau 6.

Sabicea calycina Benth.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 109; 1979-4-27

[WAG0043098]

Total: 97; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 17, Ekiti 3, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 15, Niger 1, Ogun 13, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 11, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Sabicea capitellata Benth.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67667; 1973-2-22

[WAG0110971]

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Sabicea duparquetiana Baill. ex Wernham

— Introduced

Robb s.n.; -- [BM000820042]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Sabicea elliptica (Schweinf. ex Hiern)

Hepper

Stipularia elliptica Schweinf. ex Hiern

Emwiogbon, JA 190; 1972-5-6 [WAG.1172670]

Total: 1.

Sabicea floribunda K.Schum.

Ejiofor M.C. FHI21883; 30-04-1952 [K]

Total: 5; Cross River 2.

Sabicea floribunda var. *floribunda*

Sabicea gabonica (Hiern) Hepper

Stipularia gabonica Hiern

Daramola, BO; Bola; Mobolaji; Fagbemi, A FHI 71112; 1974-8-4 [WAG0034276]

Total: 4; Edo 3, Ondo 1.

Sabicea geophiloides Wernham

Eijnatten, CLM van 1485; 1966-5-10 [WAG0082755]

Total: 14; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Edo 4, Kwara 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 3.

Sabicea gigantostipula K.Schum.

Percy Amaury Talbot 259; 1911-- [BM011025797]

Total: 3; Anambra 1, Cross River 2.

Sabicea johnstonii K.Schum. ex Wernham

Ariwaodo J.O. 1136; 1966-2-28 [BR0000013569303]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Imo 1, Osun 1.

Sabicea lanuginosa Wernham — Endemic

Millen, H. 69; -- [K000414565]

Total: 10; Lagos 8, Oyo 1.

Sabicea medusula K.Schum. ex Wernham

Literature

Total: 0.

Sabicea pedicellata Wernham

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70542; 1973-3-8

[WAG0110928]

Total: 7; Cross River 5.

Sabicea rosea Hoyle

Batten-Poole, W.H. 1; -- [K000043332]

Total: 2; Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Sabicea schumanniana Büttner

Latilo M.G. 47693; 1963-6-11 [BR0000013941956]

Total: 2; Abia 1, Rivers 1.

Sabicea speciosa K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1623; 1971-5-14 [WAG0110871]

Total: 9; Abia 2, Cross River 4.

Sabicea talbotii Wernham — Endemic

Percy Amaury Talbot 2032; 1912-- [BM000820036]

Total: 1.

Sabicea tchapensis K.Krause

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 63173; 1972-6-29

[WAG0034271]

Total: 10; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Taraba 2.

Sabicea urceolata Hepper

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 36325; 1957-2-7 [K000414560]

Total: 5; Abia 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1.

Sabicea xanthotricha Wernham

Percy Amaury Talbot 249; 1911-- [BM000820038]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Sacosperma paniculatum (Benth.) G.Taylor

Peltospermum paniculatum Benth.

Daramola, BO D 35; 1977-8-1 [WAG.1400324]

Total: 21; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 1, Oyo 6, Rivers 1.

Sacosperma parviflorum (Benth.) G.Taylor

Pentas parviflora Benth.

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD 144; 1972-5-4 [WAG.1400378]

Total: 7; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 2, Kaduna 2.

Schumanniphyton magnificum (K.Schum.)

Harms

Tetrastigma magnificum K.Schum.

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [281A] [1990271843]

Total: 21; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Schumanniphyton magnificum var. *magnificum*

Tetrastigma magnificum K.Schum.

Daramola B.O. FHI72341; 05-10-1973 [K]

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Scleromitron diffusum (Willd.) R.J.Wang

— Introduced

Hedyotis diffusa Willd.

Vogel, JRT; Niger Expedition s.n.; 1841-8-1 [L.2941631]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Sericanthe auriculata (Keay) Robbr.

Tricalysia auriculata Keay

Rosevear, D.R. C.34; -- [K000346957]

Total: 3; Abia 2.

Sericanthe chevalieri (K.Krause) Robbr.

Tricalysia chevalieri K.Krause

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65950; 1972-12-9 [WAG.1400914]

Total: 25; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Sericanthe chevalieri var. *coffeoides*

(A.Chev.) Robbr.

Feretia coffeoides A.Chev.

Olorunfemi, J FHI 54972; 1964-8-10 [WAG.1400924]

Total: 23; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Sherbournia amaraliocarpa (Wernham)

Hepper

Randia amaraliocarpa Wernham

Percy Amaury Talbot 3021; -- [BM000903066]

Total: 3.

Sherbournia bignoniiflora (Welw.) Hua

Gardenia bignoniiflora Welw.

Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1083; 1971-12-28

[WAG.1401245]

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Ogun 5, Osun 2.

Sherbournia calycina (G.Don) Hua

Gardenia calycina G.Don

Bels, L 96; 1950-4-26 [U.1581567]

Total: 2; Lagos 1.

Sherbournia hapalophylla (Wernham)

Hepper

Randia hapalophylla Wernham

Meer, PPC van 1507; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1819827]

Total: 5; Cross River 3.

Sherbournia hapalophylla subsp.

hapalophylla

Randia hapalophylla Wernham

John D. 744; 10-06-1982 [K]

Total: 1.

Sherbournia millenii (Wernham) Hepper

Amaralia millenii Wernham

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32813; 1981-6-18

[WAG.1819836]

Total: 37; Borno 6, Edo 4, Lagos 7, Ogun 6, Ondo 4, Osun 3, Oyo 5.

Sherbournia zenkeri Hua

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 385; 1977-10-15

[WAG.1819772]

Total: 32; Abia 1, Cross River 11, Edo 7, Kogi 2, Osun 2, Oyo 1.

Spermacoce articularis L.f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Spermacoce chaetocephala DC.

; 1994-10-22 [FR-0016226] [3046045002]

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Borno 4, Kogi 1.

Spermacoce exilis (L.O.Williams)

C.D.Adams ex W.C.Burger & C.M.Taylor

Borreria exilis L.O.Williams

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 742; 1971-9-19

[WAG.1818824]

Total: 12; Benue 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Spermacoce filifolia (Schumach. & Thonn.)
J.-P. Lebrun & Stork

Octodon filifolium Schumach. & Thonn.
Denys, E 827; 1982-8-5 [WAG.1818747]
Total: 7; Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Taraba 1.

Spermacoce filiformis Hiern

Barter 1720; -- [K000422899]
Total: 24; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 4.

Spermacoce hepperiana Verdc.

Spermacoce compressa Afzel. ex Hiern
C. Barter 1231; 1857-- [barcode-01154855]
Total: 2; Gombe 1, Niger 1.

Spermacoce hillii (Chippend.) Govaerts —
Introduced

Borreria hillii Chippend.
R.F. Butler-Cole 6; -- [BR0000008204820]
Total: 2; Kogi 1, Ogun 1.

Spermacoce intricans (Hepper) H.M. Burkill

Borreria intricans Hepper
Pilz G.E. 2160; 09-10-1977 [K]
Total: 1.

Spermacoce kirkii (Hiern) Verdc. —
Introduced

Diodia kirkii Hiern
Bels L. 7; 1951-7-6 [BR0000008211903]
Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Spermacoce lasiocarpa R.Br.

Literature
Total: 0.

Spermacoce latifolia Aubl. — Introduced

Literature
Total: 0.

Spermacoce natalensis Hochst.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1319; 1972-5-10
[WAG.1818666]
Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 5.

Spermacoce octodon (Hepper) Hakki

Borreria octodon Hepper
Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 86; 1977-10-5
[WAG.1553198]
Total: 62; Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 4, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Kogi 1, Kwara 7, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 2, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 2.

Spermacoce ocymoides Burm.f. —
Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 288; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1553217]
Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Spermacoce princeae (K.Schum.) Verdc.

Borreria princeae K.Schum.
Daramola, BO FHI 86161; 1977-8-25
[WAG.1818585]
Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Spermacoce pusilla Wall.

Daramola, BO FHI 86154; 1977-8-25
[WAG.1819183]
Total: 16; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Spermacoce quadrisulcata (Bremek.) Verdc.

Borreria quadrisulcata Bremek.
1994-10-8 [FR-0016246] [3046047999]
Total: 2; Borno 2.

Spermacoce radiata (DC.) Sieber ex Hiern

Borreria radiata DC.
Pilz, GE 1851; 1976-11-14 [WAG.1553245]
Total: 37; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 1, Edo 2, Jigawa 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 5, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 3.

Spermacoce ruelliae DC.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi DO 167; 1979-5-4
[WAG.1819054]
Total: 30; Borno 3, Cross River 2, Ekiti 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 6, Oyo 3, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Spermacoce spermacocina (K.Schum.)

Bridson & Puff
Paragophyton spermacocinum K.Schum.
Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86188; 1978-5-2
[WAG.1818936]
Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Spermacoce sphaerostigma (A.Rich.) Oliv.

Hypodematum sphaerostigma A.Rich.
Literature
Total: 0.

Spermacoce stachydea DC.

Pilz, GE 2257; 1977-12-29 [WAG.1553275]

Total: 18; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Plateau 1, Yobe 2.

Spermacoce verticillata L. — Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65756; 1972-8-17

[WAG.1830529]

Total: 36; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 6, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Tarenna baconoides Wernham

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1595; -- [K000411776]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Tarenna bipindensis (K.Schum.) Bremek.

Chomelia bipindensis K.Schum.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji ODA 246; 1983-5-13

[WAG.1172805]

Total: 27; Benue 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 10, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Tarenna conferta (Benth.) Hiern

Stylocoryna conferta Benth.

Meer, PPC van 963; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1172856]

Total: 27; Bayelsa 3, Edo 2, Lagos 9, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Tarenna eketensis Wernham

Talbot, Mr P.A. 3827; -- [K000411778]

Total: 26; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Osun 1, Rivers 6.

Tarenna eketensis var. *eketensis*

Meer, PPC van 1801; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1172982]

Total: 13; Cross River 3, Edo 1, Osun 1, Rivers 4.

Tarenna eketensis var. *situtela* N.Hallé

Van Meer P. 1801; 1971-5-25 [BR0000090003196]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Tarenna fuscoflava (K.Schum.) S.Moore

Chomelia fuscoflava K.Schum.

Talbot P.A. 232; 1911-- [BR0000090004261]

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Tarenna grandiflora (Benth.) Hiern

Stylocoryna grandiflora Benth.

Gentry A.H. 32943; 1981-6-21 [BR0000090006715]

Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 7.

Tarenna lasiorhachis (K.Schum. & K.Krause) Bremek.

Pavetta lasiorhachis K.Schum. & K.Krause

Binuyo A. FHI41402; 1959-7-23 [BR000008014108]

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Tarenna nitidula (Benth.) Hiern —

Introduced

Stylocoryna nitidula Benth.

; -- [53231] [2428998011]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Lagos 2.

Tarenna pallidula Hiern

Talbot, D.A.; Talbot, Mr P.A. 3257; -- [K000642874]

Total: 13; Akwa Ibom 11, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Tarenna pavettoides (Harv.) Sim

Kraussia pavettoides Harv.

Total: 6; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Tarenna pavettoides subsp. *guineensis*

Degreef

Chapman J.W.F. 3149; 1973-5-24

[BR0000090006562]

Total: 6; Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Tarenna thomasii Hutch. & Dalziel

Onochie, C.F.A. ; 1958-3-30 [P00101034]

Total: 17; Benue 2, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Lagos 1, Niger 1.

Tricalysia acocantheroides K.Schum. —

Introduced

Chapman J.W.F. 499; 1957-12-10

[BR000006719302]

Total: 2.

Tricalysia biafrana Hiern

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70700; 1973-3-3

[WAG.1375277]

Total: 36; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 15.

Tricalysia bifida De Wild.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST 70543; 1973-3-6

[WAG.1375299]

Total: 6; Abia 2, Cross River 2.

Tricalysia coriacea (Benth.) Hiern

Randia coriacea Benth.

Daramola, BO; Emwiogbon, JA FHI 44282; 1961-2-

12 [WAG.1375464]

Total: 7; Edo 5, Plateau 1.

Tricalysia coriacea subsp. *coriacea*

Randia coriacea Benth.

Kennedy J.D. 2800; -- [BR0000019623306]

Total: 2; Edo 2.

Tricalysia elliottii (K.Schum.) Hutch. &

Dalziel

Probletostemon elliottii K.Schum.

Latilo; Olorunfemi; FHI33692; 1954-01-28
[K004931116]

Total: 4; Edo 1.

Tricalysia elliotii var. *elliotii*

Proletostemon elliotii K.Schum.

Tricalysia obanensis Keay

Talbot; Talbot, Mr P.A. 1324; -- [K000419991]

Total: 6; Cross River 3, Kwara 1.

Tricalysia obanensis subsp. *obanensis*

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. 1324; 09-02-1912 [K]

Total: 1.

Tricalysia okelensis Hiern

F. N. Hepper 1464; 1957-11-26 [S17-32716]

Total: 37; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Niger 1, Oyo 4,
Plateau 9, Taraba 4.

Tricalysia okelensis var. *okelensis*

Gbile, ZO 1076; 1972-4-20 [WAG.1376001]

Total: 32; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Niger 1, Oyo 4,
Plateau 7, Taraba 4.

Tricalysia oligoneura K.Schum.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 21; 1979-4-11

[WAG.1376034]

Total: 29; Cross River 1, Edo 6, Ogun 3, Ondo 5, Oyo 8.

Tricalysia pallens Hiern

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000019779478]

Total: 34; Abia 2, Borno 2, Cross River 7, Edo 13,
Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1.

Tricalysia pallens var. *pallens*

Meer, PPC van 1267; 1971-4-14 [WAG.1376170]

Total: 1.

Tricalysia wernhamiana (Hutch. & Dalziel)

Keay — Endemic

CreMASpora wernhamiana Hutch. & Dalziel

Meer, PPC van 1322; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1925935]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 4.

Trichostachys aurea Hiern

Onochie, C.33411; 1953-7-29 [947] [912078138]

Total: 9; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 4, Ondo 3.

Trichostachys interrupta K.Schum.

Percy Amaury Talbot 1045; 1911-- [BM000021492]

Total: 1.

Uncaria africana G.Don

Onochie, C.F.34065; 1953-9-19 [5044] [912050612]

Total: 5; Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Uncaria africana var. *africana*

Latilo M.G. FHI73553; 15-01-1976 [K]

Total: 2; Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Uncaria angolensis (Havil.) Hutch. & Dalziel

Uncaria africana var. *angolensis* Havil.

Onochie C.F.A. FHI34065; 19-09-1953 [K]

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Uncaria domatiifera subsp. *xerophila*

(E.M.A.Petit) O.Lachenaud & Ntore

Uncaria africana var. *domatiifera* E.M.A.Petit

Mr and Mrs Talbot P.A. ; 1911- [K]

Total: 1.

Uncaria talbotii Wernham

Talbot, Mr P.A. 168; -- [K000394918]

Total: 8; Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Osun 1.

Vangueria agrestis (Schweinf. ex Hiern)

Lantz

Fadogia agrestis Schweinf. ex Hiern

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 66369; 1973-5-16
[WAG.1500748]

Total: 28; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 12,
Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Oyo 2,
Plateau 1.

Vangueria madagascariensis J.F.Gmel.

Jones E.W. 50; 02-05-1958 [K]

Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Kogi 1.

Vangueria madagascariensis var.

madagascariensis

Barter, C 1250; 1857-1-1 [U.1585942]

Total: 1.

Vangueriella campylacantha (Mildbr.)

Verdc.

Plectronia campylacantha Mildbr.

Binuyo, A FHI 41232; 1959-4-14 [WAG.1297474]

Total: 7; Cross River 3, Niger 1, Oyo 2.

Vangueriella chlorantha (K.Schum.) Verdc.

Plectronia chlorantha K.Schum.

Meer, PPC van 1364; 1971-4-19 [WAG0114940]

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Vangueriella laxiflora (K.Schum.) Verdc.

Plectronia laxiflora K.Schum.

Literature

Total: 0.

Vangueriella nigerica (Robyns) Verdc.

Vangueriopsis nigerica Robyns

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 417; 1978-5-11
[WAG.1325155]
Total: 17; Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 12.

Vangueriella spinosa (Schumach. & Thonn.)
Verdc.

Phallaria spinosa Schumach. & Thonn.
Meer, PPC van 1084; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1325259]
Total: 10; Cross River 1, Ogun 5, Oyo 3.

Virectaria angustifolia (Hiern) Bremek.
Virecta angustifolia Hiern

Literature
Total: 0.

Virectaria angustifolia var. *angustifolia*
Virecta angustifolia Hiern

Literature
Total: 0.

Virectaria major (K.Schum.) Verdc.
Virecta major K.Schum.

Daramola, BO 124; 1977-8-18 [WAG.1325387]
Total: 21; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross
River 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 4.

Virectaria major subsp. *major*
Virecta major K.Schum.

Sharland R.E. 2037; 20-07-1981 [K]
Total: 1.

Virectaria major subsp. *spathulata* (Verdc.)
Dessein & Robbr.

Virectaria major var. *spathulata* Verdc.
Thomas B. Croat 53456; 1981-11-18 [2377985]
[1259685644]
Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Virectaria multiflora (Sm.) Bremek.
Virecta multiflora Sm.

Okeke, RE; Ekwuno, PO; Macauley, S FHI 72629;
1974-8-8 [WAG.1325498]
Total: 43; Abia 6, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 9, Cross
River 1, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Imo 3, Kogi 1,
Niger 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Rivers 2, Sokoto 1,
Taraba 1.

Virectaria procumbens (Sm.) Bremek.
Virecta procumbens Sm.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65654; 1972-5-30
[WAG.1325603]
Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Edo 2, Ogun
1, Osun 3, Rivers 1.

Xanthophytum papuanum Wernham —
Introduced
Forbes, H.O.; 1885-1-1 [P04815034]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

GENTIANACEAE

Anthocleista djalonensis A.Chev.

Chaloner, WG s.n.; 1966-4-26 [WAG.1815109]
Total: 94; Abia 2, Anambra 4, Benue 3, Cross River 3,
Edo 3, Enugu 2, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Lagos 8, Niger
2, Ogun 11, Ondo 4, Osun 4, Oyo 29, Plateau 2,
Taraba 4.

Anthocleista grandiflora Gilg — Introduced
<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3879588547>
Total: 1.

Anthocleista liebrechtsiana De Wild. &
T.Durand

Onochie, CFA FHI 40423; 1958-11-13
[WAG.1809991]
Total: 6; Edo 4, Ogun 1, Plateau 1.

Anthocleista microphylla Wernham
Talbot P.A. 304; 1911-- [BM000930191]
Total: 1.

Anthocleista nobilis G.Don

A.P.D. Jones & C.F.A Onochie FHI17264; 1946-4-3
[MA-01-00259483]
Total: 8; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 2, Osun 2, Oyo
1.

Anthocleista obanensis Wernham

Talbot, PA 305; 1912-1-1 [WAG.1809789]
Total: 18; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Delta
1, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Niger 1.

Anthocleista procera Lepr. ex Bureau
<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3866519532>
Total: 4.

Anthocleista schweinfurthii Gilg

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11349; 1977-3-28
[WAG.1809608]
Total: 3; Edo 2.

Anthocleista vogelii Planch.

Lowe, J 1733; 1969-4-29 [WAG.1809662]
Total: 74; Abia 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 9, Delta 2,
Edo 1, Enugu 2, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 10,
Niger 5, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 12, Plateau 3,
Taraba 4.

Canscora alata (Roth) Wall.

Exacum alatum Roth
Geerling, C 4340; 1971-10-7 [WAG.1808915]

Total: 36; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 2, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Canscora diffusa (Vahl) R.Br. ex Roem. & Schult.

Gentiana diffusa Vahl

Latilo, MG FHI 64637; 1971-11-22 [WAG.1808877]

Total: 37; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Congolanthus longidens (N.E.Br.) A.Raynal

Neurotheca longidens N.E.Br.

Daramola, BO FHI 46923; 1962-12-25 [WAG.1809123]

Total: 10; Gombe 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 3.

Cyrtophyllum fragrans (Roxb.) DC. —

Introduced

Fagraea fragrans Roxb.

J.A. Emwiogbon; 1965-12-28 [57731]1990430871

Total: 5; Oyo 4.

Exacum oldenlandioides (S.Moore) Klack.

Sebaea oldenlandioides S.Moore

Ariwaodo, JO 154; 1977-1-17 [WAG.1807315]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Exacum quinquenervium Griseb. —

Introduced

Ekwuno P.O.; Others 560; 1981-9-10 [95764] 1990433186

Total: 28; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 2, Cross River 6, Edo 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 2.

Exochaenium gracile (Welw.) Schinz —

Introduced

Belmontia gracilis Welw.

Stanfield D.P.; 1957-10-10 [40017] [1990429405]

Total: 1.

Exochaenium grande (E.Mey.) Griseb.

Belmontia grandis E.Mey.

Leeuw, PN de 1940; 1967-8-3 [WAG0132906]

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Plateau 4.

Exochaenium oliganthum (Gilg) Kissling

Belmontia oligantha Gilg

Hall, J.B.; 854; 1968-11-03 [K001871600]

Total: 2; Ekiti 1.

Exochaenium pumilum (Baker) A.W.Hill

Belmontia pumila Baker

Barter C. 1680; -- [K000096661]

Total: 5; Benue 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Faroa pusilla Baker

Barter C. 1008; -- [K000096859]

Total: 14; Gombe 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Neurotheca loeselioides (Spruce ex Progel) Baill.

Octopleura loeselioides Spruce ex Progel

Geerling C. [BR0000017530736]

Total: 73; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 10, Bauchi 3, Cross River 6, Delta 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Enugu 6, Kaduna 4, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Neurotheca loeselioides subsp. *loeselioides*

Octopleura loeselioides Spruce ex Progel

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO 961; 1971-11-18 [WAG.1289032]

Total: 1.

Sebaea brachyphylla Griseb.

Daramola, BO 151; 1977-8-19 [WAG0132863]

Total: 14; Sokoto 1, Taraba 12.

Swertia abyssinica Hochst.

Literature

Total: 0.

Swertia eminii Engl.

B.O. Daramola FHI 62361; 1968-11-29 [S-PL-9211]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Swertia mannii Hook.f.

Lawlor & Hall 349; 1962-8-25 [S-PL-9184]

Total: 21; Bauchi 3, Kaduna 2, Plateau 11, Sokoto 2.

Swertia quartiniana A.Rich.

Chapman, JD 2908; 1972-6-21 [WAG.1289376]

Total: 5; Taraba 5.

Swertia welwitschii Engl. — Introduced

P.N. de Leeuw 1807; 1966-8-18 [S-PL-9054]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Voyria primuloides Baker

Mann 514; -- [K000096903]

Total: 2.

LOGANIACEAE

Spigelia anthelmia L. — Introduced

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 411; 1971-9-19 [WAG.1061377]

Total: 76; Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 10, Niger 2, Ogun 12, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Strychnos aculeata Soler.

Meer, PPC van 718; 1968-4-25 [WAG.1061787]

Total: 10; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 5.

Strychnos afzelii Gilg

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI32235 [K005427185]

Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1.

Strychnos angolensis Gilg

Talbot s.n.; 1915-- [CM269385]

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Strychnos asterantha Leeuwenb.

Onochie, CFA FHI 31247; 1957-6-27

[WAG.1062326]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ogun 1.

Strychnos barteri Soler.

Meer, PPC van 1599; 1971-5-12 [WAG.1062301]

Total: 15; Anambra 4, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2.

Strychnos boonei De Wild.

Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 72746; 1974-6-1

[WAG.1062487]

Total: 11; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Kogi 2, Oyo 2.

Strychnos camptoneura Gilg & Busse

Pilz, GE 2022; 1977-4-26 [WAG.1062740]

Total: 23; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Edo 6, Gombe 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5.

Strychnos canthioides Leeuwenb.

Meer, PPC van 1805; -- [WAG.1062791]

Total: 1.

Strychnos chrysophylla Gilg

Meer, PPC van 1186; 1971-4-6 [WAG.1062872]

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 5, Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Strychnos congolana Gilg

Sola;Daramola; 2011-1-1 [3928] [3808439157]

Total: 3; Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Strychnos cuniculina Leeuwenb.

Daramola, BO 94/ 372; 1994-2-5 [L.3891312]

Total: 1.

Strychnos densiflora Baill.

Pilz, GE 1985; 1977-4-25 [WAG.1063418]

Total: 5; Cross River 2, Rivers 1.

Strychnos dolichothyrsa Gilg ex Onochie & Hepper

Literature

Total: 0.

Strychnos fallax Leeuwenb. — Introduced

Gentry 32903; 1981-6-21 [413810] [1261114612]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Strychnos floribunda Gilg

Meer, PPC van 1059; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1063872]

Total: 14; Kaduna 2, Lagos 2, Ondo 5, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Strychnos gnetifolia Gilg ex Onochie & Hepper

Percy Amaury Talbot 574; 1911-- [BM000930154]

Total: 1.

Strychnos icaja Baill.

Talbot, PA 1256; 1912-1-1 [WAG0002204]

Total: 13; Cross River 7, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 2.

Strychnos innocua Delile

Latilo, MG FHI 47773; 1963-4-18 [WAG.1064370]

Total: 32; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 5, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Strychnos innocua var. *innocua*

Daramola, BO FHI 62668; 1969-6-4 [WAG.1064393]

Total: 1.

Strychnos innocua var. *pubescens* Soler.

C. Barter1160; 1857-- [barcode-00076814]

[1999239741]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Strychnos johnsonii Hutch. & M.B.Moss

Tamajong, S. 20739 [K005427416]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Strychnos longicaudata Gilg

Sola;Daramola; 2011-1-1 [3921] [3808439179]

Total: 1.

Strychnos malacoclados C.H.Wright

Talbot, Mr P.A. 1661; -- [K000426580]

Total: 4; Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Strychnos memecyloides S.Moore

Meer, PPC van 1330; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1065230]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 13, Niger 2.

Strychnos ndengensis Pellegr.

Literature

Total: 0.

Strychnos ngouniensis Pellegr.

Meer, PPC van 905; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1065452]

Total: 4; Oyo 4.

Strychnos nigritana Baker

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK; Macauley, S FHI 66486; 1973-5-21 [WAG.1065579]
Total: 24; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Strychnos phaeotricha Gilg
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 45344; 1962-3-29 [WAG.1065834]
Total: 4; Edo 3.

Strychnos samba P.A.Duvign.
Meer, PPC van 1329; 1971-4-16 [WAG.1066082]
Total: 2; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Strychnos soubrensis Hutch. & Dalziel
Medler, JA 377; 1970-5-2 [WAG.1066390]
Total: 14; Cross River 2, Edo 5, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1.

Strychnos spinosa Lam.
Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK FHI 69990; 1973-5-12 [WAG.1066569]
Total: 55; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Kano 4, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 17, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Strychnos splendens Gilg
Meer, PPC van 631; 1968-2-25 [WAG.1066812]
Total: 12; Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.

Strychnos staudtii Gilg
Meer, PPC van 1409; 1971-4-21 [WAG.1066885]
Total: 6; Cross River 5, Ondo 1.

Strychnos talbotiae S.Moore
Leeuwenberg, AJM 11272; 1977-3-28 [WAG.1066927]
Total: 14; Cross River 5, Edo 5, Niger 1.

Strychnos tricalysioides Hutch. & M.B.Moss
Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32846; 1981-6-20 [WAG.1067058]
Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Strychnos urceolata Leeuwenb.
Meer, PPC van 1297; 1971-4-15 [WAG.1067118]
Total: 11; Cross River 8, Ondo 1, Taraba 1.

Strychnos usambarensis Gilg ex Engl.
Emwiogbon, JA; Anyadiegu, JC 641; 1974-3-28 [WAG.1067330]
Total: 26; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 12.

Usteria guineensis Willd.
Daramola, BO FHI 86328; 1979-2-7 [WAG.1067785]

Total: 35; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5.

GELSEMIACEAE

Mostuea batesii Baker
Meer, PPC van 1256; 1971-4-14 [WAG.1060535]
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Mostuea brunonis Didr.
Ariwaodo j.O.249; 1978-4-19 [92524] [1990433023]
Total: 34; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 1, Cross River 21, Kogi 1, Oyo 4, Rivers 1.

Mostuea brunonis var. *brunonis*
Meer, PPC van 1673; 1971-5-18 [WAG.1060885]
Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 6, Kogi 1.

Mostuea hirsuta (T.Anderson ex Benth. & Hook.f.) Baill.
Coinochlamys hirsuta T.Anderson ex Benth. & Hook.f.

Olorunfemi, J FHI 55150; 1964-12-15 [WAG.1061044]
Total: 14; Cross River 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Nasarawa 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

APOCYNACEAE

Adenium obesum (Forssk.) Roem. & Schult.
Nerium obesum Forssk.
Hepper, F.N. 1609 18/12/1957; K
Total: 36; Adamawa 7, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kwara 3, Oyo 2, Taraba 4.

Alafia barteri Oliv.
Talbot, P.A. 301 1911; K
Total: 204; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Cross River 15, Delta 2, Edo 34, Ekiti 3, Enugu 4, Kaduna 2, Kogi 5, Lagos 9, Niger 4, Ogun 22, Ondo 12, Osun 11, Oyo 43, Rivers 1.

Alafia benthamii (Baill.) Stapf
Ectinocladus benthamii Baill.
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 38322 30/03/1958; K
Total: 14; Anambra 3, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Lagos 4.

Alafia erythrophthalma (K.Schum.) Leeuwenb.
Tabernaemontana erythrophthalma K.Schum.
Latilo & Onyeachusim FHI 54262 25/02/1964; K

Total: 17; Anambra 1, Cross River 7, Edo 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2.

Alafia landolphioides (A.DC.) K.Schum.

Holarrhena landolphioides A.DC.

Meikle, R.D. 933 02/01/1950; K

Total: 20; Abia 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Alafia lucida Stapf

Mann, G. 2245 02/1863; K

Total: 7; Abia 1, Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1.

Alafia multiflora (Stapf) Stapf

Holafia multiflora Stapf

Nwosu, N.A. FHI 58347 18/03/1966; K

Total: 11; Anambra 1, Imo 5, Lagos 2, Taraba 1.

Alafia schumannii Stapf

Onyeachusim, H.D. FHI 46995 07/02/1963; K

Total: 6; Ogun 3, Oyo 2.

Allamanda blanchetii A.DC. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1372; 1966-4-15 [WAG.1549581]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Allamanda cathartica L. — Introduced

Magaji, S.O. MG757 /1975; K

Total: 23; Edo 3, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Oyo 7.

Allamanda schottii Pohl — Introduced

Hagerup, O. 757; 1927-12-23 [K006087435]

Total: 1.

Alstonia boonei De Wild.

Wit, P. et al. 2340 06/12/1972; K

Total: 108; Anambra 2, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 7, Enugu 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 16, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 11, Oyo 35, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 3.

Alstonia congensis Engl.

Dalziel, J.M. 1256 03/10/1917; K

Total: 33; Delta 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 17, Niger 1, Taraba 2.

Ancylobothrys amoena Hua

Meikle, R.D. 1005 13/01/1950; K

Total: 54; Adamawa 2, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Niger 2, Ondo 4, Plateau 15, Taraba 4.

Ancylobothrys pyriformis Pierre

Onochie, C.F.A. & Jones, N. FHI 55237 18/08/1964; K

Total: 6; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1.

Ancylobothrys scandens (Schumach. & Thonn.) Pichon

Strychnos scandens Schumach. & Thonn.

Emwiogbon & Anyandiegwu FHI 72924 28/03/1974; K

Total: 15; Benue 2, Enugu 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Taraba 1.

Anisopus efulensis (N.E.Br.) Goyder

Marsdenia efulensis N.E.Br.

Talbot, P.A. 1684 /1912; K

Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Anisopus magniflorus (P.T.Li) S.Reuss, Liede & Meve

Marsdenia grandiflora C.Norman

Faremi, I.B. 365 13/05/1974; K

Total: 1.

Anisopus mannii N.E.Br.

Akpaba, G.K. 1114 20/03/1948; K

Total: 5; Edo 4.

Asclepias ameliae S.Moore

Daramola B.O.; 1969-5-14 [62710] 1944995308

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 2, Plateau 1.

Asclepias curassavica L. — Introduced

Lowe, J. 4448 27/11/1983; K

Total: 19; Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Ondo 6, Oyo 4.

Asclepias foliosa (K.Schum.) Hiern

Gomphocarpus foliosus K.Schum.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 22915 08/05/1948; K

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 8, Plateau 2.

Asclepias kamerunensis Schltr.

Thompson s.n. 24/06/1945; K

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Asclepias palustris (K.Schum.) Schltr.

Gomphocarpus palustris K.Schum.

Vely, H.V. 442 18/07/1921; K

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Asclepias solstitialis A.Chev.

Thornton, J. s.n. recd. 26/08/1913; K

Total: 9; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1.

Aspidoglossum interruptum (E.Mey.)

Bullock

Lagarinthus interruptus E.Mey.

Dalziel, J.M. 574 30/06/1911; K

Total: 9; Benue 1, Katsina 2, Niger 2, Taraba 1.

Baissea axillaris (Benth.) Hua

Zygodia axillaris Benth.
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 20691 24/02/1947; K
Total: 31; Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 4, Edo 3, Lagos 4, Ogun 2, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Baissea baillonii Hua
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 34894 20/05/1955; K
Total: 17; Abia 2, Delta 1, Edo 9, Kaduna 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1.

Baissea calophylla (K.Schum.) Stapf
Codonura calophylla K.Schum.
Brenan, J.P.M. 9162; 1948-02-27 [11751.000]
Total: 3; Edo 3.

Baissea campanulata (K.Schum.) de Kruif
Oncinotis campanulata K.Schum.
Binuyo, A. FHI 41294 12/05/1959; K
Total: 11; Ogun 7.

Baissea gracillima (K.Schum.) Hua
Guerkea gracillima K.Schum.
Datilo & Oguntayo FHI 70520 09/03/1973
Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Baissea laxiflora Stapf
Onochie, C. FHI.38307; 1952-03-29 [30509.000]
Total: 1; Edo 1.

Baissea leonensis Benth.
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 32935 13/05/1953; K
Total: 17; Akwa Ibom 5, Anambra 2, Cross River 2, Kano 1, Rivers 3.

Baissea multiflora A.DC.
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 38314 30/03/1958; K
Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Lagos 2.

Baissea subsessilis (K.Schum.) Stapf
Oncinotis subsessilis K.Schum.
Schlechter, F.R.R. 12310; 1899-03-01 [K000234015]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Baissea welwitschii (Baill.) Stapf ex Hiern
Perinerion welwitschii Baill.
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 37702 26/11/1958; K
Total: 19; Cross River 2, Edo 9, Ondo 3, Osun 1.

Batesanthus purpureus N.E.Br.
Ujor, E. FHI 30024 07/04/1951; K
Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 8, Niger 1.

Beaumontia grandiflora Wall. — Introduced
Echites grandiflorus Roxb.
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 57962; 1966-11-11 [WAG.1476131]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Beaumontia murtonii Craib — Introduced
L. Aké Assi; 1977-2-15 [1571695600]
Total: 1.

Callichilia barteri (Hook.f.) Stapf
Tabernaemontana barteri Hook.f.
Meikle, R.D. 1404 12/04/1950; K
Total: 208; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Akwa Ibom 7, Anambra 11, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 32, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 11, Enugu 7, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 11, Nasarawa 2, Niger 4, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Osun 6, Oyo 47, Rivers 5, Taraba 2.

Callichilia basileis Beentje
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 37016 22/05/1957; K
Total: 14; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Ogun 1.

Callichilia bequaertii De Wild.
Talbot, P.A. s.n. /1909; BM
Total: 1.

Callichilia inaequalis Stapf
Ujor, E. FHI 30819 10/05/1952; K
Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Katsina 1.

Calotropis procera (Aiton) W.T.Aiton
Asclepias procera Aiton
Olorunfemi, J. FHI 55750 18/03/1965; K
Total: 81; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 7, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 6, Kogi 3, Kwara 6, Lagos 9, Niger 11, Ogun 9, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 2, Sokoto 3.

Caralluma adscendens (Roxb.) Haw.
Stapelia adscendens Roxb.
Brown, N.E. 367; -- [K000614110]
Total: 1.

Caralluma dalzielii N.E.Br.
Dalziel, J.M. 367 07/1910; K
Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Niger 3, Plateau 2.

Carissa macrocarpa (Eckl.) A.DC.
Arduina macrocarpa Eckl.
Eijnatten CLM van; 1965-12-08 [WAG.1492904]
Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Carissa spinarum L.
Kennedy, J.S. FHI 7206 no date; K
Total: 52; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 10, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 12, Taraba 3, Zamfara 1.

Catharanthus roseus (L.) G.Don — Introduced
Vinca rosea L.
Stubbings, H.G. 198 17/08/1957; K

Total: 33; Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 10, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 6.

Ceropegia banforae (J.-P.Lebrun & Stork)

Bruyns

Brachystelma simplex subsp. banforae J.-
P.Lebrun & Stork

Stanfield, D.P. 196 29/05/1966; K

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Ceropegia bracteolata (Meve) Bruyns —

Endemic

Brachystelma bracteolatum Meve

Specks 549 10/1994; K

Total: 4; Plateau 4.

Ceropegia campanulata G.Don

Hopkins [FHI.52206.0]

Total: 30; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 6, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 4, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2.

Ceropegia campanulata var. *campanulata*

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 23434 26/02/1948; K

Total: 1.

Ceropegia campanulata var. *flavovirens*

L.E.Newton — Endemic

Newton, L.E. 1183 03/04/1972; K

Total: 1.

Ceropegia deightonii Hutch. & Dalziel

Milne-Redhead, E.; 1941-03-02 [K.23280.0]

Total: 8; Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Ceropegia deightonii subsp. *conjuncta*

H.Huber

Milne-Redhead, E. 5044 02/03/1941; K

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Ceropegia elliptica (A.Rich.) Bruyns

Brachystelma ellipticum A.Rich.

Daramola, B.O. FHI 62731 20/08/1969; K

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Ceropegia exilis (Bullock) Bruyns

Brachystelma exile Bullock

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25848 06/1965; K

Total: 6; Kaduna 5.

Ceropegia fusiformis N.E.Br.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25501 29/10/1949; K

Total: 29; Cross River 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Oyo 18.

Ceropegia ledermannii Schltr.

Young, J.D. s.n. /1922

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Kwara 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Ceropegia linophyllum H.Huber

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 37908 16/08/1959; K

Total: 4; Ondo 3.

Ceropegia neo-omissa Bruyns

Brachystelma omissum Bullock

Daramola FHI 62718 17/05/1969; K

Total: 2; Taraba 2.

Ceropegia nigra N.E.Br.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 34936 31/10/1955; K

Total: 10; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3.

Ceropegia porphyrotricha W.W.Sm.

Dalziel, J.M. 418 /1908; K

Total: 1.

Ceropegia racemosa N.E.Br.

Daggash, M., 24855. 12/08/1949; K

Total: 49; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Kaduna 11, Nasarawa 2, Niger 7, Ogun 2, Plateau 10, Taraba 1.

Ceropegia racemosa subsp. *racemosa*

Keay, R.W.J. & Clayton, W.D. FHI 37084

01/07/1957; K

Total: 1.

Ceropegia rhynchantha Schltr.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25951 10/07/1950; K

Total: 22; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 7, Kwara 2, Niger 2, Plateau 3.

Ceropegia sankuruensis Schltr.

Talbot, P.A. 174 /1911; K

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1.

Ceropegia stenoloba Hochst. ex Chiov.

Lawlor, D.W. & Hall, J.B. 452 18/05/1962

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Ceropegia talbotii S.Moore

Talbot, P.A. 116 /1911; K

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Ceropegia togoensis (Schltr.) M.G.Gilbert

Brachystelma togoense Schltr.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25856 08/06/1950; K

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 5, Niger 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Ceropegia tourana A.Chev.

Hambler 650

Total: 1.

Ceropegia yorubana Schltr.

- Meikle, R.D. 1256 12/03/1950; K
Total: 13; Cross River 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 9.
- Clitandra cymulosa* Benth.
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 34238 21/11/1954; K
Total: 17; Cross River 2, Edo 4, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1.
- Cryptolepis eburnea* (Pichon) Venter
Mangenotia eburnea Pichon
Dalziel, J.M. 1405 recd. 09/07/1920; K
Total: 3; Lagos 3.
- Cryptolepis oblongifolia* (Meisn.) Schltr.
Ectadium oblongifolium Meisn.
Olorunfemi, J. FHI 55719 26/02/1965; K
Total: 86; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 21, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 14, Oyo 9, Plateau 11.
- Cryptolepis sanguinolenta* (Lindl.) Schltr.
Pergularia sanguinolenta Lindl.
Daramola, B.O. FHI 38040 21/06/1958; K
Total: 39; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 8, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.
- Cryptostegia grandiflora* Roxb. ex R.Br. —
Introduced
Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-04-04 [WAG.1659478]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.
- Cryptostegia madagascariensis* Bojer ex
Decne. — Introduced
Burton, G. s.n. no date; K
Total: 1; Kaduna 1.
- Cyclocotyla congolensis* Stapf
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 15533 27/04/1953; K
Total: 9; Akwa Ibom 1, Ogun 5.
- Cylindropsis parvifolia* Pierre
Ujor, E. FHI 31796 08/05/1952; K
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Niger 1.
- Cynanchum adalinae* (K.Schum.) K.Schum.
Vincetoxicum adalinae K.Schum.
Jones A.P.D.; Onochie C.F.A.; 1946-05-28
[FHI.23259X]
Total: 30; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 5, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 1.
- Cynanchum adalinae* subsp. *adalinae*
Vincetoxicum adalinae K.Schum.
Tamajong, S. FHI 23259 29/04/1947
Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 5.
- Cynanchum boveanum* subsp. *boveanum*
Onyeachusim H.D.; Binuyo A.; 1966-03-06
[FHI.58342.0]
Total: 1.
- Cynanchum boveanum* subsp. *nubicum*
(Decne.) Khanum & Liede
Latilo, M.G. FHI 62767 03/08/1969; K
Total: 20; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Sokoto 1, Zamfara 1.
- Cynanchum insipidum* (E.Mey.) Liede &
Khanum
Pentarrhinum insipidum E.Mey.
Onyeachusim, H.D. FHI47206 [K005671720]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.
- Cynanchum longipes* N.E.Br.
Latilo, M.G. FHI 67538 20/09/1973; K
Total: 4; Lagos 2, Osun 1.
- Cynanchum praecox* Schltr. ex S.Moore
Milne-Redhead, E. 5030 15/02/1941; K
Total: 4; Kaduna 1, Taraba 2.
- Cynanchum viminale* (L.) L.
Euphorbia viminalis L.
Batten-Poole, W.H. [K000211319]
Total: 31; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Edo 3, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Ondo 6, Oyo 10, Plateau 1.
- Cynanchum viminale* subsp. *suberosum*
(Meve & Liede) Goyder
Sarcostemma viminale subsp. *suberosum* Meve
& Liede
Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 34687 07/04/1955; K
Total: 16; Edo 2, Gombe 1, Ondo 6, Oyo 4.
- Cynanchum viminale* subsp. *viminale*
Euphorbia viminalis L.
Onochie C.F.A.; 1955-04-07 [FHI.34687.0]
Total: 1.
- Desmidorchis retrospiciens* Ehrenb.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Dictyophleba leonensis* (Stapf) Pichon
Landolphia leonensis Stapf
Baldwin, J.T.Jr. 13770 20/11/1949; K
Total: 1.
- Dictyophleba lucida* (K.Schum.) Pierre
Landolphia lucida K.Schum.
Onochie, C.F.A. & Charter, J.R. FHI 34646
27/07/1955; K
Total: 2; Delta 1, Ondo 1.

Dictyophleba ochracea (K.Schum. ex Hallier f.) Pichon

Landolphia ochracea K.Schum. ex Hallier f.
Latilo, M.G. FHI 41323 11/03/1959; K
Total: 6; Cross River 6.

Dictyophleba stipulosa (S.Moore ex Wernham) Pichon

Landolphia stipulosa S.Moore ex Wernham
Talbot, P.A. 1296 1911/1912; K
Total: 6; Cross River 2, Niger 2, Osun 1.

Dischidia ovata Benth. — Introduced

Schlechter, R.; 1908-10-29 [P03899406]
Total: 1.

Dischidia soronensis Becc. — Introduced

Schlechter, R.; 1909-8-21 [P03899396]
Total: 1.

Epistemma assianum D.V.Field & J.B.Hall

Jones, A.P.D. 19546 19/08/1946; K
Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Farquharia elliptica Stapf

Latilo, M.G. FHI 31860 11/07/1952; K
Total: 12; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Plateau 1.

Funtumia africana (Benth.) Stapf

Kixia africana Benth.
Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 67659 23/02/1973; K
Total: 49; Abia 6, Benue 1, Cross River 12, Edo 6, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Osun 4, Oyo 3.

Funtumia elastica (Preuss) Stapf

Kixia elastica Preuss
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28291 20/12/1950; K
Total: 69; Bayelsa 3, Cross River 5, Edo 3, Gombe 1, Kano 7, Lagos 13, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Osun 4, Oyo 17, Plateau 2.

Gomphocarpus fruticosus (L.) W.T.Aiton — Introduced

Asclepias fruticosa L.
Bairnes, J. s.n.; 1871-10-02 [K001920456]
Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Gomphocarpus physocarpus E.Mey. — Introduced

Lely H.V. [FHI.9734.0]
Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Gomphocarpus semilunatus A.Rich.

Wit, P. et al. FHI 66742 10/05/1972 /1966; K
Total: 7; Taraba 3.

Gongronemopsis angolensis (N.E.Br.)

S.Reuss, Liede & Meve
Marsdenia angolensis N.E.Br.
Lely, H.V. P.515 07/1930; K
Total: 1.

Gongronemopsis latifolia (Benth.) S.Reuss, Liede & Meve

Gongronema latifolium Benth.
Emwiogbon, J.A. FHI 45501 17/04/1962; K
Total: 4; Anambra 1, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Rivers 1.

Gymnema sylvestre (Retz.) R.Br. ex Sm.

Periploca sylvestris Retz.
Latilo, M.G. FHI 62649 31/07/1969; K
Total: 51; Bauchi 5, Borno 4, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 8, Sokoto 4.

Holarrhena floribunda (G.Don) T.Durand & Schinz

Rondeletia floribunda G.Don
Adekunle, A.O. FHI 3007 13/03/1943; K
Total: 180; Anambra 2, Bauchi 5, Cross River 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 7, Kano 2, Katsina 7, Kebbi 1, Kogi 5, Kwara 2, Lagos 8, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 14, Ondo 18, Osun 11, Oyo 49, Plateau 5, Sokoto 3, Taraba 4, Zamfara 1.

Huernia nigeriana Lavranos — Endemic

Newton, L.E. 1194 fl. in cult. 02/1973 sub Leach 14902; K
Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Hunteria simii (Stapf) H.Huber

Polyadoa simii Stapf
Latilo, M.G. 196 [K005989562]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Hunteria umbellata (K.Schum.) Hallier f.

Carpodinus umbellata K.Schum.
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25705 31/03/1951; K
Total: 117; Benue 1, Cross River 10, Delta 1, Edo 7, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Lagos 9, Niger 1, Ogun 30, Ondo 7, Osun 8, Oyo 24.

Isonema buchholzii Engl.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 40444 01/12/1958; K
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 1, Rivers 1.

Kanahia laniflora (Forssk.) R.Br.

Asclepias laniflora Forssk.
Latilo, M.G. FHI 62599 21/07/1969; K
Total: 59; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 7, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 16, Oyo 10, Rivers 1, Sokoto 4.

Kopsia fruticosa (Roxb.) A.DC. —

Introduced

Cerbera fruticosa Roxb.

Leeuwenberg, AJM 11234; 1977-3-23

[WAG.1612085]

Total: 7; Osun 4, Oyo 3.

Lacmellea utilis (Arn.) Markgr. —

Introduced

Tabernaemontana utilis Arn.

John D.; 1982-2-22 [1084] 2274829380

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Landolphia buchananii (Hallier f.) Stapf

Clitandra buchananii Hallier f.

Hall, J.B. 2299 24/03/1971; K

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Plateau 1.

Landolphia calabarica (Stapf) E.A.Bruce

Carpodinus calabarica Stapf

Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 67660 23/02/1973; K

Total: 65; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 9, Anambra 3, Cross River 13, Edo 9, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 7, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Landolphia congolensis (Stapf) Pichon

Carpodinus congolensis Stapf

Ariwaola, J.O ARS 1276 07/1966; K

Total: 7; Abia 2, Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Landolphia deweyrei Stapf

Talbot, P.A. 1038 1911/1912; K

Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Niger 1.

Landolphia dulcis (Sabine ex G.Don)

Pichon

Carpodinus dulcis Sabine ex G.Don

Jones, A.P.D. FHI 648 11/02/1943; K

Total: 145; Abia 4, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 4, Cross River 29, Delta 3, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Enugu 6, Imo 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 4, Lagos 26, Niger 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 11, Osun 1, Oyo 12, Rivers 2.

Landolphia dulcis var. *barteri* (Stapf)

Pichon

Carpodinus barteri Stapf

Seen ; 00-01-1900 [LUH]

Total: 32; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 3, Cross River 6, Delta 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 4, Imo 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Landolphia dulcis var. *dulcis*

Carpodinus dulcis Sabine ex G.Don

Landolphia elliptica Lessia

Leeuwenberg A.J.M.; Malcomber S.T.; Rapanarivo

S.H.J.V. 14200; 1991-12-8 [105177] 1945001482

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Landolphia foretiana (Pierre ex Jum.)

Pichon

Carpodinus foretiana Pierre ex Jum.

Binuyo, A. FHI 41398 22/07/1959; K

Total: 6; Cross River 4.

Landolphia glabra (Pierre ex Stapf) Pichon

Carpodinus glabra Pierre ex Stapf

Okafor, J.C. & Emwiogbon, J.A. FHI 60232

16/07/1966; K

Total: 6; Cross River 4.

Landolphia hirsuta (Hua) Pichon

Carpodinus hirsuta Hua

Latilo, M.G. FHI 18220 17/01/1958; K

Total: 28; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Landolphia incerta (K.Schum.) J.G.M.Pers.

Carpodinus incerta K.Schum.

Onochie, C. FHI 8233 21/05/1945; K

Total: 25; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 3, Cross River 8, Edo 3, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Landolphia kirkii Dyer ex Hook.f. —

Introduced

Chevalier A. [BR0000014310188]

Total: 2.

Landolphia landolphioides (Hallier f.)

A.Chev.

Clitandra landolphioides Hallier f.

Chapman, J.D. 5189 03/02/1978; K

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Landolphia leptantha (K.Schum.)

J.G.M.Pers.

Carpodinus leptantha K.Schum.

Onyeachusim FHI 54069 23/02/1964; K

Total: 6; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3.

Landolphia mannii Dyer ex Dewèvre

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 22807 21/04/1948; K

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Oyo 5.

Landolphia maxima (K.Schum. ex Hallier f.)

Pichon

Carpodinus maxima K.Schum. ex Hallier f.

Talbot, P.A. 1304 no date; BM

Total: 2; Cross River 2.

Landolphia owariensis P.Beauv.

Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 67606 20/02/1973; K
Total: 95; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 7, Bauchi 1, Cross River 13, Edo 3, Enugu 7, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 5, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ondo 6, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Landolphia parvifolia var. *johnstonii*
(A.Chev.) Pichon

Literature
Total: 0.

Landolphia robustior (K.Schum.)

J.G.M.Pers.

Clitandra robustior K.Schum.
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28266 15/12/1950; K
Total: 12; Benue 1, Cross River 9, Delta 2.

Landolphia stenogyna Pichon

Talbot, P.A. 1055 no date; BM
Total: 1.

Landolphia subrepanda (K.Schum.) Pichon

Carpodinus subrepanda K.Schum.
Comm. McLeod, N.C. 09/1905; K
Total: 2.

Landolphia togolana (Hallier f.) Pichon

Cylindropsis togolana Hallier f.
Keay, R.W.J. FHI 21199 23/03/1947; K
Total: 12; Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 8.

Landolphia uniflora (Stapf) Pichon

Carpodinus uniflora Stapf
Talbot, P.A. 1480 no date; K
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Landolphia violacea (K.Schum. ex Hallier f.) Pichon

Carpodinus violacea K.Schum. ex Hallier f.
Onyeachusim & Latilo FHI 54007 17/02/1964; K
Total: 7; Cross River 5.

Leptadenia arborea (Forssk.) Schweinf.

Cynanchum arboreum Forssk.
Daramola, B.O. FHI 63684 01/12/1970; K
Total: 19; Bauchi 2, Borno 12, Kano 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 1, Yobe 2.

Leptadenia lanceolata (Poir.) Goyder

Cynanchum lanceolatum Poir.
Hepper F.N. [BR0000014830846]
Total: 38; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Borno 6, Jigawa 1, Kano 3, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 6, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Zamfara 1.

Leptadenia lanceolata subsp. *lanceolata*

Cynanchum lanceolatum Poir.

Latilo, M.G. FHI 62604 22/07/1969; K

Total: 3; Niger 2.

Leptadenia pyrotechnica (Forssk.) Decne.

Cynanchum pyrotechnicum Forssk.
Gbile et al. 1153 FHI 65382 26/04/1972; K
Total: 28; Borno 19, Jigawa 2, Niger 3, Yobe 1.

Malouetia bequaertiana Woodson

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 40441 01/12/1958; K
Total: 2; Rivers 1.

Malouetia mildbraedii (Gilg & Stapf)

J.Ploeg

Alafia mildbraedii Gilg & Stapf
Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25205 29/12/1948; K
Total: 11; Borno 1, Cross River 8.

Margaretta rosea Oliv.

Keay R.W.J.; 1957-07-05 [FHI.37113.0]
Total: 35; Adamawa 4, Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Plateau 13, Taraba 11.

Margaretta rosea subsp. *occidentalis*

Goyder

Wimbush, S.H. 54 FHI 48397 02/1959; K
Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 5.

Mondia whitei (Hook.f.) Skeels

Chlorocodon whitei Hook.f.
Daramola, B.O. FHI 38043 22/06/1958; K
Total: 76; Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 47, Taraba 1.

Motandra paniculata (Poir.) I.M.Turner

Echites paniculatus Poir.
Olorunfemi & Fagbemi FHI 70685 02/03/1973; K
Total: 86; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Anambra 1, Borno 2, Cross River 4, Delta 1, Edo 10, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 7, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 27, Taraba 1.

Nerium oleander L. — Introduced

Magaji, S.O. MG776 /1975; K
Total: 14; Enugu 1, Lagos 9, Ogun 2, Oyo 2.

Oncinotis glabrata (Baill.) Stapf ex Hiern

Motandra glabrata Baill.
Keay, R.W.J. & Onochie, C.F. FHI 19672 26/10/1946; K
Total: 18; Cross River 7, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Oncinotis gracilis Stapf

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 22531 16/03/1948; K

Total: 39; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 13, Ogun 6, Oyo 6.

Oncinotis nitida Benth.

Dalziel, J.M. 1347 07/06/1919; K

Total: 6; Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Oncinotis pontyi Dubard

Unwin, A.H. s.n. Recd. 05/04/1906; K

Total: 4; Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 2.

Oncinotis tenuiloba Stapf

Chapman, J.D. 38 FHI 70838 01/08/1973; K

Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Orthopichonia barteri (Stapf) H.Huber

Clitandra barteri Stapf

Barter 3310 no date; K

Total: 13; Edo 2, Kwara 7, Rivers 1.

Orthopichonia cirrhosa (Radlk.) H.Huber

Clitandra cirrhosa Radlk.

Talbot, P.A. 1351 1911/1912; K

Total: 14; Cross River 6, Niger 2.

Orthopichonia indeniensis (A.Chev.)

H.Huber

Clitandra indeniensis A.Chev.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 38311 29/03/1958; K

Total: 15; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Niger 2.

Oxystelma bornouense R.Br.

Wit, P. et al. FHI 47389 25/04/1972; K

Total: 47; Bauchi 2, Borno 8, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Ogun 7, Oyo 5.

Pachycarpus bisacculatus (Oliv.) Goyder

Gomphocarpus bisacculatus Oliv.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25897 25/06/1950; K

Total: 22; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 3, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Osun 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Pachycarpus lineolatus (Decne.) Bullock

Gomphocarpus lineolatus Decne.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25837 04/06/1950; K

Total: 27; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 7, Katsina 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 5, Taraba 4.

Pachycarpus petherickianus (Oliv.) Goyder

Schizoglossum petherickianum Oliv.

Dalziel, J.M. 1 02/01/1906; K

Total: 15; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 4, Niger 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Parquetina calophylla (Baill.) L.Joubert & Bruyns

Omphalonus calophyllus Baill.

Keay, R.W.J. & Latilo, M.G. FHI 37131 16/07/1957; K

Total: 1.

Parquetina nigrescens (Wennberg)

L.Joubert & Bruyns

Periploca nigrescens Wennberg

Eimunjeze & Oguntayo FHI 70242 17/05/1974; K

Total: 1.

Pentatropis nivalis (J.F.Gmel.) D.V.Field & J.R.I.Wood

Asclepias nivalis J.F.Gmel.

Dalziel, J.M. 94 18/08/1907; K

Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Pergularia daemia (Forssk.) Chiov.

Asclepias daemia Forssk.

Gregor T.; 1928-11-22 [FHI.9747-1]

Total: 80; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 9, Ogun 8, Osun 3, Oyo 28.

Pergularia daemia subsp. *daemia*

Asclepias daemia Forssk.

Latilo & Fagbemi FHI 66270 19/10/1972; K

Total: 8; Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 4.

Pergularia tomentosa L.

Latilo, M.G. FHI 62795 08/08/1969; K

Total: 13; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Sokoto 4, Yobe 2.

Picralima nitida (Stapf) T.Durand &

H.Durand

Tabernaemontana nitida Stapf

Onyeachusim FHI 48005 23/10/1963; K

Total: 54; Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 1, Cross River 9, Ebonyi 1, Edo 7, Katsina 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 4, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 7.

Pleiocarpa mutica Benth.

Ujor, E. FHI 30169 16/06/1952; K

Total: 25; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 17, Kwara 1.

Pleiocarpa pycnantha (K.Schum.) Stapf

Hunteria pycnantha K.Schum.

Latilo, M.G. FHI 31758 22/01/1952; K

Total: 38; Abia 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Ondo 2, Osun 11, Oyo 5, Taraba 5.

Pleiocarpa rostrata Benth.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28277 17/12/1950; K

Total: 21; Cross River 13, Niger 2, Rivers 1.

Pleioceras barteri Baill.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 26700 30/12/1952; K

Total: 86; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 5, Kwara 2, Lagos 30, Ogun 17, Ondo 2, Osun 5, Oyo 12, Taraba 1.

Pleioceras gillettii Stapf

Latilo, M.G. FHI 47780 01/11/1963; K

Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1.

Pleioceras zenkeri Stapf

Talbot, P.A. 3008 1912/1913; BM

Total: 2.

Plumeria alba L. — Introduced

Oduoye, O.T 2010-06-16 [3901264104]

Total: 2; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Plumeria rubra L. — Introduced

Students 2008-07-22 [3808438760]

Total: 9; Lagos 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 5.

Pycnobotrya nitida Benth.

Kennedy, J.D. 2085 no date; K

Total: 17; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Delta 7, Edo 4.

Raphionacme brownii Scott Elliot

Jackson 2563 FHI 59152 13/11/1963; K

Total: 28; Adamawa 1, Benue 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 6, Nasarawa 2, Niger 3, Oyo 6, Plateau 1.

Raphionacme keayi Bullock

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25990 30/07/1950; K

Total: 4; Kaduna 3.

Raphionacme splendens Schltr.

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Raphionacme splendens subsp. *bingeri*

(A.Chev.) Venter

Stanfield, D.P. s.n. 19/07/1966; K

Total: 1.

Raphionacme vinei E.A.Bruce

Literature

Total: 0.

Rauvolfia caffra Sond.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 33212 20/05/1953; K

Total: 21; Anambra 1, Cross River 3, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 10, Taraba 2.

Rauvolfia ligustrina Roem. & Schult.

John D.; 1982-3-15 [1087] 2274829366

Total: 1.

Rauvolfia mannii Stapf

Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 70549 09/03/1973; K

Total: 27; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 18, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Rauvolfia vomitoria Wennberg

Binuyo, A. FHI 41255 18/04/1959; K

Total: 368; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 2, Benue 3, Borno 1, Cross River 26, Delta 10, Edo 55, Ekiti 5, Enugu 2, Imo 3, Kaduna 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 27, Niger 3, Ogun 64, Ondo 20, Osun 17, Oyo 52, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 9.

Saba comorensis (Bojer ex A.DC.) Pichon

Vahea comorensis Bojer ex A.DC.

Adebusuyi, J.K. FHI 43959 04/08/1960; K

Total: 129; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 9, Bauchi 4, Benue 2, Cross River 6, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 16, Kano 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 3, Niger 15, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 25, Plateau 13, Taraba 3.

Saba thompsonii (A.Chev.) Pichon

Landolphia thompsonii A.Chev.

Onochie, C. FHI 7664 06/09/1944; K

Total: 36; Anambra 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 3, Lagos 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Secamone afzelii (Roem. & Schult.)

K.Schum.

Ichnocarpus afzelii Roem. & Schult.

Okeke, R. FHI 30135 14/08/1959; K

Total: 76; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 10, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 10, Ondo 4, Osun 6, Oyo 16, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Secamone brevipes (Benth.) Klack.

Rhynchosigma brevipes Benth.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25590 26/11/1949; K

Total: 20; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 6, Katsina 1, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ondo 1.

Stephanotis abyssinica (Hochst.) S.Reuss,

Liede & Meve

Pterygocarpus abyssinicus Hochst.

Binuyo, A. FHI 36903 25/03/1958; K

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Stephanotis crinita (Oliv.) S.Reuss, Liede &

Meve

Marsdenia crinita Oliv.

Patel, M.B. FHI 51345 05/1960; K

Total: 3; Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Stephanotis schimperi (Decne.) S.Reuss,
Liede & Meve

Marsdenia schimperi Decne.

Literature

Total: 0.

Strophanthus barteri Franch.

Latilo, M.G. FHI 21007 19/05/1947; K

Total: 64; Cross River 4, Edo 6, Lagos 4, Niger 1,
Ogun 5, Osun 3, Oyo 33.

Strophanthus bullenianus Mast.

Mann, G. 2247 02/1863; K

Total: 10; Cross River 8, Niger 1.

Strophanthus gracilis K.Schum. & Pax

Baldwin, J.T.Jr. 13756 19/11/1949; K

Total: 20; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Bayelsa 7, Cross
River 1, Edo 1, Niger 2.

Strophanthus gratus (Wall. & Hook.) Baill.

Roupellia grata Wall. & Hook.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28166 08/12/1950; K

Total: 23; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 2,
Lagos 1, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 4.

Strophanthus hispidus DC.

Jones, A.P.D. & Onochie, C.F. FHI 16070

26/03/1946; K

Total: 104; Abia 2, Anambra 2, Benue 1, Cross River
6, Edo 3, Kaduna 10, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger
24, Ogun 13, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 1,
Taraba 2.

Strophanthus preussii Engl. & Pax

Meikle, R.D. 1457 18/04/1950; K

Total: 121; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 27,
Ebonyi 1, Edo 31, Imo 2, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 9,
Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 16.

Strophanthus sarmentosus DC.

Ejiofor, M.C. FHI 19832 25/02/1950; K

Total: 169; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 3,
Anambra 3, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River
13, Edo 10, Ekiti 4, Imo 3, Kaduna 7, Katsina 4, Kogi
2, Kwara 2, Lagos 6, Nasarawa 5, Niger 10, Ogun 7,
Ondo 11, Oyo 20, Plateau 7, Sokoto 5, Taraba 3,
Zamfara 2.

Strophanthus thollonii Franch.

Latilo, M.G. 1 FHI 40901 16/03/1959; K

Total: 7; Cross River 6.

Tabernaemontana brachyantha Stapf

Talbot, P.A. s.n. 1911/1912; K

Total: 2; Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Tabernaemontana crassa Benth.

Onyechusim & Latilo FHI 54031 18/02/1964; K

Total: 17; Cross River 8.

Tabernaemontana divaricata (L.) R.Br. ex
Roem. & Schult.

Nerium divaricatum L.

Odewo T.K.; Adedeji 365; 1983-5-18

[99973]1945000699

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Tabernaemontana eglandulosa Stapf

Daramola, B.O. & Emwiogbon, J.A. FHI 32770
08/01/1961; K

Total: 64; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Cross
River 12, Delta 1, Edo 9, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kano 1,
Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Ogun 11, Ondo 5, Osun 3, Oyo 6,
Rivers 1.

Tabernaemontana glandulosa (Stapf)

Pichon

Gabunia glandulosa Stapf

Latilo & Oguntayo FHI 70509 05/03/1973; K

Total: 4; Cross River 3, Edo 1.

Tabernaemontana pachysiphon Stapf

Emwiogbon, J.A. FHI 63922 08/03/1972; K

Total: 94; Abia 8, Anambra 3, Cross River 5, Edo 20,
Imo 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 14, Ogun 9, Ondo 4, Osun 2,
Oyo 5, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Tabernaemontana penduliflora K.Schum.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 38308 29/03/1958; K

Total: 53; Cross River 6, Delta 1, Edo 12, Niger 1,
Ogun 6, Oyo 7, Rivers 1.

Tabernaemontana psorocarpa (Pierre ex
Stapf) Pichon

Gabunia psorocarpa Pierre ex Stapf

Talbot, P.A. 3228A 1912/1913; K

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Tabernaemontana ventricosa Hochst. ex
A.DC.

Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25214 29/12/1948;
K

Total: 5; Cross River 3, Kaduna 1.

Tacazzea apiculata Oliv.

Jackson, J.A.D. 221 FHI 54541 24/05/1964; K

Total: 112; Bauchi 4, Benue 5, Cross River 1, Edo 1,
Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 25, Kano 4, Kebbi 1, Kogi
4, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 20, Ogun 1, Osun 1,
Oyo 5, Plateau 14, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Tacazzea pedicellata K.Schum.

Dalziel, J.M. 1348 14/01/1919; K

Total: 4; Lagos 2.

Telosma africana (N.E.Br.) N.E.Br.

Pergularia africana N.E.Br.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25892 23/06/1950; K

Total: 76; Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Oyo 35, Taraba 1.

Thevetia peruviana (L.) Lippold —

Introduced

Cerbera peruviana Pers.

Emwiogbon, J.A. FHI 55874 12/03/1965; K

Total: 1.

Vahadenia laurentii (De Wild.) Stapf

Landolphia laurentii De Wild.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 31242 27/06/1957; K

Total: 14; Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 2, Ogun 1.

Vincetoxicum badium (E.Mey.) Meve & Liede

Astephanus badius E.Mey.

John D.; 1982-8-8 [1017]2274829314

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Vincetoxicum caffrum (Meisn.) Kuntze

Tylophora caffra Meisn.

Dalziel, J.M. 687 04/07/1912; K

Total: 1.

Vincetoxicum cameroonicum (N.E.Br.) Meve & Liede

Tylophora cameroonica N.E.Br.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 33430 29/08/1953; K

Total: 13; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 2, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Vincetoxicum carnosum (R.Br.) Benth.

Oxystelma carnosum R.Br.

John D.; 1982-3-22 [1015]2274829350

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Vincetoxicum conspicuum (N.E.Br.) Meve & Liede

Tylophora conspicua N.E.Br.

Binuyo, A. FHI 41355 14/05/1959

Total: 7; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Edo 2, Ondo 1.

Vincetoxicum dahomense (K.Schum.) Meve & Liede

Tylophora dahomensis K.Schum.

Faremi, I.B. 457 07/10/1974; K

Total: 3; Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Vincetoxicum gillettii (De Wild.) Meve & Liede

Tylophora gillettii De Wild.

Talbot, P.A. 3252 1912/1913; K

Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Niger 1.

Vincetoxicum oblongum (N.E.Br.) Meve & Liede

Tylophora oblonga N.E.Br.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 28064 03/11/1950; K

Total: 22; Akwa Ibom 2, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Edo 8, Oyo 2, Zamfara 2.

Vincetoxicum oculatum (N.E.Br.) Meve & Liede

Tylophora oculata N.E.Br.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 37676 28/09/1958; K

Total: 7; Kogi 1, Ondo 4, Oyo 2.

Vincetoxicum sylvaticum (Decne.) Kuntze

Tylophora sylvatica Decne.

Odewo, T.K. FHI 67142 21/09/1973; K

Total: 71; Abia 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Benue 1, Cross River 7, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Ogun 6, Ondo 3, Osun 4, Oyo 22, Plateau 1.

Voacanga africana Stapf

Meikle, R.D. 1376 05/04/1950; K

Total: 137; Akwa Ibom 8, Anambra 4, Benue 2, Cross River 4, Edo 16, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Lagos 10, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 17, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 20, Plateau 2, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Voacanga bracteata Stapf

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 36425X 25/02/1957; K

Total: 12; Cross River 8.

Voacanga diplochlamys K.Schum.

Talbot s.n. 1912/1913; K

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4.

Voacanga psilocalyx Pierre ex Stapf

Onyeachusim & Latilo FHI 48174 13/02/1964; K

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 15.

Voacanga thouarsii Roem. & Schult.

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI 40221 23/06/1958; K

Total: 24; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kogi 1, Niger 10, Taraba 6.

Xysmalobium heudelotianum Decne.

Keay, R.W.J. FHI 25930 05/07/1950; K

Total: 48; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Kaduna 17, Kano 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 12, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

BORAGINACEAE

Arnebia hispidissima (Sieber ex Lehm.)
A.DC.

Lithospermum hispidissimum Sieber ex Lehm.
Hereźniak J.; 1975-1-29 [POZG-V-0030398]
Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Katsina 1, Ogun 1,
Sokoto 1.

Coldenia procumbens L.

Leeuw, PN de 1898; 1967-3-20 [WAG.1397945]
Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Kano 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4,
Zamfara 1.

Cordia africana Lam.

Latilo, MG FHI 64743; 1971-12-4 [WAG.1398093]
Total: 16; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Gombe 1, Kano 2,
Taraba 1.

Cordia alliodora (Ruiz & Pav.) Oken —
Introduced

Cerdana alliodora Ruiz & Pav.
; 1969-1-27 [2252244411]
Total: 3; Enugu 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Cordia aurantiaca Baker

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70568; 1973-3-11
[WAG.1398138]
Total: 18; Cross River 8, Edo 2, Plateau 1.

Cordia millenii Baker

Latilo, MG FHI 47114; 1963-3-11 [WAG.1398275]
Total: 26; Benue 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 6, Oyo 4, Taraba 3.

Cordia myxa L. — Introduced

; -- [48835]2428992421
Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Osun 2.

Cordia platythyrsa Baker

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32968; 1981-6-23
[WAG.1398406]
Total: 22; Lagos 4, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Taraba 2.

Cordia senegalensis Juss. ex Poir.

Rowland s.n.; -- [K000418704]
Total: 6; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2.

Cordia sinensis Lam.

Leeuw, PN de 1892; 1967-3-20 [WAG.1398504]
Total: 5; Abia 2, Borno 1, Ogun 1.

Cordia uncinulata De Wild.

Patel, MB FHI 45742; 1962-3-10 [WAG.1398542]
Total: 4; Oyo 3.

Cordia vignei Hutch. & Dalziel

41280; 1959-5-8 [BR0000013486419]
Total: 4; Cross River 2, Oyo 2.

Cynoglossum amplifolium Hochst. ex A.DC.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cynoglossum amplifolium var. *subalpinum*
(T.C.E.Fr.) Verdc.

Literature

Total: 0.

Cynoglossum coeruleum var. *mannii* (Baker
& C.H.Wright) Verdc. — Introduced

Hepper, F.N.; 1958-- [B 10 0473988]

Total: 1.

Cynoglossum lanceolatum Forssk.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1368; 1972-5-11
[WAG.1481340]

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Niger 1, Plateau 3,
Taraba 1.

Ehretia crebrifolia (Miers) ined.

Rhabdia crebrifolia Miers

Literature

Total: 0.

Ehretia cymosa Thonn.

Ariwaodo, JO 28; 1976-12-11 [WAG.1482022]

Total: 34; Cross River 2, Ebonyi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2,
Lagos 9, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Rivers 1.

Ehretia cymosa var. *cymosa*

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 297; 1978-5-5
[WAG0177499]

Total: 17; Ebonyi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 4, Ogun
1, Oyo 4, Rivers 1.

Ehretia cymosa var. *zenkeri* (Gürke ex

Baker & Wright) Brenan

Phillips 34; 1901-08 [K000542292]

Total: 5; Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Euploca ovalifolia (Forssk.) Diane & Hilger

Heliotropium ovalifolium Forssk.

Denys, E 665; 1982-7-18 [WAG0177592]

Total: 26; Adamawa 2, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Kano
2, Niger 2, Osun 2, Oyo 6.

Euploca strigosa (Willd.) Diane & Hilger

Heliotropium strigosum Willd.

Denys, E 686; 1982-7-19 [WAG0177591]

Total: 60; Bauchi 7, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Edo 2,
Kaduna 13, Kano 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 2,
Niger 8, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Heliotropium bacciferum Forssk.

; 1995-10-23 [FR-0017944]

Total: 16; Borno 8, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe
2.

Heliotropium bacciferum subsp. *bacciferum*

Vogel 13; 00-01-1900 [K]

Total: 3; Borno 2.

Heliotropium indicum L. — Introduced

Geerling, C 3494; 1971-3-24 [WAG0083285]

Total: 75; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Gombe 2, Kaduna 4, Kano 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 7, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 8, Taraba 1.

Heliotropium pterocarpum (DC.) Hochst. & Steud. ex Bunge

Heliophytum pterocarpum DC.

Latilo, MG FHI 69429; 1974-5-31 [WAG.1928292]

Total: 15; Bauchi 3, Borno 7, Ogun 1, Plateau 1.

Heliotropium supinum L.

Popov G. 60/194; -- [BR0000014217449]

Total: 11; Borno 7, Niger 1, Yobe 1.

Heliotropium zeylanicum (Burm.f.) Lam.

Heliotropium curassavicum var. *zeylanicum* Burm.f.

Latilo, MG FHI 69406; 1974-5-29 [WAG.1366483]

Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Borno 9, Jigawa 2, Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Rotula aquatica Lour.

Jackson J.A.D. 653; 25-12-1965 [FHI20517, K]

Total: 5; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 1.

Trichodesma africanum (L.) Sm.

Borago africana L.

Latilo, MG FHI 64648; 1971-11-30 [WAG.1455863]

Total: 18; Adamawa 2, Benue 1, Borno 6, Gombe 2, Niger 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Trichodesma ambacense Welw.

Total: 12; Bauchi 4, Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Trichodesma ambacense subsp. *hockii* (De Wild.) Brummitt

King D. s.n; 1986-08 [K]

Total: 12; Bauchi 4, Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Trichodesma physaloides (Fenzl) DC. — Introduced

Friedrichsthalia physaloides Fenzl

1955-04-16 [I143711.0]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

VAHLIACEAE

Vahlia dichotoma (Murray) Kuntze

Heuchera dichotoma Murray

Daramola, BO FHI 62945; 1969-5-31

[WAG.1188384]

Total: 29; Bauchi 2, Borno 5, Edo 1, Gombe 4, Kaduna 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 3.

Vahlia digyna (Retz.) Kuntze

Oldenlandia digyna Retz.

Leeuw, PN de 1912; 1967-3-19 [WAG.1188415]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Borno 1.

Vahlia geminiflora (Caill. & Delile) Bridson

Bistella geminiflora Caill. & Delile

Marchal ; -- [P04399975]

Total: 3.

CONVOLVULACEAE

Aniseia martinicensis (Jacq.) Choisy —

Introduced

Convolvulus martinicensis Jacq.

Geerling, C 3302; 1970-10-31 [WAG.1541568]

Total: 39; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 3, Niger 2, Ogun 9, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Argyreia nervosa (Burm.f.) Bojer —

Introduced

Convolvulus nervosus Burm.f.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 67263; 1973-2-20 [WAG.1541596]

Total: 1.

Astripomoea lachnosperma (Choisy)

A.Meeuse

Ipomoea lachnosperma Choisy

Dalziel J.M. 371; 1910-08-25 [K001760997]

Total: 8; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kano 1.

Astripomoea malvacea (Klotzsch) A.Meeuse

Breweria malvacea Klotzsch

Peter, GA 51831; 1918-7-14 [WAG.1541655]

Total: 7; Adamawa 3.

Astripomoea malvacea var. *floccosa* (Vatke)

Verdc.

Ipomoea floccosa Vatke

Dalziel J.M. 72; 1909-06-12 [K001761002]

Total: 2.

Astripomoea malvacea var. *malvacea*

Breweria malvacea Klotzsch

Astripomoea malvacea var. *parviflora*

(Rendle) Staples

Astrochlaena stuhlmannii var. *parviflora* Rendle
[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Bonamia thunbergiana (Roem. & Schult.)
F.N.Williams

Convolvulus thunbergianus Roem. & Schult.
[Jones A.P.D. 2432; 1942-12-21 \[4843-1\]1949703236](#)
Total: 16; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Enugu 3, Kogi 3,
Lagos 5, Ogun 1.

Calycobolus africanus (G.Don) Heine
Codonanthus africana G.Don

[Onochie C.F.A. 8882; -- \[BR0000018869200\]](#)
Total: 15; Cross River 2, Edo 4, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Calycobolus campanulatus (K.Schum. ex
Hallier f.) Heine

Prevostea campanulata K.Schum. ex Hallier f.
[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Calycobolus campanulatus subsp. *oddonii*
(De Wild.) Lejoly & Lisowski

Prevostea oddonii De Wild.
[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Calycobolus gilgianus (Pilg.) Heine
Prevostea gilgiana Pilg.

[P.A. Talbot & D.A. Talbot 3702; -- \[BM000998015\]](#)
Total: 1; Akwa Ibom 1.

Calycobolus goodii Heine
Prevostea mayumbensis R.D.Good

[Latilo, M.G.; 1964-3-1 \[P00754209\]](#)
Total: 1.

Calycobolus heudelotii (Baker ex Oliv.)
Heine

Breweria heudelotii Baker ex Oliv.
[Ariwaodo, JO 471; 1977-3-27 \[WAG.1542065\]](#)
Total: 60; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 6, Edo 10,
Ekiti 4, Kogi 3, Lagos 8, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 17.

Calycobolus heudelotii subsp. *heudelotii*
Breweria heudelotii Baker ex Oliv.

Camonea umbellata (L.) A.R.Simões &
Staples

Convolvulus umbellatus L.
[Arewaodo J.O. 1441; 1966-11-09 \[K001754736\]](#)
Total: 12; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1,
Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2.

Convolvulus arvensis L. — Introduced
[Lely, H.V. 362; 1921-07-05 \[K001806062\]](#)

Total: 1; Kwara 1.

Convolvulus aschersonii Engl. —
Introduced

[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Convolvulus glomeratus Choisy
[Sharland, R.E.; s.n.; 1981-02-01 \[K001806060\]](#)
Total: 3.

Convolvulus glomeratus var. *glomeratus*

Cuscuta australis R.Br.
[Dalziel, J.M. 1353 \[K001805643\]](#)
Total: 4; Lagos 1.

Cuscuta australis var. *australis*

Cuscuta campestris Yunck. — Introduced
[C. Parker 2056; 1977-10-28 \[ODU00001416\]](#)
Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Cuscuta chinensis Lam.
[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Cuscuta scandens Brot.
[Jones A.P.D.; Campbell S.S.; 1945-10-26 \[FHI.13870.0\]](#)
Total: 9; Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Distimake aegyptius (L.) A.R.Simões &
Staples

Ipomoea aegyptia L.
[Geerling, C 3429; 1971-1-27 \[WAG.1756470\]](#)
Total: 18; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Niger 3, Ogun
1, Oyo 5.

Distimake cissoides (Lam.) A.R.Simões &
Staples — Introduced

[Literature](#)
Total: 0.

Distimake dissectus (Jacq.) A.R.Simões &
Staples

Convolvulus dissectus Jacq.
[Bels, L 137; 1950-4-27 \[U.1230876\]](#)
Total: 6; Borno 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Distimake kentrocaulos (C.B.Clarke)
A.R.Simões & Staples

Ipomoea kentrocaulos C.B.Clarke
[Latilo, MG FHI 64733; 1971-12-3 \[WAG.1756928\]](#)
Total: 13; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Niger 2,
Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Distimake quinquefolius (L.) A.R.Simões &
Staples — Introduced

Ipomoea quinquefolia L.

IBAAN; 1977-2-8 [2239681855]

Total: 3; Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Distimake tuberosus (L.) A.R.Simões & Staples — Introduced

Onochie, C.F.A.; FHI18658; 1958-01-14

[K001743130]

Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Evolvulus alsinoides (L.) L.

Convolvulus alsinoides L.

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 236; 1978-5-2

[WAG.1270913]

Total: 98; Bauchi 13, Benue 4, Borno 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 15, Kano 3, Katsina 3, Kogi 11, Kwara 4, Niger 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 10, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 2, Zamfara 1.

Hewittia malabarica (L.) Suresh

Convolvulus malabaricus L.

Odewo, TK; Adedeji 333; 1983-5-17 [WAG.1271156]

Total: 65; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Cross River 7, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Imo 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Niger 3, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 16, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Ipomoea acanthocarpa (Choisy) Hochst. ex Schweinf. & Asch.

Calonyction acanthocarpum Choisy

Dalziel J.M. 183; 1907-- [49905-1]1949704431

Total: 5; Bauchi 2, Borno 1.

Ipomoea aitonii Lindl.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1184; 1966-2-23 [WAG.1208775]

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1.

Ipomoea alba L.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 66282; 1972-10-20

[WAG.1208807]

Total: 27; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Ekiti 2, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.

Ipomoea aquatica Forssk.

Emwiogbon J.A.; Okafor J.C. 515; 1974-1-26 [72203]

Total: 96; Adamawa 8, Anambra 2, Bauchi 7, Bayelsa 1, Benue 2, Borno 11, Delta 3, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 6, Kwara 2, Lagos 4, Niger 9, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 4, Rivers 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 2.

Ipomoea aquatica var. *aquatica*

Ipomoea argentaurata Hallier f.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 67262; 1973-11-20

[WAG.1208981]

Total: 79; Adamawa 5, Bauchi 3, Benue 3, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 13, Kogi 7, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 12, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 6, Yobe 2.

Ipomoea asarifolia (Desr.) Roem. & Schult.

Convolvulus asarifolius Desr.

Olorunfemi J.; Binuyo A.; Babagbemi. 372; 1981-11-15 [96671]

Total: 87; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 5, Borno 3, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kano 4, Katsina 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Niger 14, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 2, Sokoto 3.

Ipomoea barteri Baker

Lely H.V. P. 510; 1930-7-[K001594353]

Total: 13; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Ipomoea barteri var. *barteri*

Dalziel J.M. 70; 28-07-1909 [K001594350]

Total: 1.

Ipomoea batatas (L.) Lam. — Introduced

Convolvulus batatas L.

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 140; 1977-10-6

[WAG.1209083]

Total: 33; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Edo 4, Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Yobe 1.

Ipomoea biflora (L.) Pers.

Convolvulus biflorus L.

Denys E. 778; -- [BR0000017392068]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Ipomoea blepharophylla Hallier f.

Geerling, C 3565; 1971-7-20 [WAG.1209122]

Total: 29; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 3, Oyo 3, Plateau 6, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Ipomoea cairica (L.) Sweet

Convolvulus cairicus L.

Olorunfemi J.; Oguntayo S.T.; Ihe 128; 1978-9-20 [88347]1944998839

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 3, Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Ipomoea carnea Jacq. — Introduced

Tijani Ganiyat; 2012-7-11 [5425]3808438697

Total: 4; Borno 1, Lagos 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Ipomoea carnea subsp. *fistulosa* (Mart. ex Choisy) D.F.Austin — Introduced

Lowe J. 4403; 1983-10-16 [101491]1945000878

Total: 2; Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Ipomoea chrysochaetia Hallier f.

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 67704; 1973-2-27 [WAG.1209266]

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Taraba 2.

Ipomoea chrysochaetia var. *velutipes*

(Welw. ex Rendle) Lejoly & Lisowski

Latilo, MG. FHI 64622; 1971-11-11 [K001587959]

Total: 1.

Ipomoea coccinea L.

Adolf Hafström; 1936-12-31 [S14-2206]1096843885

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Rivers 1.

Ipomoea coptica (L.) Roth

Convolvulus copticus L.

Dalziel J.M.; 1907-01-01 [FHI.49901.0]

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Borno 5, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Ipomoea coptica var. *coptica*

Convolvulus copticus L.

; 1993-9-17 [FR-0011689]3046043786

Total: 1.

Ipomoea coscinosperma Hochst. ex Choisy

Ibhanesebhor G.; Osanyinlusi; Adedeji 52; 1983-10-28 [100942]1945000758

Total: 12; Borno 5, Niger 1, Sokoto 1.

Ipomoea eriocarpa R.Br.

Gbile Z.O.; Olorunfemi J.; Emwiogbon J.A. 961; 1971-11-16 [64555]

Total: 108; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 8, Benue 1, Borno 10, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 5, Imo 1, Kaduna 16, Kano 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 4, Lagos 3, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 14, Plateau 6, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Ipomoea fulvicaulis var. *asperifolia* (Hallier f.) Verdc.

Aniseia fulvicaulis Hochst. ex Choisy

Meikle R.D. 1350; 1950-03-29 [K001740273]

Total: 1.

Ipomoea hederifolia L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1090; 1966-1-23 [WAG.1209648]

Total: 46; Cross River 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 11, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 11, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.

Ipomoea heterotricha Didr. — Introduced

Magaji, SO; Leeuw, PN de 158; 1967-9-14 [WAG.1209699]

Total: 41; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Niger 8, Ondo 4, Osun 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Rivers 1.

Ipomoea horsfalliae Hook. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1444; 1966-4-24 [WAG0274335]

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Ipomoea imperati (Vahl) Griseb.

Convolvulus imperati Vahl

Lowe J. 4903; 1990-11-11 [K001594384]

Total: 12; Bayelsa 2, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Rivers 1.

Ipomoea indica (Burm.) Merr. —

Introduced

Convolvulus indicus Burm.

; -- [11770]2821275863

Total: 5; Lagos 1, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Ipomoea intrapilosa Rose — Introduced

Brenan, J.P.M. 8970; 1948-2-6 [5505]912055684

Total: 7; Oyo 7.

Ipomoea involucrata P.Beauv.

Geerling C. [BR0000016085503]

Total: 127; Abia 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Cross River 15, Delta 3, Edo 6, Ekiti 3, Enugu 6, Imo 4, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 15, Niger 4, Ogun 11, Ondo 7, Osun 4, Oyo 18, Plateau 2, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Ipomoea lapathifolia Hallier f.

Lawlor, D.W.; Hall, J.B.; 22873.0 [K001740292]

Total: 3; Ondo 1.

Ipomoea linosepala Hallier f.

Total: 1; Adamawa 1, Kebbi 1.

Ipomoea linosepala subsp. *alpina* (Rendle)

Lejoly & Lisowski

Daramola B.O.; 1969-5-22 [62746]1944995387

Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Ipomoea mauritiana Jacq.

Kamphorst, A 47; 1960-1-1 [WAG.1528871]

Total: 102; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Benue 2, Cross River 11, Delta 1, Edo 2, Ekiti 2, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 13, Ondo 7, Osun 3, Oyo 19, Plateau 1, Rivers 3, Taraba 1.

Ipomoea muricata (L.) Jacq. — Introduced

Convolvulus muricatus L.

Dalziel J.M. 372; -- [BR0000017395083]

Total: 8; Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1.

Ipomoea nil (L.) Roth — Introduced

Convolvulus nil L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 66628; 1973-7-14

[WAG.1528961]

Total: 35; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 2, Delta 1, Enugu 3, Kaduna 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 3.

Ipomoea obscura (L.) Ker Gawl.

Convolvulus obscurus L.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000016096134]

Total: 11; Bauchi 1, Ogun 3, Plateau 4.

Ipomoea obscura var. *obscura*

Convolvulus obscurus L.

Dalziel J.M. 376; -- [BR0000016096134]

Total: 1.

Ipomoea ochracea (Lindl.) Sweet

Convolvulus ochraceus Lindl.

; 1995-9-15 [FR-0018266]3046111110

Total: 36; Adamawa 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Enugu 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Ipomoea pes-caprae (L.) R.Br.

Convolvulus pes-caprae L.

Wit, HCD de 7123; 1955-7-26 [WAG.1529150]

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Lagos 4.

Ipomoea pes-tigris L.

Dalziel J.M.; 1907-01-01 [FHI.49908.0]

Total: 11; Bauchi 2, Borno 4, Gombe 1, Yobe 1.

Ipomoea pileata Roxb.

Ogunwenmo K.O. KOOG 111; 1991-10-11 [K001591309]

Total: 2.

Ipomoea prismatosyphon Welw.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ipomoea prismatosyphon var.

prismatosyphon

Literature

Total: 0.

Ipomoea pyrophila A.Chev.

Meikle R.D. 1350; -- [BR0000017389082]

Total: 13; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 4, Plateau 3.

Ipomoea quamoclit L. — Introduced

Wit, P; Fagbemi, A 1225; 1972-2-24 [WAG.1529327]

Total: 16; Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

Ipomoea rubens Choisy

Geerling, C 3375; 1970-11-28 [WAG.1744669]

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 3, Osun 1, Plateau 2.

Ipomoea sagittifolia Burm.f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Ipomoea stenobasis Brenan

Adebusuyi, JK FHI 43598; 1961-11-28

[WAG.1744555]

Total: 9; Ondo 9.

Ipomoea tenuirostris Choisy

B.O.Daramola; 2008-10-25 [LUH.1277.0]

Total: 8; Cross River 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Ipomoea tenuirostris subsp. *tenuirostris*

B.O.Daramola; 2008-10-25 [1277]3808438417

Total: 1.

Ipomoea tricolor Cav. — Introduced

A. P. D. Jones FHI.13728; -- [US 1993650]

Total: 3; Oyo 3.

Ipomoea triloba L. — Introduced

Isawumi & Elufisan 1799; 1995-11-15 [S20-18818]

Total: 6; Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Ipomoea ugborea Ogunw. — Endemic

Literature

Total: 0.

Ipomoea vagans Baker

Denys, E 825; 1952-8-5 [WAG.1755044]

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Borno 6, Yobe 3.

Ipomoea verbascoidea Choisy

Lawlor D.W. & Hall J.B. 411; 1962-08-15

[K001587969]

Total: 10; Bauchi 4, Niger 1, Plateau 4.

Jacquemontia pentanthos (Jacq.) G.Don —

Introduced

Convolvulus pentanthos Jacq.

; [11771.0]

Total: 2.

Jacquemontia tamnifolia (L.) Griseb.

Ipomoea tamnifolia L.

; 1995-9-12 [FR-0018287]3046114119

Total: 33; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 14, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 2.

Lepistemon owariensis (P.Beauv.) Hallier f.

Ipomoea owariensis P.Beauv.

Pilz, GE 2218; 1977-11-27 [WAG.1756524]

Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 3.

Lepistemon parviflorus Pilg. ex Büsgen

Onochie, C.F.A. FHI5237; 1957-12-11 [K000044648]

Total: 6; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ondo 1.

Merremia emarginata (Burm.f.) Hallier f.

Evolvulus emarginatus Burm.f.

1995-9-12 [FR-0018303]3046044115

Total: 2; Borno 2.

Merremia hederacea (Burm.f.) Hallier f.

Evolvulus hederaceus Burm.f.

Meikle R.D. [BR0000017253697]

Total: 26; Adamawa 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 3, Taraba 2.

Merremia hederacea f. *hederacea*

Evolvulus hederaceus Burm.f.

Latilo, MG FHI 61416; 1971-10-28 [WAG.1756973]

Total: 1.

Merremia pterygocaulos (Choisy) Hallier f.

Ipomoea pterygocaulos Choisy

Geerling, C 3414; 1971-1-16 [WAG.1756773]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 3.

Merremia xanthophylla Hallier f.

Talbot P.A. 832; 1910-09- [K000097238]

Total: 3; Benue 2.

Neuropeltis acuminata (P.Beauv.) Benth.

Porana acuminata P.Beauv.

Meer, PPC van 935; 1968-11-14 [WAG.1417459]

Total: 42; Cross River 3, Edo 5, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 6, Osun 1, Oyo 4.

Neuropeltis alnifolia Lejoly & Lisowski

Meer, PPC van 786; 1968-5-15 [WAG.1574201]

Total: 12; Edo 2, Ondo 7, Oyo 2.

Neuropeltis velutina Hallier f.

Gentry 32737; 1981-6-16 [433306]1261135361

Total: 2; Ogun 1, Rivers 1.

Stictocardia beraviensis (Vatke) Hallier f.

Ipomoea beraviensis Vatke

Fred Ruel Jones 7338; 1943-11-4 [BM001253012]

Total: 18; Cross River 1, Ebonyi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Ondo 3.

Xenostegia pinnata (Hochst. ex Choisy)

A.R.Simões & Staples

Ipomoea pinnata Hochst. ex Choisy

Geerling, C 2977; 1970-10-21 [WAG.1756838]

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Yobe 2.

Xenostegia tridentata subsp. *angustifolia*

(Jacq.) Lejoly & Lisowski

Convolvulus tridentatus L.

Wit, P 443; 1971-9-20 [WAG.1756045]

Total: 15; Enugu 1, Kano 2, Kogi 5, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Xenostegia tridentata subsp. *tridentata*

Convolvulus tridentatus L.

Daramola, BO FHI 36932; 1958-6-6 [WAG.1756051]

Total: 1.

SOLANACEAE

Browallia americana L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van s.n.; 1966-1-1 [WAG.1525515]

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Oyo 1.

Brugmansia arborea (L.) Sweet —

Introduced

Datura arborea L.

Daramola, BO FHI 40607; 1959-1-16

[WAG.1925082]

Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Brugmansia candida Pers. — Introduced

Daramola, B.O. FH40607; 1959-01-16 [K001821677]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Niger 1.

Brugmansia suaveolens (Humb. & Bonpl.

ex Willd.) Sweet — Introduced

Datura suaveolens Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd.

Ariwaodo J.O. 341; 1978-5-23 [93347]1944999610

Total: 1; Rivers 1.

Brunfelsia americana L. — Introduced

P. Ogua FHI13634; -- [US 1993644]

Total: 6; Benue 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 4.

Brunfelsia pauciflora (Cham. & Schltdl.)

Benth. — Introduced

Franciscea pauciflora Cham. & Schltdl.

Ogah; 1945-10-22 [13633]1944988830

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Brunfelsia uniflora (Pohl) D.Don —

Introduced

Franciscea uniflora Pohl

P. Ogua FHI13633; -- [US 1993643]2235947219

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Capsicum annum L. — Introduced

Odewo, TK; Adedeji s.n.; 1983-5-12 [WAG.1526076]

Total: 32; Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Capsicum chinense Jacq. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Datura innoxia Mill. — Introduced
Etkin 192; 1987-11-18 [469593]1262253423
Total: 15; Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Yobe 1.

Datura metel L. — Introduced
Eimunjeze, VE; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70217; 1974-5-16 [WAG.1831676]
Total: 54; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 7, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 5, Ogun 3, Ondo 6, Osun 4, Oyo 14.

Datura stramonium L. — Introduced
Olorunfemi, J.O.; 1965-9-16 [P00327211]
Total: 13; Borno 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Discopodium penninervium Hochst.
Chapman, J.D.; 3742; 1975-02-23 [K001779779]
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Lycium chinense Mill. — Introduced
; -- [2532125]3950489700
Total: 1.

Nicotiana rustica L. — Introduced
Ujor, E. FHI30339; 1951-05-11 [K001827081]
Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Nicotiana tabacum L. — Introduced
Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70711; 1973-3-5 [WAG.1526605]
Total: 54; Anambra 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 17, Ondo 9, Osun 1, Oyo 12, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Physalis angulata L. — Introduced
Daramola, BO D 9; 1977-8-12 [WAG.1526798]
Total: 252; Abia 2, Adamawa 4, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Bayelsa 2, Benue 4, Borno 7, Cross River 22, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 9, Ekiti 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 4, Imo 7, Kaduna 5, Kano 6, Kogi 12, Kwara 8, Lagos 12, Niger 14, Ogun 30, Ondo 21, Osun 3, Oyo 27, Plateau 5, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 10.

Physalis lagascae Roem. & Schult. — Introduced
Physalis parviflora Lag.
Daramola, BO D 12; 1977-6-12 [WAG.1526949]
Total: 40; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 6, Osun 3, Oyo 5, Taraba 5.

Physalis peruviana L. — Introduced
Daramola, BO D 48; 1977-8-15 [WAG.1527062]
Total: 24; Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 7, Taraba 6.

Schwenckia americana L. — Introduced
Daramola, BO D 13; 1977-8-12 [WAG.1527242]
Total: 168; Abia 2, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 8, Bauchi 5, Benue 4, Cross River 11, Edo 17, Enugu 5, Imo 3, Kaduna 9, Kano 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 9, Lagos 5, Niger 5, Ogun 13, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 16, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 9.

Solandra grandiflora Sw. — Introduced
Oyebanji O.O. LUH6730; 2015- [LUH]
Total: 1.

Solanum aculeastrum Dunal
Odewo, TK OM 180; 1982-5-27 [WAG.1527464]
Total: 25; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 13.

Solanum aculeastrum subsp. *aculeastrum* — Introduced
Chapman, J.D. 2515; 1971-8-26 [K000489431]
Total: 3; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Solanum aculeatissimum Jacq. — Introduced
Odewo, TK OD 174; 1982-5-27 [WAG.1527496]
Total: 23; Cross River 3, Edo 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 12.

Solanum aethiopicum L. — Introduced
Odewo, TK 179; 1982-5-27 [WAG.1203948]
Total: 121; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Anambra 2, Borno 2, Cross River 8, Edo 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 3, Kaduna 4, Kogi 7, Kwara 14, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 33, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Solanum americanum Mill. — Introduced
Gbile Z.O. 1/11; 1981-11-3 [95178]1944999959
Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Taraba 2.

Solanum anguivi Lam.
Odewo, TK 138; 1982-5-24 [WAG.1202996]
Total: 102; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 3, Cross River 13, Delta 2, Edo 3, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 7, Taraba 14.

Solanum anomalum Thonn.
Meer, PPC van 720; 1968-4-25 [WAG.1203039]
Total: 14; Delta 1, Edo 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 5, Osun 1.

Solanum asperolanatum Ruiz & Pav. — Introduced
Soladoye M.O.; Daramola B.O. 147; 1978-11-2 [86083]1944998599
Total: 6; Delta 1, Edo 2, Kogi 1, Oyo 2.

Solanum cerasiferum Dunal

Dalziel, J.M. 183; 1909-4-30 [K000414050]

Total: 6; Borno 1, Gombe 2.

Solanum dasyphyllum Schumach. & Thonn.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi FHI 90114; 1979-4-9 [WAG.1203572]

Total: 90; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 10, Kaduna 2, Kogi 5, Lagos 4, Niger 7, Ogun 4, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 5, Taraba 13.

Solanum donianum Walp. — Introduced

Pilz, GE 2380; 1980-5-14 [WAG.1834148]

Total: 22; Cross River 1, Edo 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 7.

Solanum erianthum D.Don — Introduced

Gillett, J.B. FHI15283; 1962-8-7 [K001155743]

Total: 105; Cross River 3, Edo 12, Gombe 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 5, Niger 5, Ogun 20, Ondo 18, Osun 2, Oyo 25.

Solanum giganteum Jacq.

Chapman, J.D. 4004; 1975-12-2 [K000489378]

Total: 5; Taraba 4.

Solanum grandiflorum Ruiz & Pav. —

Introduced

Dr Kadiri A.B.; 2015-9-12 [6730]3808442441

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Solanum incanum L.

Dalziel, J.M. 184; 1909-3-25 [K000788644]

Total: 18; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Enugu 1, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Niger 3, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2.

Solanum lasiocarpum Dunal — Introduced

Odewo T.K. 137; 1982-5-24 [97117]1945000316

Total: 56; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 22.

Solanum lycopersicum L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1318; 1966-3-26 [WAG.1587420]

Total: 36; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 7, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Solanum macrocarpon L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1045; 1965-12-15

[WAG.1204386]

Total: 46; Abia 3, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 12, Rivers 1.

Solanum madagascariense Dunal —

Introduced

Talbot P.A. 3211; -- [K000414057]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Solanum mammosum L. — Introduced

Latilo M.G.; 1975-2-18 [71069-1]1949704627

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Solanum mauritianum Scop. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Solanum melongena L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1144; 1965-12-15

[WAG.1204651]

Total: 20; Edo 1, Gombe 1, Katsina 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Solanum melongena subsp. *melongena* —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1144; 1965-12-15

[WAG.1204651]

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Solanum muricatum Aiton — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2012-11-24 [114A]1990271688

Total: 1; Anambra 1.

Solanum pittosporifolium Hemsl. —

Introduced

B.O.Daramola; 2009-10-1 [2016]3808442473

Total: 1.

Solanum sarrachoides Sendtn. —

Introduced

Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O. 51; 1974-11-22

[76912]1944997135

Total: 1; Kaduna 1.

Solanum scabrum Mill.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1143; 1965-12-15

[WAG.1842982]

Total: 54; Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Niger 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 14.

Solanum tanderemotum Bitter

John McEwan Dalziel s.n.; 1912-- [BM000943032]

Total: 4; Enugu 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 1.

Solanum terminale Forssk.

Chapman, J.D. 70885; 1973-8-9 [K000489341]

Total: 25; Cross River 1, Edo 2, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 4, Taraba 7.

Solanum torvum Sw. — Introduced

Thomas H.R. Hall; 1949-10-19 [27027-1]1949703798

Total: 246; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 39, Delta 2, Edo 26, Ekiti 3, Enugu 1, Kogi 8, Lagos 18, Niger 12, Ogun 28, Ondo 25, Osun 14, Oyo 46, Rivers 5, Taraba 3.

Solanum tuberosum L. — Introduced

Ujor, E. FHI30070; -- [K001170399]

Total: 4; Kogi 1, Plateau 2.

Solanum villosum Mill.

Etkin 63A; 1988-3-16 [469546]1262253368

Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Kano 1.

Solanum welwitschii C.H.Wright

Meer, PPC van 1481; 1971-4-26 [WAG.1229123]

Total: 7; Benue 1, Cross River 4, Kogi 1, Rivers 1.

Solanum wrightii Benth. — Introduced

Akpabla, G.K.1860; 1958-1-28 [K000658712]

Total: 6; Cross River 3, Imo 1, Oyo 1.

Withania somnifera (L.) Dunal

Physalis somnifera L.

Lely, H.V.; P209; 1929-04-01 [K001620764]

Total: 7; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Plateau 1.

SPHENOCLEACEAE

Sphenoclea dalzielii N.E.Br.

Dalziel, J.M. 201 [K000425230]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Sphenoclea zeylanica Gaertn.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3746; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1229970]

Total: 99; Abia 2, Adamawa 2, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 4, Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River 3, Delta 3, Edo 2, Gombe 3, Kaduna 2, Kano 3, Kogi 5, Lagos 10, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 8, Ondo 1, Oyo 19, Plateau 1, Rivers 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

HYDROLEACEAE

Hydrolea floribunda Kotschy & Peyr.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3735; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1514676]

Total: 21; Adamawa 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Delta 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Niger 8, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Hydrolea macrosepala A.W.Benn.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 67264; 1973-11-20 [WAG.1514693]

Total: 16; Borno 1, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Hydrolea palustris (Aubl.) Forsyth f.

Sagonea palustris Aubl.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 53; 1979-4-20 [WAG.1514754]

Total: 22; Cross River 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 3, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Rivers 1.

OLEACEAE

Fraxinus ornus L. — Introduced

; -- [50665]2428995437

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Jasminum bakeri Scott Elliot

Meer, PPC van 1831; 1971-5-25 [WAG.1125533]

Total: 4; Cross River 3.

Jasminum dichotomum Vahl

Geerling, C 4293; 1971-9-30 [WAG.1125630]

Total: 51; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 8, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 10, Taraba 7.

Jasminum flavovirens Gilg & G.Schellenb.

Literature

Total: 0.

Jasminum fluminense Vell.

Hepper F.N.; 1957-10-21 [BR0000019303970]

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Plateau 6.

Jasminum fluminense subsp. *fluminense*

Hepper F.N. 1089; 1957-10-21 [BR0000019303970]

Total: 1.

Jasminum multiflorum (Burm.f.) Andrews

— Introduced

Nyctanthes multiflora Burm.f.

Wit, P 541; 1971-10-3 [WAG.1125973]

Total: 13; Anambra 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 6.

Jasminum obtusifolium Baker

Wit, P 1753; 1972-5-4 [WAG.1126018]

Total: 24; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Niger 10, Sokoto 1.

Jasminum pauciflorum Benth.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 372; 1978-5-9 [WAG.1126101]

Total: 37; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Jasminum preussii Engl. & Knobl.

Meer, PPC van 1984; 1971-5-24 [WAG.1126203]

Total: 19; Cross River 9, Ogun 5, Ondo 3, Oyo 1.

Jasminum sambac (L.) Aiton — Introduced

Nyctanthes sambac L.

; -- [11830]2821279857

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Jasminum turneri C.T.White — Introduced

Takeuchi, W.; 1990-9-6 [P05108243]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Noronhia africana (Knobl.) Hong-Wa & Besnard

Mayepea africana Knobl.

Daramola 489; 1994-10-27 [100638845]

Total: 5; Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.

Noronhia mannii (Soler.) Hong-Wa & Besnard

Linociera mannii Soler.

1973-1-4 [2252245211]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Noronhia mildbraedii (Gilg & G.Schellenb.) Hong-Wa & Besnard

Campanolea mildbraedii Gilg & G.Schellenb.

Matthew Walters; 2012-12-11

Total: 3; Borno 1, Taraba 2.

Noronhia nilotica (Oliv.) Hong-Wa & Besnard

Linociera nilotica Oliv.

Latilo, MG; Daramola, BO FHI 28883; 1954-12-10 [WAG.1124328]

Total: 53; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 4, Edo 1, Kaduna 10, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 3, Niger 4, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Taraba 3, Zamfara 2.

Olea capensis L.

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Olea capensis subsp. *macrocarpa* (C.H.Wright) I. Verd.

Chapman, J.D.; 4432; 1976-05-04 [K005998886]

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Schrebera arborea A.Chev.

Okafor, JC; Emwioigbon, JA FHI 66029; 1973-2-27 [WAG.1127169]

Total: 18; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 9.

Schrebera trichoclada Welw. — Introduced

Wembley Exhibition s.n.; -- [L.1140390]

Total: 9.

GESNERIACEAE

Episcia reptans Mart. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1375; 1966-4-15 [WAG.1826316]

Total: 1.

Epithema tenue C.B.Clarke

Chapman, J.D. 4505, 30/6/1976; K

Total: 1.

Streptocarpus elongatus Engl.

Daramola B.O. FHI62365, 28/11/1968, K

Total: 9; Borno 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Streptocarpus lineatus (B.L.Burt) Mich.Möller & M.Hughes

Nodonema lineatum B.L.Burt

Medler J. 836, 17/8/1973, K

Total: 1.

Streptocarpus nobilis C.B.Clarke

Ogbeni J. FHI5199, 23/10/1957, K

Total: 33; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Nasarawa 2, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Streptocarpus strigosus (Hook.f.) Nishii & Mich.Möller

Acanthonema strigosum Hook.f.

Hewan s.n., 1862, E

Total: 1.

PHRYMACEAE

Glossostigma diandrum (L.) Kuntze

Limosella diandra L.

KERSHAW NGA-29614; 1966-01-01 [1948980682]

Total: 1.

Mimulus gracilis R.Br.

Lely H.V. P 355; 1930-7- [10663] [2013040225]

Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

PLANTAGINACEAE

Angelonia salicariifolia Bonpl. —

Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1069; 1966-1-20 [WAG.1355531]

Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Enugu 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 3.

Bacopa crenata (P.Beauv.) Hepper

Herpestis crenata P.Beauv.

Eimunjeze Ekwuno; 1973-11-18 [68119]1990431567

Total: 35; Adamawa 2, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Edo 1, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Nasarawa 1, Niger 5, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.

Bacopa egensis (Poepp.) Pennell

Hydrantheium egense Poepp.

Hens, F.; 119; 1888-07-07 [K005383698]

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Bacopa floribunda (R.Br.) Wettst.

Herpestis floribunda R.Br.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A 67261; 1973-11-20
[WAG.1355887]

Total: 25; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1,
Kwara 1, Niger 6, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 3.

Bacopa hamiltoniana (Benth.) Wettst.

Herpestis hamiltoniana Benth.

Hepper F.N.1192; 1957-11-1 [BR0000019040202]

Total: 23; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Edo 1,
Gombe 2, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Taraba 5, Yobe
3.

Bacopa hamiltoniana var. *angustisepala*

Hepper

Hepper F.N.976; 1957-9-9 [52922] [1990430539]

Total: 2; Imo 1, Niger 1.

Bacopa hamiltoniana var. *hamiltoniana*

Herpestis hamiltoniana Benth.

Latilo, MG 61411; 1971-10-28 [WAG.1355932]

Total: 8; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Kaduna 1,
Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Bacopa monnieri (L.) Wettst.

Lysimachia monnieri L.

Hepper F.N. 2249; 1958-3-7 [52968]

Total: 5; Bayelsa 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 3.

Bacopa occultans (Hiern) Hutch. & Dalziel

Moniera occultans Hiern

Barter 1689 [K005383700]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

Dopatrium baoulense A.Chev.

Latilo M.G1; 1962-7-28 [53874] [1990430554]

Total: 3; Ogun 2, Oyo 1.

Dopatrium junceum (Roxb.) Buch.-Ham. ex
Benth.

Gratiola juncea Roxb.

Geerling, C 3695; 1971-7-22 [WAG.1836375]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Oyo 2.

Dopatrium longidens Skan

D.W. Lawlon & J.B. Hall FHI45597; 1962-7-24
[BR0000018026016]

Total: 49; Bauchi 2, Benue 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1,
Kaduna 10, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 7,
Oyo 6, Plateau 8, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Dopatrium senegalense Benth.

Okafor J.C.36864; 1958-1-31 [1116]2013044680

Total: 4; Kogi 4.

Limnophila barteri Skan

Lowe, J 1961; 1970-1-5 [WAG.1471405]

Total: 12; Edo 4, Kebbi 1, Niger 3, Oyo 1.

Limnophila fluviatilis A.Chev.

Vaillant, A.; 2785; 1962-11-16 [K005382833]

Total: 2; Kebbi 1.

Limnophila indica (L.) Druce

Hottonia indica L.

Geerling, C 3361; 1970-11-23 [WAG.1570686]

Total: 7; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Niger 2, Yobe 1.

Mecardonia procumbens (Mill.) Small —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Plantago lanceolata L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Plantago major L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Russelia equisetiformis Schlttdl. & Cham. —

Introduced

Wit P.545; 1971-10-3 [64390] [2013042681]

Total: 2; Oyo 2.

Scoparia dulcis L. — Introduced

Denys, E 611; 1982-4-16 [WAG.1835420]

Total: 271; Abia 3, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 2,
Anambra 6, Bauchi 6, Bayelsa 4, Benue 3, Borno 7,
Cross River 20, Delta 3, Edo 26, Ekiti 6, Enugu 7,
Gombe 2, Imo 6, Kaduna 12, Kano 3, Katsina 3, Kogi
12, Kwara 1, Lagos 20, Nasarawa 3, Niger 4, Ogun
24, Ondo 14, Osun 8, Oyo 21, Plateau 10, Taraba 11,
Yobe 2.

Sibthorpia europaea L.

Hepper F.N. 2009; 1958-2-15 [BR0000018143157]

Total: 2.

Stemodia serrata (Hochst.) Benth.

Sutera serrata Hochst.

Wickens, G.E.; 3559; 1975-12-11 [K006242808]

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Stemodia verticillata (Mill.) Hassl. —

Introduced

Erinus verticillatus Mill.

Daramola B.O.268; 1975-9-21 [78551] [2013043273]

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Veronica abyssinica Fresen.

Hepper F.N. 1718; 1958-1-20 [BR0000018089783]

Total: 5; Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

SCROPHULARIACEAE

Anticharis arabica Endl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Anticharis senegalensis (Walp.) Bhandari

Doratanthera senegalensis Walp.

Literature

Total: 0.

Aptosimum pumilum (Hochst.) Benth.

Chilostigma pumilum Hochst.

Literature

Total: 0.

Capraria biflora L. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Diclis ovata Benth.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63307; 1970-4-4

[WAG.1469683]

Total: 4; Taraba 3.

Rhabdotosperma ledermannii (Schltr. ex

Murb.) Hartl

Celsia ledermannii Schltr. ex Murb.

Chapman, J.D. 3365; 1974-11-01 [K001840586]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Taraba 1.

STILBACEAE

Nuxia congesta R.Br. ex Fresen.

Hepper F.N. 2203; 1958-2-26 [BR0000015867568]

Total: 17; Cross River 2, Gombe 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 8.

LINDERNIACEAE

Artanema longifolium (L.) Vatke

Columnea longifolia L.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000019036410]

Total: 59; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 12, Edo 3, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 13, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 7.

Artanema longifolium var. *longifolium*

Columnea longifolia L.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO; Odewo, TK FHI 67037;

1974-6-12 [WAG.1355753]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 1.

Craterostigma abyssinicum (Engl.)

Eb.Fisch., Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Lindernia abyssinica Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Craterostigma newtonii (Engl.) Eb.Fisch.,

Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Lindernia newtonii Engl.

Summerhayes, G.V.; 155; 1958-07-19 [K001853899]

Total: 2.

Craterostigma nummulariifolium (D.Don)

Eb.Fisch., Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Vandellia nummulariifolia D.Don

Eijnatten, CLM van 2099; 1966-9-27 [WAG.1472233]

Total: 17; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Crepidorhopalon debilis (Skan) Eb.Fisch.

Lindernia debilis Skan

Hepper F.N.1249; 1957-11-7 [42822] [2013041729]

Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Crepidorhopalon schweinfurthii (Oliv.)

Eb.Fisch.

Torenia schweinfurthii Oliv.

Geerling C.3602; 1971-7-20 [44199] [1990429783]

Total: 8; Niger 4, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Crepidorhopalon spicatus (Engl.) Eb.Fisch.

Torenia spicata Engl.

Geerling, C 3217; 1970-10-29 [WAG.1527871]

Total: 10; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 1.

Lindernia madagascariensis (Bonati)

Eb.Fisch., Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Bryodes madagascariensis Bonati

Onochie, C.F.A. Dalziel J.M. 415; --

[BR0000017456982]

Total: 5; Edo 1, Lagos 4.

Lindernia parviflora (Roxb.) Haines

Gratiola parviflora Roxb.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3840; 1971-7-28 [WAG.1527831]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Oyo 2.

Lindernia rotundata (Pilg.) Eb.Fisch.

Ilysanthes rotundata Pilg.

Hepper F.N. 1713; 1958-1-20 [BR0000020106010]

Total: 5; Taraba 4.

Lindernia rotundifolia (L.) Alston —

Introduced

Gratiola rotundifolia L.
Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 62895; 1970-4-2
[WAG.1472321]

Total: 6; Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Linderniella gracilis (Skan) Eb.Fisch.,
Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Ilysanthes gracilis Skan

Geerling, C 3686; 1971-7-21 [WAG.1527826]

Total: 22; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 1,
Borno 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Kogi 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 4,
Plateau 3.

Linderniella trichotoma (Oliv.) Eb.Fisch.,
Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Bonnaya trichotoma Oliv.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 240; 1971-9-15
[WAG0104182]

Total: 18; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 1,
Benue 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 6, Sokoto 1.

Stemodiopsis rivae Engl.

Hepper, F.N.; 1957-12-18 [B 10 0002524]
[144898270]

Total: 1.

Torenia crustacea (L.) Cham. & Schldl.

Capraria crustacea L.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65660; 1972-5-30
[WAG.1472113]

Total: 54; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 1,
Cross River 15, Edo 4, Imo 3, Kogi 2, Lagos 1,
Nasarawa 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 7, Plateau 8.

Torenia dinklagei Engl.

Leeuwenberg A.J.M. 10323; 1972-09-07
[BR0000018085686]

Total: 2; Rivers 1.

Torenia thouarsii (Cham. & Schldl.)

Kuntze

Nortenia thouarsii Cham. & Schldl.

Daramola, BO FHI 70324; 1973-2-16
[WAG.1837427]

Total: 43; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Edo
1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1,
Ondo 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Vandellia diffusa L.

Rosevear D.R.; 1931-01-15 [FHI.10659.0]

Total: 76; Abia 1, Anambra 3, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1,
Borno 1, Cross River 14, Delta 2, Ebonyi 1, Edo 12,
Enugu 4, Imo 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 4, Niger 5,
Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Vandellia diffusa var. *diffusa*

Emwiogbon, JA; Onyeachusim, HD FHI 65891; 1972-
10-11 [WAG.1472146]

Total: 1.

Vandellia senegalensis Benth.

Medler J.600; 1971-3-15 [29629] [2013041103]

Total: 3; Borno 1, Cross River 2.

Vandellia vogelii (Skan) Eb.Fisch.,

Schäferh. & Kai Müll.

Lindernia vogelii Skan

Barter 27 [K001857002]

Total: 1; Niger 1.

THOMANDERSIACEAE

Thomandersia hensii De Wild. & T.Durand

Latilo, MG; Oguntayo, ST FHI 70555; 1973-3-11
[WAG.1838534]

Total: 22; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Borno 2, Cross River
8, Kwara 1, Rivers 2.

Thomandersia laurentii De Wild.

Literature

Total: 0.

Thomandersia laurifolia (T.Anderson ex
Benth.) Baill.

Scytanthus laurifolius T.Anderson ex Benth. &
Hook.f.

Gbile Z.O.; Daramola B.O.; 1980-10-20
[94163]1990433468

Total: 22; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 19, Edo 1,
Kaduna 1.

PEDALIACEAE

Pedalioidiscus macrocarpus Ihlenf. —

Introduced

Bels L. 10; -- [BR0000017629638]

Total: 1.

Pedaliium murex L.

Bels, L. 10; 1951-07-07 (U)

Total: 2; Edo 1, Lagos 1.

Rogeria adenophylla J.Gay ex Delile

Daggash, M. s.n.; 1950-01-15 (FHI)

Total: 10; Bauchi 1, Borno 2.

Rogeria adenophylla subsp. *adenophylla*

Daggash, M. s.n.; 1950-01-15 (FHI)

Total: 1.

Sesamum alatum Thonn.

Daramola, B.O. s.n.; 1968-05-29 (FHI)

Total: 7; Katsina 1, Niger 2.

Sesamum angustifolium (Oliv.) Engl.

Sesamum indicum var. *angustifolium* Oliv.

Denys, E. 765; 1982-07-29 (BR)

Total: 10; Borno 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2.

Sesamum calycinum subsp. *calycinum*

Olorunfemi, J. & Fagbemi, A. FHI 70723; 1973-03-06 (WAG)

Total: 3; Enugu 2, Ondo 1.

Sesamum indicum L. — Introduced

van Eijnatten, C.L.M. 1627; 1966-06-16 (WAG)

Total: 34; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Osun 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Sesamum integribracteatum (Engl.) Byng & Christenh.

Ceratotheca integribracteata Engl.

Literature

Total: 0.

Sesamum radiatum Thonn. ex Hornem.

Ataholo, M. 1444; 1995-10-18 (FR)

Total: 51; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Sesamum sesamoides (Endl.) Byng & Christenh.

Ceratotheca sesamoides Endl.

Neumann, K. 1284; 1992-09-04 (FR)

Total: 43; Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Oyo 5, Plateau 1.

LAMIACEAE

Achyrospermum africanum Hook.f. ex Baker

J.D.Chapman 4674, 11 Feb 1977 (K)

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Achyrospermum erythobotrys Perkins

Savory & Keay 25211, 29. Dec. 1948 [K000437858]

Total: 1.

Achyrospermum oblongifolium Baker

Keay, R.W.J. FHI28195; 1950-12-9 [15284]

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Achyrospermum schlechteri Gürke

Literature

Total: 0.

Achyrospermum sp. aff. *aethiopicum* Welw.

Savory & Keay 25024, 19 Dec. 1948 (K)

Total: 1.

Aeollanthus angustifolius Ryding

Chapman 108, 17 Aug. 1973

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 2, Taraba 2.

Aeollanthus cucullatus Ryding

Literature

Total: 0.

Aeollanthus pubescens Benth.

unknown [K000405619]

Total: 55; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 3, Niger 3, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 10, Plateau 4, Sokoto 3.

Aeollanthus repens Oliv. — Introduced

Daramola, BO FHI 62919; 1969-05-24

[WAG.1614588]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Katsina 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1.

Aeollanthus suaveolens Mart. ex Spreng.

Hepper F.N.; 1953-11-20 [FHI.52300.0]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Aeollanthus trifidus Ryding

Literature

Total: 0.

Basilicum polystachyon (L.) Moench

Ocimum polystachyon L.

Meikle R.D. [BR0000017727020]

Total: 66; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 4, Ebonyi 1, Ekiti 3, Gombe 4, Kwara 2, Lagos 11, Niger 6, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 2.

Cantinoa americana (Aubl.) Harley &

J.F.B.Pastore — Introduced

Nepeta americana Aubl.

Lowe J; 1968-11-15 [WAG.1712505]

Total: 29; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Gombe 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Kebbi 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Sokoto 3, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Clerodendrum bipindense Gürke

Keay R.W.J.; 1950-12-09 [FHI.28182.0]

Total: 6; Cross River 2, Edo 1.

Clerodendrum buettneri Gürke

Latilo, M.G. 31813, 30.5.1952 (FHI,K).

Total: 5; Cross River 5.

Clerodendrum capitatum (Willd.)

Schumach.

Volkameria capitata Willd.

[E01126729]

Total: 105; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Edo 7, Ekiti 2, Enugu 5, Gombe 2, Kaduna 8, Kano 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 7, Ondo 5, Osun 4, Oyo 20, Plateau 6, Taraba 2.

Clerodendrum chinense (Osbeck) Mabb. —

Introduced

Cryptanthus chinensis Osbeck

Emmanuel; 2016-4-22 [6974]3808439914

Total: 3; Bayelsa 1, Lagos 1.

Clerodendrum dusenii Gürke

Barter, C.; 1858-01-01 [P00442335]

Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Edo 3, Osun 2.

Clerodendrum excavatum De Wild.

Eimunjeze & Oguntayo 70240, 17.5.1974 (FHI, K)

Total: 15; Cross River 1, Edo 8, Ogun 1.

Clerodendrum formicarum Gürke

Talbot, P.A.; 1913-01-01 [M.CM142206]

Total: 31; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 2, Edo 12, Nasarawa 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Taraba 5.

Clerodendrum japonicum (Thunb.) Sweet

— Introduced

Volkameria japonica Thunb.

Daramola B.O. FHI40612; 1959-1-15

[BR0000019274157]

Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2.

Clerodendrum melanocrater Gürke

Daramola B.O.; 1965-10-19 [FHI.56412.0]

Total: 3; Cross River 3.

Clerodendrum paniculatum L. —

Introduced

; -- [11810]2821281857

Total: 8; Akwa Ibom 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 6.

Clerodendrum polycephalum Baker

[E01126764]

Total: 91; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Delta 5, Edo 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 2, Lagos 23, Nasarawa 2, Niger 3, Ogun 16, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 17, Taraba 1.

Clerodendrum silvanum Henriq.

Moses & Jonathan19181 (FHI, K)

Total: 46; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 13, Ekiti 4, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 10.

Clerodendrum silvanum var. *silvanum*

[E01126715]

Total: 7; Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1.

Clerodendrum sinuatum Hook.

Edwin Ujor; 1950-07-12 [FHI.26621.0]

Total: 12; Lagos 4, Ogun 7, Oyo 1.

Clerodendrum splendens G.Don

Olorunfemi, J.& Fagbemi 70671, 17.4.1973 (FHI, K)

Total: 175; Abia 14, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 7, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 32, Edo 22, Ekiti 3, Enugu 7, Imo 4, Kaduna 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 13, Niger 2, Ogun 17, Ondo 4, Osun 8, Oyo 11, Rivers 6, Taraba 1.

Clerodendrum thomsoniae Balf.f.

Talbot, 3393, 1912/13 [K001400520] Type of *C.*

ekatense Wernham

Total: 32; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 2, Cross River 6, Edo 7, Imo 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1.

Clerodendrum thyrsoideum Gürke

Keay R.W.J.; Savory H.J.; 1947-11-27 [FHI.22452.0]

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Clerodendrum tomentellum Hutch. &

Dalziel — Endemic

J. Young 205a, 1922 (K, type)

Total: 24; Bauchi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 18.

Clerodendrum umbellatum Poir.

Savory, H.J. & Keay R.W.J. 25269, 31.12.1948 (FHI, K)

Total: 63; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 5, Bauchi 1, Cross River 13, Delta 2, Enugu 2, Kogi 3, Ogun 8, Ondo 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 18.

Clerodendrum volubile P.Beauv.

[E01126798]

Total: 102; Abia 3, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 3, Benue 2, Borno 1, Cross River 5, Ebonyi 1, Edo 15, Enugu 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 5, Niger 1, Ogun 5, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 30, Plateau 2, Rivers 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6.

Clerodendrum welwitschii Gürke

Talbot, P.A. (Mr.); Talbot, P.A. (Mrs.); 3033; 1912-01-01 [K004112237]

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.

Clinopodium robustum (Hook.f.) Ryding

Nepeta robusta Hook.f.

Gbile ZO; Daramola BO; 1970-04-05
[WAG.1656166]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Clinopodium uhligii (Gürke) Ryding

Satureja uhligii Gürke

Total: 5; Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Clinopodium uhligii var. *obtusifolium*
(Avetta) Ryding

Calamintha simensis var. obtusifolia Avetta

Chapman, J.D.; 3381; 1974-11-02 [K005907244]

Total: 5; Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Coleus alpinus Vatke

Literature

Total: 0.

Coleus barbatus (Andrews) Benth. ex

G.Don — Introduced

Plectranthus barbatus var. barbatus

Literature

Total: 0.

Coleus bojeri Benth.

Hepper F.N. [BR0000016453593]

Total: 7; Benue 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Coleus caillei A.Chev. ex Hutch. & Dalziel

Hepper, N.K. [K.1236.0]

Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 6.

Coleus conglomeratus (T.C.E.Fr.) Robyns &
Lebrun

Englerastrum conglomeratum T.C.E.Fr.

Ekwuono; Osanyinlusi; Okoro [EOO127]

[K005569641]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Coleus decurrens Gürke

Literature

Total: 0.

Coleus engleri (Briq.) A.J.Paton

Anisochilus engleri Briq.

Meikle R.D. [BR0000016649927]

Total: 16; Cross River 1, Niger 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 3.

Coleus esculentus (N.E.Br.) G.Taylor

Plectranthus esculentus N.E.Br.

Chapman JD; 1973-01-30 [WAG.1715645]

Total: 6; Plateau 4.

Coleus gracillimus (T.C.E.Fr.) Robyns &
Lebrun

Englerastrum gracillimum T.C.E.Fr.

Barter, C. [K000431860]

Total: 12; Kaduna 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3,
Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Coleus guerkei (Briq.) A.J.Paton

Plectranthus guerkei Briq.

Hepper F.N. [BR0000017059510]

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Coleus humulopsis (B.J.Pollard) A.J.Paton

Plectranthus humulopsis B.J.Pollard

Meikle R.D. [BR0000016046320]

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Ondo 2, Oyo
1, Plateau 1.

Coleus kirkii (Baker) A.J.Paton

Pycnostachys kirkii Baker

Hepper, F.N. 1600; 1957-12-16 [K004875946]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1.

Coleus mannii Hook.f.

Literature

Total: 0.

Coleus meyeri (Gürke) A.J.Paton

Pycnostachys meyeri Gürke

Wit P; Gbile ZO; Daramola BO; 1972-05-11

[WAG.1711527]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1,
Taraba 2.

Coleus monostachyus (P.Beauv.) A.J.Paton

Ocimum monostachyum P.Beauv.

Meikle, R.D. [K.11407.0]

Total: 102; Abia 2, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 1, Ekiti 1,
Kaduna 2, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 4, Lagos 12,
Niger 6, Ogun 7, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 18, Plateau 7,
Rivers 2, Taraba 4.

Coleus monostachyus subsp. *marrubiiifolius*
(Brenan) A.J.Paton

Solenostemon monostachyus var. marrubiiifolius

Brenan

Keay, R.W.J.; 1954-09-21 [K.17449.0]

Total: 6; Ekiti 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Coleus monostachyus subsp. *monostachyus*

Ocimum monostachyum P.Beauv.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000017670821]

Total: 36; Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 2,
Lagos 4, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 2.

Coleus monostachyus subsp. *perennis*

(J.K.Morton) A.J.Paton

Solenostemon monostachyus subsp. perennis

J.K.Morton

Summerhayes, G.V.; 11; 1954-07-28 [K005568163]

Total: 9; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Katsina 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Coleus nigericus (Alston) A.J.Paton

Englerastrum nigericum Alston

Lely H.V.; 1930-09-01 [FHI.12322.0]

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Kaduna 3, Taraba 1.

Coleus repens Gürke

Onochie, C.F.; Jones, A.P.D. FHI18904; 1946-05-26 [K005568298]

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Niger 1.

Coleus reticulatus A.Chev.

1972-04-22 [1152621.0]

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1.

Coleus rhodesianum (N.E.Br.) A.J.Paton

Englerastrum rhodesianum N.E.Br.

Charter J.R.; 1955-10-11 [FHI.35212.0]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Plateau 2.

Coleus rhodesianus (N.E.Br.) A.J.Paton

Sharland 882; 1979-10-01 [K005568281]

Total: 10; Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Coleus rotundifolius (Poir.) A.Chev. & Perrot

Germanea rotundifolia Poir.

Barter, C.; 1858-01-01 [P00450779]

Total: 8; Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Coleus scutellarioides (L.) Benth. —

Introduced

Ocimum scutellarioides L.

KESHIRO WADUDAT; 2013-6-14

[5817]3808441257

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Coleus sylvestris (Gürke) A.J.Paton & Phillipson

Plectranthus sylvestris Gürke

Chapman, J.D. 3379; 1974-11-02 [K005569650]

Total: 2; Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Coleus tenuicaulis Hook.f.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-09-26 [WAG.1712465]

Total: 1.

Equilabium glandulosum (Hook.f.) Mwany. & A.J.Paton

Plectranthus glandulosus Hook.f.

DR. A.B. KADIRI AND OTHERS; 2008-12-01

[LUH.1476.0]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Equilabium kamerunense (Gürke) Mwany. & A.J.Paton

Plectranthus kamerunensis Gürke

Literature

Total: 0.

Gmelina arborea Roxb. ex Sm. —

Introduced

Pilz, GE 1899; 1976-12-29 [WAG.1717883]

Total: 16; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Haumaniastrum alboviride (Hutch.)

P.A.Duvign. & Plancke

Acrocephalus alboviridis Hutch.

Lely, H.V.; 1921-07-19 [K000347265]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 1.

Haumaniastrum buettneri (Gürke)

J.K.Morton

Acrocephalus buettneri Gürke

Daramola, B.O. FHI62416 [K005417285]

Total: 1; Benue 1.

Haumaniastrum caeruleum (Oliv.)

P.A.Duvign. & Plancke

Acrocephalus caeruleus Oliv.

Olorunfemi J. [BR0000016530034]

Total: 72; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 12, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 8, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 9, Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Haumaniastrum villosum (Benth.) A.J.Paton

Acrocephalus villosus Benth.

Dent Young, J.; 208; 1922-01-01 [K005417443]

Total: 12; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Holmskioldia sanguinea Retz. — Introduced

; 1969-10-6 [2252242317]

Total: 2; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Hoslundia opposita Vahl

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000016634381]

Total: 67; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Lagos 9, Niger 5, Ogun 3, Osun 5, Oyo 18, Plateau 2, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Hyptis brevipes Poit. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Hyptis capitata Jacq. — Introduced

Barter, C 1284; -- [U.1353404]

Total: 1.

Hyptis lanceolata Poir. — Introduced

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86224; 1979-2-7 [WAG.1717380]

Total: 56; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 3, Cross River 7, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 6, Ondo 1, Oyo 5, Rivers 2.

Isodon ramosissimus (Hook.f.) Codd

Plectranthus ramosissimus Hook.f.

Hepper FN; 1957-01-01 [WAG.1717201]

Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Nasarawa 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Lavandula coronopifolia Poir.

Newby, J.E. ZP92; 1979-03-30 [K005571692]

Total: 3; Niger 3.

Leonotis nepetifolia (L.) R.Br.

Phlomis nepetifolia L.

Usang felix; 2005-10-10 [LUH.140.0]

Total: 34; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 3, Cross River 3, Kaduna 3, Kogi 3, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Plateau 3.

Leonotis nepetifolia var. *africana* (P.Beauv.)

J.K.Morton

Phlomis africana P.Beauv.

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-09-26 [WAG.1714305]

Total: 24; Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Plateau 3.

Leonotis nepetifolia var. *nepetifolia*

Phlomis nepetifolia L.

Latilo MG; Oguntayo ST; 1973-02-25

[WAG.1714276]

Total: 2; Kogi 2.

Leucas deflexa Hook.f.

DR. A.B. KADIRI AND OTHERS

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3808439789>

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Leucas martinicensis (Jacq.) R.Br.

Clinopodium martinicense Jacq.

Leeuw PN de; 1963-12-06 [WAG.1713728]

Total: 43; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 8, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Yobe 1.

Leucas oligocephala Hook.f.

Hepper F.N. [BR0000016569898]

Total: 26; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 12, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Leucas oligocephala var. *bowalensis*

(A.Chev.) Sebald

Daramola BO; Okoro M; 1982-11-01

[WAG.1713657]

Total: 4; Ondo 1, Plateau 2.

Leucas oligocephala var. *oligocephala*

Hepper F.N.; 1957-10-14 [BR0000006250072]

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Plateau 7.

Leucas songeana Sebald

Literature

Total: 0.

Mesosphaerum suaveolens (L.) Kuntze —

Introduced

Ballota suaveolens L.

Bels L. [BR0000016648654]

Total: 73; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 10, Kano 5, Kogi 8, Kwara 1, Lagos 8, Ogun 3, Ondo 4, Osun 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 4, Yobe 1.

Micromeria imbricata (Forssk.) C.Chr.

Thymus imbricatus Forssk.

Tuley, P.; Jackson, J.K.; Magaji, S.O.; 1989; 1969-11-19 [K005423449]

Total: 13; Adamawa 2, Kwara 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 8.

Micromeria imbricata var. *imbricata*

Thymus imbricatus Forssk.

DR. A.B. KADIRI AND OTHERS; 2008-12-01 [LUH.1480.0]

Total: 1.

Ocimum americanum L.

MacDonald, K.P. B1/39. 23.1.1939 (K)

Total: 38; Borno 8, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Ocimum basilicum L. — Introduced

Eijnatten CLM van; 1966-05-17 [WAG.1710645]

Total: 14; Anambra 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 6, Oyo 5.

Ocimum gratissimum L.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000016583726]

Total: 66; Anambra 2, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Lagos 21, Ogun 13, Ondo 2, Osun 4, Oyo 8, Plateau 3, Taraba 6.

Ocimum gratissimum subsp. *gratissimum*

Sharland 870, 9.1939 (K)

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Ocimum gratissimum subsp. *macrophyllum*

Briq.

Chapman, H.M. 40, 1.8.1973 (K)

Total: 1.

Ocimum obovatum E.Mey. ex Benth.

Olorunfemi, J. 55766, 8.4.1965 (FHI, K)

Total: 41; Bauchi 5, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Plateau 10, Taraba 4.

Ocimum obovatum var. *obovatum*

Total: 41; Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Plateau 10, Taraba 4.

Orthosiphon rubicundus (D.Don) Benth. — Introduced

Plectranthus rubicundus D.Don

Morton, JK K 419; 1955-4-18 [WAG.1699877]

Total: 4; Bauchi 2, Niger 2.

Orthosiphon schimperi Benth.

Lely, H.V.; 186; 1921-05-17 [K005204524]

Total: 21; Benue 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 3, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Plateau 3.

Orthosiphon thymiflorus (Roth) Sleesen

Ocimum thymiflorum Roth

Foster, E.W.; 348; 1907-10-04 [K005204564]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1.

Otostegia hildebrandtii (Vatke & Kurtz)

Sebald — Introduced

Ballota hildebrandtii Vatke & Kurtz

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/1948981329>

Total: 1.

Platostoma africanum P.Beauv.

Kennedy J.D. [BR0000017150248]

Total: 66; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Cross River 10, Delta 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 4, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Platostoma gabonense A.J.Paton

Barter [K000467462]

Total: 4; Anambra 2, Edo 2.

Platostoma rotundifolium (Briq.) A.J.Paton

Geniosporum rotundifolium Briq.

D. Tuley [BR0000017154192]

Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Premna angolensis Gürke

[FHI.94763.0]

Total: 9; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3.

Premna milnei Baker

Literature

Total: 0.

Premna quadrifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Onochie C.F.A.; 1945-05-13 [FHI.8222.0]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Oyo 2.

Premna serratifolia L. — Introduced

Olorunfemi J.; 1968-8-19 [58746]1990430868

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Rotheca alata (Gürke) Verdc.

Clerodendrum alatum Gürke

Lely, H.; 1921-08-23 [K000192842]

Total: 14; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Rotheca microphylla (Blume) Callm. &

Phillipson — Introduced

Adelosa microphylla Blume

Charter J.R.; Onweloze B.S.K.; 1964-9-19

[54600]1990430577

Total: 2; Oyo 1.

Rotheca violacea (Gürke) Verdc.

Clerodendrum violaceum Gürke

J. T. Baldwin; 1948-05-04 [US 2070210]

Total: 16; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 1, Cross River 2, Edo 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Rotheca violacea subsp. *violacea*

Clerodendrum violaceum Gürke

Onochie CFA; 1958-03-28 [WAG.1699151]

Total: 3; Edo 1.

Salvia coccinea Buc'hoz ex Etl. —

Introduced

A. P. Jones FHI13873; -- [US 1993651]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Salvia splendens Sellow ex Nees —

Introduced

; -- [11802]2821315860

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Scutellaria schweinfurthii Briq.

Literature

Total: 0.

Scutellaria schweinfurthii subsp. *paucifolia*

(Baker) A.J.Paton

Lely, H.V.; P245; 1929-04-01 [K006041446]

Total: 2.

Scutellaria violacea B.Heyne ex Benth. —

Introduced

Chapman, J.D. 3513; 1974-11-14 [K006041447]

Total: 1; Sokoto 1.

Scutellaria violascens Gürke

Literature

Total: 0.

Stachys aculeolata Hook.f.

Lowe, J. 2721 [K006345777]

Total: 2; Borno 1, Cross River 1.

Stachys aculeolata var. *aculeolata*

Stachys pseudohumifusa Sebsebe

Literature

Total: 0.

Stachys pseudohumifusa subsp. *saxeri*

Y.B.Harv.

Literature

Total: 0.

Stachys pyramidalis J.K.Morton — Endemic

Literature

Total: 0.

Syncolostemon bracteosus (Benth.)

D.F.Otieno

Ocimum bracteosum Benth.

Albert Ernest Kitson; 1908-01-01 [BM000606128]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Syncolostemon welwitschii (Rolfe)

D.F.Otieno

Orthosiphon welwitschii Rolfe

Gbile ZO; Daramola BO; 1970-03-31

[WAG.1714952]

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Taraba 2.

Tectona grandis L.f. — Introduced

Amewobi Elizabeth [LUH7049]

Total: 21; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 2, Oyo 6.

Tinnea aethiopica Kotschy ex Hook.f.

Meikle, R.D. [K.2786.0]

Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Kaduna 4, Ogun 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Tinnea aethiopica subsp. *aethiopica*

Meikle R.D. [BR0000017729956]

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Kaduna 3, Ogun 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Tinnea barteri Gürke

Geerling C. [BR0000017731577]

Total: 35; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 4, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kebbi 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Niger 10, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Vitex agnus-castus L. — Introduced

; -- [E01121311]3702737488

Total: 9; Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 6.

Vitex bogalensis Wernham — Endemic

Yola, s.d., Dalziel 115 (P)

Total: 4; Adamawa 3.

Vitex bojeri Schauer — Introduced

Gentry 32668; 1981-6-14 [446817]1261149933

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Vitex chrysocarpa Planch.

Barter C [WAG.U.1762487]

Total: 27; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Niger 7, Ogun 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Rivers 1.

Vitex doniana Sweet

Vitex umbrosa G.Don ex Sabine

Unknown [WAG.L.1066023]

Total: 190; Adamawa 5, Anambra 4, Bauchi 7, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 10, Kaduna 16, Kano 6, Kebbi 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 6, Lagos 8, Niger 20, Ogun 11, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 25, Plateau 15, Rivers 3, Sokoto 5, Taraba 13, Yobe 1, Zamfara 4.

Vitex ferruginea Schumach. & Thonn.

[E01121323]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Delta 1, Edo 2, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 2.

Vitex grandifolia Gürke

Barter, C. [P00486886]

Total: 71; Benue 1, Cross River 15, Delta 5, Edo 10, Lagos 13, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Rivers 1.

Vitex madiensis Oliv.

Daramola BO; 1969-06-04 [WAG.1701181]

Total: 24; Bauchi 3, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Vitex madiensis subsp. *madiensis*

Barter [K000192748]

Total: 1.

Vitex oxycuspis Baker

Mann 2243, February 1863, (holotype: K [barcode K000192745])

Total: 25; Abia 1, Benue 1, Cross River 19, Edo 1, Ogun 1.

Vitex rivularis Gürke

Kennedy D.P.; 1929-10-01 [FHI.10891.0]

Total: 12; Cross River 1, Edo 3, Niger 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Taraba 1.

Vitex thyrsoflora Baker

Rowland s.n., 1893, (Lectotype: K [barcode K000192742]!)

Total: 45; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 10, Osun 1, Oyo 8, Plateau 1.

OROBANCHACEAE

Alectra basserei Berhaut

Literature

Total: 0.

Alectra capensis Thunb. — Introduced

Geerling C. 3025; 1970-10-22 [39380]1990429387

Total: 5; Benue 1, Plateau 2.

Alectra linearis Hepper

Jones, A.P.D. 6142; 1942-5-8 [K000405228]

Total: 4; Anambra 3.

Alectra sessiliflora (Vahl) Kuntze

Gerardia sessiliflora Vahl

Eijnatten, CLM van 2015; 1966-9-22 [WAG.1355284]

Total: 54; Adamawa 3, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Cross River 6, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Kebbi 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 3, Taraba 15.

Alectra virgata Hemsl.

Millson, A. s.n.; 1894-4-23 [K000405227]

Total: 3; Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Alectra vogelii Benth.

; 1995-9-30 [FR-0021025]

Total: 16; Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Buchnera capitata Burm.f.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63219; 1970-3-28 [WAG.1356174]

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Buchnera decandollei Govaerts

Buchnera capitata Benth.

Hepper F.N. 1355; 1957-11-14 [BR0000019042343]

Total: 40; Adamawa 2, Benue 3, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Niger 1, Ondo 5, Plateau 4, Taraba 20.

Buchnera hispida Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don

Okonkwo, SNC s.n.; 1972-1-1 [WAG.1356304]

Total: 61; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 4, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Enugu 3, Gombe 5, Kaduna 14, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 2, Yobe 2, Zamfara 2.

Buchnera leptostachya Benth.

Hepper F.N. 3886; 1969-11-12 [BR0000019049014]

Total: 26; Adamawa 2, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 1, Kogi 2, Niger 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 3, Taraba 5.

Cycnium adonense E.Mey. ex Benth.

Eimunjeze, VE; Adebusuyi, JK; Macauley, S FHI 66545; 1973-5-21 [WAG.1469325]

Total: 71; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Edo 3, Kaduna 4, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 18, Plateau 9, Taraba 8, Zamfara 1.

Cycnium petunioides Hutch.

McClintock, A. (Miss); 214; 1955-02-10 [K004142374]

Total: 4; Plateau 2.

Cycnium tubulosum subsp. *tubulosum*

Gerardia tubulosa L.f.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 62856; 1970-3-31 [WAG.1469477]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Hedbergia abyssinica (Hochst. ex Benth.)

Molau

Bartsia abyssinica Hochst. ex Benth.

Hepper F.N. 1661; 1958-1-13 [BR0000018031256]

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 3, Taraba 2.

Micrargeria barteri Skan

Keay, R.W.J. FHI22275; 1947-11-08 [K004179731]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Oyo 2.

Micrargeria filiformis (Schumach. & Thonn.) Hutch. & Dalziel

Gerardia filiformis Schumach. & Thonn.

Latilo, MG; Fagbemi, A FHI 67260; 1973-11-20 [WAG.1184024]

Total: 42; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 4, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 6, Kebbi 1, Kwara 4, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1.

Rhamphicarpa fistulosa (Hochst.) Benth.

Macrosiphon fistulosus Hochst.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1137; 1972-4-25 [WAG.1835245]

Total: 51; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Borno 5, Cross River 1, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 8, Katsina 2, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Sopubia mannii Skan

Jackson J.K.; Magaji S.O.; Tuley P.2005; 1969-11-19 [33109] [2013041324]

Total: 5; Taraba 4.

Sopubia mannii var. *mannii*

Chapman, JD 2616; 1971-11-24 [WAG.1841790]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Sopubia parviflora Engl.

Geerling C.4328; 1971-10-7 [31369] [2013041165]

Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 4.

Sopubia ramosa (Hochst.) Hochst.

Raphidophyllum ramosum Hochst.

Latilo, MG FHI 64764; 1972-9-18 [WAG.1841421]

Total: 44; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 3, Katsina 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 3, Nasarawa 4, Niger 9, Ogun 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 6, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Sopubia simplex (Hochst.) Hochst.

Raphidophyllum simplex Hochst.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1331; 1972-4-20 [WAG.1841952]

Total: 55; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Kaduna 6, Kogi 4, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 10, Taraba 11.

Striga asiatica (L.) Kuntze

Buchnera asiatica L.

Geerling, C 4152; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1841235]

Total: 93; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 3, Adamawa 2, Anambra 5, Bauchi 8, Benue 1, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 8, Imo 2, Kaduna 6, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 13, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Striga aspera (Willd.) Benth.

Euphrasia aspera Willd.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2031; 1966-9-23 [WAG.1841197]

Total: 54; Anambra 1, Bauchi 4, Bayelsa 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 12, Oyo 1, Plateau 9, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Striga baumannii Engl.

Dalziel J.M. 709; 1912-- [BR0000018139945]

Total: 11; Adamawa 2, Benue 2, Kogi 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Striga bilabiata (Thunb.) Kuntze

Buchnera bilabiata Thunb.

Rowland; s.n.; 1893-01-01 [K000379798]

Total: 33; Bauchi 2, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 6, Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Striga bilabiata subsp. *barteri* (Engl.)

Hepper

Striga barteri Engl.

Barker 1170; -- [K000379799]

Total: 6; Kogi 1.

Striga bilabiata subsp. *rowlandii* (Engl.)

Hepper

Striga rowlandii Engl.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3796; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1841171]

Total: 25; Bauchi 2, Ekiti 2, Kaduna 6, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 2.

Striga brachycalyx Skan

Barter, C. s.n.; -- [K000379795]

Total: 13; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 4, Kwara 2.

Striga dalzielii Hutch.

Dalziel, J.M. 168; 1906-10-26 [K000379803]

Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Striga forbesii Benth.

[Omandinjo] FHI24005; 1948-8-9

[BR0000018144475]

Total: 19; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Niger 3, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Striga gesnerioides (Willd.) Vatke

Buchnera gesnerioides Willd.

Gbile, ZO 500; 1971-9-14 [WAG.1841088]

Total: 14; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Delta 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Striga hermonthica (Delile) Benth.

Buchnera hermonthica Delile

Croat, TB 53417; 1981-11-14 [WAG.1840996]

Total: 59; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 7, Delta 1, Edo 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 9, Kano 2, Kebbi 3, Kwara 4, Lagos 1, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 5, Yobe 3, Zamfara 1.

Striga klingii (Engl.) Skan

Buchnera klingii Engl.

Geerling, C 3025; 1970-10-22 [WAG.1840952]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Nasarawa 1.

Striga linearifolia (Schumach. & Thonn.)

Hepper

Buchnera linearifolia Schumach. & Thonn.

Keay, R.W.J.; FHI22864; 1948-05-16 [K004127424]

Total: 7; Katsina 1, Niger 2, Oyo 1.

Striga macrantha (Benth.) Benth.

Buchnera macrantha Benth.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO Z 45; 1974-11-23

[WAG.1837331]

Total: 31; Abia 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 2.

Striga passargei Engl.

Geerling, C 4099; 1971-8-20 [WAG.1837350]
Total: 14; Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 1,
Plateau 1.

Striga primuloides A.Chev.

Literature

Total: 0.

LENTIBULARIACEAE

Genlisea hispidula Stapf

Chapman, H.M. 21 [K004658426]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Genlisea stapfii A.Chev.

Literature

Total: 0.

Utricularia andongensis Welw. ex Hiern

Lawlor 429; 1962-8-16 [101093117] 2268987263

Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Imo 1, Kwara 2,
Osun 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 1.

Utricularia arenaria A.DC.

Lawlor 485; 1962-8-21 [101093107] 2268987744

Total: 24; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Lagos 2,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 4.

Utricularia benjaminiana Oliv.

Akenra inflata Benj.

Onochie34314; 1954-9-7 [4817] [912048093]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Edo 10, Rivers 3.

Utricularia firmula Welw. ex Oliv.

Meikle, R.D.1022; 1950-1-14 [12994] [912008194]

Total: 10; Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau
1.

Utricularia foliosa L.

Vaillant, A.; 2784; 1962-11-16 [K004656318]

Total: 3; Akwa Ibom 1, Kebbi 1.

Utricularia foveolata Edgew.

Stanfield122; 1957-9-18 [1141] [912006393]

Total: 4; Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Utricularia gibba L.

Brenan J.P.M. & Jones E.W. 8598; 1948-1-11

[BR0000017402699]

Total: 43; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 1,
Cross River 1, Edo 13, Kaduna 1, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1,
Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 6, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Utricularia inflexa Forssk.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2115; 1966-9-14 [WAG.1055371]

Total: 29; Abia 2, Borno 2, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1,
Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 4, Rivers 1.

Utricularia mannii Oliv.

Meer, PPC van 1788; 1971-5-24 [WAG.1055419]

Total: 5; Cross River 3, Taraba 2.

Utricularia micropetala Sm.

Stanfield, D.P.FH1.54924; 1964-8-23 [27387]

[912024444]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Oyo 2.

Utricularia odontosepala Stapf —

Introduced

Hugh Vandervaes Lely, Lely 636; 1930-8-

[101094429] [2268986100]

Total: 1.

Utricularia pubescens Sm.

Dalziel, J.M. 731; 1912-11-4 [K000430219]

Total: 15; Kaduna 2, Niger 3, Ondo 5.

Utricularia raynalii P.Taylor

McClintock, A. (Miss) 107 [K004656482]

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Utricularia reflexa Oliv.

Barter s.n.; -- [K000430205]

Total: 23; Borno 1, Edo 7, Kaduna 3, Kwara 1, Lagos
4, Niger 3.

Utricularia rigida Benj.

Hepper, FN 102 a; 1957-10-15 [WAG.1055533]

Total: 16; Bauchi 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Plateau 9.

Utricularia scandens Benj.

Literature

Total: 0.

Utricularia stanfieldii P.Taylor

Stanfield, D.P. 121; 1957-9-24 [K000430210]

Total: 10; Ogun 1, Ondo 6, Oyo 2.

Utricularia stellaris L.f.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3807; 1971-7-27 [WAG.1055596]

Total: 8; Borno 1, Edo 2, Niger 1, Osun 2, Oyo 1.

Utricularia striatula Sm.

Richards P.W. 9253; -- [BR0000017408110]

Total: 6; Abia 3, Plateau 2.

Utricularia subulata L.

Geerling, C 4304; 1971-10-5 [WAG.1055624]

Total: 29; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra
1, Benue 1, Edo 6, Kaduna 1, Katsina 1, Niger 6,
Ondo 5, Oyo 3, Plateau 1.

Utricularia tetraloba P.Taylor

N.N. SanfordSanford 6743; 1971-3-18 [101096294]

[2268989618]

Total: 1.

Utricularia tortilis Welw. ex Oliv.

Meikle, R.D.1092; 1950-1-21 [3902] [912038178]

Total: 2; Niger 2.

ACANTHACEAE

Acanthopale decempedalis C.B.Clarke

Stone, R.H. 65 27 Aug. 1955; K

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Acanthus guineensis Heine & P.Taylor

Chapman, J.D. 3954 25 Nov. 1975; K

Total: 2; Cross River 1, Taraba 1.

Acanthus montanus (Nees) T.Anderson

Cheilopsis montana Nees

Adekunle, A.O. in FHI 24244 20 Nov. 1948; FHI, K

Total: 67; Abia 1, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Cross River 3, Edo 8, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 8, Oyo 3, Plateau 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 4.

Afrofittonia silvestris Lindau

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 45809 23 Feb. 1962; FHI, K

Total: 16; Abia 1, Cross River 14.

Andrographis paniculata (Burm.f.) Wall. ex

Nees — Introduced

Justicia paniculata Burm.f.

ABAYOMI AJAYI 6904 30 Apr. 2012; LUH

Total: 7; Lagos 1, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Anisostachya tenella (Nees) Lindau

Rostellularia tenella Nees

Daramola, B.O. in FHI 72323 5 Oct. 1973; FHI, K

Total: 4; Edo 2, Niger 1.

Ascotheca paucinervia (T.Anderson ex

C.B.Clarke) Heine

Justicia paucinervia T.Anderson ex C.B.Clarke

Percy Amaury Talbot; 1912-01-01 [BM000799847]

Total: 5; Cross River 2.

Ascotheca paucinervia var. *paucinervia*

Justicia paucinervia T.Anderson ex C.B.Clarke

Onochie, C.F.A. & Olorunfemi, J. in FHI 36124 23

Jan. 1957; FHI, K

Total: 1.

Asystasia buettneri Lindau

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25528 31 Oct. 1949; FHI, K

Total: 28; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

Asystasia gangetica (L.) T.Anderson

Justicia gangetica L.

Chapman, JD 2548; 1971-09-26 [WAG.1738756]

Total: 217; Abia 5, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 4, Bauchi 1, Benue 3, Borno 1, Cross River 39, Delta 4, Edo 20, Ekiti 2, Enugu 8, Imo 2, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 7, Kwara 4, Lagos 8, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 9, Oyo 35, Plateau 15, Rivers 2, Taraba 13.

Asystasia gangetica subsp. *micrantha*

(Nees) Ensermu

Asystasia coromandeliana var. *micrantha* Nees

Oladoyinbo, A. in FHI 24264 24 Sep. 1948; FHI, K

Total: 1; Rivers 1.

Asystasia glandulifera Lindau

Hepper, F.N. 1585 12 Dec. 1957; K

Total: 1.

Asystasia intrusa (Forssk.) Blume

Ruellia intrusa Forssk.

Oladoyinbo, A. in FHI 24264 24 Sep. 1948; FHI, K

Total: 8; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Asystasia leptostachya Lindau

Talbot, P.A. 380 1911; K

Total: 4; Cross River 2.

Asystasia macrophylla (T.Anderson)

G.Nicholson

Dicentranthera macrophylla T.Anderson

Latilo, M.G. & Oguntayo in FHI 67758 28 Feb. 1973; FHI, K

Total: 26; Abia 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 14, Lagos 1.

Asystasia vogeliana Benth.

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 33669 3 Dec. 1953; FHI, K

Total: 117; Abia 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 1, Cross River 22, Delta 1, Edo 12, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 3, Niger 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 9, Osun 11, Oyo 15, Plateau 1, Taraba 12.

Asystasia vogeliana subsp. *infudibuliformis*

I.Darbysh. & A.Bello ined. — Endemic

Medler, J. 971 27 Sep. 1973; IFE, K

Total: 1.

Avicennia germinans (L.) L.

Bontia germinans L.

Miller, R.G. in FHI 43297 22 Dec. 1962; FHI, K

Total: 32; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bayelsa 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 17, Niger 1, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Barleria bornuensis S.Moore

McElderry, J.C.K. in FHI 16372 25 Jun. 1946; FHI, K

Total: 8; Borno 1, Katsina 3, Niger 1, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Barleria brownii S.Moore

Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 5235 10 Dec. 1957; FHI, K
Total: 8; Cross River 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 1.

Barleria candida Nees — Introduced

DP 153; 1958-10-14 [43144] 1990429715
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 2, Oyo 1.

Barleria cristata L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1068; 1966-1-20 [WAG.1358503]
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Barleria eranthemoides R.Br. ex C.B.Clarke

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28030 30 Aug. 1950; FHI, K
Total: 5; Adamawa 3, Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Barleria eranthemoides var. *eranthemoides*

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28030 30 Aug. 1950; FHI, K
Total: 1.

Barleria lupulina Lindl. — Introduced

Wit P. 531; 1971-10-3 [64376] 1990431278
Total: 4; Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Barleria oenotheroides Dum.Cours.

Jones, A.P.D. & Onochie, C.F. in FHI 14726 9 Feb. 1946; FHI, K
Total: 6; Niger 3, Ogun 1, Osun 1.

Barleria opaca (Vahl) Nees

Justicia opaca Vahl

Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 34948 10 Nov. 1955; FHI, K
Total: 49; Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 4, Niger 1, Ogun 8, Osun 3, Oyo 23, Taraba 2.

Barleria ruellioides T.Anderson

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 37306 31 Dec. 1957; FHI, K
Total: 28; Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Ekiti 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Barleria villosa S.Moore

Batten-Poole, W.H. 206 1946; K
Total: 28; Abia 1, Adamawa 5, Bauchi 4, Cross River 1, Kano 1, Niger 1, Ondo 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Blepharis glumacea S.Moore

Olorunfemi, J. in FHI 24398 29 Sep. 1948; FHI, K
Total: 9; Kaduna 2, Niger 4, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Blepharis linariifolia Pers.

Chapman, J.D. 3216 in FHI 62110 14 Sep. 1973; FHI, K

Total: 29; Adamawa 7, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kano 1, Niger 4, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Blepharis maderaspatensis (L.) B.Heyne ex Roth

Acanthus maderaspatensis L.

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 5474 18 Oct. 1947; FHI, K
Total: 54; Bauchi 1, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 9, Ondo 2, Oyo 13, Sokoto 2, Taraba 1, Yobe 1, Zamfara 1.

Brachystephanus africanus S.Moore

Chapman, J.D. 3294 without date; K
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Brachystephanus africanus var. *africanus*

Chapman, J.D. 3294 without date; K
Total: 1.

Brachystephanus giganteus Champl.

Johnstone, A.T. s.n. [K000518784]
Total: 1.

Brachystephanus jaundensis Lindau

Sanford, M.M. 6366 18 Aug. 1968; FHI, IFE, K
Total: 3.

Brachystephanus jaundensis subsp.

jaundensis

Sanford, M.M. 6366 18 Aug. 1968; FHI, IFE, K
Total: 2.

Brachystephanus longiflorus Lindau

van Mer, P.P.C. 1741 22 May 1971; K, WAG
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Brillantaisia lamium (Nees) Benth.

Leucorhaphis lamium Nees

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 67539 20 Sep. 1973; FHI, K
Total: 90; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross River 11, Delta 1, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 1, Niger 11, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Plateau 4, Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Brillantaisia lancifolia Lindau

Talbot, P.A. 1270 1911–1912; K
Total: 5; Niger 2.

Brillantaisia owariensis P.Beauv.

Daramola, B.O. & Emwiogbon, J.A. in FHI 32774 8 Jan. 1961; FHI, K
Total: 83; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 8, Cross River 8, Edo 11, Kaduna 3, Kebbi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 12, Taraba 5.

Brillantaisia vogeliana (Nees) Benth.

Leucorhaphis vogeliana Nees
Binuyo, A. in FHI 45407 18 Nov. 1961; FHI, K
Total: 10; Taraba 1.

Champluviera populifolia (C.B.Clarke)
I.Darbysh. & T.F.Daniel
Schaueria populifolia C.B.Clarke
Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28157 7 Dec. 1950; FHI, K
Total: 11; Cross River 10.

Chlamydocardia buettneri Lindau
Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28278 17 Dec. 1950; FHI, K
Total: 9; Cross River 4, Edo 1, Ondo 2.

Crossandra flava Hook.
Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 34349 10 Nov. 1954; FHI, K
Total: 12; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1,
Ondo 2, Osun 1.

Crossandra obanensis Heine
Richards, P.W. 5190 15 Mar. 1955; K
Total: 2; Abia 1.

Crossandrella dusenii (Lindau) S.Moore
Pseudoblepharis dusenii Lindau
Talbot, P.A. 1269 1911–1912; K
Total: 3.

Cryptacanthus virens (Nees) I.Darbysh. &
Kiel
Leptostachya virens Nees
Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 19749 21 Feb. 1953; FHI, K
Total: 1.

Dicliptera adusta Lindau
Keay, R.W.J. & Jones, E.W. in FHI 37623 12 Apr.
1958; FHI, K
Total: 11; Kaduna 3, Niger 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2.

Dicliptera elliotii C.B.Clarke
; 1988-01-01 [Ogundipe, 1888, (K)]
Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 1,
Ogun 1.

Dicliptera hyalina Nees
Thomas, N.W. 1394 1911; K
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 1, Niger 1.

Dicliptera laxata C.B.Clarke
Daramola, B.O. in FHI 62454 30 Nov. 1968; FHI, K
Total: 6; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Taraba 3.

Dicliptera laxispica Lindau
Talbot, P.A.s.n. 1911–1912; K
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Dicliptera obanensis S.Moore
Daramola, B.O. in FHI 55529 19 Feb. 1965; FHI, K
Total: 7; Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Dicliptera paniculata (Forssk.) I.Darbysh.
Dianthera paniculata Forssk.
Meikle, R.D. 843 16 Dec. 1949; K
Total: 36; Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 2, Borno 9, Edo 1,
Gombe 3, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Katsina 1, Niger 5, Oyo
1, Taraba 1, Yobe 2.

Dicliptera pumila (Lindau) Dandy ex
Brenan — Introduced
Duvernoia pumila Lindau
Lely 712; -- [K000378952]
Total: 3; Kebbi 1, Niger 1.

Dicliptera sp. aff. *elliotii* C.B.Clarke
Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25165 26 Dec.
1948; FHI, K
Total: 1.

Dicliptera sp. nov. aff. *welwitschii* S.Moore
Sharland, R.E. 1097 Jan. 1980; K
Total: 1.

Dicliptera verticillata (Forssk.) C.Chr.
Dianthera verticillata Forssk.
Daramola, B.O. in FHI 61586 30 Dec. 1968; FHI, K
Total: 10; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Niger
1, Oyo 2.

Dischistocalyx hirsutus C.B.Clarke
Mann, G. ; 1862-- [P00350161]
Total: 1.

Dischistocalyx obanensis S.Moore
Talbot, P.A. 1485 1912; K
Total: 4; Cross River 4.

Dischistocalyx thunbergiiflora (T.Anderson)
T.Anderson ex B.D.Jacks.
Ruellia thunbergiiflora T.Anderson
Latilo, M.G. in FHI 30941 6 May 1952; FHI, K
Total: 8; Cross River 6.

Dyschoriste heudelotiana (Nees) Kuntze
Calophanes heudelotianus Nees
Chapman, J.D. 3633 19 Jan. 1975; K
Total: 12; Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 1,
Ondo 2, Plateau 2.

Dyschoriste nagchana (Nees) Bennet
Dipteracanthus nagchana Nees
Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O. in FHI 73640 22 Nov.
1974; FHI, K
Total: 44; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 1, Borno 1, Cross
River 2, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Kwara 1,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 3, Plateau
4, Taraba 1.

Elytraria acaulis (L.f.) Lindau

Justicia acaulis L.f.
 Barker 1302 without date; K
 Total: 5; Cross River 1, Edo 4.

Elytraria imbricata (Vahl) Pers. —
 Introduced
Justicia imbricata Vahl
 Bels, L 127; 1950-4-16 [U.1046334]
 Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Elytraria marginata Vahl
 Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 15511 24 Apr. 1953; FHI, K
 Total: 38; Abia 1, Cross River 6, Edo 6, Ekiti 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Rivers 1.

Eranthemum pulchellum Andrews —
 Introduced
 ; -- [IFE, 12098, (K)] 3347140668
 Total: 3; Lagos 1.

Eremomastax speciosa (Hochst.) Cufod.
 Paulo-wilhelmia speciosa Hochst.
 Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28226 12 Dec. 1950; FHI, K
 Total: 57; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Cross River 8, Kaduna 8, Kogi 5, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 5.

Graptophyllum glandulosum Turrill
 Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 7708 7 Mar. 1945; FHI, K
 Total: 10; Anambra 1, Cross River 7, Niger 1.

Hygrophila abyssinica (Hochst. ex Nees)
 T.Anderson
Polyechma abyssinicum Hochst. ex Nees
 Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O. in FHI 63215 28 Mar. 1970; FHI, K
 Total: 15; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Hygrophila africana (T.Anderson) Heine
Adenosma africana T.Anderson
 Vaillant, A. 2705 12 Jan. 1962; K
 Total: 4; Niger 4.

Hygrophila borellii (Lindau) Heine
Brillantaisia borellii Lindau
 Latilo, M.G. in FHI 60846 1 Dec. 1966; FHI, K
 Total: 2; Ogun 1.

Hygrophila brevıtuba (Burkill) Heine
Synnema brevıtubum Burkill
 Hepper, F.N. & Daramola, B.O. 1557 7 Dec. 1957; K
 Total: 7; Adamawa 2, Benue 4.

Hygrophila chevalieri Benoist
 Vaillant, A. 2709 26 Feb. 1962; K
 Total: 3; Niger 2.

Hygrophila laevis (Nees) Lindau
Nomaphila laevis Nees
 Wit, P. & Wit, J. 1117 in FHI 64810 18 Jan. 1972; FHI, K
 Total: 8; Katsina 1, Niger 4, Rivers 1.

Hygrophila niokoloensis Berhaut
 Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28122 17 Nov. 1950; FHI, K
 Total: 14; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

Hygrophila pobeguınii Benoist
 Latilo, M.G. in FHI 64720 3 Oct. 1971; FHI, K
 Total: 8; Bauchi 2, Benue 2, Edo 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Hygrophila schulli (Schumach.) Heine
Bahel schulli Buch.-Ham.
 Olorunfemi, J. in FHI 55003 9 Sep. 1964; FHI, K
 Total: 21; Adamawa 2, Borno 7, Gombe 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Oyo 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Hygrophila senegalensis (Nees) T.Anderson
Physichilus senegalensis Nees
 Latilo, M.G. in FHI 73576 12 Nov. 1975; FHI, K
 Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Kebbi 1, Kogi 1, Plateau 1, Yobe 1.

Hygrophila uliginosa S.Moore
 Sharland, R.E. 1556 14 Nov. 1980; K
 Total: 6; Lagos 1, Plateau 4.

Hypoestes aristata (Vahl) Sol. ex Roem. & Schult.
Justicia aristata Vahl
 Keay, R.W.J. & Onochie, C.F. in FHI 21536 17 Nov. 1946; FHI, K
 Total: 18; Abia 1, Cross River 4, Enugu 1, Nasarawa 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Hypoestes cancellata Nees
 Ekwunjo, P.O. 249 in FHI 77188 21 Nov. 1975; FHI, K
 Total: 10; Adamawa 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Taraba 5.

Hypoestes forskoolii (Vahl) R.Br.
Justicia forskoolii Vahl
 Jackson, J.K.; Magaji, S.O.; Tuley, P.; 1986; 1969-11-19 [K004678664]
 Total: 33; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Hypoestes rosea P.Beauv.
 Latilo, M.G. in FHI 27334 22 Jan. 1951; FHI, K
 Total: 8; Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 2.

Hypoestes strobilifera S.Moore

Keay, R.W.J.; 34222; 1957-11-24 [4232.000]

Total: 10; Kaduna 7, Kwara 1, Plateau 1.

Hypoestes strobilifera var. *tisserantii*

Benoist

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 21029 3 Nov. 1947; FHI, K

Total: 9; Kaduna 6, Kwara 1, Plateau 1.

Hypoestes triflora (Forssk.) Roem. & Schult.

Justicia triflora Forssk.

Ekwuno, P.O. 320 in FHI 77259 26 Nov. 1975; FHI, K

Total: 11; Cross River 4, Taraba 5.

Isoglossa glandulifera Lindau

Stone, R.H. 78 30 Aug. 1955; K

Total: 2; Borno 1.

Isoglossa nervosa C.B. Clarke

Ekwuno, P.O. 297 in FHI 77236 26 Nov. 1975; FHI, K

Total: 2.

Justicia acuta (C.B. Clarke) Fourc. —

Introduced

Monechma acutum C.B. Clarke

John D.; 1981-8-10 [1057]2274829360

Total: 1.

Justicia anselliana (Nees) T. Anderson

Adhatoda anselliana Nees

Daramola, B.O. in FHI 36940 11 Jun. 1958; FHI, K

Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Delta 4, Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Justicia biokoensis V.A.W. Graham

Justicia maculata T. Anderson

Literature

Total: 0.

Justicia buchholzii (Lindau) I. Darbysh.

Duvernoia buchholzii Lindau

Jones, A.P.D. 2510 in FHI 6859 14 Jan. 1943; FHI, K

Total: 7; Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Justicia camerunensis (Heine) I. Darbysh.

Adhatoda camerunensis Heine

Daramola, B.O. in FHI 62364 28 Nov. 1968; FHI, K

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Justicia extensa T. Anderson

Keay, R.W.J. & Onochie, C.F. in FHI 21593 28 Oct. 1946; FHI, K

Total: 22; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1.

Justicia flava (Forssk.) Vahl

Dianthera americana var. *flava* Forssk.

Olorunfemi, J. in FHI 55136 12 Dec. 1964; FHI, K

Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 3.

Justicia hepperi Heine — Endemic

Hepper, F.N. 1393 18 Nov. 1957; K

Total: 1.

Justicia insularis T. Anderson

Onyeachusim, H.D. in FHI 54248 4 Mar. 1964; FHI, K

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ondo 1.

Justicia kuntzei subsp. *robusta* (Rusby)

Wassh. & J.R.I. Wood — Introduced

Justicia robusta Rusby

Ogundipe 977; 1990-10-01 [K:TIS-000025193]

Total: 1.

Justicia ladanoides Lam.

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25389 12 Sep. 1949; FHI, K

Total: 19; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Niger 4, Ondo 2, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1, Yobe 1.

Justicia laxa T. Anderson

Talbot, P.A. 978 1911; K

Total: 6; Cross River 3.

Justicia maxima (Lindau) S. Moore

Duvernoia maxima Lindau

Onochie, C.F.A. et al. in FHI 40300 7 Nov. 1958; FHI, K

Total: 5; Edo 2, Rivers 1.

Justicia nigerica S. Moore — Endemic

Talbot, P.A. 1270 1911–1912; K

Total: 9; Abia 1, Cross River 3, Niger 2.

Justicia orbicularis (Lindau)

V.A.W. Graham

Duvernoia orbicularis Lindau

Talbot, P.A. 975 1911; K

Total: 1.

Justicia scandens Vahl

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 62296 17 Nov. 1968; FHI, K

Total: 2; Abia 1.

Justicia secunda (Lam.) Griseb —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Justicia striata (Klotzsch) Bullock —

Introduced

Adhatoda striata Klotzsch

Ariwaodo JO; 1976-12-11 [WAG.1745940]

Total: 30; Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Cross River 6, Gombe 1, Kaduna 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Justicia striata subsp. *occidentalis*

J.K.Morton

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28097 7 Nov. 1950; FHI, K

Total: 18; Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Kaduna 5, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Justicia tenuipes S.Moore

Talbot, P.A. 1327 1911–1912; K

Total: 4; Niger 2.

Justicia tocontina (Nees) V.A.W.Graham —
Introduced

Chaetothylax tocontinus Nees

Apejoye F. I. ; 1981-9-18 [1055] 2274829363

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Justicia tristis (Nees) T.Anderson

Adhatoda tristis Nees

Onochie, C.F.A. & Okafor, J.C. in FHI 36052 18 Jan. 1957; FHI, K

Total: 4; Cross River 2.

Justicia unyorensis S.Moore

Chapman, J.D. 3285 in FHI 68578 27 Oct. 1973; FHI, K

Total: 5; Borno 1, Cross River 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Lankesteria barteri Hook.f.

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 41324 11 Mar. 1959; FHI, K

Total: 30; Abia 1, Cross River 11, Edo 3, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Lankesteria elegans (P.Beauv.) T.Anderson

Justicia elegans P.Beauv.

McElderry, J.C.K. in FHI 7602 11 Jan. 1944; FHI, K

Total: 51; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 13, Edo 8, Imo 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 1, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 1.

Lankesteria thyrsoides S.Moore

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 45805 20 Feb. 1962; FHI, K

Total: 52; Cross River 13, Kano 1, Niger 1, Ogun 11, Ondo 1, Oyo 8.

Lepidagathis alopecuroidea (Vahl) R.Br. ex
Griseb.

Ruellia alopecuroidea Vahl

Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25144 24 Dec. 1948; FHI, K

Total: 30; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Cross River 7, Kaduna 3, Niger 3, Ogun 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Lepidagathis chariensis Benoist

Dalziel, J.M. 139

Total: 1.

Lepidagathis collina (Endl.) Milne-Redh.

Russegera collina Endl.

Ujor, E. in FHI 31601 12 Jan. 1952; FHI, K

Total: 19; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 2, Cross River 1, Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Lepidagathis diversa C.B.Clarke

Jackson, J.A.D. 136 in FHI 59442 1963-11-09; FHI, K

Total: 21; Adamawa 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 6, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Plateau 5, Taraba 2, Yobe 1.

Lepidagathis scariosa Nees

Daramola, B.O. in FHI 45541; 1962-10-27; FHI, K

Total: 2; Borno 2.

Mendoncia iodoides (S.Moore) Heine

Afromendoncia iodoides S.Moore

Talbot, P.A. 388 1911; K

Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Metarungia pubinervia (T.Anderson) Baden

Rungia pubinervia T.Anderson

Chapman, H.M. 561 29 Dec. 2003; BR, CAS, K, UCI, WAG

Total: 2.

Mimulopsis solmsii Schweinf.

Chapman, J.D. 5143 30 Dec. 1977; K

Total: 8; Cross River 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Nelsonia canescens (Lam.) Spreng.

Justicia canescens Lam.

Ejiofor, M.C. in FHI 19815 22 Feb. 1950; FHI, K

Total: 157; Abia 2, Adamawa 5, Anambra 3, Bauchi 9, Borno 11, Cross River 6, Ebonyi 1, Edo 5, Ekiti 6, Enugu 5, Gombe 6, Imo 1, Kaduna 13, Kano 7, Katsina 1, Kogi 3, Kwara 7, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 14, Ogun 4, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 8, Plateau 7, Taraba 11.

Nelsonia smithii Oerst.

Wit, P. & Wit, J. 1131 in FHI 64824 23 Jan. 1972; FHI, K

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Edo 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Odontonema cuspidatum (Nees) Kuntze —
Introduced

Thyrsacanthus cuspidatus Nees

Lekan A.; 1994-10-12 [105262] 1990433690

Total: 5; Oyo 2.

Phaulopsis angolana S.Moore

Keay, R.W.J. & Onochie, C.F. in FHI 21502 1 Nov. 1946; FHI, K

Total: 19; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 4, Enugu 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 3, Oyo 1.

Phaulopsis barberi T.Anderson

Hepper F.N. [BR0000019190242]

Total: 94; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 7, Kaduna 14, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3, Niger 8, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 12, Taraba 12.

Phaulopsis barberi var. *barteri*

Okafor, J.C. in FHI 46873 28 Nov. 1962; FHI, K

Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Phaulopsis barberi var. *pauciglandula*

Mankt.

Lowe, J. 1344 20 Jan. 1969; FHI, K

Total: 4; Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Phaulopsis ciliata (Willd.) Hepper

Origanum ciliatum Willd.

Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 31897 17 Dec. 1952; FHI, K

Total: 98; Abia 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 3, Edo 8, Enugu 1, Kaduna 9, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Ogun 13, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 19, Plateau 4, Taraba 5.

Phaulopsis imbricata (Forssk.) Sweet —

Introduced

Ruellia imbricata Forssk.

Latilo, M.G. in FHI 62245 12 Nov. 1968; FHI, K

Total: 4; Benue 2, Ogun 1.

Phaulopsis imbricata subsp. *poggei*

(Lindau) Mankt.

Micranthus poggei Lindau

Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25022 18 Dec.

1948; FHI, K

Total: 3; Benue 2.

Phaulopsis savannicola Mankt.

Leeuwenberg 10521 10 Oct. 1972; WAG

Total: 1.

Phaulopsis symmetrica Mankt.

Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25155 27 Dec.

1948; FHI, K

Total: 4; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

Phaulopsis talbotii S.Moore

Talbot, P.A. 977 1911; K

Total: 3; Niger 2.

Physacanthus batanganus (J.Braun & K.Schum.) Lindau

Ruellia batanganus J.Braun & K.Schum.

Daramola, B.O. in FHI 55318 10 Oct. 1964; FHI, K

Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 5.

Physacanthus talbotii S.Moore

Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 33170 15 May 1953; FHI, K

Total: 7; Akwa Ibom 2, Cross River 2.

Pogonospermum ciliatum (Jacq.) I.Darbysh. & Kiel

Justicia ciliata Jacq.

Daramola, B.O. in FHI 72382 19 Oct. 1973; FHI, K

Total: 2; Anambra 1.

Pogonospermum depauperatum

(T.Anderson) I.Darbysh. & Kiel

Justicia depauperata T.Anderson

Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 251145 24 Dec.

1948; FHI, K

Total: 3; Anambra 2.

Pseuderanthemum dispernum Milne-Redh.

Talbot, P.A. 1552 1912; K

Total: 7; Cross River 4, Edo 2.

Pseuderanthemum ludovicianum (Büttner)

Lindau

Eranthemum ludovicianum Büttner

Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25199 29 Dec.

1948; FHI, K

Total: 13; Cross River 11.

Pseuderanthemum maculatum (G.Lodd.)

I.M.Turner — Introduced

Justicia maculata G.Lodd.

John D.; 1982-09-18 [FHI.1048.0]

Total: 1.

Pseuderanthemum tunicatum (Afzel.)

Milne-Redh.

Justicia tunicata Afzel.

Daramola, B.O. & Emwiogbon, J.A. in FHI 32793 23

Jan. 1961; FHI, K

Total: 74; Abia 4, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 3, Bayelsa

1, Cross River 19, Edo 15, Enugu 1, Kano 1, Lagos 2,

Ogun 6, Ondo 3, Osun 3, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

Ruellia primuloides (T.Anderson ex Benth.)

Heine

Endosiphon primuloides T.Anderson ex Benth. & Hook.f.

Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28190 9 Dec. 1950; FHI, K

Total: 8; Abia 1, Cross River 6.

Ruellia togoensis (Lindau) Heine

Dischistocalyx togoensis Lindau

Daramola, B.O. 451, 15 May 1978; FHI

Total: 10; Kaduna 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 2, Oyo 3.

- Ruellia tuberosa* L. — Introduced
Ibhanesebhor G.; 1994-11-11 [FHI.105245.0]
Total: 3; Lagos 1, Oyo 2.
- Rungia congoensis* C.B.Clarke
Meikle, R.D. 920 31 Dec. 1949; K
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2.
- Rungia dimorpha* S.Moore — Endemic
Talbot, P.A. 1528 1912; K
Total: 1.
- Rungia grandis* T.Anderson
Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 21951 24 Dec. 1946; FHI, K
Total: 20; Cross River 3, Edo 2, Lagos 2, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 4, Taraba 1.
- Rungia paxiana* (Lindau) C.B.Clarke
Justicia paxiana Lindau
Savory, H.J. & Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25041 19 Dec. 1948; FHI, K
Total: 2; Cross River 1.
- Ruspolia hypocrateriformis* (Vahl) Milne-Redh.
Justicia hypocrateriformis Vahl
Daramola, B.O. in FHI 62448 14 Dec. 1968; FHI, K
Total: 16; Katsina 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 4.
- Sclerochiton preussii* (Lindau) C.B.Clarke
Pseudoblepharis preussii Lindau
Hall, J.B. 2945 Nov. 1973; FHI, K
Total: 1.
- Staurogyne kamerunensis* (Engl.) Benoist
Zenkerina kamerunensis Engl.
[FHI.36063X]
Total: 9; Cross River 4.
- Staurogyne kamerunensis* subsp.
calabarensis Champl.
Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28210 10 Dec. 1950; FHI, K
Total: 3.
- Stenandriopsis guineensis* (Nees) Benoist
Crossandra guineensis Nees
Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 33258 18 Aug. 1953; FHI, K
Total: 24; Abia 1, Benue 1, Cross River 8, Edo 1, Lagos 1, Ondo 4, Osun 1.
- Stenandriopsis talbotii* (S.Moore) Heine
Crossandra talbotii S.Moore
Brenan, J.P.M. 8463 10 Dec. 1947; K
Total: 12; Cross River 3, Edo 4.
- Stenandrium thomense* (Milne-Redh.)
Vollesen
Crossandra thomensis Milne-Redh.
Literature
Total: 0.
- Stenostephanus sanguineus* (Nees) Wassh.
— Introduced
Habracanthus sanguineus Nees
Croat 53437; 1981-11-18 [2377961]
Total: 1; Ogun 1.
- Strobilanthes auriculata* var. *auriculata* —
Introduced
Talbot, P.A. 996; 1911-01-01 [K005340940]
Total: 5; Cross River 3.
- Thunbergia alata* Bojer ex Sims
Onochie, C.F.A. & Latilo, M.G. in FHI 44578 20 Jun. 1961; FHI, K
Total: 8; Kogi 1, Osun 1, Oyo 4.
- Thunbergia chrysops* Hook.
Ugbogu; Odewo; 2001-06-22 [FHI.106189.0]
Total: 1; Edo 1.
- Thunbergia cynanchifolia* Benth.
Thomas, N.W. 1146 1911; K
Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Benue 1, Delta 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Osun 1.
- Thunbergia erecta* (Benth.) T.Anderson
Meyenia erecta Benth.
Latilo, M.G. & Daramola, B.O. in FHI 28912 16 Dec. 1954; FHI, K
Total: 19; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Ogun 1, Osun 5, Oyo 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.
- Thunbergia fasciculata* Lindau
Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 28276 17 Dec. 1950; FHI, K
Total: 12; Cross River 2, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 5, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.
- Thunbergia grandiflora* Roxb. —
Introduced
Okafor & Onyeachusim [BR0000020154806]
Total: 20; Cross River 3, Kogi 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 1, Rivers 2.
- Thunbergia laurifolia* Lindl. — Introduced
Eijnatten, CLM van 1074; 1966-1-1 [WAG.1237041]
Total: 3; Oyo 2.
- Thunbergia rufescens* Lindau
Keay, R.W.J. in FHI 25477 27 Oct. 1949; FHI, K
Total: 8; Ondo 8.
- Thunbergia togoensis* Lindau
Onochie, C.F.A. in FHI 40265 21 Aug. 1958; FHI, K

Total: 16; Cross River 1, Edo 1, Ogun 7, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Thunbergia vogeliana Benth.

Obomanu, I.A.I. in FHI 26930 17 Nov. 1950; FHI, K Total: 26; Abia 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 6, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Whitfieldia elongata (P.Beauv.) De Wild. & T.Durand

Ruellia elongata P.Beauv.

Chizea, L.G. in FHI 24476 23 Nov. 1948; FHI, K Total: 66; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 3, Anambra 4, Cross River 8, Delta 1, Edo 24, Imo 3, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1, Oyo 4.

MARTYNIACEAE

Martynia annua L. — Introduced

Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC 499; 1978-5-25 [WAG.1090458]

Total: 17; Abia 1, Edo 2, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 6.

BIGNONIACEAE

Crescentia cujete L.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1176; 1965-12-4 [WAG.1334946] Total: 3; Oyo 2.

Jacaranda mimosifolia D.Don

Daramola, BO FHI 40590; 1959-1-12 [WAG.1282638]

Total: 6; Abia 3, Cross River 2, Niger 1.

Kigelia africana (Lam.) Benth.

Bignonia africana Lam.

Küppers K 1938; 1997-5-8 [WAG.1282799] Total: 69; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 10, Cross River 8, Kaduna 5, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Osun 1, Oyo 10, Zamfara 2.

Kigelia africana subsp. *africana*

Bignonia africana Lam.

Denys E. 616; -- [BR0000014167027] Total: 8; Borno 4, Niger 3.

Kigelia africana subsp. *moosa* (Sprague)

Bidgood & Verdc.

Kigelia moosa Sprague

Kennedy J.D. 2112; -- [BR0000014167997] Total: 5; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 1.

Markhamia lutea (Benth.) K.Schum.

Spathodea lutea Benth.

Gentry 32819; 1981-6-18 [482902]

Total: 4; Ogun 3.

Markhamia tomentosa (Benth.) K.Schum. ex Engl.

Spathodea tomentosa Benth.

Howard, WJ 14; 1972-6-2 [WAG.1283102]

Total: 65; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Benue 3, Cross River 4, Delta 2, Edo 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 5, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 3, Niger 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 3.

Newbouldia laevis (P.Beauv.) Seem. ex Bureau

Spathodea laevis P.Beauv.

Gledhill, D 796; 1968-1-4 [WAG.1283328]

Total: 74; Anambra 2, Cross River 4, Enugu 2, Gombe 2, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 7, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Osun 4, Oyo 25, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Pyrostegia venusta (Ker Gawl.) Miers — Introduced

Bignonia venusta Ker Gawl.

Streemadhavan 5716; 1976-3-7 [1219828]

Total: 2; Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Spathodea campanulata P.Beauv.

Gentry 32777; 1981-6-16 [482557]

Total: 45; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Enugu 2, Kaduna 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 3, Osun 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Spathodea campanulata subsp. *campanulata*

Gillett, JB 15306; 1962-8-8 [WAG.1283673]

Total: 20; Anambra 1, Cross River 2, Enugu 1, Kogi 3, Lagos 2, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Spathodea campanulata subsp. *nilotica* (Seem.) Bidgood

Chapman J.D. 3260; 08-10-1973 [FHI 68554, K]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1.

Stereospermum acuminatissimum K.Schum.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32959; 1981-6-22 [WAG.1283744]

Total: 21; Cross River 3, Edo 1, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 2, Ondo 3, Osun 2, Oyo 3, Rivers 1.

Stereospermum kunthianum Cham.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1579; 1972-4-28 [WAG.1391411]

Total: 45; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 5, Delta 1, Kaduna 5, Kano 1, Lagos 2, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4, Zamfara 3.

Tabebuia pallida (Lindl.) Miers —
Introduced

Bignonia pallida Lindl.
; 1963-6-25 [2252243483]
Total: 2; Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Tabebuia rosea (Bertol.) DC. — Introduced

Tecoma rosea Bertol.
; -- [11755]2821312865
Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Tecoma stans (L.) Juss. ex Kunth

Bignonia stans L.
Emwiogbon, JA FHI 47151; 1963-2-6
[WAG.1391593]
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 1.

Tecomaria capensis (Thunb.) Spach —
Introduced

Bignonia capensis Thunb.
Eijnatten, CLM van 1350; 1966-4-4 [WAG.1391645]
Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Taraba 1.

VERBENACEAE

Duranta erecta L. — Introduced

Eijnatten, CLM van 1726; 1966-7-27 [WAG.1189474]
Total: 36; Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Lagos 16, Ogun 8, Oyo 5.

Glandularia tenera (Spreng.) Cabrera —
Introduced

Adebusuyi, J.K. FHI43964; 1960-08-05
[K004299068]
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Lantana camara L. — Introduced

Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO 4; 1980-2-14
[WAG.1189704]
Total: 59; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Borno 1, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1, Katsina 1, Lagos 11, Niger
1, Ogun 10, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 15, Plateau 1,
Rivers 2, Taraba 2.

Lantana camara subsp. *aculeata* (L.)

R.W.Sanders — Introduced
Lantana aculeata L.
Meikle, R.D. 1125; 1950-01-31 [K004502353]
Total: 5; Niger 1, Oyo 1.

Lantana camara subsp. *glandulosissima*
(Hayek) R.W.Sanders — Introduced

Lantana glandulosissima Hayek
Lely, H.V. 547; 1921-08-20 [K004502368]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Lantana trifolia L. — Introduced

s.n. s.coll. [K004502370]
Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Lantana ukambensis (Vatke) Verdc.

Lippia ukambensis Vatke
Soladoye, MO; Daramola, BO; Ihe, PC FHI 86208; --
[WAG.1189980]
Total: 33; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Benue 2, Edo 1,
Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 3,
Ogun 1, Plateau 5.

Lantana viburnoides (Forssk.) Vahl

Charachera viburnoides Forssk.
Daramola BO; 1977-08-25 [WAG.1853439]
Total: 4; Taraba 3.

Lantana viburnoides subsp. *viburnoides*

Charachera viburnoides Forssk.
Soladoye, MO; Ekwuno, PO SE 7; 1980-2-22
[WAG.1853438]
Total: 1.

Lippia chevalieri Moldenke

Latilo; Eimunjeze 65606; 1972-12-17 [K000211719]
Total: 14; Jigawa 2, Kaduna 4, Niger 1, Osun 1,
Taraba 1.

Lippia javanica (Burm.f.) Spreng. —
Introduced

Verbena javanica Burm.f.
Ugwuozor P.O.; 2010-6-20 [222B] [1990271799]
Total: 1; Enugu 1.

Lippia multiflora Moldenke

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 393; 1978-5-
10 [WAG.1853691]
Total: 45; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Edo 3, Gombe
1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 8, Niger 7, Ondo 2, Osun
4, Oyo 2, Rivers 1, Taraba 8.

Lippia rehmannii H.Pearson — Introduced

H. V. Lely320; 1921-6-23 [137846] [1930007455]
Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Lippia rugosa A.Chev.

Wit, P; Wit, J 1163; 1972-1-31 [WAG.1853592]
Total: 34; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Edo 1, Imo 1,
Kaduna 5, Katsina 3, Kwara 2, Niger 1, Oyo 1,
Plateau 8, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Lippia savoryi Meikle

Lely, H.V. 320; 1921-6-23 [K000379311]
Total: 28; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Bauchi 2,
Benue 1, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 6, Plateau 9,
Taraba 1.

Petrea volubilis L. — Introduced

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 57964; 1966-2-11
[WAG.1870031]

Total: 7; Lagos 1, Oyo 2.

Phyla nodiflora (L.) Greene

Verbena nodiflora L.

Dalziel J.M. [BR0000019554709]

Total: 32; Borno 8, Cross River 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Katsina 5, Lagos 3, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Zamfara 2.

Phyla nodiflora var. *minor* (Gillies & Hook.) N.O'Leary & Mulgura — Introduced

Lippia nodiflora var. *minor* Gillies & Hook.

Sharland 550; 1979-07-01 [K004948835]

Total: 1; Jigawa 1.

Phyla nodiflora var. *nodiflora*

Verbena nodiflora L.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1143; 1972-4-25
[WAG.1859245]

Total: 1.

Priva lappulacea (L.) Pers. — Introduced

Verbena lappulacea L.

Literature

Total: 0.

Stachytarpheta cayennensis (Rich.) Vahl — Introduced

Verbena cayennensis Rich.

Emwiogbon, JA 203; 1972-5-30 [WAG.1870335]

Total: 112; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Cross River 8, Delta 2, Edo 5, Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Lagos 17, Ogun 20, Ondo 9, Osun 10, Oyo 29, Taraba 1.

Stachytarpheta indica (L.) Vahl —

Introduced

Verbena indica L.

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 81; 1979-1-23
[WAG.1870258]

Total: 165; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 2, Anambra 7, Bauchi 1, Bayelsa 8, Benue 4, Borno 5, Cross River 18, Edo 10, Enugu 3, Gombe 3, Imo 3, Kaduna 13, Kano 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 4, Lagos 5, Nasarawa 1, Niger 12, Ogun 9, Ondo 2, Osun 3, Oyo 19, Plateau 6, Rivers 2, Taraba 2.

Stachytarpheta jamaicensis (L.) Vahl —

Introduced

Verbena jamaicensis L.

Gentry, AH; Pilz, GE 32840; 1981-6-20
[WAG.1870178]

Total: 18; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 6, Ogun 4, Oyo 2.

Stachytarpheta marginata Vahl

Eijnatten, CLM van 1500; 1966-5-14 [WAG.1870336]

Total: 1.

Stachytarpheta mutabilis (Jacq.) Vahl —

Introduced

Verbena mutabilis Jacq.

Fagbemi A.; 1972-1-31 [31694] [1990428690]

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 2.

Verbena aristigera S.Moore — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Verbena bipinnatifida Schauer —

Introduced

Adebusuyi J.K.; 1960-8-5 [43964]1990431447

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

CARDIOPTERIDACEAE

Leptaulus congolanus (Baill.) Loobr.-Callen & Villiers

Acrocoelium congolanum Baill.

Emwiogbon, JA FHI 65833; 1972-6-8
[WAG.1220049]

Total: 8; Cross River 7.

Leptaulus daphnoides Benth. & Hook.f.

Meer, PPC van 1345; 1971-4-19 [WAG.1507376]

Total: 13; Cross River 4, Edo 1, Niger 2, Plateau 1.

AQUIFOLIACEAE

Ilex coriacea (Pursh) Chapm. — Introduced

Prinos coriaceus Pursh

R.K.Godfrey; 1957-6-24 [219]3808439024

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

Ilex mitis (L.) Radlk.

Sideroxylon mite L.

Chapman, JD 2511; 1971-8-21 [WAG.1661637]

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 2, Taraba 8.

Ilex mitis var. *mitis*

Sideroxylon mite L.

Chapman, J.D.; 3360; 1974-09-29 [K005602216]

Total: 9; Plateau 2, Sokoto 2, Taraba 4.

STEMONURACEAE

Lasianthera africana P.Beauv.

Binuyo A. [BR0000015597403]

Total: 31; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 15, Imo 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1.

Lasianthera africana var. *africana*

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 347; 1977-10-12
[WAG.1398901]

Total: 1.

CAMPANULACEAE

Dielsantha galeopsoides (Engl. & Diels)

E. Wimm.

Lobelia galeopsoides Engl. & Diels

Talbot P.A. 1259; s.n [K]

Total: 3; Cross River 1.

Lobelia acutidens Hook.f.

Daramola, B.O. FHI62375; 1968-11-29
[K006035430]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Lobelia adnexa E. Wimm.

Chapman J.D. 3416; 04-11-1974 [K]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Lobelia baumannii Engl. — Introduced

Medler J. 890; 1973-8-18 [73674]

Total: 3; Cross River 1, Plateau 2.

Lobelia columnaris Hook.f.

Wit P.;Gbile Z.O.;Daramola B.O. 2067; 1972-5-11
[66771]1990431457

Total: 14; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 4, Niger 1,
Plateau 1, Taraba 7.

Lobelia djurensis Engl. & Diels

Stanfield D.P.; 1964-11-7 [55640]

Total: 10; Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1,
Osun 1, Oyo 1.

Lobelia erinus L.

Hall J.B. 470; 17-08-1968 [IFE6721] K

Total: 2; Kano 1.

Lobelia hartlaubii Buchenau

Emwiogbon, JA; Osanyinlusi 203; 1977-10-8
[WAG.1508338]

Total: 4; Borno 1, Cross River 2, Plateau 1.

Lobelia inconspicua A. Rich.

Daramola B.O.; 1968-7-4 [61518]

Total: 1; Rivers 1.

Lobelia rubescens De Wild.

Daramola, BO 92; 1977-8-17 [WAG.1508399]

Total: 32; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Borno 2, Cross
River 4, Kano 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 19.

Lobelia sapinii De Wild.

Lely, H. V. P727; -- [K000228543]

Total: 9; Adamawa 2, Kaduna 2, Nasarawa 1, Plateau
1.

Monopsis stellarioides (C. Presl) Urb.

Dobrowskya stellarioides C. Presl

Hepper F.N. 1957; 1958-2-13 [BR0000017768320]

Total: 4; Taraba 1.

Monopsis stellarioides subsp. *schimperiana*

(Urb.) Thulin

Monopsis schimperiana Urb.

Hepper F.N. ; 1957; 1958-2-13 [BR0000017768320]

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Wahlenbergia abyssinica (Hochst. ex

A. Rich.) Thulin — Introduced

Lightfootia abyssinica Hochst. ex A. Rich.

Geerling, C; Wit, P 3864; 1971-7-29 [WAG.1335562]

Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Wahlenbergia erecta (Roth ex Schult.) Tuyn

Dentella erecta Roth ex Schult.

Hepper F.N. 1280; -- [BR0000014664250]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Kogi 1.

Wahlenbergia flexuosa (Hook.f. &

Thomson) Thulin

Cephalostigma flexuosum Hook.f. & Thomson

Hepper F.N. 1100; -- [BR0000014664427]

Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Wahlenbergia hirsuta (Edgew.) Tuyn

Cephalostigma hirsutum Edgew.

Hepper F.N. 1341; -- [BR0000014664571]

Total: 25; Adamawa 1, Edo 2, Kwara 2, Niger 3, Oyo
1, Plateau 3, Taraba 8.

Wahlenbergia krebsii Cham.

Chapman J.D. 3533; 27-05-1905 [K]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Wahlenbergia krebsii subsp. *arguta*

(Hook.f.) Thulin

Wahlenbergia arguta Hook.f.

Chapman, J.D. 3533; 1974-01-01 [K005888578]

Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Borno 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Wahlenbergia lobelioides (L.f.) Link

Campanula lobelioides L.f.

Ekwuno P.O. 323; 1976-6-9 [92082]

Total: 23; Bauchi 3, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna
2, Kano 1, Kwara 1, Niger 2, Plateau 9, Taraba 1.

Wahlenbergia lobelioides subsp. *riparia*

(A. DC.) Thulin

Wahlenbergia riparia A.DC.
Dalziel J.M. 702; -- [BR0000014665806]
Total: 14; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Kwara 1,
Niger 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 1.

Wahlenbergia paludicola Thulin

Lightfootia gracillima R.E.Fr.
Chapman J.W.F 59; 1958-07 [K]
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Wahlenbergia perrottetii (A.DC.) Thulin

Cephalostigma perrottetii A.DC.
Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63222; 1970-3-28
[WAG.1336026]
Total: 82; Akwa Ibom 2, Anambra 4, Bauchi 2, Benue
1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 3,
Enugu 4, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 5, Kwara 1,
Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 2, Ondo 2, Osun
1, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Taraba 10.

Wahlenbergia ramosissima (Hemsl.) Thulin

Cephalostigma ramosissimum Hemsl.
Tuley, P.; 1918; 1969-11-16 [K005888624]
Total: 6; Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Wahlenbergia ramosissima subsp.

ramosissima

Cephalostigma ramosissimum Hemsl.
Tuley P. 2015; 19-11-1969 [K]
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Wahlenbergia silenoides Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO FHI 63277; 1970-4-5
[WAG.1336111]
Total: 14; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1,
Kaduna 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Taraba 5.

MENYANTHACEAE

Nymphoides ezannoi Berhaut

Tuley, P. 1136 [K005515520]
Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Sokoto 1.

Nymphoides forbesiana (Griseb.) Kuntze

Limnanthemum forbesianum Griseb.
Brenan, J.P.M. 8595; 1947-12-25 [K005515529]
Total: 2; Edo 2.

Nymphoides senegalensis (G.Don) Tippery

Villarsia senegalensis G.Don
Literature
Total: 0.

GOODENIACEAE

Scaevola plumieri (L.) Vahl

Lobelia plumieri L.
Onochie C.F.A.; 1954-8-13 [33488] [1990428890]
Total: 2; Edo 1, Lagos 1.

ASTERACEAE

Acanthospermum australe (Loefl.) Kuntze

— Introduced
Melampodium australe Loefl.
Latilo, M.G. [FHI69419] 06/1974; FHI
Total: 7; Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Acanthospermum glabratum (DC.) Wild —

Introduced
Acanthospermum xanthioides var. glabratum DC.
Kadiri, A.B.; Others; 2008-12-1 [2519]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Acanthospermum hispidum DC. —

Introduced
Martii, 645; K
Total: 24; Borno 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Gombe 2,
Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Niger
2, Osun 1, Oyo 3.

Acmella caulirhiza Delile

Schimper, 134 06/1837; K
Total: 55; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1,
Cross River 10, Edo 4, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Imo 2, Kogi
1, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 2,
Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 5.

Acmella uliginosa (Sw.) Cass. — Introduced

Spilanthes uliginosa Sw.
Literature
Total: 0.

Adenostemma caffrum DC.

Chapman, H.M., 29 07/1973; FHI. Drège, J.F. 3081
received in 1835; GDC.
Total: 3; Adamawa 1.

Adenostemma caffrum var. *asperum* Brenan

Brass, L.J. 16979 07/1946; K. Ghesquiere, J. 3790
02/1937; YBI.
Total: 1.

Adenostemma caffrum var. *caffrum*

Same as for *Adenostemma caffrum* DC.
Total: 1.

Adenostemma mauritanum DC.

Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B. O., 111 11/1980; FHI.
Bouton, L., s.n. [K000273390]; K.
Total: 1.

Adenostemma viscosum J.R.Forst. &
G.Forst.

Drege, s.n. [K000273392] 1837; k
Total: 28; Adamawa 2, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1,
Bayelsa 1, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1,
Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 4.

Aedesia glabra (Klatt) O.Hoffm.

Bojeria glabra Klatt

Barter, C., 713 [P024758] 1853; P
Total: 17; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Plateau
2, Taraba 3.

Aedesia spectabilis Mattf.

Chapman, J.D. 4499; 1976-06-29 [K000518400]
Total: 2; Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Afrocarduus nyassanus (S.Moore) N.Garcia,
Moreyra & Susanna

Wit, P.; Gbile, Z.O.; Daramola, B.O.; Fries, R.E.
2058; 1972-05-11 [K002008721]
Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Taraba 1.

Ageratina adenophora (Spreng.) R.M.King
& H.Rob. — Introduced

Literature
Total: 0.

Ageratum conyzoides L. — Introduced

Poiteau, P.A., s.n. [K000924541] 07/1824; K
Total: 61; Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Cross River 2, Enugu
1, Imo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 7, Ogun
5, Osun 3, Oyo 8, Plateau 4, Rivers 1, Sokoto 2,
Taraba 5.

Ageratum houstonianum Mill. — Introduced
[ABUH]

Total: 1.

Ambrosia artemisiifolia L. — Introduced

Denys, E., 672 07/1982; BR
Total: 1.

Ambrosia maritima L.

Onochie, C.F.A. [FHI18674] 06/1958; FHI
Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 5, Kwara 1, Niger
2, Plateau 2, Sokoto 1.

Anisopappus africanus Oliv. & Hiern

Medler J. 945; 26-08-1973 [IFE6022]
Total: 6; Akwa Ibom 1, Taraba 3.

Anisopappus chinensis Hook. & Arn.

Hepper, F.N., 2894 10/1957; P

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1,
Gombe 1, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1,
Zamfara 1.

Artemisia absinthium L.

Robb s.n. [WAG.1304576]; WAG
Total: 1.

Aspilia africana (Pers.) C.D.Adams

Wedelia africana Pers.

Odewo, T.K. & Binuyo, A., 119 [FHI0100879-0]
09/1982; FHI

Total: 130; Abia 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 1,
Borno 4, Cross River 9, Ekiti 2, Enugu 4, Kaduna 3,
Kano 2, Katsina 1, Kogi 2, Lagos 15, Niger 8, Ogun
14, Ondo 5, Osun 4, Oyo 13, Plateau 4, Rivers 4,
Taraba 4, Yobe 1.

Aspilia africana subsp. *africana*

Wedelia africana Pers.

Same as *Aspilia africana*

Total: 18; Cross River 2, Ogun 2, Osun 1, Oyo 2,
Plateau 1.

Aspilia angustifolia Oliv. & Hiern

Barter, 1007: K, P

Total: 20; Ekiti 1, Niger 5, Osun 1, Oyo 5, Plateau 2.

Aspilia bussei O.Hoffm. & Muschl.

Daramola B.O. FHI86465; 08-03-1979 [FHI0086465]
Total: 2; Bauchi 1.

Aspilia ciliata (Schumach.) Wild

Verbesina ciliata Schumach.

Volge, 20 09/1841; K

Total: 36; Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Gombe 1, Kogi 1,
Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Oyo
2, Plateau 6.

Aspilia helianthoides (Schumach. & Thonn.)
Oliv. & Hiern

Coronocarpus helianthoides Schumach.

Binuyo, A. et al., 45 [FHI0094310-0] 11/1980; FHI
Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Katsina 2, Kebbi 1,
Kwara 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1.

Aspilia helianthoides subsp. *helianthoides*

Coronocarpus helianthoides Schumach.

Binuyo, A. et al., 45 [FHI0094310-0] 11/1980; FHI
Total: 1.

Aspilia helianthoides subsp. *prieureana*
(DC.) C.D.Adams

Blainvillea prieureana DC.

Daramola B.O. FHI47284; 12-10-1963 [FHI020516-1]
Total: 1.

Aspilia kotschyi (Sch.Bip. ex Hochst.) Oliv.

Dipterotheca kotschyi Sch.Bip. ex Hochst.

Ekwuno, P.O. et al., 258 09/1981; FHI

Total: 19; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 4, Borno 2, Imo 1, Kano 2, Niger 1.

Aspilia kotschyi var. *alba* Berhaut

Daramola, B.O.; 1968-7-10 [P00072780]

Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Imo 1.

Aspilia kotschyi var. *kotschyi*

Dipterotheca kotschyi Sch.Bip. ex Hochst.

Same as *Aspilia kotschyi*

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Kano 1, Niger 1.

Aspilia lisowskiana D.J.N.Hind —

Introduced

Melanthera elegans C.D.Adams

Adames, P. 357; 1962-9-14 [K000453490]

Total: 4; Borno 2, Jigawa 1.

Aspilia paludosa Berhaut

Latilo, M.G. & Fagbemi, A. [FHI 70588] 11/1973; FHI

Total: 4; Gombe 1, Kwara 1.

Aspilia rudis Oliv. & Hiern

Barter, C., 1292 1858; K, P.

Total: 20; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 2, Kogi 1, Niger 2.

Aspilia rudis subsp. *fontinaloides*

C.D.Adams

Dalziel, J.M.; 1912-10-19 [P00072904]

Total: 1.

Aspilia rudis subsp. *rudis*

Barter, C., 1292 1858; K, P.

Total: 1.

Asteriscus graveolens subsp. *graveolens*

Asteriscus graveolens Forssk.

Newby, J.E. ZP93; 1979-03-30 [K002486650]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Baccharoides adoensis (Sch.Bip. ex Walp.)

H.Rob.

Vernonia adoensis Sch.Bip. ex Walp.

Pilz, G.E., 1888 12/1976; WAG

Total: 28; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 4, Katsina 2, Kwara 2, Nasarawa 1, Osun 1, Plateau 1.

Baccharoides adoensis var. *adoensis*

Vernonia adoensis Sch.Bip. ex Walp.

Same as for *Baccharoides adoensis*

Total: 1.

Baccharoides adoensis var. *kotschyana*

(Sch.Bip. ex Walp.) Isawumi, El-Ghazaly & B.Nord.

Vernonia kotschyana Sch.Bip. ex Walp.

Lely, H.V. 385; 1921-07-08 [K002535865]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Borno 1.

Baccharoides calvoana (Hook.f.) Isawumi, El-Ghazaly & B.Nord.

Stengelia calvoana Hook.f.

Dalziel, J. M., 8325 [US 1273018]; US

Total: 5; Taraba 2.

Baccharoides calvoana subsp. *calvoana*

Stengelia calvoana Hook.f.

Odewo, T.K.; Ogundipe, O.T.; Kadiri, A.B.,

LUH2940; 2008-05-26; 3460378358

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Baccharoides calvoana var. *microcephala*

(C.D.Adams) Isawumi

Vernonia calvoana var. *microcephala* C.D.Adams

ex C.Jeffrey

Hepper, F.N. s.n.; 1958-1-14 [P020069]437574825

Total: 2.

Baccharoides guineensis (Benth.) H.Rob.

Vernonia guineensis Benth.

Wit, P. et al. [FHI 66705] 05/1972; P

Total: 36; Benue 1, Edo 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 3, Taraba 7, Zamfara 1.

Baccharoides guineensis var. *guineensis*

Vernonia guineensis Benth.

same as for *Baccharoides guineensis*

Total: 1.

Baccharoides guineensis var. *procera*

(O.Hoffm.) Isawumi

Vernonia procera O.Hoffm.

Daramola, BO; Soladoye, MO; Ihe, PC 281 A; 1978-5-3 [WAG.1556398]

Total: 13; Benue 1, Edo 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 2, Zamfara 1.

Baccharoides hymenolepis (A.Rich.)

Isawumi, El-Ghazaly & B.Nord.

Vernonia hymenolepis A.Rich.

Latilo, M.G. 84; 1975-11-17 [K002535870]

Total: 5; Taraba 4.

Baccharoides pumila (Kotschy & Peyr.)

Isawumi

Vernonia pumila Kotschy & Peyr.

Heuglin, T. von, 19 12/1863; W

Total: 11; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1.

Baccharoides stenostegia (Stapf) Isawumi

Candidea stenostegia Stapf

Olorunfemi, J., s.n. [FHI0056979-0] 12/1965; FHI

Total: 9; Plateau 6.

Baccharoides tenoreana (Oliv.) Isawumi

Vernonia tenoreana Oliv.

Brunel, J.-F., 10484 03/1987; TOGO

Total: 16; Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 6.

Berkheya spekeana Oliv.

Daramola, B.O. FHI40518 02/1959; P

Total: 5; Benue 1, Cross River 1.

Bidens asperata (Hutch. & Dalziel) Sherff

Coreopsis asperata Hutch. & Dalziel

Tuley, P.; Magaji, S.O. 1758; 1969-10-25

[K002508782]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Bidens barteri (Oliv. & Hiern) T.G.J.Rayner

Coreopsis barteri Oliv. & Hiern

Keay, R.W.J., FHI28019 08/1950; P

Total: 32; Bauchi 7, Borno 1, Kaduna 5, Lagos 2,

Niger 1, Plateau 8, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Bidens bipinnata L. — Introduced

Lawlor, D.W.; Hall, J.B.; 295; 1962-08-13

[K002508905]

Total: 4; Bauchi 1, Osun 1.

Bidens biternata (Lour.) Merr. & Sherff

Coreopsis biternata Lour.

Schimper, W., 2181 09/1854; K

Total: 9; Anambra 1, Borno 2, Kano 1, Katsina 2,

Niger 1, Plateau 2.

Bidens borianiana (Sch.Bip. ex Schweinf.)

Cufod.

Coreopsis borianiana Sch.Bip. ex Schweinf.

Summerhayes, G.V., 77 11/1955; P

Total: 24; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos

4, Niger 4, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 1, Sokoto 3.

Bidens camporum (Hutch.) Mesfin

Coreopsis camporum Hutch.

Hepper, F.N., 959 10/1957; P

Total: 14; Niger 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 4.

Bidens occidentalis (Hutch. & Dalziel)

Mesfin

Microlecania occidentalis Hutch. & Dalziel

Lely, H.V., 383 07/1921; K

Total: 3; Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Bidens pilosa L.

Douglas, D., 56; K

Total: 52; Anambra 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 2, Cross River

5, Edo 2, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Lagos 5, Niger 2, Ogun

3, Osun 3, Oyo 5, Plateau 5, Taraba 8.

Blainvillea gayana Cass.

Lawlor, D.D. & Hall, J.B., 275 08/1962; P

Total: 6; Bauchi 4.

Blumea adamsii J.-P.Lebrun & Stork

Blumea alata var. *gracilis* O.Hoffm. & Muschl.

Olorunfemi; Oguntayo; 1978-1-19 [92086]

Total: 1.

Blumea axillaris (Lam.) DC.

Conyza axillaris Lam.

Dalziel J.M., 404; BR

Total: 17; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Kaduna

1, Katsina 2, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Blumea braunii (Vatke) J.-P.Lebrun & Stork

Laggera braunii Vatke

Coombe, D.E. 32; 1954-12-25 [K003187766]

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Blumea heudelotii (C.D.Adams) Lisowski

Laggera heudelotii C.D.Adams

Morton, J.K., s.n. [FHI0057681] 12/1965; FHI

Total: 6; Borno 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1.

Blumea lacera (Burm.f.) DC. — Introduced

Conyza lacera Burm.f.

Dalziel, J.M. [P032434]; P

Total: 18; Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 4,

Niger 2, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Blumea sinuata (Lour.) Merr. — Introduced

Gnaphalium sinuatum Lour.

Daramola B.O.; Binuyo A.; 1968-03-08 [FHI.61207.0]

Total: 6; Kaduna 1, Kwara 2, Oyo 3.

Bothriocline schimperi Oliv. & Hiern ex

Benth.

Savory, H.J. & Keay R.W.J., s.n. [FHI025220-1]

12/1948; FHI (fied as *Erlangea schimperi* S.Moore)

Total: 9; Cross River 3, Niger 1, Taraba 5.

Brachylaena huillensis O.Hoffm. —

Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Brenandendron donianum (DC.) H.Rob.

Vernonia doniana DC.

Kennedy, J. D., 2116; US

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Brenandendron frondosum (Oliv. & Hiern)
H.Rob.

Vernonia frondosa Oliv. & Hiern
Onochie, C.F.A. et al., s.n. [FHI0036593-1] 12/1957
FHI
Total: 32; Anambra 1, Cross River 1, Katsina 1, Kogi
1, Kwara 4, Niger 1, Osun 1.

Brenandendron titanophyllum (Brenan)
H.Rob.

Vernonia titanophylla Brenan
Literature
Total: 0.

Calostephane angolensis (O.Hoffm.)
Anderb.

Mollera angolensis O.Hoffm.
Okafor, J.C. [FHI 46898] 12/1962; WAG
Total: 16; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 7, Plateau 2.

Calostephane punctulata (Hiern) Anderb.
Mollera punctulata Hiern
Gossweiler, J., 3985; K
Total: 1; Bauchi 1.

Carduus nyassanus R.E.Fr.
Carduus leptacanthus var. nyassanus S.Moore
Schimper, 44 [K000418460]; K
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Carduus nyassanus subsp. *nyassanus*
Carduus leptacanthus var. nyassanus S.Moore
Schimper, 44 [K000418460]; K
Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Centaurea nigERICA Hutch.
Soladoye, M. O. et al., 347 10/1977; FHI
Total: 21; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2,
Niger 2, Plateau 10.

Centaurea perrottetii DC.
Latilo, M.G., s.n. [FHI0063846-0] 10/1971; FHI.
Perrottet, S., 18 04/1828; G-DC.
Total: 11; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Benue 1,
Katsina 1, Niger 1, Oyo 2, Sokoto 1.

Centaurea praecox Oliv. & Hiern
Stanfield, D.P., s.n. [FHI0059866] 07/1966; FHI (filed
under the name *Calcitrapoides praecox* (Oliv. &
Hiern) Holub). Barter, C., 1223; K, P
Total: 15; Bauchi 1, Kaduna 6, Kwara 1, Oyo 1,
Plateau 1.

Centaurea senegalensis DC.
Onochie, C.F.A., s.n. [FHI0023346-0] 06/1947; FHI
Total: 7; Borno 4.

Centipeda minima (L.) A.Braun & Asch. —
Introduced

Literature
Total: 0.

Centratherum punctatum Cass. —
Introduced

Daramola, B.O., s.n. [FHI091303-1] 11/1979; FHI (5
sheets)
Total: 5; Oyo 4.

Ceruana pratensis Forssk.
Latilo, M.G., et al., s.n. [FHI069389-1] 05/1954; FHI
(2 sheets)
Total: 21; Adamawa 5, Gombe 4, Kaduna 2, Niger 3,
Sokoto 1, Taraba 2.

Chromolaena odorata (L.) R.M.King &
H.Rob. — Introduced

Eupatorium odoratum L.
Hassler, E., 11859 07/1913; K
Total: 148; Abia 3, Adamawa 1, Anambra 5, Benue 2,
Cross River 12, Delta 3, Ebonyi 1, Edo 17, Enugu 12,
Kaduna 1, Kogi 4, Kwara 1, Lagos 18, Ogun 19, Ondo
6, Osun 4, Oyo 24, Taraba 2.

Chrysanthellum americanum (L.) Vatke —
Introduced

Anthemis americana L.
Nodza, G.I. & Ogundipe, O.T., s.n. 06/2012; LUH
Total: 7; Kaduna 4, Ogun 2, Taraba 1.

Chrysanthellum indicum DC.
Royle, J. F., 174 Reçu en 1833; G-DC
Total: 42; Bauchi 2, Borno 12, Cross River 1, Edo 1,
Kaduna 1, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos
1, Niger 3, Oyo 2, Plateau 2.

Chrysanthellum indicum subsp.

afroamericanum B.L.Turner

Barter, C., 1298 01/1858; P
Total: 10; Borno 3.

Conyza clarenceana Oliv. & Hiern
Ekwuno et al., EOO 346 02/1980; FHI
Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Conyza limosa O.Hoffm.

Literature
Total: 0.

Coreopsis basalis (Otto & A.Dietr.)
S.F.Blake — Introduced

Calliopsis basalis Otto & A.Dietr.
; -- [11862]2821273858
Total: 1; Oyo 1.

Coreopsis lanceolata L. — Introduced
Guile D.P.M. 2648; 1967-4 [IFE6131]
Total: 1.

Cosmos bipinnatus Cav. — Introduced
Andrieux, G., 307 04/1834; K
Total: 1.

Cosmos sulphureus Cav. — Introduced
Guile D.P.M. 1342; 1967-3 [IFE6122]
Total: 3; Borno 1.

Crassocephalum bauchiense (Hutch.)
Milne-Redh.

Gynura bauchiensis Hutch.
Dent Young, J., 158 1922; K
Total: 3; Bauchi 2, Plateau 1.

Crassocephalum crepidioides (Benth.)
S.Moore

Gynura crepidioides Benth.
Olorunfemi, J. et al., 54 09/1978; FHI. Vogel, 139
11/1841; K
Total: 41; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1,
Borno 3, Cross River 1, Edo 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 9, Plateau
1, Taraba 2.

Crassocephalum gracile Milne-Redh. ex
Guinea

Magaji, S.O. & Tuley, P., 1853 11/1969; K
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Crassocephalum montuosum (S.Moore)
Milne-Redh.

Senecio montuosus S.Moore
Scott-Elliot, G.F., 6587 1893; K
Total: 1.

Crassocephalum picridifolium (DC.)
S.Moore

Senecio picridifolius DC.
Coombe, D.E., 76 12/1954; K
Total: 8; Edo 1, Plateau 3.

Crassocephalum rubens (Juss. ex Jacq.)
S.Moore

Senecio rubens Juss. ex Jacq.
Dickson S.M., 21 01/1958; FHI (2 sheets)
Total: 85; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Benue 2, Borno 1,
Cross River 8, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 2, Gombe 1,
Kaduna 5, Katsina 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1,
Niger 1, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Plateau 12,
Taraba 19.

Crassocephalum rubens var. *rubens*
Senecio rubens Juss. ex Jacq.

Same as *Crassocephalum rubens*
Total: 1.

Crassocephalum rubens var. *sarcobasis*
(DC.) C.Jeffrey & Beentje

Gynura sarcobasis DC.
Medler J. 881; 18-08-1973 [IFE6176]
Total: 2; Cross River 1.

Crassocephalum togoense C.D.Adams
Stanfield D.P., s.n. [FHI0055463] 09/1964; FHI
Total: 21; Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2,
Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 9, Plateau 1.

Crassocephalum uvens S.Moore
Stolz, A., 2325 12/1913; K
Total: 1.

Crassocephalum vitellinum (Benth.)
S.Moore

Gynura vitellina Benth.
Gbile Z.O. & Daramola, B.O., 103/80 03/1980; FHI (2
sheets). Vogel, 198 11/1841; K
Total: 41; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 9,
Gombe 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 23.

Crepis hypochoeridea Thell.

Drège J.F., 3783 11/1832; P
Total: 7; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 2.

Crepis newii Oliv. & Hiern

Odewo T.K., TKO 757 08/1977; FHI
Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Crepis newii subsp. *oliveriana* (Kuntze)
C.Jeffrey & Beentje

Unknown ; 00-01-1900 [IFE771]
Total: 1.

Crystallopollen angustifolium Steetz

Brass, L.; 16090.0; 16923.0 [BR, K]
Total: 7; Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Oyo 1.

Crystallopollen serratuloides (DC.)

J.C.Manning

Webbia serratuloides DC.
Daramola, BO; Okoro, M 82/ 48; 1982-11-1
[WAG.1557325]
Total: 26; Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Enugu 1,
Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1,
Nasarawa 1, Niger 3, Plateau 4.

Cyanthillium cinereum (L.) H.Rob.

Conyza cinerea L.
Wallich, N., [3008] K001118413 01/1826; K
Total: 67; Anambra 3, Benue 1, Borno 4, Cross River
1, Edo 1, Enugu 2, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 9, Ogun 8,
Osun 3, Oyo 19, Rivers 1.

Cyanthillium cinereum var. *cinereum*

Conyza cinerea L.

Cyanthillium stelluliferum (Benth.) H. Rob.

Herderia stellulifera Benth.

Vogel, 265 03/1841; K

Total: 63; Abia 2, Benue 1, Cross River 5, Delta 1, Edo 32, Imo 3, Niger 1, Ogun 6, Ondo 2, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Dahlia pinnata Cav. — Introduced

Olorunfemi J. [FHI0055834] 06/1965; FHI

Total: 1; Plateau 1.

Dichrocephala integrifolia (L.f.) Kuntze

Hippia integrifolia L.f.

Okafor J.C. & Binuyo A., s.n. [FHI0059261] 06/1963; FHI

Total: 34; Bauchi 1, Cross River 6, Kwara 1, Niger 1, Ondo 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 18.

Dichrocephala integrifolia subsp.

integrifolia

Hippia integrifolia L.f.

Same as *Dichrocephala integrifolia*

Total: 6; Cross River 1, Kwara 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Dicoma tomentosa Cass.

Daramola, B.O. & Okoro, 14 10/1982; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 32; Adamawa 4, Bauchi 5, Borno 2, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 5, Niger 1, Yobe 1.

Distephanus biafrae (Oliv. & Hiern) H. Rob.

Vernonia biafrae Oliv. & Hiern

Mann, G., 1296 12/1861; K

Total: 5; Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Taraba 1.

Echinops amplexicaulis Oliv.

Chapman, J.D., 2508 08/1971; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 6; Taraba 6.

Echinops giganteus A. Rich.

Ariwaodo, J.O. et al., BAB 58 11/1983; FHI

Total: 8; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 4.

Echinops gracilis O. Hoffm.

Daramola B.O., Giwa, A.O., s.n. [FHI0108389] 06/2006; FHI. Chevalier, A., 6093 11/1902; BR, K, P

Total: 32; Adamawa 4, Niger 1, Plateau 3, Taraba 21.

Echinops himantophyllus Mattf.

McGregor, W., 152 01/1902; P

Total: 12; Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Plateau 5.

Echinops longifolius A. Rich.

Daramola B.O. et al., DEO 747 07/1978; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 45; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Gombe 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 9, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ogun 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 2.

Echinops mildbraedii Mattf.

Hepper F.N., 1549 12/1957; BR

Total: 7; Adamawa 3, Taraba 2.

Echinops pappii Chiov.

Pappi, A., 6848 01/1906; FT

Total: 1.

Eclipta prostrata (L.) L. — Introduced

Verbesina prostrata L.

Burkart, A. et al., 25500 [SI012573] 05/1964; SI

Total: 154; Adamawa 3, Anambra 3, Bauchi 5, Bayelsa 1, Benue 2, Borno 7, Cross River 5, Ebonyi 1, Edo 2, Gombe 5, Imo 3, Kaduna 10, Kano 1, Katsina 2, Kogi 5, Kwara 6, Lagos 8, Niger 8, Ogun 9, Ondo 6, Osun 6, Oyo 18, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6.

Elephantopus mollis Kunth — Introduced

Burchell, 759 08/1825; K

Total: 57; Abia 3, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Cross River 10, Enugu 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 4, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 4, Taraba 11.

Elephantopus senegalensis (Klatt) Oliv. & Hiern

Synchodendron senegalense Klatt

Oyayomi et al. OFOOA 135 11/1976; FHI

Total: 5; Plateau 1.

Eleutheranthera ruderalis (Sw.) Sch. Bip. — Introduced

Melampodium ruderales Sw.

Gardner, 3294 01/1841; K

Total: 10; Imo 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Eleutheranthera ruderalis var. *ruderalis* — Introduced

Melampodium ruderales Sw.

Daramola B.O. 46033; -- [BR0000015401410]

Total: 1.

Emilia abyssinica (Sch. Bip. ex A. Rich.)

C. Jeffrey

Senecio abyssinicus Sch. Bip. ex A. Rich.

Daramola, B.O., 108 08/1977; WAG

Total: 31; Bauchi 2, Borno 1, Kaduna 5, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 9, Taraba 1.

Emilia abyssinica var. *abyssinica*

Senecio abyssinicus Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.
Daramola, B.O., 108 08/1977; WAG
Total: 7; Kaduna 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Taraba 1.

Emilia baberka (Hutch.) C.Jeffrey

Senecio baberka Hutch.
Dalziel, J.M., 390 02/1908; K
Total: 24; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 7, Niger 1, Plateau 9.

Emilia coccinea (Sims) G.Don

Cacalia coccinea Sims
Nwachukwu V.A., s.n. [FHI0110090] 09/2014; FHI
Total: 166; Abia 1, Adamawa 1, Anambra 4, Cross
River 34, Delta 1, Edo 13, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Imo 2,
Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 16, Ogun 10, Ondo 15, Osun
6, Oyo 18, Plateau 5, Rivers 1, Taraba 20.

Emilia javanica (Burm.f.) C.B.Rob. —
Introduced

Hieracium javanicum Burm.f.
Timmerman-van der Sleen, EHL 8; 1960-7-1
[L.3687674]
Total: 4; Cross River 1, Rivers 2.

Emilia lisowskiana C.Jeffrey

Bernardi, 8819; LE
Total: 49; Abia 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Bayelsa 1,
Benue 2, Borno 2, Cross River 1, Edo 2, Kogi 2,
Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 3,
Rivers 2, Taraba 4, Zamfara 1.

Emilia praetermissa Milne-Redh.

George, E. Pilz, 2130 09/1977; FHI (2 sheets)
Total: 82; Abia 2, Anambra 4, Cross River 7, Edo 11,
Enugu 6, Imo 1, Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 7,
Niger 2, Ogun 4, Ondo 5, Osun 5, Oyo 10, Plateau 1,
Rivers 2, Taraba 1.

Emilia schinzii (O.Hoffm.) Cron —
Introduced

Senecio schinzii O.Hoffm.
Coombe D.E. 92; -- [BR0000015404718]
Total: 1.

Emilia sonchifolia (L.) DC.

Cacalia sonchifolia L.
Baldwin J.T. (Jr.) [BR0000013892425]
Total: 42; Anambra 3, Bayelsa 1, Borno 3, Cross
River 1, Edo 1, Enugu 1, Imo 1, Kogi 5, Lagos 3,
Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 1, Rivers 4.

Emilia sonchifolia var. *sonchifolia*

Cacalia sonchifolia L.
Ule, E., 9123 01/1910; K
Total: 1.

Emilia tenuicaulis C.D.Adams

Bafutia tenuicaulis C.D.Adams

Ujor, E., 30216 [K000306837] 09/1951; K
Total: 10; Borno 3, Kogi 3, Taraba 2.

Enydra fluctuans Lour.

Gardner, G., 5522; K
Total: 1.

Erechtites hieraciifolius (L.) Raf. ex DC. —
Introduced

Senecio hieraciifolius L.
Vogel, JRT s.n.; 1841-8-1 [L.3687112]
Total: 1.

Erigeron bonariensis L. — Introduced

Van Eijnatten, C.L.M., 2241 03/1968; WAG
Total: 2; Osun 1.

Erigeron canadensis L. — Introduced

Literature
Total: 0.

Erigeron floribundus (Kunth) Sch.Bip. —
Introduced

Conyza floribunda Kunth
Ogungbe, I.V., s.n [FHI0110233] 05/2015; FHI
Total: 79; Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 1, Benue
1, Cross River 15, Delta 1, Edo 9, Ekiti 2, Enugu 1,
Kogi 3, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Ogun 7, Ondo 13, Osun 1,
Oyo 7, Plateau 2, Taraba 11.

Erigeron karvinskianus DC. — Introduced

Wit, P., 1403 04/1972; WAG
Total: 4; Plateau 3, Taraba 1.

Erigeron steudelii (Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.)
Sch.Bip. ex Schweinf.

Conyza steudelii Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.
Daramola B.O. & Ekwuno P FHI67302; 13-07-1970
[IFE6123]
Total: 3; Benue 1, Plateau 1.

Erigeron sumatrensis Retz. — Introduced

Hind, D.J.N. et al., H50474 12/1992; K (filed as
Conyza sumatrensis)
Total: 16; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 2, Edo 1,
Ekiti 1, Imo 1, Ondo 2, Taraba 1.

Eschenbachia gouanii (L.) G.L.Nesom

Erigeron gouanii L.
Gbile, Z.O., 1355 05/1972; FHI (filed as *Conyza*
gouanii)
Total: 3; Cross River 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Eschenbachia stricta (Willd.) Raizada

Conyza stricta Willd.
Thompson, T., 885 01/1845; K
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Eschenbachia subscaposa (O.Hoffm.)

G.L.Nesom

Conyza subscaposa O.Hoffm.

Latilo, M.G., 02 11/1972; FHI (filed as *Conyza subscaposa*)

Total: 11; Adamawa 1, Enugu 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 5.

Ethulia conyzoides L.f.

Magbagbeola, MFO 69 06/1981, FHI

Total: 145; Abia 5, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 5, Bauchi 6, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 9, Delta 1, Edo 7, Enugu 5, Gombe 2, Imo 2, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 17, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 7, Nasarawa 1, Niger 13, Ogun 5, Ondo 2, Osun 4, Oyo 3, Plateau 11, Taraba 6, Zamfara 2.

Ethulia conyzoides subsp. *conyzoides*

Magbagbeola, MFO 69 06/1981, FHI

Total: 1.

Felicia boehmii O.Hoffm.

Keay, R.W.J., s.n. [FHI0037207] 11/1957; FHI

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Fleischmannia microstemon (Cass.)

R.M.King & H.Rob. — Introduced

Literature

Total: 0.

Gaillardia pulchella Foug. — Introduced

Guile D.P.M. 105; 1967-5 [IFE6295]

Total: 2; Kano 1.

Galgera decurrens (Vahl) Anderb. &

Bengtson

Erigeron decurrens Vahl

[J. E. Newdy] 2[P] 172; 1977-03-27 [K003187849]

Total: 1.

Galinsoga parviflora Cav. — Introduced

Olorunfemi, J. et al. [FHI0096611] 11/1981; FHI

Total: 22; Borno 1, Kaduna 1, Osun 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 9, Zamfara 1.

Galinsoga quadriradiata Ruiz & Pav. —

Introduced

Hinds, s.n. [K000009853] 01/1841; K

Total: 20; Cross River 1, Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 9, Taraba 6.

Geigeria alata (Hochst. & Steud.) Benth. &

Hook.f. ex Oliv. & Hiern

Cichorium alatum Hochst. & Steud.

Schimper, W., 853 01/1837; K

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Gerbera jamesonii Adlam — Introduced

Van Eijnatten, C.L.M., 1062 01/1966; WAG

Total: 3; Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Gerbera piloselloides (L.) Cass.

Arnica piloselloides L.

Chapman, J.D. 4428 1976-05-02 [K001556454]

Total: 5; Kaduna 1, Taraba 3.

Gnaphalium polycaulon Pers.

Daramola, B.O. 63696; 1970-12-01 [K002391806]

Total: 2; Adamawa 1, Borno 1.

Grangea ceruanoides Cass.

Denys, E., 660 [BR0000015163325] 07/1982; BR

Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Kano 1.

Grangea grangeoides J.-P.Lebrun & Stork

Akeassia grangeoides J.-P.Lebrun & Stork

Jackson, J.A.D., FHI 57126 [WAG0260036] 06/1965; WAG

Total: 13; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Borno 2, Kaduna 4, Niger 2, Osun 1, Rivers 1.

Grangea maderaspatana (L.) Poir.

Artemisia maderaspatana L.

Ujo, E.F.A., s.n. [FHI0021931] 06/1948; FHI

Total: 11; Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 5, Jigawa 1, Niger 1, Yobe 1.

Guizotia abyssinica (L.f.) Cass.

Polymnia abyssinica L.f.

Latilo M.G. & Daramola B.O., s.n. [FHI0028966] 12/1954; FHI

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Guizotia scabra (Vis.) Chiov.

Veslingia scabra Vis.

Daramola, B.O. & Okoro, M., DO31 11/1980; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 80; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 3, Imo 1, Kaduna 17, Kogi 1, Niger 10, Plateau 14, Sokoto 3, Taraba 10.

Guizotia schimperi Sch.Bip.

Schimper, 401 10/1837; BM, K, TUB

Total: 2; Kano 1.

Gutenbergia rueppellii Sch.Bip.

Olorunfemi et al., OBB 236 11/1980; FHI

Total: 15; Kaduna 6, Plateau 5.

Gymnanthemum amygdalinum (Delile)

Sch.Bip.

Vernonia amygdalina Delile

John, D., UC/PESH/0001031 10/1981; UNICAL (image not available). Coombe, D.E., [P019658] 12/1954; P

Total: 108; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 5, Cross River 5, Enugu 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Gymnanthemum auriculiferum (Hiern)

Isawumi

Vernonia auriculifera Hiern

Welwitsch, F., 3258 01/1855; K, LISU

Total: 1.

Gymnanthemum coloratum (Willd.) H.Rob. & B.Kahn

Eupatorium coloratum Willd.

Meikle R.D. [BR0000014948213]

Total: 29; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Borno 1, Ekiti 1, Niger 3, Ogun 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Gymnanthemum glaberrimum (Welw. ex O.Hoffm.) H.Rob.

Vernonia glaberrima Welw. ex O.Hoffm.

Daramola, B.O. & Ihe, P.C., 525 05/1978; WAG (filed as *Vernonia glaberrima*)

Total: 36; Bauchi 2, Enugu 2, Kaduna 2, Kebbi 3, Kogi 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 2, Ondo 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 4.

Gynura amplexicaulis Oliv. & Hiern

Bels, L., 76 [U.1127234] 04/1950; U

Total: 3; Lagos 2.

Gynura procumbens (Lour.) Merr.

Cacalia procumbens Lour.

S.coll., 13864 09/1912; K

Total: 5; Lagos 1, Ogun 1, Osun 2.

Gynura pseudochina (L.) DC.

Senecio pseudochina L.

Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1348; 1972-5-10 [WAG.1195550]

Total: 15; Adamawa 1, Benue 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 10.

Helianthus annuus L. — Introduced

Barros, C.S.S., 141 11/1993; K

Total: 3; Lagos 1.

Helichrysum albiflorum Moeser

Burchell, W.J., 4733 02/1814; K

Total: 6; Benue 1, Cross River 3, Taraba 2.

Helichrysum cameroonense Hutch. & Dalziel

Gbile, ZO FHI 63271; 1970-4-5 [WAG.1196224]

Total: 3; Taraba 3.

Helichrysum cymosum (L.) D.Don ex G.Don

— Introduced

Gnaphalium cymosum L.

Wit, P.;Gbile, Z.O.;Daramola, B.O.; 1972-5-10 [P00037514]

Total: 7; Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Helichrysum cymosum subsp. *cymosum* — Introduced

Gnaphalium cymosum L.

Wit P.;Gbile Z.O.;Daramola B.O. W 1942; 1972-5-10 [66689]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Helichrysum foetidum (L.) Moench

Gnaphalium foetidum L.

Savory, H.J. & Keay R.W.J. [FHI0025095] 12/1948; FHI

Total: 5; Cross River 4.

Helichrysum foetidum var. *foetidum*

Gnaphalium foetidum L.

Savory, H.J. & Keay R.W.J. [FHI0025095] 12/1948; FHI

Total: 3; Cross River 2.

Helichrysum forskahlii (J.F.Gmel.) Hilliard & B.L.Burt

Gnaphalium forskahlii J.F.Gmel.

Daramola, BO 144; 1977-8-19 [WAG.1315461]

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Helichrysum forskahlii var. *forskahlii*

Gnaphalium forskahlii J.F.Gmel.

Daramola, B.O., 144 08/1977; WAG

Total: 1.

Helichrysum globosum Sch.Bip.

Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O., s.n. [FHI0063300] 04/1970; FHI

Total: 17; Cross River 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 13.

Helichrysum globosum var. *globosum*

Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O., s.n. [FHI0063300] 04/1970; FHI

Total: 1.

Helichrysum indicum (L.) Grierson

Gnaphalium indicum L.

Daramola & Josephine, s.n. [FHI0063696] 12/1970; FHI

Total: 1; Borno 1.

Helichrysum luteoalbum (L.) Rchb.

Gnaphalium luteoalbum L.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1713; 1972-5-3 [WAG.1409621]

Total: 33; Bauchi 4, Benue 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 3, Kano 2, Plateau 6, Taraba 6.

Helichrysum mechowianum Klatt

Jones, A.P.D., 860 02/1942; FHI

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 6.

Helichrysum mechowianum var. *ceres*

(S.Moore) Beentje

Literature

Total: 0.

Helichrysum mechowianum var. *mechowianum*

Jones, A.P.D., 860 02/1942; FHI

Total: 1.

Helichrysum nudifolium (L.) Less.

Gnaphalium nudifolium L.

Daramola, BO FHI 62917; 1969-5-24 [WAG.1170208]

Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 5.

Helichrysum odoratissimum (L.) Sweet

Gnaphalium odoratissimum L.

Hepper, F.N., 1676 01/1958; S (image not available)

Total: 12; Cross River 3, Taraba 9.

Helichrysum quartinianum A.Rich.

Chapman, J.D., 2783 06/1972; FHI

Total: 16; Borno 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 11.

Helichrysum stenopterum DC. —

Introduced

Gbile, ZO FHI 63263; 1970-4-3 [WAG.1170533]

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Herderia truncata Cass.

Jones, A.P.D., 1452 04/1942; FHI

Total: 13; Anambra 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Osun 1.

Hilliardiella smithiana (Less.) H.Rob.

Vernonia smithiana Less.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1987; 1972-5-10 [WAG.1555287]

Total: 10; Adamawa 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 6.

Hypericophyllum multicaule Hutch.

Meikle, R.D., 1058 01/1950; [BR0000014759024]

Total: 13; Kaduna 2, Niger 6, Sokoto 1.

Inula glomerata Oliv. & Hiern

Latilo, M.G., s.n. [FHI0077363] 11/1975; FHI

Total: 8; Lagos 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 6.

Inula klingii O.Hoffm.

Oyayomi et al., OFOOA 384 11/1976; FHI

Total: 19; Kaduna 4, Katsina 1, Niger 2, Plateau 8, Taraba 1.

Inula mannii (Hook.f.) Oliv. & Hiern

Vernonia mannii Hook.f.

Medler J. 938; 26-08-1973 [IFE6370]

Total: 1.

Inula paniculata Klatt

Monactinocephalus paniculatus Klatt

Hall, J.B., 1691 04/1970; P

Total: 1.

Kinghamia angustifolia (Benth.) C.Jeffrey

Gymnanthemum angustifolium Benth.

Hepburn, I.D. s.n. [K002069395]

Total: 1.

Kinghamia macrocephala (Oliv. & Hiern) C.Jeffrey

Gutenbergia macrocephala Oliv. & Hiern

Eimunjeze & Oguntayo s.n. [FHI0072840] 10/1974; FHI

Total: 12; Borno 1, Edo 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Ogun 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 1.

Kinghamia nigritana (Benth.) C.Jeffrey

Oiospermum nigritianum Benth.

Daramola, B.O. & Okoro, M., DO68 12/1982; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 138; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 2, Adamawa 1, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 6, Edo 5, Ekiti 1, Enugu 13, Kaduna 17, Kogi 7, Kwara 4, Niger 6, Ogun 13, Ondo 9, Oyo 13, Plateau 8, Taraba 3.

Kleinia abyssinica (A.Rich.) A.Berger

Notonia abyssinica A.Rich.

Keay, R.W.J., s.n. [FHI023438-1] 02/1948; FHI (3 sheets)

Total: 3; Oyo 2.

Kleinia abyssinica var. *abyssinica*

Notonia abyssinica A.Rich.

Keay, R.W.J., s.n. [FHI023438-1] 02/1948; FHI (3 sheets)

Total: 1.

Kleinia cliffordiana (Hutch.) C.D.Adams

Senecio cliffordianus Hutch.

Okafor, J.C. & Daramola, B.O., s.n. [FHI0054632] 04/1964; FHI

Total: 29; Abia 1, Bauchi 4, Kaduna 3, Niger 3, Osun 1, Plateau 15.

Kleinia schweinfurthii (Oliv. & Hiern)

A.Berger

Notonia schweinfurthii Oliv. & Hiern

Dalziel, J.M., 351 05/1908; K [K000377736]

Total: 2; Kaduna 1, Niger 1.

Lactuca glandulifera Hook.f.

Dummer, R. A., 3542 01/1918; K

Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Lactuca indica L. — Introduced

Olorunfemi, J; Fagbemi, A FHI 70663; 1973-2-27 [WAG.1515332]

Total: 1; Ondo 1.

Lactuca inermis Forssk.

Chapman, JD 2994; 1972-12-26 [WAG.1515421]

Total: 86; Bauchi 5, Benue 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 5, Kano 2, Kogi 3, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Niger 3, Ogun 2, Oyo 7, Plateau 10, Sokoto 1, Taraba 18.

Lactuca lasiorhiza (O.Hoffm.) C.Jeffrey

Sonchus lasiorhizus O.Hoffm.

Goetze, 1261; B

Total: 1.

Lactuca praevia C.D.Adams

Hepper F.N. 1764; 1958-1-24 [48993]

Total: 2; Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Lactuca sativa L. — Introduced

Olubuyi Tomisin; 2015-7-14 [6585]

Total: 2; Lagos 2.

Lactuca schweinfurthii Oliv. & Hiern

Daramola, B.O., s.n. [FHI0062749] 05/1969; FHI

Total: 3; Oyo 1, Taraba 1.

Lactuca ugandensis C.Jeffrey

Daramola, B.O., D 68 08/1977; FHI - 3 specimens

Total: 7; Plateau 2, Taraba 4.

Laggera alata (D.Don) Sch.Bip. ex Oliv.

Erigeron alatus D.Don

Hepper F.N. 1532; 1957-12-5 [48327]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Enugu 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Laggera crispata (Vahl) Hepper &

J.R.I.Wood

Conyza crispata Vahl

Chevalier, A., 6474 11/1902; K

Total: 47; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2, Cross River 2, Delta 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 2, Lagos 1, Niger 9, Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 5, Plateau 6, Sokoto 1, Taraba 5.

Laggera oloptera (DC.) C.D.Adams

Blumea oloptera DC.

Ekwuno, P.O., EOO 190 02/1980; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 14; Benue 1, Borno 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 1, Niger 3, Plateau 1, Taraba 1, Yobe 2.

Lasianthaea fruticosa (L.) K.M.Becker —

Introduced

Bidens fruticosa L.

D. Chaves; 355; 1927-10-16 [US 1406274]

Total: 2; Kogi 1.

Launaea brunneri (Webb) Amin ex Boulos

Rhabdotheca brunneri Webb

Dalziel, J.M. 411; 1911-02-01 [K002065222]

Total: 3; Kano 1.

Launaea cabrae (De Wild.) N.Kilian —

Introduced

Lactuca cabrae De Wild.

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Launaea cabrae subsp. *cabrae*

Lactuca cabrae De Wild.

Gbile & Daramola, FHI 62871 03/1970; WAG.

Hepper, F. N., 2013 02/1958; B

Total: 3; Taraba 1.

Launaea cornuta (Hochst. ex Oliv. & Hiern)

C.Jeffrey

Sonchus cornutus Hochst. ex Oliv. & Hiern

Lowe, J., s.n. [P015892] 11/1968; P

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Gombe 1.

Launaea intybacea (Jacq.) Beauverd

Lactuca intybacea Jacq.

Noble, H.L., s.n. [P015976] 11/1951 P

Total: 5; Borno 1, Gombe 1, Kano 1.

Launaea nana (Baker) Chiov.

Lactuca nana Baker

Rowland, s.n. [K000251717] 01/1893; K

Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Lagos 2, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Launaea nudicaulis (L.) Hook.f.

Chondrilla nudicaulis L.

Anon, s.n. [FR-0034792] 02/2004; FR (image not available)

Total: 1; Ogun 1.

Launaea rarifolia (Oliv. & Hiern) Boulos

Sonchus rarifolius Oliv. & Hiern

Rowland, J.W., s.n. [P00179704] 01/1893; P

Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Kaduna 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Taraba 3.

Launaea taraxacifolia (Willd.) Amin ex

C.Jeffrey

Sonchus taraxacifolius Willd.

Faremi, O.T., s.n. [FHI0110308] 06/2015; FHI

Total: 73; Bauchi 2, Borno 9, Ekiti 2, Gombe 2, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Lagos 2, Nasarawa 1, Niger 1, Ogun 2, Ondo 5, Osun 2, Oyo 28, Taraba 2.

Lepidaploa pineticola (Gleason) H.Rob. —
Introduced

Vernonia pineticola Gleason
John D.; 1985-10-12 [1033]2274829395
Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Linzia gerberiformis (Oliv. & Hiern) H.Rob.

Vernonia gerberiformis Oliv. & Hiern
Haygarth, W.J., s.n. [K000273254] 12/1898; K
Total: 16; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 1, Kano 2, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Taraba 1.

Linzia gerberiformis subsp. *gerberiformis*

Vernonia gerberiformis Oliv. & Hiern
Haygarth, W.J., s.n. [K000273254] 12/1898; K
Total: 1.

Linzia gerberiformis subsp. *macrocyanus*
(O.Hoffm.) Isawumi

Vernonia macrocyanus O.Hoffm.
Coombe, D.E., 47 12/1954; P
Total: 1.

Linzia glabra Steetz — Introduced

Akinsoji, A.A.; 2011-01-12 [LUH.4769.0]
Total: 19; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Plateau 7, Taraba 8.

Linzia infundibularis (Oliv. & Hiern)
H.Rob.

Vernonia infundibularis Oliv. & Hiern
Keay, R.W.J. & King, D.E.S., FHI 23087 [P022204]
07/1957; P
Total: 14; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Plateau 4.

Linzia ituriensis (Muschl.) H.Rob.

Vernonia ituriensis Muschl.
Total: 4; Plateau 2.

Linzia ituriensis var. *occidentalis*
(C.D.Adams) Isawumi

Vernonia glabra var. *occidentalis* C.D.Adams
Onochie C.; FHI34855; 1955-3-19
[BR0000008881595]
Total: 4; Plateau 2.

Linzia nigritiana (Oliv. & Hiern) C.Jeffrey

Vernonia nigritiana Oliv. & Hiern
Gbile, Z.O. et al., FHI 64144 [WAG.1557131]
09/1971; WAG
Total: 65; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 5, Cross River

1, Kaduna 7, Kogi 4, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Nasarawa 2, Niger 9, Ogun 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 6, Taraba 4.

Lipotriche abyssinica (Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.)
Orchard

Wuerschmittia abyssinica Sch.Bip. ex Walp.
Schimper, 1533 11/1842; K
Total: 1; Borno 1.

Lipotriche elliptica (O.Hoffm.) D.J.N.Hind

Melanthera elliptica O.Hoffm.
Magbagbeola et al., MA 214 07/1983; FHI
Total: 63; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Borno 2, Kaduna 32, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Nasarawa 1, Niger 8, Oyo 2, Plateau 4, Sokoto 1, Taraba 1.

Lipotriche rhombifolia (O.Hoffm. &
Muschl.) D.J.N.Hind

Melanthera rhombifolia O.Hoffm. & Muschl.
Keay, R.W.J., s.n. [FHI0025825] 06/1950; FHI
Total: 10; Kaduna 6, Taraba 2.

Lipotriche scandens (Schumach. & Thonn.)
Orchard

Buphthalmum scandens Schumach. & Thonn.
Thonning, P., 52; C
Total: 25; Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Ogun 3, Ondo 1, Taraba 1.

Lipotriche scandens subsp. *scandens*

Buphthalmum scandens Schumach. & Thonn.
Thomas, N.W.; 1677; 1912-01-01 [K002493158]
Total: 9; Ogun 3, Ondo 1.

Lipotriche scandens subsp. *subsimplificifolia*
(Wild) Orchard

Melanthera scandens subsp. *subsimplificifolia*
Wild
Milbraed, 10752 12/1928; K
Total: 14; Kaduna 1, Nasarawa 1, Taraba 1.

Litogyne gariepina (DC.) Anderb.

Ethulia gariepina DC.
Drege, s.n. [K000274130]; K
Total: 3; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Sokoto 1.

Macleodium sessiliflorum subsp.
sessiliflorum

Dicoma sessiliflora Harv.
Keay, R.W.J., FHI0037233 11/1957; FHI
Total: 1.

Macleodium sessiliflorum subsp.
stenophyllum (G.V.Pope) S.Ortiz

Dicoma sessiliflora Harv.
Dalziel, 33 10/1908; K

Total: 1.

Micractis bojeri DC.

Schimper, 1059 11/1838; K

Total: 2; Osun 1.

Microglossa afzelii O.Hoffm.

Daramola, B.O. & Adebusuyi, J.K., s.n. [FHI0038426] 10/1958; FHI

Total: 8; Kaduna 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Ondo 3.

Microglossa densiflora Hook.f.

Hall, J.B. 3052; 1971-03-21 [K002624829]

Total: 2; Plateau 2.

Microglossa pyrifolia (Lam.) Kuntze

Conyza pyrifolia Lam.

Eijnatten, C.L.M. van, 1013 12/1965; wag

Total: 58; Adamawa 1, Benue 2, Borno 3, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 4, Ogun 4, Osun 1, Oyo 13, Plateau 3, Rivers 2, Taraba 3.

Microglossa pyrhopappa (Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.) Agnew

Conyza pyrhopappa Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.

Fagbemi, A 457; 1979-8-19 [WAG.1248685]

Total: 62; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 3, Benue 2, Cross River 1, Plateau 16, Taraba 30.

Mikania chenopodiifolia Willd.

Wit, P., Gbile, Z.O., Daramola, B.O. 1467 04/1972; WAG

Total: 30; Adamawa 2, Cross River 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 7, Plateau 3, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Mikania chevalieri (C.D.Adams)

W.C.Holmes & McDaniel

Mikania cordata var. *chevalieri* C.D.Adams

Chevalier, A., 22651 12/1909; K

Total: 16; Bayelsa 1, Borno 2, Cross River 2, Edo 4, Lagos 1, Ogun 3.

Mikania cordata (Burm.f.) B.L.Rob.

Eupatorium cordatum Burm.f.

George, E. Pilz, 2656 11/1981; MO

Total: 34; Akwa Ibom 1, Anambra 1, Benue 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Ondo 5, Osun 1, Oyo 7, Taraba 1.

Mikania microptera DC.

Fendler, A., 626 1854; K

Total: 4; Abia 1, Ogun 1.

Mikania scandens (L.) Willd. — Introduced

Eupatorium scandens L.

s.coll. 395; 1911-07-01 [K003179341]

Total: 4.

Mikaniopsis paniculata Milne-Redh.

Savoy, H.J., & Keay, R.W.J., s.n. [FHI0025238-1] 12/1948; FHI, K

Total: 8; Cross River 8.

Monosis conferta (Benth.) C.Jeffrey

Vernonia conferta Benth.

Welwitsch, F.M.J., 3259; K

Total: 19; Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 5, Oyo 2, Taraba 1.

Monosis theophrastifolia (Schweinf. ex Oliv. & Hiern) C.Jeffrey

Vernonia theophrastifolia Schweinf. ex Oliv. & Hiern

Schweinfurth, 2990 02/1870; K

Total: 8; Plateau 3, Taraba 2.

Nicolasia nitens (O.Hoffm.) Leins

Pluchea nitens O.Hoffm.

Volkens, G., 529 07/1895; K

Total: 4; Adamawa 1, Kogi 1, Taraba 1.

Nicolasia stenoptera (O.Hoffm.) Merxm.

Laggera stenoptera O.Hoffm.

Schinz, H., 702 12/1884; K (Type). Hepper, F.N., 1554 12/1957; BR, P

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Taraba 3.

Nidorella aegyptiaca (L.) J.C.Manning & Goldblatt

Erigeron aegyptiacus L.

Shodeinde, s.n. [FHI040750-1] 10/1959; FHI (2 sheets)

Total: 39; Adamawa 3, Anambra 2, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Ekiti 1, Gombe 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Plateau 14.

Nidorella attenuata (DC.) J.C.Manning & Goldblatt

Conyza attenuata DC.

Baron, R., 4036; K

Total: 18; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Osun 1, Plateau 4, Taraba 2.

Nidorella spartioides (O.Hoffm.) Cronquist

Conyza spartioides O.Hoffm.

Daramola, B.O. FHI 62711 05/1969; WAG

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Taraba 3.

Nothovernonia purpurea (Sch.Bip. ex Walp.) H.Rob. & V.A.Funk

Vernonia purpurea Sch.Bip. ex Walp.

Geerling, C. 3630 07/1971; WAG

Total: 26; Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Kogi 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1, Niger 3, Oyo 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 2.

Ocephala stenocephala (Oliv.) H.Rob.

Vernonia stenocephala Oliv.
Meikle, R.D., s.n. [P024492] 12/1949; P
Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Kaduna 5, Plateau 4.

Orbivestus blumeoides (Hook.f.) Isawumi
Vernonia blumeoides Hook.f.
Ikehuamen, Ariwaodo, J.O. & Binuyo, BAB 73
11/1983; FHI
Total: 7; Cross River 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 2.

Orbivestus karaguensis (Oliv. & Hiern)
H.Rob.
Vernonia karaguensis Oliv. & Hiern
Scott Elliot, G.F., 6920 01/1893; K
Total: 6; Kogi 1, Plateau 4.

Orbivestus turbinata (Oliv. & Hiern) H.Rob.
Vernonia turbinata Oliv. & Hiern
Latilo, M.G. MGL39; 1975-11-15 [K002536525]
Total: 3; Taraba 2.

Orbivestus undulatus (Oliv. & Hiern)
H.Rob.
Vernonia undulata Oliv. & Hiern
Schweinfurth, G.A., 3950 06/1870; K
Total: 14; Kaduna 4, Niger 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 3.

Pegolettia senegalensis Cass.
Curror, 25 01/1842; K
Total: 2; Borno 1.

Picris humilis DC.
Gbile, Z.O., Wit, P. & Daramola, B.O., 1115 04/1972;
WAG
Total: 3; Bauchi 1, Plateau 1.

Picris xylopoda Lack
Coombe, D.E., 44 12/1954; K
Total: 3; Plateau 2.

Piloselloides hirsuta (Forssk.) C.Jeffrey ex
Cufod.
Arnica hirsuta Forssk.
Hepper, F.N., 2110 02/1958; FHI
Total: 14; Benue 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 9.

Pluchea bequaertii Robyns — Introduced
Latilo, M.G., s.n. [FHI044581-1] 10/1961; FHI (2
specimens)
Total: 6; Edo 1, Ekiti 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Ogun 1,
Ondo 1.

Pluchea ovalis (Pers.) DC.
Baccharis ovalis Pers.
Latilo, M.G., FHI 64702 12/1971; WAG
Total: 2; Gombe 2.

Polydora angustifolia Steetz

Crystallopollen angustifolium Steetz
Brass, L., 16090 05/1946; BR, K
Total: 1.

Porphyrostemma chevalieri (O.Hoffm.)
Hutch. & Dalziel
Porphyrostemma grantii var. chevalieri O.Hoffm.
Latilo, M.G., FHI 64709 12/1971; WAG
Total: 13; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Gombe 2, Kaduna 1,
Kogi 1, Plateau 1.

Pseudelephantopus spicatus (Juss. ex Aubl.)
C.F.Baker — Introduced
Elephantopus spicatus Juss. ex Aubl.
Guile D.P.M. 1377; 1966-12 [IFE6247]
Total: 9; Adamawa 1, Lagos 2, Ogun 3, Oyo 1, Taraba
1.

Pseudoconyza viscosa (Mill.) D'Arcy
Conyza viscosa Mill.
Gledhill, D., 904 02/1968; BR
Total: 52; Adamawa 2, Anambra 3, Bauchi 3, Benue
1, Ebonyi 1, Edo 4, Enugu 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 1,
Kano 3, Kogi 2, Kwara 3, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Oyo 5,
Sokoto 2, Taraba 4.

Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum (L.) Hilliard
& B.L.Burt
Gnaphalium luteoalbum L.
Hall J.B. 1099; 30-03-1969 [IFE6367]
Total: 24; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Cross River 1, Edo
1, Ekiti 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 2, Kano 3, Katsina 1,
Kwara 1, Plateau 3, Sokoto 1, Taraba 3.

Pseudognaphalium undulatum (L.) Hilliard
& B.L.Burt — Introduced
Gnaphalium undulatum L.
Medler J. 299; 30-03-1970 [IFE6315]
Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Pulicaria incisa (Lam.) DC.
Inula incisa Lam.
Hepper, F.N., 1632 01/1958; S (image not available).
Roussillon, s.n. [G00468090: G-DC], [FI006464: FI]
Total: 1; Adamawa 1.

Pulicaria undulata (L.) C.A.Mey.
Inula undulata L.
Keay, R., F.H.I.21136; BR. Forsskål, Pehr, s.n.
[LINN-HL999-15]; LINN
Total: 49; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 4, Borno 6, Gombe 1,
Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Niger 10, Plateau 2,
Taraba 1, Yobe 1.

Pulicaria undulata subsp. *argyrophylla*
(E.Gamal-Eldin) D.J.N.Hind & Boulos

- Pulicaria crispa* subsp. *argyrophylla* E.Gamal-Eldin
Latilo, M.G., FHI 64645 11/1971; WAG
Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Taraba 1.
- Pulicaria undulata* subsp. *undulata*
Inula undulata L.
Unknown LUH1205A; 26-06-2012 [LUH]
Total: 20; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 3, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 1, Kano 3, Niger 4, Plateau 1.
- Rudbeckia laciniata* L. — Introduced
Guile D.P.M. 3336; 1967-6 [IFE6451]
Total: 1.
- Sclerocarpus africanus* Jacq.
Olorunfemi, J., FHI 55004 09/1964; WAG
Total: 24; Benue 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Ondo 1, Osun 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 3.
- Senecio hochstetteri* Sch.Bip. ex A.Rich.
Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O., FHI 62866 03/1970; WAG
Total: 6; Kwara 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 3.
- Senecio lelyi* Hutch.
Chapman, J.D., JDC.2767 04/1972; FHI
Total: 12; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 5.
- Senecio pachyrhizus* O.Hoffm.
Hall J.B. 2170; 13-07-1970 [IFE6294]
Total: 2; Plateau 1.
- Senecio ruwenzoriensis* S.Moore
Pegler, A., 486 06/1909; K
Total: 1.
- Solanecio biafrae* (Oliv. & Hiern) C.Jeffrey
Senecio biafrae Oliv. & Hiern
Meikle, R.D., s.n. [P0001278] 04/1950; P
Total: 19; Ekiti 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 6, Taraba 1.
- Solanecio mannii* (Hook.f.) C.Jeffrey
Senecio mannii Hook.f.
Daramola, B.O., fhi 40452 02/1959; P
Total: 5; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Oyo 1, Taraba 2.
- Sonchus angustissimus* Hook.f.
Van Eijnatten, C.L.M., 2090 09/1966; WAG
Total: 1; Kaduna 1.
- Sonchus asper* (L.) Hill
Sonchus oleraceus var. *asper* L.
Lowe, R. T., 860 06/1850; K
Total: 2.
- Sonchus asper* subsp. *asper*
- Sonchus oleraceus* var. *asper* L.
Lowe, R. T., 860 06/1850; K
Total: 1.
- Sonchus camporum* (R.E.Fr.) Boulos ex C.Jeffrey
Sonchus schweinfurthii var. *camporum* R.E.Fr.
Fries, R.E. & Fries, T.C.E., 513b 01/1922; K
Total: 1.
- Sonchus oleraceus* L.
Van Eijnatten, C.L.M., 1998 09/1966; WAG
Total: 5; Cross River 1, Plateau 1.
- Sonchus schweinfurthii* Oliv. & Hiern
Hepper, F.N., 1656 01/1958 FHI
Total: 8; Plateau 2, Taraba 1.
- Sphaeranthus angustifolius* DC.
Wit, P. & Daramola, B.O., 2747 04/1973; FHI
Total: 10; Bauchi 3, Borno 2, Kaduna 1, Lagos 1, Sokoto 2.
- Sphaeranthus flexuosus* O.Hoffm.
Gbile, Z.O., Wit, P. & Daramola, B.O., 1243 05/1972; FHI
Total: 3; Borno 1, Ogun 1.
- Sphaeranthus senegalensis* DC.
Olufsen, O., 623; BR
Total: 18; Bauchi 1, Borno 2, Gombe 1, Kaduna 4, Kano 4, Plateau 1.
- Sphaeranthus steetzii* Oliv. & Hiern
Oligolepis angustifolia Steetz
Schimper, 525 11/1839; K
Total: 1.
- Sphaeranthus talbotii* S.Moore
Leeuw, P.N.de., 1348 11/1964; FHI. Talbot, W.A., 1004 01/1911; K
Total: 6; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Kano 1, Oyo 1, Yobe 1.
- Sphagneticola trilobata* (L.) Pruski — Introduced
Silphium trilobatum L.
Adegbite Oluwatolu; 2015-07-14 [LUH.6586.0]
Total: 4; Akwa Ibom 2, Lagos 2.
- Stomatanthes africanus* (Oliv. & Hiern) R.M.King & H.Rob.
Eupatorium africanum Oliv. & Hiern
Whyte, A., s.n. [K000768734] 12/1896; K
Total: 22; Adamawa 2, Bauchi 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 8.
- Stomatanthes helenae* (Buscal. & Muschl.) Lisowski

Eupatorium helenae Buscal. & Muschl.
 Thienpont, D., 35 08/1945; BR
 Total: 1.

Struchium sparganophorum (L.) Kuntze —
 Introduced
Ethulia sparganophora L.
 Gardner, G., 1045 11/1837; K
 Total: 75; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
 Anambra 2, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Edo 10, Ekiti 4,
 Imo 1, Kano 1, Kogi 1, Lagos 5, Ogun 5, Ondo 5,
 Osun 1, Oyo 14, Plateau 1.

Synedrella nodiflora (L.) Gaertn. —
 Introduced
Verbesina nodiflora L.
 Peter, G.A., 54403 03/1917; K
 Total: 93; Abia 4, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
 Cross River 15, Edo 3, Ekiti 1, Enugu 1, Imo 2,
 Kaduna 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 3, Niger 1, Ogun 4, Ondo
 3, Osun 4, Oyo 29, Rivers 1, Taraba 1.

Tagetes erecta L. — Introduced
 Onijamowo, R.O. [FHI0030683] 12/1971; FHI
 Total: 6; Lagos 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba
 2.

Tithonia diversifolia (Hemsl.) A.Gray —
 Introduced
Mirasolia diversifolia Hemsl.
 Bourgeau, 2319 01/1865; K
 Total: 47; Abia 1, Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1,
 Anambra 1, Cross River 4, Ekiti 1, Kwara 2, Lagos 1,
 Niger 1, Ogun 10, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 15, Plateau 1,
 Taraba 6.

Tithonia rotundifolia (Mill.) S.F.Blake —
 Introduced
Tagetes rotundifolia Mill.
 King, R.M. & Mori, S.A., 7996 07/1979; K
 Total: 5; Lagos 1, Ogun 3, Osun 1.

Tridax moorei H.Rob. — Introduced
 Effa E. A.; 2013-5-9 [1035]2274829325
 Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Tridax procumbens L. — Introduced
 Hind et al., PCD3612 07/1996; K
 Total: 99; Adamawa 1, Anambra 1, Bauchi 3, Benue
 1, Borno 2, Cross River 3, Delta 1, Edo 1, Enugu 3,
 Imo 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Kwara 6, Lagos 8, Niger 6,
 Ogun 2, Ondo 1, Osun 2, Oyo 29, Plateau 3, Rivers 1,
 Taraba 2, Zamfara 1.

Tussilago farfara L. — Introduced
 Literature
 Total: 0.

Verbesina encelioides (Cav.) Benth. &
 Hook.f. ex A.Gray — Introduced
 Literature
 Total: 0.

Vernonellaacrocephala (Klatt) H.Rob. &
 Skvarla
Vernoniaacrocephala Klatt
 Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O. FHI 63332 04/1970;
 WAG
 Total: 2; Taraba 1.

Vernonella chthonocephala (O.Hoffm.)
 H.Rob. & Skvarla
Vernonia chthonocephala O.Hoffm.
 Welwitsch, 3886; K
 Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Plateau 1.

Vernonella subaphylla (Baker) H.Rob. &
 Skvarla
Vernonia subaphylla Baker
 Daramola, B.O., fhi 40609 01/1959; P
 Total: 2; Plateau 1.

Vernonia bauchiensis Hutch. & Dalziel —
 Endemic
 Lely, H.V., P 86 01/1929; K. Possible isotype FHI
 (FHI0010513-0)
 Total: 2; Bauchi 1, Edo 1.

Vernonia chapmanii C.D.Adams
 Chapman, J.W.F., 42 07/1958 (K000272856,
 K000272857); K
 Total: 6; Plateau 1, Taraba 4.

Vernonia galamensis (Cass.) Less.
Centrapalus galamensis Cass.
 Barter, C., s.n [P021549] 01/1862; P
 Total: 20; Adamawa 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Bauchi 2,
 Enugu 1, Gombe 3, Kaduna 2, Kogi 1, Niger 1.

Vernonia galamensis subsp. *galamensis*
Centrapalus galamensis Cass.
 Barter, C. [P021550]
 Total: 1.

Vernonia golungensis Welw. ex Mendonça
 — Introduced
 Gbile, ZO; Wit, P; Daramola, BO 1356; 1972-5-10
 [WAG.1555649]
 Total: 3; Kogi 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 1.

Vernonia kamerunensis Mattf.
 Literature
 Total: 0.

Vernonia miamensis S.Moore

Rand, R.F., 100 04/1926; BM

Total: 3; Plateau 1.

Vernonia perrottetii Sch.Bip. ex Walp.

Webbia serratuloides DC.

Daramola, B.O. & Okoro, M., 82/ 48 11/1982; WAG

Total: 1.

Vernonia plumbaginifolia Fenzl

Meikle, R.D., s.n. [P022870] 03/1950; P

Total: 2; Akwa Ibom 1.

Vernonia schweinfurthii Oliv. & Hiern

Gbile, Z.O., Wit & Daramola, B.O., 20G1310

05/1972; BR

Total: 2.

Vernonia schweinfurthii var. *schweinfurthii*

Gbile Z.O., Wit & Daramola B.O.

[BR0000014911156]

Total: 2.

Vernoniastrum ambiguum (Kotschy & Peyr.) H.Rob.

Vernonia ambigua Kotschy & Peyr.

Hepper, F.N., s.n. [P019573] 10/1957; P

Total: 60; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Adamawa 2, Anambra 1, Bauchi 1, Benue 1, Borno 4, Edo 1, Jigawa 1, Kaduna 3, Kano 1, Kogi 2, Kwara 1, Lagos 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Ogun 1, Oyo 4, Plateau 5, Taraba 2.

Vernoniastrum camporum (A.Chev.)

Isawumi

Vernonia camporum A.Chev.

Lowe, J 1581; 1968-11-17 [WAG.1381645]

Total: 21; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Akwa Ibom 1, Benue 1, Gombe 3, Lagos 1, Niger 6, Ondo 1, Plateau 1, Taraba 2.

Vernoniastrum migeodii (S.Moore) Isawumi

Vernonia migeodii S.Moore

Daramola, BO; Osanyinlusi 79/ 166; 1979-5-4 [WAG.1556920]

Total: 32; Anambra 2, Benue 1, Borno 3, Cross River 1, Kaduna 2, Kogi 4, Kwara 3, Lagos 2, Ondo 2, Osun 2, Oyo 1.

Vernoniastrum nestor (S.Moore) H.Rob.

Vernonia nestor S.Moore

Buchanan, J., 44 01/1891; K

Total: 19; Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 4, Kogi 1, Niger 1, Plateau 8, Taraba 2.

Vicoa indica (L.) DC.

Inula indica L.

Etkin 176; 1987-11-19 [589811]

Total: 44; Adamawa 3, Bauchi 3, Borno 4, Edo 2, Kaduna 3, Kano 3, Lagos 1, Niger 6, Ogun 1, Oyo 2, Plateau 1, Sokoto 2, Taraba 3, Yobe 1.

Xanthium strumarium L.

Gardner, G., 524 03/1837; K

Total: 3; Ogun 1.

Zinnia angustifolia Kunth — Introduced

Guile D.P.M. 1479; 1967-3 [IFE6636A]

Total: 1.

Zinnia elegans Jacq. — Introduced

Usang Felix; 2005-10-03

<https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3913474601>

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

CAPRIFOLIACEAE

Scabiosa africana L. — Introduced

Felix; 2005-10-16 [346]3913474438

Total: 1; Lagos 1.

PITTOSPORACEAE

Pittosporum viridiflorum Sims

Odewo, TK OD 191; 1982-5-27 [WAG.1424076]

Total: 54; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 1, Borno 1, Cross River 7, Edo 1, Kaduna 7, Kano 1, Niger 1, Plateau 12, Sokoto 1, Taraba 14, Zamfara 1.

ARALIACEAE

Aralia spinifolia Merr.

John D.; 1981-6-10 [1007]2274829347

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Astropanax abyssinicus (Hochst. ex A.Rich.) Seem.

Aralia abyssinica Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Chapman, J.D. 2712; 1972-03-01 (FHI)

Total: 9; Plateau 3, Taraba 4.

Astropanax barteri Seem.

Barter, C. 1851 (K)

Total: 10; Akwa Ibom 3, Cross River 2, Taraba 2.

Astropanax mannii (Hook.f.) Seem.

Paratropia mannii Hook.f.

Magajie & Tuley 2187 (K)

Total: 14; Benue 1, Cross River 4, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Cussonia arborea Hochst. ex A.Rich.

Barter, C. 815 (K)

Total: 60; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Anambra 3, Bauchi 4, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 11, Nasarawa 4, Niger 3, Ogun 9, Osun 1, Oyo 6, Plateau 8, Taraba 2.

Cussonia bancoensis Aubrév. & Pellegr.

Gledhill, D. 978; 1968-11-26 (K)

Total: 2; Ondo 1, Oyo 1.

Heptapleurum arboricola Hayata

John D.; 1981-5-8 [1006]2274829322

Total: 1; Cross River 1.

Hydrocotyle bonariensis Comm. ex Lam. — Introduced

Brown, R.C. 960; 1974-01-03 [BR0000015686435]

Total: 12; Akwa Ibom 4, Cross River 3, Kogi 1, Lagos 4.

Hydrocotyle mannii Hook.f.

Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O. FHI62894; 1970-04-02 (FHI)

Total: 6; Taraba 5.

Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides Lam.

Wit, P., Gbile, Z.O. & Daramola, B.O. 1940; 1972-05-10 (WAG)

Total: 4; Plateau 1, Taraba 3.

Panax ginseng C.A.Mey. — Introduced

Ugwuozor P.O.; 2014-11-25 [149A]1990271739

Total: 1; Kogi 1.

Polyscias fulva (Hiern) Harms

Panax fulvum Hiern

Latilo & Daramola FHI 34351 (BR, K, P)

Total: 24; Adamawa 3, Akwa Ibom 1, Cross River 2, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 2, Taraba 9.

APIACEAE

Afroligusticum petitianum (A.Rich.)

P.J.D.Winter

Peucedanum petitianum A.Rich.

Hepburn, I.D. 93; -- [K000311297]

Total: 2.

Anethum graveolens L. — Introduced

Hepper F.N. 1759; 1958-1-23 [BR0000018815320]

Total: 6; Adamawa 2, Taraba 4.

Berula repanda (Welw. ex Hiern) Spalik &

S.R.Downie

Sium repandum Welw. ex Hiern

Chapman, JD 2555; 1971-9-30 [WAG.1171941]

Total: 7; Plateau 1, Taraba 5, Zamfara 1.

Centella asiatica (L.) Urb.

Hydrocotyle asiatica L.

Daramola, BO FHI 86043; 1977-8-17

[WAG.1847648]

Total: 37; Abuja Federal Capital Territory 1, Bauchi 2, Benue 1, Cross River 1, Enugu 1, Kaduna 3, Kogi 1, Kwara 1, Lagos 1, Niger 1, Ondo 2, Oyo 1, Plateau 9, Taraba 10, Zamfara 1.

Cryptotaenia africana (Hook.f.) Drude

Anthriscus africana Hook.f.

Eijnatten, CLM van 1977; 1966-9-20 [WAG.1858567]

Total: 6; Adamawa 1, Cross River 1, Kaduna 1, Taraba 3.

Daucus carota L. — Introduced

Abayomi Abosedo; 2015-1-8 [6329]

Total: 5; Lagos 5.

Daucus incognitus (C.Norman) Spalik, Reduron & Banasiak

Caucalis incognita C.Norman

Matthew Walters; 2012-11-24 00:00:00

Total: 1; Taraba 1.

Daucus melananthus (Hochst.) Reduron, Spalik & Banasiak

Agrocharis melanantha Hochst.

Chapman, JD 2639; 1972-1-5 [WAG.1847845]

Total: 1.

Diplophium africanum Turcz.

Wit, P; Oguntayo, ST 2311; 1972-8-10

[WAG.1849139]

Total: 29; Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Kwara 3, Niger 1, Oyo 3, Plateau 9, Taraba 1.

Diplophium diplophiioides (H.Wolff) Jacq.-Fél.

Physotrichia diplophiioides H.Wolff

Literature

Total: 0.

Heteromorpha occidentalis P.J.D.Winter

Latilo, M.G.; 132; 1975-11-17 [K002751306]

Total: 3; Kwara 1, Taraba 1.

Lefebvrea abyssinica A.Rich.

Literature

Total: 0.

Lefebvrea angustisecta Engl.

Chapman H.M. 143; 1973-8-20 [70937]

Total: 3; Adamawa 1, Kaduna 1, Plateau 1.

Lefebvrea grantii (Kingston ex Oliv.)

S.Droop

Peucedanum grantii Kingston ex Oliv.

Hepburn, I.D. 93; 1929-10- [K000311297]

Total: 16; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 3, Nasarawa 1, Niger 2, Plateau 2, Taraba 1.

Pimpinella hirtella (Hochst.) A.Rich.

Tragium hirtellum Hochst.

Eijnatten, CLM van 2002; 1966-9-22 [WAG.1853968]

Total: 24; Abia 1, Adamawa 2, Bauchi 2, Kaduna 2, Niger 2, Plateau 10, Taraba 1.

Pimpinella ledermannii H.Wolff

Lely, H.V. 450; 1921-8-23 [K000312955]

Total: 2; Adamawa 2.

Pimpinella schimperi Dawit

Literature

Total: 0.

Pycnocycla ledermannii H.Wolff

Lely, H.V.; 1921-08-23 [K000312955]

Total: 22; Bauchi 1, Benue 2, Edo 1, Kaduna 1, Niger 1, Oyo 1, Plateau 10.

Sanicula elata Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don

Hepper F.N. 1794; 1958-1-27 [BR0000019578163]

Total: 7; Adamawa 1, Sokoto 1, Taraba 4.

Steganotaenia araliacea Hochst.

Wit, P; Gbile, ZO; Daramola, BO 1342; 1972-4-20 [WAG.1172172]

Total: 46; Adamawa 1, Bauchi 5, Borno 1, Kaduna 14, Kano 6, Niger 5, Plateau 9, Taraba 1.

Steganotaenia araliacea var. *araliacea*